

PARE

PERSPECTIVES FOR AERONAUTICAL RESEARCH IN EUROPE

Perspectives for Aeronautical Research in Europe 2018 Report

FINAL REPORT

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Chapter 1 - Introduction and Set of Recommendations

The PARE yearly report consists of two parts. The PART I addresses the fundamental objective of considering the progress towards the 23 ACARE Goals, the gap eventually remaining and measures that could contribute to its closure.

The PART II considers several specific aspects related to the Flightpath 2050 objectives, such market, competitive and cooperative conditions, emerging technologies and material and human resources.

The introduction (Chapter 1) lists a set of recommendations indicating the chapters, sections and subsections where they are detailed. The conclusion (Chapter 12) includes a number of “what if” assessments and of potential evolution of market conditions and their implications on the EU aeronautics program.

The PART I on the assessment of the 23 ACARE goals groups them in five chapters as in the Flightpath 2050 document: (Chapter 2) Meeting Societal and Market Needs; (Chapter 3) Maintaining and Extending Industrial Leadership; (Chapter 4) Protecting the Environment and the Energy Supply; (Chapter 5) Ensuring Safety and Security; (Chapter 6) Prioritizing Research, Testing Facilities and Education.

The PART II addresses and number of issues closely related to the ACARE Goals: (Chapter 7) Long-range Air Transport; (Chapter 8) Emerging Technologies relevant to Aviation; (Chapter 9) Cooperation beyond European Borders; (Chapter 10) Attraction of Young Talent to Aviation; (Chapter 11) Gender contribution to Aeronautical Progress.

The Chapters 2 to 6, in PART I, and 7 to 11, in PART II, have a similar structure:

- (i) A baseline generic text gives a balanced coverage of the subject, and identifies specific critical issues or key points;
- (ii) In order not to break the flow of basic text, each key topic is treated as a separate article with its own illustrations and references.

The report is based entirely on open sources of information upon which are superimposed multiple layers of interpretation and assessments using the expertise of the consortium.

The basic text originates with the coordinator and the key topics with the individual partners, as a collective effort in which each partner can contribute to improve all texts. The basic text is self-consistent whereas the Key Topics can reflect different views on the same subject looked at from different angles. The report does not presume to be a final assessment and aims only to give a valid contribution to the issues relating to perspectives for aerospace research in Europe.

The Figures, Tables and Key Topics are numbered by Chapter, e.g. Key Topic T2.5 in Chapter 2. The references are numbered by order of appearance.

The PARE First Year report has served as the background and justification for a set of “68 PARE Recommendations on Aeronautics in Horizon Europe” that combines:

- The 23 ACARE Goals as stated in the document Flight Path 2050 that is the basis of Part I of this report;
- The 35 PARE Objectives that support their implementation as presented in the part II of this report.

This ensemble may be seen as an advisory input into the preparation of the aeronautical themes for the EU research program Horizon Europe as a follow-on to the current Horizon 2000.

It also serves as a summary and introduction to the contents of this Report since each of the 68 Recommendations includes a concise justification and refers for further details to the relevant section of the First Year PARE Report.

The list of recommendations is based on the first draft of the First Year Report of the CSA “Perspectives for Aeronautical Research in Europe” (PARE) that provides the detailed background and justification. The list of recommendations can serve as a detailed “executive summary”, highlighting the main issues, and serving as a subject index indicating in which Chapter and Section of the PARE Report the relevant aspects are discussed.

The List of Recommendations for Aeronautics in Horizon Europe is structured like the PARE report that is based upon. The Part I consists of recommendations aiming to implement each of the 23 ACARE goals in the present circumstances, suggesting the more urgent and effective means to pursue the objectives stated in Chapters 2 to 6. The Part II contains recommendations concerning the 35 PARE objectives that are the subjects of chapters 7-11, namely long-range air transport, emerging technology, cooperation beyond Europe’s borders, attracting young talent in general and, in particular, fostering the participation of women.

There are interfaces and partial overlaps among the 23 ACARE Goals in Part I and 5 sets of PARE Objectives in the Part II. The recommendations are structured so that they mostly cover one topic at a time, without overlaps. Even avoiding repetitions, the number of recommendations is significant, so a ranking scheme is used.

The highest rank (***/three asterisks) concerns broad issues with major impact on the future of aviation in which critical concerns have to be tackled. The lowest rank (no asterisks) concerns subjects for which the current rate of progress is adequate but should not be overlooked. The two intermediate ranks (one and two asterisks) make the transition.

Since this set of recommendations is based on a first draft of a yearly report of a project started 9 months ago, it is certainly open for improvement, bearing in mind that it is entirely based on open sources of information. The PARE report is open access at: <https://www.pareproject.eu/publications>.

Structure of the recommendations

Each of the 23 ACARE goals and 35 PARE Objectives is taken as the basis for 58 sets of recommendations ordered by number. All sets of recommendations use the following format:

- Statement:** text of the ACARE goal or PARE objective;

- b. **Recommendation(s):** brief statement of the actions to be taken.
- c. **Rationale:** current situation and future prospects motivating the recommendation;
- d. **Stakeholders:** institutions that could contribute to implementation: European Union (EU), Member States (MS), Aerospace Industry (AI), Research Centres (RC), Universities and Academia (UA), Certification Authorities (CA), Accident Assessment Organizations (AA), Air Navigation Service Providers (AN), Airlines (AR), Airports (AP), Professional Associations (PA);
- e. **Relevance:** potential impact of the initiative;
- f. **Priority:** justification of the priority rating on a scale from 3 asterisks (top) to zero asterisks;
- g. **Justification:** reference to the section of the PARE Report containing more detailed information.

PART I – Recommendations towards the Implementation of the 23 ACARE Goals

The recommendations are made in the same order as the ACARE goals that appear in the PARE report. There may be one or more recommendations per ACARE Goal and the justification is referred to the sections and key topics of the Part I of the PARE Report.

1. Meeting Social and Market Needs

1a. ACARE GOAL 1: *An air traffic management system is in place that provides a range of services to handle at least 25 million flights a year of all types of vehicle, including unmanned and autonomous systems that are integrated into and interoperable with the overall air transport system with 24 hour efficient operation of airports. European air space is used flexibly to facilitate reduced environmental impact from aircraft operations.*

1b. Recommendation 1*:** A broad and deep research effort must be maintained concerning all aspects of Air Traffic Management (ATM) that can contribute to increase airspace capacity with equal or greater safety.

1c. Rationale: The growth of air transport puts increasing demands on air traffic capacity with undiminished safety. The foreseen operation of UAVs in manned airspace will increase the demand for capacity. As capacity limits are approached there are more delays that cause inconvenience to passengers and increase emissions and fuel costs. Together airport noise and air traffic capacity could become the two main bottlenecks for the growth of aviation.

1d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AN, AP, AR, AI, RC, UA.

1e. Relevance: The air traffic capacity must increase with undiminished or improved safety to accommodate traffic growth and UAV's without incurring major delays.

1f. Priority: Air traffic capacity could potentially become an obstacle to the growth of aviation and past experience shows that approaching capacity limits can cause major disruption in terms of flight delays and operating costs and emissions.

1g. Justification: PARE report Section 2.1 and Topics T2.1 and T2.2.

2a. ACARE GOAL 2: *A coherent ground infrastructure is developed including: airports, vertiports and heliports with the relevant servicing and connecting facilities, also to other modes.*

2b. Recommendation 2*: Urban and land planning methodologies need to be developed to optimise on a regional basis the location of airports, vertiports and heliports to simultaneously provide convenient links to other transportation nodes and minimise environmental impacts and disturbance of populations.

2c. Rationale: The integration of airports into regional planning must include the interfaces with other modes of transport and also the compatibility with other land users.

2d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AP, AR, AN.

2e. Relevance: The airport network should cover population needs at regional, national and European and intercontinental level.

2f. Priority: There is the need to harmonize inter-modal transport at regional level and fast air transport on a European scale.

2g. Justification: PARE report Section 2.2 and Topic T2.3.

3a. ACARE GOAL 3: *European citizens are able to make informed mobility choices and have affordable access to one another, taking into account: economy, speed, and level of service (which can be tailored to the individual customer). Continuous, secure and robust high bandwidth communications are provided for added value customer applications.*

3b. Recommendation 3*: Promote a one-shop centralised travel information site where the EU citizen can readily find the alternative options for connecting any two locations, including costs and timetables, with links to reliable booking.

3c. Rationale: There are many sources of travel information and services with different objectives and priorities making a choice confusing and often non-comparable.

3d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AR, AP, CA, AR, PA.

3e. Relevance: An independent, reliable and comprehensive source of comparable and reliable travel information would serve the interests of the citizen and fair competition to offer the highest quality and most efficient air travel, promoting the growth of air transportation.

3f. Priority: The information is available, although in a scattered and inconsistent form, with plenty of scope for improvement.

3g. Justification: PARE report Section 2.3 and Topic T2.4.

4a. ACARE GOAL 4: *90% of travellers within Europe are able to complete their journey, door-to-door within 4 hours. Passengers and freight are able to transfer seamlessly between transport modes to reach the final destination smoothly, predictably and on time.*

4b. Recommendation 4*: Revise the goal to take into account (a) the distance and duration of flight and (b) cover the time period from arrival at the departure airport to exit from the destination airport.

4c. Rationale: The aviation sector (b) cannot be responsible for what happens outside the aircraft and airports and cannot influence travel time between home/work and the airport. The flight distances within the EU can go up to 3 000 Km, and some aircraft are slower (propeller driven) than others (jet powered) so travel times can differ.

4d. Stakeholders: AR, AP, MS, EU.

4e. Relevance: The realistic information that can be provided to a traveller consists of: (i) Flight time that airlines can provide; (ii) Time for departure and arrival procedures that the airport can manage. Travel beyond the airport is out of control of the aviation sector.

4f. Priority: The information is available or predictable but not as reliable or accurate as the business traveller needs and can disrupt leisure travel connections and plans.

4g. Justification: PARE report Section 2.4 and Topics T2.5, T2.6 and T2.7.

5a. ACARE GOAL 5: *Flights arrive within 1 minute of the planned arrival time, regardless of weather conditions. The transport system is resilient against disruptive events and is capable of automatically and dynamically reconfiguring the journey within the network to meet the needs of the traveller if disruption occurs. Special mission flights can be completed in the majority of weather, atmospheric conditions and operational environments.*

5b. Recommendation 5.1: More comprehensive weather data is made available to ATM and airlines to assist achieving punctuality targets (see recommendations 13 and 15.1).

Recommendation 5.2: A rapid near real time simulation capability is developed for ATM to (a) accommodate special emerging flights and (b) adjust to major disruptive events.

5c. Rationale: Punctuality of air transport in adverse weather conditions depends on availability of meteorological data sufficiently in advance for efficient re-routing. Disruptive events and special flights that require reconfiguration of multiple flight paths can be made efficiently if supported by fast and reliable simulation tools.

5d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AN, AC, AR, AI, RS, NA.

5e. Relevance: Being able to maintain a steady flow of air traffic is particularly relevant, and more difficult, during major disruptive weather events, like ash clouds or freezing conditions.

5f. Priority: This is an area of gradual progress where steady effort should be maintained, but nothing revolutionary is expected.

5g. Justification: PARE report Section 2.5 and Topic T2.8.

2. Maintaining and Extending Industrial Leadership

6a. ACARE GOAL 6: *"The whole European aviation industry is strongly competitive, delivers the best products and services worldwide and has a share of more than 40% of the world market."*

6b. Recommendation 6*:** Maintain a broad-based application-oriented research and development activity covering all sectors relevant to the global competitiveness of the European aircraft industry.

6c. Rationale: The importance of the aeronautical industry to the prosperity of Europe is well documented. Since aeronautics is a synthesis of advanced technologies it requires a mastery of all of them to remain competitive.

6d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA, AN, AA, AP, PA.

6e. Relevance: taking as example the market for airliners with more than 100 seats, maintaining the Airbus share of 50% of the world market will require technological leadership in a broad range of technologies.

6f. Priority: This is the core of the aircraft market worldwide. The problems of the Airbus A380 with the passenger infotainment system and those of the Boeing 787 with the lithium-ion batteries show that even seemingly secondary aspects can cause major disruption.

6g. Justification: PARE report Section 2.5 and Topic T2.8.

7a. ACARE GOAL 7: *Europe will retain leading edge design, manufacturing and system integration capabilities and jobs supported by high profile, strategic, flagship projects and programmes which cover the whole innovation process from basic research to full-scale demonstrators.*

7b. Recommendation 7:** Support an observatory of global trends in aviation to ensure that major breakthroughs occur first in Europe or are matched without a delay in reaching the market.

7c. Rationale: The industry does by itself a good job of ensuring its own competitiveness, although shorter term needs may prevail over longer terms prospects. The EC and MS programs aim at long-term competitiveness on the basis of professional recommendations but could still benefit from a stable independent observatory of citizen needs, market trends and technological advances that could meet them.

7d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, AR, RC, UA

7e. Relevance: Although the European aerospace industry is currently quite competitive there are a number of emerging technologies that could be used by current and new competitors to change the balance; these need to be monitored and supported to ensure Europe remains a leader in the aeronautical sector.

7f. Priority: Current mechanisms to remain competitive though still relevant in the future may not be sufficient.

7g. Justification: PARE report Section 3.3 and Topics T3.4 and T3.5.

8a. ACARE GOAL 8: *Streamlined systems engineering, design, manufacturing, certification and upgrade processes have addressed complexity and significantly decreased development costs (including a 50% reduction in the cost of certification). A leading new generation of standards is created.*

8b. Recommendation 8: Analyse the architecture of industrial aviation programmes, to identify the best practices in matching design, development, certification, production, operations and maintenance in the most cost-effective and time-efficient manner. The introduction of new technologies and stricter safety requirements should be accompanied by more efficient testing and validation to minimise time and cost.

8c. Rationale: Emerging technologies like 4.0, Artificial Intelligence and Big Data offer the prospect of more efficient integration of the aircraft life-cycle from design through production to operations but require large investments in complex systems that should preferably be phased in a try-and prove approach.

8d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA, AR, CA.

8e. Relevance: The 4.0 factory is the next big trend in industry, and aeronautics is no exception, adding operations and maintenance to designs and production.

8f. Priority: Developments in this area are widespread in industry, and aeronautics requires specific adaptations.

8g. Justification: PARE report Section 3.3 and Topics T3.4 and T3.5.

3. Protecting the Environment and the Energy Supply

9a. ACARE GOAL 9: *“In 2050 the technologies and procedures available allow a 75% reduction in CO₂ emissions per passenger kilometre and a 90% reduction in NO_x emissions. The perceived noise emission of flying aircraft is reduced by 65%. These are relative to the capabilities of typical new aircraft in 2000”.*

9b. Recommendation 9.1*:** Support a broad research effort to reduce aircraft noise (a) at the source (b) through operating procedures and (c) taking into account psychoacoustic effects.

Recommendation 9.2*: Besides struggling with short term solutions to an increasingly pressing noise problem a modest effort should be made towards a long-term definitive solution: aircraft inaudible outside airport boundaries.

Recommendation 9.3:** Formulate a set of trade-offs between (a) different types of emissions (CO₂, NO_x, particles and water vapor) in (b) local airports and global cruise flights.

Recommendation 9.4: Besides struggling with short-term emissions problems put a modest effort towards a long-term definitive solution: the hydrogen powered aircraft.

9c. Rationale: The growth of air transport at a rate of 3 to 7% per year, leads to flights increased to the double by 2030, and triple by 2050; in order to avoid increased noise exposure near airports and emissions in cruise the corresponding reductions must be made per flight. Noise is dominated by the engine at high thrust at take-off and by aerodynamics at approach with the engine at idle: thus, the full range of noise sources needs to be tackled, the operating procedures optimized, and psychoacoustic effects accounted for in order to succeed in this major challenge. The requirements for low emissions of CO₂, NO_x, particles and water vapor near airports and in cruise are sometimes

contradictory and a reasonable compromise needs to be defined to guide engine design. The 'definitive' solutions to aircraft noise and emissions, such as aircraft inaudible outside airports and hydrogen propulsion that emits only water vapor, are far away but deserve a modest effort to establish how they might be viable.

9d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA, AN, AR, AP.

9e. Relevance: Tolerance to airport noise is reducing and court or other actions to limit airport operations are likely to increase if overall noise exposure cannot be contained. Aviation should have a non-increasing and preferably decreasing role in global emissions.

9f. Priority: It is very challenging to contain total noise exposure at airports and failure to do so could limit airport operations and become a bottleneck for the growth of aviation. Emissions are a major local and global environmental concern and aviation should be an example of positive action. Beyond the pressing short-term issues of noise and emissions a modest effort should be made to assess and mature in out-of-the-box long-term solutions.

9g. Justification: PARE report Section 4.1 and Topics T4.1 and T4.2.

10a. ACARE GOAL 10: *Aircraft movements are emission free when taxiing.*

10b. Recommendation 10: Develop a methodology to comprehensively assess the implications of electric aircraft taxiing and electrical energy supply in terms of requirements, costs, land and environmental impact for a variety of airport configurations.

10c. Rationale: Aircraft taxiing under the power of its own engines and to a lesser extent auxiliary power unit (APU) running contribute to airport emissions that could be avoided by electric towing and power supplies.

10d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AP, AR, CA.

10e. Relevance: Although electric towing and power supplies are feasible, the investment in vehicles and support infrastructure must be assessed as well as how costs are covered.

10f. Priority: This is mainly an implementation issue that will be supported by progress in electric power, especially batteries.

10g. Justification: PARE report Section 4.2 and Topic T4.3.

11a. ACARE GOAL 11: *Air vehicles are designed and manufactured to be recyclable.*

11b. Recommendation 11: Make a comprehensive assessment of materials used in aircraft production and assess recyclable alternatives and related issues of availability, ease of use, certification, maintenance and cost.

11c. Rationale: The trend towards recycling is industry wide, and in the case of aeronautics as others can be integrated as one of the objectives of goal 8.

11d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, AU, AR, CA.

11e. Relevance: Aviation must share the goal of preventing depletion of limited resources and making better and repeated use of materials already available.

11f. Priority: This is a wide effort among most industries, which aviation must share taking into account its specific needs.

11g. Justification: PARE report Section 4.3 and Topic T4.4.

12a. ACARE GOAL 12: *Europe is established as a centre of excellence on sustainable alternative fuels, including those for aviation, based on a strong European energy policy.*

12b. Recommendation 12: Perform a comparative study of potential alternative fuels, their availability in the required large quantities and the feasibility and cost of large-scale production, distribution and use.

12c. Rationale: There is a strong need to reduce the dependence on fossil fuels and although there are several potential alternatives it is not easy to match the energy density, usability and cost of kerosene in large quantities.

12d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, Energy industry; AI, RC, UA, AR, CA.

12e. Relevance: Avoiding fast depletion of finite oil resources, finding alternative less polluting fuels and possibly also safer handling with undiminished energy density per unit weight and volume: demanding and necessary.

12f. Priority: This is an issue affecting all modes of transport, among which aviation is a major but not the largest user and should try to improve its position and contribution to the whole.

12g. Justification: PARE report Section 4.4 and Topic T4.5.

13a. ACARE GOAL 13: *Europe is at the forefront of atmospheric research and takes the lead in the formulation of a prioritised environmental action plan and establishment of global environmental standards.*

13b. Recommendation 13: Use the regular airliner flights to collect in-situ atmospheric data and process this large amount of information to have near real time knowledge of conditions along flight routes. This data could be supplemented by drones specially designed to fly in more remote regions of the atmosphere.

13c. Rationale: It is possible to obtain much more comprehensive weather data both in time and location by using sensors aboard aircraft in regular flights. The collection, organization and processing of this data with quite homogeneous structure should be feasible by big data methods.

13d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AN, AR, CA, AI, RC, UA.

13e. Relevance: Detailed weather data with higher spatial and temporal resolution is the key to achieve several objectives of timeliness and safety of aviation, like ACARE goals 5 and 15.

13f. Priority: This major improvement in geographical and temporal coverage of weather data can be of use to other sectors as well as aviation.

13g. Justification: PARE report Section 4.5 and Topic T4.6.

4. Ensuring Safety and Security

14a. ACARE GOAL 14: *Overall, the European air transport system has less than one accident per ten million commercial aircraft flights.*

14b. Recommendation 14*: Consider accident causes by order of statistical occurrence and for each class identify and implement appropriate safeguards.

14c. Rationale: The progress in aviation safety has been remarkable and steady on a timescale of decades by progressively identifying, investigating and virtually eliminating the major causes of accidents.

14d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AA, AN, CA, AI, RC, UA, AR.

14e. Relevance: The safest mode of transport can only benefit from being made even safer, and this requires investigating accident classes, finding corrective actions and proving that they can be implemented.

14f. Priority: This is a long-term sustained effort not a peak-and-done activity.

14g. Justification: PARE report Section 5.1.

15a. ACARE GOAL 15: *Weather and other hazards from the environment are precisely evaluated and risks are properly mitigated.*

15b. Recommendation 15*: Promote low-cost basic research on flight in adverse weather conditions (wind, rain, ash clouds, lightning, icing, storms and weather fronts) and select promising advances for demonstration.

15c. Rationale: Besides collecting higher-quality and more comprehensive weather data with higher spatial and temporal resolution (ACARE goals 5 and 13) its effects on aircraft dynamics must be modelled to identify effective prevention/corrective actions that must be simulated/validated.

15d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, UA, RC, AI, AA, AN, CA, AR.

15e. Relevance: High quality weather data and accurate knowledge of its effects on aircraft promote general timeliness of air transport (ACARE goal 5) and can prevent major accidents (ACARE goal 14).

15f. Priority: This must be a long-term sustained effort of learning from incidents how to prevent them from becoming accidents.

15g. Justification: PARE report Section 5.2 and Topic T5.1.

16a. ACARE GOAL 16: *The European air transport system operates seamlessly through interoperable and networked systems allowing manned and unmanned air vehicles to safely operate in the same airspace.*

16b. Recommendation 16.1*: Assess the evolution of air traffic capacity in Europe compared with the growth of air transport to identify the spare capacity available to other users like UAVs.

Recommendation 16.2:** Establish the qualifications required of operators of UAVs and other aircraft compared with airline pilots and air traffic controllers to ensure that aviation remains the safest means of transportation.

Recommendation 16.3:** Define the design, production, certification and maintenance procedures for UAVs and other aircraft to preserve or improve on the safety levels of current airliners that operate in the same airspace.

Recommendation 16.4: Explore the increased use of partially underused airspace to enable the expansion of operations by new types of aircraft.

16c. Rationale: The air traffic capacity needs to increase to keep up with the growth of air transport and the operation of UAV's in manned airspace will require additional capacity within the total achievable. The record of aviation as the safest mode of transportation is based on the highest engineering standards and professional qualifications as regards aircraft and cannot be compromised for UAV's operating in the same airspace. The use of partially unused airspace could provide testing area and additional capacity for UAV's to prove at least equal to manned aircraft in terms of safety, which is far from case at present.

16d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, CA, RC, UA, AR, AA.

16e. Relevance: UAV's offer an immense potential to expand air operations that will be realized sooner if design and operational issues are addressed to prove they are at least as safe as manned aircraft.

16f. Priority: Is high for safety issues related to engineering standards of UAV's and qualifications of operators. Is medium for issues of sufficient airspace capacity to add UAV's as another class of users. The maturation of UAV technologies and operations to the safety standards of aircraft is the baseline fundamental effort on which other objectives depend.

16g. Justification: PARE report Section 5.3 and Topic T5.2.

17a. ACARE GOAL 17: *Efficient boarding and security measures allow seamless security for global travel, with minimum passenger and cargo impact. Passengers and cargo pass through security controls without intrusion.*

17b. Recommendation 17: Develop non-intrusive passenger screening methods and foolproof luggage checking that allow fast flow through registration, border and boarding procedures.

17c. Rationale: Unfailing detection of dangerous individuals and objects can be combined with fast and efficient passenger and luggage screening only by developing better technology at the level of detector sensitivity and data processing.

17d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AP, AR, CA, PA.

17e. Relevance: Although passengers should understand that their safety is paramount, it is preferable not to test their tolerance and patience with intrusive and lengthy airport checking procedures.

17f. Priority: As many other issues in aviation, again a matter of sustained unrelenting effort to adopt the most recent effective technologies.

17g. Justification: PARE report Section 5.4 and Topic T5.3.

18a. ACARE GOAL 18: *Air vehicles are resilient by design to current and predicted onboard and on the ground security threat evolution, internally and externally to the aircraft.*

18b. Recommendation 18.1*: Design aircraft and establish procedures to (a) prevent unauthorised entry into the cockpit, (b) allow remote take-over up to safe landing in the case of an identified flight anomaly while (c) designing the system to be immune to the most sophisticated hacking.

Recommendation 18.2*: Set up an independent observatory of external risks to aircraft overflights to advise airlines or failing that warn passengers.

Recommendation 18.3: Design a worldwide airliner flight monitoring system and accident data recorders to ensure that accident/incident data is available regardless of time and location of occurrence.

18c. Rationale: Threats to aircraft can come not only from hijackers but also from aircrew disabilities and in some cases remote control may be the only solution, that must be immune to hacking or interference. The ICAO mandated national reporting of risks to aviation safety in areas of conflict has proved inadequate in Ukraine and elsewhere, and an independent observatory is needed to advise airlines and warn passengers. The occurrence of accidents that cannot be explained or take years to be investigated should be avoided in the future by worldwide monitoring of aircraft flights and mandatory fitting of air data recorders that can survive nearly all conditions, e.g. separate from the aircraft, float in the ocean and emit location.

18d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, CA, AN, AR, AI, RES, AU.

18e. Relevance: Aircraft overflights of unsafe regions must be avoided. Interference with safe flight procedures must be prevented. If an accident occurs its causes must be known to prevent recurrence.

18f. Priority: It is imperative to prevent interference with safe flight or overflight of conflict regions. Accident investigation should be feasible even in the most extreme cases.

18g. Justification: PARE report Section 5.5 and Topic T5.4

19a. ACARE GOAL 19: *The air transport system has a fully secured global high bandwidth data network, hardened and resilient by design to cyberattacks.*

19b. Recommendation 19.1: Assess the evolution of bandwidth requirements required to cope with increasing telecommunication needs associated with improved navigation, on-board systems monitoring, passenger connection and other services.

Recommendation 19.2:** Establish evolving standards for protection against cyberattacks, with different levels, the highest for flight systems and the lowest but non-trivial for ticketing, bearing in mind the risk of intrusion from lower levels.

19c. Rationale: The increase in bandwidth is a pre-requisite for more efficient and safer air transport in such aspects as navigation and air traffic management, systems and safety monitoring and general communications. More data on more flight critical functions requires cyber protection to a higher level. The vulnerability to disruption by cyber-attacks goes to the lowest level of airline ticketing. Countering cyber-attacks at all levels also requires blocking access up to the criticality chain.

19d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AN, AR, AP, AI, RC, UA.

19e. Relevance: Aviation has been one of the preferred targets of malicious actions that could extend from hijacking to hacking. The cyber-attacks should be prevented in the future better than hijacking has been in the past.

19f. Priority: It is important to ensure cyber resistance at all levels, and in particular flight critical systems on board and on the ground. The challenges of larger bandwidth are shared by aviation with other sectors that may be competing for the electromagnetic spectrum.

19g. Justification: PARE report Section 5.6 and Topics T5.4, T5.5 and T5.6.

5. Prioritizing Research, Test Facilities and Education

20a. ACARE GOAL 20: *European research and innovation strategies are jointly defined by all stakeholders, public and private, and implemented in a coordinated way with individual responsibility.*

20b. Recommendation 20:** Safeguard the long-term competitiveness of European aviation by supporting a broad program with a wide variety of low-cost applied basic research up to TRL3, to bridge the gap between the fundamental research of ERC and near-market driven focus of JUs, ensuring that Europe does not miss out the promising new ideas that could be exploited first by others to their advantage.

20c. Rationale: The EU aeronautics programme has had a remarkable growth in the allocation of resources from 36M€ in FP2 to 3.6B€ in FP7. This has been accompanied by a shift in projects from basic research (less than 1M€), to industrial cooperation (4-10M€), to large-scale demonstration (20-120M€) to the Joint Undertakings (more than 1B€). This shift to large scale near market research and development has led to a neglect of basic fundamental research essential to the long-term competitiveness of the aeronautical sector.

20d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, UA, RC, AI.

20e. Relevance: There is a large gap between the high-quality scientific research sponsored by the ERC and the market oriented near term developments of the JUs that needs to be filled by fundamental applied research with an aeronautical focus, to ensure that Europe retains a source of new ideas that are the basis of innovation and long-term competitiveness.

20f. Priority: The prosperous current state of the aeronautical sector could be undermined by a lack of long-term vision and new ideas that can be supported at a small fraction (1-3%) of what is invested in JUs.

20g. Justification: PARE report Section 6.1.

21a. ACARE GOAL 21: *Creation of a network of multidisciplinary technology clusters based on collaboration between industry, universities and research institutes.*

21b. Recommendation 21*:** The creation of multidisciplinary technology clusters requires a balanced and proportionate support of 4 levels of projects: (a) basic (3-5%); (b) collaborative industrial (15-17%); (c) large-scale demonstrators (20-30%); joint undertakings (50-60%).

21c. Rationale: A balanced aeronautical research programme should have 4 levels: (i) 50-100 basic research UA up to 1M€ each exploring up to TRL3 all sorts of novel promising ideas; (ii) 20-40 industrial research projects (4-10€) joining AI, RC, UA develop further the more prospects; (iii) 5-10 large scale demonstrators (20-100 M€) to reach practical scale on the best results at lower level; (iv) 1-2 joint undertakings (Clean Sky and SESAR) lead by industrial shorter term applications (1-2) B€. The EU FP Programs have shifted from one end to the other and should be rebalanced.

21d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, AN, RC, UA, AR, AP, CA.

21e. Relevance: The technology clusters could provide the filtering of results up the basic-industrial-demonstration-development chain. The basic projects as sources as new ideas should be based on peer review by UA as the ERC. The three higher levels would be based on selection by industry to ensure the focus of larger investments.

21f. Priority: Only a balanced allocation of resources at all 4 levels can promote the new ideas and links to practical application that can sustain competitiveness from the present to the future.

21g. Justification: Section 6.2 and Topic T6.1

Remark: The recommendation 21 is a means of implementation of recommendation 20.

22a. ACARE GOAL 22: *Identification, maintenance and ongoing development of strategic European aerospace test, simulation and development facilities. The ground and airborne validation and certification processes are integrated where appropriate.*

22b. Recommendation 22: Compare (a) a list of simulation, testing and certification needs with (b) an inventory of existing facilities to identify the needs currently satisfied and those requiring upgraded or new facilities.

22c. Rationale: The large simulation and test facilities are an essential institutional support to the aeronautical industry. They represent large investments of the Member States that have been coordinated in some occasions (DNW, ETW). An overall approach should compare what is needed with what is available, to prepare a program of upgraded and new facilities.

22d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, RC, AI, AU, AN.

22e. Relevance: Duplicate facilities may be justified by high demand at European level or nationally funded objectives. Some facilities may have multiple uses besides aeronautics. The cost, maintenance and benefits (or indispensability) of facilities are essential issues.

22g. Justification: PARE report Section 6.3

23a. ACARE GOAL 23: *Students are attracted to careers in aviation. Courses offered by European Universities closely match the needs of the aviation industry, its research establishments and administrations and evolve continuously as those needs develop.*

23b. Recommendation 23*: Foster a comprehensive program of attraction of talent to aeronautics to all education levels, complemented by job satisfaction measures at professional level, with special measures to promote gender equality and increase the participation of women.

23c. Rationale: The attraction of young talent to aeronautics should focus equally on both genders, start with the fascination of flying in youngsters, and continue with access to high-quality diversified university courses, followed by challenging and interesting careers in industry.

23d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, UA, AI, RC

23e. Relevance: Aeronautics requires mostly but not only hard skills in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics), that are becoming less abundant and eagerly sought by other sectors: thus aviation industry must engage promising young talent of both genders as early as possible, and sustain interest through industry visits and contact with professionals.

23f. Priority: A good talent pool exists in students and educators that must be supported to continue to provide industry with the best engineers, as countries with large population outnumber Europe in aerospace graduates.

23g. Justification: PARE report Section 6.4 and Topic T6.2

PART II – Recommendations towards the Implementation of PARE Objectives

The part II of the PARE report addresses a number of major topics related to the ACARE Goals and leads to additional PARE Objectives. The ACARE Goals and PARE Objectives are related among themselves or between each other, form complementary sets, and thus are numbered sequentially together with the associated recommendations.

6. Long-range Air Transport

24a. PARE OBJECTIVE 24: *Promote a level playing field in the large aircraft market*

24b. Recommendation 24: develop a strong legal, commercial and technical basis to (a) in any case, if necessary, deal with litigation at the WTO, and (b) preferably, if possible, renew the large aircraft agreement between the EU and the USA.

24c. Rationale: The airlines that want a competitive choice of aircraft are least interested in the Airbus-Boeing duopoly becoming a monopoly. This has not deterred the long running dispute at the WTO that may become a permanent nuisance.

24d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, AR.

24e. Relevance: The distorted charges made at the WTO should not be allowed to question the fact that European success in the airline market is based on the merits of engineering quality and efficient operations.

24f. Priority: Bears in mind mean that engineering excellence is the market winner, and legal challenges should not become an obstacle.

24g. Justification: sections 7.1 and 7.2 and topics T7.1, T7.2, T7.3 and T7.5.

25a. PARE OBJECTIVE 25: *Strengthen the position of the EU in the regional aircraft market.*

25b. Recommendation 25*: Support the development of European regional aircraft in a world market with an increasing number of competitors and additionally consider synergistic tie-ups between large and regional aircraft suppliers.

25c. Rationale: the majority stake of Airbus in the Bombardier C-series renamed A220 has extended the market reach to all jet airliners above 100 seats, with Boeing-Embraer as the only major competitor. In the regional market below 100 seats, the leading position of ATR faces multiple challengers from Canada, Japan, Russia and China.

25d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA, AR.

25e. Relevance: The under 100-seat regional aircraft market is relevant both as a feeder to major hubs and as a direct link between smaller communities, both in Europe and worldwide, amounting to a large and growing market, that attracts increased competition.

25f. Priority: The leading position of ATR needs to be maintained as the number and variety of challengers increases.

25g. Justification: Sections 7.3 and 7.4 and topics 7.4 and 7.5.

26a. PARE OBJECTIVE 26: *Strengthen the position of the EU in the business jet market.*

26b. Recommendation 26*: Support the development of European business jets and their expanded use as sensor/surveillance/control platforms.

26c. Rationale: Dassault, together with Gulfstream and Bombardier, is a world leader in large business jets, and European share of the rest of the market could increase.

26d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA.

26e. Relevance: The miniaturization of electronics allows business jets to be adapted to other missions like sensor platforms, patrol and surveillance, that are high-value extensions of the baseline business jet market.

26f. Priority: This is a successful area of European aviation that needs to be sustained and could be expanded

26g. Justification: Section 7.5 and topics 7.4 and 7.5.

27a. OBJECTIVE 27: *Maintain the EU leadership in the world helicopter market.*

27b. Recommendation 27*:** Ensure that Europe keeps at least abreast of developments in high-power high-speed helicopters/convertibles with enhanced hot-and-high lift capabilities.

27c. Rationale: The USA has started a major program FVL (Future Vertical Lift) to design helicopters/convertibles with (i) twice the range, (ii) 50% higher speed, (iii) over twice the hover payload in demanding hot and high conditions, using engines with double power but similar fuel consumption, size and weight. Although it is military program it could have civil spinoffs: (i) double-range for off-shore oil exploration; (ii) higher speed for medical emergencies and executive transport; (iii) greater payload for rescue and transport missions. All this could challenge the position of Europe with over 50% of the world helicopter market.

27d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC and UA.

27e. Relevance: The FVL program in the USA is justified by the need to counter threats from near peer adversaries in Europe and elsewhere: hence it is relevant to the defence of Europe. The implications in the civil market could be to reverse the tables passing dominance from Airbus Helicopters and Agusta-Westland to Bell and Sikorsky. The FVL contenders are the Valor tilt-rotor from Bell and Defiant dual rotor plus pusher-propeller helicopter from Sikorsky; Europe has analogues in the Augusta-Bell AB609 and Airbus X3 that holds the world helicopter speed record, and competitive turboshaft engines from Turbomeca and Rolls-Royce.

27f. Priority: There is a need for a program with a minimum investment to ensure that Europe does not fall behind. It is not necessary to match the massive US funding of FVL. The result of FVL could be as expensive as the Bell V-22 Osprey with small effect on the market; or it could like the RAH-66 Comanche lead to no significant production after years and billions of investment. The aim here is to safeguard against potential surprise breakthroughs that could change the European leading market position without making large speculative investments.

27g. Justification: PARE report Section 7.6 and topics 7.5 and 7.6.

28a. PARE OBJECTIVE 28: *Provide an European alternative to the drones used in Europe with potential to also enter the world market.*

28b. Recommendation 28*:** Leverage the technological capabilities demonstrated in several prototype drones into a coherent European Programme covering all levels, to satisfy internal needs and complete in the world market.

28c. Rationale: The market for MALE (Medium Altitude Long Endurance) drones is a sad example of lack of coordination in Europe: (i) of several prototype programs (Taranis in the UK, Mako in Germany, Hammerhead in Italy, Neuron Multinational led by France) none has yet reached operational status; (ii) in the meantime several European nations have bought American drones; (iii) in the international market China has emerged as the major competitor of the US through lower prices and less export restrictions.

28d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA.

28e. Relevance: Europe has the technology to develop all classes of UAVs that are increasingly relevant to a wide range of defence and civil missions, so the issue is one of coordination in the allocation of resources.

28f. Priority: There must be an end to the European dependence on foreign UAVs, and a move to enter the international market, since there is the technology to achieve both targets.

28g. Justification: PARE report Section 7.6.

7. Emerging Aviation Technologies

29a. OBJECTIVE 29: *Keep the EU at the forefront of progress in the electrification of aircraft.*

29b. Recommendation 29*:** Make a thorough assessment followed by support measures on (a) emerging electric systems and propulsion technologies, (b) their potential to satisfy mission requirements and (c) the likely evolution of both.

29c. Rationale: Although the automobile sector may lead the electrification of transport vehicles, the specific needs of aeronautics and fast technological evolution will have increasing importance from drones to airplanes.

29d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA, AR.

29e. Relevance: Small electric drones, emerging electric air taxi, more electric airliners with bleedless engines and advances in electric propulsion and systems all point towards increasing electrification.

29f. Priority: Progress in electrification is rapid and although major market impact could be years away those caught unprepared may take a long time to catch-up.

29g. Justification: PARE report Section 8.1.

30a. PARE OBJECTIVE 30: *Promote and exploit advances in additive manufacturing.*

30b. Recommendation 30*: Consider the implications on prototyping, series production and spares supply of additive manufacturing regarding (a) usable materials, (b) quality standards and (c) life-cycle costs.

30c. Rationale: Although additive manufacturing is an industry wide activity, aeronautics may be the leader in some areas and should keep up with progress in other areas.

30d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA, AR, CA.

30e. Relevance: Additive manufacturing allows the production of complex pieces with less parts and could replace spare part inventories with local production, as limitations in series production, choice of materials and quality finish are overcome.

30f. Priority: Aeronautics needs to benefit from general progress and lead only where necessary.

30g. Justification: PARE report Section 8.2.

31a. PARE OBJECTIVE 31: *Incorporate the experience from other sectors to achieve more efficient and economical production in aeronautics.*

31b. Recommendation 31*: Consider the best combination of 4.0 technologies, including automation and information, as applicable to various production rates and scales of equipment in aeronautics.

31c. Rationale: Aeronautics can benefit from 4.0 technologies, especially by integrating the full life-cycle design-production-operation-maintenance.

31d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, AR, CA, RC, UA.

31e. Relevance: The 4.0 factory requires significant investment and reliance on big data and artificial intelligence and could lead to reduction on development time and cost of production and operation.

31f. Priority: Aeronautics is a user more than a leader except in specific areas with the large-scale integration over a long-life time as the main issue.

31g. Justification: PARE report Section 8.3 and topic 8.1.

32a. PARE OBJECTIVE 32: *Provide the telecommunications capacity needed for connected aircraft, navigation, monitoring and other services.*

32b. Recommendation 32*: Assess the growth of capacity needs for navigation, systems monitoring and passenger services, and how the required bandwidth can provide free from unintended or malicious interference.

32c. Rationale: Increases in air traffic capacity and safer and more efficient aircraft operations will require increased data sharing and larger telecommunications bandwidth protected from unintended or malicious interference.

32d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AN, AR, AI, RC, UA, AP.

32e. Relevance: The growth of air traffic and progress in safety plus passenger services may require more than proportional increases in data sharing and telecommunications.

32f. Priority: This is an issue for society in general, with particular incidence in aviation.

32g. Justification: PARE report Section 8.4 and topic 8.2.

33a. PARE OBJECTIVE 33: *Monitor threats in cybersecurity and devise timely protection for all levels of aviation systems.*

33b. Recommendation 33:** Consider the levels of cyber protection needed for the various aeronautical activities, and how to monitor and counter threats.

33c. Rationale: The informatics incidents at specific air traffic control facilities and with airline reservation systems suggest possible vulnerabilities that could be also exploited in malicious attacks.

33d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AN, AR, AP, AI, CA.

33e. Relevance: Security in aviation would be enhanced by a comprehensive cyber protection system with several levels, highest for flight critical tasks and lowest for commercial ticketing.

33f. Priority: The consequences if cyber-attacks have been seen elsewhere, aviation in the past has been a preferred target of malicious actions and thus preventive measures are desirable.

33g. Justification: PARE report Section 8.5 and topics 8.3 and 8.4.

34a. PARE OBJECTIVE 34: *Assess the implications in aeronautics of advances in big data, including the use of what is already available.*

34b. Recommendation 34*: Consider the expected benefits versus the required investment in using big data techniques in aeronautical activities for which relevant data already exists or has to be newly sourced.

34c. Rationale: Large amounts of systems data are already recorded by aircraft in flight and its use for maintenance, safety or other purposes could be enhanced.

34d. Stakeholders: AR, AN, AP, EU, MS, AI, RC, UA.

34e. Relevance: More benefit could be taken out of currently collected data and there is the prospect of gathering more data with a well targeted strategy.

34f. Priority: This is part of a global trend shared by aviation.

34g. Justification: PARE report Section 8.6 and topics 8.5, 8.6 and 8.7.

35a. PARE OBJECTIVE 35: *Assess the potential benefits and risks of the use of artificial intelligence in aeronautics.*

35b. Recommendation 35*: Identify the situations in aeronautics in which the learning processes of Artificial Intelligence can be efficient and safe and distinguish those where there is limited training material or potential dependence on imagination.

35c. Rationale: Artificial Intelligence has the advantage of systematic learning from large amounts of data ('Artificial Imitation') but lacks any form of imagination when facing untrained situations.

35d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA, AR, AN, AP.

35e. Relevance: The use of artificial intelligence can lead to much more efficient and reliable implementation of known tasks, but care is needed concerning unforeseen or untrained situations, when it cannot replace human imagination, resourcefulness or true and real intelligence.

35f. Priority: Part of a general trend that aviation may share without losing an eye on risks.

35g. Justification: PARE report Section 8.7 and topics 8.8 and 8.9.

36a. PARE OBJECTIVE 36: *Assess the implications on aircraft design, certification, operation and maintenance of new developmental and breakthrough materials and structures.*

36b. Recommendation 36:** Consider the progress in advanced materials like composites, ceramics and special alloys and also the prospects of less mature developments like nanotube structures and other nanotechnologies.

36c. Rationale: Progress in material, structures and production methods has a main steady gradual element (composites, ceramics, alloys) and there is also a potential for revolutionary breakthroughs (nanotube structures, microelectromechanical devices).

36d. Stakeholders: AI, RC, UA, EU, MS, AR, CA.

36e. Relevance: Research on materials, structures and production is a major topic, and a complement is some forward look on the maturation of long-term prospects.

36f. Priority: Maintaining current high level of activity perhaps with a little more emphasis on promising developments still lacking maturity.

36g. Justification: PARE report Sections 8.8 and 8.9, and topics 8.10, 8.11, 8.12 and 8.13.

8. Cooperation beyond Europe's borders

37a. PARE OBJECTIVE 37: *Promote the seamless compatibility of Air Traffic Management (ATM) systems worldwide, across continents and oceans.*

37b. Recommendation 37:** Support cooperation between SESAR in Europe and NextGen in the US to ensure compatibility across the North Atlantic and provide the basis for progress in the world ATM market as the growth of air travel increases capacity needs elsewhere.

37c. Rationale: Air Traffic Management is the major potential bottleneck to the growth of aviation on a global scale, with particular incidence in developed regions with dense traffic like Europe and Eastern US, but gradually spreading to other regions.

37d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AN, AR, AP, AI, RC, UA.

37e. Relevance: Air Traffic Management should be seamless across continents and oceans, and the needed increases in capacity combined with safety and security are a major market for equipment suppliers in areas of European leadership

37f. Priority: It is essential to avoid the congestion and delays of the past and cope with traffic growth and new users like UAVs

37g. Justification: PARE report Section 9.1 and topic 9.1 and 9.2.

38a. PARE OBJECTIVE 38: *Promote harmonized certification standards worldwide as already exist in other sectors to ensure the growth of aviation as the safest mode of transport.*

38b. Recommendation 38*:** Strengthen the cooperation of EASA/FAA on common certification standards and their adoption worldwide to avoid duplication or degradation in specific regions.

38c. Rationale: The coordinated and mutually accepted certification by either the FAA and EASA is a major breakthrough in avoiding costly duplication and preventing misuse of certification as a trade barrier. The Russian example of local certification is being followed by China, whose aircraft have faced long delays and major difficulties in obtaining EASA or FAA certification. Resorting to 'local certification' leads to lower safety standards that can affect not only locals but also Europeans travelling in those countries. The export of such EASA/FAA uncertificated aircraft could damage the unique overall safety record of aviation.

38d. Stakeholders: The EU and MS, possibly with US coordination, since there is a common interest in supporting EASA/FAA standards.

38e. Relevance: The EU and MS could insist on cooperation with China and Russia being conditional on progress towards worldwide certification standards. Although aircraft not certificated by EASA or FAA cannot operate in Europe, US or other developed regions their use as cheap unsafe transport elsewhere cannot be encouraged and puts European visitors at risk.

38f. Priority: It is prudent to prevent the emergence of a parallel market of local or third world aviation with degraded safety standards that are already lower elsewhere than in Europe/US. Will require diplomatic and negotiation skills.

38g. Justification: PARE report section 9.2 and topics 9.6 and 9.7.

39a. PARE OBJECTIVE 39: *Minimize the effects of aviation on the environment on a global scale.*

39b. Recommendation 39:** The reduction of environmental effects of aviation in a global scale should be a key point in the EU cooperation with other countries.

39c. Rationale: The EU has played a leading and exemplary role as champion of environmental protection in all areas including aviation and this is a worthy effort to pursue.

39d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AN, CA, AI, RC, UA, AP.

39e. Relevance: Although aviation is not the biggest polluter in general or among means of transport the objective should be to reduce its percentage by doing better than average progress.

39f. Priority: There is already a significant effort, although airport noise and en-route emissions are increasing concerns.

39g. Justification: PARE report Section 9.3 and topic 9.5.

40a. PARE OBJECTIVE 40: *Promote aviation safety worldwide including for European and other passengers flying with non-European airlines.*

40b. Recommendation 40: Support activities raising the aviation safety standards to more uniform high levels across the globe, in particular helping the improvement of airlines banned from flying into Europe that may still carry European passengers elsewhere.

40c. Rationale: The differences in aviation safety standards among airlines from different countries justify banning some from flying into Europe, and the provision of some technical assistance could help lifting the bans and improving safety in less developed regions.

40d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, CA, AN.

40e. Relevance: Besides ensuring safety (and security) of air travel in Europe it is desirable to promote similar standards in less developed regions of the world, both for the locals and for the European business or leisure travel.

40f. Priority: This is an extension of current preventive bans to cooperative improvement for non-European airlines and aviation authorities.

40g. Justification: PARE report Section 9.4 and topics 9.6 and 9.7.

41a. PARE OBJECTIVE 41: *Promote aviation security worldwide, including at airports and destinations frequently used for European business and holiday travel.*

41b. Recommendation 41: Support high security levels at airports outside Europe by cooperating with authorities eager to keep European business/tourism travel, and otherwise warn travellers of risk.

41c. Rationale: European travellers may be at greater risk when travelling in less developed regions where extremist groups target aviation and foreigners and thus support to cooperative local authorities is important to boost security.

41d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, CA, AP, AI.

41e. Relevance: Local authorities in third world countries may have an interest in attracting business and tourism and welcome assistance in making foreigners and their own citizens safer.

41f. Priority: This is a continuous, gradual and moderate effort.

41g. Justification: PARE report Section 9.5 and topic 9.8.

42a. PARE OBJECTIVE 42: *Promote as far as possible an open and fair market for aircraft at least in the civil sector.*

42b. Recommendation 42: The advances in efficiency and compliance with the highest environmental, safety and security standards can contribute to a competition based on quality rather than other interests.

42c. Rationale: Making available safe and efficient aircraft may help undermine protectionist and biased local choices.

42d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA.

42e. Relevance: Promoting a level playing field is not easy and desirability and quality may function in a more effective and subtle way than harsh political pressures.

42f. Priority: It is a matter of good business practice.

42g. Justification 43: PARE report Section 9.6 and 9.7 and topics 9.9 and 9.10.

9. Attracting Young Talent to Aeronautics

43a. PARE OBJECTIVE 43: *Stimulate the interest of children with entertaining stories about flying.*

43b. Recommendation 43: Make available on-line and accessible to primary schools and parents, children stories and cartoons involving flying that are both entertaining and educational.

43c. Rationale: Flying and space can be fascinating subjects for children and can be used to make interesting stories.

43d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, families, primary schools.

43e. Relevance: In the history of aviation many of the pioneers and major contributors started their interest at an early age.

43f. Priority: Normal activity to be sustained.

43g. Justification: PARE report Section 10.1 and 9.7 and topics 10.2 and 10.3.

44a. PARE OBJECTIVE 44: *Motivate secondary school students to choose university degrees in aerospace engineering.*

44b. Recommendation 44.1: Make available from the early teens, on-line and to secondary schools, a set of easy to implement flight experiments and challenges such as drones now so commonplace and cheap.

Recommendation 44.2*: Give secondary school students at later stages the opportunity to come to presentations and laboratories at a university, together with a parent/mentor or trusted friend.

44c. Rationale: There are readily available inexpensive 'toy' drones that give real flying experience and can teach also responsible use. Complemented by visits to university laboratories and presentations this would continue to attract good candidates of both genders.

44d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, UA, secondary schools, families, friends.

44e. Relevance: Given the variety of university degrees that university candidates can choose from and the demands of 'hard skills' in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) aeronautics can attract the best as a combination of advanced technologies with bright future prospects.

44f. Priority: In addition to suitable dissemination, the visits to universities with aeronautical education can make all the difference in attracting the best candidates.

44g. Justification: PARE report Section 10.2 and topic 10.3.

45a. PARE OBJECTIVE 45: *Attract the brightest graduates in aeronautical engineering to industry before they are lured away by attractive, well-paid offers elsewhere, e.g. by consultant and financial services.*

45b. Recommendation 45:** Provide industrial stays for students of aeronautical engineering with mentoring that values their skills and keeps track of the most promising for employment after graduation.

45c. Rationale: in order to attract bright graduates in aeronautical engineering with many alternative enticing job offers, industry and other employers should engage them at an early stage through professional stays and follow-up with attractive job offers without delay after graduation.

45d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA, AN, AR, AP.

45e. Relevance: The strong analytical and problem-solving skills of the graduates from the best aerospace engineering degrees are in much demand from other sectors in and out of engineering, so the aeronautical industry cannot afford to be slow in attraction measures.

45f. Priority: Attracting the best engineers is the key to progress in aviation, and an absolute must if Europe wants to remain a leader as other developed (US, Japan, Canada) or more populous (China, India) or lower cost (Russia, Brazil) regions strengthen their competitive challenge.

45g. Justification: PARE report Section 10.3 and topics 10.4 and 10.5.

46a. PARE OBJECTIVE 46: *Make careers in aeronautical industry interesting relative to other alternatives by focusing on fascinating technology with adequate reward.*

46b. Recommendation 46: Bring an aeronautical engineering student together with a mentor/relative/trusted friend to a one-day visit to industry to be remembered for life as a career choice.

46c. Rationale: An in-depth one-day visit to industry with briefings and access to facilities can be a day to be remembered for life and make a career decision. The company of a mentor/relative/trusted friend can play a major role in advising a mature choice.

46d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA, AN, AR, AP, PA, other employers.

46e. Relevance: Perhaps the most important question when choosing a career is “What will I do or be my work?” and convincing answers with supporting evidence is the best reply.

46f. Priority: This kind of initiative already exists and the idea of a memorable one-day visit could be expanded.

46g. Justification: PARE report Section 10.4 and topics 10.6 and 10.7.

47a. PARE OBJECTIVE 47: *Motivate and reward the workforce to promote dedication, ingenuity, efficiency and loyalty.*

47b Recommendation 47: Give employees opportunities for innovation, let them share important and interesting work, and recognise their contribution to the success of the company.

47c. Rationale: Giving opportunities for the workforce to be creative and proactive rewards the commitments of employees, creates links with a receptive management and promotes the prosperity of the enterprise.

47d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA, AN, AR, AP, CA.

47e, Relevance: The best way to keep a skilled and up-to-date workforce is to follow-up on their initiatives for progress with suitable mature support.

47f. Priority: Should be normal company practice and is well worth reminding and keeping in mind.

47g. Justification: PARE report Section 10.5 and topics 10.8 and 10.9.

48a. PARE OBJECTIVE 48: *Retain a capable and faithful workforce by providing stable employment, interesting work, reliable benefits and a friendly environment.*

48b. Recommendation 48: A worthwhile alternative to job mobility is to have competent staff, able to adapt to change and to contribute to progress, sufficiently well integrated not to wish other careers and serve as example to relatives and friends.

48c. Rationale: As an alternative to the modern high-mobility, short-term employment, and not excluding intermediate cases, there is nothing wrong with the old model of a company-family which support a dedicated workforce with long experience and attracts the next generation.

48d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, UA, AR, AN, AP, CA, other employers.

48e. Relevance: The maintenance of a faithful long-experienced workforce can also attract new ideas and support further recruitment by proving a stable and progressive environment for progress.

48f. Priority: Should be normal company practice worth keeping.

48g. Justification: PARE report Section 10.6 and topics 10.10 and 10.11.

10. Increasing the Participation of Women

49a. PARE OBJECTIVE 49: *Counter family and societal bias discouraging girls from interest in vehicles, be it cars or planes.*

49b. Recommendation 49: Make available on the internet and to primary school's children stories and cartoons where girls drive cars and fly aeroplanes as much as boys do and let them play with vehicle models or ask for them as presents.

49c. Rationale: The bias since childhood that "girls play with dolls and boys play with cars/planes" needs to be countered by gender neutral stories about boys and girls flying or collaborating in making origami' planes.

49d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, primary education, families, friends.

49e. Relevance: Flying has always been an inspiration for mankind from childhood through adulthood to old age, regardless of gender.

49f. Priority: This should be a normal steady activity.

49g. Justification: PARE report Section 11.1 and topic 11.1.

50a. PARE OBJECTIVE 50: Give girls and boys in primary schools the same opportunities to choose their games and entertainment.

50b. Recommendation 50: The primary and secondary school programmes and activities could include flight experiments equally accessible to boys and girls.

50c. Rationale: Gender bias may be countered in a natural, non-dramatic, non-political fashion by simple neutral education since primary school by providing educators with suitable material that is attractive to children of both genders.

50d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, primary schools, families.

50e. Relevance: The best way to avoid problems is not to create them by adopting a neutral attitude, and this also applies to gender in the education of children.

50f. Priority: Should be normal primary school practice and deserves further encouragement.

50g. Justification: PARE report Section 11.2 and topic 11.2.

51a. PARE OBJECTIVE 51: Encourage more girls to take aeronautical engineering degrees.

51b. Recommendation 51:** Reinforce and accelerate this slowly growing trend by visits to universities and industry, role models of success stories and the same fascinating technologies.

51c. Rationale: The measures to attract young talent to aeronautical careers are similar and some extra effort needs to be put in compensating gender bias.

51d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, UA, AI, RC, PA, other educators and employers.

51e. Relevance: Women perform at least as well as men in aeronautical engineering degrees and enlarge the talent pool both in quantity and diversity.

51f. Priority: There is a vast potential of talent that is only modestly tapped.

51g. Justification: PARE report Section 11.3 and topic 11.3.

52a. PARE OBJECTIVE 52: Provide women with attractive careers in aeronautics in industry and academia.

52b. Recommendation 52: Make all aspects of job recruitment, from the announcements, to the interview, to the benefits, gender equal, and try to compensate for eventual gender differences.

52c. Rationale: The outdated lingering view that aviation is a job for men except for attendants should be countered by recruiting campaigns that are carefully gender neutral and cleverly undermine any gender bias.

52d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA, PA, AN, AR, AP.

52e. Relevance: Women bring similar competence and different skills and having both genders is a human resources asset.

52f. Priority: Should be normal practice and offers scope for improvement

52g. Justification: PARE report Section 11.4 and topic 11.4.

53a. PARE OBJECTIVE 53: *Discourage and prevent continuation of abuse based on gender.*

53b. Recommendation 53*: Take gender abuse as seriously as gross incompetence or major financial misconduct as concerns the consequences and leave no doubts on anyone's mind about this policy.

53c. Rationale: The activity of a company and its hierarchical structure should not tolerate gender abuse as much as it should not tolerate gross incompetence or financial fraud.

53d. Stakeholders: EU and MS legislations, AI, RC, UA, PA, AR, AN, AP, all other employers.

53e. Relevance: The tendency to ignore gender abuse or look the other way if it comes from up the chain are among the examples of non-acceptable attitudes.

53f. Priority: This is a human rights issue that is a fundamental principle.

53g. Justification: PARE report Section 11.5 and topic 11.5.

54a. PARE OBJECTIVE 54: *Ensure that the protection of family, maternity and parenthood is effectively implemented with its legal basis as a minimum.*

54b. Recommendation 54: Take family, maternity and parenthood in consideration in the assignment of tasks and giving a suitable working environment.

54c. Rationale: In addition to faithfully implementing the legislation on the protection of family more can be done by goodwill towards dedicated employees.

54d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, employers in general.

54e. Relevance: Respect for family values and culture should be part of company ethics.

54f. Priority: Normal practice to be encouraged.

54g. Justification: PARE report Section 11.6 and topic 11.6.

55a. PARE OBJECTIVE 55: *Give equal recognition of achievements regardless of gender, taking into account the circumstances.*

55b. Recommendation 55: Avoid direct and reverse discrimination or bias by judging and rewarding achievements in an even, transparent and fair way, that is not seen as gender bias.

55c. Rationale: Perhaps the best way to achieve gender balance is to avoid direct or reverse discrimination and to recognise and compensate for legitimate differences.

55d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, employers in general.

55e. Relevance: Women need no favours, only fair and equal treatment so that their merits are recognised and cannot be dismissed as reverse discrimination.

55f. Priority: Should be normal practice and it is still not always the case.

55g. Justification: PARE report Section 11.7 and topic 11.7.

56a. PARE OBJECTIVE 56: *See the differences between the genders as an opportunity for a symbiosis of distinct talents that furthers smooth progress.*

56b. Recommendation 56: Assign positions and tasks using the best talents and skills available in both genders to promote creativity and efficiency.

56c. Rationale: The equality of men and women does not exclude different talents that bring most benefit in a symbiotic collaboration.

56d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, all employers.

56e. Relevance: Choosing the right person on team for the task should be based not only on experience but also the balance of skills in which gender can be one of many factors.

56f. Priority: Should be normal practice.

56g. Justification: PARE report Section 11.8 and topic 11.8.

57a. PARE OBJECTIVE 57: *Increase the participation of women in aeronautics in the most effective way.*

57b. Recommendation 57: The greater numbers of women in aeronautics should be regarded as not just as a numerical enlargement of the workforce but also as a broadening of the talent available.

57c. Rationale: The rationale for the increased participation of women in aeronautics is not just a potential increase in numbers but also an opportunity for broader individual and team skills.

57d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, AI, RC, UA, other employers.

57e. Relevance: A broad view of the added talent brought by more women in aeronautics is needed to obtain the greatest benefit.

57f. Priority: A general policy issue.

57g. Justification: PARE report Section 11.9.

58a. PARE OBJECTIVE 58: *Recognise the historic achievements of women, including in aeronautics, in biased or unfavourable circumstances.*

58b. Recommendation 58*: Consider the lives of outstanding women, including aviators and astronauts, not only from a biographical point of view but also recognising the challenges they had to overcome to realise their achievements.

58c. Rationale: The achievements of great women in aeronautics and the gender unequal challenges they had to overcome are an indicator of the obstacles that should be removed

58d. Stakeholders: EU, MS, employers

58e. Relevance: The role models serve as example for women who should be assured to have more of a gender equal treatment.

58f. Priority: It is an activity to counter unfounded and untrue preconceptions that could reduce the value of women contributions to aeronautics.

58g. Justification: PARE report Section 11.10 and topics 11.9 to 11.13.

Conclusion

The ACARE Goals and PARE Objectives are complementary:

- The ACARE Goals state broad aims, and deliberately do not detail how to achieve them, since there are many possible contributions that can be used;
- The PARE Objectives detail some specific measures that could contribute to ACARE Goals without excluding other alternatives or complementary measures.

Thus, the ACARE Goals provide the broad overall justification of an aeronautics activity, and the PARE Objectives contribute to a more detailed work plan that will include additional ideas.

The 23 ACARE goals with 32 recommendations and 35 PARE objectives with 36 recommendations add to 58 initiatives with 68 recommendations.

While it would be easy to give many high priorities, this would not be helpful and would defeat the very purpose of prioritization.

To enforce some discipline for each of the sets of ACARE goals and PARE objectives as indicated in the following table, the highest priority of 3 asterisks was limited to 4, plus 6 two asterisks, 10 one asterisk and the rest no asterisks to total 68 recommendations.

Table 1.1 Assignment of priorities to the 23 ACARE Goals and 35 PARE objectives

Initiatives for Horizon Europe 23 + 35 = 58	ACARE Goals 23	PARE Objectives 35
Highest Priority *** 4+4=8	1, 6, 9.1, 21	27, 28, 29, 38
Very High Priority ** 6+6=12	7, 9.3, 16.2, 16.3, 19.2, 20	33, 36, 37, 39, 45, 51

<p>High Priority * 10+10=20</p>	<p>2, 3, 4, 9.2, 14, 15, 16.1, 18.1, 18.2, 23</p>	<p>25, 26, 30, 31, 32, 34, 35, 44.2, 53, 58</p>
<p>Medium Priority 12+16=28</p>	<p>5.1, 5.2, 8, 9.4, 10, 11, 12, 13, 16.4, 17, 18.3, 19.1, 22</p>	<p>24, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44.1, 46, 47 48, 49, 50, 52, 54, 55, 56, 57</p>
<p>Total Recommendation 68</p>	<p>32</p>	<p>36</p>

PART I - Progress Towards the 23 Flightpath 2050 Goals

The PART I considers in sequence the 23 ACARE goals from the reference status in 2010 to the future perspectives up to 2050. Depending on the goal, four approaches are used:

- A. A baseline integrated text covering the whole subject;
- B. As the option A supplemented by an in-depth analysis of specific important aspects as key major topics;
- C. As an alternative to option B a sequential analysis in steps:
 - a. The reference state in 2010;
 - b. The current status;
 - c. The expected evolution up to the predictable horizon in 2025;
 - d. The possible extrapolation up to 2050;
 - e. The remaining gap, if any, and some possible means of bridging it.
- D. The option A supplemented by a combination of the options C and D.

Since the ACARE goals are quite diverse, the availability of these four options allows the choice of the most suited for each particular case. The PART I is divided into 5 Chapters (2 to 6) corresponding to the 5 areas in the Flightpath 2050 document. Within each Chapter there are sections for each ACARE goal.

Chapter 2 - Meeting Societal and Market Needs

This set of 5 goals concerns air traffic capacity (2.1.1), ground infrastructure (2.1.2), mobility (2.1.3), speed (2.1.4) and punctuality (2.1.5).

2.1 Air Traffic Capacity

****Flightpath 2050 Goal 1: "An air traffic management system in place that provides a range of services to handle at least 25 million flights a year of all types of air vehicles, including unmanned and autonomous systems integrated into and interoperable with the overall air transport system with 24-hour operation of airports. European airspace is used flexibly to facilitate reduced environmental impact from aircraft operation"***

The present Chapter addresses the main issue of air traffic capacity (25 million flights per year) and flexibility of operation. The integration of unmanned and autonomous aircraft is addressed in goal 16 (section 5.3). The 24-hour operation of airports and environmental impacts are addressed in goals 9 and 10 (Chapter 4). The main issue of air transport capacity (section 2.1) concerns runway (2.1.1) and airways terminal capacity (2.1.2). Airport ground infrastructure and air traffic management are considered in goals 2 and 5 (sections 2.2 and 2.5).

2.1.1 Runway Capacity and Dynamic Separation

Most often the main limit on airport capacity is the availability of runways. The simultaneous operation of runways is permitted if they are parallel (no crossing flights) and spaced more than 400 meters (the vortex wakes of aircraft operating from one runway do not affect operations from other runways). A standard separation of 90 seconds between flights would allow 40 movements (take-off or landings) per hour from a single runway. Careful planning can increase this figure up to 60 movements per hour per runway, depending on the safe separation between aircraft, which is the critical safety factor.

The safe separation (SS) is such that the vortex wake of the leading aircraft has decayed sufficiently so that its effects are within the control power of the following aircraft. The ICAO separation table divides aircraft into "light", "medium" and "heavy" and sets SS for all 9 possible pairs: the largest separation for a light aircraft behind a heavy, and vice-versa for the shortest separation. The ICAO separation rules are empirical and have proved safe, though there are exceptions: (a) the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) introduced a 'special' category for the Boeing 757 after some incidents showed that it did not fit into its weight category; (b) the world's largest airliner, the Airbus A380 is subject to 'super heavy' separation larger than the "heavy".

The SS actually depends on many more factors than just aircraft weight: (i) the characteristics of the leading aircraft that determine its vortex wake; (ii) the atmospheric conditions that affect the decay of the wake until it encounters the following aircraft; (iii) the control capability of the following aircraft in overcoming the effects of the wake encounter. The maximization of runway capacity would be achieved by "dynamic separation" that sets the separation distance or time appropriate to the characteristics of each pair of aircraft and the prevailing atmospheric conditions. The use of extended separation tables with more than 3 aircraft categories is a smaller step than the full use of dynamic separation.

2.1.2 Terminal Area Airways Capacity

Besides runway capacity, the other important factor is to manage take-offs and landings with the minimum safe separation without: (a) having aircraft circling above in holding patterns; (b) queuing on the ground to reach a runway position. The landing and take-off delays are a major contributor to emissions near airports, burning fuel that also affects airline economics. The maximum use of available runway capacity requires four-dimensional space-time navigation, so that successive aircraft land and take-off at precise times with the minimum safe separation. This requires not only efficient management of ground movements (goal 2 and section 2.2) but mainly efficient air traffic management (goal 5 and section 2.5) in the terminal area around airports that is the most congested. The issues to be resolved include: (i) the organization of incoming flights into a landing sequence with optimal separations; (ii) the management of the take-off sequence without waiting or idle times on the ground; (iii) the merging of the take-off (ii) and landing (i) sequences without holding patterns in the air; (iv) the compatibility of terminal area traffic (take-offs and landings) with another airways traffic. These items (i) to (iv) are among the most important aspects of Air Traffic Management (ATM) often with greatest impact on capacity. The current airline traffic of 10 million flights per year is expected to rise to 14 million in 2025, and the goal of 25 million by 2050 is consistent with a growth rate of air transport of 2.8 % per year in Europe. Traffic forecasts vary with region of the world and have a degree of uncertainty, and there is no doubt on the need for increased capacity to cope with traffic growth.

The evolution of the air traffic capacity is closely related to air traffic management (ATM) that is thus a Key Topic.

KEY TOPIC T2.1 – EVOLUTION OF THE AIR TRAFFIC CAPACITY

Scope of the goal

Air traffic capacity		
<p><u>Goal 1:</u> An air traffic management system in place that provides a range of services to handle at least 25 million flights a year of all types of air vehicles, including unmanned and autonomous systems integrated into and interoperable with the overall air transport system with 24-hour operation of airports. European airspace is used flexibly to facilitate reduced environmental impact from aircraft operation.</p>		
Comparison with 2017 SRIA document	Why	Lacks
<p>The description of the goal is not exactly aligned with the action lines proposed in the 2017 version of the SRIA document.</p>	<p>Although the measures included in the report in order to increase air traffic capacity are coherent (simultaneous operations, lower safe separation), they are not contemplated in the SRIA document.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performance-based operations would allow aircraft to fly the most efficient route and profile, assuring improvements in capacity. • The automation introduction and advanced navigation technologies will allow to improve accuracy, quality of the service and the system capacity.
<p>Components missing</p>	<p>The main issue of air transport capacity concerns runway system capacity, Terminal Area (TMA) capacity and En route Capacity.</p>	<p>ATM (Air Traffic Management) accounts for increases in capacity in both EN route and TMA. Although ATM is addressed in goal 5 it is necessary to address the challenges of En route capacity here at the same level than the challenges on Terminal Area</p>
<p>Components missing</p>	<p>The goal claims for a “range of services” that might be required by “all types of air vehicles”. Although unmanned and autonomous are addressed in goal 16 (section 2.4.3), this section does not cover other types of vehicles that will be part of the future population of airspace-users such as VTOL.</p>	<p>Companies like Uber are envisaging a concept of “On-demand aviation” supported by a network of small, electric aircraft that take off and land vertically (called VTOL aircraft for Vertical Take-off and Landing), will enable rapid, reliable transportation between suburbs and cities. Over a dozen companies, with as many different design approaches, are working to make VTOLs a reality.</p>

Air traffic capacity		
	<p>Additionally, all this new type of vehicles and applications for UAS will demand a new set of services provided by a new and revolutionary Traffic Management System (a safety system may be needed to help ensure this newest entrant into the skies does not collide with buildings, larger aircraft, or one another).</p>	<p>Known as UTM, this system is today only conceptual project but should become an important assess of the future Air transport system, that should also be studied as part of in goal 16 in section 2.4.3. NASA is researching prototype technologies such as airspace design, dynamic geofencing, congestion management and terrain avoidance for a UAS Traffic Management (UTM) system that could develop airspace integration requirements for enabling safe, efficient low-altitude operations.</p>

Table 2.1 – Scope of the Goal 1

Benchmarks

The main issue of air transport capacity (section 2.1) concerns runway (2.1.1) and airways terminal capacity (2.1.2), as well as en route capacity (2.5).

The expected demand of 25 Million of flights will challenge three main elements in the transport system: a) the capacity of the runway system, b) the capacity of the TMA (Terminal Manoeuvring), c) the en route capacity. The accommodation of such a growth in flights will be determined by the most restrictive of these 3 capacity limits.

The European air traffic network contains some 170,000 links between airports. Over a network of more than 2100 airports, 528 airports accounted for just 25% of airports, but 98% of the departures; and just 25 out of Europe's 2100 airports generate 44% of all flights. For all airports in Europe, the Figure 2.1 shows the number of departures by rank of airport (inset). The figure also zooms in on the largest airports (main part) to illustrate that 44% of all departures come from the 25 largest airports in Europe, two-thirds of departures from the top 75 and 90% of all traffic comes from the largest 250 airports. There is a geographical concentration of airports in the region London-Amsterdam-Munich-Milan. This creates dense air traffic, with large numbers of climbing and descending aircraft: a significant challenge for Terminal Area and en route capacity.

Figure 2.1 – 90% of departures come from the largest 250 airports.

Source: Euro control Trends in Air Traffic Volume 3. A place to stand: Airports in the European network.

The Table 2.2 shows the average number of daily IFR movements at the main European airports. As can be observed, the number of average daily IFR departures at the biggest airport in Europe (Schiphol) is of 1470 operations per day.

ICAO CODE	AIRPORT	COUNTRY	AVERAGE DAILY MOVEMENTS 2016
EDDF	FRANKFURT MAIN	GERMANY	1.319,90
EDDM	MUENCHEN 2	GERMANY	1.122,00
EGKK	LONDON/GATWICK	UNITED KINGDOM	812,1
EGLL	LONDON/HEATHROW	UNITED KINGDOM	1.314,10
EHAM	SCHIPHOL AMSTERDAM	NETHERLANDS	1.420,90
LEBL	BARCELONA	SPAIN	910,9
LEMD	MADRID BARAJAS	SPAIN	1.069,30
LFPG	PARIS CH DE GAULLE	FRANCE	1.341,50
LIRF	ROME FIUMICINO	ITALY	835,8
LTBA	ISTANBUL-ATATURK	TURKEY	1.244,20

Table 2.2 – Average number of daily IFR movements at the main European airports.

Source: Eurocontrol Statistics and forecasts (STATFOR). <http://www.eurocontrol.int/statfor>.

Airport operations depend upon a number of factors as well as on interactions between them which all affect runway capacity to some degree. In addition to physical constraints, such as airport layout, there are “strategic” factors such as airport scheduling and “tactical” factors which include, inter alia, the sequencing of aircraft and the sustainability of throughput during specific weather conditions. The runway throughput is directly related to the time needed to accommodate each flight safely. The separation requirements in segregated mode depend on the most constraining of any one of the three parameters: (1) wake vortex separation, (2) radar separation, or (3) runway occupancy time. From the **technological and operational perspectives of the runway operation**, the challenge to achieve a maximum throughput is to optimize final approach spacing in line with wake vortex, prevailing atmospheric conditions and radar separation requirements so that the spacing is close to minimum runway occupancy time. The maximization of runway capacity would be achieved by “dynamic separation” and state of the art in wake vortex, radar separation and runway occupancy time technology and procedures.

Once the maximum runway throughput has been achieved, the only way to increase capacity at congested airports will be airport expansion through additional new runways and infrastructures. This affects basically to the **social/human dimension** of the target as the growth of airports is severely constrained by social restrictions. Besides the plans for airport expansions, by 2030 no fewer than 19 European airports will be operating at full capacity eight hours a day, every day of the year. This will mean 50 % of all flights affected by delays; a system more vulnerable to disruption due to airport congestion and less able to recover from crisis situations; and delays that will persist in the system for longer and will propagate more rapidly and widely.

Exhausted the potential growth of the biggest airports demand will need to be necessarily absorbed by closest airports, which refers to **the network dimension of air the transport**. The cities closest to Europe’s busiest airports have between 4 and 46 airfields within 100 Km from the city centre, for 8 of the 10 cities close to Europe’s biggest airports, a single airport handles 80% or more of all the departures within 100km.

A more conservative upper target for runway system, TMA and en route capacity can be derived from the “Challenge of growth” study. As part of this study, the first EUROCONTROL forecast of IFR flight movements in Europe up to 2050 [1] focuses on understanding the factors that will form the future air traffic and the challenges that lie ahead. It uses four scenarios to explore European air traffic in 2050: A – Global Growth; C – Regulated Growth; C’: Happy Localism; and D – Fragmenting World. The scenarios produce different levels and flows of traffic and follow different paths of growth. The most ‘visionary’ scenario, Scenario A (Global Growth), is characterised by strong economic growth in an increasingly globalised World, with technology used successfully to mitigate the effects of sustainability challenges, such as the environment or resource availability. It reflects the highest growth with 26.1 million IFR movements forecast in Europe for 2050 – 2.7 times more than in 2012, although there will be significant unaccommodated demand (36% by 2050). This prognosis considers a region-wide trend for growth of airport capacity with incremental improvements in capacity at an annual rate of 0.8% per annum from 2035 capacities, across the network. The traffic growth will be faster in the early years, stronger in Eastern Europe and for arrivals/departures to/from outside Europe than for intra-European flights. When the capacity limits are reached, congestion at airports will increase quite rapidly which will lead to extra pressure on the network, and more delays. Even with airport capacity restrictions, airports will grow. In 2035, there will be 20 airports handling more than 150,000 departures a year in the most-likely scenario; a level of traffic currently achieved at 8 airports only. Some faster-growing airports in Southern and Eastern Europe will join the top 25 within the 20-

year horizon (though the list depends on the scenario). Therefore, it is expected, unless breakthrough take place, that airport capacity will severely limit the traffic growth; and it will be necessary for policy makers and business planners to decide if, and how, to invest in order to reduce unaccommodated demand.

The terminal area airspace (TMA) is the managed airspace environment created to assist in achieving safety and efficiency where a number of larger, more complex airports and smaller, local airports operate in close proximity. It is characterised by high numbers of aircraft conducting climbing and descending manoeuvres in a relatively small volume of airspace. Operations within TMA airspace are dynamic and heavily influenced by demand, regularly resulting in the need to delay aircraft in established vertical holding stacks and causing other delays in the air and on the ground. Biggest TMAs in Europe are today complex and saturated scenarios where the traffic of the busiest airports in Europe is integrated with the traffic of other airports in their neighbourhood. Example of high-density TMA in Europe are Paris, London and, Frankfurt.

The Paris TMA includes two major airports, i.e. Paris Charles De Gaulle or Roissy (LFPG) and Paris Orly (LFPO), some secondary airports, e.g. Le Bourget (LFPB), Pontoise (LFPT), Beauvais (LFOB) and many other general aviation aerodromes like Toussus-Le-Noble (LFPN) and Lognes (LFPL). Within the TMA, major and segregated arrival and departure flows converge and leave from the two main Paris airports, i.e. Paris CDG and Paris Orly. The two airports are close to each other (slightly less than 20 NM). Further, the vicinity of Le Bourget induces additional traffic complexity within Paris CDG approach. Considering the average daily movements at both airports (roughly 1300 at LFPG and 650 at LFPO) this TMA has to attend more than 2000 movement daily on average. The London TMA includes two major airports, i.e. Heathrow (EGLL) with 1300 movements per day and Gatwick (EGKK) with 800 movements per day, which are close to each other (slightly more than 20 NM). There are also some secondary airports (i.e. Stansted with 245 movements per day, Luton with 180 movements per day, London City), which are in expansion as low-cost airlines operate from these secondary airports. In all the TMA has to manage more than 2500 movement per day.

Regarding the airspace capacity, the highest concentration of en route traffic takes places In Europe in the "core area" comprising of the Benelux States, Northeast France, Germany, and Switzerland is the densest and most complex airspace. At this zone the density of fights is higher than 5 aircraft per hour and square kilometre.

The Table 2.3 summarises the average number of daily movements in the European Airspace, and the daily movements in the big block of Airspace. It can be observed how the core or central area of Europe (FABEC) has to accommodate almost 3/5 of the European daily traffic.

FAB (based on FIR)	Average daily Movements 2015	Average daily Movements 2016
SES Area (RP2)	25.321	25.972
Baltic FAB	2.164	2.300
BLUE MED FAB	6.375	6.479
DANUBE FAB	2.453	2.472
DK-SE FAB	2.770	2.828
FAB CE (SES RP2)	5.467	5.614

FABEC	15.525	15.977
NEFAB	2.776	2.742
SW FAB	4.881	5.272
UK-Ireland FAB	6.453	6.790

Table 2.3 – Average daily movements in the En route European Airspace
 Source: Eurocontrol ANS performance monitoring (RP2, 2016)
http://www.eurocontrol.int/prudata/dashboard/rp2_2016.html

The Figure 2.2 shows the average daily IFR flights in the top 20 European en route area control centres (2015) where the busiest centres move around 5000 movements per day.

Figure 2.2 – Average daily IFR flights in the top 20 en route area control centres (2015).
 Source: 2015 Comparison of Air Traffic Management-Related 2015 Operational Performance: U.S./Europe.
 FAA, EU, Eurocontrol.

The achievements of the benchmark for the TMA and En route movement will highly rely on the technological and operational performance of the future Air Traffic Management Systems and its social and human dimensions as discussed in section 2.5

Providing that current IFR traffic in Europe is around 10 Million IFR flights per year, an increase by a factor of 2,5 is expected by 2050. Considering a homogeneous not restricted traffic grow, high density airports, surrounded TMAs and congested en route control centres will have to accommodate figures of **about 3500 (1400*2,5), 7500 (2500*3) and 12500 (5000*2,) daily movements respectively.**

Benchmarks to be achieved in en route and terminal area will require technological, operational and also social/human improvements currently under design for the future ATM system. Key to the Future ATM concept is the business trajectory principle in which the users of the airspace and controllers define together, through a collaborative process, the optimal flight path. Taking full advantage of both existing and newly developed technologies — such as Galileo — Future ATM target concept relies on a number of new key features at 3 different dimensions:

Technological and operational dimension:

- Trajectory management, reducing the constraints of airspace organization to a minimum;
- New aircraft separation modes, allowing increased safety, capacity and efficiency;
- System-wide information management, securely connecting all the ATM stakeholders which will share the same data;

Social/human dimension:

- Humans as the central decision-makers: controllers and pilots will be assisted by new automated functions to ease their workload and handle complex decision-making processes.

Network operation dimension:

- The network operation plan, a dynamic rolling plan for continuous operations that ensures a common view of the network situation;
- Full integration of airport operations as part of ATM and the planning process;

Figure 2.3 illustrates the benchmarks discussed for goal 1.

Figure 2.3 – Technological, operational and societal/human dimension of goal 1 Benchmarks

Reference State in 2010

As stated in previous sections, Goal 1 of 25 million flight by 2050 needs to be accommodated by each of the Air Transport systems components: Airport runway system, Terminal Management Area

airspace and en route Airspace. This section states the capacity limit of each of the previous components as in 2010.

Airport runway system

As already explained the runway throughput and the number of runways becomes the principal limitation of capacity at an airport. Here after some data are provided to characterize these elements in 2010. The Table 2.4 provides high-level indicators for the main 34 airports in the Europe, including average number of runways and the number of movements, as well as average daily IFR departures in order to provide an order of magnitude of the operations of the airports.

Main 34 airports in 2010	Europe	
	2010	Vs. 2008
<i>Average number of annual movements per airport (*000)</i>	237	-9%
<i>Average number of annual passengers per airport (million)</i>	24	-3%
<i>Passengers per movement</i>	102	+6%
<i>Average number of runways per airport</i>	2.5	0%
<i>Annual movements per runway (*000)</i>	95	-9%
<i>Annual passengers per runway (million)</i>	9.7	-3%

Table 2.4 – Key data for 34 biggest European airports.

Source: 2010 Comparison of ATM-related performance: U.S. – Europe

In Europe, traffic at major airports is usually controlled (in terms of volume and concentration) in the strategic phase through the airport capacity declaration process, and the subsequent allocation of airport slots to aircraft operator's months before the actual day of operation. This is the case for 30 of the 34 airports analysed in this report which are fully coordinated (IATA Level 3).

En route Airspace

In Europe, there were, in 2010, 38 en route service providers of various geographical areas each operating their own system. This makes it more difficult to implement arrival management across national boundaries (e.g. sequencing traffic into major airports of other States) and may affect the level of coordination in ATFM and ATC capacity. Ground ATFM delays principally originate from en route capacity shortfalls in Europe, which is not the case in the US.

The next Figure 2.4 shows the traffic complexity score in 2010. At European level, the aggregate complexity score is relatively stable. In 2010, it is close to 6 minutes of interactions per flight hour. At local level, the aggregate complexity scores differ quite significantly. ¹

Figure 2.4 – Traffic complexity score in 2010.

Source: Performance review report 2010 Eurocontrol.

The next Figure 2.5 presents the more congested ACC in Europe in 2010.

¹ The complexity indicator is a composite measure calculated for the entire year which combines adjusted density (concentration of traffic in space and time) and structural complexity (structure of traffic flows¹⁰). A complexity score of 10 means that for each flight hour within the respective airspace, there were on average 10 minutes of potential interactions with other aircraft.

Figure 2.5 – Most congested ACC in Europe in 2010.
Source: Performance review report 2010 Eurocontrol

Progress up to now

Airport Runway System

The Figure 2.6 provides high-level indicators for the main 34 airports in the Europe, including average number of runways and the number of movements, as well as average daily IFR departures in order to provide an order of magnitude of the operations of the airports.

Main 34 airports	Europe	
	2015	vs. 2013
Avg. number of annual IFR movements per airport ('000)	236	3.6%
Avg. number of annual passengers per airport (million)	28.0	10.1%
Passengers per IFR movement	118	6.3%
Average number of active runways per airport	2.0	-1.5%
Annual IFR movements per runway ('000)	120	5.2%
Annual passengers per runway (million)	14.2	11.8%

Figure 2.6 – Key data for 34 biggest European airports.
Source: Comparison of ATM-related performance: U.S. – Europe, 2016

In Europe, the declared airport capacity is a limit typically set as early as six months before the day of operations through a coordination process involving the airport managing body, the airlines, and local ATC. The peak arrival throughput is an approximation of the operational airport capacity in ideal conditions. It is the 95th percentile of the number of aircraft in the “rolling” hours sorted from the least busy to the busiest hour. The indicator has, however, limitations when the peak throughput is lower than the peak declared capacity, in which case it is necessary to determine whether a variation in peak arrival throughput is driven by a change in demand or by a change in operational airport capacity.

The Figure 2.7 provides a comparison of the actual airport throughput vs declared capacity for the biggest airports in Europe in 2015. Although they are developed and used for different purposes, the values may provide some insights into the role of capacity on operational performance.

Figure 2.7 – Actual airport throughput vs declared capacity 2015.

Source: 2015 Comparison of ATM-related performance: U.S. – Europe, 2010

In 2015, the main 34 European airports spend on average 77.8% of the time in VMC, 14.2% in marginal, and 8% in instrument. At system level, weather conditions in Europe improved in 2015 compared to 2013 with a -2.0% reduction in IMC and a -1.8% reduction in marginal conditions. At the airport level, the share of time spent in VMC, MMC, and IMC vary based on differing susceptibility to weather events which is largely based on geographic location (Figures 2.8-2.9). The European airports located in the subtropical Mediterranean region including Nice (NCE), Palma (PMI), Madrid (MAD), Rome (FCO), Athens (ATH), and Barcelona (BCN) are the airports with the highest percentage of the VMC.

Figure 2.8. Weather conditions at the main 34 airports (2015)

Source: 2015 Comparison of ATM-related performance: U.S. – Europe)

Figure 2.9. Percent change in time during IMC at the main 34 airports
 Source: 2015 Comparison of ATM-related performance: U.S. – Europe, 2010

The following Table 2.5 presents an estimate of the “improvement pool” actionable by ATM comparing 2010 and 2015. The improvement over the past five years was mainly driven by a reduction of en route ATFM delay at the departure gates and improvements in the level of horizontal flight efficiency.

Estimated benefit pool actionable by ATM for a typical flight (flights to or from the main 34 airports)		Estimated average additional time (min.)						Fuel burn engines	Estimated excess fuel burn (kg) ⁴⁷			
		EUR			US				EUR		US	
		2010	2015		2010	2015		2010	2015	2010	2015	
Holding at gate per departure (only delays >15min. included)	En-route-related (% of flights)	1.9 (5.7%)	0.6 (2.0%)	↓	0.2 (0.7%)	0.3 (0.8%)	→	OFF	≈0	≈0	≈0	≈0
	airport-related (% of flights)	1.1 (3.1%)	0.7 (2.3%)	↓	1.3 (2.5%)	1.3 (2.5%)	→	OFF	≈0	≈0	≈0	≈0
Taxi-out phase (min. per departure)		4.7	4.0	↓	5.8	5.6	↓	ON	70	60	87	84
Horizontal en-route flight efficiency		2.0 ⁴⁸	1.8	↓	1.8	1.8	→	ON	94	84	82	82
Terminal areas (min. per arrival)		2.8	2.8	→	2.5	2.5	→	ON	116	117	101	101
Total estimated benefit pool		12.5	10.0	↓	11.6	11.4	↓		279	260	270	267

Table 2.5 - Summary Estimated benefit pool actionable by ATM
 Source: 2015 Comparison of ATM-related performance: U.S. – Europe, 2010

Predictions up-to-2025 and evolutionary progress up to 2050

During the past years, it has been identified a growing gap between capacity and demand at a number of busy EU hubs. Congestion at these airports will remain a concern. Traffic will continue to grow in the future, as it has done over the past 50 years despite periods of economic downturn and other disruptions. Although air traffic in Europe will grow more slowly than in emerging economies, it will nevertheless nearly double by 2030 and more than double in 2050.

However, Europe will not be in position to meet a large part of this demand due to a shortage of airport capacity. A percentage of this demand will not be accommodated because of capacity shortfalls. In concrete terms, by 2030 no fewer than 19 European airports will be operating at full capacity eight hours a day, every day of the year. This will have a major impact on the entire aviation network since by 2030 congestion at these airports will mean 50% of all flights affected by delays upon departure or arrival, or both.

In the following sections, there are proposed projects and measures that could improve air traffic capacity:

1. Eurocontrol measures to mitigate the capacity challenges
2. The SESAR project PJ02 (EARTH): Increased Runway and Airport Throughput
3. The Airport CDM concept

Although this goal focuses on increasing air traffic capacity, it is much related to the second goal: ground infrastructure and multimodal transport. Therefore, some of the measures that will be mentioned in this goal could be also applied for the second goal.

Eurocontrol measures to mitigate the capacity challenges

During past years, there has been a stable growth trend in air traffic movements. At a time horizon of 2050, the flight demand in Europe is predicted to be 25 million movements per year according to the ACARE goal, which is 2.5 times more than in 2010 with 10 million flights. This scenario is very similar to the scenario A (Global Growth) of Eurocontrol, which is characterised by strong economic growth in an increasingly globalised World, with 26.1 million IFR movements forecast in Europe for 2050, 2.7 times more than in 2012. However, it is expected that there will be significant unaccommodated demand (36% by 2050).

Eurocontrol contemplates four scenarios (Figure 2.10), each one with the following features:

Figure 2.10 – Four Air Traffic Scenarios of Eurocontrol

The IFR movements expected for each Eurocontrol scenario can be seen in the next Figure 2.11:

Figure 2.11- IFR movements forecast for 2050 (Source: Task 7: European Air Traffic in 2050, Eurocontrol)

The 25 million flights movements expected for 2050 will result in a great traffic growth in Europe. In view of the potential demand growth, it is expected that the 36% of flight demand will not be accommodated at European airports.

In addition, it is estimated that by 2035, more than 20 airports will be operating at 80% or more of capacity on a daily basis, resulting in delays of up to 5-6 minutes. On the other hand, the mismatch between capacity and demand will not be the same across Europe. There will be regions where the shortfall is likely to be bigger: Turkey will be the most penalised facing almost 30% excess of demand for arrivals and departures at their airports in the most likely scenario C by 2035. Other States located mostly in Eastern Europe, like Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania will have around 17%-22% (each) excess of demand not accommodated by 2035 in the scenario C (Figure 2.12). In terms of flights, rather than percentages, it is Turkey and the UK that will be most affected.

Figure 2.12 - Unaccommodated demand by local airports
Source: Challenges of Growth 2013 Summary Report, Eurocontrol

Therefore, due to the necessity of airport capacity in order to accommodate the future demand, Eurocontrol proposes a number of measures to mitigate the capacity challenges to reduce the levels of unaccommodated demand and increase capacity at airports:

➤ Alternative airports:

Shifting to alternative airports is considered as a real option for some airline and airport operators provided that potential issues of environmental acceptance and terminal airspace congestion can both be overcome. The measure is efficient in that it would reduce unaccommodated demand by around 30%, provided passengers and carriers are willing to relocate to such airports, which in turn is linked to the quality of the ground transportation links. This mitigation measure is also much related with the goal 2, since it will be necessary an efficient mobility between airports.

➤ SESAR improvements

The SESAR programme to increase system capacity by developing and implementing new technologies, approaches, and procedures is perceived as the strongest enabler for sustaining future long-term demand. SESAR plus investments to bring airports to the performance level of the best-in-class has the potential to increase airport capacity by a significant margin, reducing unaccommodated demand by 40%.

➤ Schedule smoothing

This approach involves moving unaccommodated flights to times of the day when more airport capacity is available. However, Schedule smoothing is not considered as an answer to the airport capacity challenge, mainly because there is often little scope for moving flights to a nearby period and because it might not be the first choice of the passenger. As a result, this measure would reduce unaccommodated demand only by around 5%.

The next Figure 2.13 provides a one-day average level of congestion for a 24-hour time period.

Figure 2.13 - One day average level of congestion

Source: The Effect of Air Traffic Network Congestion in 2035, Eurocontrol

➤ High-Speed train investment

This mitigation measure considers the impact of shifting flights to high speed train (HST). Shifting short-haul flights to high speed train is of limited benefit since there are only a small number of routes where the high-speed train could theoretically replace air services (Figure 2.14). As a result, this measure would reduce unaccommodated demand only by around 5%.

Figure 2.14 - High-Speed rail network
Source: Challenges of growth 2008, Eurocontrol

➤ Shifting to Larger Aircraft

Shifting to larger aircraft can be a real option to accommodate more demand in the presence of a limitation on the allowable daily frequency between congested airports. In case of a frequency limitation of 15 daily flights in congested airports, the method has the potential to reduce the impact of the cap by more than a third.

Some previous measures, such as alternative airports or high-speed trains, would allow not only to increase capacity, but also to improve mobility between airports, which is the objective of the goal 2.

The following Figure 2.15 summarises the demand percentage that would be accommodated for each of the measures described above.

Figure 2.15 - Mitigation Summary

Source: Task 5: Mitigation of the Challenges, Eurocontrol

As it can be seen, alternative airports and SESAR improvements appear to be the most effective measures of reducing future unaccommodated demand. SESAR improvements and investment at airports has the potential to increase airport capacity by a significant margin, thus reducing unaccommodated demand by up to 40%. However, these capacity gains require investment which is not yet reflected in airports' plans. Shifting to alternative airports reduces unaccommodated demand by 25%-40%. However, there will be environmental costs if additional ground transport is needed to reach more remote airports.

Schedule smoothing, Investment in High-Speed Train and larger aircraft are initiatives less efficient for reducing unaccommodated demand. High-Speed Train investments is a limited benefit, taking into account that building HST lines require a great cost and the demand accommodated is small. Schedule smoothing is also a limited benefit for accommodating more demand, because there is often little scope for moving flights to a nearby period. Finally, using larger aircraft to accommodate demand at congested airports is also inefficient.

Taking into account the estimation (Figure 2.16 a) made of the unaccommodated demand for the 2030, the estimation (Figure 2.16 b) for 2050 is the following one:

Figure 2.16 a – Unaccommodated demand 2030

Figure 2.16 b - Unaccommodated demand 2050

In the previous images, it can be seen the demand percentage that will be absorbed by the deferent mitigation measures proposed by Eurocontrol. It is important to highlight that, despite these mitigation measures; a demand percentage will not be accommodated.

Increased Runway and Airport Throughput - SESAR project PJ02 (EARTH)

One of the main elements that limit airport capacity is the maximum runway throughput, that is to say, the number of aircraft movements that can be safely operated. Due to the traffic growth expected in the future, there are several projects whose objective is to increase runway capacity to

accommodate the foreseen growth in the number of aircraft movements. One of these projects is the SESAR project PJ02 (EARTH): increased runway and airport throughput.

This project focuses on developing, validating and delivering separation and procedures to improve runway and airport throughput considering wake vortex, weather, the environment and noise while taking account of different levels of traffic demand, future aircraft capabilities and airport configurations.

This project contemplates several measures which can be applied to increase runway capacity:

- Reducing runway occupancy time;
- Time-based separation;
- Re-categorization of wake turbulence categories.

➤ Reducing runway occupancy time

A key indicator for runway capacity is Runway Occupancy Time (ROT).

During the arrival of an aircraft, ROT is defined as the time interval between the aircraft crossing the threshold of the runway and the tail of the aircraft leaving the runway. Runway capacity is often limited by ROT because only one aircraft can use the runway at any given time. The leading aircraft must first vacate the runway before the trailing aircraft is allowed to cross the threshold.

ROT can be reduced through the use of high-speed exits. These exits are not perpendicular to the runway, but instead use a smaller angle allowing aircraft to vacate sooner and at higher speeds, reducing ROT.

In addition, The SESAR project will investigate the use of satellite navigation and augmentation capabilities, such as GBAS and satellite-based augmentation systems (SBAS), to enhance landing performance and to facilitate advanced arrival procedures (e.g. curved approaches, glide slope increase, displaced runway threshold). By doing so, noise is reduced while runway occupancy time (ROT) is optimised. The aim is to also reduce the need for separation for wake vortex avoidance.

➤ Time-based separation

When there are strong headwinds, aircraft ground speed is reduced on final approach. This results in a reduced landing rate, causing delays and even flight cancellations (Figure 2.17).

Figure 2.17 - Comparison of observed runway arrival throughput in low headwind and in strong headwind
Source: time-based separation factsheet, Eurocontrol

The concept of time spacing is based on the performance of an aircraft in strong headwind conditions, where wake vortex is quickly dispersed, permitting then to reduce the distance between aircraft, while maintaining safety levels. Consequently, airports can operate with the same landing and capacity rates as in light wind conditions.

TBS aims at reducing the gap in landing rates in light and strong headwind conditions. It will help maintain airport capacity at the same level in all wind conditions.

TBS brings numerous benefits for airports, airlines and passengers, including:

- Increase of resilience of runway throughput and efficiency, due to space reduction between aircraft in strong headwind conditions while maintaining the same safety levels;
- a reduction in delays, cancellations and consequent operating costs
- shorter overall flight times
- advanced information for controllers, as TBS needs wind profile measurement in the final approach area and this information can be used by the controllers

➤ Re-categorization of wake turbulence categories:

Runway capacity and efficiency use is often directly linked with the minimum separation between aircraft. These minima are constrained by ATS surveillance capabilities and wake turbulence.

During recent years, knowledge about wake vortex behaviour in the operational environment has increased thanks to recorded data and improved understanding of physical processes. It is mainly for this reason that it was possible to revise wake turbulence categorisation and corresponding separation minima to enable optimisation of airport capacity and efficiency whilst maintaining acceptable levels of safety. A safe separation minimum implies to consider wake vortex generated by an aircraft but also the wake encounter impact and resistance of the following aircraft on departure or final approach. Existing ICAO wake vortex separation rules (Table 2.6) were implemented over 40 years ago and they have become outdated. These separations are based on certificated Maximum Take-off Mass (MTOM)

and it includes three categories (HEAVY, MEDIUM or LIGHT) allocating all aircraft into one of them. Because the separations are defined based on the worst case in each category, this leads to over separation in many instances.

Leader / Follower	A380-800	HEAVY	MEDIUM	LIGHT
A380-800		6 NM	7 NM	8 NM
HEAVY MTOM \geq 136 tons		4 NM	5 NM	6 NM
MEDIUM 7 tons \leq MTOM < 136 tons				5 NM
LIGHT MTOM < 7 tons				

Table 2.6 - ICAO wake turbulence categories and separation minima

Source: European Wake Turbulence Categorisation and Separation Minima on Approach and Departure, Eurocontrol

This means that each category may cover a wide range of different sized aircraft that leads to over-conservative separations in many cases, and so a loss of runway throughput.

As a result, EUROCONTROL has developed a re-categorisation of ICAO wake turbulence scheme and associated longitudinal separation minima on approach and departure, called "RECAT-EU", to the benefits of Airports and ATM Network Performance enhancement.

European Wake Vortex Re-categorisation (RECAT-EU) is (Figure 2.18) a new, much more precise categorisation of aircraft than the traditional ICAO one. It aims at safely increasing airport capacity by redefining wake turbulence categories and their associated separation minima. It divides the current Heavy and Medium categories into two sub-categories and creates a new Super Heavy one for the Airbus A380.

Figure 2.18 - RECAT-EU categories

Source: <http://www.eurocontrol.int/articles/recat-eu>

The separations minima applicable between the RECAT-EU wake turbulence categories are provided in the following Table 2.7:

RECAT-EU scheme		"SUPER HEAVY"	"UPPER HEAVY"	"LOWER HEAVY"	"UPPER MEDIUM"	"LOWER MEDIUM"	"LIGHT"
Leader / Follower		"A"	"B"	"C"	"D"	"E"	"F"
"SUPER HEAVY"	"A"	3 NM	4 NM	5 NM	5 NM	6 NM	8 NM
"UPPER HEAVY"	"B"		3 NM	4 NM	4 NM	5 NM	7 NM
"LOWER HEAVY"	"C"		(*)	3 NM	3 NM	4 NM	6 NM
"UPPER MEDIUM"	"D"						5 NM
"LOWER MEDIUM"	"E"						4 NM
"LIGHT"	"F"						3 NM

Table 2.7 - RECAT-EU WT distance-based separation minima on approach and departure
 Source: European Wake Turbulence Categorisation and Separation Minima on Approach and Departure, Eurocontrol

Thanks to this new categorisation, it is expected several benefits:

- The runway throughput benefits can reach 5% or more during peak periods depending on individual airport traffic mix
- For an equivalent throughput, RECAT-EU also allows a reduction of the overall flight time for an arrival or departure sequence of traffic, and this is beneficial to the whole traffic sequence.
- RECAT-EU will also enable more rapid recovery from adverse conditions, helping to reduce the overall delay and will also enable improvements in ATFM slot compliance through the flexibility afforded by reduced departure separations.

➤ Projection

The SESAR project is found in the first levels of development, since it is a new project that started in 2016. It is expected that this project finishes in 2019. However, this estimation is too positive because the project is in the concept phase (**TRL3**), so it is possible that it will be fully implemented by 2025.

Airport CDM Concept

An airport is a complex system that involves many stakeholders and processes. Stakeholders actively and passively participate in this system and are affected by the outcome of these processes.

However, due to this complex system, airport stakeholders often operate independent systems in isolation, focusing on their own outcomes and without a shared situational awareness across the wider airport community. This limited perspective on the operation, as a whole, can result in widespread inefficiencies. The main factors that result in a decrease of the operational efficiency at airports are the following ones (Figure 2.19):

Figure 2.19 – Factors Affecting Airport Efficiency

Lack of Common Vocabulary and Definitions: Groups with limited interaction often develop their own semantic references; this includes airport stakeholders as they may use different terminologies to cover the same reality. This lack of common definition and understanding of terms and processes across the stakeholder community can exacerbate misunderstanding and contribute to the lack of common situational awareness.

Lack of Information Exchange and Communication: Another major factor that causes inefficiencies and misunderstanding among stakeholders is a lack of clear and concise communication and information exchange processes. There are many instances where departments and organisations work independently of each other and do not share information, data and concerns, which leads to decisions and actions being reactive rather than proactive and are based on incomplete or faulty information.

Disconnected Strategies and Working in Isolation: In an effort to improve their own performance, stakeholders may work independently to deliver increased efficiencies in their area without realising the impact on other stakeholders and thus, the overall operation, including their own. These disconnected or fragmented procedures, strategies, and systems often lead to decreased efficiency and performance across the entire operation.

Due to all these factors that contribute to an operational inefficiency at airports, the CDM concept arise.

The principle of CDM is to put in place agreed cross-collaborative processes including communication protocols, training, procedures, tools, regular meetings and information sharing, which moves ATM operations from stovepipe decision-making into a collaborative management process that improves overall system performance and benefits the individual stakeholders.

Airport-CDM is a process that applies to all airports irrespective of size that supports landside, airside, and en route air traffic flow management (ATFM) operations, while enhancing forward planning and tactical decision-making. By implementing the concept of Airport CDM it could be improved the problem of congested airports.

Transparency and sharing information are fundamental principles of A-CDM. As soon as the decision is made to implement A-CDM, agreed principles, processes, and data quality standards for a multi-directional information exchange should be agreed. On the one hand, transparency allows stakeholders to make decisions based on a common situational awareness and take collaborative action that would be beyond the ability of any one stakeholder with incomplete and fragmented information. On the other hand, sharing timely and accurate information that can improve the safety and efficiency of the aircraft flight between the concerned stakeholders would allow making appropriate decisions.

➤ Airport CDM Collaboration Levels

Implementation of the Airport CDM concept involves various levels of collaboration and sharing information (Figure 2.20):

Figure 2.20 – Implementation of Airports CDM

Level 1: Define a common understanding and data sharing. Agree on flight-related information elements (for example, scheduled and actual times) that will be shared and how that information will be distributed among the stakeholders.

Level 2: Share advanced information. Weather forecasts, anticipated reduction in capacity (for example, construction on runway), surveillance data, traffic load forecast, and resource allocations create a higher degree of situational awareness.

Level 3: Share operational decisions. The stakeholders agree to share their respective decisions or intended actions. For example, an ANSP shares its decision to increase the runway arrival capacity so that the other stakeholders, such as the ground handlers, can expect an increase in gate demand and allocate resources accordingly.

Level 4: Share analysis. Based on the analysis and respective decisions, the stakeholders agree to collaborative cross-organisational decisions. For example, the airport may adapt gate availability to meet the expected arrival demand by pushing departing aircraft into remote parking locations. This requires collaborative decision-making by the ANSP, the airlines and the ground-handling agents.

Level 5: Connect to the other elements of CDM. A-CDM can assist in optimising en route traffic flow management by sharing accurate departure take-off times. This information allows better prediction of en route demand versus available capacity and facilitates improved dynamic airspace and resource planning. By sharing information about passengers (such as check-in and security), baggage and crew, it also increases the efficiency and predictability of the landside turnaround process, which improves the overall system performance.

Benefits

A-CDM would help each stakeholder to reach, as often as possible, the maximum capacity under given conditions. The process of collaboration, communication, and coordination, along with common data and a robust shared decision-making process, would help to maximise capacity, identify weaknesses, focus on operationally essential matters, and to allocate resources appropriately while minimising negative impact on each partner. Sharing information allows all stakeholders to appropriately plan and to minimise the disruptive effects of irregular operations or unusual situations, not only on their organisations, but also on all airport partners by agreeing a joint solution and defining an agreed recovery process that helps bring stability to the operation.

In addition, through its capacity optimisation, A-CDM would help in solving issues by bringing more predictability and efficiency.

It is important to highlight that the A-CDM concept could be useful not only for improving airport capacity (which is the purpose of the goal 1), but also for enhancing the airports mobility which is the aim of the goal 2. Therefore, this concept could be applied for both goals.

➤ Airport CDM implementation

The first airport to be considered fully Airport CDM was the Munich airport at 2007. Since then, A-CDM is fully implemented in several airports across Europe nowadays, which can be seen in the next figure 2.21:

Figure 2.21 – European Airports that have implemented CDM

Therefore, the A-CDM concept have been already developed, that is to say, the Technology Readiness Level correspond to number 9. The next step is to evaluate the expansion level of the A-CDM concept to all European airports (Figure 2.22):

Figure 2.22 – Increased adoption of a A-COM at European Airports

KEY TOPIC T2.2 – RELATION OF ATM WITH CAPACITY

Predictions up-to-2025

Since the beginning of the 21st century, European stakeholders have been addressing the issues related to the Single European Sky concept. The Single European Sky framework was set by EU Regulation No. 549/2004, in which it is stated that the objectives of the Single European Sky initiative are to enhance air traffic standards, to contribute to the sustainable development of the air transport system and to improve the overall performance of air traffic management (ATM) and air navigation services (ANS) for general air traffic in Europe, with a view to meeting the requirements of all airspace users.

One of the mechanisms by which these objectives were addressed by the Regulation was the creation of the so called “Performance Scheme”. The Regulation established that a Performance Scheme should be set up to improve the performance of air navigation services and network functions as much as the scheme aims to ensure that capacity is increased. As a result, flights will be significantly less delayed, saving unnecessary costs for airlines and passengers. In addition, the environmental impact of air traffic will be reduced due to more efficient and shorter flight paths. Air travellers should benefit from a punctual, greener and more cost-efficient mode of transport with a maintained or even enhanced level of safety. In this manner, the scheme should include Community-wide performance targets on the key performance areas of safety, environment, capacity and cost-efficiency. National plans ensuring consistency with this as established by this Regulation and Community-wide performance targets must be defined, and moreover periodic review, monitoring and benchmarking of air navigation services and network functions should be conducted to ensure that targets are met.

The first attempt to lay down the principles of the Performance Scheme was EU Regulation No. 691/2010. After that, EU Regulation No. 390/2013 has defined the current Performance Scheme, which lays down the necessary measure to improve the overall performance of air navigation services and network functions within the European area. As the preceding one, this Regulation defines four key performance areas (safety, environment, capacity and cost-efficiency), for each of which a set of key performance indicators (KPI) and performance indicators (PI) are defined (see Table 2.8). The performance of air navigation services should be assessed against binding targets for each of these key performance indicators.

The Regulation states that national supervisory agencies (NSA) shall be responsible for the drawing up of the performance plans, and also for the oversight and monitoring of performance. The Regulation also establishes reference periods (periods of validity and application of Union-wide performance targets and the performance plans): the first reference period, known as RP1, covered the calendar years 2012-2014, the current one, RP2, includes the calendar years 2015-2019 and RP3 will start in 2020 and subsequent periods will cover five calendar years. Key performance indicators must remain invariable during each reference period.

KEY PERFORMANCE AREA	ANS PERFORMANCE INDICATOR
Safety	Application of severity classification scheme (RAT methodology) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Separation minima infringements (SMI) • Runway incursions (RI) • ATM-Specific occurrences (ATM-S) Effectiveness of Safety Management (EoS)M) Presence of Just Culture (JC)
	Application of automated safety data recording Level of safety occurrence reporting Number of separation minima infringements, runway incursions and airspace infringements
Environment	Average horizontal en route flight efficiency of the actual trajectory Average horizontal en route flight efficiency of the last filed flight plan trajectory
	Effectiveness of booking procedures for FUA Rate of planning of Conditional Routes (CDR) Additional time in the taxi-out phase Effective use of CDR Additional time in terminal airspace
Capacity	En route ATFM delay per flight attributable to ANS Arrival ATFM delay
	Absence of ATFM slots Air traffic control pre-departure delay per outbound
Cost-efficiency	Determined Unit Cost (DUC) for en route air navigation services
	Determined Unit Cost (DUC) for terminal air navigation services

Table 2.8 - Key performance indicators (KPI, shaded in yellow) and performance indicators (PI) as established by EU Regulation No. 390/2013

The Commission has adopted Union-wide performance targets taking into account the relevant inputs from the Network Manager and the national supervisory authorities and after consultation with the stakeholders and other relevant organizations, such as EASA (see Table 2.9 for RP2 targets). The national supervisory authorities have to draw up performance plans at a functional block level that contain targets which are consistent with the Union-wide performance targets. As established in the Regulation, the national supervisory authorities and the Commission have to monitor the implementation of the performance plans, using the values reported on an annual basis. If, during the

reference period, targets are not met, the Member State will need to define and apply corrective measures and communicate them to the Commission. Transparency is a key element of the Performance Scheme whereby performance data is published and updated by the Performance Review Body (PRB) and is readily available to the general public. Member States are in charge of gathering the information from the providers and transmitting it to the PRB.

KEY PERFORMANCE AREA	ANS PERFORMANCE INDICATOR	RP2 TARGET (by the end of 2019)
Safety	Application of severity classification scheme (RAT methodology) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Separation minima infringements (SMI) • Runway incursions (RI) • ATM-Specific occurrences (ATM-S) 	80-100% report of ATM Ground RAT severity for RI and SMI classified as A (serious), B (major) or C (significant) 80-100% report of ATM Ground RAT severity for ATM-Specific occurrences with categories AA, A, B or C
	Effectiveness of Safety Management (EoSM)	Level D for management objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safety policy and objectives • Safety risk management • Safety assurance • Safety promotion Level C for management objectives Safety culture
Environment	Average horizontal en route flight efficiency of the actual trajectory	2.6%
	Average horizontal en route flight efficiency of the last filed flight plan trajectory	4.1%
Capacity	Average en route ATFM delay per flight	<0.5 minutes per flight
Cost-efficiency	Determined Unit Cost (DUC) for en route air navigation services	EUR ₂₀₀₉ 56,64 for 2015 EUR ₂₀₀₉ 54,95 for 2016 EUR ₂₀₀₉ 52,98 for 2017 EUR ₂₀₀₉ 51,00 for 2018 EUR ₂₀₀₉ 49,10 for 2019

Table 2.9. Union-wide targets for performance monitoring during reference period 2 (RP2)

If data from ANS performance monitoring [6] is collected and analysed, different outcomes can be stated. As example, en route ATFM delay across the years 2008-2017 is shown in the following Figure 2.23 (see next page):

Figure 2.23. En route ATFM delay (RP1-RP2) (min/flight)

As can be proved, en route ATFM delay (Figure 2.23) has changed along the past years. At the beginning of RP1, the average delay was lower than the target set for 2012 (0.63 vs 0.7) and, although the target has been even more restrictive every year, the average delay was also lower than the target in 2013 (0.54 vs 0.6). However, since 2014 until now, the average en route ATFM delay has been higher than the target set and, even worse, the average delay has continued increasing until set the maximum difference in the current year (1.07 vs 0.5). Therefore, as an increasing trend is underway, air traffic stakeholders must implement mitigating measures in order to chase the fulfilment of the targets for each reference period during the following years.

Consequently, if the measures taken are appropriate, parameters as average delays will be likely to decrease and other parameters as flight efficiency will be likely to increase.

These progresses that can be achieved in the following years will facilitate the fulfilment of the main purposes of Goal 1 and, if these progresses become true, it would be a good starting point in order to keep developing the systems, procedures and equipment related to air traffic operation.

Evolutionary progress up-to-2050

The RP2 targets stated above should be put into context. Whereas these targets could seem appropriate for the current status of air traffic industry, the growth of air traffic expected to become real in the next decades must be considered and hence new targets must be studied and proposed.

For example, according to 2012 data, there are 1.4 billion passengers a year in 440 airports which means that there are 26000 flights a day crossing the European sky. In other words, there are 10 million flights each year and it is expected that it will grow by up to 5% per year.

This growth can be seen in different forecasts which show that 16.9 million flights are expected to cross European skies in 20 years' time, thus in 2030 as many flights will cross Europe as there are inhabitants of Beijing. Additionally, Flightpath 2050 aims that air traffic management system is capable of handling at least 25 million flights a year, almost three times the current number of flights in Europe.

Related to that, the overall goal of the Performance Scheme (Figure 2.24) is the modernization of Europe's air traffic management (ATM) system which still operates with basic technologies from the 1950s. This modernization aims to overcome a fragmented patchwork of 27 national airspaces through the following keys:

- Tripling the airspace capacity;
- Improving safety tenfold;
- Reducing environmental impact by 10%;
- Reducing air traffic management costs by 50%.

Figure 2.24. Operational ANS Performance [7]

Besides, it is likely that demand exceeds capacity in the next decades. This difference between demand and capacity will probably lead to bottlenecks in runway configurations, terminals, passenger and baggage processes if we talk about airports, and in airspace if we talk about the systems and equipment implemented in aircraft and ATC centres (ACCs and TWRs). As example, a number of Member States' Plans risks being insufficient with regard to the capacity targets. These include France, Belgium, Netherlands, Germany, Luxembourg, Spain, Greece and Poland and hence these Member States should work with the Network Manager to reinforce their performance and try to reach the capacity targets.

Therefore, further efforts must be taken in order to make possible reaching the overall goal of the Performance Scheme, adapting periodically the requirements of each reference period to the developments carry out over the years regarding air traffic management (ATM) system.

Possible or predictable breakthroughs

The following breakthroughs could be expected:

- New developments regarding equipment, systems and procedures, including flexible use of airspace. Nowadays, for example, there are some flexible structures in airspace, among which is the conditional routes (CDR). These routes or sections of routes are not permanent, in such a way that they only can be used under specific conditions within periods previously set. The CDR are divided into three categories: CDR 1 which can be planned permanently in the flight plan (RPL and FPL); CDR 2 which only can be included in FPL according to the conditions published daily, the day before the flight; CDR 3 which cannot be planned in the flight plan, it only can be used under ATC clearance. The publication of the information about flexible structure availability is carried out

through two ways: Airspace Use Plan (AUP) which is published before 14:00 UTC of the day before the operation and its period of validity is 24 hours since 06:00 UTC of the following day; on the other hand, Conditional Route Availability Message (CRAM) is broadcasted to airlines, ARO offices, ACC/FMP, Airspace Management Cell (AMC) and CFMU at 15:00 UTC of the day before the operation and its period of validity is 24 hours since 06:00 UTC of the following day. In conclusion, availability of flexible structures is spread mainly one day before operation, so stakeholders should focus on trying that this information is available live, allowing a real flexible use of airspace during the flight operation.

- Additional runways construction and even new airports construction in order to accommodate the increasing demand.
- Developments concerning aircraft designs in order to reduce fuel consumption, wake turbulence and noise.
- Development of both aircraft and ground systems allowing lower separation minima.
- New research about innovative technologies.

Identification of Gaps

If the current figures for air traffic in Europe are studied, it can be stated that Goal 1 implies to almost triple the current number of flights. Nowadays there are 10 million flights each year and it is expected to grow by up to 5% per year. This growth will require a huge effort from the stakeholders since it will be a hard task to handle.

However, these tasks related to the improvement of ATM framework are not new in Europe as the European Union has set different goals along the years in order to allow the growth of air traffic. As example, the Commission stated in 2005 the political vision and high-level goals for the Single European Sky and its technological pillar for 2020 and beyond [1]:

- Enable a 3-fold increase in capacity which will also reduce delays, both on the ground and in the air.
- Improve the safety performance by a factor of 10.
- Enable a 10% reduction in the effects that flights have on the environment.
- Provide ATM services at a cost to the airspace users which is at least 50% less.

These vision and goals were analysed by reference to the 2020 demand and resulted into specific initial targets for that particular year, notwithstanding the subsequent evolutions necessary to meet the growing demand. These targets are gathered in the following figure 2.25.

KPA	Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Baseline		2020 Target	
		Year	Value	Absolute	Relative
Capacity	Annual IFR flights in Europe	2005	9.2 M	16 M	+ 73%
	Daily IFR flights in Europe	2005	29,000	50,000	+ 73%
	Best In Class (BIC) declared airport capacity in VMC (1 RWY), mov/hr	2008	50	60	+20%
	BIC declared airport capacity in VMC (2 parallel dependent RWYs), mov/hr	2008	90	90	+0%
	BIC declared airport capacity in VMC (2 parallel independent RWYs), mov/hr	2008	90	120	+25%
	BIC declared airport capacity in IMC (1 RWY), mov/hr	2008	25	48	+90%
	BIC declared airport capacity in IMC (2 parallel dependent RWYs), mov/hr	2008	45	72	+60%
	BIC declared airport capacity in IMC (2 parallel independent RWYs), mov/hr	2008	45	96	+110%
Cost Effectiveness	Total annual en-route and terminal ANS cost in Europe, €/flight	2004	800	400	-50%
Efficiency	Scheduled flights departing on time (as planned)			>98%	
	Avg delay of the remaining scheduled flights			<10 min	
	Flights with block-to-block time as planned			>95%	
	Avg. block-to-block time extension of the remaining flights			<10 min	
	Flights with fuel consumption as planned			>95%	
	Avg. additional fuel consumption of the remaining flights			<5%	
Flexibility	Accommodation of VFR-IFR change requests			>98%	
	Unscheduled flights departing on time (as requested)			>98%	
	Avg delay of the remaining unscheduled flights			<5 min	
	Scheduled flights with departure time as requested (after change request)			>98%	
	Avg delay of the remaining scheduled flights			<5 min	
Predictability	Coefficient of variation for actual block-to-block times: for repeatedly flown routes			<1.5%	
	Flights arriving on time (as planned)			>95%	
	Avg arrival delay of the remaining flights			<10 min	
	Total reactionary delay	2010			-50%
	Reactionary flight cancellation rate	2010			-50%
	Total service disruption delay	2010			-50%
	Percentage of diversions caused by service disruption	2010			-50%
Safety	Annual European-wide absolute number of ATM induced accidents and serious or risk bearing incidents	2005		No increase	
	Safety level (per flight)	2005			x 3
Environmental Sustainability	Avg. fuel savings per flight as a result of ATM improvements	2005			10%
	Avg. CO ₂ emission per flight as a result of ATM improvements	2005			-10%
	Compliance with local environmental rules			100%	
	Number of proposed environmentally related ATM constraints subjected to a transparent assessment with an environment and socio-economic scope			100%	

Figure 2.25. Summary of the 2020 Performance Targets [1]

If these targets are compared to today's data, it can be noticed that some of them will not be reached by 2020. It is the case of the target about annual IFR flights in Europe. There were 10 million controlled flights in 2016 and it is expected that there will be 11 million flights in 2020 (see the following figure 2.26), which is significantly lower to the target of 16 million flights in 2020 set in 2005.

Figure 2.26 - Evolution of European IFR flights (1990-2023) [2]

It is usual that macro-projects do not fulfil the expected research and implementation times, resulting in important delays or even cancellations. In this context, the differences among the real data and the targets set are owing to a cluster of external and internal factors and it is expected that next research and developments follow the same guidelines. Indeed, some of current developments related to new targets within the ATM Master Plan are suffering delays on its implementation.

For example, the implementation progress of the "Advanced Surface Movement Guidance and Control System (A-SMGCS) Level1" objective is completed at 79% but it is not fulfilling the expected deadline as can be seen in the following figure 2.27. As it is shown, it will present a 7-year delay when it is fully deployed in 2018. This is a problem in such a way that this objective is pre-requisite for other objectives and a first step in order to complete subsequent functions, producing important delays and related issues.

Figure 2.27 - Advanced Surface Movement Guidance and Control System implementation progress [3]

As a different example than the previous one, consisting of a project related to the flexible use of airspace, the implementation progress of the “Free Route Airspace” objective is completed at 61% and it is fulfilling the expected deadline as can be seen in the following Figure 2.28:

Figure 2.28 - Free Route Airspace implementation progress [3]

In this context in which is widely recognized that to increase performance, ATM modernization should look at the flights within a flow and network context rather than segmented portions of its trajectory as is the case today. Upcoming research and developments must be previously studied in order to make a wide research framework in which each project has both enough funds and duration to achieve its goals. The fact of trying that this wide framework is defined under previous studies will allow to close the gaps remaining between the goals set for 2050 and the actual improvements reached in 30 years.

If these studies about investment and duration are carried out properly, it is expected that the outcomes of the research are excellent, reducing en route and TMA direct costs per flight, reducing delays, fuel burn and flight time and improving the throughput at congested airports. The following Figure 2.29 illustrates the outcome for the optimized ATM infrastructure deployment option where performance benefits outgrow the investment ambition as of 2018, and cumulative benefits outgrow cumulative investments as of 2020, if all performance gains resulting from the performance scheme target-setting for the period 2014-2019 (RP2) are realized.

Figure 2.29 - Comparison between investments and benefits [4]

2.2 Ground Infrastructure and Multimodal Transport

***Flightpath 2050 goal 2 “A coherent ground infrastructure is developed including: airports, vertiports, heliports with the relevant servicing and connecting facilities, also to other modes”.**

The movements around an airport consist of aircraft operations in the air (goal 1 and section 2.1) and also the taxiing of aircraft and other vehicles on the ground. The ground movements in an airport can be quite complex involving besides taxiing aircraft, on their own power or towed, but also a variety of other vehicles, such as passenger buses, fuel trucks, luggage trailers, catering services, etc. The potential for incidents, especially in fog and other low visibility conditions, should not be underestimated. The tracking of vehicles on the ground can be made more difficult by buildings or other obstructions. The optimization of aircraft ground movements can save fuel in taxiing, energy of towing vehicles, reduce landing and take-off queue and contribute to timeliness of passenger services. The optimization of the use of runways, parking areas, and passenger ingress and egress, and aircraft taxiways should not be compromised by movements of other ground vehicles that provide essential services.

Besides the issue of ground movements, that can be of considerable complexity, and offer the potential for gains in efficiency, there are other possible bottlenecks, such as: (i) luggage handling; (ii) passenger check-in, passport and security checks; (iii) interfaces with other modes of transport. It may happen that the main impact of an airport on the surrounding community comes not from aircraft operations but rather from ground infrastructure, including airport access, that also affect passenger convenience.

As air traffic grows, a particular airport may reach its capacity limits, for one or more of several possible reasons: (i) runway capacity; (ii) terminal area air traffic congestion; (iii) available aircraft parking spaces; (iv) passenger and cargo management; (v) noise curfews or local restrictions on operating hours. The option of building more runways depends on land availability and community acceptance. New airports to serve major cities tend to be built farther requiring faster transport to reduce access time.

Vertiports and heliports can be sited much closer to city centres, providing an alternative with faster access than airports, if noise and community issues can be resolved.

The integration of air transport ground infrastructure with other modes of transport is presented in the Key Topic T2.3 below:

KEY TOPIC T2.3 – GROUND AND AIR OPERATIONS

Introduction

Europe is a specific area with very high population density, with short distances between large urban centres. This makes Europe's transport system characterized by a dense network of connections at short distances, with large passenger flows between transport nodes. This situation also concerns air transport.

The European Union (EU) is a political and economic union of 28 Member States that are located primarily in Europe.

Therefore, it has consequences resulting from the combination of law systems and transportation systems in one. The fragmentation of different national systems that existed before the unification of the EU are still felt.

Contrary to the United States, Europe does not have a single sky, one in which air navigation is managed at the European level. Furthermore, European airspace is among the busiest in the world with over 33,000 flights on busy days and high airport density. This makes air traffic control even more complex.

The EU Single European Sky is an ambitious initiative launched by the European Commission in 2004 to reform the architecture of European air traffic management. It proposes a legislative approach to meet future capacity and safety needs at a European rather than a local level.

The Single European Sky is the only way to provide a uniform and high level of safety and efficiency over Europe's skies.

The key objectives include:

- Restructure European airspace as a function of air traffic flows
- Create additional capacity; and
- Increase the overall efficiency of the air traffic management system

The major elements of this new institutional and organisational framework for Air Traffic Management in Europe consist of:

- Separating regulatory activities from service provision, and the possibility of cross-border Air Traffic Management (ATM) services.
- Reorganising European airspace that is no longer constrained by national borders.
- Setting common rules and standards, covering a wide range of issues, such as flight data exchanges and telecommunications.

SESAR

As part of the Single European Sky initiative, SESAR (Single European Sky ATM Research) represents its technological dimension. It will help create a “paradigm shift”, supported by state-of-the-art and innovative technology.

The SESAR programme will give Europe a high-performance air traffic control infrastructure which will enable the safe and environmentally friendly development of air transport.

SESAR aims to eliminate the fragmented approach to European ATM, transform the ATM system, synchronise all stakeholders and federate resources. For the first time, all aviation players are involved in the definition, development and deployment of a pan-European modernisation project.

By implementing the SESAR concept in 2020, ATM-related CO₂ emissions should be reduced by 10% per flight (against a 2005 baseline);

- Improve the management of noise emissions and their impact through better flight paths, or optimised climb and descent solutions;

Improve the role of ATM in enforcing local environmental rules by ensuring that flight operations fully comply with aircraft type restrictions, night movement bans, noise routes, noise quotas, etc.

Taking into account the above facts, it can be stated that the specificity of the European air traffic market and the growing number of flights performed in the European airspace generate growing challenges, the most important of which are: airport capacity, sustainability, operating a highly-congested air traffic network, fully-exploiting SESAR, and climate change. Airspace capacity will not be the greatest challenge. The use of alternative airports is a major contributor to the airport capacity challenge.

European Airports

The European air traffic network contains about 170.000 links between airports [4]. Understanding the variety of airports in Europe, their distribution, their traffic patterns and their aircraft mix, is essential to understand the strengths of the air traffic network. Taking into account short distances between the European cities, transportation on the territory of Europe is performed mainly over short and medium distances, with the domination of the first ones. The European transport market is therefore, the area of competition between the road, rail and air transport.

A characteristic feature of the European air transport service market is co-existence of several but large communication centres performing trans-continental links and dense net of local links between the majority of small cities and tourist resorts. In Europe there are (Figure 2.30) about 45 main airports (large and medium hubs) and about 450 country and regional airports (commercial service airports) (Brusow et al., 2007). European airports have almost 1350 hard take-off runways (concrete or asphalt) and 740 airports have necessary equipment to perform IFR flights (Brusow et al., 2007; Eurocontrol, 2007; Eurocontrol, 2016). In 2015, approximately 9.917 million IFR flights were performed in Europe and the forecast for 2022 assumes a 3.8 per cent increase in the number of IFR flights, which is an equivalent to 12.868 million take-offs, and the same number of landings, in the European airports (EUROCONTROL, 2016). There are serious bottlenecks in the air, especially in ECAC core areas caused by the situation where 85% of air activity is generated by 45 main airports (Brusow et al., 2007; Eurostat). This results in a very high air traffic density in the largest European airports and in their

vicinity. What it involves is that the air traffic in the largest airports and their areas of operations approaches the capacity limits.

In 2016, the total number of passengers travelling by air in the European Union could be established at 973 million, an increase of 5.9 % compared to 2015. Figure 2.31 shows the total growth of air passengers by Member State between 2015 and 2016. The disparity is particularly marked at country level, with year-on-year growths ranging from -2.7 % in Belgium to +22.5 % in Bulgaria.

Figure 2.30 - The map of Europe with the marked airports

Source: Eurostat (online data code: avia_paoc)

Figure 2.31 - EU-28 growth in total passenger air transport by Member State, 2015-2016 (Eurostat)

The Figure 2.32 indicates that the intra-EU share in total transport could be established at 47 %. It was the main destination ahead of extra-EU transport (36 %) and domestic passenger transport (17 %).

In 2016 (Table 2.10), London/Heathrow remained the largest EU-28 airport in terms of passenger transport. Paris/Charles de Gaulle remained the second largest with almost 10 million passengers less than London/Heathrow.

Figure 2.32 - Overview of EU-28 air passenger transport in 2016 (Eurostat)

Rank	Country	Airport	Total air transport (in 1000 passengers)	of which			Growth of total air transport 2015-2016 (%)	Total number of passenger flights (in 1000)	Growth of total number of flights 2015-2016 (%)
				National air transport	International intra-EU-28 air transport	International extra-EU-28 air transport			
1	UK	London/Heathrow	75 672	4 645	26 257	44 770	1.0	471	0.2
2	FR	Paris/Charles de Gaulle	65 849	6 055	26 040	33 755	0.3	444	0.9
3	NL	Amsterdam/Schiphol	63 550	0.5	37 890	25 659	9.3	467	6.2
4	DE	Frankfurt/Main	60 669	6 943	25 211	28 514	-0.4	435	-0.9
5	ES	Madrid/Barajas	49 178	14 133	21 585	13 460	6.2	354	1.5
6	ES	Barcelona/El Prat	43 750	11 789	24 837	7 124	11.0	293	6.7
7	UK	London/Gatwick	43 143	3 870	28 317	10 956	7.2	277	5.6
8	DE	München	42 159	9 593	20 709	11 858	3.2	375	3.9
9	IT	Roma/Fiumicino	41 569	12 470	17 991	11 108	3.3	310	-0.2
10	FR	Paris/Orly	31 238	14 143	10 795	6 300	5.3	235	1.5
11	DK	København/Kastrup	28 946	1 880	19 123	7 944	9.2	254	4.6
12	IE	Dublin	27 709	82	23 299	4 328	11.2	200	8.5
13	ES	Palma De Mallorca	26 230	5 803	19 179	1 248	10.6	186	11.1
14	UK	Manchester	25 598	2 295	16 477	6 827	10.9	184	12.2
15	SE	Stockholm/Arlanda	24 698	5 275	13 776	5 647	6.7	220	3.7
16	UK	London/Stansted	24 317	2 051	20 997	1 269	8.0	153	5.6
17	DE	Düsseldorf	23 497	4 476	11 933	7 088	4.7	209	3.2
18	AT	Wien/Schwechat	23 318	509	15 405	7 405	2.5	220	-0.1
19	PT	Lisboa	22 463	3 068	13 941	5 453	11.7	178	10.5
20	BE	Brussels/National	21 769	2	15 362	6 406	-6.4	192	-7.5
21	DE	Berlin/Tegel	21 245	7 769	9 596	3 880	1.2	179	1.1
22	EL	Athinaí/Eleftherios Venizelos	20 009	7 157	8 959	3 892	10.6	176	8.4
23	IT	Milano/Malpensa	19 312	2 693	9 926	6 692	4.7	150	4.0
24	FI	Helsinki/Vantaa	17 181	2 679	10 443	4 059	4.6	157	-0.5
25	ES	Malaga/Costa del Sol	16 620	2 274	12 982	1 363	15.7	115	13.5
26	DE	Hamburg	16 191	5 339	7 866	2 985	3.9	143	1.4
27	UK	London/Luton	14 642	1 043	12 132	1 467	19.4	101	18.0
28	CZ	Praha/Ruzyně	12 990	36	9 332	3 622	9.5	126	6.5
29	PL	Warszawa/Chopina	12 848	1 424	7 989	3 435	14.5	142	8.7
30	FR	Nice/Côte d'Azur	12 422	4 440	5 754	2 229	3.4	146	5.1

Table 2.10 - Top 30 airports in the EU-28 in terms of total passengers carried in 2016 (Eurostat).

More traffic in Europe will mean busier airports. In 2035, 20 airports will handle more than 150,000 departures a year in the most-likely scenario, a level of traffic currently achieved only at 9 airports in Europe (Table 2.10). Some faster-growing airports in Southern and Eastern Europe will join the top 25 (Eurocontrol, 2013).

Airport Movement

Traffic in the area of a civil airport consists of two types of activity. The first one concerns the movement of aircraft in the area of the airport (ground and air operations), the second one concerns the movement of all kinds of non-aircraft vehicles necessary for the operation of the airport.

Aircraft Operations

Standard aircraft procedures consist of:

- Parking: intended for parking, maintenance and service an aircraft.
- Push back or power back operations.
- Towing the aircraft
- Taxi out and taxi in operations,
- Take-off,
- Landing.

Parking, push back or power back and towing procedures generally are called aircraft ground handling servicing. Taxi, take-off and landing constitutes LTO (Landing and Take-Off) cycle. The main problem to be solved relates to increasing airport capacity and reducing delays and costs and reducing environmental impact of air transport, especially in the airports surrounding areas. Sources of these problems lie in both handling procedures and LTO operations.

➤ Aircraft LTO Operations

The aircraft operations and procedures are highly regulated. For example, different recommendations are present for the take-off climb procedure for performance class A aeroplanes. According to Certification Specifications (EASA, 2017), the transition from the take-off to the en route configuration and the acceleration to the final climb segment speed must be completed before the aircraft reaches 1500 (ft) net altitude (CS-25.111 (a) – EASA, 2017). The take-off path is determined by a continuous take-off path or by synthesis from segments which relate to distinct changes in configuration, power or thrust, and speed (CS-25.111 (d) – EASA, 2017). Thus, the aircraft must be 'cleaned up' in a manner preordained in CS's. The regulations specify that whilst the transition is taking place, the aircraft must avoid all obstacles that are in the 'obstacle accountability area' by a minimum vertical interval of 35 (ft) or by the horizontal distance detailed in EU-OPS 1.495. The flight path determined for the aircraft commences therefore at the end of the take-off distance required at screen height and is constructed by assuming the critical engine to be inoperative (CS-25.115(a) – EASA, 2017).

Figure 2.33 - Typical six segment net flightpaths
Source: Own elaboration based on EASA, 2017

As shown in the Figure 2.33, the segments of the flight path are also defined in detail. 1st Segment - this segment commences at screen height (CS-25.115(a) – EASA, 2017) at the end of the take-off distance required at which point the undercarriage 'UP' button is pressed. The speed is V_2 , free air safety speed, and the power set at maximum take-off power one engine inoperative. The segment ends when the undercarriage is fully retracted and is the start of the second segment. 2nd Segment - the speed and power are maintained until the aircraft attains flap retraction altitude (minimum 400 (ft) gross). The segment ends on attainment of this altitude which is the commencement of the third segment. The first and second segments are referred to as the 'Initial Climb'. 3rd Segment - this segment is an acceleration segment; it may be level or still climbing if sufficient power is available. The segment ends when the aircraft, after flap retraction, achieves the final segment climb speed which signifies the beginning of the 'Final Climb'. The maximum height of flap retraction is dependent on the take-off thrust maximum time limit. 4th Segment - this is the final climb. The power setting must be reduced after 5 minutes from the brakes release point, to maximum continuous power setting. The speed is maintained at the final segment climb speed. The net flight path ends at 1500 (ft) net height. 5th and 6th Segment - some low powered aircraft might require further two segments to reach 1500 (ft) and the en route climb speed.

At airports, aircraft emission amounts vary by aircraft operation modes and depend on the time spent at each mode/phase during the Landing and Take Off cycle (LTO). LTO includes all activities near the airport that take place below the altitude of 3000 feet (1000 m), which consists of taxiing-out, taking-off and climbing out for departures, and descending, touching down, and taxiing-in for arrivals.

Other Ground Movement

Handling activities related to aircraft during ground time may be a significant contributor to local air pollution at an airport. Such activities include all vehicles and machinery serving the aircraft on its

parking position (e.g. high loaders, baggage belts, passengers' stairs) and circulating on airside operating surfaces and service roads (e.g. lavatory trucks, catering trucks, cargo tractors).

In the context of local air quality management, it is important to assess the emissions of different sources for various pollutants. Example emission by source groups for Zurich airport is presented in the Figure 2.34:

Figure 2.34. NOx emission by source groups (Fleuti, 2014).

The interdependencies of aircraft ground handling is qualitatively characterised in the Figure 2.35. It has to be recognised that the type and number of **Ground** Support Equipment (GSE) are determined by the aircraft (size) and the aircraft stand (location and installations) as well as applicable operational procedures at the airport (e.g. APU restrictions). In consequence, any default attribution of ground support equipment must be reflected by all factors.

Figure 2.35 - Characterization of GSE (Fleuti, 2014).

GSE is used the moment an aircraft lands and until it takes off. GSE is used for tasks as diverse as towing, powering, and servicing. There is great diversity in the type of equipment used, as well as in the variety of engines (diesel or gasoline) that power GSE. The commonly used types of GSE are:

- **Baggage Tugs** (or Tractors) transport luggage or cargo between aircraft and terminals.

- **Belt Loaders** are a self-propelled conveyer belt that moves baggage and cargo between the ground and the airport.
- **Forklifts, Lifts, and Cargo Loaders** include equipment for lifting and loading cargo.
- **Ground Power Units (GPUs)** provide electricity to parked aircraft.
- **Aircraft Tugs** (pushback tractors) tow aircraft in areas where aircraft cannot use their own engines for motion. These are generally the areas between the taxiway and the terminal and between the terminal and the maintenance base.
- **Air Start Units** are trailer or truck-mounted compressors that provide air for starting up the aircraft's main engines.
- **Air Conditioning Units** are trailer or truck mounted compressors that deliver air through a hose to parked aircraft for cabin ventilation and engine cooling.
- **Deicers** are trailers equipped with tank, pump, hose, and spray gun to transport and spray de-icing fluid on aircraft (to ensure that no ice builds up on body of plane or in turbines).
- **Lavatory carts** are used to service aircraft lavatories. Other types of carts can be used to transport equipment and personnel.
- **Fuel Trucks, Utility Trucks, Maintenance, Water and Service Trucks** are used on the airside of the airport for many diverse tasks.
- **Bobtail Tractors** are on-road trucks modified to tow trailers and equipment.

A cost-effective way to reduce emissions is to replace GSE powered by an internal combustion engine with electric equipment. Electric equipment has no exhaust emissions and replacing equipment powered by ICE (internal combustion engine) engines with electric equipment will reduce NOx emissions. Electric GSE is commercially available for a number of equipment types, including belt loaders, baggage tractors, aircraft tugs, lifts, and GPU's. Several airlines and airports have conducted electric GSE demonstration programs and fleet conversion programs. Much of the experience to date with electric equipment has been quite positive. In addition to air quality benefits, users have found that electric equipment is more "task specific" than ICE equipment. Electric equipment often includes more ergonomic features and users find that it "rides better" than equivalent diesel equipment. However, the higher capital cost of electric equipment has prevented its widespread use to date.

Other Airport Impact on Climate Change

The other airport infrastructure also affects the natural environment and contributes to climate change. It is possible to indicate the sources resulting, for example, from the need to supply electricity to airport buildings, heating and cooling in airport's building, etc.

This impact can be reduced by:

- Reduction of energy consumption by retrofitting of LED technology or retrofitting of airport buildings (roof, air-conditioning, etc.)
- Use of renewable sources of energy, i.e. purchase of green electricity, production of energy from renewable sources (solar, co-generation, aquifer, biomass, etc.).
- Others.

Airports Bottlenecks

Airport Handling

Many processes take place while the aircraft is parking, which extends the aircraft handling time. Some of them can be carried out at the same time and some require a proper order. The workload and time of these processes have a significant impact on airport capacity and may be some kind of bottleneck.

The effectiveness can be characterised by turn-around time, which can be defined as the time between touch down and take off. The conceptual model of the activities in the turn-around process is presented at the Figure 2.36:

Figure 2.36 - Typical turn-around activities (Norin, 2008).

➤ The Baggage Loading and Unloading Process

Checked in baggage can be stowed in the aircraft in two different ways. Either the bags are stowed in bulk (normally smaller aircraft) or in pre-packed containers (for larger aircraft). As the containers can be packed before the aircraft arrives to the airport, the turn-around process time for loading baggage will be shorter with container loading than with bulk if the number of bags is large. The checked in baggage on a flight has to be sorted, unless it is a charter flight (or other point-to-point flight) where all bags have the same priority and destination. Otherwise there might be transferring bags, high prioritized bags or odd size bags etc.

➤ The Catering Process

The catering process involves removing leftover food from the previous flight and re-equipping the aircraft with new food. The catering can start when all passengers have left the aircraft. The catering companies use high-loaders to get the catering cabinets on and off the aircraft. All high-loaders do not fit all aircraft, so a planning of which high-loader to use for which aircraft is required.

Catering takes between 5 and 75 minutes depending on how much food that is needed and if there are pre-packs (pre-ordered commodities placed on the seat) or not. The catering teams need to go back to the depot between serving two aircraft to empty garbage and re-equip with new food.

The catering coordinator makes a rough plan from the air traffic schedule for how many workers are needed and the detailed planning of who is serving which aircraft is done manually during the day.

➤ The Cleaning Process

The airlines can request different types of aircraft cleaning. During daytime the cleaning can take from 5 (just empty garbage) up to 40 (garbage, seat-pockets, belts, vacuum cleaning etc.) minutes. The latter is only performed on aircraft with longer turn-around-times. Longer and more careful cleaning is performed during night-time when the aircraft is on the ground for longer time. On most aircraft, cleaning and catering can be performed simultaneously, but for some smaller aircraft there is not space for both. In the latter case, it does not matter if cleaning or catering is performed first.

The cleaning teams can go directly between two aircraft, but at breaks and when they need new material (like pillows and blankets) they must go to the cleaning base. There is no significant difference between the cleaning teams, so all teams can be assigned to all aircraft and cleaning types.

➤ The Fuelling Process

Usually the fuelling can be performed in two different ways. There is a hydrant system with fuel pipes in the ground that dispenser trucks can connect to, to fill up the aircraft. At aircraft stands where the hydrant system is not available, fuelling is performed by tankers. There are different types of dispenser trucks; the large type that can serve all kinds of aircraft and the smaller type that only can connect to smaller aircraft. However, the small dispensers are preferred when the area around the aircraft is tight. Also, the tankers vary in size. Normally they can take between 8 and 40 cubic meters of fuel.

Fuelling cannot be performed simultaneously with baggage loading and unloading since these services need the same area around the aircraft. Before the fuel company starts to fill up, they always check the water content in the fuel. The area around the aircraft has to be planned so that the dispenser truck or tanker has a free way for evacuation. There are also some airline specific rules about fuelling while passengers are on-board. Most airlines allow that, but only under certain conditions, e.g. there must be a fire engine ready in the immediate surrounding or there must be two-way communications between apron and aircraft. Usually the fuelling is not allowed if there is a thunderstorm.

The time it takes to fill up an aircraft depends on the capacity of the pipes in the aircraft and, of course, of the amount of fuel needed. The pilot decides how much fuel that is needed and must report that to the fuelling company before they can start to fill up the aircraft.

➤ The Water and Sanitation processes

The aircraft must be released from waste water and be re-equipped with fresh water. This is performed by two different vehicles which most often are operating on the opposite side of the aircraft body

than baggage handling and fuelling. This means that water and sanitation can be performed simultaneously with baggage loading/unloading and fuelling, but not simultaneously with each other. However, it does not matter which one of them that performs its service first.

➤ The De-icing Process

Since even very thin layers of frost and ice on the aircraft have a negative effect on the lifting force and the control of the aircraft, de-icing is needed if any part of the aircraft is covered with snow or frost, or there is precipitation that could cause this to happen. The de-icing period depends on the climate zone and specific weather conditions. The de-icing process is divided into two steps; during the first step, frost and ice are removed from the aircraft, usually by a warm, buoyant glycol mix (Type 1 fluid). The next step is called anti-icing and is performed to prevent new frost and ice from appearing on the aircraft before take-off by a thicker fluid (Type 2 fluid). The time from anti-icing to take-off (called hold-over time) is limited, as the effect of the Type 2 fluid wears off after a while. This means that it is not possible to de-ice an aircraft a long time before take-off. How long the hold-over time is depending on the type of fluid, temperature and type of precipitation. Therefore, it is important to find a de-icing truck that can serve the aircraft on the "right" time. If the aircraft is served late, the turn-around time will increase with a possible late departure as a result. If the de-icing is performed too early, the procedure might have to be repeated. Even so, this would be a fairly uncomplicated planning problem, if only the time windows were known in advance and could be considered reliable. Today, the de-icing coordinator will plan tactically based on weather conditions and the flight schedule, and operationally – when a truck is dispatched – based on a request from the pilot. At the moment the coordinator gets the request, he or she decides which truck that should be allocated to the aircraft in question. Today, there is no pre-planned schedule that the decision can be based on. This means that the truck-drivers do not know in advance which aircraft they are going to de-ice during the day.

Interfaces with Other Modes of Transport

➤ High-Speed Train

High-speed train (Figure 2.37) both competes with and complements short-haul passenger air transport. Over 50 city-pairs will be connected by new or improved links between 2019 and 2035. Operating at high speeds, the train can offer comparable transport times for distances up to 800 km. It can also successfully attract passengers by providing in some cases a lower risk of delay, less security hassle, shorter distance to the city centre. Passengers opting for rail will reduce the demand for flights by a little over 0.5% in 2035, often easing the pressure at congested airports rather than reducing the number of operated flights (Eurocontrol, 2013).

Figure 2.37 High-speed rail network mostly develops in Western Europe (Eurocontrol, 2013)

Airport Capacity Limits

Airspace capacity is the decisive factor in allocating the maximum number of air operations that can be performed, especially in the airport areas (bottlenecks). That capacity is also dependent on the principles of performing air operations in the airport areas

Airports are constrained in different ways by different types of capacity. Airport capacity is the number of passengers and amount of cargo which an airport can accommodate in a given period of time; it is a combination of runway capacity and terminal capacity (ICAO, 2016). Capacity definitions can be categorized by considering the constraining element (Figure 2.38), and then divide definitions into technical capacity, acceptable capacity and allowed capacity (Boonstra et al, 2016).

Figure 2.38 Airport Capacity Constraints

Technical capacity is defined as the maximum number of aircraft or passengers that can be accommodated in a certain period of time when there is continuous demand. It is affected by the physical constraints of the available infrastructure, such as the maximum throughput figure of a runway or the maximum number of passengers based on the limited terminal space available.

Acceptable capacity is the maximum number of aircraft or passengers than can be accommodated in a certain period of time, taking into account a maximum allowable delay or waiting time per step in the airport process.

Allowed capacity is defined by regulations and legislation that balance economic importance against any problems that may be caused for local population. For instance, a government or other authority might limit the annual number of ATMs on the basis of the limits of maximum noise or gaseous emissions. No additional aircraft (or passengers) would then be allowed at an airport, even if there was physical room for expansion.

Runway Capacity

Runway capacity is the number of aircraft movements which aeronautical authorities determine can safely be operated, usually stated as the total number of landings and take-offs per hour, taking into account such factors as the physical characteristics of the runways and the surrounding area, altitude, the types of aircraft involved (larger aircraft may mandate greater separation) and air traffic control (approach and aerodrome control) capabilities (ICAO, 2016).

A queue at the taxiway will occur when the maximum runway capacity is reached. This queue will only arise in the case of maximum peak hour capacity, and not necessarily in the case of maximum annual ATMs, which is more theoretical. If maximum environmental capacity is reached at one runway, aircraft may be required to use a different runway.

The capacities of the airports are driven by several factors. The number of runways is one of the major factors. The airports use one or several runways with finite capacity, which allocates the number of aircraft that the airport can handle safely. As the number of runways affects the capacity of the airport very strongly, the number of rapid exit ways or the meteorological conditions also influences the capacity. Because aircraft must be separated to avoid conflicts and wake vortices at the same time on the same runway, only one aircraft can take-off or land. The separations between the aircraft is necessarily higher at lower visibility conditions, or in special case, a strong side-wind can radically limit the capacity of a runway. In addition, as recent events show (e.g. in London), extreme meteorological conditions and thus the capacity of the supporting equipment's (such as de-icer) could also limit the overall runway capacity.

Another problem is the saturation of major airports in Europe. The safe separation on approach is determined by the wake vortices. The larger the leading aircraft and smaller the following aircraft, the larger separation should be used. At most of the airports is not possible to build new runways because of the lack of territory, environmental considerations or public opinion.

The issues of improving airport capacity and efficiency were taken up in the SESAR programme. Currently, they are continued under the SESAR 2020 programme within the key feature 'High Performing Airport Operations'. The most important projects implemented in this area are:

- PJ01 - Enhanced arrivals and departures. As a part of the project, concepts, tools and procedures will be developed to increase the capacity of Terminal Manoeuvring Areas (TMAs) in a safe, cost-

effective and environmentally sustainable manner. This will be achieved by taking advantage of the latest technological developments from both an airborne and a ground-system perspective and through the secure sharing of data. The needs of all Airspace Users will be addressed including General Aviation and Rotorcraft (WWW. SESAR JU).

- PJ02 - Increased Runway and Airport Throughput. As a part of the project, the concepts supporting increased runway and airport throughput were broken down into the following sub-elements: optimal Wake Turbulence Separation, enhanced arrival procedures, minimum Pair Separations based on Required Surveillance Performance (RSP), independent Rotorcraft operations at the airport, improved access into small/medium airports in Low Visibility Conditions (LVC), traffic optimisation on single and multiple runway airports and enhanced Terminal Area for efficient curved operations (WWW Eurocontrol).
- PJ04 - Total airport management. The project is aimed to Integration of airports into the ATM network through sharing information in a timely manner between the network operations plan and the individual AOPs (Airport Operations Plan) using SWIM (System Wide Information Management) technology.

Other projects implemented under the SESAR 2020 program also influence improving safety, efficiency, capacity and reducing the environmental impact of airports.

Another problem that has appeared in recent years is the integration of operations of manned and unmanned aircraft (RPAS - Remotely Piloted Aircraft System) at airport area (ground and air operations). Several projects are currently devoted to this problem, the most important of which are:

- SESAR 2020
 - o PJ02 - General Aviation, RPAS and rotorcraft integrated in a multi-aircraft and manned flight environment.
 - o PJ03 - Integration of RPAs, GA and Rotorcraft into the airport operations
 - o PJ.10 Separation Management En Route and TMA (PJ10.05 Integration of RPAS IFR flight, also in the TMA)
- Enhanced RPAS Automation (ERA) project founded by the European Defence Agency (EDA) and led by Airbus Defence and Space. The main objectives of ERA are to establish the technological baseline for automatic take-off and landing, auto-taxi, nominal/degraded mode automation functions and emergency recovery. This will be done alongside support to the regulation and standardisation of these capabilities, by providing safety assessments, procedures, simulation and flight demonstrations.

Terminal Area Air Traffic Congestion

Terminal capacity is the number of passengers and tonnes of cargo per hour which can be processed in a terminal building (sometimes referred to as passenger throughput or cargo throughput). The type of passenger or passenger mix can influence the rate of passenger throughput. International passengers who must clear customs and immigration require more time and space than domestic passengers who are not subject to these procedures. Domestic and international cargo presents a similar situation (ICAO, 2016).

Available Aircraft Parking Spaces

After passing the terminal, the passenger arrives at the gate: the area of an airport that provides a waiting area for passengers before boarding their flight. The maximum gate capacity of one gate must be in accordance with the type and size of aircraft at the corresponding apron.

The apron is the airside area of an airport used to park aircraft. Static apron capacity is the number of stands available or the number of aircraft that can occupy the apron at any given moment. Dynamic apron capacity is the number of aircraft per hour that can be accommodated, considering the time interval between successive occupancies by two different aircraft. Apron capacity becomes constrained when the number and size of aprons does not match the actual number and size of aircraft using the aprons.

Impact of Capacity Constraints On Air Fares

Airport capacity congestion is already being felt in markets across Europe and is expected to be one of the greatest bottlenecks for future growth of the aviation industry. Under the current policy framework, growth of airport capacity will not be able to keep up with aviation demand growth.

EUROCONTROL (Eurocontrol, 2013) predicts that by 2035 more than 30 European airports will be congested. These airports are operating at 80% or more of their capacity for more than 3 hours per day. In 2035, around 1.9 million flights (accounting for 12% of the demand) cannot not be accommodated in EUROCONTROL's 'most likely' traffic growth scenario. In Eurocontrol's highest growth scenario, this number rises to 4.4 million flights.

In a situation where demand for airport capacity exceeds the supply of airport capacity, and where the airport is in a position of substantial market power in the passenger market, prices are used to balance the level of demand with the capacity available. If the airport prices efficiently through its airport charges, scarcity will be reflected in higher (peak period) charges, hence in higher costs to the airlines and, in turn and depending on the market situation, in higher fares charged to passengers for travel at peak periods.

In a study for the UK Airports Commission (Burghouwt et al. 2017) it was found that airport capacity constraints are being associated with higher air fares for a selection of European airports. For all routes in the dataset, the study finds that fare revenue per passenger mile increases by 18% when the capacity utilisation increases from a non-constrained level to a severely constrained level (>95% capacity utilisation). It was also found that the fare premium in relative terms is higher at smaller airports than at larger airports. In addition, the study finds that the effect is strongest at airports operating at 99% of their stated runway capacity and less so at airports operating at around 80% of stated capacity. Below 80% of capacity use, the estimated effect on fares becomes stronger again.

Environmental Impact

All transport, including air transport, contributes to the degradation of the natural environment and has a negative impact on people. Although the aircraft noise is extremely troublesome for the people of the settlements located near airports, however, the negative impact of air transport on the environment is primarily associated with the emission of gases and particles which alter the atmospheric concentration of greenhouse gases. Aircraft emit gases and particles directly into the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere where they have an impact on atmospheric composition.

These gases and particles alter the concentration of atmospheric greenhouse gases, including carbon dioxide (CO₂), ozone (O₃), and methane (CH₄); trigger formation of condensation trails (contrails); and may increase cirrus cloudiness—all of which contribute to climate change.

Despite the fact that aviation participates only slightly (2 - 3%) in global environmental pollution, the concentration of greenhouse gases and toxic compounds produced by aircraft and accompanying equipment is particularly high at airport areas and in the upper troposphere. This impact is the stronger the more intensive air traffic takes place in a given area. The problem becomes particularly important for large airports characterized by high levels of air traffic, which are most often found in areas with high population density, which means that they involve a large group of people by their negative impact. Local environmental pollution associated with the airport's activities can be divided into two groups:

- Caused by the aircraft power units and their auxiliary power units (APU);
- Caused by the airport Ground Support Equipment (GSE), e.g. airport vehicles, electric generators, technical services etc.

The environmental impacts of aviation are both global (e.g. CO₂ emissions from burning fuel) and local (e.g. noise and local air quality impacts).

European aviation's absolute CO₂ emissions will continue to grow but at a slower rate than traffic. Emissions per passenger km may decrease by up to 2% per year if fuel efficiency and traffic forecasts evolve as expected (Eurocontrol, 2013).

Technological improvements will continue to reduce aircraft engine noise although may be offset by traffic growth and evolving public perception.

Growth in traffic may also lead to an increase in local air quality impact, despite ongoing technological and operational improvements. Impact will vary with location, scale of operation and the relative contribution of other local sources. Trends in public opposition on the grounds of air quality and odour suggest that this may be a bigger constraint in future.

➤ Measures to reduce aircraft pollutant emissions

The aircraft emission in the area of the airport may be reduced by implementing of the following activities:

- Improve airframe and engine design;
- Better flight planning and air traffic control procedures to increase flight operation efficiency;
- Increase airfield capacity to reduce congestion;
- Modify aircraft ground operations.

Local Restrictions on Operating Hours and Other Limits

There are a number of measures to mitigate noise used by airports including (EY, 2016)

- Night time and other scheduling of runway operations to remove concentrations of noise over particular areas or at particular times;
- Changes or restrictions to on-field aircraft operations including engine trials and taxiing procedures;

- Adaptations to descent and approach procedures.

➤ Night Time and other restrictions

The airports recognised that noise impact at night are particularly troubling for local populations and have put in place measures to address this. The airports can be split into two categories (EY, 2016):

1. Airports with bans on flights in night time hours.
2. Airports applying additional limits to, but not bans, on night flying.

The airports which have put in place complete limits on night time flying include:

- Sydney –no flights scheduled between 23:00 and 06:00 except freight flights and up to 24 international flights a week.
- Frankfurt –no flights between 23:00 and 05:00 and set limits for evening shoulder periods.

The remaining airports have put in place measures to constrain the number of flights and aircraft that may operate at night. For example:

- Paris Charles de Gaulle –Limited to 55 flights per night.
- Schiphol –Limit of 32,000 flights per annum and a total noise limit applied over a year.
- O’Hare –There is no night flight limitation; however proposed changes to the Fly Quiet procedures include rotating runway used in night hours to allow respite periods.

➤ Other Constraints on Aircraft Movement Numbers

In addition to the constraints on night flights, several airports operate under additional restrictions on aircraft movements.

Typically, the measures take the form of (EY, 2016):

- Limiting the number of flights either per hour or per day.
- Restricting the use of noisier aircraft through either charge incentives or operating restrictions.
- Managing flight paths away from population concentrations.
- Rotating runway use so as to spread noise patterns across wider areas.
- Restrictions on ground handling procedures such as engine run-ups, use of reverse thrust and ground power units.

➤ Descent and Departure Adaptations

A common measure put in place to moderate the impact of noise on surrounding communities is the adaptations of descent and departure paths. Fraport (FRA) for example has extensive measures in place and under development to moderate the noise impact of arrivals and departures. These include (EY, 2016):

- Limiting take off speed,
- More frequent continuous descent operations,
- Increasing the glide angle,
- Raising the minimum downwind approach altitude,
- Raising the final approach height.

Measures currently under development include:

- Continuous climb operations,
- Increasing ILS,
- Steeper approach procedures,
- Amending the point merge procedures.

Ultimately in the UK the structure and operation of local airspace will be a matter for the airport and regulatory authorities to agree; however, the extensive list above shows the types of measures that might be deployed.

Vertiports and Heliports

Every day, millions of hours are wasted on the road worldwide. On-demand aviation, has the potential to radically improve urban mobility, giving people back time lost in their daily commutes. A network of small, traditional or electric aircraft that take off and land vertically (called VTOL aircraft for Vertical Take-off and Landing, and pronounced vee-tol), will enable rapid, reliable transportation between suburbs and cities and, ultimately, within cities.

The development of infrastructure to support an urban VTOL network will likely have significant cost advantages over heavy-infrastructure approaches such as roads, rail, bridges and tunnels. It has been proposed that the repurposed tops of parking garages, existing helipads, and even unused land surrounding highway interchanges could form the basis of an extensive, distributed network of “vertiports” (VTOL hubs with multiple take-off and landing pads, as well as charging infrastructure) or single-aircraft “vertistops” (a single VTOL pad with minimal infrastructure).

In the U.S. there are 5,664 helipads with all but 66 for private use (UBER, 2016), that is, developed for use by the property owner without public assistance. Most of this infrastructure is essentially unused. After years without use, many helipads have been declared inactive and for emergency use only. Many of these are located in highly desirable downtown locations that could provide rapid access into urban areas. Los Angeles alone has over 40 high-rise helipads in the immediate downtown. Cities such as San Francisco also have many high-rise building helipads, however none has permitted use due to local ordinances that are highly restrictive due primarily to noise concerns.

In Europe, there is much less heliports than in the US. Unconfirmed reports say indicates less than 100 civilian type heliports.

Over the past two years NASA has studied the idea of VTOL air-taxis operating in dense urban areas (UBER, 2016). Specifically, they chose San Francisco as one metropolitan area to provide detailed geographic, land use, infrastructure, weather, and operational constraint considerations to bring real world issues into their study.

A VTOL fleet will likely be supported in a city through a mixture of both vertiports and vertistops. Vertiports would be large multi-landing locations that have support facilities (i.e., rechargers, support personnel, etc.) for multiple VTOLs and passengers. Following the heliport examples used in New York City and other locations, vertiports would be limited to a maximum capacity of around 12 VTOLs at any given time to achieve a compact infrastructure size while enabling capacity for multiple simultaneous VTOL take-off and landings to maximize trip throughput. Vertistops, on the other hand, would be single vehicle landing locations where no support facilities are provided, but where VTOLs

can quickly drop off and pick up passengers without parking for an extended time. An example of a vertistop includes small helipads that are atop high-rise downtown buildings today (UBER, 2016).

Delay Effects

It is obvious that the lack of airport capacity will create a congested network, but there is an associated side effect of operating near capacity: delays. Delays have been classified as primary (i.e. ATFCM and non-ATFCM delays) and reactionary (i.e. knock-on delays incurred by previous flights) (Eurocontrol, 2013).

In 2012, the airport ATFCM (Air Traffic Flow and Capacity Management) primary delays were only 0.9 minutes out of an average of 5.7 minutes of primary delay per flight and out of 10 minutes per flight of total delay including the reactionary delay. In 2013, airports were a minor contributor of delays, the main caused and the biggest part of primary delays were related to airline causes (Eurocontrol, 2013).

Within a network where 20 airports operated (2013) at 80% or more of capacity during 6 consecutive hours or more, it is likely to expect that any deviation (e.g. late bags, missing passengers) from the plan will generate delays that will accumulate rapidly along the day.

The Figure 2.39 shows the growing delay challenge at airports for the summer months, where for 2012 only a minority of them suffer delays greater than 5 minutes per flight (Eurocontrol, 2013). This is reflected in the 1.12 minutes/flight of ATFCM delay measured, that is slightly higher than the whole year value of 0.9 mentioned above. In 2035, the picture is drastically different with high level of delay present across the network and a significant number of airports that present total delays greater than 20 minutes per flight.

Figure 2.39 - Increasing number of airports with summer delay (in minutes/flight).

Main delay causes at the top 10 affected departure airports (Eurocontrol, 2013) for departure (Figure 2.40) and arrival (Figure 2.41) are presented below

Figure 2.40 - Main Delay Causes at the Top 10 Affected Departure Airports (Eurocontrol, 2017)

Figure 2.41 - Main Delay Causes at the Top 10 Affected Arrival Airports (Eurocontrol, 2017)

The fuel cost, cost of flight crew, cost of leased aircraft, airport expenses and the unmeasured costs (e.g. customer complaints and disloyalty cost) are some of the examples that airlines have to cope with as a result of an increase in the delays.

Delays in the handling chain not only provoke impacts on the quality of the service experienced by the passengers, but also affect the operational efficiency, and as a result, the costs of the airline. Delays resulting from ground handling comprise one of the highest costs of the airlines, even though handling related delays are a cheaper and easier way of reducing departure delays, and consequently the costs, when compared to the difficulty of reducing other reasons for delays, such as weather conditions and air traffic control (ATC).

2.3 Choice of Most Efficient Mobility Solutions

*** Flightpath 2050 goal 3 "European citizens are able to make informed mobility choices and have affordable access to one another, taking into account: economy, speed and level of service"**

(that can be tailored to the individual customer). Continuous, secure and high-bandwidth communications are provided for added value applications”.

The progress in mobile communications and availability of information may ensure that the passenger can make informed choices among several available travel options. The issues of interference with and security of communications at passenger information level are comparable to other societal services. A more serious constraint may come from physical limits of transportation infrastructure and the underlying issue of land planning: (i) in the expansion of existing airports or addition of more runways; (ii) in the construction of new airports, vertiports and heliports; (iii) in the road/rail infrastructure that provides fast access; (iv) in the efficient organization of ground movements within the confines of the airport.

The choice of air travel compared with other means of transport depends not only on flight time but also on the ground movements to and from the airport that is an issue addressed in the Key Topic of intermodal transport.

KEY TOPIC T2.4 – MULTIMODAL TRANSPORT

Scope of the Goal

Ground infrastructure and multimodal transport		
Goal 2:		
A coherent ground infrastructure is developed including: airports, vertiports, heliports with the relevant servicing and connecting facilities, also to other modes		
Comparison with 2017 SRIA document	Why	Lacks
Coherent	It fits to the SRIA document content. It is essential to improve the ground infrastructure processes in order to offer customers a vastly improved, seamless travel experience. This applies to airports, vertiports and any other ground infrastructure supporting airborne passenger or cargo services. It is important to achieve better performance in punctuality, predictability, delay, waiting times, convenience and availability of information.	There are no omissions. It is very similar to the SRIA document

Benchmarks

A coherent ground infrastructure implies the design and implementation of an integrated, intermodal transport system as part of which airport evolve into integrated, efficient and sustainable air transport interface nodes.

The operation of airports as an efficient node of the transport system can be analysed from three perspectives (scales or points of view).

The first one corresponds to the efficient operation of all processes within the airport itself. A certain number of issues and process of the airport operation can become bottlenecks or offer potential for

increasing efficiency such as the ground movements but also main process inside the airport as luggage handling, passenger check-in or passport and security checks. The airport of the future should offer customers an improved, seamless travel experience. Airside and landside processes at airports need to be optimised for customer comfort, predictability, performance and better integration of transport modes. In terms of performance it would be fair that airports provide equivalent quality and efficiency on the processing of travellers and flight of service as the one demanded to the ATM system, and therefore by extension it will be fair to envisage an efficient 2050 airport where flights depart within 1 minute of the planned departure time. From the technological and operational dimension processes for passenger, baggage and freight handling must be continuously improved to achieve in punctuality, predictability, delay, waiting times, convenience and availability of information. Innovative, collaborative decision-making built upon total node (airport) management is required to create seamless passenger and cargo concepts, technologies and procedures.

The second one corresponds to the interconnection among the different airports of the European Networks. Technological and operational development will allow that information of traffic departing from the origin airport will be promptly and precisely shared with all the ACC centres in the plane trajectory as well as with the destination airport. As soon as the aircraft take-off it will become of the interest of the arrival airport that will receive promptly and updated information of the flight as this evolve. This information will be exploited at the destination airport for an optimum allocation of resources minimizing waiting and processing times once the plane arrives its destination. Any disruption during the flight will also soon acknowledge at the destination so that the system can accommodate deviations from planning and disruptions.

Finally, **the third one** corresponds to the integration of the airport with other modes of transport.

The interfaces of the airport with other modes of transport must allow the 90% of travellers within Europe are able to complete their journey, door-to-door within 4 hours. That means that connections with other modes of transport should allow that passengers arrive from their houses at the plane in a time interval compatible with the 4 hours door-to door requirement. Airport access has been improved accordingly through an innovative approach towards safe, efficient, frequent, comfortable transport systems and services and connections with other mode of transport must facilitate an easy and quick access to the plain.

The Figure 2.42 shows the (great-circle) distance flown by departures from the 528 biggest in Europe. Nearly three million departures travel a distance of 250-550km. On a coarser scale, the Figure 2.43 shows that at smaller airports, departures most often travel less than 300km, and the number of more distant connections declines rapidly. Even at the large and very large airports, the 400km distance bracket is the most common, showing how they are connected to the local network as well as to a long-haul one. The very large airports have only a small number of 1500-3500km flights, but they have the largest share of the 3500km+.

According to Eurocontrol the average flight length of 80% of the flights within Europe is 504NM while the average flight length of the flight outside the regions (20%) is 878NM. That means that the average flight time of 80% of the flights in Europe do not exceed an hour. This will leave a maximum of 3 hours for the passenger to arrive from its departing point to the plane and to get from the plane to its final destination, including the processing times at the airport and all the connections with other modes of transport.

This is relevant considering that the cities closest to Europe's busiest airports have between 4 and 46 airfields within 100km of the city centre, for 8 of the 10 cities close to Europe's biggest airports, a single airport handles 80% or more of all the departures within 100km. The situation is nevertheless not homogenous around Europe. In northern Europe, beyond 150 Km the area of influence of the airports begins to overlap, with Köln/Bonn airport 138km from Frankfurt, Brussels International 160km from Amsterdam, etc. But in the South, city separations are wider: Madrid may have the 4th or 5th largest airport 13km from the city centre, but the next airport with more than 100 departures/ day is 290km away, at Valencia.

Technological and operational dimension will be of high relevance to achieve the average 3 hours target time of connection and processing time. However, the **social dimension** of such integration will become very relevant as it may happen that the main impact of an airport on the surrounding community comes not only from aircraft operations but also from ground infrastructure require to access to the airport and to connect the airport with other modes of transport.

Figure 2.42 - Great-circle distance flown by departures from the biggest 528 airports in Europe.

Source: Euro control Trends in Air Traffic Volume 3. A place to stand: Airports in the European network

Figure 2.43. Departures grouped by airport size.

Source: Eurocontrol Trends in Air Traffic Volume 3. A place to stand: Airports in the European network

The Figure 2.44 illustrates the benchmarks discussed for goal 2.

GROUND INFRASTRUCTURE & MULTIMODAL TRANSPORT

Figure 2.44 - Technological, operational, societal/human and network dimension of goal 2 Benchmarks

Reference State in 2010

Three main aspects are addressed to understand the reference state for goal 2 in 2010:

- A. The efficiency of the airport processes.
- B. The airport interconnection and delay propagation.

C. The intermodality.

Airport Efficiency

Air transport depends on a complex network architecture, where several facilities, processes and agents are interrelated and interact with each other. In this large-scale and dynamic system, **airport represent the interconnection nodes that facilitate aircraft distribution through the network and transport model changes for passengers.**

Almost 800 million passengers used EU airports in 2010, a third of the world market, almost three times more than when air traffic was liberalised in the early nineties. However major airports are already congested, and traffic flows are harder and harder to cope with. **In 2010 5 major European airport hubs were at saturation** - operating at full capacity: Düsseldorf, Frankfurt, London Gatwick, London Heathrow, and Milan Linate (*Eurocontrol PRR 2010*). The **EC Action Plan on Airport Capacity** was launched in January 2007, urged by the fear that 60 airports will be heavily congested by 2025. The Eurocontrol Study '*Challenges of Growth 2008*' envisaged that, on continuing 2010 trends, 19 key European airports will be at saturation, including for example, Paris CDG, Warsaw, Athens, Vienna and Barcelona¹. The resulting congestion could mean delays affecting 50% of all passenger and cargo flights. The Table 2.11 illustrates the forecast on airport congestion at 2010.²

Airport	2010	2017	2025	Capacity assumptions
Amsterdam Schiphol	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Assumes annual movement cap raised to 510,000 in November 2010 but no further increase
Dublin	Sufficient capacity most or all day	Sufficient capacity most or all day	Sufficient capacity most or all day	Second runway built when needed
Düsseldorf	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Assumed 10% increase in capacity in 2015 but no further increase
Frankfurt	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Sufficient capacity most or all day	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	New runway (2011) and terminal (2015) allow increases from 83 to 126 movements/hour

² The updated study EUROCONTROL 'Challenges of Growth 2013' (CG13) confirmed and reiterated the capacity challenge identified in previous studies. In the most-likely (capacity constrained) scenario, there will be 50% more flights in 2035 than in 2012. Nearly two million flights will not be accommodated (12% of total demand for travel) because of reduced airport expansion plans. That is equivalent to an estimated 120 million passengers unable to make their return flights (in total, 240 million passengers per year). In addition, by 2035, more than 20 airports will be running at or close to capacity, compared to just three in 2012 causing difficulties for managing the network (so called 'hotspot airports').

London Gatwick	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Assumes no new runway but increase of 2-3 movements/hour on current runway
London Heathrow	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Assumes no third runway, or mixed mode, or relaxation of annual movement cap.
Madrid Barajas	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Assumes ATC improvements increase capacity from 98 to 120 movements/hour by 2020 (increase phased in from 2014)
Milan Linate	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Assumes no amendment to Bersani Decree
Munich	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Sufficient capacity most or all day	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Assume third runway operational by 2017
Palma de Mallorca	Sufficient capacity most or all day	Sufficient capacity most or all day	Sufficient capacity most or all day	Assume additional capacity added when required
Paris CDG	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Assumes increase from 114 to 120 movements/hour by 2015, but no further increase (e.g. fifth runway)
Paris Orly	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Demand exceeds capacity most or all day	Assumes no relaxation of annual slot cap
Rome Fiumicino	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Assume improved ATC allowing 100 movements/hour but no new runway
Vienna	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Demand exceeds capacity during part of day	Assume third runway operational in 2020, initially allowing 80 movements/hour increasing to 90 movements/hour by 2025

Table 2.11 - Forecast airport congestion (SAMPLE AIRPORTS)

Consequently, a significant portion of delay generation occurs at airports, where aircraft connectivity acts as a key driver for delay propagation. Delays have a substantial impact in the schedule adherence of airport and airlines, passenger experience, customer satisfaction and system reliability. **Passengers and luggage processing, as well as “rotation”** (flight cycle through the airport and its surrounding

airspace, from inbound to outbound processes) have a great influence on punctuality and on the operational efficiency of the entire system.

In 2010 quality and efficiency of services at airports was demanding a great improvement. **70% of all delays to flights were caused by problems due to the turnaround of aircraft at airports** (delays caused by airlines or their ground-handlers, airports or other parties involved in the turnaround process) (*Eurocontrol PRR 2010*). Additionally, network disruptions experienced in 2010 have shown the **need for increased coordination of ground operations for European airports and the network as a whole (knock-on effects) so as to ensure continuity of airport operations.**

The unprecedented drop in traffic reduced demand far below planned capacity levels in 2009. The resulting spare capacity in most areas (airlines, airports, ATC) translated in a significant improved on-time performance in 2009. However, **air transport punctuality in Europe in 2010 was the worst recorded since 2001 although traffic was still below 2007 levels** and traffic growth was modest. In December 2010, **the average delay per delayed flight (ADD) for departure** traffic from all causes of delay **was 50 minutes**. This was an increase of 22% compared to December 2009. In addition, the percentage of flights delayed (by 5 minutes or more) went up by 13.4 percentage points to 62.9% in comparison to December 2009. The percentage of flights delayed by more than 15 minutes increased from 29.1% to 41.5%.

Some of the main causes contributing to this poor performance were ANS-related delays, primarily due to industrial actions, and higher than usual weather-related delays (snow, freezing conditions) during winter 2009 and in December 2010. The volcanic ash cloud in April/May 2010 had a limited impact on punctuality, as most of the flights were cancelled. Seasonal weather conditions predominantly affected operations in December, resulting in severe disruption to European traffic with an estimated 35,000 scheduled flight cancellations. Cold weather conditions and snowfall were experienced resulting in a significant increase in the proportion of weather-related delay from 27% to 33%. December was a record month for all causes of delay in comparison to the historically high 2009 figure, with a peak in the average delay per delayed flight seen on the 20th December of 82 minutes. Many European airports suffered from snowfall. Paris, Frankfurt, Munich and London saw disruption, Frankfurt particularly due to a lack of parking stand availability at the airport.

The next Figure 2.45 illustrates airport departure delays in 2010 in comparison with delays in the previous years.

Figure 2.45 - Evolution of airport departure delays in 2010

Source: Eurocontrol CODA Digest: Delays at Ari Transports in Europe December 2010

The **average delay per departure (ADM) from all causes increased by 55% to 31.4 minutes in December 2010 when compared to December 2009**. Regarding arrivals, the average delay per arrival increased by 56% month on month to 32.6 minutes, when compared to December 2009. These delays (Figure 2.46) were a record high for all causes of delay.³

Figure 2.46 - Average delay per movement (all causes) for Arrivals

Source: Eurocontrol CODA Digest: Delays at Ari Transports in Europe December 2010

An analysis of the delay causes and categories (grouped by IATA code) shows (Figure 2.47) an increase (in percentage points) in Reactionary delay of 4.4 points. A small increase in share was also seen in Weather related delay (up 0.9 points). Continuing the 2010 trend there was a decrease observed in Technical and Aircraft Equipment related delay share (down 1.1 points). ATFM weather at destination saw an increase (up 1.3 points).

³ 'All-causes departure delay' is calculated as the difference between the scheduled time of departure (STD) as communicated to the passenger and the actual off-block time (AOBT). In Europe, delay because assignment takes places on the ramp on departure with many airlines applying the IATA delay codes and sub-codes published in the IATA Airport Handling Manual 730 and 731. All-causes delays can be split between primary and reactionary delays. Reactionary delays are delays that are caused by the late arrival of aircraft, crew, passengers or loads from a previous journey. Primary delays are all other delays and occur during the turnaround process of the aircraft. The cost of one minute of tactical delay varies by size of aircraft, but on average is estimated at €79/minute (Ref: University of Westminster for EUROCONTROL PRC, 2004, for EUROCONTROL PRU, 2011).

Figure 2.47 - Primary and reactionary all-cause delay, by IATA code (%).

Source: Eurocontrol CODA Digest: Delays at Ari Transports in Europe December 2010

Finally, the next Figure 2.48 illustrates the causes-7drivers of departure delays. For a better understanding various delays reported were grouped into the following main categories:

- Turn around related delays (non-ATFCM): are primary delays caused by airlines (technical, boarding, etc.), airports (equipment, etc.) or other parties such as ground handlers involved in the turnaround process.

- ANS-related delays: are primary delays resulting from an imbalance between demand and available capacity.
- Weather-related delays (non-ATFCM): This group contains delays due to unfavourable weather conditions including delays due to snow removal or de-icing. Weather-related delays handled by ANS are not included.
- Reactionary delays are secondary delays caused by primary delays on earlier flight legs which cannot be absorbed during the turn-around phase at the airport. Due to the interconnected nature of the network, reactionary delay can propagate throughout the network and therefore have a considerable knock-on effect on subsequent flights.

Figure 2.48 Drivers of departure delays (2007-2010)

Source: Eurocontrol PRR 2010

Beginning the century airports were still a collection of immense infrastructures with a vast array of systems and products that must work and interact in order to keep the airport operating efficiently 24/7 all year around. Airport operations represent a complex system, which involves multiple elements and processes that are interrelated and interact with each other. There are several stakeholders (ATS providers, airlines, airport operators and ground handling companies) involved in the airport environment and they are still communicating in limited ways with each other. Because of this, inefficiencies that hamper productivity and performance can be created when these stakeholders' interface with other departments and external organisations, and any incident may easily travel the network and affect the operation of the airport as a whole.

In 2010 the concept of ACDM start to be applied at major airports to solve the previous issues. **Airport Collaborative Decision Making (ACDM)** is a system that designed by the EUROCONTROL and adopted by European Civil Aviation Conference (ECAC) Transport Ministers in the European Air Traffic Management Strategy to control the overall European airspace and airports^{4,5}. This is a concept that changes the system, hardware, human interactions with software, technology and the culture to understand the operational processes of each related parties (Air Traffic Control, Airport Operation, Pilots, Airlines, CFMU and ground Handling). Thus, enhance the airport efficiency by reducing delays, improving current airport facilities, maximize the capacity of landing allocations and slots as well as utilize the resources⁶. The development of ACDM is based on the historical data that provided by the airport authorities from each airport, by sharing and exchanging information and process would enable the best air traffic performance being implemented at European airports. ACDM is also parallel with AFTM, which is an integration of the SMEAN and SESAR programs.

In 2010 **Munich Airport is the first airport to be considered fully Airport CDM compliant** and has demonstrated the local benefits such as a reduction in average taxi times and an improvement in CFMU CTOT conformance. **Analysis of the impact of Airport CDM on delays has highlighted a room for improvement of 33%-50%**. Such a gain in terms of delay, allows the European targets to be kept in terms of delays. **If Airport CDM were implemented in the main 42 delaying European airports with the same result in performance as Munich has experienced, then an increase in sectors declared capacity could be expected by up to 4%; that corresponds to an increase of 1 or 2 extra aircraft per hour per sector.**⁷

Airport Interconnection and Delay Propagation

Due to the networking nature of Air transport potential incidents, failures and delays (due to service disruption, unexpected events or capacity contains) may propagate throughout the different nodes of the network, making it vulnerable. The situation has led in recent years to system-wide congestion problems and has worsened due to the strong growth in the number of airport operation during the last decades. Broadly, two elements determine the magnitude of delay propagation:

- the primary delay parameters (i.e. time of the day, length of the delay, etc.) and,
- the ability of the air transport system to absorb primary delay (i.e. aircraft and crew utilisation including scheduled block times and turnaround times, airline business model, contingency procedures, turn around efficiency at airports, effectiveness of airport CDM processes, etc.)

Reactionary delays are by definition a network issue and a better understanding of the contribution of airports, airlines and ANS towards those network effects and possible measured to mitigate those effects is desirable. Even though reactionary delays have a great impact on air traffic performance, the research effort to better understand and handle them in practice was limited in the past. One of the most complete studies in 2010 highlights that:

⁴ EUROCONTROL. (2010). *Airport Collaborative Decision Making*. Retrieved from EUROCONTROL on 3rd October 2010

⁵ MUNICH AIRPORT. (2010). *Collaborative Decision Making (CDM) - a new concept*. Retrieved from [Munich Airport](#) on 3rd October 2010

⁶ EUROCONTROL. (2010). *what is Airport CDM*. Retrieved from [EUROCONTROL](#) on 3rd October 2010

⁷ Eighth USA/Europe Air Traffic Management Research and Development Seminar (ATM2009) Airport CDM Network Impact Assesment Eduardo GOÑI MODREGO, Mihai-George IAGARU, Marc DALICHAMPT, Roger LANE EUROCONTROL Experimental Center, Bretigny s/ Orge, FRANCE

- **50 percent (12 minutes) of delays in low-cost operations are reactionary delays. Hub-and-spoke operators have by far the lowest ratio as reactionary delays account for nearly 40 percent of all delays (7 minutes).** Point-to-point operations lie in between the other two with around 45 percent of reactionary delay (9 minutes).
- **The larger the share of aircraft which exceed the scheduled block-to-block time, the less delay can be absorbed in the block-to-block phase.** Buffer time is included in the scheduled block-to-block phase of all types of operation. However, low-cost operators are best positioned to absorb delays in the block-to-block phase.
- **Depending on the airline business model, between 60 and 90 percent of flights exceed the scheduled turn-around time. However, only half as many flights exceed their scheduled turn-around times when additional minutes due the aircraft arriving ahead of its scheduled arrival time are removed.** Low-cost airlines appeared to have only a limited ability to absorb delay in the turnaround phase. Instead, they even added the highest level of new primary delays. Overall, hub-and-spoke and point-to-point carriers are able to absorb approximately the same amount of delay during the turn-around phase, but hub-and-spoke carriers added more new primary delays than point-to-point carriers.
- Irrespective of the airline business model, the time of the day and the length of the delay, **the majority of the root delays can be recovered within the first leg after the root delay occurred.** Those sequences (with one affected leg) accounted for 50 to 60 percent of all the analysed sequences.
- **The analysis of major European airports demonstrates that propagation is stronger in non-hub operations where reactionary delays account for up to 50 percent of total reported delays.**
- **Root delays originating from major European hubs daily effect on average between 30 and 50 other airports within the ECAC area.**

Technological and operational interconnection among the airports in the network is practically null in 2010. The only incipient attempt to interconnection is the Airport CDM initiative. Airport Collaborative Decision Making (A-CDM) involves all airport partners in the tactical phase (i.e. up to 3 hours look-ahead time). It ensures that airport partners get accurate data at the right time in the right place, thus improving shared information as well as the quality of subsequent decisions resulting from improved data.

Intermodality

The airport of the future is conceived as the central link of intermodal transport. Intermodality is understood as the transport of goods and passengers using several transport modes in one trip and involves the inter-coordination of those different transport modes. This coordination is made thanks adequate intermodal infrastructure, and to intermodal agreements concluded by transport operators. Agreements allow for common reservation for the whole trip, coordinated timetables, a common checking, and the certainty to travel to the final destination despite delays faced by one or several transport modes during the trip, etc.

Airport intermodality in Europe in 2010 is the result of **political and financial** actions, **airport connections** and **user's expectation**.

➤ Political and Financial Approach:

At late 90's European Union established guidelines for developing a trans-European transportation network that comprises roads, railways, airports, seaports, inland ports and traffic management systems that serve the entire European Union. National governments, local governments, and private transportation companies—such as airport and rail companies—all take part in the development of intermodal capabilities at airports.

Beginning XXI century, many airports owned or operated by private airport management companies, have taken the lead in planning and funding major intermodal facilities on airport property. For example, **Fraport, a private company that manages Frankfurt's airport, and Deutsche Bahn, the German rail company, invested over 300 million euros in building a station for long-distance and high-speed trains at the Frankfurt airport.** Additionally, some European rail systems are also privately operated. (Germany and France have established private companies to operate their nations' rail systems). However, the national government still takes the lead in planning and funding the building of the overall rail infrastructure, such as dedicated high-speed rail tracks. Once this infrastructure is built, it is then turned over to these private companies that operate and manage this infrastructure. At the Frankfurt airport, Deutsche Bahn and Fraport funded the construction of the long-distance train station, but all the track infrastructure was funded by the German national government. Local governments also are involved in providing intermodal transportation services to airports, with local government-owned transit agencies providing either rail or local bus service to the airport. For example, **the Rhein-Main Verkehrsverbund regional transit system provides 230 daily connections and service to about 4,000 passengers per day from the Frankfurt airport.**⁸ In the past KLM airlines took a 10% share in high speed rail NS in the Netherlands to ensure a high-speed connection to Brussels from Amsterdam airport. Due to the difficulties with the high-speed train connection (the Fyra trains are no longer operational) the share was withdrawn. (Note that trains going east to Germany no longer stop at Schiphol airport either due to lack of passengers).

It is interesting to note that **there is intense cooperation within the same transport mode, for both air and train.** For example, airlines cooperate amongst themselves especially when they are part of the same group as Sky Team, One World or Star Alliance. This enables them to share the codes and provide combined tickets for onward travel with an associated airline at lower prices. The same intra modal agreements have been reached in the rail sector with the Interrail and Eurail passes. In air cargo, providers of parcel and mail services have an integrated transport chain from door to door. These integrator companies combine all transport modes within one company including aircraft, warehouses, vans etc. It seems that intermodal passenger transport (where more independent organizations with different commercial objectives and funding arrangements need to work together) is far more difficult to organize.

➤ User Expectations:

Besides the political strategies and the financial issues, satisfying the customer's needs and assuring a positive and seamless travel experience is central to the success of intermodal passenger transport. Modair project have examined those variables which are relevant from the perspective of the passenger before, during and after the journey and depending on the type of passenger. These variables are numerous and wide ranging; however, a number of key themes have emerged, some of which are cross cutting:

⁸ GAO. Potential Strategies Would Redefine Federal Role in Developing Airport Intermodal Capabilities. 2005

- **Accessibility**, a clearly important requirement for passengers is to easily access reliable, impartial and real time information, both for pre-trip planning and to be kept informed of relevant developments during the journey.
- **Single ticket**, taking the client from start to their final destination without the use of various tickets and the availability of multi-modal check-in facilities, avoiding the passenger having to carry their luggage between the different modes throughout the journey.
- **Confident**, passengers being able to confidently find their way between modes and experiencing a feeling safety and comfort within the spaces they inhabit throughout their journey.
- **Accountability**, where there are a number of transport providers, the issue of accountability and passenger rights is raised, highlighting the need for effective coordination between operators.

All these variables concerning passenger requirements raise some obvious challenges for the transport sector (operators and infrastructure managers) in terms of logistics, operations, infrastructure, organisation and cultural factors etc., particularly with regards to single ticketing, multi-modal check in and the provision of reliable and impartial information.

We revised hereafter the status in the first decade of XXI century (according to ModAir survey) of some of these elements relevant for the users.

- **Intermodal information: Most airports had a simple link on their website to car rental, taxi, bus and rail companies and in some cases time schedules of bus and train connections are provided. None had a customer-oriented approach** where the customer is automatically informed about intermodal connections from arrival at the airport to the final destination and verse versa. There was no intermodal focus for door to door travel. The information was focused on travel from airport to airport. The current set up makes it mandatory for passengers to visit several websites to plan a door to door trip. Websites do not provide information about transit times between different travel modes, nor real time information about delays in ground transportation.
- **Single ticket and other services:** Some airlines offered single tickets or combined tickets to passengers that allow a multi modal travel by plane and train. Examples are:
 - TGVair; A combined ticket offered for rail/ flight connections by TGV in France to Paris Charles de Gaulle and Orly.
 - Air and Rail: a combined ticket between Brussels and Paris CDG airport.
 - Air and Rail: a combined ticket between Brussels and Amsterdam.
 - Rail and Fly: the opportunity to buy an airline ticket and a train ticket at the same time in Germany

Besides these ticketing possibilities there are services for luggage drop-off for airline passengers at remote locations. In Vienna for example passengers can check in and drop off their luggage in down town Vienna as a service by selected airlines.

- **Bus connections.** Low cost Carriers often use regional airports to avoid the high fees that need to be paid at hub airports. As these airports are located outside the big cities, LCC cooperate with a direct bus connection to these cities. There is no single ticket, but the time schedule of these busses matches the departure and arrival times of the LCC aircraft.

In bigger cities, some airlines own their own bus company that offer a bus-link to the downtown city. An example is Air France offering an Air France bus service to downtown Paris. The passenger needs to buy a separate ticket for that service. Another service that is worth mentioning is the possibility to

check-in at the US customs at Dublin and Shannon airports, thus avoiding long queues when entering the USA.

➤ **Airports Accessibility and Connectivity.**

During the first decade of XXI century there were more than 1270 airports and 1230 aerodromes in Europe, 543 airports of them serving commercial air transport. There were also a number of new airports planned, constructed or reclassified from General Aviation to commercial operations. Many regional airports served seasonal traffic. The Low-Cost Carriers that operated on these airports served leisure travel during the summer (and in some cases only during the winter). The distances flown by LCC are in general beyond 600 - 800 km point to point. Low Cost Carriers had in 2010 a substantial market share of about 40% in European air travel.

Regarding the **accessibility**, all of them could be accessed by car. 97%, 525 airports out of 543 were being served by taxi. 70%, 379 airports were served by regular bus services. Only 10%, 56 airports were served by local rail and light rail/tram to nearby cities or regions. At that moment there were a few high-speed rail lines (HST) in Europe, focused on massive volumes of passengers and connections between major cities.

The interconnectivity at European airports is often still limited to urban transport, with very few (high-speed) train stations located at airports. Some of the existing intermodal links do not fully meet the passengers' expectations, leading to low usage. As an example, in the UK train stations at regional airports have been closed due to the small number of passengers that made use of the facility.

Air/rail intermodality seems to offer promising opportunities for the future of the transport system by limiting the isolated use of road or air traffic (both responsible for congestion and air pollution) and providing combined trips, generally with rail. However, so far intermodal agreements are not very numerous in Europe. Funding and the possibility of signing exclusive agreements between airlines and train operator are essential enablers to foster intermodality.

In the first decade of the XXI century there are so far few examples where intermodality at airport impacted air traffic. However, the number of these examples could increase with the level of airport intermodality, and the air traffic level and distribution could then be affected significantly.

Very high-speed train point to point connections (travelling at 250km/hour) can be more time efficient than air transport over a distance up to about 600 km, although load factors are lower than in aviation (85% on average). Experience has shown that indeed there is some **substitution** taking place between air travel and HST up to that distance for example in France and Spain. In these countries regional flights have been discontinued in favour of rail travel. Eurocontrol is expecting that the annual growth in the number of European flights by 2030 may be reduced from 3.9% by 0.7% to 3.2% if all High-Speed Rail plans are realized (assuming that the European economy will grow at an average 2.7% per annum). High speed rail plans might have resulted in partial substitution of regional air travel by high speed train especially in Spain, France, UK and Denmark. A modest substitution effect may be expected in Finland, Italy, Sweden, Poland, Croatia, Germany, Greece and Portugal if all HST plans are executed. However due to the economic crisis some high-speed rail planning were put on hold.

However according to Eurocontrol and also ModAir connections analysis, HST connections are not expected to affect long distance flights and most of the Low-Cost Carrier operations as well as the intercontinental flights. Rather than focusing on substitution, the focus should be on benefits of directly connecting air travel to high speed rail travel:

- By substitution freeing airport slots, which is relevant for crowded HUB airports where runway capacity and slots are scarce;
- Creating additional airspace capacity which is scarce in Europe due to the fact that large parts of the airspace are still reserved for military operations;
- Enlarging the catchment area of HUB airports;
- Enabling airports to be interconnected via high speed rail, allowing a better distribution of air traffic over different airports.

The next Figure 2.49 summarises the Europe map of existing & planned rail connections to airports. (Source ACI June 2012)

Figure 2.49 - EUROPE map of existing & planned rail connections to airports
ACI June 2012

Progress Up-to-Now

Airport Efficiency and Airport Interconnection

Recent R&D projects and initiatives have concentrated its efforts on the development of (at different TRL) concepts, tools, technologies and solutions to improve the turnaround process at the airport. Hereafter are described some research and development initiatives developed during the period 2010-2017 that might contribute highly to the improvement of the Airport efficiency.

➤ Airport Operations Centres (APOC) and the Airport Operations Plan (AOP)

Given that it is essential to integrate airports more closely into the network, collaborative concepts are being developed under the SESAR programme, building on the success of the A-CDM (airport collaborative decision-making) project. Two of these concepts are Airport Operations Centres (APOC) and the Airport Operations Plan (AOP) on the airport side, as well as the collaborative Network Operations Plan (NOP) on the network side.

An APOC manages an airport's operations in both normal and exceptional conditions. The AOP is a rolling plan that covers the pre-tactical and tactical phases by providing dynamic data updates as an operational situation evolves. Through the timely two-way exchange of relevant airport and network information between airports and the Network Manager, AOP-NOP integration improves both the airport's and the network's operational performance. Situational awareness is heightened, and issues can be contained before they can affect other parts of the network. The exchange with the Network Manager through the AOP-NOP integration delivers local throughput status information earlier than was previously the case. This information can also be shared with other airports, airspace users and ANSPs (air navigation service providers), so facilitating improved decision-making. This is expected to improve network predictability and add to the improvements brought about with A-CDM.

2017 have seen how 10 mayor airports in Europe have implemented these advanced concepts: Frankfurt, London Heathrow, Paris Charles de Gaulle, Paris Orly, Amsterdam Schiphol, Barcelona - El Prat, Madrid - Barajas, Palma de Mallorca, Brussels and Stockholm Arlanda.

➤ INTERACTION (INnovative TEchnologies and Researches for a new Airport Concept towards Turnaround coordinatION)

INTERACTION project has developed and validated (at Athens Airport) a solution that integrates the information on the different airport processes within the same system, which has allowed to analyse the evolution of each process by itself and to predict the impact of on disruptions on one process on the overall turnaround process. The system integrates a Centralised Information Platform, Mobile application for passengers and a Handling processes tool. Additionally, the project has dealt with some advanced solutions for airport process improvement:

1. Unification of passenger and baggage process and Pooling of Equipment (GSE);
2. Cargo portal solution: the concept consists of a support platform for the cargo process which was developed in a prototype;
3. Machine Learning for Estimation of Landing Time solution;
4. Time efficient passenger and baggage processes able to move passengers up until 2 m/s;
5. A new gate concept aimed at reducing the movement and space of the apron operations that implies the standardisation of the gate design for aircraft type C such as Airbus A-320 family;
6. Conceptualising a passenger boarding bridge that can dock not only the aircraft front door but also the rear door, by going over the aircraft wing;
7. Fleet, mobile vehicles and equipment management;
8. Aircraft Navigation lights powered by tow tractor converter;
9. Feasibility study for more electrical tractor;
10. Assisted/Automated cargo loader to aircraft docking;
11. Slot assignment for passenger security screening;
12. Prediction of consumed potable water and catering goods;
13. A collaborative decision-making enhanced framework was developed which aims to avoid the delay propagation between airport sub-processes satisfying all stakeholder business models.
14. Aircraft Navigation lights powered by towbarless tractor;

15. Aircraft RFID tag identification;
16. Communication between aircraft and airport;
17. New concepts related to passenger boarding methods via passenger boarding bridges were explored and were left at concept maturity level.

➤ Total Airport Management

The full integration between Airport and Network Operations has still to be achieved (airport performance strongly depends on the performance of the Network). Management of predicted airport performance deterioration therefore needs to be aligned with the Network. Collaborative recovery procedures and support tools in coordination with all the relevant ATM stakeholders are required to facilitate the pro-active management of predicted performance deteriorations. Total Airport Demand and Capacity Balancing processes and tools require further integration with the execution tools (Arrivals and Departure Management systems and Advanced Surface Movement Guidance & Control Systems) and resource allocation planning tools (Stand/Gate Allocation Planner). Airport landside/airside performance monitoring and management processes need to be integrated refining as well the turnaround monitoring within the Airport Operations Centre (APOC) in coordination with the Airspace Users. Environmental impacts and all aspects of de-icing are currently not integrated into the planning and execution timeframes of the Airport Operations Plan (AOP). Impact assessment tools available to the APOC need to better integrate information about MET forecast uncertainty. Post-Operations Analysis processes, support tools and reporting capabilities need to be developed. This project has developed solutions that are expected to have a very positive impact on the Network through:

- A performance-driven airport through KPIs monitoring and detection of deviations, collaborative decisions using support tools and what-if functions, post-operations analysis used as learning process. A Better situational awareness through SWIM information sharing, enabling provision and reception of Airport CDM data including MET and AIM.
- A significant increase in the predictability, efficiency, environmental sustainability and flexibility of airport operations;
- Better use of existing airport capacity;
- Increased safety in the airport environment due to reduced uncertainty of operations and reduced congestion through better planning.

➤ META CDM

META CDM project has worked on laying the foundations for an extended CDM concepts that integrates Landside and Airside CDM united into the concept of Total Airport CDM. The benefits of this concept can be split into two areas.

- If the aviation system is operating normally or with mild delays passengers will receive more information that enables them to streamline their journey and to reduce uncertainty; for example, better estimates of when to leave home for the airport based on real-time information about traffic, check-in and security queues.
- In case of a major disruption with long delays and/or cancelled flights, passengers benefit from earlier and better information about any changes to their flight, and a greater range of alternative options if their flight is cancelled.

➤ TITAN Project

Titan project works to improve the turnaround process and expect to generate 2 % of operational cost reduction.

➤ Fantassy Project

Fantasy project investigated the design of the aircraft as a combination of a “carrier” and a “passenger pod” proposing 2 preliminary aircraft configurations and design studies: one that employs external attachment of the pods (EPC-External Pod Configuration) and one that accepts the pods internally (IPC-Internal Pod Configuration).

The project studied how the pod system contributes to reduce the turn-around time of the aircraft thus minimizing waiting time for the passenger but most importantly increase the aircraft/passenger throughput of the airport. As pods can be loaded in a convenient time before the in-bound aircraft is ready for take-off, the whole process is not sequential and thus less prone to delays.

It also studied how the pod system might contribute to a seamless intermodal travel finding that the most effective way to accomplish that is to develop dedicated automated lines to carry the pods between the airport and city centre terminals where crossing to local transport can be easier. This option facilitates both security and operational requirements.

Intermodality

ModAir project has identified R&D needs to favour intermodality finding that:

- Regarding integrated ticketing and luggage transfer there is a need of an updated and further detailed study on the real latent demand for integrated ticketing through a broader research on passengers’ demand.
- Regarding air-rail experiences in Europe there is a need to continue with the recently initiated cooperation between stakeholders. Although some of these experiences target their local markets and it would be difficult to broaden their scope (e.g. Eurostar from London to Paris which is directly using IATA codes for its stations and operating through GDS), it is remarkable that cooperation between stakeholders has begun. Agreements on the delays, railways available in GDSs, cooperation in situations like when volcano Eyjafjalla paralyzed the European air traffic, and other experiences make the final solution closer.
- Regarding stakeholders’ perceptions, passengers are mainly willing for better information related to intermodality, comprehensibility of the reservation systems (including better prices when booked air and rail are together), flexibility on their bookings and a secure framework with clear operators’ liability conditions. On the other side, from the supply point of view, there are disparities in their opinions. Some think that air-rail integration is already solved, and everybody should use the alternative they are providing (these still demur appearing in a common information system with competing means of transport). Others state that only a common agreement is needed and, consequently, all agents should be involved in a global working group. Most of them are enthusiastic but only if the demand for air-rail can be proved first. Greater market potential is expected for the long term.
- Regarding technologies covering intermodality (and in particular, air-rail intermodality) they are already available however, no one has been placed yet as the global solution for the air-rail market, one strives to make available developments compatible.

- Main challenges to overcome in order to achieve the desired framework for intermodality relate to standardisation and funding, but also to remote check-in and luggage handling and schedule and delays.
- Regarding standardisation issues the project focus on standardisation among railway services procedures from different companies is envisioned, and standardisation between air and rail must be addressed. The main targets within standardisation are:
 - A neutral display of air-rail alternatives over the air-air ones;
 - The provision of a common and global nomenclature system for the stations description like airport IATA codes;
 - Discussion about those rail trips with no need of reservation, or the booking of those where one seat can be booked from a to b and the same seat from b to c;
 - Harmonisation of journey classes and social discounts;
 - The need to ensure data sharing, open access and data quality;
 - A branding strategy to avoid different nomenclatures for similar services.
- Regarding luggage transfers, knowing what is happening to their baggage is one of passengers' top three priorities (Passenger IT Trends Survey 2013). Access to baggage information wherever actors are located (including on mobile devices) has to be developed. By the end of 2016, over 60% of airlines expect to be sending bag location updates and enabling missing bag reports via smartphones (Airline IT Trends Survey 2013). Efficient and cheap tag technologies (paper, RFID, Bluetooth...) must be developed, with standardized tags and data formats between modes.
- On the funding side, it will be very important to quantify the existing latent demand for the air-rail integration. This demand will determine the expected benefits for the different stakeholders in comparison with their actual demand figures. Also, it will be essential to achieve the proper cooperation between stakeholders to discuss the details of the funding based on their particular business plans. Furthermore, most of them believe that EU funding may prove to be valuable regarding, at least, the investments in standardisation.

Predictions Up-to-2025 and Evolutionary Progress Up to 2050

How To optimize An Airport

Today's globalized world would not be possible without air transport. Airlines respond to a growing demand for air transport by adding new routes and offering more connectivity to their customers. As a result, air traffic volume is growing at average rate of about 5% per year, which is equivalent to traffic tripling in 30 years. This impressive growth has also led to a number of big challenges that today's aviation is facing:

- Maintain and improve mobility despite more and more congested airspace and airports.
- Improve competitiveness and cost-efficiency of air transport.
- Address aviation's environmental footprint in terms of greenhouse gases, noise and air quality.
- Maintain and improve the safety level of aviation.
- Provide hassle-free security processes while maintaining at least the current security level.

First of all, the main objective is to optimize airports; analysing the way the different media act, times, delays, connections, etc. It is about getting an airport as efficient as possible. The critical elements for the 2050 airports are the following:

- Air traffic management will be related to a network of airports rather than local and individual airports.
- Landside and airside components need to be re-thought and **intermodal** means of transport described.

Connections between hubs and secondary airports will be possible by means of efficient and environmentally friendly public transport but will also include an optimised network for private transportation that will enable the efficient, safe use of personal ground transport. Ships may be used to connect secondary airports, depending on their location.

Air transport will include current-configuration aircraft, plus other actors such as personal air transportation vehicles or aircraft with passengers pre-loaded into standard fuselage boxes. In addition, different types of runways as well as take-off and landing assistance systems will be available to provide services for conventional take-off and landing aircraft, short-take-off and landing air vehicles or convertible vehicles. Airport networks should be designed to accommodate them all.

Interconnections within this network will be provided by multimodal transport, including high-speed trains for the national or international network, trains, subways, tramways or suburban trains at regional airports, electric ground vehicles, environmentally friendly ships or even air-buses.

The airport will use new technologies to make passengers' stay in the airport as short and comfortable as possible. One of the most important challenges will be achieving public confidence in automation, although this will demand significant advances in technology. Automation will mean that users are informed about the current status of their journey and alternative options, periodically or on demand. Information points will be distributed around the terminals and interactive devices embedded in transport systems so that passengers can access travel information at any time using smart phones or interactive panels/screens situated along the intermodal transport network.

The airport landside is the interface between air transport service providers and the passengers. Therefore, future landside infrastructure and services must focus on passenger's needs and comfort. Future airport terminals will be much less time consuming for the passenger and they will have short walking distances for passengers. Moving walkways and individual automated guided vehicle systems will cover long distances conveniently and quickly between different terminals and within large terminals.

Passengers will have information available at all times, providing a comprehensive choice of the modes of transport, prior to travel as well as in the case of rescheduling or unforeseen disruptions.

In terms of operations, by 2050, the Single European Sky (SES) four-dimensional (4D) air traffic management system will have been fully implemented. It will be important to provide airport networks with the capability to coordinate/ manage ground operations with 4D airborne operations.

In the short term, the airside will take advantage of improvements resulting from the SES programme and will evolve towards higher automation. The airport infrastructure will include revolutionary architecture adapted to any new aircraft configuration and propulsion mode (i.e. blended wing body and new fuels, such as hydrogen or biofuels).

New airport layouts and runway configurations could overcome weather restrictions and maintain capacity. A revolutionary airside development could be a circular runway, adapted to any wind

direction, to increase capacity. Associated to a terminal focused in the 'circle', such runways would enable short, fuel-saving taxiing along radii adapted for capacity and safety.

Considering weather operations, revolutionary concepts for the increase of capacity independent of weather conditions include:

- On-board equipment allowing landing with significant tail or crosswinds.
- On-board equipment to display weather information and airport infrastructure in low visibility conditions.
- Fans or other equipment to blow fog and wake turbulence away.
- Ground-based runway heating.

Efficient and Connected Airport

In this context, it is necessary to know about **intermodality**.

A main goal for the future intermodal transport system is to reduce dependence on the automobile as the major mode of ground transportation and increase use of public transport, especially in the case of the future air transport system.

Intermodality can be envisaged at several levels, from local public transport to international connections:

City centres and suburban areas have to be accessible using the tramway or subway connecting with railway stations located on the airport landside.

- At regional level, connections to a high-speed train is a strong advantage for an airport's attractiveness if it is rapid and serves the nearby cities.
- For national / international connections
 - Integration of airports within a regional/national railway network or other future modes of public transport.
 - National railway stations at airports must be part of the landside, where the passenger journey starts with passenger check-in and luggage deposit.
 - High-speed train connections to connect regional megacities.
 - Connections between regional airports to major hubs with high-speed train as an alternative to short-haul air services, releasing slots and relieving airport congestion.

One of the most important things in relation to interoperability is the **airport network**. The airports of 2050 will be integrated into a network of air, ground and even water transport that will enhance capacity and make transportation more efficient, one of the goals that are tried to achieve. The airport network (Figure 2.50) will be mainly composed of hubs connected to secondary airports that will provide services to a greater number of users and operators.

Figure 2.50 - The airport network. Air Transport System 2050 Vision to Planning for Research and Innovation. EREA

The airport landside should provide inter-terminal shuttles to provide convenient, fast and reliable services for the passenger and luggage. Automatic subway trains and/or tramways should be considered instead of buses.

In addition, CDM airport concept, which is explained in the goal 1, is another new idea directly related with airport network. CDM airports will improve connection between airports. For this reason, it is considered appropriate to include it in this section.

New Ticket Initiative

Regarding the connectivity of the airports, IATA proposes a new industry-led initiative intends to replace the multiple and rigid booking, ticketing, delivery and accounting methods, using the data communications advances made possible by the implementation of the New Distribution Capability. ONE Order, the name of this initiative, aims to modernize the order management process in the airline industry. This is the concept of a single Customer Order record, holding all data elements obtained and required for order fulfilment across the air travel cycle, such as customer data, order items, payment and billing information, fulfilment data and status.

Also, One Order will result in the gradual disappearance of multiple reservation records as well as e-ticket/EMD (Electronic Miscellaneous Document) concepts to be replaced by a single reference travel document.

A new standardized and expandable reference will become the single access point for customer orders by third parties (interline partners, distribution channels, ground handling agents and airport staff, among others). Thanks to this new project, it will provide easier product delivery and settlement between airlines and their partners with one simplified and standardized order management process.

All parties will follow a single process to service customers throughout their entire product purchase and delivery experience.

Likewise, One Order will enable "network airlines" and "low-cost carriers" to interact and provide combined services to customers. Through a new optimized process, both airline communities will be able to manage customers in a seamless and homogeneous manner despite having different business models and operational environments.

Due to this new kind of “single ticket”, it will provide multiple advantages for all airspace users.

Alternatives to Resolving the Expected Demand

According to the data provided, it is expected that by 2030, and therefore by 2050, demand will continue to grow. This will mean new measures in capacity.

Consequently, the alternatives proposed by EUROCONTROL are the following:

- Growth of airports. It will be necessary to increase the capacity of airports by increasing the number of runways or the size of these.
- Using the nearby airports, wherever possible. In this case, reference is made to those geographical areas that have a main airport and that should use their nearest airports.
- New airports. In the case of it cannot manage the great demand that is expected to be achieved, it will be necessary to have new airport infrastructures.

Also, EUROCONTROL proposes several mitigation measures, which have been explained in detail in the goal 1 that they affective directly in the airport’s mobility. Consequently, these measures are (Figure 2.51):

Figure 2.51 – Mitigation Measures for Traffic Capacity

Innovation Technologies

Every day, millions of hours are wasted on the road worldwide. In many global megacities the problem is quite serious.

On-demand aviation, has the potential to radically improve urban mobility, giving people back time lost in their daily commutes. For all these reasons, it tries to introduce new technologies in order to get the best option to go from home to the airport. Urban air transportation will use three-dimensional airspace to alleviate transportation congestion on the ground.

A possibility in the use of **VTOL** (Vertical Take-off and Landing) aircraft and electric aircraft that take off and land vertically. They will enable rapid, reliable transportation between suburbs and cities and, ultimately, within cities.

Several companies, with different design approaches, are working to make electric VTOL aircraft a reality. The closest equivalent technology in use today is the helicopter that has longer ranges, is more polluting and may have higher costs.

The VTOL aircraft that uses electric propulsion (Figure 2.52) has zero local operational emissions and will likely be quiet enough to operate in cities without disturbing the neighbours. It is claimed that at flying altitude, noise from advanced electric vehicles will be barely audible. In fact, rotor noise is a common feature. Even during take-off and landing, the noise will be comparable to existing background noise. These VTOL designs are also claimed safer than today’s helicopters because VTOLs

will not need to be dependent on any single part to stay airborne and will ultimately use autonomy technology to significantly reduce operator error.

Figure 2.52 - Aurora's VTOL aircraft use eight lifting propellers for vertical take-off, and a cruise propeller and wing to transition to high-speed forward cruise.

To reduce emissions, fossil fuels can be replaced by electrical power generated by more environmentally-friendly methods. A main challenge is the provision of the large amounts of energy needed to operate all of the vehicles and to guarantee its availability at all times and under all weather conditions. Power generation using solar or geothermal systems needs to be integrated into the future airport infrastructure.

➤ Development of Infrastructure

The development of infrastructure to support an urban VTOL network will likely have significant cost advantages over heavy-infrastructure approaches such as roads, rail, bridges and tunnels.

It has been proposed that the repurposed tops (Figure 2.53) of parking garages, existing helipads, and even unused land surrounding highway interchanges could form the basis of an extensive, distributed network of vertiports (VTOL hubs with multiple take-off and landing pads, as well as charging infrastructure) or single-aircraft vertistops (a single VTOL pad with minimal infrastructure). As costs for traditional infrastructure options continue to increase, the lower cost and increased flexibility provided by these new approaches may provide compelling options for cities and states around the world.

Furthermore, VTOLs do not need to follow fixed routes. Trains, buses, and cars all funnel people from A to B along a limited number of dedicated routes, exposing travellers to serious delays in the event of a single interruption. VTOLs, by contrast, can travel toward their destination independently of any specific path, making route-based congestion less prevalent.

The economics of manufacturing VTOLs will become more similar to automobiles than aircraft. At first, VTOL vehicles are likely to be very expensive, but because the ridesharing model amortizes the vehicle cost efficiently over paid trips, the high cost should not end up being prohibitive to getting started.

And once the ridesharing service commences (air taxi), a positive feedback loop should ensure that ultimately reduces costs and the prices for all users. As the total number of users increases, the utilization of the aircraft increases as well. Logically, this continues with the pooling of trips to achieve higher load factors, and the lower price feeds back to drive more demand. This increases the volume of aircraft required, which in turn drives manufacturing costs down.

Recently, technology advances have made it practical to build this new class of VTOL aircraft.

Furthermore, in order to reduce emissions, the terminals could have large solar panels on the roof or on airfield areas not used for aircraft or ground vehicles. Wind farms could generate the necessary energy for offshore airports.

Figure 2.53 - Top of an eight-story downtown parking garage converted to vertiport capable of supporting 12 VTOLs. Source UBER Elevate.

➤ Aircraft Performance

There is a burgeoning VTOL aircraft ecosystem, and a number of companies that are already developing and flying early vehicle prototypes, such as Zee, Aero, Joby Aviation or Airbus. The following pictures (Figure 2.54 and 2.55) shows some of this kind of aircraft:

Figure 2.54 - Joby S2

Figure 2.55 - Airbus A3 Vahana

Aircraft engines can be shut down, leading to reduced fuel consumptions and emissions. Such vehicles could be driven autonomously and fully automated.

The VTOLs envisioned as serving within a ridesharing network ("air taxis") will need to address four primary barriers to commercial feasibility: safety, noise, emissions, and vehicle performance. The two most important technologies to overcome these challenges are Distributed Electric Propulsion (DEP) and autonomous operation technologies.

VTOLs will be an affordable form of daily transportation for the masses, even less expensive than owning a car. Even though small aircraft and helicopters are of similar size, weight, and complexity to a car, they cost about 20 times more.

In addition, VTOL operations will involve the ability to take off with a rapid climb at a steep glide path angle to reach a cruising altitude up to a few thousand feet, then decelerate to land vertically at the end of the trip. There will likely be a limited need to hover for durations not exceeding one minute, with most vertical take-off and landing transitions taking place in approximately 30 seconds.

In this case, it should be noticed the following aircraft characteristics:

- Speed and range;
- Battery requirements;
- Payload;
- Autonomy (autonomous systems can be introduced). VTOL autonomy is likely to be implemented over time, as users and regulators become more comfortable with the technology and see statistical proof that autonomy provides greater levels of safety than human pilots. To fast-forward to the safest possible operational state for VTOL vehicles, network operators will be interested in the path that realizes full autonomy as quickly as possible.

➤ Applicable Regulation

One of the most important point to keep in mind is safety. Therefore, concerning the regulations applicable to this project, all aspects related to the safety of operations must be considered.

To understand the path to improving safety for urban air transportation, it is necessary to understand the root causes of historical crashes. The main causes of air accidents are due to pilot error described, controlled flight into terrain, mid-air collisions, and loss of control.

Thanks to the VTOLs, whose will necessarily make use of digital fly-by-wire systems and the will adapt these systems to include pilot aids, it will reduce significantly failure modes attributable to pilot error. Pilot aids will evolve over time into full autonomy, which will likely have a marked positive impact on flight safety.

In order to improve VTOL safety beyond that of cars, we must consider the complexity of controlling multiple propulsion motors.

Rather than physically commanding operation of engines and control surfaces, the pilot establishes a desired trajectory which the vehicle follows. Direct mechanical control workload is greatly reduced, leaving more of the pilot's attention for situational awareness, and this eliminates the need for pilot judgement in planning and executing vehicle state manoeuvres to achieve a desired trajectory.

The use of DEP (Distributed Electric Propulsion) combined with autonomy provides the opportunity for the fully digitally controlled fly-by-wire control system to interact across digital systems without complex analogy or mechanical interfaces. Digital data across each element of the propulsion system is managed through redundant master flight controllers, from battery cell voltage state of charge to motor temperatures that permit optimization of the system performance and health.

Distributed propulsion provides not only redundancy, but also the potential for additional control robustness to be designed into the aircraft system such that any component can fail gracefully, enabling a controlled landing.

The VTOL safety is also improving with new creative ideas such as whole vehicle parachutes that can be deployed in an emergency to safely bring the vehicle to the ground.

First, VTOL aircraft are new from a certification standpoint with Agusta AW609 as the precursor. The progress with certification of new aircraft concepts has historically been very slow, but this process is changing in a way that could accelerate things significantly.

Before VTOLs can operate in any country, they will need to comply with regulations from aviation authorities; the US Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and European Aviation Safety Agency

(EASA), who regulate most of the world's aviation activity. Cooperation between the FAA and EASA has resulted in reciprocal arrangements so an aircraft approved in one authority can be flown in another. Despite the pilot training and commercial operator certification vary by country, the requirements are similar.

Developing a certification path involves a number of steps:

First the regulatory authority and the manufacturer have to agree on the certification basis. This is the set of rules that will apply to the particular aircraft. Then the regulator and the manufacturer must agree how to determine the compliance of the vehicle with the certification basis. Next, the manufacturer demonstrates the compliance of the vehicle to the standards accepted by the regulator to obtain type certification; this is an iterative process.

Following type certification, manufacturing can begin while the manufacturer seeks a production certificate to demonstrate the capability of producing many copies of that aircraft to the same standards.

Before an aircraft is produced for commercial use, it is given a special airworthiness certificate in the experimental category for research and development.

Traditionally, the end-to-end certification process (type and production) takes about two to three years for a type certificate, plus another year for a new production certificate for a simple case. However, the introduction of a new type of aircraft requires a new certification basis, developed in parallel with the type certificate, and this could extend the end-to-end certification process to 4 to 8 years.

Fortunately, thanks to the new established standards, the process of developing new regulations (required for the certification of new electric VTOLs) has been accelerated, and the community assumes the responsibility of developing the certification base and then it will present it for adoption by the regulator.

The following Figure 2.56 shows a time estimate in relation to infrastructure, aircraft and the necessary regulations to start up the vertiports project:

Figure 2.56 – Some expectations on Vertiports

The most optimistic expectation (Figure 2.57) from one of the first companies in this sector of urban aviation, **McFly**, is that next year they will have the first two-seat test vehicles.

They want to start the construction of the necessary infrastructures in strategically chosen cities in 2019 and also use vehicles with 4 seats. And finally, in 2020, operate in large non-European cities such as Dallas, Abu Dhabi and Dubai. Entire fleets are operated through block chain, which will facilitate the operation to customers.

Figure 2.57 McFly road map of the expectation

The most vocal and optimistic proponents of air taxi are global taxi operators like UBER.

2.4 Overall Ground Plus Air Travel Time

****Flightpath 2050 goal 4: 90% of passengers within Europe are able to complete their journey, door to door within 4 hours. Passenger and freight are able to transfer seamlessly between transport modes to reach the final destination smoothly, predictably and on time*.***

The goal 4 (section 2.4) is a combination of all other goals 1,2,3,5 (sections 2.1, 2.2, 2.3 and 2.5) in the same set. Air travel times can vary significantly in Europe, from 1 hour in central Europe (Paris-Frankfurt) to 4 hours between extremities of the continent (Lisbon-Bucharest). Assuming that most flights do not exceed 2 hours, leaves within the four-hour total time frame, 1 hour to travel to and from the airport and go through airport services. This objective is achievable if all elements of the chain perform nominally: (i) no take-off queue, no holding pattern at landing, no major weather or ATM disruptions; (ii) efficient check-in, passport and security checks; (iii) fast luggage handling; (iv) efficient airport ground movements and operations; (v) uncongested local transport to and from home or work.

The Goals 3 and 4 are closely related and addressed as three Key Topics: 2.5 to 2.7.

KEY TOPIC T2.5 – AIR TRANSPORT AND OTHER MOBILITY CHOICES

Introduction

Goal 4 was defined in Flightpath 2050 as “90% of travellers within Europe are able to complete their journey, door-to-door within 4 hours. Passengers and freight are able to transfer seamlessly between transport modes to reach the final destination smoothly, predictably and on time”.

Comparing the scope in both Flightpath 2050 and SRIA it can be stated that both proposals are coherent themselves. It is a key factor in air transport development that the total travel time decreases substantially when passengers travel by plane. This key factor is not only focused on fulfilling

passenger's requirements but also in competing with other transport modes that have gained market share in short haul trips (about or below 700km).

For example, since the 1980s, high speed rail (HSR) has become an important competitor to airlines, presenting railway transport in a new form and notably improving the quality of the service offered. Focusing in Spain, this problem has come a reality since the launch of AVE (acronym for Spanish High Speed) in 1992 when it began to operate the route Madrid-Seville. During the last 25 years the number of passengers has sharply increased reaching, for example, 3.23 million of passengers on the Madrid-Seville route in 2016 [1] which supposes more than 89% of the market share against the air transport on this route. This also happens on the Madrid-Barcelona route which has reached 7.4 million of passengers in 2016, meaning a 62% of the market share against the air transport. These differences between air transport and high-speed rail are due to the total travel time spending by the passengers in each transport mode. For example, whilst the Madrid-Seville route duration by high speed rail are approximately 2 hours and 30 minutes, the Madrid-Seville route duration by plane is approximately 1 hour. However, the total time that passengers must spend if they travel by plane increases so that it could take approximately over 3 hours. This huge difference between the actual travel duration and the total travel time is since airports are usually far away from city centres and that airports processes are not fast enough hence passengers have to be at the airport at least 2 hours before of the estimated time of departure.

Therefore, it has been noticed that new developments concerning the optimization of the total travel time in air transport should be done in order to allow reaching the objectives stated in goal 4.

Benchmarks

Allowing passengers to be able to complete their journey to their destination within 4 hours is a difficult task that includes a cluster of key factors to be improved. Since the beginning of the air transport expansion in the 1990s until nowadays, all the systems and infrastructures related to air transport have been involved in a steady process of improvement. Some examples of this developments have been the construction of new runways in airports that needed more capacity to accommodate the growth of flights or the implementation of new navigation systems on the aircraft. Besides, this growth of passengers set a new desire of improving the connection of the airports with the city centres, developing other transport modes like underground or train. Besides, other issues related to the air transport capacity like airport ground infrastructure and air traffic management should be also considered. However, as it will be studied in other goals like goal 1, 2 or 5, it has not been considered in this document.

Nowadays, airports have evolved to become intermodal nodes where passengers can arrive at the airport in several ways. However, most of these ways make passengers spend on average, using Madrid as example, more than 30 minutes to get to the airport. In this manner, it would be interesting to develop the current transport modes both taxi and public transport, infrastructures included. Researching new ways to get to the airports from the city centres nevertheless would be the first key to actually reduce the travel duration. Relating to that, it would be interesting taking into account new developments that are being made in unmanned aircraft and the systems that would allow them to flight in the airspace over the cities and near the airports.

For example, several companies are researching new ways to transport people. One of this breakthrough technologies in the use are the VTOLs (Vertical Take Off and Landing Aircraft) which consist of a new concept of unmanned aircraft designed specifically to transport people. As example, UBER is currently researching it, known as UBER Elevate [2], in order to implement it in the near future.

These VTOLs could allow to carry people from “veliports” (Figure 2.58) placed somewhere in the cities to others “veliports” placed as nearest as possible to the airports.

Figure 2.58 - Example of “veliport” concept designed by UBER [2]

In this manner, it is essential to involve both top manufacturer companies such as Airbus or Boeing and also small companies in order to develop successfully these VTOLs, which will likely be developed across a number of different speed and range capabilities. A VTOL optimized for shorter trips (less than 50 miles) won’t require as much speed as a VTOL capable of meeting the needs of longer distance commuters. As example, Airbus is developing a new VTOL concept named as “Vahana” (Figure 2.59) with a flight range about 50 miles, seeing it as being used by everyday commuters as a cost-comparable replacement for short-range urban transportation like cars or trains.

Figure 2.59. “Vahana” VTOL concept by Airbus

Therefore, also a new regulatory framework may be necessary concerning new UAVs, VTOLs and new ATC systems. This new framework should be assessed in order to handle this exponential increase in complexity, with low altitude operations being managed through new concept systems. One new concept system could be a server request-like system that can de-conflict the global traffic, while allowing UAVs and VTOLs to self-separate any potential local conflicts with VFR-like rules, even in inclement weather. Some of new systems are already being developed, for example NASA (Figure 2.60) is studying the entry of the UAS in the low-altitude airspace [3], considering UAS operations inside uncontrolled Airspace (class G), UAS operations inside controlled airspace, but segregated from controlled air traffic and UAS operations integrated into the controlled air traffic flows.

Figure 2.60 - NASA's concept for a possible UTM system [3]

This complete study could become important because UAS can be used for many tasks (Figure 2.61) such as infrastructure monitoring, precision agriculture, public safety, search and rescue, disaster relief, weather monitoring, and delivery of goods.

Figure 2.61 - Applications of small UAS [3]

Figure 2.62 - Complete UTM architecture

The second key to actually reduce the travel duration would be the improvement of the current processes carrying out at the airports or even the design of a new system regarding both passengers and luggage processes (Figure 2.62). These processes are, concerning the passengers: check-in, security control, passport control and customs; concerning the luggage: security control, management and customs.

Nowadays, airlines advise their passengers to get to the airport with enough time to boarding. For example, Iberia set the following limit hours to check-in [4]:

Distance	Time Limit
Short and mid-haul	45 minutes
Long-haul	60 minutes

Apart from this time limit set by the airlines, the passengers have to bear in mind the time spent from the start of their journey to the airport and also the time spent in going through the processes at the airport, thereby passengers usually start their journey at least 2 hours before the estimated time of departure. In the last few years some developments have been done in order to reduce the time elapsed going through these processes: online check-in, new baggage screening devices as RAPISCAN RTT™ 110 or new procedures which are being developed within Smart Security, a joint project between IATA (International Air Transport Association) and ACI (Airports Council International). The following solutions, some of which are now permanently installed and operational in airports, have been or are being tested [5]: Innovative use and integration of advanced and new security technology and passenger processing systems, use of biometrics and data for passenger differentiation, adaptable risk-based screening capabilities, dynamic lane screening, efficient resource allocation, seamless integration of security processes into the passenger journey from curb to boarding and process efficiencies.

Reference State in 2010

Since the beginning of the liberalization of air transport in Europe (1993), many projects related to the facts stated above have been carry out. At the outset, as the growth of passengers was increasing steady over time, the first step was to expand both airside and landside, consisting in building new runways and more terminals. For example, in 1990 Amsterdam Airport Schiphol exceeded the 16-million-passenger mark and further expansion thus became essential, since that moment a new control tower was built in 1991, thus the opening of Terminal West in 1993 which meant an increase of the Terminal capacity to a total of 32 million passengers a year. Since that, several expansions were made until the opening of runway 18R-36L in 2003.

The same case as Schiphol was Madrid-Barajas Airport (Figure 2.63) which had only 2 crossed runways until 1998 when new runway 18R-36L was built. Additionally, the expansion continued during the following years with the opening of 2 new runways (18L-36R and 14L-32R), 2 new terminals (T4 and T4S) and new connections with city centre by underground and train.

Figure 2.63 - Madrid-Barajas Airport in 1998 and in 2008, respectively

Once the infrastructures were developed, the next aim in the outline was to improve the processes carried out at the airports. Regarding these processes, many projects were set in order to develop them.

For example, ASSET project (Aeronautic Study on Seamless Transport) defined the problem in 2008 as the insufficient punctuality in air transport was the high variance in off-block times (Figure 2.64).

This is related to the fact that off-block time is mainly driven by the duration of landside airport processes which contain passenger processes, baggage handling processes and aircraft turnaround processes.

Figure 2.64 - Drivers of departure delays (2007-2010)

Source: Eurocontrol PRR 2010

As can be noticed, the turnaround related processes have been the main factor that have induced delays in the air transport operation over the years. In order to decrease these percentages, researches in this field have been essential: new procedures, new devices to screen both passenger and luggage and so on. However, this cluster of processes still constrains the throughput of the air transport operations nowadays and it will be studied in the next part.

Progress Up-to-Now

Nowadays, all the different processes at the airports still remain as essential in air transport operations. For example, in a 2015 global passenger survey by IATA, 90% of respondents indicated that they prefer to check-in and reserve their seats before arriving at the airport, and nearly 50% prefer to use self-bag drop service (Figure 2.65) for their check-in luggage. Thus, it is essential to develop new systems and concepts related to this matter and since 2010 several improvements have been done.

Figure 2.65 - Self-bag drop at Hong Kong Airport [7]

As example, Hong Kong Airport has developed some new procedures and systems than allow passengers to have a better experience in a seamless environment [7]:

- Enabled home-printed bag tags due to completed trials for Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID).
- Greater check-in convenience due to the launching of self-bag drop system, reducing baggage processing time from 2-3 minutes to about 1 minute. In this manner, it is expected that 120 self-bags drop counters will be in operation by the end of 2017.
- Enhanced passenger traceability and security due to the installation of a Positive Boarding System at all departure security checkpoints to capture boarding pass data of each passenger. This data is used to improve airside security and operational efficiency, and airlines' on-time throughput.
- Began rolling out iBeacon technology to provide passengers with terminal directions, walking times to gates, lounge access and boarding alerts via their mobile devices.
- Faster baggage delivery due to a team deployed to monitor real-time baggage arrival flows and set up rescue tractor team to help operators maintain service levels during temporary shortfalls in manpower.
- Smoother immigration service at arrivals implementing real-time arrival passenger forecast, enabling the Immigration Department to deploy resources more efficiently against real-time demand.

On the other hand, another project has been carried out by Aruba (Figure 2.66), The Netherlands, Aruba International Airport, KLM, VISION-BOX™ and Schiphol Group called Happy Flow [8]. This project consists of a streamlined sequence of user-centric self-service touch points, from check-in to boarding the aircraft. At all passenger touch-points, the passenger's face image is the identification token so that passengers are only required to show their passport once, at check-in, when they also enrol their biometric data. At that moment, a virtual Passenger Data Envelope is created, containing passenger biometric and biographic information. After check-in, the passenger goes through baggage drop off, pass border control and board the aircraft without being asked to show any travel document: user-centric self-service Passenger Touch Points (Self-service Baggage Drop stations,

Automated Border Control eGates and self-boarding Gates) identify each passenger's face and match it to the passengers' database, only allowing authorized passengers to move on.

The most important thing is that the process at each Passenger Touch Point only takes a few seconds, so queues are smaller if exist.

Figure 2.66 - Different processes in Aruba Happy Flow

Predictions Up-to-2025

Following the development outline carried out during the past few years, it is expected that current systems regarding passenger and baggage processes continue to develop and, in addition, this development is expected to be implemented to the entire airport network around the world.

On the one hand, new screening machines will be operating in the next years. These devices present a technology capable of detecting suspicious baggage more accurately at the primary level 1 in order to fulfil EU Regulation No. 1087/2011, which modifies EU Regulation No. 185/2010. This Regulation establish detailed measures to enforce the basic and common regulations of air security related to Explosive Detection Systems (EDS). In this manner, the minimum detection levels required are set within Standard 3 framework which regulates and certifies them. This Standard is defined by ECAC (European Civil Aviation Conference) and these minimum levels required can only be reached using

Computed Tomography (CT) technology, whereas previous Standard 2 levels are based on simpler dual X-ray equipment (horizontal and vertical) that allow to get two simultaneous images that make staff be able to detect explosives. The main features required in each Standard are the following [8]:

ECAC Standard 1: Dual Energy X-ray and single operator image; set the base line data for Probability of Detection and False Alarm Rate. Standard 1 has been in use since January 2002 and was made mandatory for all airports in 2007.

ECAC Standard 2: Dual Energy X-ray, dual operator images; specifies that for the X-ray unit the Probability of Detection must be higher than Standard 1 and the False Alarm Rate must be lower than Standard 1; image quality parameters, resolution, wire detection, steel penetration, organic/non-organic discrimination.

ECAC Standard 3: Dual Energy X-ray + Computed Tomography (CT) technology, single operator image; specifies that for the X-ray unit the Probability of Detection must be higher than Standard 2 and the False Alarm Rate must be lower than Standard 2; image quality parameters, resolution, wire detection, steel penetration, organic/non-organic discrimination (very close to US TSA standards for BHS).

EU Regulation No. 1087/2011 states that, since September 1st, 2014, all new automatic inspection equipment installed in Europe shall be based on Computed Tomography (CT) according to ECAC Standard 3.

Regarding old inspection equipment already installed at the airports, both according to Standard 1 and Standard 2, the deadline to replace them is September 1st, 2022 (Figure 2.67), hence it is expected that current inspection equipment are upgraded during the following years.

Figure 2.67 - ECAC Standards timeline [8]

Figure 2.68 - Comparison of ECAC Standard 2 system with a proposed ECAC Standard 3 system [8]

The idea of screening bags at different levels (Figure 2.68) is to be able to screen and approve the majority of the bags as fast as possible. Bags that fail the screening process are diverted from the main flow and moved to another screening level where further, slower manual investigation is undertaken. The in-line multi-level screening approach set out in ECAC Standard 3 is designed to be able to screen the baggage in-line, faster and more cost efficiently.

The main changes specified by ECAC Standard 3 result in an increase in security standards and an increase in system availability and throughput. The modern CT machine can process up to 1500 bags per hour, which is the same as a traditional dual energy X-ray machine. However, the traditional X-ray machine only cleared approximately 70% of all bags, restricting its approval capacity to around 1050 bags per hour. The CT technology-based machines clear approximately 80% of all bags giving it an approval capacity of around 1200 bags per hour, effectively giving it a higher handling rate [8].

On the other hand, systems related to passenger processes will continue to be developed during the following years. In this manner, biometrics will be essential to make the passenger journey through airports faster and more seamlessly as much as this technology has made our personal lives easier through fingerprints (logging in to our phones), voice (Siri, Cortana) and facial recognition (logging in to Windows 10 or iPhone X with our faces).

Some of these new technologies are being trialled within Europe and the rest of the world.

For example, the US Customs and Border Protection (CBP) launched the Automated Passport Control (APC) program consisting in providing an automated process through CBP's Primary Inspection area. Travelers use self-service kiosks to respond to CBP inspection related questions and submit biographic information. Since 2015, when firstly Orlando International Airport upgraded them, the APC kiosks (Figure 2.69) include facial recognition for arriving passengers. This allow the kiosks to authenticate identity by matching people's face to the biometrics record in their e-passport. These kiosks have

helped to reduce lines by as much as 40% [9]. During the last few years this technology has been successfully implemented in most of airports across the United States.

Figure 2.69 - Passengers using APC kiosks at Miami Airport

As another example, Finnair invited 1000 of its frequent flyers to participate in a face recognition test at Helsinki airport in order to improve the airline's understanding of the applicability of face recognition technology and the impact it has on the customer experience.

This test consisted in using an Android app to send three selfies and upload Finnair loyalty card information to the test system. Then, it was used a check-in desk with face recognition technology. As customers approached the check-in desk and were recognized, service agents were provided with the name of the passenger and their flight information and could address them in a personalized way.

Evolutionary Progress Up-to-2050

The expected progress between 2025 and 2050 is a continued development and implementation of current systems that are currently being tested. These new technologies explained above such as biometric recognition or computed tomography will take up the whole air traffic industry.

However, the continued growth of air traffic during the next decades will lead to the saturation in the different processes related to aircraft operation. It is expected that the number of passengers will double in the next 20 years which will set the pace in the research and development rush.

Related to that, current air traffic capacities will not be able to accommodate this growth of passengers. The increase of the number of passengers will mean an increase of delays in the different processes involving aircraft operation from passenger handling to ATM operation going through baggage handling if no measures are taken. These processes could experience even more delays than they have already experienced in the past, as can be seen in the Figure 2.70:

Figure 2.70 Departure delay drivers 2006-2010 [10]

Therefore, the growth of passenger numbers could be considered as a driver for the increase of delays. In this manner, it is likely that the processes become bottlenecks, causing a limitation in the growth of air traffic during the following decades. This would be the case in which demand exceeds offer and it would be frightful for the development of air traffic industry.

Proper measures should be taken in order to predict and solve these bottlenecks before they become real, hence research and development will be essential for aviation industry. In that case, European Union should provide institutions, companies and other stakeholders with the tools needed for a successful development.

Possible or Predictable Breakthroughs

The following breakthroughs could be expected:

- Full implementation of technologies currently being tested (biometric recognition, computed technology and so on). These new technologies could be implemented within airport-collaborative decision making (A-CDM) framework which has been developed and implemented in European airports during the last few years. Nowadays A-CDM is implemented in 26 airports across Europe, including: Barcelona, Berlin Schönefeld, Brussels, Copenhagen, Düsseldorf, Frankfurt, Geneva, Hamburg, Helsinki, London Gatwick, London Heathrow, Lyon, Madrid, Milan Malpensa, Milan Linate, Munich, Paris CDG, Paris Orly, Oslo, Palma de Mallorca, Prague, Rome Fiumicino, Stockholm Arlanda, Stuttgart, Venice and Zurich. The addition of passenger and baggage data to the A-CDM network could mean that airport operators, airlines and other stakeholders had the right information at the right moment, and it would allow to facilitate a more seamless and secure operation through the airport.
- Construction of new runways and terminals at constrained airports, or even new airports.

- Development of both aircraft and ground systems allowing lower separation minima.
- New aircraft designs and manufacturing reducing wake turbulences and, thereby, reducing wake separation.
- New research about innovative technologies in order to accommodate the growth of traffic.

Identification of Gaps

As well as Goal 1, tasks related to Goal 4 are not new in Europe. One of the key projects that has been carried out (Figure 2.72) is the Airport-Collaborative Decision Making (A-CDM) (Figure 2.71). Its implementation is focused on enhancing the operational efficiency of airports and improving their integration into the Air Traffic Management Network (ATMN) while maintaining or improving safety levels. These objectives are achievable by increasing the information sharing between the local ANSP, airport operator, aircraft operators, ground handlers, the Network Manager and other airport service providers; and also, by improving the cooperation between these partners to enhance the predictability of events and optimize the utilization of resources therefore increase the efficiency of the overall system.

Figure 2.71 - A-CDM common objectives [5]

Airport-Collaborative Decision Making has been developed since 2004 and it was supposed to be fully operating in 2016. However, it is expected a 2-year delay until it is completely deployed, as can be seen in the following Figure 2.72:

Figure 2.72 - A-CDM implementation progress [3]

It is the same case as Goal 1, referring to that delays in projects' implementation means more spending and inconvenient and it could affect other upcoming projects if they directly depend on the previous one. The fact that future projects will be focused on seeing the airport as a whole, in such a way that most of services (regarding aircraft, passengers and baggage) will be integrated into the same network, could take more time than expected as they have to work as a mechanism with multiple pieces, each one necessary for the rest.

In this context, stakeholders will face the integration of technologies currently being developed and also new technologies that will be developed in the future into the airport network in order to achieve both a more seamless experience for the passenger and also an improved throughput, allowing to reduce the time dedicated to each process.

Moreover, future integrated technologies such as biometric recognition will face other issues related to privacy constraints. Travellers' privacy is key to the implementation of advanced IT systems for facilitating airport's processes and, as future projects aim at speeding up airport processes, specific attention must be paid that systems and equipment do not store data but rather streamline procedures until the ultimate boarding phase without infringing passengers' privacy.

The harmonization of security features and the integration of biometric identifiers is an important step towards the use of new elements in the perspective of future developments at European level, which render the travel document more secure and establish a more reliable link between the holder and the passport and the travel document as an important contribution to ensuring that it is protected against fraudulent use.

Summarizing, future projects related to seamless passenger operation could be constraint by privacy policies, hence stakeholders should work together with governments in order to set the properly regulatory framework that allows the full implementation of these new technologies.

KEY TOPIC T2.6 – OVERALL GROUND PLUS AIR TRAVEL TIME

Introduction

Europe is one of the densely populated continents on Earth. The European Union, political and economic union of 28 Member States has an area of 4,475,757 sq km with over 508 million inhabitants in 2015 (Eurostat). Geographically, it is almost 4.200 km height and 5.600 km wide. These dimensions define the framework of the market related to the European transportation.

Air transportation is considered to be the most efficient transportation mean and therefore has a dominating position at long distances. It is also significant at short or medium distances, but upon various factors influencing the passengers' mode selection criteria, it competes with rail and car transport.

Air Transport and Flight Movement

In 2016, the total number of passengers travelling by air in the European Union could be established at 973 million, an increase of 5.9 % compared to 2015. The intra-EU share in total transport could be established at 47 %. It was the main destination ahead of extra-EU transport (36 %) and domestic passenger transport (17 %). International intra-EU traffic at country level, as set out in the Table 2.12, shows that for 2016, the top ten country-to-country flows in general remained stable compared with 2015 (Eurostat).

Rank	Country pairs		2015		2016	
			Passengers carried (in 1000)	Share in total intra-EU (%)	Passengers carried (in 1000)	Share in total intra-EU (%)
1	United Kingdom	Spain	35922.6	9.1	41637.8	9.6
2	Spain	Germany	25063.9	6.3	27581.6	6.3
3	United Kingdom	Germany	13302.7	3.4	13877.	3.2
4	United Kingdom	Italy	12711.3	3.2	14123.5	3.2
5	Italy	Germany	12427.1	3.1	13296.	3.1
6	France	Spain	12201.1	3.1	13028.2	3.
7	Italy	Spain	11839.8	3.	12985.6	3.
8	United Kingdom	France	11943.6	3.	12545.2	2.9
9	United Kingdom	Ireland	11590.6	2.9	12801.6	2.9
10	Italy	France	10911.7	2.8	10961.6	2.5

Table 2.12 - Intra-EU traffic at country level: top-10 country pairs represent 40 % of 2016 intra-EU traffic (Eurostat).

At European level (ECAC area), the traffic forecast for 2016 was in line with the September 2015 forecast with a growth of 2.4% (± 1.4 pp). For 2017 (Figure 2.73), a growth of 2.1% is foreseen (± 1.3 pp). Removing the effect of the leap year (± 0.3 pp); this in fact means that it was expected (Table 2.13) a growth of 2.1% for 2016 and 2.4% for 2017. From 2018 onwards, European flight growth is expected to remain stable at around 2.2% per year over the 2018-2022 period. The 2008 peak of 10.2 million flights is forecasted to be reached again by 2017. The forecast is for 11.5 million IFR flight movements (± 1.2 million) in Europe in 2022, 16% more than in 2015 (EUROCONTROL, 2016).

ECAC		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	AAGR 2022/2015	RP2 2019/2014 AAGR
IFR Flight Movements (Thousands)	H	10,293	10,639	11,092	11,503	11,997	12,417	12,868	3.8%	3.3%
	B	9,710	9,603	9,770	9,917	10,153	10,364	10,578	10,818	11,091	11,301	11,535	2.2%	2.1%
	L	10,023	10,107	10,140	10,231	10,335	10,373	10,440	0.7%	0.9%
Annual Growth (compared to previous year unless otherwise mentioned)	H	3.8%	3.4%	4.3%	3.7%	4.3%	3.5%	3.6%	3.8%	3.3%
	B	-2.2%	-1.1%	1.7%	1.5%	2.4%	2.1%	2.1%	2.3%	2.5%	1.9%	2.1%	2.2%	2.1%
	L	1.1%	0.8%	0.3%	0.9%	1.0%	0.4%	0.6%	0.7%	0.9%

Table 2.13 - Summary of flight forecast for Europe (ECAC), (EUROCONTROL, 2016).
B-Base, H-High, L-Low

Figure 2.73 - Flight forecast details for 2017 (EUROCONTROL, 2016).

European Airports

A characteristic feature of the European air transport service market is the co-existence of several large centres performing trans-continental links and a dense net of local links between the majority of small cities and tourist resorts. According to a research report published in 2006, Europe has about 2570 airports and landing fields [Brusow, 2007], from which 2100 is used by IFR movements [EUROCONTROL, 2007].

More particularly, out of the 2570 identified locations, Europe has 1270 airports and 1300 landing fields. The geographical distribution of airports across Europe is presented in the Figure 2.74:

Figure 2.74 - All European airports location (Brusow et al., 2007)

Regarding the airports, the top airports in the EU-28, most busy – ranked by the total passengers per year in 2016 – is shown in the Table 2.14. Accordingly, there is a geographical concentration at the region London-Amsterdam-Munich-Milan. In addition, just the top 25 IFR airports generate 50% of all passenger movement [Eurostat].

Rank	Country	Airport	Total air transport (in 1000 passengers)	of which			Growth of total air transport 2015-2016 (%)	Total number of passenger flights (in 1000)	Growth of total number of flights 2015-2016 (%)
				National air transport	International intra-EU-28 air transport	International extra-EU-28 air transport			
1	UK	London/Heathrow	75 672	4 645	26 257	44 770	1.0	471	0.2
2	FR	Paris/Charles de Gaulle	65 849	6 055	26 040	33 755	0.3	444	0.9
3	NL	Amsterdam/Schiphol	63 550	0.5	37 890	25 659	9.3	467	6.2
4	DE	Frankfurt/Main	60 669	6 943	25 211	28 514	-0.4	435	-0.9
5	ES	Madrid/Barajas	49 178	14 133	21 585	13 460	6.2	354	1.5
6	ES	Barcelona/El Prat	43 750	11 789	24 837	7 124	11.0	293	6.7
7	UK	London/Gatwick	43 143	3 870	28 317	10 956	7.2	277	5.6
8	DE	München	42 159	9 593	20 709	11 858	3.2	375	3.9
9	IT	Roma/Fiumicino	41 569	12 470	17 991	11 108	3.3	310	-0.2
10	FR	Paris/Orly	31 238	14 143	10 795	6 300	5.3	235	1.5
11	DK	København/Kastrup	28 946	1 880	19 123	7 944	9.2	254	4.6
12	IE	Dublin	27 709	82	23 299	4 328	11.2	200	8.5
13	ES	Palma De Mallorca	26 230	5 803	19 179	1 248	10.6	186	11.1
14	UK	Manchester	25 598	2 295	16 477	6 827	10.9	184	12.2
15	SE	Stockholm/Arlanda	24 698	5 275	13 776	5 647	6.7	220	3.7
16	UK	London/Stansted	24 317	2 051	20 997	1 269	8.0	153	5.6
17	DE	Düsseldorf	23 497	4 476	11 933	7 088	4.7	209	3.2
18	AT	Wien/Schwechat	23 318	509	15 405	7 405	2.5	220	-0.1
19	PT	Lisboa	22 463	3 068	13 941	5 453	11.7	178	10.5
20	BE	Brussels/National	21 769	2	15 362	6 406	-6.4	192	-7.5
21	DE	Berlin/Tegel	21 245	7 769	9 596	3 880	1.2	179	1.1
22	EL	Athinai/Eleftherios Venizelos	20 009	7 157	8 959	3 892	10.6	176	8.4
23	IT	Milano/Malpensa	19 312	2 693	9 926	6 692	4.7	150	4.0
24	FI	Helsinki/Vantaa	17 181	2 679	10 443	4 059	4.6	157	-0.5
25	ES	Malaga/Costa del Sol	16 620	2 274	12 982	1 363	15.7	115	13.5
26	DE	Hamburg	16 191	5 339	7 866	2 985	3.9	143	1.4
27	UK	London/Luton	14 642	1 043	12 132	1 467	19.4	101	18.0
28	CZ	Praha/Ruzyně	12 990	36	9 332	3 622	9.5	126	6.5
29	PL	Warszawa/Chopin	12 848	1 424	7 989	3 435	14.5	142	8.7
30	FR	Nice/Côte d'Azur	12 422	4 440	5 754	2 229	3.4	146	5.1
37	HU	Budapest/Liszt Ferenc Intern.	11 383	0	9 204	2 179	11.3	84	4.7
39	RO	Bucuresti/Henri Coanda	10 979	873	8 487	1 619	18.4	99	12.4
57	CY	Larnaka	6 628	0	3 840	2 788	24.7	50	26.9
64	LV	Riga	5 385	1.6	3 943	1 440	4.6	62	-0.9
69	MT	Luqa	5 080	0.3	4 648	432	10.0	36	4.7
73	BG	Sofia	4 964	157	4 068	739	22.4	44	18.7
87	LT	Vilnius	3 811	0.4	2 820	991	14.3	37	6.8
94	LU	Luxembourg	2 984	0.7	2 686	298	12.5	47	11.1
102	HR	Zagreb/Pleso	2 757	444	1 642	670	7.0	35	4.6
118	EE	Lennart Meri Tallinn	2 215	17	1 763	435	2.5	32	0.4
132	SK	Bratislava/M.R.Stefanik	1 746	19	1 444	283	12.2	15	12.6
146	SI	Ljubljana/Brnik	1 404	0	857	547	-2.2	21	-0.9

Source: Eurostat (online data code: avia_paoa)

Table 2.14 - Top airports in the EU-28 in terms of total passengers carried in 2016

Distance Between City Pairs

For European airports/landing fields the distribution of the distance between the airport pairs is shown on the Figure 2.75. As visible, the most frequent distance is related to approximately 1000 km, while there are only few potential links above 3000 km.

Figure 2.75 - Distribution of the European airport pairs distances (Brusow et al., 2007)

Taking into account short distances between the European cities, transportation on the territory of Europe is performed mainly over short and medium distances, with the domination of the first ones. The European transport market is therefore, the area of competition between the road, rail and air transport.

Travel Time from City Centre to Airports

Seeing the facts above, it is clear the Europe has a significant number of airports. On the other hand, to assess the efficiency of the air transportation system, and more particularly once considering the door-to-door time, it is also important to know, how far these airports are located from the European city centres. To answer to this question, the Figure 2.76 presents the distribution of the distance between the European city centres (with a population over 50 thousand inhabitants) to the nearest airport. As the Figure 2.76 indicates, it is clear that for almost 80% of the European cities, the nearest airport is situated at 20 km. Such a short distance reflects that the general accessibility of the European airports is high.

Figure 2.76 Cumulative distribution function of the city distance to the nearest airport (Brusow et al., 2007).

This fact is also reflected by looking at top 10 airports in Europe, in terms of IFR flights (EUROCONTROL, 2007). London has the most airfields nearby: 46 within 100 km. Barcelona has the fewest, only 4. As shown in the Table 2.15., the typical distance of these airports from the city centres (weighted by the number of flights) is ranging between 14 and 24 km.

City	Number of Airfields within 100km of City Centre	Distance from City Centre (weighted average) km	Total Departures (k)
Amsterdam	31	16.2	244
Barcelona	4	19.3	185
Copenhagen	21	16.3	155
Frankfurt	33	13.8	258
London	46	33.9	603
Madrid	8	13.8	233
Munich	28	32.5	224
Paris	28	20.8	441
Rome	9	21.1	196
Vienna	13	23.5	145

Table 2.15 - Airports and airfields of the 10 busiest European cities [EUROCONTROL, 2007].

The DATASET2050 shows information about what the "doors" (e.g. houses, hotels, offices) are and how much time it takes to go from the "door" to the airport "kerb" (and vice-versa). The results for specific areas/airports are presented in the Tables 2.16 – 2.18:

The UK CAA has analysed this topic in detail, with some 30 specific modes of transport available to respondents, for 11 English airports (5 London and 6 provincial). Although the cost of obtaining these complete data is beyond the available budget for this project, the publicly-available summary report (CAA, 2014) provides the following:

	Gatwick	Heathrow	London City	Luton	Stansted	Birmingham	Doncaster	East Midlands	Leeds Bradford	Liverpool	Manchester
Private %	58.3	58.6	52.9	70.9	48.5	76.5	90.8	92.4	88.5	79.3	83.5
Public %	41.4	41.1	46.3	28.8	49.6	22.7	9.0	7.4	11.3	20.4	16.2
Other %	0.2	0.3	0.8	0.3	1.9	0.9	0.2	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.2
Terminating passengers (000's)	34,994	46,991	3,533	10,186	18,855	8,976	714	4,374	2,879	3,752	20,830

Table 2.16 - Surface access modes to UK airports (DATASET2050, 2016)

The French DGAC has also studied surface access in their 2014-2015 airport passenger survey (DGAC, 2015), covering 15 airports. Unfortunately, these data have been aggregated over all 15 airports. The result of 33,655 responses by non-transfer passengers to the question of how people arrived at the airport is given below:

Transport	Usage	
Kiss-and-Fly	28%	43% Dropped off at kerb by another person
Taxi	17%	
Personal car	14%	15% in car parked at airport car park
With another passenger (in their personal car)	1%	
Hire car	4%	
Hotel or other Shuttle	4%	
Local public transport	28%	
Intercity train	5%	
Other	2%	

Table 2.17 French airport surface access modes (DATASET2050, 2016)

The German Airports Group (ADV) also performs passenger surveys. The latest "Airport Travel Survey 2015" (ADV, 2015) includes summary data on the modes of transport used by (all) passengers to access one of the 22 airports in the study:

Transport	Usage
Private car (including kiss-and-fly)	44%
Taxi	21%
Metro/U-Bahn	16%
Bus (including coach)	8%
Rail	6%
Rental Car and Other	5%

Table 2.18 - Surface access mode share for 22 German airports (DATASET2050, 2016)

The Table 2.19 gives the mean and standard deviation (StD) speeds in km/h for both driving and public transport travel modes and for chosen airport.

Mode	Driving		Public transport	
	Mean	StD	Mean	StD
AMS	73.27	19.44	32.62	17.13
BCN	55.21	23.71	21.99	8.86
BRU	68.83	22.69	30.81	14.89
CDG	71.39	19.02	27.54	11.45
CPH	63.63	23.91	29.27	17.03
DUB	57.51	22.37	21.93	10.05
DUS	75.23	20.81	31.55	17.97
FCO	62.02	20.23	31.68	15.49
FRA	73.08	22.18	38.06	21.68
LGW	65.34	18.58	31.64	16.03
LHR	61.71	23.10	28.29	15.35
LIS	70.28	25.34	15.13	10.29
MAD	73.98	19.63	19.04	7.95
MAN	61.65	20.05	26.86	14.12
MUC	74.25	18.52	30.55	16.95
ORY	65.63	23.36	19.13	9.56
OSL	63.04	13.44	26.89	13.73
PMI	47.98	16.27	14.95	4.92
STN	65.26	19.88	29.35	16.68
TXL	64.98	25.43	25.53	14.22
VIE	73.77	19.32	29.73	14.17
ZRH	66.00	19.26	32.91	13.93
Total	66.67	21.86	28.16	15.61

Table 2.19 Driving and public transport speeds (km/h) by airport (DATASET2050, 2016)

The Table 2.20 provides an overview on the airport accessibility by rail of the 30 largest airports in Europe, measured by total passengers in 2008. The geographical scope is the European Economic Area and Switzerland.

Rank	Airport	Country	Passengers in millions (2008)	Long-distance trains - no. of daily services	Short-distance trains - no. of daily services	Short-distance rail journey time to city train station	Short-distance train fare - single ticket to city train station	Underground/ Metro access	Underground/ Metro journey time to city train station	Underground/ Metro fare - single ticket to city train station
1	London Heathrow	United Kingdom	67.1	-	73	00:23	20.38 €	x	00:40	5.56 €
2	Paris Charles de Gaulle	France	60.9	62	142	00:29	8.50 €	-	-	-
3	Frankfurt	Germany	53.5	167	214	00:10	3.80 €	-	-	-
4	Madrid	Spain	50.8	-	-	-	-	x	00:22	2.00 €
5	Amsterdam	Netherlands	47.4	377	294	00:16	3.70 €	-	-	-
6	Rome Fiumicino	Italy	35.1	-	101	00:31	14.00 €	-	-	-
7	Munich	Germany	34.5	-	116	00:40	9.60 €	-	-	-
8	London Gatwick	United Kingdom	34.2	-	80	00:30	18.77 €	-	-	-
9	Barcelona	Spain	30.2	-	37	00:19	3.00 €	opening 2012	-	-
10	Paris Orly	France	26.2	-	Indirect connection to the RER regional train system by an automated people mover					-
11	Dublin	Ireland	23.5	-	-	-	-	planned	-	-
12	Palma de Mallorca	Spain	22.8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13	London Stansted	United Kingdom	22.4	-	76	00:46	24.45 €	-	-	-
14	Zurich	Switzerland	22.0	116	185	00:11	4.68 €	-	-	-
15	Copenhagen	Denmark	21.5	40	182	00:13	4.63 €	-	-	-
16	Manchester	United Kingdom	21.4	-	171	00:16	4.69 €	-	-	-
17	Vienna	Austria	19.7	-	126	00:16 / 00:31	3.60 € / 10.00 €	-	-	-
18	Oslo	Norway	19.3	32	156	00:19 / 00:26	13.92 € / 21.51 €	-	-	-
19	Milan Malpensa	Italy	19.2	-	39	00:36	11.00 €	-	-	-
20	Brussels	Belgium	18.5	2	114	00:20	5.10 €	-	-	-
21	Stockholm Arlanda	Sweden	18.2	-	76	00:20	29.46 €	-	-	-
22	Düsseldorf	Germany	18.2	45	332	00:06	2.30 €	-	-	-
23	Athens	Greece	16.4	-	17	00:50	6.00 €	x	00:42	6.00 €
24	Berlin Tegel	Germany	14.5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
25	Lisbon	Portugal	13.6	-	-	-	-	opening 2011	-	-
26	Helsinki	Finland	13.4	-	opening 2014	-	-	-	-	-
27	Hamburg	Germany	12.8	-	110	00:25	2.75 €	-	-	-
28	Malaga	Spain	12.8	-	70	00:12	1.25 €	-	-	-
29	Prague	Czech Republic	12.6	-	-	-	-	opening 2014	-	-
30	Geneva	Switzerland	11.4	31	58	00:07	2.26 €	-	-	-

All values in €. Non-€ currencies were converted into € with the exchange rate of 29th June 2010.

Table 2.20 - Airport accessibility by rail for the 30 largest airports in the European Economic Area + Switzerland (DLR, 2010).

In the case of most of the 30 largest airports in Europe, passengers have a choice between different public transport service providers for access between the centres of the respective cities and the airports. Currently, 23 out of the 30 largest airports in the European Economic Area (including Switzerland) have a direct rail access at or in the vicinity of the passenger terminal. A number of rail access projects are currently being planned or under construction.

An airport should cover the area of economic transport value (a city, a place of people concentration, tourist areas) in order to attract a certain group of passengers. In the territory of Europe with regard to numerous airports, a strong competition between the airports develops in order to gain passengers, new carriers and new air links. The zone of competition between the airports is the covering the gravitation area of the neighbouring airports, called catchment areas. The value of the catchment area of an airport – the area where passengers start their air travel from a certain airport or the point where they reach their destination – is determined mainly by the time factor of getting to the airport. The value of the gravitation area which influences the potential increase in the number of passengers, raising its competitive position depends also on other factors, such as the convenience of the connections with the land transport.

Taking a simplified assumption that the value of catchment areas is influenced mainly by the time factor, while the travel time is the function of distance, the gravitation areas were determined for four European airport categories, including small, medium, large and very large. As the Figure 2.77 indicates, while generally the European airports could easily access, very large and large airports could attract passengers even from several hundreds of kilometres.

Figure 2.77 - Cumulative distribution function of the population within catchment's areas of airports and landing facilities (Brusow et al., 2007)

For each airport it can be identified catchment area. In principle all the potential passengers from that area (inhabitants, tourists, business travellers, etc.) would use that airport when taking a flight. Catchment areas can be simply defined based on the distance to the airport. The distance (to be strict: time-based distance) is measured in terms of travel time spent in the door-to-kerb process, which ultimately depends on the mode of transport chosen. Catchment areas for Budapest airport is presented in the Figure 2.78:

Figure 2.78 - Budapest 60, 90, 120, and 180 minutes' drive time

Delays Distribution

A flight delay is when an airline flight takes off and/or lands later than its scheduled time. Usually, the flight is considered to be delayed when it is 15 minutes later than its scheduled time. EUROCONTROL's Central Office for Delay Analysis (CODA) collects operational data from airlines operating IFR flights in Europe. Delay monitoring and analysis is an important aspect of the airlines' operational and financial success. The cost of delay is estimated at €82 per minute of delay for delays in excess of 15 minutes (EUROCONTROL, 2010).

The cost of delay is calculated separately for strategic delays (those accounted for in advance) and tactical delays (those incurred on the day of operations and not accounted for in advance). Tactical delay costs are given for 5, 15, 30, 60, 90, 120, 180, 240 and 300 minutes. These are scaled up to the network level because on the day of operations, original delays caused by one aircraft ('primary' delays) cause 'knock-on' effects in the rest of the network (known as 'secondary' or 'reactionary'.

The largest single group of delay reasons by total generated delay minutes are delays caused by airline operational processes. They account for approximately 50% of the primary delays. This group is followed by airport and en route delays which account for almost one-third of all delays. Weather delays may vary by season.

Past Situation

In Europe, in 2008, 15.2% of flights departed 5 minutes or more before their planned time and 60% of flights departed within 5 minutes of the planned time. Of all delayed flights on departure 21.4% were delayed by more than 15 minutes. On the other hand, 21.6% of flights arrived > 15 minutes after the STA (scheduled date and time of arrival). In 2008, the Average Delay per Movement was 12.6 minutes, a decrease of 2.1% on 2007. In 2008, the reactionary/primary delay ratio was 0.83. This means that for each minute of primary delay there was 0.83 minute of reactionary delay. In 2003 the ratio was 0.23. This evolution indicates a loss in delay recovery for airlines.

The share of Airport, Weather, Security and Miscellaneous delays are presented on the Figure 2.79 ATFCM (Air Traffic Flow and Capacity Management) en Route delays increased by 3% in 2008 compared to 2007 and represents 13% of all primary departure delays.

Figure 2.79 - Primary departure delay causes 2008 vs 2007 (EUROCONTROL, 2010).

Current Situation

In 2016, the average departure delay per flight ranged from a low of 8 minutes per flight in February to a peak of 16 minutes per flight in July. This translated to an annual average all-cause departure delay of 11.3 minutes per flight, an increase of 0.9 minutes per flight, alongside an increase in daily

flights of 2.8% in ECAC. Reactionary (knock-on) delay increased contributing 5.1 minutes to the 11.3 minutes average delay per flight, a 45% share of delay minutes meaning for every 1 minute of primary delay there were 50 seconds of reactionary delay generated. The range of reactionary delay during the year was wider than airline delay, with a range of 4 minutes being observed from the lows in February of 3.5 minutes per flight and the high in June of 7.5 minutes per flight, a month which also saw a peak in en route ATFM delay (EUROCONTROL, 2017).

In 2016, delays due to airline operations remained the main cause of primary delay, contributing 3.1 minutes to the average delay per flight. Compared to reactionary delay which doubled during the summer month’s airline delays remain relatively stable with the 2016 monthly average ranging between 2.5 to 3.5 minutes per flight. Airline reported en route ATFCM delays increased to 0.8 minutes per flight. Airport operations delay including ATFCM, remained at 1.2 minutes per flight and grouped together was the second highest cause in the share of primary delay. Yearly airline arrival punctuality decreased, with 81% of flights arriving within 15 minutes or earlier than their scheduled arrival time (STA) compared to 82% in 2015 (EUROCONTROL, 2017).

Analysis of the delay reasons in 2016 in comparison to 2015, shows that reactionary delays contributed the most to the average with 5.1 minutes per flight (Figure 2.80). Airline-related delays increased slightly by 0.1 minutes per flight. ATFCM en route delay had the third highest contribution with 0.8 minute per flight increasing by 0.3 minutes per flight compared to 2015. Total ATFM delay reported by airlines delay increased to 1.7 minutes per flight with en route restrictions mainly contributing to the overall increase, Airline and airport delays remained stable, with weather delays slightly increasing in 2016 (EUROCONTROL, 2017).

Figure 2.80 - Primary Delay Causes 2015 vs. 2016 (EUROCONTROL, 2017).

Delays from all-causes for Q3 2017 illustrates a poorer punctuality than that of Q3 2016 with 76% of flights arriving on time compared to 79% in Q3 2016 (Figure 2.81). This translated to a quarterly average all-cause departure delay of 15.1 minutes per flight, an increase of 2.6 minutes per flight on Q3 2016. A strong increase in daily flights of 4.8% in ECAC for the quarter is a common underlying factor in the main reported causes (EUROCONTROL, 2017):

- Reactionary (knock-on) delay increased by 19% contributing 6.8 minutes to the 15.1 minute average delay per flight, a 45% share of delay minutes.
- Delays due to airline operations remained the main cause of primary delay, contributing 3.8 minutes to the average delay per flight, a slight increase.
- Airlines reported that en route ATFM delays increased by 0.7 minutes per flight to 1.7 minutes per flight, following industrial action in France during September. There were also ATC capacity and en route weather issues affecting Karlsruhe and Maastricht UACs throughout the quarter.
- Airport operations delay including ATFM increased to 1.7 minutes per flight and was the second highest cause in the share of primary delay behind airline causes.

Figure 2.81 - Breakdown of the Average Delay per Delay Q3 2016 vs. Q3 2017 (EUROCONTROL, 2017a)

KEY TOPIC T2.7 – FACTORS IN OVERALL AIR TRAVEL TIME

The projected uptick in world passenger traffic challenges the stakeholders involved to optimize the current aviation system and find new solutions being able to cope with the promoted goals of international regulators such as Flightpath 2050 and ACARE. Targets are four hours door-to-door for 90 % of travellers, a 40 % reduction of turn-around times by 2050, and the arrival and departure of each aircraft should be accomplished within one minute of the scheduled time. Especially large airports are located far from the city centre, resulting in long airport access times for passengers combined with buffer times for uncertainties of durations for airport processes like security checks or even unpredictability of airport access times. Therefore, **key enablers to reduce overall travel times are a reduction in airport access times, a higher predictability of times accessing the airport and process times inside the terminal.**

"DATASET2050 (DATA driven approach for a Seamless Efficient Travelling in 2050) is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by European Commission under H2020-Call MG.1.7-2014: Support to European Aviation Research and Innovation Policy; The CSA - sometimes simply referred as "project" - is coordinated by Innaxis, with EUROCONTROL, University of Westminster and Bauhaus

Luftfahrt as partners. DATASET2050 was launched during December 2014 and will last 36 Months, ending December 2017.

The project addresses the EU passenger mobility in the context of the door-to-door (D2D) objectives defined in the Flightpath 2050 vision. Specifically, the following is the list of overall objectives, challenges and how these are being faced in the project:

- To provide useful insight into the door-to-door European travel paradigm through a cutting-edge data science approach for the present, 2035 and 2050 transport scenarios.
- Taking a passenger-centric approach, paving the way for a seamless and efficient door-to-door travelling experience.

Through this approach, the focus is to analyse how the European transport supply profile (capacity, connections, business models, regulations, intermodality, processes, and infrastructure) could adapt to the evolution of the demand profile (customers, demographics, passenger expectations, requirements).

- To identify European transport bottlenecks and improvement areas across the different scenarios, through expert application of state-of-art predictive analytics, modelling, statistical analyses, data visualisation, along with an examination of multimodal data.
- These findings will serve as a basis for the development of intermodal transport concepts by identifying possible solutions for current and predicted shortcomings. The insights gained through the project's approach will also highlight research needs for the four-hour door-to-door goal formulated by ACARE.

The performed tasks include:

- Looking at the requirements of the data to feed the DATASET2050 model at all its phases (i.e. door-to-kerb, kerb-to-gate, gate-to-gate, gate-to-kerb and kerb-to-door);
- Conducting an intensive review on what data are available, together with analysing temporal/geographical coverage, granularity, cost etc.;
- Designing and developing a visual tool that enables an easy exploration of the datasets
- Developing a data driven model capable of simulating the door-to-door processes;
- Completing the current demand profile, including the current mobility details (passenger behaviour, demographics, passenger expectations, and requirements).

DATASET2050 aims to have socio-economic impact in the context of how EU door-to-door "transport" performs and predicting how it will perform in the future. In the long term, DATASET2050's outcome will contribute to fewer disruptions and smoother travel for passengers.

The first progress beyond the state-of-the-art is calculating what the current D2D mobility metrics are. This way, a better holistic passenger-centric view will be accomplished, putting the first milestone in the path of providing D2D quantitative metrics further than the already available qualitative analyses.

In parallel, by using the data-driven model developed in the project, DATASET2050 will try to predict what will be the bottlenecks in future mobility scenarios (2035 and 2050). This prediction will include assessing and analysing how compressible the D2D sub-segments are; what are the potential futuristic scenarios; which will tentatively be the future demand and supply profiles in transport etc.

The DATASET2050 report provides a holistic view of the different, current supply-profile processes involved in European journeys involving at least one air-transport segment. The most important outcome is the amount of valuable data (both qualitative and quantitative) that can be used in modelling, specifically for adequately modelling the current mobility-supply elements. The effort allocated has enabled the discovery and access to difficult-to-reach datasets and to plan how to model the air transport supply profile. Following the DATASET2050 approach, the door-to-door process has been divided into five simpler phases: door-kerb-gate-gate-kerb-door.

The outcomes of the DATASET 2050 report range from the provision of specific data about certain airport processes (e.g. minimum times for different types of flight connection at an airport, the different surface transport options available and their timings) to the scientific research done on how to model the processes (e.g. catchment areas vs an airport feeder approach). The rationale, hypothesis, scope, literature review and some specific case studies that enable an easy understanding of the overall approach, are given in the main text sections of the reports whereas the data discovered in quantitative research are presented in tables in the appendices.

According to DLR report regarding the Flightpath 2050 goal 4 the following elements are needed for the assessment of the current state:

- European origin-destination passenger demand data matrix;
- Flight schedules;
- Train schedules (limited to air/rail code sharing);
- Ground access/egress times between NUTS regions and airports;
- Assumptions on process times (MCT, time from airport arrival to flight departure/flight arrival until exit from airport).

The minimum travel time between regions consists of the following elements:

- travel time from the point of origin to the departure airport
- the process time required from the arrival of the passenger at the departure airport to the scheduled time of departure (at)
- the flight time from the departure to the arrival airport– in case of a connecting flight, this element also contains the flight time of the first flight segment, the transfer time at the hub and the flight time of the second flight segment
- the process time required from the scheduled arrival time at the arrival airport to the point in time when the passenger leaves the arrival airport (at);
- travel time from the arrival airport to the destination point.

Using scenarios to test the desired Flightpath2050 4-hour-goal the report concludes by using data from “ETISplus”: Modelled origin-destination trip demand from EU project ETISplus and “Population product”: Theoretical situation, in which each EU citizen visits each other EU citizen that already today 91.7% of travellers can complete their journeys within 4 hours (with 60 min MCT in air transport). Only 13.1% of trips would be completed within 4 hours if every EU citizen would try to reach each other EU citizen.

The 91.7% value is due to the fact that most trips are over short distances, which can be completed within 4 hours with car/rail modes. But, if a theoretical situation in which every EU citizen should have the opportunity to visit every other EU is aspired, the goal has been achieved only to 13% (60minute MCT) or 22% (45min MCT).

The conclusion of the DLR report is that a re-phrase of the Flightpath 2050 goal is required. The proposed version states that “90% of travellers within Europe are able to complete their long-distance journey of over 200km (or 250km or 300km...), door to door, within 4 hours”.

2.5 Air Traffic Management (ATM) and Weather

****Flightpath 2050 goal 5: “Flights arrive within 1 minute of the planned arrival time regardless of weather conditions. The transport system is resilient against disruptive events and is capable of automatically and dynamically re-configuring the journey within the network to meet the needs of the traveller if disruption occurs. Special mission flights can be completed in the majority of weather, atmospheric conditions and operational environments”.***

The basic issue is overall ATM capacity, not only at airports and in terminal areas (goal 1 and section 2.1) but also en route, with spare capacity to cope with special missions, disruptions and weather hazards. The air traffic capacity must be consistent with a very high level of safety, such as the ICAO target level of safety (TLS) of probability of collision less $5E-9$ per hour. The critical parameter is separation between aircraft, in altitude, longitudinally or transversely in all flight conditions including air corridors, crossing, climbing and descending flights and turn manoeuvres. The safe separation limits the capacity available in a given airspace; increases in capacity can be obtained if the same or higher level of safety can be achieved with smaller separation; this requires greater accuracy in navigation and faster detection of position errors either random or due to use of inaccurate data.

The capacity available in each air space sector must be matched to allow the overall flow of traffic along optimal or near optimal routes that minimize travel time, fuel consumption and emissions and make air transport more convenient, economical and environmentally friendly. The weather effects can be of very different nature: (i) an airport equipped with Instrument Landing System (ILS) should not be affected by visibility conditions; (ii) a windshear warning at an airport will advise the transfer of flights to other locations; (iii) a volcanic eruption causing a large ash cloud may divert air traffic over a large area for a long time. With extreme weather events being not too frequent and adequate weather forecasting and now casting the effects can be minimized to a statistically smaller effect. Special mission flights or ultimately free flight in which each aircraft can choose its own route depend on available capacity, the ability to ensure safety and the reconfiguration of the airspace. While reconfiguration is common practice within a sector its effect across sector boundaries may require an overall adjustment of the ATM scenario. Improvements in navigation and communication may allow all weather operations at airports without special equipment and an evolution from pre-planned towards free flight.

KEY TOPIC T2.8 – WEATHER EFFECTS ON AIR TRAFFIC

Flight Efficiency

Flight efficiency Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) measure the degree to which airspace users are offered the most efficient trajectory on the day of operation. It is reported in Europe by the Central Office for Delay Analysis (CODA) and in USA by the Department of Transportation. A first estimate of the ATM-related contribution toward overall air transport performance, is identified by analysing the reports of the main delays experienced by airlines

Up to now, the pursuit of flight efficiency has been focused on assessing trajectory-based horizontal measures in order to identify opportunities of ATM improvements in the European and US system.

More recently, the attention has shifted to address vertical flight profiles and the analysis of fuel-efficient continuous descent operations. The ICAO has identified these aspects as the key steps to improve the “efficiency spectrum”, and in particular, fuel-efficiency - costs, environment - emissions that are directly related to fuel consumption. Lower fuel-burnt results in lower emissions, and environmental noise effects. The reduction of descent – related noise is a positive factor for the traffic growth and for the environmental pollution. Indeed, these operations will support the ambitious goals set out for the contribution of aviation to the world-wide emissions.

ICAOs has identified 11 Key Performance Areas (KPAs) of interest in understanding overall ATM system performance: Access and Equity, Capacity, Cost Effectiveness, Efficiency, Environmental Sustainability, Flexibility, Global Interoperability, Predictability, Participation, Safety, and Security.

Weather Hazards: Frequency and Severity

In-flight weather hazards (for the purpose of this report, “weather hazards” include weather conditions as icing, strong wind, low visibility, snow, and so on) has become a difficult problem worldwide and this impacts on Air Traffic Management (ATM) systems. For example, icing causes a significant drop in the available airport capacity and may be the cause of accidents.

In USA the Bureau of Transportation Statistics (BTS) establishes air traffic related data and statistics (see for example data on weather-dependent delay on the Figure 2.82), whereas in Europe such information (also used for the purpose of market analysis) derives from different sources. For example, Eurostat reports air traffic observed at EU-28 level, while information and data on air traffic at national level are reported by the national civil aviation authorities or associated statistics agencies. Moreover, both Europe and USA receive information on delay and operational data for scheduled flights from airlines. These features are used for punctuality indicators of flight.

In many performance analysis indicators and modelling processes concerning atmospheric condition adopted by US Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) time periods are categorized in visual or instrumental weather conditions (VMC/IMC), as indicated by the criteria in the Table 2.21. All major airports are characterized by specific thresholds associated to visual, marginal or instrumental approaches. It is, also, considered as a practical way of comparing weather changes over time.

Moreover, VCM/IMC provide a first-order observation of the primary criteria for defining weather.

Figure 2.82 – US Weather’s Share of National Aviation System (NAS) Delays in the period November 2016 – November 2017 Source: 2015 – “Source U.S. DOT Bureau of Transportation Statistics. Airline On-Time Statistics and Delay Causes. http://www.transtats.bts.gov/OT_Delay/ot_delaycause1.asp?type=4&pn=1

		Visibility (miles)		
		< 3	[3, 5)	≥ 5
Ceiling (feet)	≥ 3,000	Instrument	Marginal	Visual
	[1000, 3000)	Instrument	Marginal	Marginal
	< 1,000	Instrument	Instrument	Instrument

Table 2.21 - Ceiling and visibility criteria

Source: 2015 – “Comparison of ATM-related performance: U.S. – Europe”

At US airports, the higher frequency of instrument meteorological conditions (IMC) combined with scheduling closer to visual meteorological conditions (VMC) are key elements to reduce winter delays.

As evident from the Figure 2.82, weather-dependent delays are more relevant during summer. This variability may be related to scheduling (due to increased traffic?) and features like the heterogeneous weather conditions in the different US states. Indeed, the strong jet stream winds in the winter and convective weather in the summer impact overall predictability statistics.

It is important to note that the ATM performance depends on a number of factors and is affected by meteorological conditions, such as visibility, wind, convective weather and so on and can vary significantly by airport equipment (instrument approach system, radar, etc.), runway configurations (wind conditions), and approved rules and procedures. In light of this, a key element of system performance is to the impact on predictability of ATM, airline, and weather influences.

According to a recent document “2015 Comparison of ATM-related performance: U.S. – Europe”, both in US and Europe, weather is the predominant element affecting the airport throughput and as consequence of ATM - related departure restrictions. However, in Europe weather-related constraints represent a smaller share of delays than in USA. Indeed, Europe has also a notable feature of capacity-related delays that depend on capacity and staffing constraints. The difference between US and European data may derive from the fact, that the US system adopts “homogenous” procedures owing to the single service provider using the same tools and equipment, communication processes and so on. By contrast, at the ATC level the European system and the provision of air navigation services is still fragmented. Since 2004, Single European Sky (SES) initiative is aimed at reducing this fragmentation and at improving efficiency and interoperability of the ATM system through the creation of additional capacity. In addition, the susceptibility to weather events at the airport level, is largely based on geographic location and traffic density.

At system level, weather in Europe is less favourable than the US, but for airport related delays, the percentage of delayed flights at the gate or on the surface is slightly higher in the US than in Europe. The Figure 2.83 shows, the percent of time spent in marginal, visual and instrument flight in Europe and the US in 2013 and in 2015 between 6AM-10PM local time.

Figure 2.83 - Impact of weather conditions on flight operations in the US and Europe

Source: 2015 – “Comparison of ATM-related performance: U.S. – Europe”

Both U.S. and Europe use an effective atmospheric conditions observation system, METAR, also known as Meteorological Terminal Aviation Routine Weather Report or Meteorological Aerodrome Report, to monitor the weather. It contains data on temperature, dew point, wind speed and direction, precipitation, cloud cover and heights, visibility, and barometric pressure. Events such as rain showers, thunderstorms and strong winds, occurring during periods with high visibility and clear skies, are not assessed and ceiling and visibility provide only a preliminary step to measuring weather conditions. However, additional efforts are required to relate weather conditions on airport and air traffic performances and to develop a more comprehensive assessment of weather impact.

Over the period 2010-2015, the improvements on this issue in Europe have occurred mainly because of a notable reduction of ATM-related departure delay, enhancements in taxi-out procedures, and better en route flight efficiency. It is important to point out that in 2010 high delays in Europe have been originated not only by adverse weather, but also by Air Traffic Control (ATC) strikes. On the other hand, the performance improvement in the US can be mainly associated to a substantial improvement in taxi-out efficiency. Between 2013 and 2015 the total ATM-related ground delay in the US decreased by 12.7%, while a notable performance deterioration in Europe was attributable to a significant increase in capacity/volume related delays. However, it is worth noting that also events such as temporary maintenance of runway or dependencies with traffic flow of nearby airports during good weather may influence the performances.

As it concerns the route and traffic re-orientation under severe weather conditions in USA, Severe Weather Avoidance Plan (SWAP) routes have been pre-validated and coordinated. SWAP is a formalized program that is developed for areas where weather hazards, like thunderstorms may produce disruption in air traffic flows. In Europe, EUROCONTROL is responsible for a reference document, named the RAD- Route Availability Document, containing the policies, procedures and description for route and traffic orientation. The compatibility with national procedures ensures each State with regard to the airspace organisation.

As it concerns the apparatuses employed to assist the air operations, especially under severe weather conditions, the (ILS) Instrument Landing System is a lateral and vertical beam aligned with the runway centreline in order to guide aircraft to the runway threshold for landing. To maintain the signal integrity of the Instrument Landing System (ILS) the Low Visibility Procedures (LVPs) require increased spacing between aircraft, which in turn reduces throughput. As illustrated in the Figure 2.84 throughput rates depend on visibility conditions and are reduced significantly when LVPs have to be adopted. The analysis of performances associated to meteorological conditions provides an indication of weather impact on air traffic and put in evidence the airports mostly affected by weather:

Figure 2.84 – Impact of visibility conditions on runway throughput
Source: 2015 – “Comparison of ATM-related performance: U.S. – Europe”

ATFM delay attributed to weather at US and European arrival airports

The Air Traffic Flow Management (ATFM) is established to support Air Traffic Control (ATC) for an optimum flow of traffic. This is a service provided by the appropriate authority to promote safely, orderly and expeditious flow of air traffic.

In Figure 2.85 the average airport arrival ATFM delay at system level for the main 34 airports in Europe and USA between 2008 and 2015 are shown. For Europe all ATFM delays are included, whereas for the US only delays equal or greater than 15 minutes are included.

Figure 2.85 – Causes of weather-related airport ATFM delays in the period 2008-2015
Source: 2015 – “Comparison of ATM-related performance: U.S. – Europe”

When weather-related restrictions are present, higher ATFM delays per arrival can be observed for US compared to Europe. Major contributors to the delays in US are airports with high demand and highly variable capacity. Both in Europe and US, the main cause of delay is visibility, followed by wind, winter operations and thunderstorms. Overall, in the US between 2013 and 2015 weather related airport ATFM delays continuously decreased, whereas in Europe they have been characterized by almost the same (lower than in USA) values.

A high average weather-related airport arrival delay is usually the result of a notable capacity reduction in bad weather combined with a high level of demand.

Briefly the impact of weather on operations at an airport and as consequence on ATM performance can vary significantly in different airports and depends on a number of factors such as, airport and ATM equipment, runway configurations (wind conditions) and approved rules and procedures. Overall, the analysis of meteorological reports suggests that weather conditions at the main 34 airports in Europe are, on average, less favourable than in the US

Percentage of Airports with ILS

An Instrument Landing System (ILS) in the Airport is fundamental to enhance the reliability of landings in adverse weather conditions and to improve regularity of service, in particular, during periods of worst weather conditions. According to the European Geostationary Navigation Overlay Service (EGNOS) Bulletin, only the major airports are equipped with ILS. EGNOS is a system developed by European Commission, European Space Agency and EUROCONTROL, consisting of a network of satellites to increase the accuracy and integrity of GPS data for improving existing services or developing a wide range of new services. As an example, Italian Airports with ILS CAT III (year 2013) are 28 out of 39 (7 not having ILS, 4 having localizer) (source ENAV, 2013).

Chapter 3 - Maintaining and Extending Industrial Leadership

In order to maintain and extend its leading position in the aeronautical sector (3.1) the European industry must master each of a wide range of technologies (3.2) as well as their integration in an aircraft design and development program (3.3).

3.1 Retaining and Strengthening Market Share

Flightpath 2050 goal 6: "The whole European aviation industry is strongly competitive, delivers the best products and services worldwide and has a share of more than 40% of the world market".

The European aeronautical industry has achieved and sustained a near peer position with its worldwide competitors in the most important sectors:

- The Airbus-Boeing 'duopoly' dominates the market for jet airliners of more than 120 seats, with a full range of narrow and wide body aircraft;
- ATR is a leading supplier in the regional aircraft market;
- Airbus Helicopters (formerly Eurocopter) and Agusta-Westland are market leaders in helicopters;
- Safran and Rolls-Royce rival Pratt & Whitney and General Electric in aero-engines;
- In the equipment sector Liebherr, Safran, GKN and others are major suppliers of European and non-European aircraft;
- Dual use and specific technologies ensure an equally strong position in the world market for military aircraft, missiles, space launchers and satellites.

These impressive achievements across the full range of aeronautical products depends on:

- a. Leading-edge technologies in all the sectors contributing to the design of aeronautical vehicles;
- b. Integration of all these cutting-edge technologies in efficient aircraft production, certification and service support programmes.

These two aspects (a. and b.) are detailed in the next two sections (3.2 and 3.3). The aviation sector combines competition and collaboration in a worldwide context (Key Topic T3.1).

KEY TOPIC T3.1 - COLLABORATION STRUCTURE OF AEROSPACE FIELD BASED ON WEB OF SCIENCE DATABASE

For understanding the dynamics of a scientific field co-occurrence analysis is applied. In this report it is aimed to visualize the Aerospace Engineering field based on three categories as country, institution, and Web of Science categories. By the way, international scientific collaboration networks can be demonstrated nationally and institutionally and studied sub-fields can be determined. All visuals were prepared by using VOSviewer software (<https://www.cwts.nl/>).

Data is downloaded from Web of Science Database by using the "WC= ("Aerospace, Engineering")" query with last ten years limitation. By the way, 57.982 publications in the Web of Science Category in last decade is reached.

International Collaboration Networks

First visual is prepared for understanding the international collaboration network in the Figure 3.1:

Figure 3.1 - International Collaboration Networks with Document Frequency

As can be seen in the Figure 3.1, there are 6 clusters demonstrated with different colours. The node size is showing the publication frequency. It is clear that the largest frequency is coming with USA. It can be asserted that EuTable

ropean countries dominate four clusters except Israel's and the USA's. England, France, Germany, Netherlands, Italy, Spain, Belgium, Switzerland can be determined main actors in their clusters. This may be understood as the created innovation policy in EU level should be more diffusion-oriented not mission-oriented, because it is thought that national technological capabilities of aerospace engineering may not be collectivized but information and experience may. So, multi-objective policies may be more suitable than one. Hence, every cluster can gain excellence in different subfields and the experience and knowledge may be aggregated in a shared platform for aviation industry of EU. Moreover, from the Figure 3.1, it can be interpreted that, China's development may be analysed specifically to give insight for developing EU Aerospace Innovation policy also.

Collaboration Network of Institutions

Second visualization is prepared to understand the institutional collaboration network worldwide and demonstrated in the Figure 3.2:

Figure 3.2 - Institutional Collaboration Network

As can be seen in the Figure 3.2, there are many universities and research centres located in the map. European cluster can be identified here with blue coloured group. Two clusters are consisting the US universities and research centres. One is dominated by NASA and the other one is shared by some universities and United States Air Force.

Collaboration Networks in Aerospace Engineering Sub-Fields

Finally, last visual is prepared for understanding the research space of aerospace engineering by using the co-occurrences of different web of science categories. The prepared visual is demonstrated in the Figure 3.3:

Figure 3.3 - Collaboration Networks Based on Web of Science Categories

Naturally, main web of science category is aerospace engineering and it is the central node of the network. Clusters are covering these fields; 1. Mechanical engineering including biomedical engineering, robotics and manufacturing; 2. Physics, automation, telecommunications, electric-electronic and computer science; 3. Materials science optics, Nano-science, remote sensing; 4. Energy, polymer science; 5. Acoustics, thermodynamics; environmental studies, geology. From the visual, it can be asserted that physics, computer science and materials engineering are intersection fields. Therefore, including these fields may boost the collaborative studies while preparing funding policy for aerospace innovation.

3.2 Cutting-edge at the Full Range of Technologies

*** Flightpath 2050 goal 7: “Europe will retain leading edge design, manufacturing and system integration capabilities and jobs supported by high profile, strategic, flagship projects and programmes which cover the whole innovation process from basic research to flight demonstrators”.**

The design of a successful aircraft does not tolerate any less than first-rate solutions in an extensive range of 10 technologies. Only a few examples of each are given:

- Flight physics: This covers the most efficient aircraft designs, either refinements of the conventional tube-and-wing configuration whose development potential is not yet exhausted or more radical designs (flying wings, joined wings, flush or buried engines, hybrid and distributed propulsion) that hold greater promises and challenges.
- Aerodynamics: Advances in Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), wind tunnels and flight testing, concerning optimization of overall aircraft configurations and critical aspects like wing design, laminar flow, turbulent transition, shock waves, vortex wakes and their interactions;
- Propulsion systems including prop-fans and open rotors, high by-pass ratio turbofans, turboprops and turboshafts, hybrid and distributed propulsion over a wide range of thrust and power usable in various flight regimes;
- Lightweight structures able to withstand flight and landing loads, resist flutter and incorporate load alleviation features, with acceptable production and maintenance costs;
- Selective use of the most appropriate metals, alloys, composites, ceramics and other materials for airframes, engines and highly stressed or intensely heated components;
- Efficient production methods allowing fabrication and joining of sub-assemblies with tight tolerances and high-quality finish;
- Avionic systems including sensors, emitters, receivers, power supplies, signal conditioning and other features relevant to optimal navigation, weather and hazard detection and the accomplishment of a variety of missions;
- Integrated control for flight stability of high gain responsive systems, digital engine control, structural load alleviation, automatic navigation, safety protection and other features;
- Distributed, centralized or embedded computation and data processing capabilities in open architectures amenable to the incorporation of new components to enhance performance without degrading safety and reliability;
- Telecommunication systems for navigation and seamless integration into ATM, data exchange with the ground and other platforms, with resistance to jamming, electromagnetic interference and cyber-attacks;
- The whole range of support equipment including electric, pneumatic and mechanical actuators, air conditioning and pressurization, undercarriage and control of movable surfaces, fault diagnosis and ground support.

Since a substandard mastery of only one of these technologies can cripple an aircraft design and doom its market prospects, it is imperative to keep at the forefront of all these 10 technologies to avoid being caught off guard by a competitor. Also, these technologies must be ready for integration

in new competitive products at any time required to maintain market leadership in a new development programme (section 3.3).

The competitiveness of the aerospace industry depends on mastering cutting edge technologies over a wide range of subjects (Key Topic T3.2). An indicator of innovation in aviation as in other sectors are the patents in related subjects (Key Topic T3.3).

KEY TOPIC T3.2 – CUTTING-EDGE AT THE FULL RANGE OF TECHNOLOGIES

Introduction

Modern Europe is facing several challenges, among which is the introduction of innovative technological solutions to the European aviation market. The necessity to introduce new technological solutions results from the needs of society, new technologies that have appeared and new types of transport means and air transport systems.

Societal needs should be understood, among other things, as:

- The growing demand for air transport services,
- Expectations of increasing the availability of transport services (geographical, economic, etc.),
- Reducing the impact of air transport on people and the whole natural environment,
- Improvement of safety,
- Others.

New technologies that have appeared should be understood, among other things, as:

- New materials and fabrication technologies,
- New types of power units,
- New types of energy storage sources,
- New information technologies,
- New design technologies,
- New technologies in the area of management,
- Others.

New types of means of transport and air transport systems should be understood, among other things, as:

- Implementation and integration of flights of manned and unmanned aircraft in the common airspace,
- New air transport systems (small air transport system, sat system),
- Vertical take-off and landing aircraft,
- New take-off and landing technologies,
- Others.

The answer to these challenges are the two aviation programs currently being implemented in Europe.

The first one is Clean Sky 2, the largest European research programme developing innovative, cutting-edge technology aimed at reducing CO₂, gas emissions and noise levels produced by aircraft. Funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 programme, Clean Sky contributes to strengthening European aero-industry collaboration, global leadership and competitiveness.

The second one is SESAR 2020, demonstrating the viability of the technological and operational solutions already developed within the SESAR R&I Programme (2008-2016) in larger and more operationally-integrated environments. SESAR 2020 will prioritise research and innovation in a few areas, namely integrated aircraft operations, high capacity airport operations, advanced airspace management and services, optimised network service performance and a shared ATM infrastructure of operations systems and services.

In addition to the two main programs were accomplished or are currently developing, smaller programs solving some of the selected problems mentioned before. Among them it can be pointed:

- EPATS (European Personal Air Transportation System) continued in the frame of Small Air Transport Roadmap (SAT-Rdmp),
- FUSETRA – Future Seaplane Traffic
- GABRIEL (Integrated Ground and on-Board system for Support of the Aircraft Safe Take-off and Landing),
- ERA (Enhanced RPAS Automation).

Clean Sky 2

The Clean Sky 2 Programme consists of four different elements, as shown in the Figure 3.4.:

- Three Innovative Aircraft Demonstrator Platforms (IADPs) for Large Passenger Aircraft (LPA), Regional Aircraft and Fast Rotorcraft, operating demonstrators at vehicle level,
- Three Integrated Technology Demonstrators (ITDs), looking at Airframe, Engines and Systems, using demonstrators at system level,
- The Technology Evaluator (TE), assessing the environmental and societal impact of the technologies developed in the IADPs and ITDs,
- Two Transverse Activities (Eco-Design, Small Air Transport (SAT)), integrating the knowledge of different ITDs and IADPs for specific applications.

Figure 3.4 - Structure of the Clean Sky 2 Programme (CS2, 2015)

Large Passenger Aircraft IADP

Large Passenger Aircraft goal is high-TRL demonstration of the best candidates to accomplish the combined key ACARE goals with respect to the environment, fulfilling future market needs and improving the competitiveness of future products. The focus is on large-scale demonstration of technologies integrated at aircraft level in three distinct 'Platforms':

- Platform 1 "Advanced Engine and Aircraft Configurations"
- Platform 2 "Innovative Physical Integration Cabin – System – Structure"
- Platform 3 "Next Generation Aircraft Systems, Cockpit and Avionics"

Regional Aircraft IADP

Regional aircraft are a key element of Clean Sky through a dedicated ITD - Green Regional Aircraft (GRA), providing essential building blocks towards an air transport system that respects the environment, ensures safe and seamless mobility, and builds industrial leadership in Europe.

The following demonstration programmes for regional aircraft a/c are now foreseen:

- 2 Flying Test-beds (to minimize the technical and programme risks) using modified existing regional TP a/c with underwing mounted engines, for demonstration campaigns of: air vehicle configuration technologies; wing structure with integrated systems and propulsion integration; flight dynamics, aerodynamic and loads alleviation; advanced flight controls and general systems, and avionics functionalities.
- 5 Large Integrated Ground Demonstrators: full-scale wing, full-scale cockpit; full-scale fuselage and cabin; all including their associated systems; flight simulator; iron bird. In addition, a Nacelle ground demonstrator will be done in the Airframe ITD.

The Demonstration Programme will be divided into technologically compatible and "scope close" demonstrations sub-programmes:

- FTB1 - Innovative Wing and Flight Controls (Regional IADP)
- FTB2 - Flight Demonstration of a highly efficient and low noise Wing with Integrated Structural and related Systems solution, including power plant aspects (Regional IADP)
- Full-scale innovative fuselage and passenger cabin (Regional IADP)
- Flight Simulator (Regional IADP)
- Iron Bird (Regional IADP)
- Ground Demonstration of the wing (Airframe ITD)
- Ground Demonstration of the Cockpit (Airframe ITD)
- Nacelle ground demonstration (Airframe ITD)

Fast Rotorcraft IADP

The Fast Rotorcraft IADP consists of two separate demonstrators, the Tiltrotor demonstrator and the Compound Rotorcraft demonstrator.

The Fast Rotorcraft IADP consists of two concurrent demonstrators, the Tiltrotor demonstrator and the Compound Rotorcraft demonstrator along with transversal activities relevant for both fast rotorcraft concepts.

Airframe ITD

Aircraft level objectives on greening, industrial leadership and enhanced mobility, and the fulfilment of future market requirements and contribution to growth cannot be met without strong progress on the airframe. Within Clean Sky a more efficient wing with natural laminarity, optimised control surfaces and control systems, will have been demonstrated. Also, novel engine integration strategies will have been derived and tested, and innovative fuselage structures investigated.

Programme major Technology Streams:

- Innovative Aircraft Architecture, to investigate some radical transformations of the aircraft architecture.
- Advanced Laminarity as a key technological path to further progress on drag reduction, to be applied to major drag contributors: nacelle and wing.
- High Speed Airframe, to focus on the fuselage & wing step changes enabling better aircraft performances and quality of the delivered mobility service, with reduced fuel consumption and no compromise on overall aircraft capabilities.
- Novel Control, to introduce innovative control systems & strategies to gain in overall aircraft efficiency.
- Novel Travel Experience, to investigate new cabins including layout and passenger-oriented equipment and systems.
- Next Generation Optimized Wing Boxes, leading to progress on the aero-efficiency and the ground testing of innovative wing structures.
- Optimized High Lift Configurations, to progress on the aero-efficiency of wing, engine mounting & nacelle integration for aircraft who needs to serve small, local airports thanks to excellent field performance.
- Advanced Integrated Structures, to optimize the integration of systems in the airframe along with the validation of important structural advances and develop and to make progress on the production efficiency and manufacturing of structures.
- Advanced Fuselage to introduce innovation in fuselage shapes and structures, including cockpit & cabins.

Engines ITD

The following platforms or demonstrators are now foreseen:

- Open Rotor Flight Test,
- Ultra-High Propulsive Efficiency (UHPE) demonstrator addressing Short/Medium Range aircraft market,
- Business aviation/Short range regional Turboprop Demonstrator,
- Advanced Geared Engine Configuration (HPC and LPT technology demonstration),
- VHBR Large Turbofan demonstrator,
- Very High Bypass Ratio (VHBR) Middle of Market Turbofan technology,
- The Small Aero-Engine Demonstration.

Systems ITD

The Systems ITD in Clean Sky 2 will address these challenges through the following actions:

- Work on specific topics and technologies to design and develop individual equipment and systems and demonstrate them in local test benches and integrated demonstrators (up to TRL 5).
- Customisation, integration and maturation of these individual systems and equipment in IADPs demonstrators.
- Transverse actions will also be defined to mature processes and technologies with potential impact on all systems, either during development or operational use.

Technology Evaluator

In summary, the Technology Evaluator consists of three major tasks:

- Progress Monitoring of Clean Sky 2 achievements vs. defined environmental and societal objectives;
- Evaluation at Mission Level by integrating particular ITD outputs into TE concept aircraft/rotorcraft models;
- Impact Assessments at Airport and ATS Level using IADPs and TEs concept aircraft/rotorcraft models.

Eco-Design Transverse Activity

Eco-Design will aim for a roadmap of excellence, to provide high (European) individuality in quality and eco-compliance in the aeronautics vehicles⁹, in their whole product life.

Key Eco-Design & Recycle themes:

Identification and Life Information Strategy, MPR, manufacture & production, services to component and system (MRO, Finances/IT Know-How, limited life and extended life integration, inside-outside gate synergy processes), Integration/field-assembly-disassembly-separation, RE-Use, End of Life, Alternative Sectoral Applications, Use Phase (TE feed-back, vehicle utilization closure; eco-values).

Small Air Transport (SAT) Transverse Activity

The SAT Initiative proposed in Clean Sky 2 represents the R&T interests of European manufacturers of small aircraft used for passenger transport (up to 19 passengers) and for cargo transport, belonging to EASA's CS-23 regulatory base.

The approach builds on accomplished or running FP6/FP7 projects. Key areas of societal benefit that will be addressed are:

- Multimodality and passenger choice.
- Safer and more efficient small aircraft operation.
- Lower environmental impact (noise, fuel, energy).
- Revitalization of the European small aircraft industry.

SESAR 2020

The SESAR Vision identifies improvement areas where operational improvements supported by technical solutions will bring performance gains that yield the overall performance expected in Single European Sky High-Level Goals as set out in the European ATM Master Plan. These goals being threefold increase in ATM capacity, improve safety by a factor of 10, 10% reduction of the effects on the environment and a reduction of the cost for ATM services by 50%.

The realisation of the SESAR target concept follows strategic orientations described by four Key Features:

- Optimised ATM Network Services – its features will include activities in the areas of advanced airspace management, advanced Dynamic Capacity balancing and optimised Airspace User operations/UDPP. Innovative solutions are needed to better understand and improve the robustness (resistance to perturbations including meteorological perturbations) and resilience of the network.
- Advanced Air Traffic Services - the activities under Advanced Air Traffic Services will address enhanced arrivals & departures, separation management, enhanced air & ground Safety Nets and trajectory and performance based free routing. RPAS will be integrated into controlled airspace, enabled by suitable technical capabilities and procedures. Their trajectories are planned as compatible with the ATM network and provide an appropriate level of awareness for ATC.
- High Performing Airport Operations - the activities under this feature will address the enhancement of runway throughput, integrated surface management, airport safety nets, total airport management and remote tower for multiple airports. As airports remain one of the most significant bottlenecks in ATM and therefore represent great potential for system-wide improvement a significant focus will be placed on realising improvements.
- Enabling the Aviation Infrastructure - the enhancements described in the first three Key Features will be underpinned by an advanced, integrated and rationalised aviation infrastructure providing the required technical capabilities in a resource efficient manner. This feature will rely on enhanced integration and interfacing between aircraft and ground systems, including ATC and other stakeholder systems such as flight operations and military mission management systems. Communications, Navigation and Surveillance systems, SWIM, Common Support Services and the evolving role of the human will be considered in a coordinated way for application across the ATM system in globally interoperable and harmonised manner. Currently, RPAS operations are not routinely integrated into the ATM environment. The successful integration of RPAS, General Aviation (GA) and Rotorcraft with the commercial air traffic is a major activity in this feature.

OTHER PROJECTS

A few projects outside the Joint Undertakings (JUs) Clean Sky and SESAR are given as examples:

EPATS

Date: 2007-01-01 to 2008-06-30

The EPATS (European Personal Air Transportation System) focused on the future Highly Customer Oriented and Time and Cost-Efficient Air Transport System. It fills niche between Surface and

Scheduled Air Transport. Future mobility cannot be satisfied only through investments in hub and spoke, or rail - and highway systems.

This future EPATS system will provide a wide choice of transportation mode - and the wider use of small aircraft, served by small airports, to create access to more communities in less time.

The goal of the EPATS proposal was to demonstrate the needs and potential of small aircraft business development and to propose recommendations for the introduction of this new European Air Transportation System in the context of the European Research Areas.

The EPATS study will address the following issues:

The potential new market for personal aviation up to 2020.

- The potential impact of this new way of transport on the European ATM, and airport infrastructures, as well as the environmental, safety and security issues involved.
- The EPATS general specification and R&D Roadmap
- The studies will be carried out by a Consortium supported by representative experts of the EPATS stakeholder community.

The deliverables of these studies were rapports containing a joint vision of the personal air transportation system in Europe to 2020 and proposals for developing this new small aircraft business at a European level.

The EPATS SSA proposal fitted in the framework of FP6-2002-Aero-2

SAT-Rdmp

Date: 2011-01-01 do 2013-03-31

The Small Air Transport (SAT) focuses on the new affordable, accessible, energy effective component of Air Transport System (ATS). It fills niche between Surface Transport and Scheduled Large Aircraft Air Transport.

This future SAT system will provide enlarge choice of transportation mode, and the wider use of small aircraft served by small airports will create access to transport to more communities in a cost-effective way and in a short time.

The goal of the SAT-Rdmp study (CSA-SA) proposal was to improve the understanding of the commercial role that small-size aircraft operating on scheduled or non-scheduled flights, as a component of the Air Transport System, in order to satisfy the needs of transportation in regions where transport networks (especially surface transport) are underdeveloped.

Main issues of the SAT-Rdmp study (CSA-SA) proposal were:

- Definition of a common vision of the small aircraft transport system for inter-regional mobility through the identification of the corresponding requirements. The requirements will identify the technology needs and regulatory issues to be addressed.
- Definition of a business case compliant with the identified requirements which describes the relations among all the system's components.

- Assessment of current capabilities versus the ATS demand, collection of previous results and involvement of the stakeholders in Europe among all actors (manufacturers, research establishment, EASA, airspace users, infrastructure providers, airport managers, small aircraft service providers).
- Definition of a roadmap to fill the technology/regulatory/operative gaps in order to fulfil the requirements considering the current capabilities. Identification of dissemination actions and establishment of a network of stakeholders.
- Assessment of risks and benefits of the identified new system's concept.

The SAT-Rdmp study (CSA-SA) was a very important tool to support the European Commission in defining appropriate actions and a roadmap to implement the Agenda for Sustainable Future in Business and General Aviation. This was recommended by the EU Parliament Resolution on 3rd February 2009.

The SAT-Rdmp study (CSA-SA) was building the European synergy in that segment of Air Transport System, and was created European General Aviation Community by discussing, agreeing, finding common approach of European Key Players: Users, ATM, Manufacturers, Regulators, Research establishments.

The SAT-Rdmp study used the results from the previous EPATS (European Personal Air Transportation System) project. It also kept in close contact to the PPLane (Personal Plane) project funded by the Commission. Organisations that were involved in the EPATS and PPlane projects were also involved in SAT-Rdmp. This prevented a situation that studies were done twice and were ensure that SAT-Rdmp is complementary.

The SAT-Rdmp (CSA-SA) proposal fitted in the framework of FP7-AERONAUTICS and AIR TRANSPORT (AAT)-2010-RTD-1 Topic AAT.2010.7-12 "Assessing and further developing the role of small aircraft in the air transport system".

FUSETRA

Date: 2009.12.01 - 2011.08.31

The general objective of the FUSETRA project was to demonstrate the needs and to quantify the potential of seaplane traffic business development, and to propose recommendations for the introduction of new seaplane/amphibian transportation system, in the context of the European Research Area like the improvement of passenger's/customer's choice for better time and cost-efficient travel and transport. The main objectives were:

- Identification of possibilities to improve seamless travelling by implementation of seaplane transportation systems within the European air- & landside transportation infrastructure (connectivity of possible seaplane harbours to other means of transportation).
- Development of solutions which will be ready for implementation by ensuring passenger acceptance (Evidence of seamless travel, flight time reduction, reduced operational cost, reduced travel charges, operational safety, better access to international air traffic).
- Identification of reduced environmental impact of air transport by developing solutions for point-to-point seaplane operations (De-congestion of major airports, seaplane routes over uninhabited areas).

- Propositions for enabling uniform implementation (EC wide) of the chosen seaplane operational system (Regulatory issues, water landing fields, etc.).
- Improvement of the accessibility of regions by serving business as well as private mobility by new seaplane/amphibian connection.
- Identification of number of seaplanes or amphibians needed to replace existing aeroplanes and needed to satisfy the potential new demand.
- Improvement of trans-national co-operation by organising international workshops.

FUSETRA contributed substantially to the objectives of the EC policies, society and the scientific and technical objectives of the aeronautics priority by organizing international workshops and by inviting all relevant stakeholders as political and public authorities, decision makers, research communities, industries. FUSETRA contributed to the integration of old and new EC member states. The venues of Greece and Poland were intentionally chosen as being an ideal location to integrate the new member states in South-East and North-East Europe. This procedure supports building networks and tight cooperation's, too; and allows a wide distribution of crucial information on FP7. Partners and stakeholders of the new and old Member States have the possibility to network and to give examples of their experience and achievements by giving papers or participating in working groups with specific work packages. Seaplane operators and industrial stakeholder were mainly small and medium-sized enterprises. The workshops and the technical objective to prepare an action plan and road map for future seaplane traffic systems was particularly addressed to those companies. FUSETRA was directly linked to the vision 2020 of the aeronautical strategy ACARE. Two objectives of the ACARE research agenda were in the focus of this proposal. With new concepts for sea parks and scheduled flights of Seaplane/amphibian operations and its integration to the sea/air/land transport chain, this proposal contributed to "novel solutions for efficient airport use and connecting air transport to the overall transport system" and will "increase the time efficiency of air transport".

GABRIEL

Date: 2011.09.01 - 2014.08.31

The future air transport system will be confronted with new challenges: it must be safer, greener and more effective than the current system. There will be more global industrial competition and fossil fuel reserves will diminish leading to increased fuel prices. New radical ideas, methods and technologies are needed to respond to these challenges and to keep Europe world leader in aviation. One of the ideas that came from the Out of the Box project was to launch and recover aircraft by using ground-based power. Several ideas were proposed like using microwave power technology, hoisting aircraft in the air, aircraft carriers type of aircraft launch and recovery etc.

The GABRIEL proposal was based on a system using magnetic levitation technology to enable aircraft take-off and landing. This unique solution will reduce aircraft fuel consumption since aircraft weight can be reduced as no undercarriage will be needed, less fuel needs to be carried on-board and engines can be smaller as less thrust is needed. Using ground power will also reduce CO₂ and NO_x emissions at airports whilst noise levels can be substantially reduced since only airframe noise will be produced during take-off. Airport capacity can be increased by introducing multiple launch and recovery ramps thus alleviating the problem of limited runway capacity in Europe.

Gabriel was investigated if such a system is feasible and cost effective.

Magnetic levitation is already a developed and deployed technology in rail transportation. However, research is needed to prove the technical feasibility of the concept in air transportation. GABRIEL was investigated how to adapt the existing magnetic levitation technology and to redesign the aircraft and more particularly its fuselage. The project also studied the feasibility of launch and recovery in connection to operating limits and aircraft flight controls. Operational and safety issues were studied extensively. A small-scale test was designed to validate, assess the feasibility and estimate the limits of the assisted take-off and landing concept. The issue of emergency landings was addressed.

The project also performed an extensive cost benefit analysis, covering the effects on fuel savings, environmental benefits, new airport infrastructures and the required power supply.

The GABRIEL was a typical “out of the box” project that involved 12 partners from 7 European countries.

ERA

Date: 2015.02.12 – 2019.12.30

The project will support the use of military and civil RPAS in non-segregated airspace in Europe. It will also help in the integration of RPAS in airport operations to address capability gaps that have been identified in the European RPAS steering group roadmap for RPAS air traffic insertion.

The project will work with the European Organisation for Civil Aviation Equipment (EUROCAE) to develop draft standards, with collaboration from stakeholders including the Eurocontrol and European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA). The project will also work towards establishing European standards that will offer technical grounds for the certification of auto-taxi, automatic take-off and landing and automation and emergency recovery functionalities.

To achieve the project goals, technical and procedural solutions will be developed, and demonstrated by simulations and flight trials.

ERA is a European Defence Agency (EDA) ad-hoc project launched by five Member States: France, Italy, Poland, Sweden and Germany as the lead nation. The planned duration of the project is 42 months with an overall budget of around €31 million (excl. VAT).

The ERA industrial consortium is led by Airbus Defence and Space, and composed of sixteen partners from five EDA Member States: Airbus Defence and Space and ESG Elektronik system- und Logistik-GmbH from Germany; Sagem, Thales and ONERA from France; Saab from Sweden; Finmeccanica from Italy; and nine partners from Poland: Air Force Institute of Technology (leadership Polish consortium), Institute of Aviation, Hertz Systems Ltd., EUROTECH, PIAP (Przemysłowy Instytut Automatyki i Pomiarów), Eskadra Grzegorz Trzeciak, Politechnika Rzeszowska (Rzeszow University of Technology – RUT), WB Electronics S.A., Asseco Poland S.A.

KEY TOPIC T3.3 – MAPPING PATENTS IN AVIATION TECHNOLOGIES

Introduction and Short Background Literature for Aviation Technologies

According to IATA records first scheduled commercial airline flight took place from St. Petersburg, FL to Tampa, FL on January 1914. Beginning with national flights, international flights came forward and long-range flights have taken place in a decade by KLM in 1924. And now, 4 million people scheduled, and 58.2 million freight transported with a revenue of 743 billion in 2017 (IATA Fact Sheet, 2017). However, there are many challenges for aviation industry especially from the environmental side. The amount of greenhouse gases generated by the aviation industry accounts for about 3% of the total generated amount in the world. Moreover, because the greenhouse gases are exhausted in high-altitude areas trees and plants cannot absorb it as in road-related greenhouse gases. Therefore, aforementioned 3% becomes 13% of the overall greenhouse effect by the aviation industry.

Now, the dilemma is coming for aviation industry with increasing demand on passenger traffic and the environmental goals of the next few decades. Based on the study of Kellari et al. (2017) general domains of study in aviation technology includes *"the optimization of existing aircraft architectures for maximizing aircraft performance or minimizing environmental impact; examining potential future architectures which have superior performance over the current dominant design; and, extrapolating performance trends in order to predict future aircraft performance."*

Optimization studies are mostly aimed to minimize fuel burn, emissions or noise, or operating costs. Multidisciplinary design optimization is generally used in this field for optimization. Kellari et al. (2017) mentioned some technological advancements as blended-wing body or flying wing architecture; "double-bubble" and "hybrid wing body" architecture of NASA. According to author, engine architecture is a major driver for aircraft architecture. Bypass ratio, increasing individual component efficiency, and increasing turbine inlet temperature along with increasing overall pressure ratio are the study trends on engine improvement field. However, there are technical constraints regarding material thermal properties, emission regulations, aerodynamic issues and geometric constraints of the dominant architecture.

There are a few scholarly works in accordance with the technological analysis on aviation technology. One of them is Nakamura et al. (2012)'s study which aimed to map aerospace engineering comparatively with citation network analysis by using patent data of aerospace industry and Toyota. They found that, in system level there are similar technology fields for improvement in both aviation and Toyota. In another study Kwon and Lee (2012) prepared a technology forecast for sustainable (green) aviation by using patent analysis. Based on the study findings, it is asserted that technology developments for fuel cell and noise area in the green aviation technology area were continuously performed in the 2000s. Finally, they forecasted that new aircraft engines would be expected to be focused on for development as a new technology for future green aviation.

Data and Methodology in Brief

Patents, as a vital data source, are main outputs of research and development that represent the characteristics of technology. A vast amount of recent technical knowledge is available in patent documents and the importance of exploiting this knowledge has been constantly increasing since electronic patent database accessible worldwide (Ernst, 2003). Hence, patent data have been considered as an important source in technology evaluation and analysis research.

Patent analyses have been used to assess the knowledge diffusion and transfer processes in research and development which extract useful knowledge from databases. There are, of course, classification on using patent data as indicators of technology analysis (Karki, 1997). Patent analysis can be divided into macro-level research of national or industrial analysis (Curran & Leker, 2011) and micro-level research of particular technological diffusion analysis (Lee, Kim, & Cho, 2010) and forecasting (Chang et al., 2009). In the macro level, the major topics are technological innovation and evaluation of technological competitiveness of nations. In the micro-level, research activities, such as identifying technological advantages and disadvantages of competitors (Choi, Kim, & Park, 2007; Cotropia, Lemley, & Sampat, 2013; Harhoff, Narin, Scherer, & Vopel, 1999; Trajtenberg, 1990).

The patent analysis method has been used at length to understand the invention and innovation processes (Schmookler, 1966; Griliches, 1990). There are several different uses patent data such as the analysis of the time-lag between the allocation of research funds and patents issues (Daim et al, 2007); to assess innovation diffusion (Nelson, 2009); or predicting the future directions of technological development (Choi et al., 2011). There were two accepted perspectives in patent technology analysis; citation-based and content-based approaches. Citation-based studies consider the citations between two patents as knowledge flows (Gress, 2010). By using these knowledge flows main technological trends may be discovered. However, these visualizations neglected the patent contents and the quality of citation relationship cannot be recognized. On the other hand, content-based studies used text-mining techniques to measure the content similarity between pairs. Another alternative approach is network-based patent analysis which prepared for overcoming drawbacks of citation analysis. Although network analysis shares some commonality with citation analysis, its relative advantage is substantial. First, network analysis shows the relationship among patents as a visual network and therefore assists the analyser in intuitively comprehending the overall structure of a patent database. Second, network analysis enriches the potential utility of patent analysis because it takes more diverse keywords into account and produces more meaningful indicators (Yoon & Park, 2004). Network analysis based on text mining which decreases search time and cost. Therefore, it can be said that by applying network analysis approach content-based studies and citation-based studies are combined. A general patent analysis scenario may be demonstrated as in the Figure 3.5:

Figure 3.5 - Typical Patent Analysis Steps

As can be seen in the Figure 3.5 typical patent analysis steps begins with defining the scope, concepts, and purposes of the analysis. Second issue is deciding the search query strategy. After searching and downloading the related patents data should be segmented, cleaned and normalized. In the fourth step, patent content should be analysed to summarize their claims, topics, functions, or technologies. By clustering in the fifth step analysed patents grouped or classified based on some used metrics. These groups are visualized in sixth step and then technology or business trends and relations predicted at last step. As can be seen, this scenario requires the analyst to have a certain degree of expertise in information retrieval, domain-specific technologies, and business intelligence. This multi-discipline requirement makes such analysts hard to find or costly to train. Therefore, automated technologies for assisting analysts in patent processing and analysis are thus in great demand (Tseng, Lin, & Lin, 2007).

The patent analysis in the current study was performed with the use of the Vantage Point software (Watts *et al.*, 1997). Derwent Innovations Index is used as a data source. In Derwent Innovations Index, patents are divided into 20 broad subject areas or sections. These sections are grouped into three areas as; Chemical Sections (A - M), Engineering Sections (P - Q), Electrical and Electronic Sections (S - X). These sections are then further subdivided into classes. Each class consists of the section letter, followed by two digits. For example, X22 is the class designation for Automotive Electrics and C04 is the class for all Chemical Fertilizers.

Search term is used as 'aviation' in Topic field of patents and reached 23,508 patents. Because this study is configured as explanatory, filters are not applied to limit the data corpus at first. Data retrieved from the database and then cleaned for further analysis. Some pre-specified thesaurus and fuzzy clustering algorithms applied in this stage.

Findings

Trends of Patents on Aviation

Figure 3.6 – Number of patents in aviation per year

Figure 3.7 IPC subclasses year chart

(A; Human Necessities: B; Performing Operations; Transporting: C; Chemistry; Metallurgy: D Textiles; Paper: E; Fixed Constructions: F; Mechanical Engineering; Lighting; Heating; Weapons; Blasting: G; Physics: H; Electricity)

Figure 3.8 - Macro Classes

Figure 3.9 – Medium Classes

Figure 3.10 - Micro Classes

Sunburst Diagram for General and a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h Subclasses

Figure 3.11 Sunburst diagram for general and a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h subclasses

Code	%	Definition
G	27,3	Physics
B	24,9	Performing Operations; transporting
H	16,2	Electricity
C	13,1	Chemistry; Metallurgy
F	12,2	Mechanical Engineering lighting; Heating; Weapons; Blasting
A	3,7	Human Necessities
E	1,3	Fixed Constructions
D	1,3	Textiles; Paper

Table 3.1 – Some patent codes

Code	%	Definition
G01	12,7	Measuring; Testing
B64	9,3	Aircraft; Aviation; Cosmonautics
H01	6,2	Basic Electric Elements

Cod e	%	Definition
G06	6,2	Computing; Calculating; Counting
H04	4,0	Electric Communication Technique
C08	3,1	Organic Macromolecular Compounds; Their Preparation Or Chemical Working-Up; Compositions Based Thereon
C10	3,1	Petroleum, Gas or Coke Industries; Technical Gases Containing Carbon Monoxide; Fuels; Lubricants; Peat
F16	2,9	Engineering Elements or Units; General Measures For Producing And Maintaining Effective Functioning Of Machines Or Installations; Thermal Insulation In General
F02	2,9	Combustion Engines; Hot-Gas or Combustion-Product Engine Plants
H02	2,8	Generation, Conversion, or Distribution of Electric Power
B23	2,6	Machine Tools; Metal-Working Not Otherwise Provided For
G05	2,5	Controlling; Regulating
G08	2,0	Signalling
G09	1,9	Educating; Cryptography; Display; Advertising; Seals
C22	1,7	Metallurgy; Ferrous Or Non-Ferrous Alloys; Treatment Of Alloys Or Non-Ferrous Metals

Table 3.2 – Some patent sub codes (cont.1)

Cod e	%	Definition
B64C	4,1	Aeroplanes; Helicopters
B64D	3,7	Equipment for Fitting in Or To Aircraft; Flying Suits; Parachutes; Arrangements Or Mounting Of Power Plants Or Propulsion Transmissions
G06F	3,7	Electric Digital Data Processing
G01 N	2,2	Investigating or Analysing Materials by Determining Their Chemical Or Physical Properties
G01C	1,9	Measuring Distances, Levels or Bearings; Surveying; Navigation; Gyroscopic Instruments; Photogrammetry or Videogrammetry
G01 M	1,8	Testing Static or Dynamic Balance of Machines or Structures; Testing Structures Or Apparatus Not Otherwise Provided For
C08L	1,7	Compositions of Macromolecular Compounds
H01L	1,7	Semiconductor Devices; Electric Solid-State Devices Not Otherwise Provided For
G01R	1,4	Measuring Electric Variables; Measuring Magnetic Variables
B32B	1,4	Layered Products, I.E. Products Built-Up of Strata of Flat Or Non-Flat, E.G. Cellular Or Honeycomb, Form

Table 3.3 – Some patent sub-sub codes (cont.2)

Country Evaluations

Basic Patent Country	Patent Number
China	11876

Basic Patent Country	Patent Number
United States of America	3249
Russian Federation	2140
Soviet Union (USSR)	1393
World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO)	1327
Korea (South)	1308
European Patent Office	637
Germany	369
France	305
Japan	254
United Kingdom	191
India	98
Canada	56
Brazil	37
Australia	28
Belgium	28
Taiwan	26
Romania	19
Spain	15
Poland	14

Table 3.4 – Patent by country

➤ World Map

Figure 3.12 – World map distribution

➤ Top 10 Country Patent Numbers Per Year

Figure 3.13 – Evolution in the number of patents

➤ Top 10 Country Patent Numbers based on Subclasses Per Year

Figure 3.14 – Aviation patents per country

Patent Assignees

Patent Assignees	Record
Stats Chippac Ltd	369
Honeywell Int Inc	233
Shenyang Liming Aero Engine Group Corp	222
General Electric Co	193
Univ. Beijing Aeronautics & Astronautics	189
Univ. Nanjing Aeronautics & Astronautics	165
Boeing Co	151
Harbin Inst Technology	145
State Grid Corp China	142
Rockwell Collins Inc	123
Univ. Beihang	106
Avic Comml Aircraft Engine Co Ltd	103
Aviation Ind Corp China Shenyang Engine	99
Stats Chippac Pte Ltd	94
Univ. Northwestern Polytechnical	90
Aviation Materials Res Inst	88
Univ. China Civil Aviation	83
Thales	75
Avic Shenyang Engine Design Inst	71
United Technologies Corp	71

Table 3.5 - Top 20 Firms by number of patents

➤ Patent Numbers Per Year

Figure 3.15 - Top 10 Firms by patent number

➤ Patent Numbers Based on Subclasses Per Year

Figure 3.16 – Number of patents per holder

➤ Title Words Network

Figure 3.18 – Patents per subject

3.3 Efficient Development and Life-Cycle Management

Flightpath 2050 goal 8 “Streamlined systems engineering, design, manufacturing, certification and upgrade processes have addressed complexity and significantly decreased development costs (including a 50% reduction in the cost of certification). A leading new generation of standards is created”.

It is not sufficient to master the cutting-edge of all 10 relevant aeronautical technologies (goal 7 and section 3.2) it is also necessary to integrate them into a product with timely arrival in the market and competitiveness over the whole life-cycle:

- The mature and cost-effective technologies in all 10 relevant areas must be selected and incorporated in a new high-performance design that significantly improves over all existing products without an excessive development risk;
- The development program must focus on validation and verification of all new features that may involve a higher risk, while making sure that lessons learned are used to improve all other items;
- The production process must be as reliable and fast as possible, allowing for unexpected modifications with minimal upset and providing a margin for product evolution;
- The certification process must be considered from the beginning of design through development and production, to minimize the risk of redesigns and costly delays, that may have a domino effect on market availability and share;
- The supply chain and final assembly capabilities need to be able to keep up with high market demand, and survive market lows without cost penalties, while ensuring prompt service support in all situations;
- If the aircraft is not the first to the market it should try to claw back leadership by embodying performance enhancing features that cannot be incorporated in the existing competitors;
- If the aircraft is first to the market, it should anticipate the possible responses by competitors, leaving no room for alternatives that could render it outdated or uncompetitive;
- The competitiveness should be maintained by upgrades to keep the product ahead of other alternatives in performance, cost, availability and service support;
- In parallel with gradual improvement of the existing aircraft, a whole series of clean sheet designs covering a wide range of options should be pursued, to be ready to introduce the follow-on product at the right time to keep or increase market share.

The growing capability and complexity of modern aircraft increases the relevance of life-cycle analysis (Key Topic T3.4) that needs to be considered also at component level (Key Topic T3.5).

KEY TOPIC T3.4 – AIRLINER DEVELOPMENT TIME AND COST

Benchmarks

Current programmes did show a continuous rise in the cost of development (including certification) which is correlated with the increased complexity of the machine (frequently supported by new technologies) on one hand and the ever-larger demands for safety and lower life-cycle costs. The development time has shown a similar trend, responding to the same factors:

Aircraft	Year of First Service	Development Costs (Constant 2014 \$)	Development Time in Years
Douglas DC-3	1936	4.9 Million	2
Douglas DC-6	1946	173 Million	3
Boeing 707	1958	1.5 Billion	6
Boeing 747	1970	5.8 Billion	4
Boeing 777	1995	8.0 Billion	6
Airbus A380	2007	16.5 Billion	7
Boeing 787	2012	13.6 Billion	7
Airbus A350 XWB	2014	15.6 Billion	8

Table 3.6 – Some data on recent widebodies

Source: Bowen, J. *The Economic Geography of Air Transportation: Space, Time, and the Freedom of the Sky*. London: Routledge, 2010. Adapted and extended

An important remark is that all the programmes listed above were clean sheet projects. A significant upgrade of an existing model could reduce both the costs (by a factor of 1:5 to 1:10) and the time to first delivery (by a factor of 1:1.5 to 1:3), factor depending on the quantity of the improvement targeted. As an example, data available for Airbus A320neo (first delivery 20 January 2016) show a duration of the development of 5 years and an estimated cost of \$1.3 Billion.

Unfortunately, a comparative analysis of the tendency of the two measures in the Table above would not provide a correct indication of the degree of evolution because one would compare different sizes and generations of aircraft. So, the benchmark is to be created otherwise.

A simple and accessible approach is taken by P. Nolte et al in an article published by R. Curran and L. Fischer in *Air Transport and Operations. Proceedings of the Third International Conference* (page 525). The author considers the complexity by defining a Specific Development Cost (per number of model's passenger seats), SDC. Similarly, the development period might be corrected by the same parameter, resulting SDP – Specific Development Period. (The source mentioned here proposed one other measure, Development Cost per Seat Built, which we do not consider relevant for our purpose.)

Aircraft	Number of Seats	Development Costs (Constant 2014 \$ mil)	Development Time (Years)	SDC (\$mil/seat)	SDP (\$mil/year)
Douglas DC-3	21	4.9	2	0.2	2.5
Douglas DC-6	60	173	3	2.9	57.7
Boeing 707	145	1500	6	10.3	250.0
Boeing 747	410	5800	4	14.1	1450.0
Boeing 777	335	8000	6	23.9	1333.3
Airbus A380	545	16500	7	30.3	2357.1
Boeing 787	242	13600	7	56.2	1942.9
Airbus A350 XWB	325	15600	8	48.0	1950

Table 3.7 – Some data on legacy and current airliners

For this application, restricting the analysis to SDC and SDP is not expected to induce major errors. However, for a future increase of accuracy, other factors as service life, life cycle costs etc. should be considered.

Progress Up to Now

The programmers started around 2000 represent a peak in both SDC and SDP. What followed a decade later is a slight reduction in both, but much below the objective. As identified in SRIA 2017, significant reductions in the measures of aeronautical development efficiency (SDC and SDP) could be achieved by:

- Intensive use of modelling and simulation instead of physical test and experiment
- More specific, flexible and adaptive regulatory requirements (standards) for certification, including the involvement of airworthiness authority in virtual design.
- “A fully integrated multi-physics and multi-scale model of the complete aircraft including its engines and systems should be coupled with aerodynamic and thermal models, eliminating ground test rigs completely” (SRIA 2017 Action Area 2.9. page 45).

KEY TOPIC T3.5 – EFFICIENT DEVELOPMENT AND LIFE-CYCLE MANAGEMENT OF BATERIES

Life-Cycle Management for Secondary Batteries Possibly Used in Ground-Vehicles (e.g. towing-tractor) or Aircraft

LCA of EV´s [SOURCE: Procedia CIRP 29 (2015), 233-238]

The following consideration is related to automotive electro mobility and must of course have be adapted to general condition of aviation economy (e.g. ground-moving vehicles, taxiing etc.)

The environmental impacts of EVs depend on various parameters related to the vehicle’s characteristics, their location of use and user influences. Variations of driving patterns of different users and the use of heating and cooling due to local climate conditions have an impact on the energy consumption of EVs. In combination with the regional electricity mix these parameters influence the environmental impact of EVs. Therefore, the vehicles must be considered a part of the setting with which it interacts to answer specific LCA questions. When neglecting these interdependencies, important aspects might be missed and left out. Connecting external influences with the use phase of the vehicles assists the LCA practitioner to evaluate the influence of parameters on the environmental impact. Setting up a descriptive framework allows the LCA practitioner to translate external influencing factors into environmental impacts reducing the uncertainty of LCAs.

The Figure 3.19 shows the proposed framework and illustrates the EV as an element in a larger system of influencing factors and highlights the connection of energy consumption and external factors. The material and energy flows over the entire life cycle necessary to manufacture and operate the vehicle define the life cycle of the EV (mid-level). The setting of external factors in which the EV is deployed (top level) influences the life cycle and the LCA results. These external factors can be divided into three groups: the user, the infrastructure and the surrounding conditions.

Figure 3.19 LCA framework for electric vehicles [Source: TLKthermos, Institut für Werkzeugmaschinen und Fertigungstechnik]

➤ Vehicle

In the use phase specific characteristics of the vehicle influence the energy. These factors are considered internal in this framework as they are inherent properties of the vehicle.

➤ User

The user of the EV influences the environmental impact of the EV through the driving and charging behaviour as well as through the intensity of the use of auxiliaries. A more aggressive driving style leads to a higher energy consumption whereas a more cautious driving style results in a more efficient use of energy. Depending on the charging behaviour and the willingness to install renewable energy specifically for the EV (e.g. in the form of solar panels), the share of renewable energy can be increased significantly compared to the use of grid energy in many countries.

➤ Infrastructure

The electricity mix is one of the most crucial parameters for the LCA calculation. Using a mix based entirely on renewable energies delivers a completely different result than an energy mix based on fossil fuels. Choosing the adequate mix which reflects the real-world situation and leads to fair and reliable results is challenging.

SOURCE: Duce AD, Egede P, Öhlschläger G, Dettmer T, Althaus H-J, Bütler T, Szczechowicz E eLCAr—guidelines for the LCA of electric vehicles. January 31, 2013: Proj.no. 285571. (Report from project “E-Mobility Life Cycle Assessment Recommendations”, funded within the European Union Seventh Framework Programme—FP7/2007-2013).

In many LCAs an energy mix is used which is based entirely on renewable energy. However, often it is not clear if this represents the actual grid situation or if it is a case of crediting renewable energy to the EV rather than a different use. In the latter case it must be considered if the crediting can be justified. The charging of EVs can in principle often be carried out at regular household plugs. Yet, often more sophisticated solutions are required at workplaces or in public areas to allow adequate and safe charging. Depending on the conditions of the site the installation of these charging stations demands major building activities. These activities can be significant for specific scenarios in which only one or a few vehicles use one charging station. The available charging infrastructure also influences the options of smart charging. Smart charging applications can increase the share of renewable energy used to charge the EV.

➤ Surrounding Conditions

The surrounding conditions influence the environmental impact of EVs. The climate, the topography and the type of road are identified as significant factors for the energy consumption. The climate influences the need for heating and cooling appliances in the vehicle. The temperature varies both on a seasonal as well as on a daily level leading to a fluctuation of the energy consumption. Depending on the interaction of temperature and humidity the wind shield of the car can fog up and require ventilation or the use of the air conditioning and/or heating. Currently, resistance heating is mostly applied in EVs.

Recycling of Batteries Possibly Used in Ground-Vehicles (e.g. Towing-Tractor) or Aircraft [Source: B. Scrosati et. al, Advances in Battery Technologies for Electric Vehicles, Elsevier 2015]

The interest in sustainable vehicles, namely hybrid and/or electric (HEV, BEV), is increasing worldwide due to the growing concern about global warming and air pollution in large urban cities [1]. Predictions suggest that hybrid and/or electric vehicles in the year 2035 will have a 35% share of the automobile market, with an associated, considerable reduction of CO₂ emissions. To be successfully achieved, this important goal requires (Figure 3.19) an efficient power source for the electric engine and, in view of its high energy density, long life, and rate capability, the lithium-ion battery is an ideal candidate for this purpose [2].

[1] **Tarascon and Armand, 2001** [Tarascon, J.M., Armand, M., 2001. Issues and challenges facing rechargeable lithium batteries. *Nature* 414, 359.]

[2] **Scrosati and Garche, 2010** [Scrosati, B., Garche, J., 2010. Lithium batteries: status, prospects and future. *J. Power Sources* 195, 2419.]

For consumer electronics, e.g., for powering mobile phones, only a single cell is sufficient, whereas car driving battery packs require the assemblage of many cells and the inclusion of a safety battery management system (BMS).

The worldwide reserves of lithium carbonate (i.e., the lithium main natural source) are still large. Considering that the yearly production amounts to about 0.16 M tons and that ~0.5 kg of Li_2CO_3 are needed per kWh battery, we can estimate from 80 to 100 years of reserves. Nevertheless, almost 70% of the global lithium deposits are concentrated in South America's ABC (Argentina, Bolivia, and Chile) salars [3], and this poses an inherent risk for the accessibility of the raw material since unexpected events may condition the supply with a resulting impact on the battery price and consequently on the vehicle cost [4].

[3] **Scrosati, 2011** [Scrosati, B., 2011. Technology: charging towards the super-battery. *Nature* 473, 448]

[4] **Fletcher, 2011** [Fletcher, S., 2011. Bottled Lightning: Super-batteries, Electric Cars and the New Lithium Economy. Hill and Wang, New York. ISBN: 978-0-8090-3053-8]

Figure 3.20 - Battery pack as BEV power system. [Courtesy of Prof. Doron Aurbach, Bar Ilan University, Tel Aviv, Israel]

Furthermore, one has to consider that lithium is also the material of choice for applications other than batteries, including pharmaceuticals, ceramics, and glasses. Actually, the present consumption rate of lithium by OEMs is limited to a minor fraction, accounting for only about one quarter of the current lithium production. However, in the prospect of large road diffusion of BEVs (1 million expected in 2020), the amount of lithium needed to meet the market demand is expected to increase considerably. The prices of lithium constantly increased over the last 10 years; at time of publication, prices were \$5500–6000 per ton of lithium carbonate, depending on applications. Accordingly, considerable increases are expected if the demand rises. To limit the risks, many battery materials manufacturers underwent investment in partnerships with the South American ABC countries to secure the lithium supply and hence, to control prices fluctuations.

The above considerations clearly outline the need for recycling lithium car batteries once they have exhausted their operational life, with the final goal of reusing them back to the car manufacturers. The idea is well represented by the general scheme reported below, as proposed by the Japanese

Sumitomo company, see the Figure 3.20. The future of battery recycling, however, is still uncertain; see below.

Figure 3.21 - General operational loop for EV battery saving

The main goal of recycling is that of separating battery components, as well as of removing waste from the environment. However, the process is affected by a series of issues that make it very challenging. About 100,000 tons of spent batteries are forecast in the prospect of 1 million EV cars on the road and their treatment is not straightforward.

The main problem is in the collection rate, which is still at a very limited extent, even for lithium batteries used in mobile electronic devices. Although the circulating number of these devices, and hence of their batteries, is extremely high, the collection is scarce for a series of reasons. First, there are not many lithium battery collection points in the municipalities. In principle, the shops selling lithium battery-operating devices should serve as collection points for the related exhausted batteries. However, this rarely happens and the customer, out of laziness or forgetfulness, tends to drop the old telephone with the included battery in a drawer. The problem is serious to the point that often the capacity of the plants is not matched by the number of received spent batteries. Obviously, the situation is even more of concern for the car batteries, considering the very limited number of EVs presently in the road.

Another serious issue is associated with the intrinsic safety risk owing to the high reactivity of the lithium batteries, especially if they arrive at the recycling plant still with residual charge or if they are damaged. In fact, if overheated or overcharged, as it may happen by shorting when they are stored in masses, the batteries can enter a state of thermal runaway which can eventually lead to fire or even explosion. In addition, metallic lithium can also form on the graphite anode by overcharge and/or by abnormal deposition, whose high reactivity greatly increases the risk of explosion. The energy released by these explosions is powerful enough to melt the metal containers with resulting serious safety hazards.

The other serious issue is related to the fact that the lithium battery market is in continuous evolution with the advent of many new chemistries. Further, in addition to the rechargeable Li-ion batteries, also

primary lithium batteries, using cathodes such as manganese oxide or thionyl and sulfuryl chloride, are still in the market and they may arrive to the plant as well. Finally, also the electrolyte may widely change, passing from a variety of liquid organic solutions to polymer membranes. Clearly, this high diversity makes it difficult to develop a universally valid recycling process, as well as affecting its economics, since the new chemistries may not involve components worth being recovered.

Indeed, the European Commission has mandated a Battery and Accumulator Directive, which imposes to the state members the following targets [5].

[5] http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/portal/page/portal/waste/key_waste_streams/batteries.

- A 45% collection rate for waste-portable batteries to be met by September 2016.
- A recycling efficiency to ensure that a high proportion of the weight of waste batteries is recycled, this including 65% of lead-acid, 75% of nickel-cadmium, and 50% of "other waste batteries," the latter likely referring to lithium batteries.

Considering the present low economic value, these targets can be met only if subsidies are provided, usually adding a tax to each manufactured battery, as indeed is the case. Under this scheme, battery recycling plants are now operating in Europe (e.g., Batrec in Switzerland, Umicore in Belgium, and SNAM and Recupyl in France) to honour the mandate [6].

[6] Papers presented at 19th International Congress for Battery Recycling, ICBR 2014, Hamburg, Germany, and September 24–26, 2014

Plants are also in force under different schemes in the United States (e.g., Toxco) and in Japan (e.g., Sony and Sumitomo Metal). Due to the still scarce production of lithium-ion batteries of EV types, the recycling is for the moment limited to the portable ones. However, EV battery recycling is expected to gain quite a significant importance in the years to come, this enhancing the role of the experience obtained with the present small-scale prototypes.

Figure 3.22 - Typical lithium battery recycling flow sheet

➤ Government Regulations

Battery recycling (Figure 3.22) has been a task for many years motivated by environmental awareness and waste legislation mandates. With the public's increase in environmental sensibility, growing attention is paid to sustainable management of natural resources. The public also has an increasing concern with the hazardous properties of metals and substances, a concern that certainly encompasses batteries of all types. European (if not worldwide) regulations have designated all batteries as hazardous waste that require treatment before disposal, with the following tasks to be accomplished, in order of priority:

1. Waste reduction at the origin, by means of cleaner products and processes.
2. Recovery of valuables from wastes, where possible.
3. Treatment of non-recoverable wastes to make them safe and disposable.

These regulations require large efforts to be devoted to the collection and recycling of batteries of any kind, despite the possibility that they may contain a low content in heavy metals. To cope with these directives, several recycling plants are in operation in Europe, the United States, and Japan.

Initially, the activity was mainly restricted to zinc-carbon batteries, namely the common “dry” primary AA or AAA cylindrical cells that are largely present in the low-value electronic market. For these dry cells, regulations have been imposed requiring that they be produced as “mercury-free” systems, which is the case for European and American manufacturers. However, the market globalization has favoured circulation from countries where environmental sensitivity is not as acute as in Europe and the United States, with the result that a considerably large amount of mercury is still recovered when recycling these batteries. Interestingly, the majority of the plants are still treating mostly consumer batteries, such as the quoted dry cells, and the rechargeable NiCd and NiMH batteries, while little attention has thus far been devoted to the collection and the recycling of lithium batteries. On the contrary, recycling of conventional automotive batteries, such as starting lighting and ignition (SLI) lead-acid, are in full operation worldwide.

The low recycling rate of lithium batteries is rather surprising since they are products that strongly influence our everyday life. Due to their favourable characteristics, lithium-ion batteries are in fact the power sources of choice in the consumer electronics market and, as such, are sold by several billions per year. Primary lithium batteries are mainly marketed to generic consumer markets for use in cameras, watches, and similar, whereas lithium-ion secondary batteries are marketed for mobile devices of increasing sophistication, such as cellular phones and laptop computers.

The large expansion of these markets (it is assumed that today billions of cellular phones are circulating worldwide) is evidence of the importance of the problem, which will only worsen with the expected advent of a high number of lithium-ion battery-powered electric cars. We need to increase the number of recycling plants for treating these batteries which, despite being rechargeable, will inevitably come to the end of their life at some point. Even though in the last few years protocols and plants have been developed in Europe, the United States, and Japan, much still needs to be done to assure a full collection and an effective recycling program for lithium-ion batteries. We hope that this review will provide the motivation and the stimulus for achieving this important goal, in the near future.

Chapter 4 - Protecting the Environment and the Energy Supply

This set of 5 goals consists of reductions of noise and emissions (section 4.1), emissions free taxing (section 4.2), recycling enabled by design (section 4.3), alternative fuels (section 4.4) and atmospheric research (section 4.5).

ACARE runs three research projects to achieve these goals: X-Noise EV, which relates to aviation noise research, Forum AE, which relates to emissions research, and Core-JetFuel, which relates to alternative aviation fuels. In 2015 ACARE published a 2014/2015 activity update. This update reports on the progress of each of these projects including an assessment of performance against ACARE's goals. The report concludes that noise research is on track to meet its target, that significant work is required to meet the emissions targets, specifically technology maturation, and that a quantitative target is required at European level for alternative fuels.

Politically, there is a shared awareness that climate change will dramatically modify our societies in the longer term. The image of Air Transport in the public mind has been tarnished by its perceived impact on the environment. The main levy to reduce aviation emissions will be to reduce travel demand through taxes and/or individual emissions quotas. Aviation environmental impacts include gaseous emissions and noise issues. Hardly any technical solution is able to reduce both types of impact. Trade-off decisions have to be made by all industry actors. The potentially negative impact of any drastic "green" approach on the supply industry is a concern. There is a need for global agreements on such measure to maintain fair competition.

ICAO, as the lead United Nations (UN) Agency in matters involving international civil aviation, is conscious of and will continue to address the adverse environmental impacts that may be related to civil aviation activity and acknowledges its responsibility and that of its Member States to achieve maximum compatibility between the safe and orderly development of civil aviation and the quality of the environment. In carrying out its responsibilities, ICAO and its Member States will strive to:

- a) Limit or reduce the number of people affected by significant aircraft noise;
- b) Limit or reduce the impact of aviation emissions on local air quality; and
- c) Limit or reduce the impact of aviation greenhouse gas emissions on the global climate.

In 2008 the global stakeholder associations of the aviation industry (Airports Council International, Civil Air Navigation Services Organization, International Air Transport Association and International Coordinating Council of Aerospace Industries Association), under the umbrella of the Air Transport Action Group, committed to addressing the global challenge of climate change and adopted a set of ambitious targets to mitigate CO₂ emissions from air transport:

- An average improvement in fuel efficiency of 1.5% per year from 2009 to 2020;
- A cap on net aviation CO₂ emissions from 2020 (carbon-neutral growth);
- A reduction in net aviation CO₂ emissions of 50% by 2050, relative to 2005 levels.

To achieve these targets, all stakeholders agreed to closely work together along a four-pillar strategy:

- Improved technology, including the deployment of sustainable low-carbon fuels;
- More efficient aircraft operations;
- Infrastructure improvements, including modernized air traffic management systems;
- A single global market-based measure, to fill the remaining emissions gap.

For that latest ICAO Assembly adopted three environmental resolutions [ICAO Resolution A39-1, ICAO Resolution A39-2, ICAO Resolution A39-3], providing in such way very ambitious policy for environment protection from civil aviation impact and for the sustainable growth of aviation as important element for future economic growth and development (ICAO contributes to ten of 17 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals). ICAO has established a Committee on Aviation Environmental Protection (CAEP) for the purpose of assisting in the further development of Standards, Recommended Practices and Procedures and/or guidance material on aircraft noise and engine emissions to assist States in implementing them in efficient way.

4.1 Reduction of Noise and Emissions

*** Flightpath 2050 goal 9: "In 2050 technologies and procedures available allow a 75% reduction in CO₂ emissions per passenger km and a 90% reduction in NO_x emissions. The perceived noise of flying aircraft is reduced by 65%. These are relative to the capabilities of typical new aircraft in 2000".**

This goal covers noise and emissions. The distinction is made between engine (4.1.1) and aerodynamic (4.1.2) noise and local (4.1.3) and global (4.1.4) emissions.

4.1.1 Engine Noise for Turbofans and Propfans

Since the start of the jet age enormous progress has been made in lowering noise levels and reducing the noise footprint per aircraft movement. Some of this progress has been offset by air traffic growth that can lead to increased total noise exposure unless noise reductions continue. The major contributor to the reduction of engine noise has been the increase in the by-pass ratio of turbofan engines: the larger by-pass flow at a lower speed radiates less noise and shields and scatters the sound from the hot high-speed core flow. Increasing the by-pass ratio also decreases fuel consumption, leading both to lower emissions and more favourable economics. This triple win-win-win situation of lower fuel consumption-less noise-lower emissions may be reaching its limits for by-pass ratios (BPR) in the range 15-20.

For higher BPR the size and weight of the engine nacelle and the limited space for acoustic liners and other noise reduction measures point towards the open rotor. The propfan promises reductions in fuel consumption up to 20% corresponding to a BPR of 30-40 not feasible with engine nacelles. The reductions in fuel consumption have direct benefits in lower emissions and better economics. The open contra-rotating rotors require careful optimization both from the aerodynamic and noise aspects, with the aft rotor cutting the wake of the forward one. Taking as noise metric the average of sound level (EPNDB) at the 3 certification measuring points the prop-fan could meet current noise standards. Future noise standards could be more challenging depending on the further reductions sought below the current standard.

In parallel with an evolution largely driven by global environmental issues, there is evidence of increased sensitivity to noise in local communities impacted by aviation operations despite significant reduction of aircraft source noise over the years. The air transport growth perspectives in Europe are still conditioned by improvements in all three elements of the ICAO Balanced Approach [ICAO Resolution A39-1]. The initial SRA1 approach presiding over the definition of the ACARE 2020 noise targets remains valid (Figure 4.1), as originally based on the Balanced Approach concept developed by ICAO:

- The first noise target aims at reducing noise emission of flying vehicles by half, which was translated in quantitative terms as an **average reduction of 10 decibels per operation**, taking into account technology benefits as well as operational improvements.
- The second noise target aims at ensuring that the 10dB benefit in noise emission anticipated for fixed-wing aircraft effectively leads to **no impacted people outside airport boundaries**, provided the appropriate management practices are in place.

Figure 4.1 - ACARE SRA 1: Noise Goals for Fixed-Wing Aircraft

Three years ahead of 2020, the progress registered since 2000 is significant, reaching an excellent level of completion with about 64% of expected benefits secured, due to effective implementation of the research roadmap and associated priorities. In terms of identified ACARE contributors, the investigation and development of recommended ACARE solutions have been well supported at European level over the years, complemented by a steady activity at national level. The first two elements of the Balanced Approach concept (noise reduction at source, noise abatement procedures) constitute the identified contributors to the 10dB reduction aircraft noise target, and can be further described in terms of associated technical and operational solutions as shown below:

- **Quiet Aircraft contributor** associated solutions: Noise Reduction Technologies (NRT) generation 1 and 2, Novel aircraft and engine/power plant architectures
- **Noise Abatement Procedures contributor** associated solutions: Improved Operating Practices with Current Concepts / Optimized Operations with New Technology / ATM-ATC Integration

At the occasion of previous progress assessment exercises, a methodology has been established in EU XNoise project (**X-NOISE network** as part of its activity, has identified gaps and priorities, supporting the definition of a general strategy addressing the anticipated 10 dB reduction per Operation in a phased approach by means of a significant effort on Technology as well as Noise Abatement Procedures), based:

- On the internationally recognised **Technology Readiness Level scale** (Figure 4.2), that allows to keep track of the situation of individual technologies identified in the SRA1.
- On a dedicated process, called **Technology Evaluator**, involving a predictive model with capability to roll up the benefits of individual technologies at solution level and establish the progress achieved globally, including operational aspects.

Figure 4.2 - Technology Readiness Level Classification (TRL) used for solutions assessment

An approach by consensus based on expert’s judgement, assessment of the TRL situation and results from the technology evaluation exercises has then been used to perform the 2015 progress assessment, coming up with updated progress achievement figures and formulating associated recommendations for future research. Recommended Phased Approach to meet ACARE Noise Goal #1 includes analysis of expected advances on noise reduction with Noise Reduction Technology 1 (NRT1) and NRT2, as well as the Noise Abatement Procedure, (Figure 4.3).

Figure 4.3 - Expected advances on noise reduction with NRT1 and NRT2, as well as the Noise Abatement Procedure

Since the year 2000 several civil air transport aircraft have been certified by the European industry, a few others, still in their development phase are planned to be certified before 2020. Certification requirements for aircraft noise during these 20 years period were changed twice (Figure 4.4) – in 2006 and 2017, once again basing on NRT1 and NRT2 achievements, reached in EU (Figure 4.5). The prime purpose of noise certification is to ensure that the latest available noise reduction technology is incorporated into aircraft design demonstrated by procedures which are relevant to day to day operations, to ensure that noise reduction offered by technology is reflected in reductions around airports.

The results of aircraft noise certification provide a representative panel of effective implementation of state-of-the-art Generation 1 Noise Reduction Technologies delivered to TRL6 by completed research programmes such as Silence(r) and Vital (Figure 3.26). The observed average achievement is in fact slightly over the expected 30% of the ACARE target. In dealing with the further steps towards the -10dB target (NRT Generation 2, Novel Architectures), the 2015 assessment exercise benefits from the achievements of the OPENAIR project as well as interim results from CLEAN SKY in specific areas related to business jets and regional aircraft, in particular.

Figure 4.4. Certification requirements for aircraft noise due to ICAO standards

Figure 4.5. Roadmap of EU Aircraft Noise Research Projects vs Key Technical Areas (Generation 1 and 2 solutions - NRT1 and NRT2 performances – were achieved by results of the projects shown and classified in accordance with priority acoustic sources)

At the end of the OPENAIR project NRT2 have achieved TRL 4/5 (look in the Figures 4.2 and 4.6) through large scale testing in wind tunnels and dedicated engine fan or exhaust rigs. These technologies have been aimed primarily at Short-Medium Range and Long-Range aircraft fitted with advanced ducted turbofans. Through CLEAN SKY, additional efforts reached similar TRL achievements on complementary noise reduction solutions aimed at Regional Aircraft (low noise landing gear and high lift devices) and Business Jets (U-Tail). In addition to technology solutions, CLEAN SKY will also bring further consolidation of noise abatement procedures benefits. At last CLEAN SKY has produced a first noise evaluation of the Counter Rotating Open Rotor (CROR) engine concept at mission level on a Short-Medium Range aircraft.

Figure 4.6 - Noise Reduction Technologies Development & Validation

When combining CLEAN SKY interim analysis (2014) with the OPENAIR final analysis at airport level and considering the relative importance of business and regional operations, it can be concluded that a typical 2.5 dB additional benefit relative to the 5dB already consolidated at TRL 6 can be expected from NRT2 provided such technologies mature to TRL6 in time for 2020 (Table 4.1).

While such a progress has been registered in terms of secured achievements, the gap to be covered by new programmes has basically stayed at the level identified in previous assessments. This is due on the one hand to uncertainties that remain about the capability to support successful OPENAIR technologies to TRL6 through static and flight demonstrations before 2020 and on the other hand to a similar lack of visibility relative to the emergence of ambitious multidisciplinary initiatives dedicated to environmentally friendly advanced aircraft configurations and design. In contrast, similar projects have gained momentum in other parts of the world.

Technology or Enabler	Description	Previous projects	On going project	Technology Readiness Level	
				Achieved in 2001	Achieved In 2009
Advanced low noise nacelle concepts	Intake lip liner (BPR7-9)	Silence®		3	5
	Intake lip liner (BPR6)	Silence®		3	5
	Negatively Scarfed Intake (BPR 6)	Ranntac Silence®		4	6
	Negatively Scarfed Intake (BPR7-9)	Silence®		1	6
	Bypass duct lined splitters		Openair	1	3
	Scarfed nozzles		Openair	1	3

Table 4.1. Technology Readiness Level and Technology Status

In conclusion, relative to the ACARE noise target of -10dB per operation, the aircraft noise research effort can be considered as globally on track to meet its objective but will require significant support in the few years remaining before 2020. Actions critical to the ultimate success of the global approach initiated around 2000 can be summarized through the following recommendations:

- Bring the most promising NRT2 solutions put forward by the OPENAIR project to TRL6, through an appropriate full-scale validation effort across the board (engines, nacelles, landing gears, airframes).
- Drastically increase the effort dedicated to Low Noise Aircraft configurations noting that while programme prospects are good concerning novel engines architectures, the effort on aircraft configurations is lagging.
- Take advantage of the sustained effort on low noise operational procedures to consolidate wider implementation capability.

Relative to the second ACARE 2020 noise target (no people impacted outside airport boundaries), a pilot study led to the following observations:

- Benefits of each individual element differs significantly (very airport dependent)
- The effect of Land Use Planning may be of the same order of magnitude as that of noise reduction at source
- A combination of actions is required to maintain future population affected below 2000 levels.

The full assessment process however will require a very significant amount of input data and need effective support if it is to be in place and validated ahead of the next assessment exercise. In the meantime, dedicated research actions should address the development of updated dose-response relationships to allow a translation from exposure (L_{DEN}) to annoyance fitted to the characteristics of today's and tomorrow's operations.

At this stage, it should also be pointed out that in noise reduction the main expectations are based on benefits associated with ducted turbofans engine concepts. In parallel, Counter Rotating Open Rotor (CROR) engine concepts have re-emerged in recent years as a serious option to provide the needed fuel burn benefits implied by the targets set for aviation CO₂ emissions reduction, noise was considered as a major issue in the initial investigation effort of such engine concept which culminated in a series of noise evaluation flight tests performed in the US in 1986-1987. As consequence, a significant research effort has been and still is dedicated to noise reduction of CROR engine concepts (Figure 4.7). At this stage, based on results from model tests in anechoic wind tunnel (TRL4), CROR powered aircraft with an EIS between 2025 and 2030 can be expected to produce noise levels similar

to those of turbofan powered aircraft currently under development. When placed in perspective with the best expectations resulting from the 1987 post flight test assessment, this represent a typical 20dB noise reduction on a cumulative basis, a spectacular achievement for the European research effort initiated in 2008. To consolidate such advances, it is important that the effort is maintained through dedicated research aimed at rotor blade aeroacoustics design, engine/airframe installation (Figure 4.8) and flow control techniques. It is generally assumed that though 2020 objectives will be reached through enforcing new Noise Abatement Procedures (NAP) in addition to NRTs, 2050 objectives will require a breakthrough in aircraft architectures.

Figure 4.7 - Programme Level & EPNL reduction for aircraft noise due to technology improvements

Figure 4.8 - Airbus views on a futuristic design for 2030 - future noise reduction technologies with contribution of engine/airframe installation effects

4.1.2 Aerodynamic Noise and Operating Procedures

The progress in the reduction of engine noise implies that: (i) it still remains the dominant noise source at take-off and with cut-back in climb; (ii) on approach to land, with the engine at idle, the aerodynamic noise can predominate. Thus, overall noise reduction at airports requires consideration of not one but two classes of noise sources;

- Engine noise sources such as fan, turbine and jet noise, combustion and buzz-saw (shock waves) noise with tonal and broadband components;

- Aerodynamic noise from the extended undercarriage and its wells and other cavities, and the deflections of control and high-lift surfaces.

Depending on the noise mechanism various measures can be taken to reduce the noise at the source or to reduce the effects of its emission. Noise reduction measures may not be additive, with the overall noise reduction less than the sum of the parts. The overall noise exposure of near airport residents can be reduced by land planning and by operational measures. The effects of noise on the near airport residence can be addressed at all of 7 links in a long chain: (i) the noise of an isolated engine in a test stand; (ii) the noise of the engine installed in aircraft subject to reflections; (iii) the noise in flight with flow effects and aerodynamic noise sources; (iv) the modification of sound by wind, turbulence, stratification and dissipation while propagating in the atmosphere; (v) the effect of different types of ground (concrete, snow, soil) and obstacles (terrain and buildings) in sound absorption and interference; (vi) the outdoor to indoor sound transmission through windows and other apertures; (vii) the psychoacoustic effects depending on the different types of activity: sleep, study, talking or other tasks. All the factors can play a role in the "noise annoyance", which can motivate noise restrictions at airports.

Starting from a low noise design, the only technology which may be available for additional noise reduction uses flow control, today at TRL 1 to 2 (Figure 4.9). The expected noise reduction is no more than 1 dB at the component level, which is additive to the benefit of the low noise design but is so small that it would be not very significant at the aircraft level. The IEP concluded that no additional noise reduction can be expected for a conventional configuration (under the wing installed engine). It appears that the only way to obtain more landing gear noise reduction at the approach condition seems to be the development of fuselage mounted short landing gear, which of course necessitates corresponding change of the aircraft structure, as described in [Dobrzynski W. M].

Figure 4.9 - Airframe noise reduction technologies

High lift devices – slat and flap – with low noise designs (including in particular the slat cove filler), today at TRL 1 to 2 are expected to be at TRL 6 by 2020 with a potential of 5 dB maximum reduction at the component level. The current TRL of these technologies is too low and the benefits too

uncertain to obtain credible estimates on the benefit at the aircraft level which in any case will be small with conventional aircraft configurations.

Most of the novel airframe/engine concepts currently being developed and evaluated within the aviation industry today have to be viewed as one integrated system and cannot strictly be assessed separately. The low noise characteristics of these concepts are partly due to the shielding of the engine noise (fan inlet, fan exhaust, core and jet, Figure 4.8) by the Blended-Wing-Body (BWB) and partly airframe noise reduction features such as low noise landing gear and the omission of flaps. Benefits of about 11 EPNdB cumulative were quoted relative to a conventional State-of-the-Art reference aircraft but more research is in progress on those noise reduction features as well as installation effects before these noise reduction concepts can be quoted with reasonable confidence.

The noise of aircraft is subject to ICAO certification rules that are intended to apply worldwide. This does not prevent local authorities from applying stricter noise standards at specific airports. For example, the noise limits at a major airport like Heathrow cannot be ignored by the main airliner manufactures Airbus and Boeing. Local airport rules can include noise limits, curfews and fines on excessive noise levels. These measures can limit the capacity of airports by reducing the operating hours; and they can affect the economics of flight by limiting take-off weight and payload. The certification rules do not cover interior noise, though airlines may have their own standards.

Noise abatement operational procedures are being employed today to provide noise relief to communities around airports from both arriving and departing aircraft. PANS-OPS, Volume 1, contains guidance for the development of a maximum of two noise abatement departure procedures (NADP's) designed generally to mitigate noise either close in (NADP 1) to the airport, or further out (NADP 2) along the departure path. Review [ICAO Document 9888] contains a list of current NADP's in use by air carriers for a wide range of aircraft types. A number of them was assessed during EU Silence(R) project for their possible contribution to ACARE 2020 goal (Figure 4.10):

Figure 4.10. Departure and approach noise abatement procedures

Operational procedures can often be implemented with the existing fleet and have the potential to make an immediate improvement in the environmental impact of aviation. Noise abatement operational procedures in use today can be broken down into three broad categories:

Noise abatement flight procedures:

- Continuous Descent Arrival (CDA);

- Noise Abatement Departure Procedures (NADP);
- Modified approach angles, staggered, or displaced landing thresholds;
- Low power/low drag approach profiles;
- Minimum use of reverse thrust after landing.

Spatial management:

- Noise preferred arrival and departure routes;
- Flight track dispersion or concentration;
- Noise preferred runways.

Ground management:

- Hush houses and engine run up management (location/aircraft orientation, time of day, maximum thrust level);
- APU management;
- Taxi and queue management;
- Towing;
- Taxi power control (Taxi with less than all engines operating).

The NAPs listed above can make a measurable contribution to reducing noise levels and other environmental benefits in the vicinity of airports [ICAO Document 9888]:

- 3 to 12 dB noise reduction, and 8% to 36% reduction in noise contour areas on approach;
- 2 to 9 dB noise reduction and 23% to 42% reduction in noise contour areas on departure;
- As much as 35% reductions in CO₂, HC and NO_x and 50 to 1000 pounds fuel savings per landing; and
- 90 to 630 kg CO₂ and 60 to 440 pounds fuel savings per departure.

The magnitude and scope of the reductions, as well as the specific procedures to be used to achieve them should be determined through a comprehensive noise study. The study should also include an analysis of emissions impacts and fuel burn, as these variables may be affected by procedure changes both in the air and on the ground. The aircraft operators and ANSP should be parties to the study to ensure the safety and feasibility of the procedures and to take advantage of their technical expertise. The environmental benefits of some operational procedures are straightforward and easy to visualize: preferential runways or flight tracks move aircraft away from more noise sensitive locations. Conversely, the benefits assessments for NADP's and CDA procedures are extremely complex and may require detailed modelling in order to be well understood. It is imperative that accurate aircraft operating data and specific operator flight procedures are applied as input to the noise and emissions models and that impacts on airport and airspace capacity be analysed. It is worth repeating that some noise abatement operational procedures may increase emissions or derogate airport capacity while providing significant noise relief. Appropriate consideration of all potential environmental impacts is essential, particularly as priorities change and procedures evolve or come up for review.

CAEP Independent Expert Panel (IEP) evaluated NAP methods, how and when they might be used to supplement new noise reduction technology developments in the next 10 years, to further reduce noise exposure around the airport community, as well as during climb and descent. A very significant improvement in cumulative noise reduction is expected from the introduction of NRT and increased BPR, but this improvement is not expected to be the same between take-off and landing, most of this improvement occurring at take-off (lateral and flyover) with much smaller benefits predicted at approach. In general, the benefits at landing/approach are ~3 to 4 dB less than at departure. The main contributor at landing, at least for the SMR and LR classes of aircraft, is the undercarriage-generated

noise, even when engine noise has a no negligible contribution. So, the difference between take-off and landing suggests a difference in the potential role of operational procedures for aircraft noise reduction. NAP may useful for reducing noise exposure at take-off, but may be essential for the final approach, depending on what noise levels are ultimately deemed acceptable.

Continuous descent approach (CDA) is still under study, mainly to save fuel, but noise exposure reduction is also a benefit of this procedure. The challenge is to combine the aircraft deceleration and the rate of descent from the end of cruise to the final approach (with the gear down), under ATC rules. To avoid increasing noise exposure, the trajectory adjustments have to be minimized in particular at low altitude, and the gear operation cannot be earlier than in the current practice. As the engines, during this phase of flight, are at or close to idle, the noise reduction technologies and increased BPR have no appreciable noise exposure benefit.

In order to exploit new technology and low noise operations developments, and to enable integrated impact mitigation solutions, it was considered of utmost importance to [Collin D]:

- Improve and continuously update the understanding of how noise from air transport operations affects people, with a significant focus on the influence of non-acoustic factors. The Figure 4.11 provides a rough survey of the most important non-acoustic variables for long-term annoyance and for annoyance at night.
- Provide the technical support for the successful implementation of planning policies compatible with traffic growth for the long-term benefit of the communities. This will require specific thematic research aimed at better integration of land use planning (LUP) in decision making.

Figure 4.11. Overview of most important non-acoustic factors contributing to aircraft noise annoyance [Collin D]

Consistent with this comprehensive strategy, a number of “Enabling Factors” are foreseen as key contributors to the 2050 noise goal achievement, namely [Collin D]:

- Improved numerical simulation capabilities, together with test facilities incorporating advanced measurement techniques, in order to support further noise reduction at source level, and the implementation of multi-disciplinary optimization techniques and aircraft/engine integrated design practices that contribute to lower noise through efficient integration of noise reduction solutions, reduced weight, decreased drag, improved power plant efficiency, and enhanced flight path design.
- Stimulated advances in related technology areas, such as materials and electronics, to allow the introduction of novel low noise technologies, including active/adaptive techniques.

- Updated, and internationally recognized, annoyance and sleep disturbance models, that take into account the evolution of aircraft noise signatures and traffic conditions (multiple events), and that consider airport specificities.
- Improved tools to support transparent communication policies that cover relevant indices, online forecast and tracking flight path operations, and comprehensive assessment of environmental interdependencies, and the monetization of impacts.

The ACARE SRIA confirmed the importance of addressing the impacts aspects as part of a coordinated research strategy, stating that the targeted 65% noise reduction relative to the 2000 baseline “should be achieved through a significant and balanced research programme aimed at developing novel technologies and enhanced low noise operational procedures, complemented by a coordinated effort providing industry, airports and authorities with better knowledge and impact assessment tools to ensure that the benefits are effectively perceived by the communities exposed to noise from air transport activities”.

4.1.3 Local Emissions of CO₂ and NO_x

There are growing concerns about the impact of aviation on the atmosphere with respect to local air quality (LAQ) and the associated human health and welfare impacts. Aviation emissions in airports are produced by aircraft, support vehicles and ground transportation dominantly. The emissions from these sources fall into two categories: emissions that cause deterioration in local air quality and emissions that cause climate change. Emissions that cause climate change from aviation also fall into two categories. The first category is GHGs, which are gases that cause climate change by trapping heat in the atmosphere. These emissions are produced when fossil fuels are combusted. Secondly, emissions from aircraft can alter radioactively active substances, trigger the formation of aerosols and lead to changes in clouds. Together these effects are known as radiative forcing.

LAQ issues are caused by Nitrogen Oxides (NO_x), Sulphur Oxides (SO_x) and Particulate Matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}). In high concentrations these pollutants have been shown to cause health effects, among them to exacerbate a range of cardiovascular diseases including chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (an umbrella term for lung diseases including chronic bronchitis), heart disease, lung cancer and asthma. Health impact depends on population exposure. Somewhere visibility impairment from NO_x and PM is a subject of control also. Requirements to LAQ are driven by local regulations usually. Significant LAQ pressure exists already - noted 2010 NO₂ EU directive exceeded today at several EU airports [ICAO CAEP/7-IE/WG/3].

From a scientific and a health point of view – and subsequent policy interest, monitoring and control – the most important pollutants to focus on are nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), regional ozone (O₃) and particulate matter (PM) - currently PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and ultrafine particles (UFP). Concerning airports, this especially concerns UFP emissions on the apron area (airside) where ramp workers are exposed. The identification of such particles and tackling of their sources remain issues of importance and further investigations. Moreover, appropriate technology and air quality standards, limitations or any other criteria linked to ultrafine particles are still lacking and need to be defined [FORUM-AE].

FORUM-AE puts important emphasis on ACARE environmental goals related to aircraft emissions, but sufficient openness is necessary. New topics may emerge, which were not initially shaped. This is the case for instance of: ultra-fine particles (higher LAQ concerns at European airports, perspective of a future nvPM international standard), cruise NO_x emissions to be distinguished from LTO NO_x, cruise emissions influence on air quality, drop-in kerosene (fossil or renewable) composition optimisation, fuel sulphur content, contrail avoidance strategy, possible CO₂ or non-CO₂ trade-offs with noise environmental constraint, comparison between other transport modes (particles,

CO₂), introduction of a new aircraft CO₂ metric from future CAEP standard. Ambient measurements in the vicinity of airports typically show little to no contribution from airport emissions (Zurich Airport, 2013). However, recent studies have shown elevated PM number levels near airports [Hudda et al., 2014; Keuken, et al. 2015]. Measurement protocols and guidance are established for criteria pollutants. However, the ambient measurement of ultrafine particle number concentrations is not yet standardized.

The Figure 4.12 provides a representation of aircraft emissions and how they ultimately contribute to ambient pollutant concentrations that impact public health and welfare. Even from this Figure one may conclude on site specific LAQ in airports. While aircraft emissions can be directly measured at the source and ambient pollutant concentrations can be measured at any location, modelling is required to attribute the contribution of aircraft to ambient pollutant concentrations [Miake-Lye R]. Some of the gaps for the production of airport emission inventories are displayed in the Table 4.2:

Figure 4.12 - Schematic presentation of emissions, dispersion, concentrations and impacts with their interaction at airport level [Miake-Lye R]

Source	Activity	Emission factor	Calculation
Aircraft engine	Stop & go behaviour, Idle vs taxi, flex take-off	ICAO Engine Emissions Data Bank, but not yet PM	BFFM2, but FOA for PM
Auxiliary Power Unit (APU)	Environmental Control System Duration	Rudimentary in Doc 9889	Simple product
Aircraft frame	Brakes, tires	Assumptions	Simple product
Ground Support Equipment (GSE)	Machinery good, else poor	EU Non Road Mobile Machinery (EUNRMM)	Simple product
Stationary Sources	Usually well known	EMEP-EEA, manufacturer	Simple product
Landside vehicles	Fair, many assumptions	HBEFA, Coppert, etc.	Simple product

Table 4.2. Level of understanding in airport emission inventory: green (good); yellow (fair); red (poor) (Updated from [Forum-AE, 2015])

ACARE's environmental research is driven by five goals to be achieved by 2050. Among them are CO₂ emissions per passenger kilometre have been reduced by 75%, NO_x emissions by 90% relative to the year 2000. Engine manufacturers, cognizant of aviation's growing impact on the environment, continue to develop and introduce into service cleaner and more fuel-efficient engines. It must be understood that technology development and introduction of products into revenue service is heavily influenced by customer pull. To address this environmental concern, manufacturers continually work to develop technology for cleaner and more efficient new engine designs, and periodically update existing engines to maintain state of the art durability, performance and emissions.

Airport emission inventory and air quality modelling improvements are required, which will ask that models more accurately predict concentrations. As illustrated in previous Table there is still a lot for improvement in airport emission inventory making and that further consolidation is needed in knowledge of airport emissions sources and their activity (performance), emission factor and calculation algorithm. Linked to both inventory making and air quality modelling, there is the need for further development and validation of performance-based emissions modelling, and the need for harmonisation in this area.

The efforts to reduce (i) noise and emissions, (ii) different types of emissions like CO₂ and NO_x at (iii) local airport or global earth level are not always compatible. A highly efficient engine with low fuel consumption and high speed of the jet exhaust is likely to be noisy. High temperature combustion to increase thermal and propulsive efficiency increases NO_x emissions. Reducing CO₂ emissions may not lead to the same thermodynamic cycle than reducing NO_x emissions.

In order to improve fuel efficiency, engine pressures and temperatures are increased with time which can lead to higher NO_x emissions. As such, following the adoption of the original emissions standards, more stringent NO_x limits have been periodically introduced in order to mitigate the potential trade-off with market-driven fuel burn improvements. The NO_x limits are referred to by the CAEP meeting number at which they were agreed (i.e. CAEP/2, CAEP/4, CAEP/6 and CAEP/8). The regulatory limits for smoke, HC and CO have not changed from their original value as they are considered to provide adequate environmental protection. These regulatory limits provide a design space for aircraft engine technology within which both NO_x emissions and fuel burn can be reduced.

Latest advances in engine combustor design technologies were considered in the context of the existing mid- and long- term CAEP goals. To provide the latest state of technology, currently CAEP is working on an integrated independent expert technology goals assessment and review for engines and aircraft which aims to be delivered to the CAEP/11 meeting in February 2019 [ICAO Secretariat]. A certification Standard to control the amount of oxides of nitrogen (NO_x) permitted to be produced by civil turbo-jet and turbo-fan aircraft engines was first adopted by ICAO in 1981. The stringency of that Standard was successively increased at CAEP/2, 4, 6, and most recently at CAEP/8 in 2010. The introduction of a standard to control NO_x production was originally driven by concerns relating to surface air quality (SAQ) where NO_x is implicated in the production of ozone in the vicinity of airports. To complement the Standard-setting process, CAEP agreed in 2001 to pursue the establishment of technology goals over the medium and long term. These were to be challenging yet achievable targets for researchers and industry to aim at, in cooperation with States. Also, they provide policy makers with a view of what technology could be expected to deliver for emission reductions in the future. The first of these reviews was to focus on NO_x , and to help achieve this, a panel of Independent Experts (IEs) was appointed and tasked with:

- Leading a review of technologies for the control of NO_x .
- Recommending technology goals for NO_x reduction from aircraft engine technologies over the 10 years and 20 years' time horizon.

The goals can be seen in the Figure 4.13, which is taken from the 2006 report of the IEs, together with goals proposed by the EU ACARE and the US Ultra Efficient Engine Technology (UEET). It is important to note that these other goals were not used to influence the CAEP goals and were plotted simply for comparison. The graph also illustrates the historic ICAO NO_x Standards and highlights the large gap between the goals and the latest standard. It is important to note that the goals indicate that significant NO_x reductions are achievable over the 10- and 20-years timescales based on the leading edge of control technologies; while standards on the other hand are based on already certified technology.

Figure 4.13. Historical ICAO certification Standards together with the 2006 MT & LT goals.

The Figure 4.13 also illustrates the continuous improvement achieved over time with newly certified engines achieving the largest margin to the limits. Some of the engines certified since 2008 are already close to mid-term and long-term technology goals. The Figure 4.14 illustrates the evolution of the average margin to the CAEP/6 NO_x limit for EASA certified in-production engine models. During the last five years the margin has increased by approximately 3% per year. It is noted however that the trend is influenced by which engines go out of production, and whether the new entries in the ICAO Aircraft Engine Emissions Databank represent new engines or derived versions of existing engines with smaller evolutionary improvements.

The Figure 4.13 uses the recognized NO_x certification metrics and shows the amount of NO_x produced from an LTO cycle (Figure 4.15) on the vertical axis (grams per kN of thrust), and the engine overall pressure ratio (OPR) at the take-off condition on the horizontal axis. It is evident that the larger, higher thrust engines operating at higher pressure ratios, and consequently at higher thermal efficiencies, produce greater amounts of NO_x. In relation to the degree of uncertainty, it should be noted that the band width was greater for the longer time period. The medium term (MT) goal for 2016 was agreed at 45% ± 2.5% below CAEP/6 at OPR 30, and the long term (LT) goal for 2026 at 60% ± 5% below CAEP/6 also at OPR 30.

Figure 4.14. Improving average NO_x margin to CAEP/6 limit for in-production engines shown in successive versions of the ICAO EEDB

Figure 4.15. Illustration of ICAO emissions certification procedure in the LTO cycle.

The second CAEP IE review for NO_x emission was intended to be less extensive and was focused on what had changed in the intervening three years since the first review. The IEs concluded that the scientific evidence supports continued efforts to reduce aircraft NO_x emissions and that the evidence of impact of aircraft NO_x on both surface air quality and global climate change was, if anything, more compelling than during the first review. Nevertheless, given the still considerable uncertainty about the quantification of these impacts, the IEs recommended continued research on NO_x emissions, and other emerging concerns such as particulate matter (PM), and the role of NO_x in PM formation. As in the 2006 report, it was again concluded that for SAQ, NO_x continues to be an important pollutant and in the context of Global Climate Change (GCC) ranking versus CO_2 continues to depend crucially on the length of the time horizon. It appears that NO_x is more important in shorter time periods, with CO_2 dominating in the longer term, and then continuing to do so over many hundreds of years.

Since 2006, further significant reductions in NO_x emissions have been evident, something for which manufacturers should be congratulated. Advanced combustors can be categorized into two broad types: RQL systems (rich burn, quick quench, lean burn), and staged-DLI (direct lean injection), also called staged lean burn systems. In very simple terms, RQL combustors control NO_x production through a series of changes to the air to fuel ratio as the combustion air progresses through the combustor. Staged-DLI combustors operate quite differently with NO_x control being achieved by switching (staging) between pilot and main burner zones arranged in concentric circles. Although reductions in NO_x production were shown to have been achieved by both types of combustor, neither was deemed to have met the goals set at the first review - defined as having reached Technology Readiness Level 8 (TRL8) - although they were possibly close to that.

The Figure 4.16 provides a summary presentation of the test data results received for this review with the two types of combustor identified separately; the data points coloured grey being for RQL combustors, and those in red being for the new staged-DLI combustors. As with the first review, the conclusion reached was that RQL combustors appear likely to meet the MT goal, though a significant challenge remains, but the LT goal may not be achievable particularly for high OPR engines. Dramatic reductions in NO_x production from the use of new generation staged DLI combustors were in line with the expectations recorded in the 2006 Report, although the migration towards the LT goal was not

expected so soon. However, the wide spread of NO_x performance raised questions about how such families of engines might be handled in the future within a goal setting process.

Information presented for advanced RQL combustors was believed not to challenge the definition, or levels, of the goals established at the first review. The somewhat limited information relating to the new generation staged-DLI combustors however was thought to offer something of a challenge to both the definition and the goal levels. Nevertheless, since they are untested in commercial service, the IEs decided not to change the goals at this review but to wait until further experience had been gained. It was concluded that staged-DLI combustors were likely to be essential to meet the LT goal, particularly at high OPRs. A critical factor for future goal setting will be the extent to which advanced RQL and staged-DLI systems can be made to work effectively for (smaller) low and mid-OPR engines.

Figure 4.16. 2009 Review data with RQL combustors in grey and new mid-OPR engines. Generation staged DLI combustors in red. Note these data points area mixture of certificated engines and high TRL developments

The objectives of the European programs are to reduce short & long-term development costs, incorporate new technology faster into future products and improve the environmental impact with regards to emissions. Specific goals of the EC FP6 Aeronautics Work Programme are to reduce NO_x emissions over the ICAO-LTO cycle by 80% compared to the CAEP/2 standard and achieve a NO_x emission index of 5 g/kg at cruise [ICAO CAEP/8-IP/11].

Good progress has been shown on state-of-the-art Single Annular Combustors with rich burn (air blast) injection, Double Annular Combustors/Axially Staged Combustors (rich pilot / rich main) and Lean Burn Combustors. The latest state-of-the-art lean burn fuel injection systems with centrally integrated pilot fuel injection for flame stabilisation have achieved up to 70 to 75% of NO_x reduction at TRL3 (demonstrated in a high-pressure single sector combustor test rig) relative to the CAEP/2 certification standard. A technology deterioration factor, which describes the transition from TRL3 to TRL6 needs to be considered, leading to likely technological progress by the end of Framework 7 of a range of approximately 60 to 65% NO_x reduction. It is most likely that in Framework 8, research initiatives will need to focus on further improvements towards 70 to 85% NO_x reduction, which may lead to another 50% relative NO_x reduction and to higher Technology Readiness Levels [ICAO CAEP/8-IP/11].

Lessons learned from the example of technology transition are: that the technology transition process is complex and expensive, and may not progress in a predictable fashion; commitment of a new technology to product requires a solid technology foundation (complete TRL 6 demonstration), understanding of environmental benefits and trade-offs, a clear customer need, and enabling technologies (e.g. digital control and fuel nozzle protection technologies); initial research goals tend to overestimate benefits because the environmental benefit relative to evolving current technologies tends to decrease with time and the time required to complete product transition tends to exceed initial estimates; and technology transition is not complete at certification (TRL8). Product upgrades continue to cover more engine models and improve combustor performance after TRL8 [ICAO CAEP/8-IP/11].

All aircraft emit CO₂ as a fuel combustion product. Fuel use by the global aircraft fleet has increased approximately linearly over four decades (up to 2013) based on International Energy Agency estimates. Fuel use per revenue passenger kilometre (RPK) has decreased since the 1970s as aircraft structures, aircraft engines and aircraft operations have become more fuel efficient [Lee *et al.*, 2009]. Aviation fuel use and CO₂ emissions are projected to continue increasing in the coming decades as aviation demand increases, even as CO₂ per RPK decreases due to technological and operational improvements.

The eighth meeting of ICAO's Committee on Aviation Environmental Protection (CAEP/8) held in February 2010, made important decisions regarding technological means to reduce the impact of aviation on climate change. It was agreed that the effort would be referred to as a "CO₂ Standard" based on "fuel efficiency concepts" within the certification requirement metric. This was decided in order to ensure the necessary transparency and public understanding that is essential to demonstrate that this work is contributing to efforts to reduce aviation's impact on climate change.

Following six years of development, ICAO's CAEP at its tenth meeting (CAEP/10) recommended an Aeroplane Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) Emissions Certification Standard. This new standard is a part of the ICAO "basket of measures" to reduce greenhouse gas emissions from the air transport system, and it is the first global technology Standard for CO₂ emissions for any sector with the aim of encouraging more fuel-efficient technologies into aeroplane designs.

The recommended CO₂ Standard has been developed at the aeroplane level, and therefore has considered all technologies associated with the aeroplane design (e.g. propulsion, aerodynamics and structures). Once adopted by the ICAO Council, the Aeroplane CO₂ Emissions Certification Standard will be published as a new Annex 16, Volume III. The framework for the CO₂ Standard consists of a certification requirement and regulatory limit, as shown in the Figure 4.17, and the work to develop the CO₂ Standard was divided into two phases. Phase 1, which was completed at the ninth meeting of the CAEP (CAEP/9) in February 2013, resulted in the approval of some of the details regarding the

applicability of the Standard, the CO₂ Metric System and the development of a CO₂ Standard certification requirement. Phase 2 involved the development of the regulatory limit lines and the applicability requirements such as scope and date.

Figure 4.17 -The framework and development phases of the CO₂ Standard

The results of the CAEP/10 meeting were unprecedented, because it was the first time CAEP had been able to recommend two completely new standards in one meeting, on CO₂ and non-volatile particulate matter (nvPM) emissions. The recommended Aeroplane CO₂ Emissions Certification Standard is a technology standard with the aim of encouraging more fuel-efficient technologies into aeroplane designs. This technology-based approach is similar to the current ICAO engine emissions standards for LAQ and the aircraft noise standards. The recommended CO₂ standard has been developed at the aeroplane level, and therefore has considered all technologies associated with the aeroplane design (e.g. propulsion, aerodynamics and structures). This approach is similar to the current ICAO aircraft noise standards. The CO₂ standard will apply to subsonic jet and turboprop aeroplanes that are new type (NT) designs from 2020, as well as to those aeroplane type designs that are in-production (InP) in 2023 and undergo a change. Regarding the latter, if after 2023 any InP aeroplane type design that is changed to the extent that it triggers applicability, it would then need to be made compliant with the standard. In 2028, there is a production cut-off. This means that InP aeroplanes that do not meet the standard can no longer be produced from 2028, unless the designs are modified to comply with the standard.

The recommendation on the CO₂ emissions standard was supported by a significant data driven process and the cost-benefit modelling analysis of several different CO₂ stringency options. The new CO₂ emissions Standard is recommended as being included in an entirely new Volume to Annex 16 (Volume III). The Figure 4.18 shows an overview of the CO₂ Standard regulatory limit lines for both NT and InP CO₂ Standards. The CO₂ Standard covers a broad range of aeroplane masses and types and is especially stringent where it will have the greatest impact: for larger aeroplane types with an MTOM of greater than 60 tonnes. CAEP considers technical feasibility very carefully during the development of environmental standards, and as such, the decision at CAEP10 recognised the fact that the larger aeroplane designs have access to the broadest range of CO₂ emissions reduction technologies. This is less so for aeroplanes below 60 tonnes where the standard provides additional margin for a sector. This is particularly recognised for aeroplanes of MTOMs less than 60 tonnes and with fewer than 19 seats maximum passenger seating capacity, where for new aeroplane type designs the applicability date of the standard is 2023.

Figure 4.18 - The CO₂ Standard regulatory limits for the aircraft

It is complex to fully understand the impact of the CO₂ Standard due to potential unknown market driven responses to the regulation, and the fact that the CO₂ Standard cost-effectiveness analysis was a comparative investigation of regulatory limit lines. However, it is clear that the new standard will have direct effects by increasing the importance of fuel efficiency in the design process such that an aeroplane type not just meets the regulatory limit but also has good relative product positioning in terms of a margin to the limit.

The Figure 4.19 presents full-flight CO₂ emissions for international aviation from 2005 to 2040, and then extrapolated to 2050. This Figure only considers the CO₂ emissions associated with the combustion of jet fuel, assuming that 1 kg of jet fuel burned generates 3.16 kg of CO₂. As with the fuel burn analysis, this analysis considers the contribution of aircraft technology, improved air traffic management and infrastructure use (i.e., operational improvements). In addition, the range of possible CO₂ emissions in 2020 is displayed for reference to the global aspirational goal of keeping the net CO₂ emissions at this level. Although not displayed in a separate Figure, the demand uncertainty effect on the fuel burn calculations shown in Figure 4.19 has an identical effect on the CO₂ results. Based on the maximum anticipated fuel consumption in 2020 (Scenario 1) and the anticipated Scenario 9 fuel consumption in 2040, a minimum CO₂ emission gap of 523 Mt is projected in 2040. Extrapolating Scenario 9 to 2050 results in a 1,039 Mt gap.

Figure 4.19 - CO₂ Emissions Trends from International Aviation, 2005 to 2050

The Figure 4.20 provides results for global full-flight fuel burn for international aviation from 2005 to 2040, and then extrapolated to 2050. The fuel burn analysis considers the contribution of aircraft technology, improved air traffic management, and infrastructure use (i.e., operational improvements) to reduce fuel consumption. The Figure 4.20 also illustrates the fuel burn that would be expected if ICAO’s 2 per cent annual fuel efficiency aspirational goal were achieved. The trends presented in the Figures 4.19 and 4.20 were developed in the context of a longer-term view. Short term changes in global fuel efficiency can be affected substantially by a wide range of factors such as fluctuations in fuel prices, and global economic conditions.

The CO₂ emissions that affect the global climate, and emissions that affect local air quality are expected to increase through 2050, but at a rate slower than aviation demand. Under an advanced aircraft technology and moderate operational improvement scenario, from 2030, aircraft noise exposure may no longer increase with an increase in traffic. However, it has to be kept in mind that the uncertainty associated with future aviation demand is notably larger than the range of contributions from technology and operational improvements.

Figure 4.20. Fuel Burn Trends from International Aviation, 2005 to 2050

International aviation fuel efficiency is expected to improve through 2050, but measures in addition to those considered in this analysis will be required to achieve ICAO's 2 percent annual fuel efficiency aspirational goal. Sustainable alternative fuels have the potential to make a significant contribution, but sufficient data are not available to confidently predict their availability over the long term. Also, considering only aircraft technology and operational improvements, additional measures will be needed to achieve carbon neutral growth relative to 2020.

The Figure 4.21 shows the estimated excess CO₂ emissions generated per flight that can be attributed to inefficiencies related to overall Air Navigation Services. These excess emissions have decreased by 7% since 2012, with the climb and descent phase decreasing by 6%, the taxi phase by 8% and the en route phase by 7%. It should be noted that the inefficiencies in the individual flight phases are average excess emissions compared to theoretical optima. These theoretical optima are not achievable in reality at the air traffic system level due to safety or capacity limitations. Therefore, the excess emissions indicated cannot be reduced to zero, as a certain level of excess fuel burn is necessary if a network system is to be run safely and efficiently.

Figure 4.21. Estimated excess CO₂ emissions per flight are decreasing in taxi, take-off, climb/descent and en route phases

FORUM-AE’s reference when assessing European progress towards ACARE emissions CO₂ & NO_x goals is shown in the Figure 4.22. One should also note that NO_x emissions are considered either at local level when addressing air quality concern or at global scale when addressing climate change. Still referring to SRIA Vol. 1, Appendix, the timing assumption to progress towards CO₂ & NO_x goals is the following [FORUM-AE]:

Figure 4.22. ACARE CO₂ & NO_x goals calendar (using CAEP6 margin for NO_x) [FORUM-AE]

Air traffic CO₂ share will keep increasing unless adapted measures are taken. ACARE 2050 ambitious objectives would permit to mitigate the increase of aviation part in anthropogenic CO₂. If ACARE technology goals were not achieved, if technology improvements were not introduced in the fleet early enough, and if global anthropogenic CO₂ was not growing as much as assumed, share of aviation could be above 5% in 2050.

ACARE 2050 very challenging CO₂ reduction objective would permit to mitigate substantially the increase of aviation CO₂, with realistic traffic growth assumption. Therefore, it is essential to pursue a tremendous effort at the aircraft level, the engine level and the ATM & flight operation level in order to progress towards this ambitious goal.

Aircraft/Engine panel of technologies (an exhaustive list would be very long, and one can refer to SRIA-Vol.2 enablers table and to FORUM-AE relevant workshops proceedings) must be further and continuously improved or newly introduce both for evolutionary aircraft or engine applications and longer-term disruptive applications.

Unconventional configurations like aircraft equipped with CROR concept or UHBPR concepts, must be further developed. Their mitigation potential, complemented with laminar wing benefit, must be maximised and their maturity must be pushed over TRL5, recognizing there is still some gap towards ACARE 2020 CO₂ goal.

The recommended new nvPM standard (ICAO CAEP/9 meeting in 2013) has been developed for the certification of aircraft engines emissions and is set at the engine level, in a similar way to the current ICAO engine emission standards. The recommended new nvPM standard will apply to engines manufactured from 1 January 2020 and is for the certification of aircraft engines with rated thrust greater than 26.7kN. The new nvPM standard is the first of its kind, and it includes a full standardized certification procedure for the measurement of nvPM, and the regulatory limit for the nvPM mass concentration set at the current ICAO smoke visibility limit. The new nvPM standard is recommended as a new Chapter to Annex 16, Volume II. The agreement on the new nvPM standard will set the basis for a more stringent nvPM standard during CAEP/11.

Consensus appears that nvPM reduction must be also achieved, in addition to NO_x. This induces critical R&T on [FORUM-AE]:

- The combustor technology itself in order to ensure both NO_x & nvPM ambitious low levels: enhanced lean combustion in general (achieving TRL6 maturity & extending its application to smaller-size and/or smaller OPR engine combustors), and focus on more specific aspects which may be beneficial to particles reduction (improved atomisation);
- The modelling of emissions, which for particles emissions is far from being predictable today, because of the physical complexity of particles formation (gaseous precursors formation, particles nucleation & oxidation...), and the modelling of combustion related operability aspects;
- The experimental analysis, which is absolutely necessary to support modelling development or to assess technology. This assumes advanced measurements (in particular intrusive and non-intrusive measurements of particles in the combustion chamber) and appropriate test capability (from multi-sector tests to full annular tests, with ability to achieve high pressure levels).

4.1.4 Cruise Efficiency and Global Emissions

In 2012, aviation represented 13% of all EU transport CO₂ emissions, and 3% of the total EU CO₂ emissions. It was also estimated that European aviation represented 22% of global aviation's CO₂ emissions. Similarly, aviation now comprises 14% of all EU transport NO_x emissions, and 7% of the total EU NO_x emissions. In absolute terms, NO_x emissions from aviation have doubled since 1990, and

their relative share has quadrupled, as other economic sectors have achieved significant reductions [EEA, **Transport and Environment Reporting Mechanism 2014**].

In 2010, Member States agreed to work through the ICAO to achieve a global annual average fuel efficiency improvement of 2%, and to stabilize the global net carbon emissions of international aviation at 2020 levels. During 2012, Member States submitted voluntary Action Plans to the ICAO outlining their annual reporting on international aviation CO₂ emissions and their respective policies and actions to limit or reduce the impact of aviation on the global climate. New or updated action plans were submitted during 2015 and are expected once every three years thereafter.

Combining air traffic and environmental indicators together shows some signs of growing economic and connectivity benefits from aviation (measured in passenger kilometres flown) without a proportionate increase in environmental impact (Figure 4.23). The diverging trends of passenger kilometres flown and noise energy between 2005 and 2014 have shown that this is possible, and that there is the potential for this to continue in the future. Nevertheless, the absolute noise energy and emissions of aviation are expected to grow further in the next twenty years.

Aircraft emit gases and aerosol that change the composition of the atmosphere, because increases in cloudiness through contrail formation and spreading, and modify natural clouds. At present, these changes together are estimated to cause a net positive forcing of Earth's climate system, which contributes to surface warming and other responses. There is substantial understanding of the components of aviation climate forcing, particularly CO₂. Important uncertainties remain in quantifying some of the aviation non-CO₂ climate terms and in the underlying physical processes. This paper presents a summary of recent progress in the state of the science since the 2012 ICAO/CAEP/ISG paper, especially related to contrails and induced cloudiness, contrail avoidance, and aerosol and NO_x effects. The number and diversity of newly available studies has created a need to re-evaluate best estimates of aviation climate forcing. Our understanding and confidence in aviation climate forcing's would be enhanced by a new international scientific assessment.

Figure 4.23 - Noise and emissions forecast to grow slower than passenger kilometres

The connections between aviation emissions and radiative forcing, climate change, and its impacts and potential damages are shown in the Figure 4.24. The principal greenhouse gases (GHGs) emitted are carbon dioxide (CO₂) and water vapour (H₂O). Emissions of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) impact the concentrations of other GHGs, mainly ozone (O₃) and methane (CH₄). Black carbon (soot) is a directly emitted aerosol, and sulphur oxides (SO_x), NO_x, and hydrocarbons (HC) lead to aerosol production after emission. Water vapour emissions in combination with emitted or background aerosol lead to contrail formation. Persistent contrails, which form at high ambient humidity and low temperatures, increase cloudiness. Additionally, aviation aerosol may modify natural clouds or trigger cloud formation. There is high confidence that these are the primary pathways by which aviation operations affect climate.

The evaluation requires knowledge of many physical and chemical processes in the atmosphere and requires summing over the global aircraft fleet operating under diverse meteorological conditions in the upper troposphere and lower stratosphere where most emissions occur. The Lee *et al.* (2009) study is the most recent assessment in the literature of the best estimates of aviation RF terms.

Figure 4.24 - Updated schematic of the principal emissions from aviation operations and the relationship of emissions to climate change and impacts. The terminology, ΔX, indicates a change in component X. The term, Δclouds, represents contrail induced cloudiness and aerosol-cloud interactions. (From Brasseur *et al.*, 2015).

The recent ACCRI report drew similar conclusions in noting that recommendations for best estimates were precluded in their study due in part to the varied modelling approaches that did not all account

for climate system couplings and feedback processes (Brasseur *et al.*, 2015). Continued progress in understanding and quantifying aviation climate forcing and responses requires continued focused research activities and would be enhanced by a new international scientific assessment that would assess new published results available, for example, for contrails, contrail cirrus and indirect cloud effects. An updated science assessment would also identify important remaining gaps in understanding and, hence, guide future research directions.

Aircraft CO₂ emissions increased from 88 to 156 million tonnes (+77%) between 1990 and 2005 according to the data reported by EU28 and EFTA Members States to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) (Figure 4.25). According to data from the IMPACT emissions model, CO₂ emissions increased by 5% between 2005 and 2014. The increase in emissions is however less than the increase in passenger kilometres flown over the same period (2005 to 2014). This was due to an improvement in fuel efficiency driven by the introduction of new aircraft, removal of older aircraft, and improvements in operational practice. The average fuel burn per passenger kilometre flown for passenger aircraft, excluding business aviation, went down by 19% over this same period. However, projections indicate that future technology improvements are unlikely to balance the effect of future traffic growth. Under the base traffic forecast and advanced technology improvement rate, CO₂ emissions increases by 44% from 144 Mt in 2005 to 207 Mt in 2035.

Figure 4.25 - After remaining stable between 2005 and 2014, aircraft CO₂ emissions are likely to increase further

NO_x emissions have also increased significantly (Figure 4.26): +85% (316 to 585 thousand tonnes) between 1990 and 2005 according to the Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution (CLRTAP) data from the UN Economic Commission for Europe, and +13% between 2005 and 2014 according to IMPACT data. Under the base air traffic forecast and assuming an advanced NO_x technology improvement rate, emissions would reach around 920 thousand tonnes in 2035 (+42% compared to 2005).

Current and future technological developments to achieve the challenging ACARE 2050 CO₂ goal are essential to mitigate substantially the increase of aviation CO₂, with realistic traffic growth assumption

(Figure 4.27). A large part of the effort of the last decade was supported within Clean Sky, and within other European projects like LEMCOTEC, ENOVAL and E-BREAK.

Most promising solutions appear to be laminar wing, and ultra-high by-pass ratio engines like Open Rotor (medium term) and distributed propulsion (longer term as explored in DISPURSAL project). New and light materials (e.g. composites for fan blade) should also provide benefits. It is unclear what is projected on new aircraft architectures before 2050, but AHEAD project illustrates a radical aircraft configuration change.

Figure 4.26 - NOx emissions are likely to increase in the future, but advanced engine combustor technology could help mitigate their growth

Figure 4.27 - Global aviation CO₂ forecast with ACARE assumption

(Assumptions: ACARE 2050 is achieved in 2050 and fully introduced in the 2050 fleet; there is a continuous improvement of average efficiency from now to 2050; ICAO 37th assembly average traffic growth of 4.6% is taken)

A new assessment was performed against ACARE CO₂ and NO_x goals and is summarized in the following Table 4.3. Although, there is no ACARE objective related to ultrafine particles, this is now a key environmental and regulatory concern, which requires appropriate mitigation solutions (combustor technology and fuel composition).

	Reference 2000	ACARE 2020 Goals (at TRL6)		ACARE 2050 Goals (at TRL6)	
		High Level	detailed (SRA)	High Level	detailed (SRIA)
CO ₂	<i>Representative technology of aircraft & engine with 2000 EIS, & representative 2000 ATM</i>	"-50% per pass km"	aircraft: -20% to -25% engine: -15% to -20% ATM: -5% to -10%	"-75% per pass km"	aircraft & engine: -68% ATM: -12% Other: -12%
NO _x (LTO)		"-80%"	engine: -60% CAEP6 ; complement achieved by aircraft + ATM	"-90%"	engine: -75% CAEP6 ; complement achieved by aircraft + ATM
NO _x (Cruise)		"-80%"	Achieved through -50% Fuel Burn & -60% cruise EINO _x reduction	"-90%"	Achieved through -75% Fuel Burn & further cruise EINO _x reduction
Other emissions		"damaging emissions reduced"	emissions qualitatively reduced (particles, CO, UHC) and better understanding of impacts	"emissions-free taxiing" + qualitative reduction	knowledge of emissions (particles, VOC) and better understanding of impacts

Table 4.3 - FORUM-AE assessment against ACARE emissions goals [FORUM-AE]

Operational measures are among the elements in the basket of measures available to States to address the impact of aviation on the environment. Improved operational measures have the potential to reduce fuel consumption, and in turn, CO₂ emissions. For every tonne of fuel reduced, an equivalent amount of 3.16t of CO₂ are avoided. CAEP has developed updated guidance material to replace [ICAO Circular 303]. This was done in order to provide States and other stakeholders.

For example, the aircraft designed for (a) high cruise efficiency and low global emissions and (b) low noise and emissions at take-off and landing near airports may be quite different. The objective (b) leads to a glider like aircraft with wide span wing and engine with a slow cold exhaust, for low engine and aerodynamic noise and reduced emissions; this configuration has a low cruise speed and poor efficiency leading to longer travel times and higher fuel consumption and emissions in cruise flight. Conversely the objective (a) leads to an aircraft with a sweptback wings and high jet exhaust velocities for fast cruise and low fuel consumption and emissions that will be noisier and have more emissions near airports because of higher speeds and exhaust velocities at take-off and landing.

The multitude of engine and noise sources and the compatibility of low CO₂ and NO_x emissions at local and global levels are a formidable set of environmental constraints and objectives that may require major breakthroughs such as: (i) variable cycle engines with high jet speeds at cruise and lower exhaust velocities at take-off and landing; (ii) novel aircraft configurations like flying wings, joined wings, V- or U-tails with shielding of noise and/or flush or buried engines. These developments that may be needed to meet (a) ever stricter environmental standards must be compatible with (b) increased efficiency and economy, since both enable the continuation of air traffic growth at the service of mobility.

In 2008, the EU decided to include aviation activities in the EU ETS [EC, 2008, Directive 2008/101/EC]. These emissions now form part of the EU's internal 20% greenhouse gas (GHG) emission reduction target for 2020. On the basis of national GHG emission reports to the United Nations Framework

Convention on Climate Change, domestic aviation from the EU Member States accounts for less than 0.5% of total EU GHG emissions³⁷, whereas international aviation represents 3%, a relative share which is increasing [EEA, 2014]. One example is the ETS which is a cornerstone of the EU's policy to combat climate change and its key tool for reducing industrial greenhouse gas emissions cost-effectively. The ETS either incentivises CO₂ emission reductions within the sector, or through the purchase of emission reductions in other sectors of the economy where abatement costs can be lower.

In addition to improving operational efficiency and achieving technological progress, aviation community is putting significant efforts in promoting the use of sustainable alternative fuels that have a reduced carbon foot print compared to conventional jet fuel. However, hurdles (mainly economic) still exist to prevent a large-scale production. A complementary global MBM scheme would act as a policy tool that would allow for an immediate response to the need for stabilising the emissions in a cost-effective manner for international aviation to meet its aspirational goal.

According to Assembly Resolution A39-3, paragraph 4, the role of a global MBM scheme is to complement a broader basket of measures to achieve the global aspirational goal (of carbon-neutral growth from 2020 onwards). Paragraph 5 of the Assembly Resolution decides to implement a global MBM scheme in the form of the Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSA) to address any annual increase in total CO₂ emissions from international civil aviation (i.e. civil aviation flights that depart in one country and arrive in a different country) above the 2020 levels, taking into account special circumstances and respective capabilities. The average level of CO₂ emissions from international aviation covered by the scheme between 2019 and 2020 represents the basis for carbon neutral growth from 2020, against which emissions in future years are compared. In any year from 2021 when international aviation CO₂ emissions covered by the scheme exceed the average baseline emissions of 2019 and 2020, this difference represents the sector's offsetting requirements for that year.

As in paragraph 9 of the Assembly Resolution, the CORSA is implemented in phases, starting with participation of States on a voluntary basis, followed by participation of all States except the States exempted from offsetting requirements, as follows:

- Pilot phase (from 2021 through 2023) and first phase (from 2024 through 2026) would apply to States that have volunteered to participate in the scheme; and
- Second phase (from 2027 through 2035) would apply to all States that have an individual share of international aviation activities in RTKs in year 2018 above 0.5 per cent of total RTKs or whose cumulative share in the list of States from the highest to the lowest amount of RTKs reaches 90 per cent of total RTKs, except Least Developed Countries (LDCs), Small Island Developing States (SIDS) and Landlocked Developing Countries (LLDCs) unless they volunteer to participate in this phase.

States that voluntarily decide to participate the CORSA may join the scheme from the beginning of a given year and should notify ICAO of their decision to join by June 30 the preceding year. CORSA *would* be the first global MBM scheme for a whole sector, and a major step to complement the efforts made by States in the context of the Paris Agreement. Action for the implementation of the global MBM scheme for international aviation from 2020 will start right after the Assembly.

The major environmental issues of aviation concern noise and emissions (Key Topic T4.1) that are the subject of different views in literature (Key Topic T4.2). The prospect of emissions free airport movements is related to the battery technology (Key Topic T4.3).

The long-term sustainability of aviation may depend on the availability of alternative fuels (Key Topic T4.4). The atmospheric research contributes to minimise the weather and environmental effects of aviation (Key Topic T4.5).

KEY TOPIC T4.1 – REDUCTION OF NOISE AND EMISSIONS

Benchmarks

As a result of technological improvements, the noise footprint of new aircraft is at least 15% smaller than that of the aircraft they replace.

According to ICAO, aircraft being produced today are 75% quieter than those manufactured 50 years ago. In spite of technological and operational advances, many airports have responded to community pressure by introducing noise-related charges on aircraft. However, the introduction of noise-related charges is often not an effective means to reduce the exposure of local communities to airport noise. Noise-related charges do not drive the development of quieter aircraft nor their deployment to airports. Additionally, noise-related charges are often introduced without a proper airport noise management plan and are often based on criteria that are inconsistent across airports and lack transparency. Funds generated by such charges are also not always dedicated to noise alleviation and prevention measures. Furthermore, the additional financial burden they put on airlines and passengers has a negative impact on the local economy.

In 2001, the ICAO Assembly unanimously endorsed the ICAO Balanced Approach to Aircraft Noise Management by adopting Resolution A33-7. The core principle of the Balanced Approach is that the noise situation at each airport is unique and that there is no one-size-fits-all solution. The ICAO Balanced Approach therefore requires that all available options be evaluated in order to identify the most suitable measure or combination of measures to mitigate a specific noise problem.

New Engine Architectures

Preliminary studies to probe various technologies have already been conducted, or are being conducted, both for Ultra High Bypass Ratio engines and for Open Rotors. These two technological tracks are both presumed to lower fuel consumption and to reduce noise emission (at least jet noise, since tonal noise may dramatically increase for Open Rotors).

For instance, from 2008 to 2011, within the DREAM project (EC 7 framework program), preliminary campaigns were led to compare noise measurements and numerical simulations on some Open Rotor configurations. Computational Fluid Dynamic (CFD) and Computational AeroAcoustics (CAA) made by Onera (France) appeared to be in good agreement with the measurements performed by Tsagi (Russia).

Progress Up-to-Now/ Predictions up-to-2025/ Evolutionary Progress Up-to-2025

In 2014, ICAO adopted a new standard that will result in a reduction of 7 Effective Perceived Noise Decibels (EPNdB) compared to the current Chapter 4 Standard. The new standard will apply from 2018.

As a result of technological improvements, the noise footprint (85 dB(A) maximum sound pressure level contour) of new aircraft is up to 50% smaller than that of the aircraft they replace (Source: Lufthansa)

Further design improvements such as blended wing body and engine shielding by fuselage and tail plane offer the potential to reduce perceived noise from aircraft by 65% by 2050 (Source: Sustainable Aviation) Airlines will be investing USD 4.5 trillion in newer and quieter aircraft over the next 20 years (Source: IATA) ICAO's final report to CAEP/8 meeting established the goals for four classes or categories of aircraft were as follows (Table 4.4):

Aircraft Category	Margin to Chapter 4 (EPNdB)	
	Mid-Term (2018)	Long-Term (2028)
Regional Jet	13.0±4.6	20.0±5.5
Small-Med. Range Twin	21.0±4.6	23.5±5.5
Long-Range Twin	20.5±4.6	23.0±5.5
Long-Range Quad	20.0±4	23.5±5.5

Table 4.4 -The noise reduction goals for four classes or categories of aircraft (Source: ICAO)

The use of measured static engine test noise data or pseudo-random noise signals with spectral shape and tonal content representative of **turbofan engines** is an acceptable alternative to the use of actual flight test noise data samples for determination of analysis system compatibility. The systems can be considered to be compatible if the resulting differences are no greater than 0.5 PNdB for an integration time of 32 seconds.

New Engine Architectures

Beyond these local improvements, some attempts have been made to experiment far more dramatic modifications of the engine architectures.

Extensions of works made from 2008 to 2011, within the DREAM project (EC 7 framework program) are now conducted within the Clean Sky Framework: In France for instance, Snecma's Hera test vehicle underwent preliminary testing in Onera's S1 wind tunnel in July 2013. Full-scale propeller tests were made in 2015.

Further new technological research programs have already been launched. Especially, it is worth mentioning COBRA, a new EU-Russia cooperation program that started in October 2013 and that is considered as the continuation of VITAL and DREAM. Actually, COBRA is dedicated to the consolidation of Ultra High Bypass Ratio (UHBR) Contra-Rotating TurboFan (CRTF) that was once explored by Kuznetsov – one of the Russian partners – in the early 90s and further explored within VITAL. CRTFs associate two contra-rotating fans in a nacelle and thus appear as a kind of hybrid between turbofans and Open Rotors. CRTFs envisaged by COBRA strongly differ from those experimented with within the VITAL program and by the Russian engine manufacturer. Kuznetsov's NK-93 (BPR ~ 16.5) highlight the good behaviour in term of performance of this concept, but the design was made over more than 20 years ago without the current computational tools and free from present environmental constraints.

At the time being indeed, first NK-93 full scale tests showed that noise performances of such UHBR CRTFs were not so bad and that the combustion chamber has been up to now one of the most efficient among the Russian ones. Compared to VITAL, COBRA plans to explore a higher bypass ratio (BPR ~

11 within VITAL) with the obligation to use a gear box in order to reduce the fan speed. This reduction will directly impact the tip velocity and thus will allow the fan noise to be reduced. Within the COBRA project, the BPR investigated is from 15 up to 25, according to the detailed specifications proposed by the partners in charge of this activity (Snecma and Kuznetsov).

A specific conception/optimization will be proposed by European research centres (Onera and DLR) and by Russian partners (CIAM, Kuznetsov, AEROSILA and MIPT). Both designs will be manufactured by COMOTI and tested at CIAM's C3-A test rig facility.

NASA/P&W Ultra High Bypass Turbofan Research

Under the Engine Validation of Noise and Emissions Reduction Technologies (EVNERT) task of the NASA Glenn Revolutionary Aero Space Engine Research (RASER) contract, which was sponsored by the NASA Quiet Aircraft Technology program, NASA and Pratt & Whitney (P&W) formed a collaborative partnership to develop an Ultra High Bypass engine demonstrator. The goal was to verify the potential advantages in reducing fuel burn, noise and emissions that could be achieved with an engine cycle having a fan to core flow bypass ratio of 13 and a fan pressure ratio of 1.3. P&W designed their engine, which they labelled the Geared Turbofan (GTF), with a geared Low-Pressure Core fan allowing the core and fan to operate at different speeds, thus optimizing the performance and reducing the complexity of the core.

NASA UHB Fan Noise Reduction Research

To help meet the aggressive N+1 noise reduction goal of 32 dB cumulative below the Stage 4 noise regulation, the SFW Project supported a high fidelity wind tunnel experiment of a scale model UHB turbofan-simulator to investigate the potential of two advanced noise reduction technologies, called Over-the-Rotor (OTR) metal foam acoustic treatment and Soft Vanes (SV) acoustically treated stator vanes, for the UHB engine cycle (Figure 4.28). The technologies were developed in a partnership between the NASA Glenn Research Centre and the NASA Langley Research Centre. The testing was conducted in the NASA Glenn 9'x15' LSWT using the Glenn UHB Drive Rig propulsion simulator at test section velocities simulating aircraft take off, approach and landing speeds. The goal of these two technologies was to reduce the noise generated by the fan rotor, and that generated by the interaction of the rotor wakes with the stator vanes with a minimum impact on the aerodynamic performance of the fan.

Figure 4.28 - Illustration of the UHB Fan Model identifying the locations of two noise reduction technologies used during the NASA Ultra High Bypass Fan Noise Reduction Test, which were Over-the-Rotor acoustic treatment and Soft Stator Vanes.

The Over-the-Rotor acoustic treatment was designed to replace the traditional hard wall fan case and rub strip over the fan tip. The new design consisted of a 0.10" thick perforated hard plastic polymer flow surface with a 1.5" thick porous metal foam material behind it and contained within a steel shell which interfaced with the rest of the model hardware. The hard-plastic flow surface had 0.035" holes drilled into it resulting in a 20% open area and allowing the acoustic pressure disturbances to pass through into the metal foam liner behind it. The size and number of holes was designed to minimize impact on the fan aerodynamic performance. The metal foam had a density of 6% to 8% (or 94% to 92% open area) with extremely small holes of approximately 100 pores per cubic inch of material. The metal foam presented a random and tortuous path to the incoming acoustic waves, forcing dissipation of the wave energy internally in the foam.

The design allows the local acoustic waves on the vane suction surface to penetrate into the vane's four internal chambers, where the acoustic energy would dissipate.

Possible or Predictable Breakthroughs

Ultra-High Bypass Ratio engines (UHBR) are being studied, but with very hard integration issues, since the fan diameter is even greater than that presently used. With this option, noise reduction would basically entail pushing the same technologies further than those presented above. However, it must be kept in mind that new noise sources could emerge from these more "open" engines, especially if traditional ones, such as fan and jet, are lowered. In this case, core machinery noise, such as compressor noise, turbine noise or even combustion noise would need to be considered.

Currently, there is reasonable confidence that Open Rotors will be able to meet the strictest regulation of Chapter 14 in a few years. From a programmatic standpoint, the main framework for such integrated research is the Clean Sky research program, which will allow the engine manufacturer Snecma to produce a demonstrator by the end of the decade. Through this platform, new noise technologies, such as 3D-optimized blade design and pylon blowing in order to strongly reduce the interaction of the pylon wake with the blades, will be demonstrated. Current liner-based technologies

will probably be used less, since they are both inefficient and impossible to insert into open architectures.

Figure 4.29 - Open Rotor mounted on Hera vehicle (Snecma) and under test at the S1 Onera wind tunnel and the simulation of interactions between the two propellers (Onera)

It is also worth mentioning that the most recent trends tend to locate these forthcoming Open Rotors (Figure 4.29) rearward, near the empennage, between two vertical stabilizers, both to gain from the masking effect for community and to increase comfort and safety for passengers. Currently, aircraft manufacturers have not yet chosen between the two competitive technologies of UHBR and Open Rotors, but this critical choice is considered as imminent and was likely to arise before 2015. Neither the first nor the second technological route will be sufficient to meet the stringent new objectives defined by ACARE for 2020 (Figure 4.30).

It is generally assumed that though 2020 objectives will be reached through enforcing new Noise Abatement Procedures (NAP) in addition to NRTs, 2050 objectives will require a breakthrough in aircraft architectures.

Figure 4.30 - Further ACARE objectives for 2050

Clearly, these most silent configurations would then involve integrating engines into the aircraft fuselage, or architectures where the engines would be completely shielded. Once again, these future configurations would strongly reduce both fuel consumption – through a dramatic reduction of the drag – and noise, with masking effects. Succeeding to build up such a configuration is a huge challenge, since it would involve fully reinventing the entire aircraft with unexplored aerodynamic effects and brand-new propulsion systems. In particular, these engines would ingest air flows with intense distortion of the boundary layer, an unfamiliar configuration that remains to be addressed by research. However, the greatest challenge is probably not technical but commercial and psychological. Before engaging in such developments, manufacturers need to convince airliners of the expected benefits and the latter need to accustom their customers to the idea of embarking on such new aircraft. These challenges go far beyond technical issues.

Identification of Gaps

Some of these technologies are suspected to increase the aircraft overall weight and, above all, they lead to additional drag.

Currently, few things are known about these sources, but some preliminary work suggests that they could be more complex than expected. For instance, combustion noise is known to be divided into “direct noise” – i.e., sound directly stemming from the combustion process in the chamber – and “indirect noise”, due to the conversion of vortices into sound waves through the turbine stages. “Direct noise” was thought to be more important than “indirect noise”, however, a recent study tends to prove the contrary. Investigation work is still underway.

In addition to UHBR, another strategy could also be to continue increasing BPR using the Open Rotor architecture (OR). Noise is then the most critical issue, along with safety: Whereas single propellers radiate mostly tonal noise in the propeller plane, two counter-rotating rotors without nacelle radiate many tones over a wide frequency-range due to complex and intense noise interference mechanisms. Actually, the radiated frequencies combine all of the possible linear combinations between the two blade passing frequencies and this spectrum is propagated in all directions.

Ongoing research activities are facing this drawback and several tricks are being investigated to lower this excessive noise: Tuning parameters, such as blades shape, blade length (especially differentiating the length between the first propeller and the second) and the gap between the two propellers, or even their respective rotating speeds or clocking, are among the various methods being experimented.

KEY TOPIC T4.2– LITERATURE ON THE ASSESSMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL TARGETS OF AVIATION

Air Pollution Related Studies

It is clear that between alternative transport modes aviation’s impact on climate change deserves special attention. Due to typical flight altitudes in the upper troposphere and above, the effect of aircraft engine emissions like e.g. water vapour, nitrogen oxides and aerosols on radiative forcing agents is substantial. It is thought that doubling of aircraft movements in the next 15 years will increase the impact of aviation on global climate. For instance, Macintosh and Wallace (2009) analysed the contribution of aviation industry to climate change since 1990 and projected the international civil aviation emissions to 2025. They found that CO₂ emission of international aviation would increase

more than 110% between 2005 and 2025 and so they concluded that the emissions could unlikely to be stabilized at levels consistent with risk averse climate targets without restricting demand.

Therefore, supra-national organizations on aviation put forward some challenges regarding mitigating the risks on global warming and climate change. According to Schilling (2016)'s Report the objectives set by aviation industry in 2009 cannot be met especially the long-term reduction goal of CO₂ emissions by 2050. AIRCAT project is a collaborative work of IATA and DLR to identify possible challenges, obstacles and roadblocks to the deployment of new technologies. They selected three aircraft designs of low-emissions concepts as battery-driven, hybrid wing body and strut braced wing with open rotor design. In addition, analyse two types of low-carbon alternative fuels as drop-in solar jet fuel and natural liquid gas. Consequently, they assessed that the majority of emissions reductions necessary to meet the 2050 goal would have to come from low-carbon fuels and radically new fuels. Another study is coming with Hassan et al. (2017)'s criticism regarding the challenges. Hassan et al. (2017) studied the feasibility of the aviation goals on CO₂ emission reductions designated for 2050 and by considering 40 different scenarios they found that these goals are not feasible because of the high demand growth. Moreover, with medium or low demand growth coupled with high technology introduction rates and faster retirement of old aircraft they found that the goals are feasible. According to Jovanevic and Vracarevic (2016) especially rising travel demand constrained to perform designated challenge. They studied the feasibility of global climate stabilization goals (70% reduction of CO₂ emissions) with the International Civil Aviation Organization's forecasts of future commercial aviation growth and found that, air transport's emissions were going to rise five-fold (4.9 times) in the 2005-2040 period and CO₂ emissions of air transport would be higher by 50% in 2040 than in 2005 due to the sudden increase in the volume of air-transport tourist trips. Moreover, they proposed that policy focus should shift to more efficient implementation of market-driven instruments, which, apart from creating incentives to develop and use low-emission technologies can also reduce the demand for travel.

Beyond travel demand, Heinemann et al. (2017) analysed tube and wing configurations in terms of reaching the Flightpath 2050 goals. They used simplified methods to model the technologies and produce statements on how fuel burn was changed on overall aircraft level. Finally, they found that with selected technologies in the study it was not likely to reach any of the goals. They proposed that for reaching the aforementioned goals of EU considering noise and NO_x goals radical approaches would be necessary for the airframe and the propulsion system. However, Ozaki (2017)'s study contradicted to Heinemann et al. (2017)'s study from a different perspective. He studied the potential of NO_x and proposed that if all of NO_x has been used global warming can be protected. According to Ozaki (2017) NO_x elimination should be stopped because based on his calculations for eliminating the World consumption of 2.5×10^9 tons of NO_x 17.6 billion tons of CO₂ was released. He asserted that NO_x is playing most important role for the promotion of CO₂ assimilation and nutrient N and P in drainage should be used for fixing CO₂ and protecting global warming.

Alternative fuel usage is another option among the researchers. However, according to Noh et al. (2016) using alternative energy fuels has other research issues that should be met in future. Noh et al. (2016) examined alternative energy bio-jet fuel with maintenance perspective and based on their evaluations they asserted that the use of biofuel would offer the benefit to aircraft maintenance. In addition, they argued that global aviation world need to be underpinned by the awareness of the good effect of the usage of biofuel on engine process and procedure.

For mitigation alternatives, Linke et al. (2017) proposed Intermediate Stop Operations which was discussed in several scholarly works by combining it with different models. Finally, they found that a

more realistic medium-range aircraft for flying ISO could on the other hand have a positive climate impact due to the expected lower cruise altitudes.

It is clear that dealing with global warming and climate change issue is holistic and should be analysed with a systemic perspective. Lue et al. (2016) presented the main results of 'REACT: A European Strategic Research Agenda for climate-friendly transport' project, which was co-financed by the European Commission, in their study. Based on their findings, technology alone would not be sufficient to achieve the necessary reductions in carbon emissions and they proposed that integrated solutions should be necessary. For instance, technological improvements might offer significant GHG reduction potential, but strong interventions in policy schemes would be needed. In addition, they asserted that long-term technological solutions could not be treated independently from the short-term behavioural change and behavioural and social changes should be recognized as paramount. Another social or policy perspective is coming from Gössling et al. (2016) analysed the issue and asserted that scientific insights were not translated into transport policies far reaching enough to achieve climate mitigation objectives and called this issue as an "implementation gap". In their study they analysed the issue on EU level and found that policy officers had diverging ideas of the level of decarbonisation that needed to be achieved in the transport sector and over which timelines; responsibility ownership; applied concrete measures to cut emissions. Therefore, they concluded that there were number of vital reasons why significant climate policy for the transport sector was not being effectively developed at the EU supranational level and implemented in member states.

Chen et al. (2016) applied en route traffic demand model and for estimating the fuel consumption used Boeing Fuel Flow Method in their study. Based on their real-time application results, they asserted that the proposed method could characterize well the dynamics and the fluctuation of the en route emissions and provided satisfactory prediction results with appropriate uncertainty limits.

Dahlmann et al. (2016) focused in their study on preparing a methodology based on Monte Carlo simulation of an updated non-linear climate-chemistry response model AirClim. They integrated uncertainties in the climate assessment of mitigation options. After applying it to a use case they demonstrated that proposed methodology could be used to analyse even small differences between scenarios with mean flight altitude variations.

It can be asserted that all researchers in this field have a consensus on the demand of new technologies enabling ways to significantly improve aircraft performance for ACARE goals regarding emission reduction. Kling et al. (2016) discussed the issue on the modification of the inlet of an Ultra-High Bypass Ratio turbofan nacelle with adaptive structure technology with a EU funded project MorphElle which was concluded between October 2013 and November 2015. They established a pool of concepts for an adaptive nacelle inlet and performed a down selection and identified most promising one. They elaborated by using Computational Fluid Dynamics and structural simulations the selected concept and examined the impact at aircraft level. Finally, they developed a first prototype of shape adaptive mechanism as proof of concept. They found that the aircraft assessment demonstrated a possible fuel burn reduction of up to 5% for the considered mission. However, they stated that this benefit was strongly coupled with the use reference nacelle geometry which did not reflect a state-of-the-art nacelle contour.

Hayes et al. (2017) discussed the applications of exergy applications in the aviation sector by reviewing the recent literature focusing primarily on commercial applications. They derived the limitations and discussed the potential benefits for furthering proliferation of the second law method in aerospace community. They demonstrated that exergy analysis and mapping exergy destruction would provide to aerospace industry with following six items. These were;

- “A consistent common currency to allow consistent accounting across sub systems,
- Loss-producing mechanisms can be readily mapped at the system level,
- Analysis space provides physically possible/meaningful bounds,
- Provides foundation for robust and efficient optimization,
- should produce same result regardless of technique utilized, and also match the results of first law implicit methods, but providing additional insight on top of this
- an understanding of how one system influences and interacts with other non-discipline specific sub-systems” (Hayes et al., 2017)

Another perspective is coming from Balakrishnan et al. (2016) with next generation air transportation system which was presented as FAA’s vision of how nation’s aviation system would operate in 2025 and beyond. The NextGen initiative was established in 2003 in order to meet the challenges of predicted increase in demand. The system was including satellite-based navigation and control of aircraft, advanced digital communications, advanced infrastructure for greater information sharing, and enhanced connectivity between all components of the air transportation systems. They asserted that these characteristics of the system might have the potential to increase system efficiency by reducing delays, robustness by reducing the impact of weather disruptions and energy efficiency by reducing fuel burn. Therefore, these improvements would lead to decrease environmental impact with ensuring safety and accommodating the increased demand. For the European Counterpart Single European Sky Air Traffic Management Research (SESAR) initiative may be accepted as similar ongoing effort also.

Reynolds (2016) prepared a report for monetizing the environmental benefits of Terminal Flight Data Manager (TFDM) capabilities which reduce fuel burn and gaseous emissions, and in turn reduce climate change and air quality effects. He created a methodology for taking TFDM “engines on” taxi time savings and converts them to fuel and CO₂ emissions savings, accounting for aircraft fleet mix at each of 27 TFDM analysis reports over a 2016-2048 analysis timeframe. Finally, for all 27 TFDM analysis airports for 2016-2048, it was estimated that totally 954.000 metric tons of fuel reduction and 2.0 million tons of CO₂ reduction would be reached.

Galssock et al. (2017) analysed two case studies for highlighting the positive advantages of hybrid electric propulsion for aircraft. However, they asserted that negative compromise of electric propulsion remained significant because of the increased system weight compared to pure internal combustion alternatives. They proposed the use of Hybrid Electric Propulsion systems for transition to fully electric aircraft first and stressed that because there were hybrid and electric aircraft concepts emerging from small light sport types through to intercontinental heavy transport regulatory and certification systems should be reformed.

Karcher (2016) prepared a theoretical model for predicting properties of water droplets and ice particles in jet contrails and found that avoiding contrail cirrus formation would mitigate aviation climate impact and changing contrail formation stage had large but unexplored mitigation potential. For future developments he proposed that the atmospheric response to reductions in initial contrail ice number should be explored using global climate models with an interactive parameterization scheme for contrail ice formation depending on variable soot particle number emissions and atmospheric conditions.

Owen et al. (2010) presented new aviation emission scenarios to 2050 that were designed to interpret the IPCC SRES storylines under the four main families A1B, A2, B1, and B2 with a further look to 2100. Moreover, they calculated an additional scenario assuming that the technology targets of ACARE were achieved or not. They found that emissions of CO₂ from aviation between 2000 and 2050 were

projected to grow by between a factor of 2.0 and 3.6 depending on the applied scenario and emissions of NO_x from aviation over the same period were projected to grow by between a factor of 1.2 and 2.7. Furthermore, based on their findings, they asserted that B1-ACARE scenario would differ from the SRES scenarios as it would require significant continuing improvements in fuel efficiency and some radical technological advances in the second half of the century probable.

Noise-Reduction Related Studies

Bernardo et al. (2016) studied on noise reduction by considering fleet-level analysis. They used rapid automated airport noise models which can be simulated by using Design of Experiments. They used surrogate models to model the airport noise space in conjunction with the equivalency assumption to examine two potential technology scenarios in a target forecast year, simulating technology and market performance factors to identify vehicle classes that could have the greatest impact in reducing contour area. Based on their findings, they asserted that technology and market performance of future notional Small Single Aisle and Large Single Aisle vehicle aircraft have the highest positive correlations with potential reductions in contour area.

Schwaiger and Wills (2016) proposed that cyclo-gyro propulsion can be used for vertical launch and had potential to achieve efficiency beyond the range of conventional fixed wing and rotorcraft. They assumed that their technology was feasible for VTOL aircraft that can safely form densely packed swarms and would solve the challenges facing the air environment of the future.

Postorino and Mantecchini (2016) analysed the effectiveness of airport noise mitigation strategies and considered airport-related factors, flying paths, and aircraft type in their study. They tested their assessment process on a real case in Italy and found that their assessment model provided a priori evaluation measures that are in line with current data concerning the implemented post-variant scenario. With their approach they considered simultaneously a number of standard measures together and by the way several potential scenarios could be compared.

Bartlett (2016) aimed to determine whether current turbofan noise reduction nozzles could reduce the amount of noise for turbojet engines at two different thrust levels. He tested experimentally three turbofan engine nozzles by comparing the original turbo jet engine. He recorded six samples of thirty decibel levels and frequencies at idle and at a higher thrust level. Finally, he found that the turbofan nozzle designs used in this research project did not make any major improvements in reducing the overall noise. He determined some reductions in DB levels for some specific frequencies. Moreover, he identified that engine cycle efficiencies were degraded by these nozzles as compared to the original and proposed that alternate designs that did not penetrate the gas path could reduce the negative effects on engine parameters.

There are many studies regarding noise and aviation in literature. Therefore, for understanding the noise problem in aviation, scientometric approach is applied. Data is retrieved from Web of Science database by using "aviation" and "noise" keywords in Topic Sentence field. After search, 461 publications are reached, and metadata of these publications downloaded in text format. Then, pre-processing is applied as duplication check. Citespace open-source software is used for visualization (Chen, 2006). The timeline view of the intersection of noise and aviation field is demonstrated in the Figure 4.31:

Figure 4.31 - Timeline Demonstration of Noise Related Scholarly Publication

As can be seen in figure 4.31 studies initiated since 1994 and there are 8 clusters. All clusters are represented by the yellow lines and size of nodes is representing the volume of the studies and different colours in these nodes are representing the time interval that concept studied. It can be seen that health and social issues regarding noise are mostly studied in the literature. Actually, it is assumed to find out a technology cluster in this graph but as can be seen in the fig. 1, technology related nodes are not revealed as expected. It is thought that selected keywords may affect this result.

4.2 Emissions Free Taxiing at Airports

***Flightpath 2050 goal 10: "Aircraft movements are emissions free when taxing".**

The taxiing of aircraft on engine power and the use of auxiliary power units (APU) on the ground can be significant contributors to emissions at airports and also generate noise. The most obvious way to achieve goal 10 is to use electric towing vehicles. There are technical aspects like ensuring compatibility of towing brackets and enough traction power. Also, infrastructure aspects with recharging facilities for a fleet of electric towing vehicles. At last, but not least, the coverage of the initial investment and operating cost. These must be seen in the context of lower environmental impact.

- Input:

- Fuel spent, and emissions associated with taxiing at airports: worldwide and at specific airport;
- Availability of vehicles, infrastructure and other costs.

The feasibility and economic of emissions - free taxiing thus critically depends on the available battery technology (Key Topic T4.2).

KEY TOPIC T4.3 – AIRCRAFT TOWING BY ELECTRIC VEHICLES

Benchmark / State of the Art-Battery

The currently preferred battery technology for ground movements at the airport or on the airfield and in the aircraft, itself are the lead-acid and the nickel cadmium battery.

Aircraft:

- a. Internal engine starter generator (ESG) set;
- b. Auxiliary power unit (APU) which includes battery and super/ultra-capacitor;
- c. Flight control actuation, and a fault tolerant Power Management and Distribution (PMAD);
- d. Motor drive system.

Other motorized movements at the airport:

- a. Moving the aircraft from the gate to the starting position;
- b. Other motorized movement at the airport.

Both technologies are long in the field and therefore technically very mature but suffer from insufficient energy density and cycle life. In order to meet the future requirements, substantial

improvements in energy density, lifetime, cost and charging infrastructure are needed. The following Tables 4.5 – 4.8 give an overview of the most important key figures of common battery systems.

	Characteristics	Ni-Cd	Ni-MH	Lead Acid	Li-Ion
1	Cell voltage / V	1.25	1.25	2	3.7
2	Spec. energy density / Wh kg ⁻¹	40-60	60-90	30-50	50-250
3	Energy density / Wh dm ⁻³	150-190	300-340	80-90	100-700
6	Cycle life	1000-1500	500-1000	200-300	300-10000
7	Operating Temperature / °C	-40 to 60	-20 to 60	-20 to 60	-20 to 60
8	Self-discharge / month	20 %	up to 30 %	5 %	<5 %
9	Overcharge tolerance	Moderate	low	high	Very low
10	Maintenance	1-2 month	?	3-6 month	Not required

Table 4.5 - Comparison of different types of battery chemistries [adapted from Gianfranco Pistoia, "Batteries for Portable Devices", Elsevier 2005]

➤ Aircraft- Batteries

	Battery manufacturer/model nr.	Chemistry	Aircraft	System Voltage / V	Capacity / Ah
1	Saft-2758	Ni-Cd	A320	24	23
2	Saft- 4059	Ni-Cd	A340	24	40
3	Saft-405 CH	Ni-Cd	A330	24	40
4	Acme Aerospace Inc-263BA101-2	Fibre Ni-Cd (FNC)	B-777	24	47
5	Saft-539 CH1	Ni-Cd	B-737NG	24	53
6	Saft-539 CH1	Ni-Cd	B-767-400	24	53
7	Saft-539 CH2	Ni-Cd	A380	24	50
8	GS Yuasa LVP-40-8-65	Li-Ion	B-787	28.8	75
9	Saft-40176-7	Ni-Cd	B_747 x	24	40
10	Concorde RG150-1	VRLA	B-717	24	3.5
11	Marathon Nacro 7-75M3-120	Ni-Cd		8.4	75
12	Concorde D8565/5-1	SLA, lead acid	C-130	24	30
13	Concorde D8565/11-1	SLA, lead acid	C-141, F4	24	10

Table 4.6 - Details of batteries used in different aircraft [Adapted from a. Aircraft batteries - current trend towards more electric aircraft IET Electr. Syst. Transp., 2017, 7, 2, 93-103]

	Li-ion*	Ni-Cd**
Nominal cell voltage / V	3.20	1.20
Battery voltage / V	25.6	24.0
Capacity / Ah	45-55	23
Energy / Wh	1280	552

	Li-ion*	Ni-Cd**
Typical battery cost / US \$	~21.000	~6.500
Battery Cost per Wh / US \$	16.4	11.1
Spec. Energy density, Wh/kg	110.0	21.65
Weight / kg	22-25	26
*EagerPicher Technologies, LLC MAR-9526 (LFP), ** SAFT 410946 Mod. 2758		

Table 4.7 - Comparison of Li-ion and Ni-Cd aircraft grade batteries [Adapted from a. Aircraft batteries - current trend towards more electric aircraft IET Electr. Syst. Transp., 2017, 7, 2, 93-103]

➤ Automotive Batteries (towing tractor, etc....)

	Cell level energy density Wh/kg	Cell level energy density Wh/L	Durability cycle life 100% DoD	Price estimate US\$/Wh	Power C-rate	Safety thermal runaway onset, °C	Voltage / V	Temperature range in ambient conditions °C
LiCoO ₂	170-185	450-490	>500	0.31-0.46	1 C	170	3.6	-20 to 60
LiFePO ₄ (EV/PHEV)	90-125	130-300	>2.000	0.3-0.6	5 C cont. 10 C pulse	270	3.2	-20 to 60
LiFePO ₄ (HEV)	80-108	200-240	>2.000	0.4-1.0	30 C cont. 50 C pulse	270	3.2	-20 to 60
NCM (HEV)	150	270-290	>1.500	0.5-0.9	20 C cont. 40 C pulse	215	3.7	-20 to 60
NCM (EV/PHEV)	155-190	330-365	>1.500	0.5-0.9	1 C cont. 5 C pulse	215	3.7	-20 to 60
Titanate vs. NCM/LMO	65-100	118-200	>>12.000	1-1.7	5 C cont. 10 C pulse	Not susceptible	2.5	-50 to 75
Manganese spinel (EV/PHEV)	90-100	280	>1000	0.45-0.55	3-5 C cont.	255	3.8	-20 to 50

Table 4.8 - Summary of the main (Automotive) Lithium-ion types / State of the art [Adapted from Johnson Metthey Technol. Rev., 2015, 59, (1), 4-13]

Taxiing Concepts

➤ Off-Board Systems

- **Hybrid-Electric Tractor for Taxiing "TaxiBot"** [TaxiBot, "TaxiBot Product Homepage," Available: <http://www.taxibot-international.com/>, [Accessed 11 2017]

- **Electric Schlepper “eSchlepper”** [E-PORT AN, „Homepage“, Available <http://www.e-port-an.de/projekt/die-neuen-e-fahrzeuge/eschlepper.html>], [Accessed 11 2017]
- **Taxiing Vehicle by Airbus**, [Airbus, <http://www.aircraft.airbus.com/innovation/future-by-airbus/smarter-skies/low-emission-ground-operations/>], [Accessed 11 2017]
- **Trace Towbot**, [<http://towbots.us/>], [Accessed 11 2017]

➤ Off-Board Systems

- **Electric Taxiing Systems (ETS)/ Green Taxi Systems (On-Board)**
- **Battery/fuel cell-based Electrical Energy Storage Systems (ESS)**, [<http://www.wheeltug.gi/>], [Accessed 11 2017]; [<http://www.env-isa.com/en/expertise/egts-electric-green-taxiing-system-safran/>], [Accessed 11 2017]

Reference State in 2010 - Battery

Since the lead acid batteries and the nickel-cadmium batteries are technically exhausted (Table 4.9), no significant improvement in the energy and power density is expected. Therefore, a reference value for 2010 is difficult to set for lead-acid and the nickel cadmium battery. Rather, there is a shift to lithium-ion technology in the aviation industry. Lithium-ion chemistry offers a large variety of materials and cell architectures, which enables the possibility to design high-power as well as high energy systems. In this respect, it has to be noted again that choice of active material, which is able to reversibly insert and extract lithium-ions within vacancies in their crystal structure, decisively influences the amount of energy that can be stored in LIBs. The commercial breakthrough of lithium-ion batteries did not happen until the discovery of these insertion compounds, also known as host matrices.

	Characteristics	Ni-Cd	Ni-MH	Lead Acid	Li-Ion
1	Cell voltage / V	1.25	1.25	2	3.7
2	Spec. energy density / Wh kg ⁻¹	40-60	60-90	30-50	50-250
3	Energy density / Wh dm ⁻³	150-190	300-340	80-90	100-700
6	Cycle life	1000-1500	500-1000	200-300	300-10000
7	Operating Temperature / °C	-40 to 60	-20 to 60	-20 to 60	-20 to 60
8	Self-discharge / month	20 %	up to 30 %	5 %	<5 %
9	Overcharge tolerance	Moderate	low	high	Very low
10	Maintenance	1-2 month	?	3-6 month	Not required

Table 4.9 - Comparison of different types of battery chemistries [adapted from Gianfranco Pistoia, "Batteries for Portable Devices", Elsevier 2005]

For the lithium-ion technology, it can be stated that these are mainly based on carbon as the anode and transition metal oxides, as well as phosphate as the cathode material. This combination and its variation have been state-of-the-art for years. Increase in the energy density could be mainly achieved by optimizing the cell production process. As an example of the state of the art from 2010 for an energy cell (Figure 4.32), the Panasonic NRC18650 should serve with an energy density of about 230 Wh/kg.

Figure 4.32 – Specification sheet for the Panasonic NRC 18650

Due to the wide range of applications, different requirement profiles result and thus many types of cells with different specifications results. Improvements are achieved with consistent chemistry mainly through improvements in manufacturing and engineering. The Table 4.10 shows an overview of various cells launched since 2010.

Cell type	Manufacturer	Nominal voltage	Capacity	Weight	Temp. Range	Specific energy	Energy density	Specific power	Cycle life	Comments
		V	Ah	g	°C	Wh/kg	Wh/L	W/kg	cycles	
LiAlMn oxide with LTO	Altair nano	24	60	2740	-40 to 55	52	106	~800	>16000	Available as a module, data taken from an evaluation specification sheet. Cycle life to 80% balance of life (BOL) capacity at 2C charge discharge with 100% DOD at 25°C. Calendar life of ~25 years. Can be recharged in ~15 min
LiFePO ₄ and graphite	Lifebatt 2295130	3.3	18	550	-40 to 60	108	~210	>1300	2000-3000	This is a larger form factor prismatic cell. For 1s pulses, the specific power is >2600 W/kg. Maximum charge current is 90A, full charge in ~ 15 min
Li Mn and NMC	Molicell IBR18650BC	3.6	1.5	45	-30 to 60	129	326	~2100	750	Cycle life is to 80% BOL capacity for 20A discharge at 23°C, would be higher for lower discharge rates.
LiCoO ₂ and graphite	Panasonic UR18650Y	3.7	2	43.3	-20 to 60	162	421	~300		Standard type of cell
LiCoO ₂ and graphite	Panasonic UR18650E	3.6	2.15	44.5	-20 to 60	162	432	~500	>500	High power cell. Capacity ~85% of BOL at 500 cycles

Li NMC	Molicell <i>IHR18650BN</i>	3.6	2.2	45	-20 to 60	170	450	~700	>700	Cycle life is to 80% BOL capacity at 4 A and 23°C
LiCoO ₂ and graphite	Panasonic <i>NCR18650</i>	3.6	2.25	45		180	~500	~1400	400	High power cell, cycle life I to 80% BOL
LiCoO ₂ and NMC and graphitic	Molicell <i>ICR18650M</i>	3.7	2.8	50	-30 to 60	216	609	~300	>300	Capacity >90% of BOL after 300 cycles at 23°C
New Nickel Platform with heat resistant	Panasonic <i>NCR18650B</i>	3.6	3.35	47.5	-20 to 60	243	676	~450		High energy cell, highest specific energy in readily available cells
LiCoO ₂ and tin-based	Sony <i>NexelionWH1</i>	3.5	3.5	53.5		226	723		~300	Paucity of technical information available. Cells mostly used in Sony own laptops. Bare details in Chinese with Arabic numbers from: www.sony.com.cn/news_center/press_release/technology/1955_3787

Table 4.10 - Some characteristics of commercially available secondary lithium-ion cell, ordered by specific energy [Underwater Technology, 33, 3, 2016]

Progress Up-to-Now - Battery

Since the lead acid batteries and the nickel-cadmium batteries are technically exhausted, no significant improvement in terms of energy density, cycle life, calendar life etc. is expected. In the fields of lithium-ion batteries, the situation looks a bit more optimistic. In general, an increase in the energy density, with state-of-the-art chemistry, could be mainly achieved by optimizing the form factor and the cell production process. As an example, a Panasonic NRC1865 cell should be mentioned (Figure 4.33) in which the energy density could be increased from 230 Wh/kg in ~2010 to 243 Wh/kg within the last years.

Cell Type NCR18650B		
Specifications		
Rated Capacity (at 20°C)		Min.3200mAh
Nominal Capacity (at 25°C)		Min.3250mAh
		Typ.3350mAh
Nominal Voltage		3.6V
Charging Method		Constant Current -Constant Voltage
Charging Voltage		4.2V
Charging Current		Std.1625mA
Charging Time		4.0hrs.
Ambient Temperature	Charge	+10~+45°C
	Discharge	-20~+60°C
	Storage	-20~+50°C
Weight (Max.)		47.5g
Dimensions (Typ.) of Bare Cell	H	64.93mm
	D	18.2mm
	d	7.9mm
Dimensions (Max.) Maximum size without tube		(D) 18.25mm
		(H) 65.10mm
Volumetric Energy Density		676Wh/l
Gravimetric Energy Density		243Wh/kg

Figure 4.33 – Specification of the Panasonic NRC1865 battery

Nevertheless, even if the current (Li-Ion)- battery chemistry has proven itself, efforts are still to be made to increase the energy density as well as other key performance parameters to meet future requirements. In R&D advanced and post-lithium concepts are also considered, which are still far away from being commercialized.

Predictions up-to-2025 - Battery

In our opinion, especially the development of batteries for ground-operation-vehicles (e.g. towing tractors) is closely linked to the development of batteries for automotive electro mobility. Of course, there are some differences in the technical requirements. For example, a long driving range is for an airport vehicle less important than high power (e.g. towing tractor). On the other side for small unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) a high energy density of the battery is very important for traveling long distances. Therefore, one can't give a solution that meets all requirements. Rather, it requires a tailor-made solution for the different purposes. However, in the following some information on the necessary developments regarding (state of the art) lithium-ion batteries.

There are several deficiencies of actual day lithium ion batteries that, if remedied with suitable ease and cost parameters, would enable superior lithium ion batteries that could open new applications and expand the market for present ones.

First it is important to consider certain market factors that will have important ramifications on cost, material availability, and needed technology improvements to enable mass production of different cell types and sizes. Market pull is strongly acting on lithium ion battery manufacturers as application companies and governments around the world are asking for increased capacity and energy with lower cost to fulfil the needs of greenhouse gas reductions through implementation of electric vehicles of all types to replace petroleum and energy storage. So that intermittent renewable energy sources such as wind and solar can replace coal and natural gas fuels for energy production. The cost element is particularly important, for example, for motive power applications, e.g. for plug-in hybrid vehicles (PHEV) and battery electric vehicles (BEV). Recent estimates place the cost of producing lithium ion cells is as low as \$145 per kWh and the cost of a battery pack as low as \$190 per kWh. [[http://www.greencarreports.com/news/1103667_electric-car-battery-costs-tesla-190-per-kwh-for-pack-gm-145-for-cells.](http://www.greencarreports.com/news/1103667_electric-car-battery-costs-tesla-190-per-kwh-for-pack-gm-145-for-cells)]

A second area of major production possibility is that of energy storage in connection with stabilization and storage for the electric grid. This area is driven as much by the requirements of government regulations and incentives to enable renewable energy sources such as solar and wind generation, which are inherently intermittent, to fit the demands of electrical utility producers and users.

In addition, cost is a very important driver for use of lithium ion, but some applications such as frequency stabilization are not as cost sensitive. If lithium ion batteries are adopted for these applications, great demands will be placed on the availability of materials, especially lithium carbonate. To consider the likelihood of specific energy improvements in lithium ion batteries we need to consider the limitations that exist now [Source: G. E. Blomgren, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 2017, 164, 1, A5019].

The Table 4.11 gives a picture of the main deficiencies and possible remedies as the author perceives them.

Location of Deficiency	Deficiency	Possible remedy
Carbonaceous anode (negative electrode)	Low capacity (Ah/kg, Ah/L)	Replace carbon with improved alloy anode that allows high coulombic efficiency, good power capability, low irreversible capacity, and low cost with little or no loss of specific capacity or cell voltage
Negative electrode-electrolyte interface	Low coulombic efficiency with ally anodes caused by solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) growth on first cycle and continuing with cycling	Improved coatings, functional binders and/or electrolyte additives to protect the interface during large volume changes
Positive electrode (lithiated transition metal oxide or phosphate)	Low capacity (Ah/kg, Ah/L) and charging voltage limit	Replace with new cathode material that allows high coulombic efficiency, good power capability, low irreversible capacity, and lower

Location of Deficiency	Deficiency	Possible remedy
		cost with little or no loss of capacity density or cell voltage
Positive electrode-electrolyte interface	Low coulombic efficiency at higher voltage limiting specific capacity and cycle life and causing increased cell impedance with cycling	Improve coating of cathode material, binders and/or electrolyte additives that can prevent impedance increase with cycling, dissolution of transition metal ions
Separator	Penetration with conductive particles or lithium dendrites	Improved coatings of separators that do not impede ion flux, salt diffusion or fluid flow, but can improve penetration strength or combine chemically with lithium dendrites
Metal collectors	Solid metal foils add to cost and take away from energy as they are inert in the system, yet must be thick enough to provide adequate electrical and thermal conductance	Perforated or expanded metal collector are in common use for primary lithium batteries and secondary aqueous batteries, but have not been engineered for lithium ion

Table 4.11 - Deficiencies of present lithium ion batteries and possible remedies [Source: G. E. Blomgren, J. Electrochem. Soc., 2017, 164, 1, A5019]

Evolutionary Progress up-to-2050- Battery

The history of lithium batteries is not that old, in contrast to fuel cells that have been described by Grove the first time in 1839. In the last 40 years, two new battery systems, Li-Ion and Ni/MeH, have not only dominated the portable electronics business, but in many ways enabled it. They are now beginning to do the same for transportation, and Li-Ion has entered the electric grid market.

These advances have all been based on the concept of intercalation reactions. Now the question arise how much further can intercalation chemistry be pushed? At a minimum, these cells will almost certainly displace Ni/Cd in consumer applications, as cadmium-based cells are banned from sale. There is still much room for improvement in the storage capability of Li-Ion cells.

- There is much dead weight and volume in today's batteries and supercapacitors; in addition, the full capability of the active materials has not been attained. For example, the volumetric energy density of Li-ion batteries has increased from 250 to 680 Wh/L over the last decade.
- There is no reason to believe that the energy density can't be further increased, possibly even as far as 50% on both volumetric and gravimetric basis within the next ten years. For almost all applications, the volumetric energy density is much more important than the gravimetric one.

However, further improvements will need significant changes in the materials used. One measure is to switch from lithium to magnesium. However, much effort will be needed to make a successful magnesium battery, including an anode, an electrolyte but most importantly a

high-energy cathode. The beginnings of such cells will be accomplished within ten years, but without significant breakthroughs it will probably not go commercial until 2030. Within ten years, the carbon electrode will have been replaced by metal alloy systems, perhaps tin or silicon based. There is a finite probability that pure metals will be used in some liquid electrolyte cells by 2030. They find application today in all solid-state thin film cells.

Related to conversion reactions is the chemistry involved in metal air and metal sulphur systems. The ambient temperature Li/S battery has been under development for more than a decade by e.g. *Sion Power* and *Oxis Energy*. Some cells are commercial and are used in some military markets for flight power today [*SionPower, Lithium Sulfur Batteries, 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://www.sionpower.com/>]. They already substantially exceed the gravimetric energy storage capability of Li ion but have a much lower volumetric storage capability.*

It is important to keep in mind that energy storage devices, like batteries, capacitors have an upper limit to their storage capabilities, and this can be readily calculated. Today, depending on cell chemistry, less than 20% of the theoretical volumetric capacity got out of a battery so there is room for improvement in the engineering of the system as well as in the use of new materials and reactions.

If the demand to get more energy out of a system at the same power rating, then flow batteries or fuel cells are recommended alternatively in which the tanks of the reactants are increased while keeping the electrochemical cell itself at the same size. The use of photovoltaics or wind power will require much more energy storage capabilities, probably at the local level as well as centrally.

Low-cost sealed metal–oxygen or metal–sulphur will probably have advanced to gain a significant market share. Intercalation-based batteries will retain a significant fraction of the market but will have switched to non-lithium-based electrochemistry, as there are predictions that it is almost certainly not enough lithium in the world to provide for transportation, grid storage, and home/office storage. Lithium could be replaced by magnesium, or if suitable electrodes can be found, sodium; zinc is not out of the question, but its storage capability is much lower because of the low cell voltage, ~1.5 V, compared to the 4 V for lithium-based cell systems.

For safety, it is likely that the sodium will be contained in some other host material, because the low melting point of sodium, around 100 °C, makes the possibility of thermal runaway too hazardous. Supercapacitors possibly will have morphed into batteries (hybrid-battery-capacitor), with the consumer having the opportunity to buy the desired battery that can supply electric energy from 90% power intensive to 90% energy intensive.

The final word on the degree of penetration of energy storage in the transportation and grid sectors will be determined by legal provisions, but technology can win out if all else is equal.

Possible or Predictable Breakthroughs – Battery

- a. Improvement of Energy density:
 - Development of Li/Sulphur Cell (→2025);
 - Replacement of Graphite with silicon (→2020);
 - Replacement of Graphite with lithium (→2020);

- Development of metal/air cells (→2030);
 - Development of high voltage/capacity cathode (→2025).
- b. Improvement of Power density:
 - The increase of operating temperature (→ 2025);
 - Development of Nano-carbon additives (→2025);
 - c. Improvement of Safety:
 - Employ hardly inflammable electrolytes based on ionic liquids, polymers or glass (→2025).
 - d. Decrease material costs:
 - Reduce use or entirely replace cobalt with low cost material (→2025).

Identification of Gaps / Risks – Battery

- a. The required power and energy density of the battery-system is too low;
- b. The required temperature operating range for demanding climatic conditions is too narrow;
- c. A sufficient charging infrastructure can't be build up for fast charging;
- d. The investment cost and operating costs are too high comparing state of the art.

4.3 Design and Manufacture Bearing in Mind Recycling

***Flightpath 2050 goal 11: "Air vehicles are designed and manufactured to be recyclable"**

Recycling of aircraft parts depends mostly on the materials used and also on the fabrication process. The choice of materials for an aircraft is subject to a considerable set of constraints related to performance, weight, availability, cost, ease of manufacture and maintenance, durability and resistance to hostile environments. Adding the recycling ability is an additional constraint which can bring benefits in several of other areas; it may require consideration of materials not previously used in the aerospace industry and take advantage in the major progress made synthesizing new substances with tailor-made properties (graphene).

An illuminating example of the experience and challenges of recycling is given by batteries (Key Topic T4.3).

KEY TOPIC T4.4 – BATTERIES FOR MORE ELECTRIC AIRCRAFT (MEA)

1) Requirements for Aircraft Grade Batteries

Competition in the aircraft industry market and global warming has driven the industry to think along economic and environmental lines. This has resulted in the emergence of a more electric aircraft (MEA) concept, providing for the utilization of electric power for all non-propulsive systems.

Traditionally these non-propulsive systems are driven by a combination of different secondary power sources such as hydraulic, pneumatic, mechanical and electrical. Recent technological advances in the field of power electronics, fault-tolerant architecture, electro-hydrostatic actuators, flight control systems, high density electric motors, power generation and conversion systems have ushered the era of the MEA. This trend is accelerating, as aircraft manufacturers collaborate with their suppliers to design new systems and implement new

electrical-intensive architectures. Adoption of the *MEA* concept is seen as critical enabler for the aircraft industry to unlock significant improvements in terms of aircraft weight, fuel consumption, aircraft noise, total life cycle costs, maintainability and aircraft reliability.

The tremendous increase in the power demand of aircraft, especially in the last two decades, coupled with advancement in battery materials and technology has led to the development of many aircraft grade battery systems with high energy density (more than 100 Wh/kg) and low-temperature capability with following key trades:

- To deliver power reliable and be certifiable safe;
- To be lightweight;
- To have a consistent power output over their operating environment;
- To have a reasonable long life.

A small size, high energy density battery (Table 4.12) is the need of the aircraft industry as a 10kg decrease in the weight of aircraft will result in the saving of 17,000 tons of fuel and 54,000 tons of carbon dioxide emission per year for all air traffic worldwide. The reduction in battery weight is also profitable in terms of cost.⁹

2) Types of aircraft batteries:

Serial no.	Criteria	Li-ion	Ni-Cd	Pb-acid
1	nominal cell voltage, V	3,20	1,20	2,00
2	typical battery cost in US\$, (V, Ah, Wh)	207 (12, 21,252)	100 (12,20,240)	67 (12,20,240)
3	cost per Wh in US\$	0.82	0.42	0.28
4	cycle life (no.)	3000	1500	250
5	cost per cycle in US\$	0.069	0.067	0.268
6	cost per Wh per cycle in US\$	0.00027	0.00028	0.00112
7	specific energy density, Wh / kg	135	65	40
8	operating temperature, °C	-20-60	-30-60	-20-60
9	self-discharge / month	2–3%	4–6%	15–20%
10	overcharge tolerance	very low	moderate	high
11	maintenance	not required	1–2 months	3–6 months

Table 4.12 - Comparison of different cell chemistries used in aeronautics⁹

Only vented Pb-acid batteries were in use in aircraft until the 1950s. In the late 1950s, military aircraft started using vented Ni-Cd due to higher low temperature capability, which was adopted by commercial aircraft. The use of alternative battery chemistries like Ag-Zn was discontinued because of high costs and poor reliability. From late 1960s, the development of sealed Ni-Cd batteries, followed by sealed Pb-acid batteries in the late 1970s started for aircraft application, in which maintainability and reliability have been improved significantly. Ultra-low maintenance Ni-Cd batteries were developed by *SAFT* and *Marathon Norco* since the mid-80s, replacing the conventional vented Ni-Cd batteries.

⁹ M.Tariq, A.I.Maswood, C. J. Gajanayake, A.K.Gupta, IET Electr. Syst. Transp., 2017, Vol. 7 Iss.2, pp 93-103

The most common voltage rating for main aircraft batteries is 24V, as capacities are available between 23 and 75Ah. The number of batteries installed in the aircraft depends on the system architecture, e.g. the Airbus A380 has a complex architecture requiring three 24 V, 50 Ah Ni–Cd batteries. A fourth 50 Ah battery is dedicated to APU starting. The total weight of the batteries is about 210 kg. The life duration of an aircraft battery depends on various factors such as number of operating hours, ambient temperature, start frequency and on-board charge. It is therefore difficult to determine in advance how long the expected life of a battery will be in the real situation. Typically, the life of Ni–Cd batteries on long-range transport jets is 6–9 years, while in commuter aircraft is 5–7 years. On the other hand, in military trainers and fighters it is typically 4–6 years. By comparison, the life of Pb-acid batteries is half to one-third that of Ni–Cd.

Though most of the civil aircraft have used Ni-Cd batteries, the trend is shifting (Table 4.13) towards Li-ion batteries with its tremendous opportunities to be employed in *MEA*.

Li-ion cells comprise a sensitive electrochemistry which needs a detailed knowledge of its characteristics to allow its benefits to be exploited fully while ensuring maximum safety. We are likely to see further improvements in Li-ion performance as new electrode materials; electrolyte compositions and cell geometries are under research. Nano-materials now being developed will also have a role to play. Nevertheless, Li-ion batteries are not currently envisaged as retrofit solutions, so Ni-Cd and Pb-acid batteries still have many years of work ahead of them.

Furthermore, many manufacturers include the Li-ion battery system with proper integrated battery management (BMS) and safety monitoring system, which are commercially available, e.g. the Li-ion battery with LiFePO₄-cell chemistry by *EaglePicher Technologies*.

Most new batteries face the same adoption curve, starting with initial resistance and then acceptance.

Aviation Battery Manufacturer	Cell type	Function in the aircraft	Civil Aircraft	Ah
<i>GS Yuasa (Japan)</i>	Pb-acid	Main Aircraft		36
<i>GS Yuasa</i>	Li-ion		B-787	75
<i>SAFT (France)</i>	Ni-Cd	Main Aircraft, Auxiliary Power Unit (APU), a.s.o.	B-737, B-747, B-767, A320, A330, A340, A380, Bombardier, Gulfstream G650, ComacC919	23-53
<i>SAFT</i>	Li-ion		Airbus, Boeing	
<i>SAFT</i>	Ni-MeH	Emergency door, floor escape path lighting, electronic flight bags.		
<i>Changhong Battery (China)</i>	Li-ion	Starting aircraft engine, DC emergency power supply.	Airbus, Boeing	60

	Ni-Cd		Airbus, Boeing	
	Ag-Zn	Emergency starting power supply or on-board back up power supply	Airbus, Boeing, Tu-154	45
<i>Concorde Battery (US)</i>	Pb-acid		C-130, C-141	10-30
<i>Concorde Battery</i>	Ni-Cd		B-717	3,5
<i>Hawker Energy Products Ltd (US)</i>	Pb-acid			
<i>Teledyne Battery Product (US)</i>	Pb-acid			
<i>Marathon Norco Aerospace (US)</i>	Ni-Cd			75
<i>EaglePicher (US)</i>	Li-ion	Emergency Batteries (2006), Main Engine Start Battery for Light Jet(2010)	Honda Jet	30-65
<i>EaglePicher</i>	Ag-Zn			0.8-800
<i>True Blue Power (US)</i>	Li-ion	Starting aircraft engine	Robinson R44, Bell Jet Ranger helicopter	17-46
<i>Acme Aerospace (US)</i>	Ni-Cd	APU, Avionics, Environmental systems	B-777	47

Table 4.13 - Details of batteries used in different aircraft

3) Life Cycle Management – Recycling

In general, the same processes used to recycle automotive batteries are used to recycle aircraft batteries.¹⁰

A serious issue is related to the fact that the lithium battery market is in continuous evolution with the advent of many different new chemistries. Further, in addition to the rechargeable Li-ion batteries, also primary lithium batteries, using cathodes such as manganese oxide or thionyl and sulfur chloride, are still in the market and they may arrive to the recycling plant as well. Finally, also the electrolyte may widely change, passing from a variety of liquid organic solutions to polymer membranes. Clearly, this high diversity makes it difficult to develop universally valid recycling process, as well as affecting its economics, since the new chemistries may not involve components worth being recovered.¹¹

Indeed, the European Commission has mandated a Battery and Accumulator Directive, which imposes to the state members the following targets:¹²

¹⁰ D. Vutetakis, The *Avionics Handbook*, 2001, Ch. 10, pp. 9

¹¹ B. Scrosati et. al, *Advances in Battery Technologies for Electric Vehicles*, Elsevier 2015: Recycling of Batteries possibly used in ground-vehicles or aircraft.

¹² http://epp.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/portal/page/portal/waste/key_waste_streams/batteries

- A 45% collection rate for waste-portable batteries to be met by 2016. A recycling efficiency to ensure that a high proportion of the weight of waste batteries is recycled, this including 65% of lead-acid, 75% of nickel–cadmium, and 50% of “other waste batteries,” the latter likely referring to lithium batteries.

Considering the present low economic value, these targets can be met only if subsidies are provided, usually adding a tax to each manufactured battery, as indeed is the case. Under this scheme, battery recycling plants are now operating in Europe (e.g., *Batrec* in Switzerland, *Umicore* in Belgium, and *SNAM* and *Recupyl* in France) to honour the mandate.

Recycling plants are also in force under different schemes in the US (e.g., *Toxco*) and in Japan (e.g., *Sony* and *Sumitomo Metal*). Due to the still scarce production of Li-ion batteries of EV types, the recycling is for the moment limited to the portable ones.

However, EV battery recycling is expected to gain quite a significant importance in the years to come.

4) Risks Related to (Li-ion) Batteries in Aircraft

Due to the use of certain chemical compounds in combination with high energy densities and the use of control electronics (potential of technical defect) required for secondary batteries, Li-ion batteries are associated with specific potential hazards which need to be taken into special consideration with regard to safety. Spectacular incidents have raised public awareness of potential problems associated with Li-ion batteries.

- On 3 September 2010, UPS Airlines flight 6, a Boeing 747-400, crashed close to Dubai International Airport on its way to Cologne Bonn Airport, leaving two crew members dead. The crash had been caused by fire in the cargo area which contained lithium ion and lithium metal batteries.
- After a Boeing 787 coming from Japan had landed in Boston/US on 7 January 2013, fire broke out, caused by the thermal runaway of a Li-ion battery. Consequently, the US-Federal Aviation Agency FAA has mandated to install a casing for the battery to contain/extinguish the fire (Figure 4.35):

Figure 4.34 - Boeing-787 relaunched the Li-ion battery system with the new design, adding an extra weight of 68kg to the weight of the airplane.

- On 12 July 2013, a non-rechargeable lithium metal battery in an ELT (emergency locator transmitter) of a Boeing 787 at London Heathrow Airport caught fire.

It is characteristic of a battery that it releases chemically stored energy in the form of electric energy in the course of the discharging process. In case of a “thermal runaway”, the entire energy is not released as electrical energy in a controlled manner, but uncontrollably in the form of thermal energy. In case of such a failure, the thermal energy released by a lithium ion battery may be 7 to 11 times higher than the energy stored electrically. The produced heat accelerates the reaction, resulting in a critical overheating of the battery.

In addition, it is possible that cathode materials disintegrate at high temperatures. This reaction also produces heat (exothermic reaction) and releases bound oxygen; when fire breaks out, the thus released oxygen makes it difficult to control the fire. It is even impossible to extinguish such a fire using conventional fire extinguishing methods.

Causes of battery fires:

- Improper handling;
- Mechanical damage;
- Secondary thermal stress;
- External short circuit, Internal short circuit caused by a cell failure or crash;
- Overcharge, Over discharge and exhaustive discharge;
- Cooling system defect (large-scale batteries);
- Counterfeit lithium ion batteries and chargers.

5) Threats Regarding Aircraft Batteries

5.1) Permanently installed batteries¹³

Figure 4.35 – Use of batteries in a typical aircraft.

¹³ Airbus, 18th Flight safety conference Berlin, 19-22 March 2012

There are a number of potential threats that can be associated with aircraft batteries (Figure 4.35), their distribution networks and their charging and monitoring systems:

- Battery Leakage. Overfilling a wet cell battery can cause leakage. Likewise, damage to the battery case caused by mishandling, overcharging or freezing can result in leakage.
- Battery Internal Failure or Short Circuit. Manufacturing defects or inappropriate handling can result in internal failures.
- Battery Overcharging. Batteries can be overcharged due to faulty charging equipment or inappropriate maintenance practices.
- Excessive Battery Charging/ Discharging Rate. Some battery types are vulnerable to high rates of charge or discharge.
- Battery Bus Fault or Fire. A Battery Bus Bar is "hot" - it cannot be electrically isolated from the source battery without physically removing the battery.¹⁴

As a consequence, following preventive measures should be undertaken:

- Containment of thermal effect;
- High standard electronic protection against overheat (overcurrent, overvoltage, short circuits);
- Specific choice of battery structural material and design;
- Battery management system with cooling system;
- Mitigation of pressure release effect;
- Venting areas within the battery/module;
- Specific venting outside the battery/aircraft when relevant;
- High robustness to shocks (handling) and ageing;
- Adequate integration in the Aircraft.

5.2) Li-ion batteries in the cabin¹⁵

¹⁴ https://www.skybrary.aero/index.php/Aircraft_Batteries

¹⁵ Airbus, 18th Flight safety conference Berlin, 19-22 March 2012

Figure 4.36 – Batteries in the cabin of an airliner

By accident of intentionally triggered thermal runaway of Li-ion cells occur due to devices carried by passengers in an aircraft cabin (Figure 4.36).

5.3) Li-ion batteries in the cargo area¹⁶

Figure 4.37 – Cargo with batteries that can cause safety risks

Shipping lithium batteries has also caused havoc in the airline cargo industry. In the last years, the *U.S. Postal Service* banned the shipment of lithium batteries until the ruling was reversed

¹⁶ Airbus, 18th Flight safety conference berlin, 19-22 March 2012

in November. *Cathay Pacific* and *British Airways* recently discussed banning the shipment of any related Li-ion battery devices in their cargo holds.

There is so much concern in the industry over on-board fires related to lithium ion that the FAA released a Safety Alert for Operators dated Oct. 8, 2010. The title is "Risks in Transporting Lithium Batteries in Cargo by Aircraft."

Furthermore, cargo areas are not accessible for direct firefighting and *Halon 1301*, used as fire extinguishing agent in cargo holds or engines, is insufficient to stop the thermal runaway and prevent propagation to adjacent cells.

4.4 Sustainable Alternative Fuel Sources

***Flightpath 2050 goal 12: "Europe is established as a centre of excellence for sustainable alternative fuels, including those for aviation, based on a strong European energy policy."**

The supply of fuel alternative to querosene is subject to major efforts by large consumers like the U.S. Air Force. The consumer base is more diversified in the airline industry, but it is no less important due to the large number of flight hours. Although airlines have been willing to test new fuels a coordinated effort must be done far upstream to: (i) consider a variety of sources of fuel, that do not interfere with food production and whose environmental impact is neutral or positive (waste disposal); (ii) establish the technical feasibility to meet all applicable quality and safety standards and certification requirements; (iii) assess the economic and environmental feasibility of large-scale sustained production, distribution and use.

For example, hydrogen is a clean fuel that produces only water vapour by combustion; however, the quantities produced, and altitudes should be considered as for contrails. Hydrogen has a low volume power density and requires cryogenic conditions; water is an abundant source of hydrogen but its separation by hydrolysis is energy consuming. At the opposite extreme some algae have high yields per unit area of culture; the full processing chain up to flight grade fuel needs to be considered. In between other options exist, making multiple sources of aviation fuel all the more desirable.

The Key Topic (T4.4) is thus the availability and sustainability of alternative fuel sources.

KEY TOPIC T4.4 – PROPERTIES OF POTENTIAL ALTERNATIVE FUEL

The European Commission, Airbus, and high-level representatives of the Aviation and Biofuel producer's industries launched in 2011 the European Advanced Biofuels Flightpath. This action is scheduled to achieve 2 million tons of sustainable biofuels used in the EU civil aviation sector by the year 2020. The overview of objectives, tasks, and milestones of this Flight Path¹⁷ is shown in the Table 4.14:

¹⁷ (https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/20110622_biofuels_flight_path_launch.pdf).

Time horizons	Action	Aim/Result
Short-term (next 0-3 years)	Announcement of action at International Paris Air Show	To mobilise all stakeholders including Member States.
	High level workshop with financial institutions to address funding mechanisms.	To agree on a "Biofuel in Aviation Fund".
	> 1,000 tons of Fisher-Tropsch biofuel become available.	Verification of Fisher-Tropsch product quality. Significant volumes of synthetic biofuel become available for flight testing.
	Production of aviation class biofuels in the hydrotreated vegetable oil (HVO) plants from sustainable feedstock	Regular testing and eventually few regular flights with HVO biofuels from sustainable feedstock.
	Secure public and private financial and legislative mechanisms for industrial second generation biofuel plants.	To provide the financial means for investing in first of a kind plants and to permit use of aviation biofuel at economically acceptable conditions.
	Biofuel purchase agreement signed between aviation sector and biofuel producers.	To ensure a market for aviation biofuel production and facilitate investment in industrial 2 nd generation biofuel (2G) plants.
	Start construction of the first series of 2G plants.	Plants are operational by 2015-16.
Mid-term (4-7 years)	Identification of refineries & blenders which will take part in the first phase of the action.	Mobilise fuel suppliers and logistics along the supply chain.
	2000 tons of algal oils are becoming available.	First quantities of algal oils are used to produce aviation fuels.
	Supply of 1.0 M tons of hydrotreated sustainable oils and 0.2 tons of synthetic aviation biofuels in the aviation market.	1.2 M tons of biofuels are blended with kerosene.
Long-term (up to 2020)	Start construction of the second series of 2G plants including algal biofuels and pyrolytic oils from residues.	Operational by 2020.
	Supply of an additional 0.8 M tons of aviation biofuels based on synthetic biofuels, pyrolytic oils and algal biofuels.	2.0 M tons of biofuels are blended with kerosene.
	Further supply of biofuels for aviation, biofuels are used in most EU airports.	Commercialisation of aviation biofuels is achieved.

Table 4.14 - Objectives, tasks, and milestones of European Advanced Biofuels Flightpath

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Possible Alternative Aviation Fuels.

Biofuels

In the initial 2011 Biofuel Flightpath document only three candidates were considered, but by now several alternative biofuels are under scrutiny or already approved¹⁸.

➤ Synthetic Fischer-Tropsch (FT) Based Kerosene Produced Through Biomass Gasification

Fischer-Tropsch synthesis entails a process which produces a gaseous mixture of hydrogen and carbon monoxide called syn-gas, over the surface of a catalyst material¹⁹. This is then converted into liquids of various hydrocarbon chain length and product distributions. These hydrocarbons can then be further processed into higher quality liquid fuels such as gasoline and diesel.

➤ Hydrogenated Esters and Fatty Acids (HEFA) and Hydrogenated

HEFA derived synthetic paraffinic kerosene is based on triglycerides and fatty acids which can originate from plant oils, animal fats, algae and microbial oil. Hydrogen demand for hydro processing of different feedstock qualities varies, resulting in conversion cost advantages for certain raw materials like palm oil and animal fats. HEFA production is already proven on full commercial scale. Neste Oil operates two 190,000 t/a HEFA plants in Finland and one 800,000 t/a plant each in Singapore and Rotterdam. UOP and its customers have announced several HEFA projects worldwide. In Europe both ENI and Galp Energia have plans for HEFA plants at 330,000t/a each, but these facilities are designed for diesel replacement in road transport and as such cannot be used for aviation unless some process modifications are carried out on the existing facilities.

➤ Pyrolysis Oils (HPO) Produced from Lignocellulosic Biomass.

HPO is still at research phase. It entangles developing fast pyrolysis processes. A few of them (e.g. Ensyn/Envergent Technologies (a joint venture between UOP and Ensyn Corp from Canada) and BTG in the Netherlands) are implementing the pyrolysis process on a commercial scale to produce crude pyrolysis oil. Pyrolysis oil, unlike vegetable oils (VO), contains a few hundred different chemical species. For application in the transport sector the crude oil needs further upgrading to produce HPO. One or more hydrogenation steps are required to achieve the desired product quality. The scale of operation for producing the pyrolysis oil can be quite different from the upgrading activities. The latter one might be combined with current refinery operations. Envergent/UOP, for example, is conducting a demonstration project for Pyrolysis and the Upgrading technology to transport fuels at the Tesoro refinery in Hawaii. Contrary to FT and HEFA fuels HPO will still contain a certain number of aromatic compounds which are

¹⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/20130911_a_performing_biofuels_supply_chain.pdf

¹⁹ A. D. Surgenor, J. L. Klettlinger, C. H. Yen, and L.M. Nakley, "Alternative Fuel Research in Fischer-Tropsch Synthesis", <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/search.jsp?R=20130000439> 2017-11-17T11:23:50+00:00Z

currently needed in jet fuel to avoid engine sealing problems. Therefore, HPO may complement HEFA and FT.

➤ Alcohol to Jet (ATJ)

The alcohol to jet (ATJ) is characterised by the production of alcohols as an intermediate product derived from biomass as shown in the Figure 4.38:

Figure 4.38 - Possible pathways to obtain ATJ biofuel. Source "2 million tons per year: A performing biofuels supply chain for EU aviation - August 2013 Update http://ec.europa.eu/energy/technology/events/2011_05_18_biofuels_in_aviation_en.htm)

The overall process consists of alcohol synthesis from the raw materials followed by chemical synthesis into jet fuel. An advantage of the ATJ technology is that it can be fully integrated with a wide variety of different front-end technologies for the production of alcohol intermediates. ATJ is currently still at pilot plant scale. Major players are Swedish Biofuels AB in Europe and Gevo in the United States. The technology called Direct Sugar to HydroCarbons, DSHC, developed by Amyris and Total, produces pure iso-paraffinic molecules by fermentation of any type of sugar, followed by a mild hydrogenation. The first industrial molecule, a C15 hydrocarbon called farnesane, can be safely incorporated in fossil jet-fuel at 10% and ASTM certification is presently under way.

Advantages and Limitations

Advantages

The most important motivations for biofuel usage concern the mitigation of climate change, the reduction of fossil fuel dependence, the conservation of biodiversity and water, as well as the development of agriculture. For example, F-T jet fuel has been shown to reduce particulate emissions without effecting engine performance. F-T fuel is characterized by excellent thermal stability at elevated temperatures and very good properties at low temperatures.

Limitations

Potential negative impacts of biofuel usage can be associated to the massive production of a few vegetal species with detrimental effects on global biodiversity and the triggering of market reactions to increased production of feedstock.

Current Status and Future Prospects

The use of alternative biofuels has been explored under 7thFP European project "ITAKA"²⁰(2012-2016). The main milestone achieved concerns the use of bio jet blend mixed in the conventional airport fuel systems (tanks, pipelines, hydrants) during conventional operation of the airport. This logistics mode appears economically viable, technically feasible and fully compliant with airport operations and users. Since the end of 2015, all flights departing from Oslo airport (Gardermoen) have used a biojet fuel blend (below 3%), which corresponds to about 60,000 flights and about 6 million of passengers. The biojet fuel was the camelina oil 100% made in the EU. It was produced in Spain (accumulated in three seasons, more than 1000 t), and refined to biojet fuel in Finland. Camelina plantations have been cultivated in a wide range of climatic and soil conditions. As consequence, camelina yield has varied from 500 to 2,500 kg per hectare, depending on the cultivation and weather/soil conditions. Barley data has been used as an indicator of the land quality. So, a farmer harvesting 3,000 kg/ha of barley in a given year should expect a camelina harvest of 1,500 kg/ha (50%). It has been demonstrated that sustainable camelina oil can be produced in Europe, in large amounts, with low risk of ILUC (Indirect Land Use Change), generating additional social and economic benefits for the farmers. The GHG (greenhouse gases) savings in a scaled-up production can achieve 66% reduction. Besides, the savings can go over 70% if a fertilization strategy is put in place, using i.e. ammonium sulphate (NH₄) instead nitrate (NO₃) for fertilization.

The use of the biofuel has been tested in two series of flights. The first series of 18 long haul flights from Amsterdam to Aruba, on an Airbus A330-200 (carrying around 4,500 passengers informed about the project) was performed using biojet fuel blend in one engine to compare the performance of the two engines. No significant performance differences were noted, but that the water accumulated in the tanks during flights can be lowered using the synthetic fuel, reducing the maintenance frequency and costs. The second series of 80 short haul flights, from Oslo to Amsterdam, on an Embraer E190, carrying about 8,000 passengers, using the camelina biojet blend in both engines, confirmed the no detrimental effects on operation with similar or slightly better fuel consumption and, no variation in fuel gauging systems. The flight series were complemented with a series of lab-based emission measurements using a testbed Auxiliary Power Unit (APU). APU emissions tests were completed for the two ITAKA fuel batches and baselined against a standard fossil Jet fuel: performance parameters were as expected quite similar, fuel consumption decreased up to 1% (saving fuel and CO₂ emissions), and the emitted particulate matter (PM) decreased up to a 50% for a 50:50 fuel blend. PM emissions are a major air quality concern that are linked with a significant number of premature deaths across Europe. High paraffinic fuels such as HEFA biojet could significantly help to reduce the impact of this pollutant in the vicinity of airports. The information obtained has been supplied to the International Civil Aviation Organization for the development of future standards for aircraft engines.

²⁰ http://www.itaka-project.eu/nav/pages/progress_results_7.aspx

4.5 Atmospheric Research, Weather and the Environment

*** Flightpath 2050 goal 13: “Europe is at the forefront of atmospheric research and takes the lead in the formulation of a prioritized environmental protection plan and the establishment of global environmental standards”.**

Atmospheric hazards have been a safety concern throughout the history of aviation and are addressed in the goal 15 (section 4.2). A better modelling and understanding of atmospheric phenomena can reduce disturbances of air traffic management (goal 5 and section 2.5) and allow an increase of runway capacity at airports (goal 1 and section 2.1). As major users of the airspace aviation can contribute to the monitoring of the atmosphere and to the establishment and implementation of global environmental standards. The monitoring of the atmosphere is performed by a vast array of earth and satellite sensors, plus specialized weather aircraft like those used by NOAA (National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration in the US) to fly through tropical storms and collect in-situ atmospheric data. The data transmission capabilities of airliners in modern ATM systems could be used not only for traffic purposes but also to collect atmospheric data in support of environmental standards and policies. It is in the interest of airlines to preserve their flight environment and if appropriate some of the millions of flights around the world could be a source of in-situ measurement and monitoring.

More details on the contribution of aviation to the undertakings of atmospheric and weather effects are given in the Key Topic T4.5.

KEY TOPIC T4.6 – WEATHER EFFECTS ON AIRCRAFT OPERATIONS

Scope of the Goal

Atmospheric research: weather and environment		
Goal 13: Europe is at the forefront of atmospheric research and takes the lead in the formulation of a prioritized environmental protection plan and the establishment of global environmental standards		
Comparison with 2017 SRIA document	Why	Lacks
Coherent	Both the SRIA document and the report mark that the atmospheric hazards will always be a safety concern. Therefore, the monitoring of the atmosphere could be enhanced through specific instruments such as sensors carried on air vehicles as well as	The SRIA document highlights the climate change effects on aviation, which is not included in the report. According to the document, it will be required to adapt and build resilience to the possible effects of climate change as well as to analyse the new threats that will appear as a consequence of the climate change.

	information on global atmospheric conditions collected by earth observation and prediction systems.	It is considered necessary that Europe understands completely the climate change risks in order to be at the forefront of atmospheric research.
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Table 4.15 – ACARE Flightpath 2050 Goal 13

Benchmarks for Goal 13

There are two ways of assessing the atmosphere impact:

On the one hand, evaluating the impact of the atmosphere on the aviation which is analysed in the goal 15. In this goal, weather and other hazards from environment are precisely evaluated and risks properly mitigated.

On the other hand, it is necessary to evaluate the aviation impact on the atmosphere. This impact can be negative such as the CO₂ and NO_x emissions and the noise disturbances which are analysed in detail in the goal 9.

Finally, within the aviation impact on the atmosphere it is important to assess how the aviation can contribute to the atmosphere knowledge. This is the objective to be evaluated in the goal 13: "Europe is at the forefront of atmospheric research and takes the lead in the formulation of a prioritized environmental protection plan and the establishment of global environmental standards".

In quantitative terms, the objective to be achieved could be that the 100% of the data that the aircraft can obtain and process from the atmosphere could be shared between other aircraft and ground infrastructure that would allow to obtain a real-time atmospheric model capable of predicting weather hazards as well as to evaluate the possible geographic location of these threats.

In order to achieve this objective, it would be necessary a series of measures such as those proposed in the following points:

- Aircraft equipped with systems capable of processing great amount of data;
- Communications network;
- Real-time broadcast;
- Prediction models.

Aircraft Equipped with Systems Capable of Processing Great Amount of Data

Aircraft would need to have on board systems capable of processing significant amounts of information from the environment (not only atmospheric which is the main purpose of this goal but also other kind of information which can be useful for the rest of goals).

Some initiatives which are currently in development are new modern aircraft engines such as the Pratt & Whitney's Geared Turbo Fan (GTF) engine which is fitted with 5,000 sensors that generate up to 10 GB of data per second, which could result in 800 TB per day and per engine.

Taking into account the goal of 25 million flights, it would be necessary that aircraft generate on average 6000 million TB of data to comply the goals to be achieved. This is called Aviation 4.0 which is part of the upcoming Industry 4.0 revolution. The Industry 4.0 refers to the current trend of higher levels of automation, digitalization and data exchange in manufacturing technologies. It includes cyber-physical systems, the Internet of Things and cloud computing among others technological assets.

Within this Industry 4.0 the concept of aviation 4.0 is introduced, which establish the evolution of commercial aircraft. With this type of digital and smart airplane, the amount and diversity of operational data that can be collected on board of the aircraft and by ground operations will raise exponentially. These smart aircraft are able to sense their environment, self-diagnose their condition and adapt in such a way so as to make the design more useful and efficient thanks to their information technology, measurement science, sensors, actuators, signal processing, cybernetics, artificial intelligence, etc.

In addition, this type of aircraft offers significant improvements in aircraft total weight and manufacturing cost. It also helps to improve the aircraft's life cycle, reduce its maintenance and decrease generated noise. One example of these aircraft is the A350, the new and latest member of the Airbus family.

Communications Network

An aircraft should have an advanced communication system, capable of transmitting data through multiple datalinks, directly to the ground, to other aircraft and via satellite, digitally and at high speed, providing communication services for all aircraft needs, each with its own required quality of service. In this way, all the detailed information, such as the weather situation, obtained from the on-board equipment and from the sensors can be shared between the ground infrastructures and the aircraft in a quick and reliable manner. However, this system should be economic so that installing it on as many aircraft as possible will be profitable. In addition, this communication system should be safe, robust and resilient to the possible cyberattacks since the system will need larger bandwidth due to the great amount of data exchanging.

Real-Time Broadcast

The data obtained from the aircraft sensors is broadcasted to all the stakeholders, such as other aircraft and the ground infrastructure in real time. In this way, the whole system will be aware of the possible weather threats and their possible location. In addition, all this information could be used to develop prediction models that would allow to predict weather hazards in advance.

Prediction Models

Thanks to all the data obtained from the equipped systems and their broadcasted to other stakeholders, predictions models could be obtained in order to foresee the possible weather hazards.

One example could be to identify and locate the areas with presence of ice crystals thanks to the sensors equipped in the aircraft. The presence of High-altitude ice crystals causes engine damage and engine power loss. There are some initiatives that research how to identify the formation of these crystals through the sensor TAT (Total Air Temperature). This is because Total Air Temperature (TAT) anomaly has occurred in many cases near the time of the engine power loss events. When this sensor reports zero degrees it is an evidence of ice crystals presence in the atmosphere. This anomaly is due to ice crystals building up in the area where the thermocouple resides, where they are partly melted by the heater, causing the zero degrees reading. Therefore, TAT anomalies monitoring might alert of areas in which it is probably the presence of High-altitude ice crystals and this information could be shared between other aircraft and the ground infrastructure in real time. The Figure 4.39 illustrates the benchmarks discussed for goal 13

ATMOSPHERIC RESEARCH : WHEATHER AND ENVIRONMENT

Figure 4.39 - Benchmarks for goal 13

Reference State in 2010

Environmental Issues and Climate Risks

Aviation is one of the most climate/weather sensitive industries. It is affected by changes to visibility, storminess, temperature, icing events, flooding events, and the operational effects of these. Therefore, one of the most important activities is to assess the atmosphere and the environment state in order to predict the future climate issues and develop mitigation strategies. This will help to reduce possible disturbances in the airspace and may allow for an increase in airports capacity.

Environmental policy in the European Union developed substantial improvements to the state of the environment. However, there were still major environmental challenges which have significant consequences for Europe and they continue to be investigated nowadays. Taking this into account, the European environment policy priority areas are the following ones:

- Climate change
- Nature and biodiversity
- Natural resources and waste
- Health and quality of life

➤ Climate Change

Climate change has become one of the most environmental concerns since it has a wide range of consequences for biological and socio-economic systems. Aviation is a small but important contributor to climate change and, for that reason, in recent years considerable effort has been carried out to mitigate aviation's impact on the climate and to increase Europe's resilience. Some climate change effects are in the following Table 4.16:

Global mean temperature change	During the 2000-2010 decade there has been a continued increase in the average global temperature with an average of 0,26 C
Greenhouse gas emissions	There has been an increase in carbon dioxide and other trace gases such as methane, ozone and the HCFCs. Aerosols also play a part, by perturbing the Earth's radiative balance
energy efficiency	In the EU, significant improvements in energy efficiency occurred due to technological development in, for example, industrial processes, engines, electrical appliances, etc.
Renewable energy sources	Deployment of renewable energies sources has increased rapidly in recent years, and their share is projected to increase substantially

Table 4.16 – Some climate change effects

➤ Nature and Biodiversity

Europe has established an extensive network of protected areas and programmes to reverse the loss of endangered species and the degradation of ecosystems (Table 4.17):

Biodiversity (loss of species)	Climate change is expected to have significant influences on terrestrial biodiversity at all system levels, including species-level reductions in range size and abundance, especially amongst endemic species
Degradation of soil	Loss of soil organic carbon results in land degradation, and land degradation is one of the leading challenges for sustainable development and biodiversity conservation

Table 4.17 – Endangered species and ecosystem

➤ Natural Resources and Waste

Environmental regulation has increased resource efficiency through a relative decoupling of resource use, and waste generation (Table 4.18):

Waste generation	In Europe, resource use and waste generation continue to rise
Waste management	Waste management has been always a focus of EU environmental policies. Such policies, which increasingly require the reduction, reuse and recycling of waste, are contributing to closing the loop of material use

Table 4.18 – Waste generation and management

➤ Environmental and Health

Water and air pollution have declined but not enough to achieve good ecological quality in all water bodies or to ensure good air quality in all urban areas (Table 4.19):

Water quality	The quality of water supply in coastal and island regions is at risk from rising sea level and changes in precipitation. Rising sea level and the occurrence of drought can increase the salinity of both surface water and ground water through salt water intrusion.
Air quality	the quality of air over populated areas is of continuing concern as the degradation of air quality has a major impact on human health, agricultural productivity and natural ecosystems

Table 4.19 – Water and Air quality

All these environmental issues result in climate risks and impacts for aviation which are shown in the following Table 4.20:

Climate risks	Impact
Precipitation change 	disruption to operations (for example airfield flooding) reduction in airport throughput inadequate drainage system capacity inundation of underground infrastructure (e.g. electrical) inundation of ground transport access (passengers and staff)
Temperature change 	changes in aircraft performance changes in noise impact due to changes in aircraft performance heat damage to airport surface (runway, taxiway) increased heating and cooling requirements

<p>Sea-level rise</p>	<p>loss of airport capacity impacts on en-route capacity due to lack of ground capacity loss of airport infrastructure loss of ground transport access</p>
<p>Wind changes</p>	<p>convective weather: disruption to operations and route extensions jet stream: potential increase in en-route turbulence local wind patterns: potential disruption to operations and changes to distribution of noise impact</p>
<p>Extreme events</p>	<p>disruption to operations, route extensions disruption to ground transport access disruption to supply of utilities</p>

Table 4.20– Climate risks and their impact

Monitoring the Atmosphere

Taking into account the main environmental issues and their effects on aviation, it is essential to develop a series of methods that allow to assess the atmosphere state and to measure its composition with the objective of facing these issues and to develop mitigation strategies.

There are several methods to monitor the atmosphere with the objective to state its composition in order to face the global issues mentioned before:

- Routine ground-based measurements
- Systematic aircraft measurements;
- Satellite measurements

➤ Ground Based Instrumentation

Thanks to new technologies and a variety of sophisticated measurement techniques, it is possible to measure accurately the atmosphere composition. The globally distributed ground stations provide high quality observations for:

- detecting long-term trends in atmospheric concentrations;
- monitoring air quality on a regional to global scale;
- evaluating and developing regional to global scale models that include atmospheric chemicals (e.g. local and regional weather and air quality forecast models, long-range transport models and climate models);
- and calibration and validation of satellite observations.

There are several initiatives that monitor and observe the atmosphere such as the Global Atmosphere Watch programme of WMO, which coordinates global ground-based networks

measuring greenhouse gases, ozone, UV radiation, aerosols, atmospheric pressure, wind speed and direction, air temperature and relative humidity.

➤ Airborne Instrumentation

Thanks to the on-board systems, aviation offers a cost effective and efficient way of collecting information related to atmosphere conditions and state. Continuous, real time information captured and communicated by aircraft can be used to update weather observations in a reliably way and to increase weather prediction capabilities. There are several programs whose objective is to evaluate the atmosphere state by using data collected form aircraft system:

IAGOS (In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System): it is a European research infrastructure which aims at constructing a global observation system for atmospheric composition by deploying autonomous instruments aboard a fleet of passenger aircraft. It is one component of the European Research Infrastructure for gathering long-term, routine in-situ observational data on the state of the atmosphere. By deploying a set of autonomous instruments aboard passenger aircraft of internationally operating airlines, IAGOS collects crucial atmospheric data at a global scale. The first IAGOS aircraft went into service in 2011, namely aircraft equipped with fully automated instruments for the measurement of several parameters such as ozone, carbon monoxide, and humidity (ICH) and cloud particles (BCP).

MOZAIC (Measurement of Ozone and Water Vapour on Airbus In-service Aircraft): it is a European program that uses automatic instruments for probing atmospheric state parameters and chemical composition, such as water vapour, ozone and carbon monoxide. These instruments have been installed on several commercial aircraft in 1994 and have, since then, provided regular data for the upper troposphere/lower stratosphere with more than 2000 flights and 4000 tropospheric profiles per year.

The SpectraSensors Water Vapour Sensor System (WVSS-II) provides laser fast and accurate measurement of water vapour in the upper atmosphere, which is an essential parameter for accurate weather modelling. The water vapour detection helps to improve forecasting of weather and climate change. A fleet of aircraft equipped with the Water Vapour Sensor System (WVSS-II) can provide thousands of times the number of vertical profiles accurately, automatically, and at a fraction of the operational cost.

EUFAR: EUFAR was born out of the necessity to create a central network for the airborne research community in Europe with the principal aim of supporting scientists, by granting them access to research aircraft and instruments otherwise not accessible in their home countries. In this way, scientists all over Europe can have an equal chance to carry out various atmospheric and in situ measurements on board research aircraft.

As it can be seen, aircraft measurements are one of the most efficient tools for obtaining representative information of the troposphere and stratosphere at high resolution and with uniform quality.

In addition, this type of measures is really important since the global climate change represents one of the most serious environmental issue today. Reliable predictions of the future climate using climate models are central and fundamental requirements for determining future

mitigation strategies. The use of commercial aircraft allows the collection of highly relevant observations on a scale and in numbers impossible to achieve using research aircraft, and where other measurement methods (e.g., satellites) have technical limitations.

Land and sea based sensors and data collected by aircraft are complemented by satellites.

➤ Satellite Instrumentation

Compared to measurements made by ground-based sensors (land based and buoys) and by airborne instrumentation (aircraft and balloons), the advantage of space-borne sensors is their global three-dimensional coverage and regular repeat cycle.

Meteorological satellites have been successfully used for tropospheric measurements of clouds and other parameters required for weather prediction. Geostationary satellites can be used to measure wind velocity by tracking clouds and water vapour. Satellite sensors, communications and data assimilation techniques are evolving steadily so that better use is being made of the vast amount of satellite data. Improvements in numerical modelling in particular, have made it possible to develop increasingly sophisticated methods of deriving the temperature and humidity information directly from the satellite radiances.

Research satellites, such as ENVISAT and AURA, contribute strongly to monitor atmosphere composition.

ENVISAT: Envisat was launched as an Earth observation satellite. Its objective was to service the continuity of European Remote-Sensing Satellite missions, providing additional observational parameters to improve environmental studies. Currently, scientific disciplines use the data acquired from the different sensors on the satellite, to study such things as atmospheric chemistry, ozone depletion, biological oceanography, ocean temperature and colour, wind waves, hydrology (humidity, floods), agriculture and arboriculture, natural hazards, digital elevation modelling (using interferometry), monitoring of maritime traffic, atmospheric dispersion modelling (pollution), cartography and study of snow and ice. The contact with the satellite was lost in 2012.

AURA. Aura is a multi-national NASA scientific research satellite in orbit around the Earth, studying the Earth's ozone layer, air quality and climate. The scientific findings of these studies address key NASA research objectives related to stratospheric composition, air quality, and climate change.

Aura's instruments measure trace gases in the atmosphere by detecting their unique spectral signatures. MLS (Microwave Limb Sounder) observes the faint microwave emissions from rotating and vibrating molecules. HIRDLS (High Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder) and TES (Tropospheric Emission Spectrometer) observe the infrared thermal emissions also due to molecular vibrations and rotations. OMI (Ozone Monitoring Instrument) detects the molecular absorption of backscattered sunlight in the visible and ultraviolet wavelengths.

Progress Up-to-Now

A brief description of current European projects is shown below. The objective of these projects is to assess the atmosphere state through ground and satellite infrastructure:

Copernicus: previously known as the Global Monitoring for Environment and Security (GMES) programme, Copernicus is a European Union programme aimed at developing European information services based on satellite Earth Observation and in situ (non-space) data. The provision of Copernicus services is based on the processing of environmental data collected from Earth observation satellites and in situ sensors. Copernicus services are based on information from a dedicated constellation of satellites, known as “Sentinels”, as well as tens of third-party satellites known as “contributing space missions”, complemented by “in situ” (meaning local or on-site) measurement data. In situ data are an essential and integrated part of Copernicus used to provide robust integrated information and to calibrate and validate the data from satellites (e.g. ground based weather stations, ocean buoys and air quality monitoring networks).

EUMESAT: is the European operational satellite agency for monitoring weather, climate and the environment. EUMETSAT operates a fleet of satellites in geostationary and polar orbit, which provide a wide array of Earth observation data for weather, climate and environmental monitoring. The ground segment constitutes the ground-based infrastructure necessary to support the operation of the satellites, including the control of the spacecraft in orbit, and the acquisition, reception, processing and delivery of their data.

The Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW): it is a programme of WMO which provides reliable scientific data and information on the chemical composition of the atmosphere, its natural and anthropogenic change, and helps to improve the understanding of interactions between the atmosphere, the oceans and the biosphere. Monitoring has focused on greenhouse gases and aerosols for possible climate change, ozone and ultraviolet radiation for both climate and biological concerns, and certain reactive gases and the chemistry of precipitation for a multitude of roles in pollution chemistry.

Finally, it is important to note that, in this objective, it is very difficult to differentiate between the 2010 state of the art and the 2017 state of the art due to several reasons:

On the one hand, the European projects mentioned before, which have as objective monitoring the atmosphere, have been in development for several years. On the other hand, the main environmental issues described before (such as climate change), that concerns nowadays, and which arose years ago, are still under study. In addition, it is important to highlight that the timeframe of these aspects extends into a broader period. For these reasons, it is difficult to evaluate accurately the progress made from 2010 to 2017.

Existing Technologies, Breakthrough Technologies and Evolutionary Progress Up-to-2050

Atmospheric composition matters to several areas such as climate, weather forecasting, human health, terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, aeronautical operations, etc. Due to its importance, it is necessary to develop new and enhanced methods to evaluate its composition in order to better understand the future environmental issues and carry out mitigation plans. The principal missions and goals for long-term horizon are the following ones:

- Ensuring that the climate continues to be monitoring by applying new techniques that provides better predictions.

- Improving global, regional and local long-term climate forecasts
- Observing atmospheric additional parameters
- There are many environmental issues that should be considered in the future, which are explained in the section.

Environmental Issues and Climate Risks

As it happened nowadays, climate change will be considered as the main environmental issue of risk. Although in recent years the aviation sector has initiated several measures and actions with the objective of mitigating the climate change effects, it is clear that its effects will not be fully neutralized and, as a consequence, some degree of climate change will be inevitable. In addition, other environmental hazards will emerge and, therefore, new mitigations strategies will be necessary. Moreover, taking this into account the aviation sector will need to build climate resilience and to adapt to the emerging threats.

In the following Table 4.21 it is shown the main climate risks, their effects and their impact for European aviation. It covered a time horizon up until 2050, a period where initial impacts may begin to be experienced by the industry.

Environmental issues	Primary effects	Possible aviation impacts
Temperature change 	<input type="checkbox"/> Higher mean temperatures, especially in winter for Northern Europe and summer for South Europe. <input type="checkbox"/> Higher, colder tropopause	<input type="checkbox"/> Runway demand mismatch <input type="checkbox"/> Airspace demand mismatch <input type="checkbox"/> Cruise altitude changes <input type="checkbox"/> Airspace design changes <input type="checkbox"/> Aircraft performance changes
Snow and frozen ground 	<input type="checkbox"/> Fewer days of snow/frost	<input type="checkbox"/> Demand re-distribution <input type="checkbox"/> Changed de-icing and snow clearance requirements
Precipitation and water supply 	<input type="checkbox"/> Increased precipitation in Northern Europe <input type="checkbox"/> Increased freezing rain <input type="checkbox"/> Decreased precipitation in South Europe	<input type="checkbox"/> Airport and runway demand mismatch <input type="checkbox"/> Loss of Airport availability and hence perturbation and delay <input type="checkbox"/> Reduced ability to meet demand due water shortages
Sea level 	<input type="checkbox"/> Higher mean sea level <input type="checkbox"/> Increased impacts of storm surges and flooding	<input type="checkbox"/> Loss of Airport availability <input type="checkbox"/> Loss of ground access to airports <input type="checkbox"/> Delay and perturbation <input type="checkbox"/> New airports or infrastructure required
Convective weather 	<input type="checkbox"/> Increased intensity of precipitation events, lightning, hail and thunderstorms	<input type="checkbox"/> Disruption and delay <input type="checkbox"/> Potential safety issues if frequency and severity increases Potential loss of en-route capacity
Visibility 	<input type="checkbox"/> Decrease in winter days affected by fog	<input type="checkbox"/> Fewer capacity restrictions due to reduced visibility <input type="checkbox"/> Reduced business case for low-visibility related technologies

Table 4.21– Environmental issues and their implications for aviation

Changes to temperature, precipitation, and storm patterns are all expected in the near-term, certainly by 2030. The impacts of sea level rise are more gradual and not expected until later in the century. However, more frequent and intense storm surges will have an earlier impact, reducing capacity and increasing delay.

Environmental Issues Forecasts by Region

In the following images, it can be seen the potential environmental issues and their main impacts on aviation in Europe. It is expected that these possible effects vary greatly with region as shown in the Figures 4.40 and 4.41:

Figure 4.40– Environmental issues effects by region

0.....

Figure 4.41– Environmental issues impacts on aviation by region

Duration and Timing of Environmental Impacts

In this section, it is analysed the timeline of the main future environmental issues and how they will affect aviation industry. It is expected that the environmental issues will predominantly affect infrastructure and operations (Table 4.22). However, some impacts may not be a concern until the middle of the century while others may be experienced sooner.

Table 4.22– Effects of climate change on aviation

Atmosphere Composition

In order to face the environmental issues mentioned previously, it is essential to have a better knowledge of the atmosphere composition in order to achieve better forecasts and predictions that would allow to develop mitigation strategies. There are several initiatives and projects which are currently in development and they are expected to progress significantly in long term. Their main methods to monitor atmosphere are based on satellite and airborne instrumentation. Some examples of these projects are described in the following sections.

Satellite Instrumentation:

➤ Copernicus Project:

Copernicus is the European system for monitoring the Earth and it is coordinated and managed by the European Commission. It consists of a complex set of systems which collect data from multiple sources: earth observation satellites and in situ sensors such as ground stations and airborne sensors. It processes this data and provides users with reliable and up-to-date information through a set of services related to environmental and security issues. Copernicus: The Copernicus programme is supported by a dedicated constellation of satellites, known as "Sentinels", which are specifically designed to meet the needs of the Copernicus services and their users. The first of these sentinels was launched in 2014 and it is expected to launch more satellites in the next years. Copernicus also draws on a large number of in situ (meaning on-site or local) measurement systems put at the disposal of the programme by the EU Member States. These include sensors placed on the banks of rivers, carried through the air by weather balloons, pulled through the sea by ships, or floating in the ocean. In situ data are used to calibrate, verify and supplement the information provided by satellites, which is essential in order to deliver reliable and consistent data over time.

Copernicus improves the capabilities to monitor, forecast and make projections about the changing climate, by increasing the number and sources of raw data at disposal, producing services based on integration, modelling and analysis of these data, and by coordinating the production of certified climate information from multiple sources. With the new satellites that are expected to be launched in the next years, these measurements, predictions and projections of the climate will be more accurate and reliable. The sentinels programme launch is presented below in the Figure 4.42:

Figure 4.42– The Sentinel families of European environmental satellites

The Sentinel-1 mission is designed as a two polar-orbiting satellites constellation: Sentinel-1A, the first satellite that was launched on 3 April 2014 and Sentinel-1B which was launched on April 2016. Sentinel-1 is a radar imaging satellite which delivers images day and night under all weather conditions, for land and sea monitoring.

Sentinel-2 provides high-resolution optical imagery for land services. It provides for example, imagery of vegetation, soil and water cover, inland waterways and coastal areas. Sentinel-2 also delivers information for emergency services. The twin satellites Sentinel-2A and Sentinel-2B were respectively launched on June 2015 and on March 2017.

Sentinel-3 will provide high-accuracy optical, radar and altimetry data for marine and land services. It measures variables such as sea-surface topography, sea- and land-surface temperature, ocean colour and land colour with high-end accuracy and reliability. The first Sentinel-3 satellite (S-3A) was launched on February 2016 and is supporting ocean forecasting systems, as well as environmental, agriculture and climate monitoring. A second satellite (S-3B) is scheduled for launch in 2018.

Sentinel-4 will provide data for atmospheric composition monitoring. Its objective is to monitor key air quality trace gases and aerosols over Europe at high spatial resolution with a fast (hourly) revisit time. It will be a payload embarked on EUMETSAT's Meteosat Third Generation (MTG), which is scheduled to be launched around 2019.

Sentinel-5 will also be dedicated to atmospheric composition monitoring. It will be a payload embarked on a EUMETSAT's Metop Second Generation (Metop-SG) to be launched in 2021 timeframe. It will provide accurate measurements of key atmospheric constituents such as ozone, nitrogen dioxide, sulphur dioxide, carbon monoxide, methane, formaldehyde, and aerosol properties.

Sentinel-6 will provide high accuracy altimetry for measuring global sea-surface height, primarily for operational oceanography and for climate studies. It is a cooperative mission developed in partnership between Europe (EU, ESA and EUMETSAT) and the U.S. (NOAA and NASA). It is planned for launch in 2020, as shown in the Sentinel maturity plan (Figure 4.43).

As it can be seen, the launch of new satellites will provide better predictions and measurements of the atmosphere thanks to new advanced instruments and techniques.

Sentinels Projection

Figure 4.43– Maturity Plan for the Sentinel family.

➤ COSMIC Mission

New research indicates that the COSMIC microsatellite system (Figure 4.45), which uses a technology known as GPS radio occultation to observe remote regions of the atmosphere, can significantly improve predictions of climate.

The COSMIC mission (Constellation Observing System for Meteorology, Ionosphere, and Climate) is a collaborative project between Taiwan and the United States to demonstrate the use of the radio occultation (RO) technique for weather prediction, climate monitoring, and space weather forecasting. The two countries plan to launch an additional six COSMIC satellites in 2016 and another six in 2018, which will give forecasters and researchers far more data.

Forecasts traditionally draw on observations taken by instruments on Earth's surface or by radiosondes, which are lifted into the atmosphere by balloons. But both these approaches are limited in hard-to-access places, like the open ocean. In contrast, GPS radio occultation measurements can be made almost anywhere, and they are unaffected by clouds, light rain, or airborne aerosols. By using GPS signals to monitor the atmosphere in three dimensions, the FORMOSAT-3/COSMIC satellite constellation has led to improved global weather monitoring, especially in data-sparse regions. This microsatellite system has proved its value, providing many applications for weather forecasting.

Figure 4.44– Cosmic microsatellite system

Applications:

Weather

- Improve global weather analyses, particularly over data-void areas (such as oceans and polar regions);
- Improve skill of global and regional weather prediction models;
- Improve understanding of tropical, midlatitude, and polar weather systems and their interactions;

Ionosphere and space weather

- Observe global electron density distribution;
- Improve the analysis and prediction of space weather;
- Improve monitoring/prediction of scintillation and related phenomena (e.g., equatorial plasma bubbles, sporadic E clouds);

Climate

- Monitor climate change and variability with unprecedented accuracy and precision;
- Evaluate global climate models and analyses;
- Calibrate infrared and microwave sensors;

Data collected by COSMIC are especially useful for forecasting tropical cyclones, including typhoons and hurricanes. In addition, COSMIC is able to provide critical observations of water vapour, the fuel that drives tropical cyclones, in high vertical resolution, which means scientists can determine how much water is present at what height in the atmosphere.

➤ Advanced Satellite Aviation Weather Products (ASAP)

The Advanced Satellite Aviation Weather Products (ASAP) initiative has been developed to provide satellite derived meteorological products and expertise to the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) weather research community.

Research areas important to the aviation community that are addressed by the ASAP initiative include:

1. Convective Weather (Figure 4.45)

- Develop satellite-based information that will aid in the real-time nowcasting of convective initiation (CI) and the diagnosis of convection on meso- and synoptic scales.
- Develop a series of CI "interest fields" from existing satellite sensors that can help predict future convection on local scales (i.e., 1-4 km).
- Develop new methods for using hyperspectral data for accomplishing these goals.

Figure 4.45 – Convective initiation

2. Turbulence Detection (Figure 4.46)

- Develop satellite-based techniques to identify and characterize regions of moderate and severe clear-air (e.g., mountain waves), and cloud-induced turbulence (e.g., thunderstorms), as detectable in GOES, and especially MODIS infrared data.
- Develop value-added products of turbulence from satellite data sets that can be used in conjunction with numerical simulation and existing PDT turbulence prediction systems.

Figure 4.46 – Turbulence Detection

3. Oceanic Weather (Figure 4.47)

- Apply satellite-based information that will aid in the forecasting and analysis of hazardous weather over oceans. Overlaps with other PDT efforts.
- Use products that help identify regions of high flight-level winds, dust, turbulence, convection, and clouds that can assist in trans-oceanic travel.

Figure 4.47 – Oceanic Weather

4. Cloud Properties (Figure 4.48)

- Develop satellite-based information that will aid in the real-time diagnosis of cloud microphysical properties and cloud type.
- Emphasize use of MODIS imagery and other high-spectral resolution data.

Figure 4.48 – Cloud properties

5. Volcanic Ash (Figure 4.49)

- Develop satellite-based information that will aid in the real-time diagnosis of volcanic ash, ash clouds and ash characteristics.
- Emphasize use of MODIS imagery and other high-spectral resolution data.

Figure 4.49 – Volcanic Ash

6. Winds (Figure 4.50)

- Incorporate satellite-derived winds to identify possible turbulent regions associated with upper tropospheric jets.

Figure 4.50 – Winds

➤ EUMETSAT

EUMETSAT is the European operational satellite agency for monitoring weather, climate and the environment. It operates a system of meteorological satellites that observe the atmosphere and ocean and land surfaces – 24 hours a day, 365 days a year. This data is supplied to the National Meteorological Services of the organisation's Member and Cooperating States in Europe, as well as other users worldwide. Its main objectives include identifying and monitoring the development of potentially dangerous weather situations as well as issuing timely forecasts and warnings to emergency services and local authorities, helping to mitigate the effects of severe weather. EUMETSAT operates a fleet of satellites in geostationary and polar orbit, being the Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) the satellites which are currently operative, providing images of the whole Earth, and data for weather forecasts. Some applications of these satellites are monitoring convective storms, volcanic ash clouds and the distribution and behaviour of fog.

EUMETSAT is planning and developing (Figure 4.52) the future satellite systems required to deliver and further improve observational inputs to forecasting and climate monitoring in the 2020-2040 timeframe. This is carried out in cooperation with the European Space Agency (ESA). The projects which are being prepared for the long-term future are Meteosat Third Generation (MTG) and EUMETSAT Polar System Second Generation (EPS-SG).

- The Meteosat Third Generation (MTG) programme (Figure 4.53) was fully approved by EUMETSAT Member States in February 2011, thereby establishing the first pillar of EUMETSAT's future in the 2020-2040 timeframe. The MTG programme will revolutionise weather forecasting and environmental monitoring by providing significant improvement

over the capabilities of the current Meteosat generation. It should guarantee access to space-acquired meteorological data until at least the late 2030s. The Satellite Concept is based on:

- Four Imaging Satellites (MTG-I) (20 years of operational services expected)
- Two Sounding Satellites (MTG-S) (15.5 years of operational services expected)

Therefore, the satellite series will comprise four imaging and two sounding satellites. The imaging satellites, MTG-I, will fly the Flexible Combined Imager (FCI) and the Lightning Imager (LI), an imaging lightning detection instrument. The sounding satellites, MTG-S, will include an interferometer, the Infra-red Sounder (IRS), with hyper-spectral resolution in the thermal spectral domain, and the Sentinel-4 instrument, the high resolution Ultraviolet Visible Near-infrared (UVN) spectrometer. Such improvements will allow better are spatial resolution and as consequence, better predictions and forecasts.

Figure 4.51 – Successive generation of EUMETSAT

- The EUMETSAT Polar System Second Generation (EPS-SG) is the second pillar (Figure 4.54) of EUMETSAT's future, expected to continue the global observations of EPS in the 2020-2040 timeframe. The main priorities of the programme will be to support operational weather forecasting and to provide operational services in support of climate monitoring and new environmental services. EPS-SG represents Europe's contribution to the future Joint Polar System (JPS), which is planned to be established together with the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) of the United States, following on from the Initial Joint Polar System (IJPS). Polar orbiting satellites, due to their global coverage and of the variety of passive and active sensors that can be deployed from Low Earth

Orbits, have the most significant positive impact on Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP). The EPS-SG system will provide global, regional and local data service. The EPS-SG Programme is expected to be one of the most important sources of satellite observations for all forecasts based on NWP in the 2021–2040 timeframe. In the next image it can be seen the overview of EUMETSAT programs, with all the satellites programme launches:

Meteosat Third Generation Projection:

Figure 4.52 – Meteosat Third Generation Satellite Maturity Plan

Figure 4.53 - Polar System Second Generation (EPS-SG) Projection

In the next image (Figure 4.54), it can be seen the data that will be provided by monitoring satellites mentioned before:

Figure 4.54 – Image obtained by several environmental satellite systems

Airborne Instrumentation

The main current project which provides atmospheric data through airborne instrumentation is the IAGOS project. In-service Aircraft for a Global Observing System (IAGOS) is a European Research Infrastructure for global observations of atmospheric composition from commercial aircraft. IAGOS combines the expertise of scientific institutions with the infrastructure of civil aviation in order to provide essential data on climate change and air quality at a global scale. In order to provide optimal information, two complementary systems have been implemented:

- IAGOS-CORE providing global coverage on a day-to-day basis of key observables. IAGOS-CORE cooperates with several airlines for quasi-continuous measurements of trace gases, aerosol and cloud particles from a fleet of long-haul passenger aircraft. Each aircraft is equipped with the IAGOS-CORE rack which contains all necessary provisions for installing fully automated instruments for the measurement of ozone, carbon monoxide, humidity and cloud particles.
- IAGOS-CARIBIC providing a more in-depth and complex set of observations with lesser geographical and temporal coverage. IAGOS CARIBIC is an innovative scientific project to study and monitor important chemical and physical processes in the Earth's atmosphere. Detailed and extensive measurements are made during long distance flights. CARIBIC deploys a modified airfreight container with automated scientific apparatus which are connected to an air and particle (aerosol) inlet underneath the aircraft.

In the following image (Figure 4.55), it can be seen examples of installation of IAGOS-CORE instrumentation aboard aircraft:

Figure 4.55 – Instrumentation installed in aircraft for environmental purpose

At the present time, eight aircraft are flying for IAGOS (one with IAGOS-CARIBIC and seven with IAGOS-CORE). Therefore, the technology for monitoring atmosphere through on-board system already exists and the objective is to expand this technology. That is to say, the purpose for the future will be to increase the fleet of aircraft with this technology on-board. The long-term plan is to increase the number of aircraft to 20 in order to further enhance the geographical coverage. New instruments will be developed in response to future scientific and societal challenges.

Timeline Projection:

As the technology has already been deployment, the corresponding TRL is the number 9. Therefore, the projection which is represented below is the expansion of this technology. Taking into account that the current IAGOS fleet is 8 aircraft the projection could be as shown in the Figure 4.56:

Figure 4.56 – Expected growth in the size of the fleet of aircraft equipped with IAGOS instrumentation

The IAGOS project is only one of several projects which use aircraft on board systems to measure the atmosphere composition. In the future, the objective will be to **equipped aircraft** in a massive way with this type of instruments. In this way, the atmospheric composition measurement will be more accuracy and reliable. In addition, one initiative of recent years is to use **drones** to measure atmospheric composition since a drone will be able to fly to any point in the vertical atmosphere and take air sample readings and transmitting them to a ground computer for monitoring. They could also be used on routes which aircraft normally do not use and provide atmosphere data closer to the ground. These two measures will suppose the main breakthrough in the future.

Breakthrough Measures to Monitor Atmosphere

In the future, there are three possible ways of development that could suppose breakthrough:

- Equipped aircraft in a massive way with instruments capable of measuring atmospheric parameters
- Using drones to monitor atmosphere
- Alternative ways to measure atmospheric parameters (the weather company)

In the following sections are described the previous measures that could suppose breakthroughs in the way in which the atmosphere is monitored.

➤ On Board Instrumentation

The IAGOS project described previously is only one of several projects which use aircraft on-board systems to measure the atmosphere composition. However, as it was mentioned previously, the IAGOS fleet which is equipped with instruments to measure atmosphere parameters consists only of 8 aircraft at the present time, which is a very small number. However, the measurements taken by these aircraft have a great value to evaluate the atmosphere composition and to predict weather events. Therefore, equipping aircraft in a massive way with this type of instruments could provide an important breakthrough in this study field since the atmospheric composition measurements will be more accurate and reliable.

In addition, the aircraft should have not only this type of equipment available but also a communication system capable of broadcasting in real-time the measures taken by this equipment to all the stakeholders. Therefore, it will be required on-board advanced communication systems capable of collecting all the relevant data from the atmosphere, processing and sharing it with all the actors. In this way, the weather predictions and forecasts will be more accurate and efficient. Taking this into account, it will be necessary to assure the integrity, reliability and availability of the on-board communication systems.

➤ Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS)

The availability of high-quality atmospheric measurements over extended spatial and temporal domains provide unquestionable value to meteorological studies. Traditional methods related to atmospheric measures include remote sensing instruments (radars, lidars, sodars and radiometers) or in-situ probes carried by balloons or manned aircraft. An alternative to these traditional approaches is the acquisition of atmospheric data through the use of highly capable unmanned aircraft systems (UAS) working in coordination with weather radar systems and other observing stations and platforms.

At the present time there is a key information gap between instruments on Earth's surface and on satellites. UAS could solve that gap revolutionizing the ability to monitor and understand the global environment, by operating at a lower altitude than aircraft and collecting data from dangerous or remote areas, such as the poles, oceans, wildlands, volcanic islands, and wildfires. Better data and observations would improve understanding and forecasts allowing better anticipation to dangerous weather events.

The use of unmanned aircraft systems (UAS) or unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) has become the most promising technology in atmospheric monitoring over the last few decades. UAS have the potential to become a major resource for scientific research and weather monitoring

as they can fly to any point in the vertical atmosphere and take air sample readings. They could also be used on routes which aircraft normally do not use and provide atmosphere data closer to the ground.

The capabilities of UAS have increased dramatically over the past decade, especially with improvements in autonomous flight performance. Moreover, the ability to send a UAS on a mission without the need for a pilot greatly expands the potential for extended measurements while simultaneously lowering the operational costs.

UAS could measure meteorological state parameters, such as wind, temperature, humidity, turbulence and other variables with great accuracy as well as rates of variation of these parameters. Over the last few decades government agencies and private sector companies have employed UAS for surveying and atmospheric research, including hurricane research and volcanic plume sampling. UAS use for meteorological and other environmental monitoring began in the 1990s and became routinely used in the 2000s. Through several missions, National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) and National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) have proved their capability to be operated routinely to obtain science-quality data over remote atmospheric regions.

One recent example is a small unmanned aircraft system which is being developed by Black Swift Technologies for research in extreme environments. This UAS called SuperSwift XT (Figure 4.57) has been designed to collect data in harsh environments and to carry out in situ observations from inaccessible regions. One of its uses will be to explore volcanoes in order to improve air traffic management systems and the accuracy of ash fall measurements. This drone will be compound by sensors specifically designed to measure selected gases and atmospheric parameters, including temperature, pressure, humidity and 3D winds, as well as more advanced measurements, such as particle sizing and trace gases.

Figure 4.57 – An UAV designed for environmental monitoring in hazardous conditions

The sensor and sensor coverage component will depend on the requirements of the systems and these requirements will depend on the application. A sensor will have to provide information about absolute, or process parameters at twice their natural temporal and spatial variability to ensure a representative natural data parameter field. Data processing architecture should be able to handle real-time, near terabyte per second data volumes, and data of multiple formats. It should also be able to accept and send secure communications. It will also require an on-board archive and ground station archive points to facilitate operational activities, ensure protection and minimize data loss.

In the following Table 4.23 it is shown a subset of the capabilities that an unmanned aircraft system could contain:

Function	Capability
Sensing	Atmospheric profiles surface to flight-level: air temperature, dewpoint temperature, 3D wind components, turbulent fluxes, static pressure, spectral irradiance, super cooled liquid water content. Atmospheric constituents and composition (aerosols, cloud, precipitation, trace gases, total water content) Surface characteristics (spectral reflectance, soil moisture, soil temperature profiles).
Data processing	Able to process terabytes of data per second; functional tools, decision support; calibration/validation
Software	Algorithms to yield required information, data logging, data processing

Table 4.23 – Capabilities expected of an UAV designed for environmental monitoring

However, the use of unmanned aircraft systems to monitor atmosphere will have to address several risks:

The drones will have to operate in an airspace with other aircraft. Therefore, it will be necessary to develop procedures and rules so that both can operate without collision risks. For example, by the assurance of safe separation distances between unmanned aircraft and manned aircraft when flying in the national airspace;

One of the unmanned aircraft main uses will be to operate in severe weather regions or in inaccessible areas. This will imply higher risks since they could suffer damage due to the severe conditions that will imply higher costs.

Due to the large amount of communications and data, unmanned aircraft could be exposed to security threats. Therefore, it will be required to assure data integrity and quality, data information dissemination and storage.

Despite the risks mentioned previously, using unmanned aircraft to monitor atmosphere will have a lot of benefits that will allow to develop better weather prediction models and forecasts. Although UAS are deployed operationally worldwide, they have not been integrated yet in weather monitoring operations at the present time. Using these systems on a global scale could support a great breakthrough in atmosphere monitoring. This is because as these

systems become more common, it would allow to improve significantly weather modelling and forecasting.

➤ Cognitive intelligence for weather prediction: The weather company.

Using data from commercial aircraft and mobile phones to measure atmospheric parameters closer to the ground have been one of the most revolutionary ways to monitor atmosphere in recent years. It has allowed to dispose of more data to develop better weather predictions. This initiative has been carried out by the Weather Company.

The Weather Company is a weather forecasting and information technology company, which provides the world's leading technology platforms and services leveraging weather and related data. It provides critical weather information to a variety of business industries: aviation, energy, insurance and utility, as well as visualization software for broadcast media and digital platforms.

In addition, the company delivers critical weather data from around the globe to airlines worldwide, producing 26 billion individual forecasts daily. Meteorological insights are drawn from satellites, weather stations, planes, radar, terminal and en route data.

Within the aviation sector, the Weather Company offers products that streamline aeronautical decision-making with accurate and highly reliable aviation and inflight weather data and decision support tools.

The objective of the weather company is mapping the entire atmosphere through data collected from:

- Sensors of aircraft 200 airlines/50,000 flights a day (pressure and wind speed).
- Drones and smartphones for measurements closer to the ground
- Satellites collect data from high above the globe

Therefore, the weather company develops weather forecasts through data provided by all type of sources such as mobile phones and aircraft. It is a new perspective which has not been considered previously and which has a lot of applications for the future.

For example, one of its major success is to predict turbulence, which is one of the main causes of loss of security and efficiency. The difficulty in predicting turbulence is a lack of high-quality data and workflow integration around turbulence information.

In response, The Weather Company launched WSI Total Turbulence, an initiative which provides a workflow integrated, end-to-end solution that improves certainty and reduces turbulence impacts and their associated costs. WSI Total Turbulence delivers timely, precise and actionable turbulence alerts and guidance (Figure 4.59) through:

- On-board software that automatically and objectively measures and immediately reports turbulence events using existing airplane instrumentation. The sensors report every 15 minutes in non-turbulence situations and increase reporting to once every minute during a turbulence event.

- Cylinder shaped turbulence alerts that report precise location and severity in a visual manner that is easy to act upon.
- Constantly updated forecast models & alerts based upon integrated update feeds, the accuracy of which has gone through extensive validation testing.
- Distribution of alert information to all impacted operations and flight staff for consistent information sharing.

By applying these techniques, it has been obtained beneficial results. For one airline using WSI Total Turbulence they experienced:

- A 50% reduction in Flight Attendant injuries;
- Year over year reduction in maintenance (40%);
- Captains accepting a higher number of planned flights;
- Decrease in turbulence encounters.

In conclusion, this type of weather forecasts will suppose a breakthrough in technology which will be enhanced in the future and it will allow to develop better prediction models, decreasing damages caused to aviation due to weather conditions.

Figure 4.58 – Weather alert available for aviation

Chapter 5 – Ensuring Safety and Security

Aviation safety has steadily improved (section 5.1) including in the mitigation of weather hazards (section 5.2). Aviation has been one of the preferred targets of malicious actions, stressing the importance of physical security (section 5.4) and resilience to internal and external attacks (section 5.5). Progress also brings new challenges, such as the integration of 'drones' (section 5.3) that contributes to the need for vast safe exchanges of data (section 5.6).

*** Flight 2050 goal 14: "European air transport system has less than one accident per million commercial aircraft flights"**

Aviation is the safest mode of transport. In addition, aviation safety has steadily improved to the point where no hull loss was recorded in one year. It can be expected that more years will come without a single major aviation accident. The safety target in the goal 14 can be achieved by strengthening the cradle-to-grave safety chain of aviation: (i) aircraft design based on the most reliable scientific methods, validated and tested in the more stringent conditions; (ii) meeting comprehensive certification standards in all aspects related to operations and safety; (iii) control of the supply of raw materials, documentation of fabrication processes and production quality checks; (iv) qualification of all human actors, including pilots, maintainers and air traffic controllers; (v) provision and maintenance of all support systems and equipment at the required standards; (vi) strict implementation of safety rules and procedures; (viii) reporting of incidents, without identification or blame, before they become accidents; (viii) swift implementation of protective measures once a potential hazard has been identified; (ix) continuous search for best practices and their timely implementation; (x) use of existing and development of new monitoring, fault tolerant and adaptive systems and emergency intervention strategies.

Safety fundamentally contributes to the sustainable growth of a sound and economically viable international civil aviation system. The report 'Flightpath 2050 Europe's Vision for Aviation' sets a goal for year 2050 of reducing the accident rate of commercial aircraft flights to less than **one per ten million flights**, i.e. half the reached current level. However, whilst the aviation accident rate continues to decline, the rate of decline has slowed markedly since 2004 and at the same time we are seeing a continued growth in the number of flights, which are set to almost double by 2030. As consequence, in order to preserve the current low level of fatalities resulting from air accidents, we **must ensure** that the rate of accidents continues to decline in order to counterbalance the predicted growth in the number of flights.

To improve the currently existing levels of aviation safety (somewhere in a text flight safety and aviation safety are used in a same meaning, but in general case an **aviation safety** is considered as much wider and deeper term, including *flight safety*, *aviation security*, *environmental safety*, etc. [M. Kulyk]), especially when considering the continuing growth of the industry, additional measures are required. One such measure is to encourage individual aircraft operators to introduce their own Safety Management System (SMS).

SMS is an organized approach to managing safety. The system in the concept of SMS means a framework of functions to manage safety. Management is about controlling the function of

the system towards the safety objectives. Another goal of the introduction of SMS is the facilitation of safety oversight by the national authorities. Two arguments drive the promotion of SMS by the regulatory authorities. Furthermore, due to the growth of aviation activities, budget constraints in the safety oversight function of the authorities require a new way of safety oversight that reduces costs [Dijkstra A.]. Also safety levels vary considerably. There have been specific years without a hull loss by major airlines. In contrast, accident rates are much higher in remote regions subject to harsh weather, in third-world countries with less technological and regulatory resources and in other aviation sectors like private and agricultural.

Europe has started to implement a Safety Management System to become more pro-active in the identification of hazards and with the ultimate goal of further reducing our already good safety record. This system complements the existing system of developing safety regulations, complying with them and investigating accidents and serious incidents when they occur [EASA EASp 2014 – 2017]. One of the key elements of an SMS is managing safety risks, which means identifying hazards, assessing the risks and making decisions on the best course of action to mitigate those risks.

International regulations and standards (including ICAO Standards and Recommended Practices, SARPs, especially of the Annex 11 "Air Traffic Services" [ICAO Annex 11], in paragraph 2.26.5, and Annex 14 "Aerodromes" [ICAO Annex 14], in paragraph 1.4, Single European Sky Common Requirements [EU Regulation 1035/2011] and EUROCONTROL Safety Regulatory Requirements - ESARRs) require that any change to a system that has an impact on the safety of aerodrome operations or air traffic services (ATS) shall be subject to a risk assessment and mitigation process to support its safe introduction and operation. Within the ICAO *Safety Management Manual* [ICAO Doc. 9859] a safety assessment process is defined by a seven-step process (Figure 5.1).

Figure 5.1. The Seven-Step Approach to Safety Assessment Process [ICAO Doc. 9859]

The terms 'system' and 'project' are used throughout this report and should be considered to include the following constituents:

- a) Any equipment;
- b) Any procedure (e.g. operational procedure used by the aerodrome operator or air traffic service provider or, alternatively, a maintenance procedure for related equipment); and

c) The people involved and their organization.

Aerodrome and ATS projects commonly pass through a variety of phases during their life from initial concept through to decommissioning. Safety needs to be planned for and addressed in all of these phases although the depth of risk assessment will vary depending upon the stage of the project and the degree of risk that exists [UK CAA CAP 760].

Risk management is generally understood as the holistic process involved in recognizing possible risks and the measures undertaken to reduce and monitor them. It thus comprises a modular cycle of communication, documentation, control, early warning mechanisms, and advancement (Figure 5.1).

Performing risk assessment early in the project can identify hazards that impact on the design of the system. It is better that these hazards and their impact are identified early in a project so that the system can be designed to take account of them, rather than incurring expense trying to change a design or retrospectively to generate safety assurance evidence later in a project.

Early in the project it is beneficial to identify the Applicable Safety Regulatory Requirements, including National and International SARPs, local Regulations and guidance material applicable to the intended system. These will influence the design of the system and compliance to these standards and regulations will often mitigate hazards inherent to the project. For example, for ATS systems the following may be applicable:

- a) ICAO SARPs, e.g. ICAO Annex 11 and others,
- b) Single European Sky Interoperability Rules and Common Requirements,
- c) European Standards e.g. Eurocae MOPS (Minimum Operational Performance Specifications); Eurocontrol ESARRS (European Safety Regulatory Requirements),
- d) National Civil Aviation Authority (CAA) Safety Requirements.

For example, for aerodrome projects the following may be applicable [UK CAA CAP 760]:

- a) ICAO SARPs e.g. ICAO Annex 14,
- b) European Standards, e.g. EUROCONTROL ESARRs,
- c) CAA Safety Requirements for Licensing of Aerodromes,
- d) CAA Safety Requirements for Aerodrome Survey Information,
- e) CAA Safety Requirements for Airside Safety Management,
- f) CAA Safety Requirements for the Assessment of Runway Surface Characteristics,
- g) CAA Safety Standards for the Competence of Rescue and Fire Fighting Service (RFFS) Personnel Employed at Licensed Aerodromes,
- h) CAA Safety Requirements for Aircraft Fuelling and Fuel Installation Management.

Several reasons why the accident rates in aviation sector vary so much between different parts of the world (Figure 5.2). The first that comes to mind is that *safety cultures* vary between countries and airlines. It is not an easy task to establish *a safety culture*—it is more a development which takes time and commitment and must be understood by everyone within an organization. An organization's culture is defined by what the people do and which decisions they take. This reveals the basic values of an organization. A *positive* safety culture will move a company forward to a maximum achievable safety level, despite business cycles and times of recession where financial pressure is evident. A positive safety culture can be split

into four different components: Informed culture; Reporting culture; Just culture and Learning culture.

Figure 5.2 - Fatal accident rate of scheduled passenger and cargo fatal accidents per 10 million flights, by region of the world, using the regions defined by the ECCAIRS taxonomy from 2004 to 2013 [EASA EASp 2014 – 2017]

Theoretically, differences should not exist because air traffic management rules are international and almost all countries are ICAO members, thus they have adopted its regulations and recommendations. Another noticeable aspect is that there are only a few manufacturers of airliners in the world and their standards are practically equal. From this aspect there should be no differences between the different regions and countries because all airlines are customers of these companies and their training and maintenance programmes. However, significant differences exist in the age of the aircraft, resources allocated to their maintenance and regulators oversight and the problem should be solved efficiently. One solution would be large scale knowledge and information interchange between actors in the airline industry.

In order to improve aviation safety in Europe it is vital that the output of the safety analysis process is used to support the data-driven approach to the identification and prioritization of actions of the European Plan for Aviation Safety (EPAS) [EASA Annual Safety Review 2016].

The Safety Risk Management (SRM) process aims to establish a clear framework that supports the EPAS (Figures 5.1 and 5.3). The resulting actions on the safety issues that are identified in the SRM process will translate into rulemaking activities, focused oversight, research activities, safety promotion and potentially also in actions for Member States.

Figure 5.3. Safety risk management cycle

The 5 steps of the Safety Risk Management Cycle include:

1. The identification of safety issues (or hazards) that affect the European aviation system;
2. The assessment of safety issues (or hazards), which aims at assessing the risks associated with the consequences of the safety issues (or hazards) identified in the previous phase;
3. The definition and programming of safety actions seeking to identify strategies (or mitigation actions) to address those issues (or hazards) whose level of risk cannot be tolerated following the assessment;
4. The implementation and follow-up of safety actions aimed at tracking the status of and report on the agreed strategies; and
5. Safety Performance aimed at reviewing identified risk areas to assess if the risks previously identified have been mitigated and to compare them with safety performance indicators.

All safety issues in aviation are monitored. Aircraft operators, organizations that maintain aircraft, as well as other entities in aviation are required to report any safety issues they detect. The reports are analysed to identify any concerns. This continuous monitoring allows the early detection of potential problems. EASA takes immediate and appropriate action to ensure that the highest safety standards are maintained. Improving the standards of aviation safety and environmental protection requires rules to be continuously reviewed and improved based on the latest scientific knowledge. The rules are drafted and adapted to reflect the changing technology and needs of aviation with safety as the first priority. EASA advises the European Commission on safety rules and is responsible for describing in technical terms the best ways to achieve a high level of safety. Rules are reviewed in consultation with industry and citizens to ensure they are proportional to the aims they aspire to.

The introduction of Risk-based Oversight (RBO) in aviation sector, as can be seen today [EASA TE.GEN.00400-003], will allow for a more effective use of the available oversight resources. Risk

assessment and mitigation is a structured and systematic process for the identification of hazards and the assessment of the risk associated with each hazard, or group of hazards. The acceptability of the risks is determined by comparing the assessed level of risk to the predetermined safety assessment criteria or Safety Objectives. The chart below (Figure 5.4) gives an overview of the RBO's benefits. While aviation is growing, traditional oversight will remain but will also request a similar increase in the number of required resources. RBO, through increased efficiency would keep this requested increase at a lower level. Moreover, it would also increase effectiveness of oversight and contribute to achieving the objective of keeping a reducing trend in the number of accidents in spite of the increased exposure.

At State's level, RBO provides a mechanism for better identifying hazards, measuring associated risks as well as demonstrating effective mitigation of these risks. Ultimately it allows the Competent Authority to focus its attention on organizations that require additional or higher attention, strengthening the efficiency of the oversight. At the same time, an improved understanding of the risks across the aviation system will enable better calibration of the oversight, on the basis of an improved risk picture that takes into account the causal factors of all safety occurrences, from isolated events to incidents and accidents.

Figure 5.4 - Benefits of Risk-based Oversight implementation in aviation sector [EASA TE.GEN.00400-003]

5.1 Ultra-Low Accident Rate in Commercial Flight

*** Flight 2050 goal 14: "European air transport system has less than one accident per million commercial aircraft flights"**

Aviation is the safest mode of transport. Air safety 2010-2015 on EU territory with EU-registered aircraft: 188 fatalities in commercial air transport (the 155 fatalities in 2015 occurred in three accidents: one in Slovakia (4 fatalities), one in Spain (1 fatality), and one in France (150 fatalities), (Figures 5.5 and 5.6) and 1 196 in other categories [Eurostat 2017]. In January 2016, a Bombardier CRJ-200 operated by a cargo operator from one of the EASA Member States (EASA MS) crashed in Sweden, killing the two-flight crew. This was the only fatal accident

involving any EASA Member State operators of Commercial Air Transport involving aeroplanes during 2016. In the last decade, there have been a total of 12 fatal accidents involving operators from the EASA Member States, one every year since 2014.

The Figure 5.7 shows the evolution of the number of fatal accidents and fatalities for Commercial Air Transport Large Aeroplane operations (MTOW above 5,700 kg) – CAT Aeroplane for the period 2007-2016. Security related occurrences, such as the Russian A320 of Metrojet that exploded over the Sinai Peninsula (Egypt), the A321 Daala Airlines in Mogadishu and the MH17 was shot down over Ukraine, are not included within this review. The Germanwings accident, the A320 Egypt Air over the Mediterranean Sea (terrorist action not yet confirmed) and the missing MH370 aircraft are still included.

Figure 5.5. Commercial Air Transport by EU-28-registered aircraft, number of persons killed in air transport accidents (Source: Eurostat)

Figure 5.6 - Persons killed in air accidents on the territory of the EU, involving aircraft registered in EU-28 countries, 2015, by aviation category (Source: Eurostat)

Figure 5.7. Worldwide Fatal Accidents and Fatalities - 2007 to 2016 [EASA Preliminary Safety Review 2017]

The 39th ICAO Assembly (2016) [A39-WP/29] stressed the need for continuous improvement of aviation safety through a reduction in the number of accidents and related fatalities in air transport operations in all parts of the world, particularly in States where safety records are significantly worse than the worldwide average. In addition, aviation safety has steadily improved to the point where no hull loss was recorded in one year. It can be expected that more years will come without a single major aviation accident.

The actual number of accidents in the previous 10-year series varies from the lowest in 2009 with 17 accidents to a maximum of 31 accidents in 2012. In 2015 there were 25 accidents, which is within the average of the historical series. In terms of fatalities, the single fatal accident resulted in 150 fatalities, which is higher than the 10 years average. There was also a slight increase in serious injuries with 11 compared with 9.2 over the previous 10 years. At the same time, there was a 24% reduction in the number of serious incidents over the same period with a total of 58 serious incidents compared with the average of 75.8. EASA MS AOC holders show a lower rate of fatal accidents per one million departures than the rest of the world. The rate has remained well below 0.5 fatal accident per million departures since 2006 (Figure 5.8):

Figure 5.8 - CAT aeroplane fatal accident rate per million departures world-wide vs EASA MS [EASA Annular Safety Review 2016]

The split in terms of operation type of the aircraft involved in accidents or serious incidents in 2015 shows passenger or cargo commercial transport the main player and the presence of other operation types such as military operations or pleasure flights where they have interacted with CAT aeroplane operations in occurrences (Figure 5.9). These two last ones being part of near mid-air collisions.

Figure 5.9 - CAT aeroplane accidents and serious incidents by operation [EASA Annular Safety Review 2016]

The counting of accidents and serious incidents is not a good risk measure. The introduction of the European Risk Classification Scheme in 2017, as part of the implementation of Regulation (EU) 376/2014, will help to provide a better picture of the existing safety risks. The Scheme will help to shift the focus to the probable potential harm of identified hazards to the European aviation system (risk level associated to hazards) instead of directly measuring the severity of a realized outcome (fatalities, injuries, damage). The Aeroplanes Safety Risk Portfolio is the result of the identification of safety issues through the analysis of safety data (historical occurrence data), and includes the joint expert judgment of the Agency, the Member States and industry, through the Network of Analysts (NoA) and the Collaborative Analysis Group in the Commercial Air Transport domain (CAT CAG), respectively. In terms of timeframe, the data populating safety issues covers a 5 years period (2011-2015), while for the safety

issues risk areas the data covers 10 years. This is to increase the representativeness of the data for risk areas that are mainly associated with accidents, which are less frequent in the CAT aeroplane domain.

The Figure 5.10 compares the average number of CAT EASA MS accidents and serious incidents for the period 2007-2015 with that for 2016. The number of occurrences (accidents and serious incidents) for all Key Risk Areas, except for System Failure and Runway Excursion, remains very similar to the average for the period 2007-2015; thus, showing a stable pattern. Considering the positive trend in the period 2007-2015, followed by that in the period 2015-2016, the Key Risk Areas of System Failure, Airborne Conflict and Runway Excursion show a negative change in 2016 (from stable to increasing or from decreasing to increasing) in contribution to fatal accidents in the last 10 years with 18% of those accidents.

Figure 5.10 - EASA MS Operator Accidents and Serious Incidents by Key Risk Area –average 2007 to 2015 compared with 2016 [EASA Annular Safety Review 2016]

Aircraft Upset represents only 3% of the accidents and serious incidents involving an EASA MS operator in 2016. However, it continues to be the most fatal risk area for EASA MS Operators. In 2016, the Preliminary Impact Assessment on “Loss of Control In-Flight” indicated the need for specific actions in this area within the European Plan for Aviation Safety (EPAS). The EPAS is the key strategic document for improving aviation safety at European Level. With 45% of fatal accidents involving technical failures in some way during the past 10 years, this is both a major accident outcome and a precursor to other types of accident. Specific analysis work is ongoing to identify the systemic, safety issues that may be present in the domains of airworthiness, maintenance and production. Over the last 10 years, 27 % of fatal accidents involved ground collision and other associated ground events. The risk area “Controlled Flight Into Terrain (CFIT)” is the second.

Safety Issues are the areas of safety concern that may cover one or more identified safety deficiencies that may lead to an accident. The Safety Issues are defined following an analysis of the causal and contributory factors involved in occurrences, using neutral language for the wording of the issue. Within each Safety Risk Portfolio, the Safety Issues are grouped usually

into the areas of Operational, Technical, Human and Organizational. They are then ordered by the number of fatal accidents, accidents, serious incidents and incidents (taken from the ECR) in which those Safety Issues are seen to be present or involved. This ordering is then used to support initial prioritization of follow up analysis. In the Safety Risk Portfolios, Event Types in the ECCAIRS/ADREP Taxonomy have been matched as closely as possible to the different Safety Issues but this was not a perfect match in all cases and therefore the numbers should be taken as indicative of the general number of occurrences related to each Safety Issue. A total of 64% of fatal accident outcomes involve “loss of control” (Figure 5.9), which has been the most frequent fatal accident type during the last 10 years. This risk area also includes events that are direct precursors to a loss of control event, such as a deviation from flight path, abnormal airspeed or triggering of stall protections. Below are the actions currently ongoing in the European Plan for Aviation Safety (EPAS) that are related to this key risk area.

Accidents and Serious Incidents mostly involve complex situations involve multiple causes and contributors. The graph below (Figure 5.11) highlights the origins of the causal and contributory factors behind the Accidents and Serious Incidents involving EASA Member State Operators between 2007 and 2016.

The safety target in the goal 14 can be achieved by strengthening the cradle-to-grave safety chain of aviation: (i) aircraft design based on the most reliable scientific methods, validated and tested in the more stringent conditions; (ii) meeting comprehensive certification standards in all aspects related to operations and safety; (iii) control of the supply of raw materials, documentation of fabrication processes and production quality checks; (iv) qualification of all human actors, including pilots, maintainers and air traffic controllers; (v) provision and maintenance of all support systems and equipment at the required standards; (vi) strict implementation of safety rules and procedures; (viii) reporting of incidents, without identification or blame, before they become accidents; (viii) swift implementation of protective measures once a potential hazard has been identified; (ix) continuous search for best practices and their timely implementation; (x) use of existing and development of new monitoring, fault tolerant and adaptive systems and emergency intervention strategies.

Figure 5.11 - The causal and contributory factors behind the Accidents and Serious Incidents involving EASA Member State Operators between 2007 and 2016

Safety levels in Europe are also influenced by events in countries outside the European Union. Aircraft fly into the US and Europe from all over the world, and the F.A.A. first and subsequently EASA too have banned flights by foreign airlines with dubious safety or maintenance standards. Conflicts around the world continue to challenge aviation authorities in their efforts to ensure the safe transport of passengers. The new threats highlight the need to further strengthen the links with security agencies. Safety and security risks are taking new forms through cybersecurity weaknesses and threats. The European Commission and the Member States through the EASA Management Board have endorsed the Agency's Cybersecurity strategy which is currently being implemented. Due to the increasing population of unmanned aircraft systems (drones), EASA has been very active in this field, having proposed a flexible regulatory scheme to ensure the operation of drones does not affect the safety of the rest of the aviation system. Also, the Agency together with manufacturers and scientists is assessing the risk of collisions between drones and other aircraft.

5.2 Weather Hazards and Risk Mitigation

*** Flightpath 2050 goal 15: "Weather and other hazards from environment are precisely evaluated and risks properly mitigated"**

Atmospheric conditions continue to be a major factor in aircraft operations, although much progress has been made in flying safety through what were in the past hostile scenarios. As safety progresses former hazards are overcome, and new ones are discovered, that were previously hidden behind other events. For example, windshear or microbursts must have been the cause of accidents in the past of aircraft flying through storms, but were identified clearly only 3 decades ago, as other safety hazards were overcome. General weather predictions and on-board sensors like weather radar are basic indicators of potential hazards; laser Doppler radar is a good complement not generally fitted to airliners. The information from flights of preceding aircraft on similar routes can also be a useful warning.

An example is a windshear associated with a microburst: (i) a toroidal vortex lies above the ground; (ii) it creates a down flow through its core; (iii) the following horizontal flow changes from head wind to tail wind as an aircraft flies under the core; (iv) the combination of down flow and tailwind can lead to stall and/or crash. The wind shear is most readily detected by LIDAR that measures wind speed; it can be detected by the weather radar if the microburst is associated with rain. The indications of an aircraft that has recently flown a similar path are a warning for the safest option of wind shear avoidance.

The mitigation of weather hazards thus requires: (i) supplementing meteorological data by information from ground based or airborne weather radars or lidars and flight reports; (ii) early warning of the flight concerned on the type and severity of the hazard likely to be encountered; (iii) accurate assessment of the risk, survival tactics and timely decision of avoidance if appropriate. The training of pilots on mitigation strategies is the last-ditch defence if warnings have failed. For example, in a wind shear the best strategy is to fly at maximum power and angle-of-attack to minimize altitude loss and sink speed (rather than dive trying to gain speed and lift). Other weather hazards like winds, clear air turbulence, various types of clouds, rain, icing, lightning, volcanic ash clouds, hail, require different strategies.

The aviation system is highly sensitive against disturbing weather effects such as wind gusts, snow falls or cold waves. Atmospheric conditions continue to be a major factor in aircraft operations, although much progress has been made in flying safety through what were in the past hostile scenarios. Weather is responsible for: 13% of aircraft losses between 1995 and 2004 were defined primarily by weather; 33% of all accidents/incidents due to adverse weather – thunderstorms are top-ranked by pilots as hazards affecting flight safety; 40-50% of delays at European airports [Gerz T.]. The severe weather-related accidents and incidents can be attributed to the following weather-related hazards [EUROCONTROL Report]:

- In-flight icing;
- Severe air turbulence (convective cloud origin);
- Hail damage;
- Lightning strike;
- Low visibility due to fog or precipitation;
- Strong low level/surface winds and windshear.

The most likely series of events that harms aviation in EU region takes place when the wind gusts over 17 m/s blow over the area. In addition, fog and cold wave and especially even 1cm/day snow are considered as prevailing weather events in this climate region combined with the high volume of passengers in the area, the effects in terms of delays can be described as massive on a European level [EWENT D5.1].

As seen in Figure 5.12 the risk indicator for accidents due to extreme weather is calculated to be zero [EWENT D5.1]. This ensues the calculations which were done by taking into account the accident rates during the last years (accidents caused by adverse weather). Congruent with the risk indicators of other transport modes the highest risk indicator is in Hungary and Poland where high population and transport density together with low GDP and low quality of infrastructure produce a high-risk level. However, the risk level in aviation is significantly lower than in railway or road transport.

Figure 5.12 - Risk indicators in the Temperate Central region for aviation passenger's transport due to extreme weather events [EWENT D5.1]

The differences concerning the prevailing weather events in this eastern part of the temperate region in comparison to the ones in the western part are not same from a meteorological point of view. In the Eastern Temperate region, the most likely aviation disturbing weather phenomena seem to be snowfalls (over 1 cm/d) and cold waves when temperature drops

under -0°C . Due to these phenomena there exists operating restrictions which lead to delays and increased fuel consumption because of airborne holding for arriving aircraft [EWENT D5.1].

Also delays for flight cancellation are possible (Figure 5.13). Compared to other modes of transport even slight disruptions in the flight plans at airports being at their capacity limit can lead to massive disruptions throughout Europe and the rest of the world.

Figure 5.13 - Risk indicators for delays in EU [EWENT D5.1]

At the European level, estimates of accidents costs resulting from extreme weather for aviation, the two significant cost items were operator costs resulting from cancellations of flights and time costs for passengers. Operator costs were calculated for selected airports, covering 88% of daily volumes in Europe based on reported number of bad weather days on which an average rate of cancellations was calculated. For passenger time costs, the Eurocontrol official values of time were used to calculate the average delay for each passenger during the number of bad weather days reported for 2010 at the major European airports (the average cancellation rate has been 10 per cent of daily flights). The average delay represents the fact that accumulated delays in major airports results in a continuous problem of delays during the day and sensitivity analyses were carried out with respect to the estimated duration of the delay for each passenger.

The annual operator costs for aviation in 2010 were 606 million euros. This is calculated on the bases of 10% cancellation rate for medium jets. The annual time costs for aviation in 2010 were 980 million euros. This calculation is based on 30 minutes average delay/flight on selected airports (Figure 5.14) [EWENT D5.1]. The data shows the annual impact of cancellations for those airports reviewed by Eurocontrol. The reason why the Northern European climate region dominates the calculation is naturally the volume of extreme weather days compared to other regions. Due to the regional classification between the Temperate Eastern and the Temperate Central regions no airports reviewed feature in the Temperate Eastern region.

Aviation has the most advanced and standardized safety and operational regulations, naturally due to the very strong weather-related safety risks, and these are and must be followed with precision (Figure 5.15). The severe weather impact can be associated to two different, yet

interdependent, risks, notably *Flight Safety Risk* and *Flight Efficiency Risk*. The *Flight Efficiency Risk* is associated to the likelihood and potential extent of incurred flight delays or even cancellations made due to severe weather risk management. The *Flight Safety Risk* is the ultimate driver for the existence of the severe weather impact management. Flight Safety Risk can have different sources and manifestations: In-flight Safety Risk (impact on flight crew and to put the *Hazard Encounter Risk* at the core of the approach as it is the original reason for the existence of the array of activities associated to severe weather risk management) and ATCO Excessive Overload Risk. For the purposes of this approach the management of the Hazard Encounter Risk is described using two generic risk management functions: *risk prevention* and *risk mitigation*.

Risk prevention is understood as any action aimed at avoiding the materialization of the risk. These actions are further assigned to three-time phases:

- Pre-tactical prevention – all actions taken before the day of operation;
- Tactical prevention – all actions taken on the day of operation, but before the commencement of the flight (off-block);
- In-flight prevention – all actions taken after commencement of the flight (off-block) but before hazard encounter.

Figure 5.14. Costs (mill. €) for road accidents' fatalities (red; socio-economic costs) and aviation cancellations (black; operators' costs) and aviation delays (blue; passenger time costs) by climate regions [EWENT D5.1]

Figure 5.15 - Hazard encounter risk management model [EWENT D5.1]

Risk mitigation could be described as the actions taken by the concerned actors to contain the impact and minimize potential adverse safety effects on ATM and flight operations following hazard encounter or when encounter is imminent. Expected further elaborations for that in meteorology [Gerz T.]:

- Need for system-wide information sharing among all aviation stakeholders;
- ... necessary for their collaborative decision-making processes;
- Derive simple, unambiguous and standardised products;
- Combine different hazards when and where appropriate: seamless, and in aviation sector;
- Develop impact scenarios for various stakeholders
- Derive business cases to tailor MET info to the user's needs.

5.3 Integrating Drones in Manned Airspace

*** Flightpath 2050 goal 16: "The European air transport system operates seamlessly through interoperable and networked systems allowing manned and unmanned air vehicles to safely operate in the same airspace"**

The term "drones", although possibly inaccurate or inappropriate, is used for brevity as in colloquial language, to designate UAVs (Unmanned Air Vehicles), RPVs (Remotely Piloted

Vehicles), Remotely Piloted Aircraft Systems (RPAS), AAVs (Autonomous Air Vehicles), etc ... The use of drones currently falls into 3 categories:

- Long-range global operations like “Global Hawk” imply take-off and climb and descent and landing in restricted military airspace and cruise above airline traffic at altitudes of 18 km or more;
- Flight in line-of-sight, in good weather, not overflying populated areas, at a limited altitude (usually below 100 m), as an extension of the traditional radio-controlled aircraft models;
- Unrestricted flight in remote, uncontrolled war-torn regions like Afghanistan, Syria or Iraq, with lack of safety standards or their enforcement.

Two main areas are identified within the UAS spectrum in terms of the types of operation: 1) the professional use of drones for various security, safety, survey and other tasks and 2) the recreational use where the general public are using drones for fun and private activities.

Ensuring safety with Unmanned Aircraft requires a different approach (Figure 5.16) that [Stark B.]:

1. Incorporates dynamic risk management systems;
2. Has built in mechanisms for improvement, and,
3. Scales appropriately to risk.

In Risk Assessment a Quantitative Statistics is a basic element. The number of drones within the EU has multiplied over the last 2 years. EASA has already introduced a technical opinion to initiate the definition of the regulatory framework required at EU level. Most of the occurrences in this RPAS analysis were related to either airspace infringements which occasionally lead to a near collision with an aircraft. Analysis of RPAS occurrences in the European Central Repository identified 584 occurrences of all severity levels, of which 37 accidents had been classed as accidents (2011-2015), none of the accidents involved fatalities and there were only four minor injuries reported in the period since 2010 (Figure 5.17). The application of the definition of accident in relation to RPAS has improved since new definitions were provided in ICAO Annex 13.

UAS Safety Management System

Figure 5.16 - UAS Safety Management System [Stark B.]

Figure 5.17 - RPAS occurrences per year – 2010 to 31 May 2016 [EASA SM1.1]

This graph (Figure 5.17) shows an increasing trend in the number of reported UAS occurrences (both accidents and incidents) per year from 2010 to June 2016 that involve UAS, with a clear and significant jump in 2014. Up to 31 May 2016, the number of occurrences in 2016 reached 50% of those in 2015 and this does not take into account the reporting process time lag between an occurrence happening and it being reported through an NAA to the ECR. In considering the risk of a collision between a manned aircraft and a small unmanned aircraft, the EU Task Force considered that the key risk to address was firmly centred on a collision with a large commercial aeroplane; this view was supported by the responses received to the related survey question as shown in the Figure 5.18:

Figure 5.18 - Responses to the question on “Main Perceived Risks” [EASA SM1.1]

The Figure 5.19 shows the initial Event Types analysis in which precursors to Airborne Conflict accidents unsurprisingly feature highly. These include Airspace infringements and Loss of

Separation, as well as near collisions. The vast majority of the Safety Issues subsequently identified, and the analysis that follows, covers this outcome category. It can be seen that 63% of occurrences are related to Airborne Conflict, which is the main Key Risk Area. This means that airspace infringements and proximity of drones to other aircraft is causing a significant number of occurrences.

Figure 5.19 - UAS Occurrences 2010- May 2016 - Safety Events [EASA SM1.1]

The Figure 5.20 shows the number of reported Airborne Conflict occurrences taken from the ECR which highlights the different numbers across the EASA MS. Further data is becoming available from other sources in individual States (such as from the ANSV – Accident Investigation Board Italy). The data from operators collected through the CAT Aeroplanes CAG was used to cross-check the number of occurrences in different states.

Figure 5.20 - UAS Airborne Conflict occurrences per state. Time period 2010-May2016 [EASA SM1.1]

The Figure 5.21 provides details of the airspace class where occurrences took place (limited to the occurrences where this information was available) provided also with the flight phase of the aircraft that reporting the occurrence. The graph shows that the highest number of

occurrences took place in D and G class airspace. Class D – Controlled airspace: IFR and VFR flights are permitted, and all flights are provided with air traffic control service, IFR flights are separated from other IFR flights and receive traffic information in respect of VFR flights, VFR flights receive traffic information in respect of all other flights (ICAO Airspace Classifications). Class G – Uncontrolled airspace: IFR and VFR flights are permitted and receive flight information service if requested. It can also be seen that most of the occurrences happen during Approach and during En route phases of the flight. It also needs to be considered that many occurrences do not have any airspace information coded which limits the usability of the data.

Figure 5.21. UAS Occurrences in Relation to Airspace by Flight Phase. Time period 2010-May2016 [EASA SM1.1]

In contrast with this limited use, there is a vast potential to be exploited, and no shortage of highly visible candidates like Amazon and Google wanting to offer delivery, surveillance and other services. These services and experiments can be authorized on a case-by-case basis to ensure safety. Prospective users like Google have suggested blanket approvals like: all space below 100 m reserved for drones; ignoring that low altitude air space is used by police helicopters, emergency medical services, etc..... The safety risks are well documented by a variety of incidents involving unauthorized use of drones violating legal rules, such as: (i) numerous cases of drones flying near airports, including cases in which the aircraft had manoeuvre to avoid a collision; (ii) landing a drone in the lawn of the White House in the US, the building of the prime minister of Japan, a North Korean drone near the office of the prime minister of South Korea; (iii) several overflights of French nuclear power stations by drones; (iv) a drone seen on television crashing just behind an alpine skier in a competition it was filming; (v) ISIL used drones to drop rudimentary bombs in Iraq and Syria. Setting aside unauthorized use and the difficulties in preventing it, the main question is what conditions should drones be allowed to share airspace with manned aircraft? At least 4, namely:

- Professionalism: The record of aviation as the safest mode of transport relies on the highest professional standards: the engineers who design the aircraft, the authorities that certify it, the pilots that fly it, and the air traffic controllers that direct it. Where fits a layman flying a drone? What qualifications, training and safeguards are needed so that this is not the weak, unprofessional link?

- Quality: Commercial aircraft are high quality products in the design, testing, materials, production and operation, all of which are neither easily achievable nor cheap. Can a cheap drone produced without quality control be a safe partner in a congested airspace, or must it meet at least the same quality standards?

- Sense and avoid: This is the issue discussed most often concerning the safety of removing the local pilot and remote air traffic controller from the critical process of collision avoidance. If the traffic density is too high collision avoidance may become impossible: how does a drone recognize this? How is it avoided?

- Capacity: Air Traffic Management (ATM) capacity has been broadly sufficient to cope with manned air traffic, with occasional delays or disruptions. It has managed to keep ahead of air traffic growth, not a mean feat, though not by a wide margin. Is there the spare capacity for a large number of drones? How to limit their number if demand turns out to be huge as market prospects suggest?

Analyse the existing studies on the subject of impact between drones and aircraft:

- Study the vulnerabilities of aircraft (windshields, engines, and airframe) taking into account the different categories of aircraft (large aeroplanes, general aviation, and helicopters) and their associated design and operational requirements.
- Consider the possibility to do further research and perform actual tests (for example on windshields).

The regulatory framework for the safe operations of drones in Europe currently being developed by EASA already addresses the issue of collision between drones and aeroplanes. A combination of measures is envisaged such as: operate in visual line of sight, fly under 150 m height above ground, be equipped with identification and geo-limitation functions and be registered. Any operation of drones close to aerodromes would require a specific authorization from the national aviation authority based on a risk assessment.

The Key Risk Areas (Outcomes) identified from the data were [EASA SM1.1]:

- Airborne Conflict: The number of reported near-miss occurrences between drones and aircraft has increased significantly in the past 2 years. There have been a small number of collisions between drones and GA aircraft, fortunately with no fatalities so far. However, it should be noted that many of the reports of near-misses with UAS are unconfirmed and might in fact involve other objects such as birds. Indeed, some of the reports of near-misses with UAS have occurred at altitudes where UAS are not normally able to operate.

- Aircraft Upset. The 2nd Key Risk Area identified involved Aircraft Upset, which covers the full range of Loss of Control situations, which presents the potential for injuries to people on the ground.

- System Failures. Both System/ Component Failure Power plant and Non-Power plant feature in the outcome types and therefore is also included in the Key Areas as it could also lead to injuries to people on the ground, especially in certain types of UAS operation.

- Third Party Conflict. The final Key Risk Area covers the risk of UAS conflicts (collisions) with people or property (i.e. not involving aircraft) where they may cause injuries or damage. There were no occurrences involving such damage or injuries, but expert judgement identified this as a key risk area that could occur through causes not associated with loss of control

(Aircraft Upset) or technical failure in situations where a drone operator accidentally flies into people or property.

Control Strategies and the Hierarchy of Controls is shown in the Figure 5.22:

Figure 5.22 - Control Strategies for UAS safety management [Stark B.]

5.4 Comprehensive and Unobtrusive Security Measures

*** Flight 2015 goal 17: “Efficient boarding and safety measures allow seamless security for global travel with minimum passenger and cargo impact. Passengers and cargo pass through security controls without introduction”**

Aviation safety has seen a steady and spectacular progress into the safest mode of transport (sections 5.1 – 5.2). The recent societal threat going back to barbarism, seeks to maximize loss of life through terrorist acts aimed at most transports.

The ingenuity that has achieved the safety of air transport must also be applied to ensure its security at all stages of travel: (i) at the departure airport, through check-in, passport and luggage inspection; (ii) in the transit to the aircraft; (iii) in flight; (iv) at the arrival airport. Terrorists who fail their murderous attempts may still see some success in the disruption caused by the safety measures needed to foil their evil intents. While the patience and understanding of passengers is essential there should be the minimum of delay, intrusion and disruption in the implementation of safety measures, through the use of the most appropriate equipment and airport architectures. The standards of European airports may not be taken for granted at some remote or holiday destinations, possibly requiring further security initiatives.

Aviation will face serious continuing and new security risks from terrorist groups, radicalized individuals and persons acting for other reasons (as documented in consecutive editions of the Aviation Security Global Risk Context Statement) against the backdrop of the evolving global security situation, passenger and cargo traffic growth, infrastructure expansion, commercial and fiscal pressures and other developments in air transportation. Security related events, such as criminal acts affecting (interference, sabotage) aircraft, crew member actions, aviation critical infrastructure or the safety of airspace (acts of war) are more challenging, while concurrently demanding a close coordination between the Safety Investigation and the authorities in charge of the judicial investigation.

A clear need exists for the strengthening of security to be applied to all phases and processes associated with the carriage of persons, their cabin and hold baggage, cargo, mail, courier and express parcels, and in protecting civil aviation against cyber-attacks and cyber threats [ICAO A39-WP/17].

Considering that international passenger traffic is expected to reach 6 billion by 2030 from about 3.3 billion today, while air cargo transported is expected to increase to 125 million tonnes from 50 million (based on ICAO and IATA air traffic forecasts), growth of the aviation industry will have significant ramifications for the aviation sector's security risk profile. While the ten acts of unlawful interference recorded by ICAO in 2015 is less than the 21 acts in the previous year, high-priority risk areas for aviation in the coming years include landside security, the threat of a cyber-attack on the aviation sector, the increasing use of Remotely Piloted Aircraft Systems (RPAS) as well as the use of person-delivered improvised explosive devices.

The policy instruments have shaped ICAO's aviation security programme direction, and provided focus for priority setting for the Organization [ICAO A39-WP/14]:

- a) Declaration on Aviation Security, adopted through Resolution A37-17, which reaffirmed Member States' commitment to strengthen global aviation security;
- b) The ICAO Comprehensive Aviation Security Strategy (ICASS), which emphasizes seven Strategic Focus Areas of the Organization over two triennia (2011-2016) mandated by the 37th Assembly;
- c) Conclusions and recommendations of the 2012 High-level Conference on Aviation Security aimed at strengthening the global aviation security framework, particularly by mitigating the risks to air cargo and mail security and addressing the insider threat; and
- d) Resolutions adopted by the ICAO Assembly on the consolidated statement of continuing ICAO policies related to aviation security.

The 39th ICAO Assembly (in 2016), recognizing the need to strengthen aviation security worldwide, in light of the continuing threat to civil aviation, including the attempted sabotage of Northwest Airlines flight 253 on 25 December 2009; and acknowledging the value of the joint declarations on civil aviation security emanating from regional conferences held with a view to enhancing international cooperation, hereby urges Member States to take the following actions to enhance international cooperation to counter threats to civil aviation [ICAO A39-WP/16]:

- 1) strengthen and promote the effective application of ICAO Standards and Recommended Practices, with particular focus on Annex 17 [ICAO Annex 17] — Security, and develop strategies to address current and emerging threats;
- 2) strengthen security screening procedures, enhance human factors and utilize modern technologies to detect prohibited articles and support research and development of technology for the detection of explosives, weapons and prohibited articles in order to prevent acts of unlawful interference;

- 3) develop enhanced security measures to protect airport facilities and improve in-flight security, with appropriate enhancements in technology and training;
- 4) develop and implement strengthened and harmonized measures and best practices for air cargo security, taking into account the need to protect the entire air cargo supply chain;
- 5) promote enhanced travel document security and the validation thereof using the ICAO Public Key Directory (PKD) in conjunction with biometric information, and the commitment to report on a regular basis, lost and stolen passports to the INTERPOL Lost and Stolen Travel Documents Database to prevent the use of such travel documents for acts of unlawful interference against civil aviation;
- 6) improve Member States' ability to correct deficiencies identified under the Universal Security Audit Programme (USAP) by ensuring the appropriate availability of audit results among Member States, which would enable better targeting of capacity-building and technical assistance efforts;
- 7) provide technical assistance to States in need, including funding, capacity building and technology transfer to effectively address security threats to civil aviation, in cooperation with other States, international organizations and industry partners;
- 8) promote the increased use of cooperation mechanisms among Member States and with the civil aviation industry, for information exchange on security measures in order to avoid redundancy, where appropriate, and for early detection and dissemination of information on security threats to civil aviation, including through the collection and transmission of advance passenger information (API) and passenger name record (PNR) data, as an aid to security, whilst ensuring the protection of passengers' privacy and civil liberties; and
- 9) share best practices and information in a range of key areas, such as: screening and inspection techniques, including assessments of advanced screening technology for the detection of weapons and explosives; document security and fraud detection; behaviour detection and threat-based risk analysis; screening of airport employees; the privacy and dignity of persons; and aircraft security.

A more integrated approach to aviation safety and security is needed, as illustrated by issues such as cybersecurity and remotely-piloted aircraft systems; aviation security requires a cross-functional approach that ensures appropriate coordination with facilitation, aviation safety, air navigation and other relevant fields. More real-time sharing of critical information between States and industry, and between aviation security professionals and partners who have a need to know should be encouraged, as highlighted by recent events related to civil aviation operations near conflict zones.

The seven Strategic Focus Areas of the ICASS should remain as a solid foundation for addressing current and future aviation security challenges and should therefore be used to help shape the Global Aviation Security Plan (GASeP). It is envisaged that the ICASS would transition seamlessly into the GASeP when the latter is approved, with the Strategic Focus

Areas of the ICASS being given renewed emphasis in a more holistic and global framework. Other supporting strategies (for example, ICAO Assistance and Capacity Building Strategy) could also be integrated therein.

The main components for defining the GASeP, as illustrated in the Figure 5.23, should be built around six key themes, under which specific goals and targets (Table 5.1) could be pursued. It also includes four broad areas of “enablers”, which contribute towards achieving goals related not only to one key theme but across all themes. While further details of the GASeP would need to be elaborated and refined, the six key themes of the GASeP, could be used to help frame the deliberations [ICAO A39-WP/15].

Key objectives from 2017 used for ICAO comprehensive aviation security strategy and development of the ICAO GASeP [ICAO A39-WP/14]:

Strategic Focus Area 1: Addressing new and existing threats. ICAO made continued efforts to enhance risk awareness, promote risk policy, and implement a risk-driven security culture with a view to ensuring risk-based Standard-setting and rule-making on the basis of guidance material such as the Aviation Security Global Risk Context Statement. *Key objectives for 2017-2019:* Continue efforts to ensure States take substantial steps to incorporate effective threat and risk assessment methodologies and mechanisms into their national aviation security programmes.

Strategic Focus Area 2: Promoting innovation in aviation security. ICAO focused on innovation, collaborative actions and coordinated efforts such as through the organization of an ICAO Symposium on Innovation in Aviation Security (2014), supporting the ACI Airport Excellence (APEX) programme, the establishment of an AVSEC Panel Working Group on Innovation in Aviation Security (WGIAS) and enhancements to the AVSECPaedia within the ICAO secure portal (<https://portal.icao.int>); all designed to stimulate innovative, effective, and efficient security approaches to aviation security. *Key objectives for 2017-2019:* Promote the increased sharing among States of best practices and emerging trends in aviation security systems and technologies utilizing ICAO platforms.

Figure 5.23 - Key themes, under which GAsEP specific goals and targets could be pursued [ICAO A39-WP/15]

Goals	Targets
1: Improved capacity to address all threats to aviation security	1. By 20xx, States have utilized effective threat and risk assessment methodologies; 2. By 20xx, States have made significant efforts to promote risk-based measures and approaches; 3. By 20xx, States have implemented mechanisms to ensure greater threat information sharing;
2: Achieve higher levels of effective implementation of ICAO Annex 17	4. By 20xx, compliance by States and Regions to substantially improve levels of aviation security; 5. By 20xx, mobilize additional financial resources for effective implementation of aviation security; 6. By 20xx, substantial reduction of States with significant security concerns (SSeCs);
3: Promote development of human resources in aviation security	7. By 20xx, substantial steps taken by States to promote security culture across all organizations; 8. By 20xx, significant efforts by States to promote greater capacities of security professionals;
4: Effective and efficient security measures through process and technology innovation	9. By 20xx, States have strengthened technological capacity to address the threat posed by LAGs;

	<p>10. By 20xx, substantial efforts made by States to enhance research and to foster innovation;</p> <p>11. By 20xx, all States have utilized ICAO platforms for sharing screening best practices;</p> <p>12. By 20xx, greater efforts by States to recognize other States' systems where determined equivalent;</p>
5: Enhance implementation through capacity building	13. By 20xx, enhance regional partnerships for implementing effective and targeted capacity-building activities to support regional initiatives and plans;
6: Integrated approach to aviation safety, security and other disciplines	14. By 20xx, more efforts by all States to ensure a cross-functional approach to aviation security.

Table 5.1 - Indicative list of GAsEP goals and targets

Strategic Focus Area 3: Sharing of information. Efforts have been made to continuously strengthen ICAO capacity to securely gather, collate and disseminate information on security incidents, threat and risk concerns, and trends through improved functionalities of the relevant ICAO platforms, particularly the Point of Contact (PoC) Network, which currently includes PoCs from nearly all ICAO Member States, the Acts of Unlawful Interference Database, and information on Universal Security Audit Programme (USAP) audit results and Significant Security Concerns (SSeCs). *Key objectives for 2017-2019:* Improve mechanisms for the reporting by States of acts of unlawful interference in accordance with Annex 17 and the dissemination of relevant information.

Strategic Focus Area 4: Promoting global compliance and establishing sustainable aviation security oversight capability of States. Throughout the triennium, ICAO ensured greater coherence and coordination in rectifying deficiencies identified by the USAP including the Comprehensive Regional Implementation Plan for Aviation Security and Facilitation in Africa (AFI SECFAL), which was launched as an ICAO Programme to enhance the coordination of assistance activities in Africa [ICAO A39-WP/20, A39-WP/28]. *Key objectives 2017-2019:* Enhance implementation and address deficiencies in States identified through audit and monitoring activities, capacity-building and resource mobilization to support effective implementation of regional plans and initiatives focused on assisting developing States to achieve improved levels of security.

Strategic Focus Area 5: Improving human factors and security culture. Increased emphasis was placed on addressing the continuing need for global and regional aviation security training, by collaborating with the institutions within the ICAO ASTC Network, which now comprises 30 members. *Key objectives 2017-2019:* Enhance aviation security training efforts by collaborating with the institutions within the ICAO Aviation Security Training Centre Network.

Strategic Focus Area 6: Mutual recognition of aviation security processes. Continued efforts in promoting mutual recognition of aviation security processes were made through extensive collaboration with stakeholders and industry, including dissemination of the newly developed guidance material Recognition of Equivalence of Security Measures as well as information exchange and debate through the AVSEC Panel. *Key objectives 2017-2019:* Reduce unnecessary duplication of measures towards the optimal use of aviation security resources,

in order to achieve the desired and appropriate balance between the effectiveness of security measures and the efficiency of air transport, including optimized facilitation.

Strategic Focus Area 7: *Emphasizing the importance of aviation security worldwide.* Increased outreach activities at the national, regional and international levels led to improved awareness of the global aviation security threat environment. For example, to strengthen air cargo security, ICAO carried out a range of joint initiatives with the World Customs Organization (WCO), designed to heighten awareness among aviation security authorities, customs administrations and stakeholders of the need to strengthen aviation and border security while facilitating the flow of cargo. Intensified ICAO/WCO collaboration included, for example, Joint ICAO/WCO Conferences, alignment of regulatory frameworks, joint training courses and the publication of a document entitled *Moving Air Cargo Globally*. *Key objectives 2017-2019:* Improve awareness of the global aviation security threat environment, and promotion of dialogue on new and emerging aviation security challenges.

The foundational element of the framework should be based on the notion of progressive aviation security enhancement as the core objective, consistent with ICAO's Strategic Objective. For practical purposes, aviation security enhancement is defined as the improvement in the effectiveness and efficiency of aviation security to mitigate the risk of acts and attempted acts of unlawful interference, and to mitigate its consequences; it is the achieving and acquiring of qualitative improvement while managing security costs [ICAO A39-WP/15].

5.5 Resilience to External and Internal Threats

*** Flightpath 2050 goal 18: "Air vehicles are resilient by design to current on-board and on the ground security threat evolution, internally and externally to the aircraft"**

The safety door limiting access to the cockpit is an example that safety measures can in some cases function in intended and unintended ways: (i) in most cases it may have prevented hijackings; (ii) in the isolated case of the mentally disturbed German Wings co-pilot it prevented the captain from entering the cabin and preventing an intentional crash. The security measures also depend on the perceived level of threat and accepted level of risk: (i) El Al aircraft are equipped with DIRCM (Directed Infra-Red Counter Measures) to counter shoulder fired anti-aircraft missiles, whereas most other airliners do not have such systems, originally developed for military aircraft; (ii) Israeli and at same time U.S. commercial aircraft have armed Sky Marshalls, although the use of firearms in a pressurized aircraft has risks.

Security issues can lead to difficult dilemmas: if an liner is hijacked, and refuses to follow the flight and landing instructions from an armed interceptor aircraft, and heads to a major inhabited area like 9/11, should weapons be used? An alternative would be to take over control of the aircraft remotely by building in this capability at the design stage. Doing so assumes that: (i) it is possible to decide remotely if the aircraft has been hijacked, the crew has suicidal intents or is unconscious due to hypoxia or other problems; (ii) the communications and controls allow safe flight to the closest suitable airport; (iii) the systems is immune to spoofing, cyber-attack or other malicious use. Ultimately people on board, if not controlled, have several means to cause a crash, reinforcing the need for airport security and preventive measures.

The EU is facing one of the greatest security challenges in its history [EC JOIN REPORT]. Threats are increasingly taking non-conventional forms, some physical such as new forms of terrorism, some using the digital space with complex cyber-attacks. Others are subtler and are aimed at the coercive application of pressure including misinformation campaigns, and media manipulation. Recent coordinated cyber-attacks across the globe, for which attribution has proved challenging, have demonstrated the vulnerabilities of our societies and institutions. EU leaders have placed security and defence at centre-stage in the debate about the future of Europe. This was acknowledged in the Rome Declaration of 25 March 2017 which set out a vision of a safe and secure Union committed to strengthening its common security and defence.

Transport security is a source of general concern. Recent events have shown that it is particularly true for air transport. First, dramatic events have a detrimental effect on air transport growth. Second, security checks reduce travelling convenience and increase airport transit time. This goes against the efficiency target set by the air transport community in the ACARE vision document. This is the reason why security is considered one of the three main research topics in ACARE SRA2 addendum, along with environment and alternative fuels.

Access control and filtering cover border control, security filters, *etc.* The public seems to increasingly accept the idea of security screenings and resulting delays. However, the industry is looking for filtering solutions which overcome security delays for passengers. A concept that might be considered at political level is the idea of the “trusted passenger” - that is, someone who is willing to renounce a large part of his or her data protection rights to speed up passage through security checks. This concept, supported by robust identification systems such as fingerprint and iris detection, might enable reduced airport transit times.

Security has become a major factor in civil and commercial aviation. Aviation security system to be “[r]ecognized as the world leader in civil aviation security—identifying and countering aviation-related threats to U.S. citizens worldwide” [Federal Aviation Administration]. The strategic goal stated in the plan was to let “[n]o successful attacks against U.S. civil aviation” occur. In comparison to the breadth and depth of the post-9/11 focus on aviation security, the desired key results stated in this document in retrospect seem quite modest and the goal tragically unattained.

In recent decades, the number of threats to aviation security has grown significantly. Current and emerging threats have been clustered into the following eight threat categories [COPRA SECURITY D5.1]:

- Improvised Explosive Devices (IED), firearms and close range destructive threats;
- Chemical, Biological, Radioactive, Nuclear and Explosive (CBRNE) threats;
- Ground-to-air threats;
- Ground-to-ground threats;
- Cyber threats;
- Electromagnetic threats;
- Sabotage, seizure and hijacking;
- Bluff threats and threats from social media.

Threat assessment defines the level of the threats against critical assets by evaluating the types, means and possible tactics of those who may carry them out. In a threat assessment it is important to be aware of national threats and to identify the threats specific to the airport and to the airlines serving it. For in-depth analysis, it is also interesting to identify the history of criminal or disruptive incidents in the area surrounding the airport, but not primarily directed toward the airport operations (Figure 5.24).

This has led to even more security regulations as the threats evolved. Thereby, security procedures have become exceedingly complex, time consuming and invasive to passenger privacy. At the same time, passenger and cargo traffic are expected to double in the next 15 years. It is clear that the current complex security system cannot be adapted to such growth. It has already and will increasingly become a major market restraint [Bart E.].

Currently, aviation security is primarily based on the preventive phase and is inflexible to new threats. This is also mirrored in the research landscape for aviation security: Most projects concentrate on preventive measures such as the detection of CBRNE-substances. EU Project [COPRA SECURITY D5.1] recommends that the future aviation security system (and research) should be based on all elements of the resilience cycle in a well-balanced composition. It should embrace processes and technologies to support each phase of the resilience cycle (Figure 5.25).

Figure 5.24 - Aviation Security Threat Sources, Tactics, and Targets [Bart E.]

Resilience is defined as the ability to: prepare (take into account); prevent (repel or thwart); protect against (absorb or mitigate); respond to (cope with) and recover from (and adapt to), Figure 5.25.

Figure 5.25 - Resilience cycle depicting possible actions associated with the different phases

The aviation security system should be resilient to the evolving threat situation. It should therefore be based on the complete resilience cycle of “prepare, prevent, protect, respond and recover”. This should enable stakeholders to “learn and adapt” instead of exclusively be ruled by reactive, strict and inflexible regulations.

Security concepts should aim at involving different measures at different stages of the passengers’ travel. The COPRA Aviation Security Research Roadmap [COPRA SECURITY D5.1] has been developed in the final Work Package of the COPRA project. The goal of the roadmap is: *‘To provide the European Commission and the Member states with clear guidelines for future R&D activities responding to operational and economic market needs while being attentive of the acceptance by citizens’.*

The measures should be adequate for the respective stage and even further reduce the risk of attacks. The security concepts should thus make sure not only to concentrate on the prevention of dangerous objects to be brought into the airport or aircraft, but also should contain elements of the other phases of the cycle. E.g., measures in the “protect” phase of the cycle could remove the need for prevention of tiny incidents or could mitigate large events to make them manageable; measures in the “prepare” phase could take into account analysis of evolving threats in order to be able to adjust the other phases accordingly. Measures at each phase should thus correspond and connect to measures in the other phases of the resilience cycle. Therefore, covering and balancing the complete resilience cycle means that as much emphasis as required is to be put on [COPRA SECURITY D5.1]:

- Pre-incident issues (i.e. Prepare, prevent),

- Inter-incident issues (protect) and
- Post-incident issues (respond, recover).

A visual representation of the roadmap with all roadmap items plotted in a chart was designed and shown on the Figure 5.26:

Figure 5.26 - Recommendations and goals for future aviation security concepts [COPRA SECURITY D5.1]

5.6 High-Bandwidth Data Resilient to Cyberattacks

*** Flightpath 2050 goal 19: “The air transport system has fully secured global high bandwidth data network, hardened and resilient by design to cyber-attacks”**

So far there have been no major reports of jamming of civil aircraft communications or cyberattacks on air traffic infrastructure. Some isolated incidents from the past indicate that it can happen: (i) a Tornado aircraft flying over Radio Free Europe in southern Germany may have suffered loss of control due to high power radio transmissions interfering with on board systems; (ii) the Iranian television showed an American UAV intact (except for undercarriage) that did an emergency landing (US version) or was remotely diverted (Iranian version). It is not without reason that all airliner flights request switching off of electronic devices or changing

to flight mode. It is known that the standard GPS navigation signals can be easily jammed, leading at least in the U.S., to the development of "jam-resistant" GPS versions and entirely separate alternative navigation systems. The operation of air traffic will require increasing amounts of data exchanging, needing larger bandwidth; this will give more opportunities for jamming and more entry points for cyberattack. There are countermeasures and protection methods, some developed by the military that should be sufficient to stop a not too sophisticated attacker.

The vulnerabilities that need to be taken into account are: (i) in a large, complex interconnected system there are many entry points for cyber intrusion and many links to spread the cyber-attack; (ii) the weakest node may be the preferred entry point, for example small suppliers of equipment or codes well protected by large industries or government bodies. Cyber protection involves hardware and software and their human users in very diverse scenarios; the civilian and military cyber training events are a way to gain and update skills and tend to have a regular and expanding participation. In some cases, the hosts are the victims of cyber-attacks that have experienced their consequences and want to avoid similar situations in the future.

The principles of cyber-defence are: (i) protect each node against intrusion by multiple identification/screening/rejection measures, some of which can be quite simple; (ii) have an independent monitoring of the network capable of detecting and locating anomalies and quickly isolating them; (iii) design the system for cyber-security so that affected parts can be isolated, and the lost functions can be allocated elsewhere. It should be borne in mind that: (i) the only code that cannot be broken is that used only once; (ii) It is not possible to protect software 100% with another software. The blockchain is one of the favourites current technologies focused on cyber-security. Perhaps the most famous or infamous user of blockchain technology is the bitcoin whose value has risen and fluctuated widely; there have been several reported instances of hackers stealing large sums of bitcoins...

The World Economic Forum has identified cybersecurity among its top global risks for the last eight years. Its Cyberspace 2025 Model includes airports with their transformative technologies to reduce costs, increase customer (passenger) satisfaction, and increase productivity in airport operations. Digital landscape will greatly impact airports across the globe and unfortunately, cybersecurity threats are growing faster than cybersecurity mitigation measures.

A cyber-attack can be conducted for numerous reasons in general case:

- Disruption of airport operations, perhaps in advance of a physical attack
- Theft, Loss of data, Embarrassment to the airport and its management
- Or for no reason at all
- A cyber-attack can be carried out by numerous actors:
- Disgruntled passenger
- Hacktivists
- Criminals
- Anonymous
- Insider threats
- Nation-states, Terrorists

Different security systems are currently used stand-alone and their results are not necessarily combined to achieve a combined assessment. Aviation systems such as for booking, check-in, security scanning (carry-on luggage and goods) or access control all work using completely different techniques; each system is unique and works on its own without any connection between them. A network of information as well as process interactions should be developed that are able to collect and use the data resulting from different security checks [COPRA SECURITY D5.1]. A seamless end-to-end process for goods and cargo requires a continuous flow of information of different security systems. For reasons of efficiency, systems should be integrated to interact with each other in order to be able to provide a security solution for all stakeholders by exploiting synergic effects. For example, analytic systems could be connected with different information gathering systems such as results of luggage checks or booking, boarding and travel information systems. The joint information might be used as input in, for example, behavioural pattern recognition algorithms for achieving improved results. Such connected and auto-analytic systems might also solve situations where several quasi-simultaneous events – each of which not a conspicuous situation as such – could lead to a potential security relevant event. Therefore, integrated security systems and the corresponding algorithms should be developed that are able to collect, merge and analyse data from completely different sources/systems across all stakeholders in aviation. These systems should facilitate the creation of completely seamless security processes.

The use of digital data and the level of interconnection of IT systems are strongly increasing in civil aviation. Consequently, stakeholders of the air transport system like airlines, airports and air traffic control are more and more interlinked (Figure 5.27) and, thus, depend on secure means of data exchange.

ISO 27002 is a Security Program Benchmark and stresses a holistic approach to cyber security. Airport approach to cyber security management:

- Recognize the Reality and Don't Underestimate the Problem
- Cybersecurity is a Top Management Issue
- Think Aviation Industry-Wide
- Establish a Security Program
- Perform Risk Assessment and Prioritize Your Defence
- Establish a Strong Patching Program
- Include Cybersecurity in all levels of the Organization
- Increase your Internal Capability/Acquire Qualified External Assistance
- Develop an Adaptive Security Architecture
- Participate in the ACI World IT Security Benchmarking Tool

Figure 5.27 - Interconnection of the air transport system: Arrows indicate the interfaces for information exchange and, thus, represent risks for contagion effects in the case of false or missing information

ICAO Assembly calls upon States and industry stakeholders to identify the threats and risks from possible cyber incidents on civil aviation operations and critical systems, and the serious consequences that can arise from such incidents. Based on a common understanding of cyber threats and risks, adopt a flexible, risk-based approach to protecting critical aviation systems through the implementation of cybersecurity management systems [ICAO A39-WP/17].

Cyber-attacks can impact aviation businesses in several ways, from the loss of data and intellectual property to business interruption and more. To protect all key assets and effectively manage cyber risk, it's critical that you understand the cyber scenarios your organization is most likely to face — and how much they can cost your business.

To assess your cyber risk, you should:

- Identify and inventory key assets — data, systems, and infrastructure — that are essential to your operations.
- Review your internal controls and digital profile to identify internal vulnerabilities and external threats.
- Value your cyber assets at risk using modelling and other data and technology tools.

By taking these steps, you can objectively measure your cyber risk, and incorporate quantitative data into your risk management decision-making.

Four comprehensive scenarios address different segments of the air transport system and serve as a basis for the analysis of specific attack vectors from internal or external aggressors

(Table 5.2). One scenario, for example, considers an incorrect representation of the airspace during transatlantic flights or near airports. In such a case, the determination of the position of one or more aircraft could be impaired, which would lead to a loss of integrity of the respective airspace. Another scenario addresses a spoofed data link between two air transport stakeholders in an area relevant for safe operation. Here, the entire air transport system could be impacted due to contagion effects.

Table 5.2 - Horizontal scenario space illustration: Both key process steps in the lifetime of an aircraft and each of the scenario spaces are depicted. Own illustration, based on EATMA (European Air Traffic Management Architecture)

Based on these potential threat scenarios, an aviation consortium is able to assess potential threats and risks for the air transport system. The project [Cyber resilience scenario] the developed scenarios will be transferred to a demonstrator for the purpose of analysing how air traffic resilience could be improved with respect to potential cyber threats.

Risk Management for cyber security in airports, airlines and flight control organizations is realized in accordance with system approach and view, it is shown in the Figure 5.28. ATC is highly dependent on the availability and integrity of its technical infrastructure, buildings, IT and communications systems. In recent years, particular attention has been given to this topic. But this remains an important area of concern with regard to potential penetrations aimed at causing dramatic incidents (e.g., the SAIFIT project on IT security, SAFEE on advanced aircraft security system).

It is not without reason that all airliner flights request switching-off of electronic devices or changing to flight mode.

The increasing complexity and interconnection of systems provides more entry points for cyber-attacks and more paths for its spread. A cyber-protection system must continuously monitor the whole network, quickly detect anomalies, isolate the affected systems, and restore their functions by other means.

The consideration of safety and security measures, indicates the importance of the following topics.

Figure 5.28. Risk Management for cyber security

- The mitigation of weather hazards is one of the safety aspects of air traffic management (Key Topic T5.1).
- A major challenge is the integration of drones in controlled air space (Key Topic T5.2).
- On the ground side airports need to implement comprehensive and unobstructed security measures (Key Topic T5.3).

The provision of high-bandwidth data resilient to cyber-attacks for the aviation sector (Key Topic T5.4) is one aspect of the wider issue of cyber-protection (Key Topic 5.5) for which specific technologies are being developed (Key Topic 5.6).

KEY TOPIC T5.1 – EVALUATION AND MITIGATION OF WEATHER AND OTHER HAZARDS

Goal 15 was defined in Flightpath 2050 as "Weather and other hazards from environment are precisely evaluated and risks properly mitigated".

Comparing the scope in both Flightpath 2050 and SRIA it can be stated that both proposals are coherent between themselves. The objective of ensuring high levels of operational safety make that the knowledge of most of weather phenomena, other hazards and their possible

effects can outcome as a great value in the pursuing of safety through mitigating their related risks.

Moreover, it is necessary to take into account the climate change and the possible effects that could become a reality in the future, either short or long term. In this matter, research and development become essential in order to understand possible new hazards and to set mitigating measures that should be implemented to reduce their associated risks.

Benchmarks

It is a statement that aviation could not exist without the air. This is owing to lift principles being based on the variation of air speed between intrados and extrados of the wings which generates a variation of pressure that translates into the coming up of a upwards force called lift.

This variation of air speed is extremely important for the aircraft performance thereby airplanes usually take off and land upwind in order to increase this variation of speed between air and aircraft, obtaining a larger lift.

However, usually wind and other meteorological effects become hazardous for the aircraft operation producing different setbacks such as delays or even incidents and accidents. The following weather hazards should be considered in the air traffic operation [9]:

- **Icing:** one of simplest assumptions made about clouds is that cloud droplets are in a liquid form at temperatures warmer than 0°C and that they freeze into ice crystals within a few degrees below zero. In reality, however, 0°C marks the temperature below which water droplets become 'supercooled' and are capable of freezing. While some of the droplets actually do freeze spontaneously just below 0°C, others persist in the liquid state at much lower temperatures. Aircraft icing occurs when supercooled water droplets strike an aircraft whose temperature is colder than 0°C. The effects icing can have on an aircraft can be quite serious (Figure 5.29) and include:
 - Disruption of the smooth laminar flow over the wings causing a decrease in lift and an increase in the stall speed. This last effect is particularly dangerous. An "iced" aircraft is effectively an "experimental" aircraft with an unknown stall speed.
 - Increase in weight and drag thus increasing fuel consumption
 - Partial or complete blockage of pitot heads and static ports giving erroneous instrument readings.
 - Restriction of visibility as the windshield glazes over.

Figure 5.29 - Effects of icing on an aircraft [9]

- **Visibility:** reduced visibility is the meteorological component which impacts flight operations the most. There are several causes of reduced visibility:
 - **Lithometers:** lithometers are dry particles suspended in the atmosphere and include haze, smoke, sand and dust. Of these, smoke and haze cause the most problems. The most common sources of smoke are forest fires. Smoke from distant sources will resemble haze but, near a fire, smoke can reduce the visibility significantly.
 - **Precipitation:** rain can reduce visibility; however, the restriction is seldom less than one mile other than in the heaviest showers beneath cumulonimbus clouds. Drizzle, because of the greater number of drops in each volume of air, is usually more effective than rain at reducing the visibility, especially when accompanied by fog. Besides, snow affects visibility more than rain or drizzle and can easily reduce it to less than one mile. Blowing snow is a product of strong winds picking up the snow particles and lifting them into the air. Fresh fallen snow is easily disturbed and can be lifted a few hundred feet. Under extreme conditions, the cockpit visibility will be excellent during a landing approach until the aircraft flares, at which time the horizontal visibility will be reduced abruptly.
 - **Fog:** it is the most common and persistent visibility obstruction encountered by the aviation community. A cloud based on the ground, fog, can consist of water droplets, super cooled water droplets, ice crystals or a mix of super cooled droplets and ice crystals. There are different types of fog:
 - **Radiation fog:** it begins to form over land usually under clear skies and light winds typically after midnight and peaks early in the morning. As the land surface loses heat and radiates it into space, the air above the land is cooled and loses its ability to hold moisture. If an abundance of condensation nuclei is present in the atmosphere, radiation fog may

- develop before the temperature-dew point spread reaches zero. After sunrise, the fog begins to burn off from the edges over land but any fog that has drifted over water will take longer to burn off.
- **Precipitation or frontal fog:** it forms ahead of warm fronts when precipitation falls through a cooler layer of air near the ground. The precipitation saturates the air at the surface and fog forms. Breaks in the precipitation usually results in the fog becoming thicker.
 - **Steam fog:** it forms when very cold arctic air moves over relatively warmer water. In this case moisture evaporates from the water surface and saturates the air. The extremely cold air cannot hold all the evaporated moisture, so the excess condenses into fog. The result looks like steam or smoke rising from the water and is usually no more than 50 to 100 feet thick. Steam fog, also called arctic sea smoke, can also produce significant icing conditions.
 - **Advection fog:** it forms when warm moist air moves across a snow, ice or cold-water surface.
 - **Ice fog:** it occurs when water vapour sublimates directly into ice crystals. In conditions of light winds and temperatures colder than -30°C or so, water vapour from manmade sources or cracks in ice covered rivers can form widespread and persistent ice fog. The fog produced by local heating systems, and even aircraft engines, can reduce the local visibility to near zero, closing an airport for hours or even days.
- **Wind, shear and turbulence:** unravelling the daily variations of the winds, where they blow and how strong they do remain a problem for meteorologists. The problem becomes even more difficult when local effects such as wind flow through coastal inlets or in mountain valleys are added to the issue. The result of these effects can give one airport persistent light winds while another has nightly episodes of strong gusty winds. Besides, one of the most dangerous effects for aviation is wind shear. It is nothing more than a change in wind direction and/or wind speed over the distance between two points. In the aviation world, the major concern is how abruptly the change occurs. If the change is abrupt, there will be a rapid change of airspeed or track and, depending on the aircraft type, it could take a significant time to correct the situation, placing the aircraft in danger, mostly during take-off and landing. Significant shearing can occur when the surface wind blowing along a valley varies significantly from the free-flowing wind above the valley. Changes in direction of 90° and speed changes of 25 knots are reasonably common in mountainous terrain. This is the case of Bilbao Airport, where a significant number of go arounds are registered every year. For example, in 2001, an Embraer ERJ-145 EP operated by Portugalia, made a first ILS approach on runway 30. When was on final, the pilot decided to go around and follow the missing approach procedure in order to make a second try. During the second approach, the pilot decided to try again the ILS 30 approach having been informed of variable wind of 250/21 with gusts of 25 kt. The aircraft landed passed half of the runway and seconds later made a runway excursion, stopping over the grass 135 meters far away from runway 12 threshold. Fortunately, none of the passengers and flight crew were seriously injured. Related to that, mechanical turbulence is a form of shear induced when a rough surface disrupts the smooth wind flow depending on the wind speed,

roughness of the obstruction and the stability of the air. Besides, turbulence is the direct result of wind shear in such a way that the stronger the shear, the greater the tendency for the laminar flow of the air to break down into eddies resulting in turbulence. However, not all shear zones are turbulent, so the absence of turbulence does not infer that there is no shear.

- **Lee waves:** when air flows across a mountain or hill, it is disturbed the same way as water flowing over a rock. The air initially is displaced upwards across the mountain, dips sharply on the lee side, then rises and falls in a series of waves downstream. These waves are called “mountain waves” or “lee waves” (Figure 5.30) and are most notable for their turbulence.

Figure 5.30 - Amplitude (A) and wavelength (W) in lee waves [9]

- **Thunderstorms:** no other weather encountered by a pilot can be as violent or threatening as a thunderstorm. Thunderstorms produce many hazards to the aviation community, and, it's important that pilots understand their nature and how to deal with them. To produce a thunderstorm, there are several drivers which must be in place. These include an unstable air mass, moisture in the low levels, something to trigger them (e.g. daytime heating, upper level cooling...) and for severe thunderstorms it is necessary wind shear. The environment in and around a thunderstorm can be the most hazardous encountered by an aircraft. In addition to the usual risks such as severe turbulence, severe clear icing, large hail, heavy precipitation, low visibility and electrical discharges, there are other hazards that occur in the surrounding environment:
 - **The gust front:** it is the leading edge of any downburst and can run many miles ahead of the storm. This may occur under relatively clear skies and, hence, can be particularly nasty for the unwary pilot. Aircraft taking off, landing, or operating at low levels can find themselves in rapidly changing wind fields that quickly threaten the aircraft's ability to remain airborne. In a matter of seconds, the wind direction can change by as much 180°, while at the same time the wind speed can approach 100 knots in the gusts. All of this will likely be accompanied by considerable mechanical turbulence and induced shear on the frontal boundary up to 6,500 feet above the ground.
 - **Downburst, macroburst and microburst:** A downburst is a concentrated, severe downdraft which accompanies a descending column of precipitation underneath the cell. When it hits the ground, it induces an outward, horizontal burst of damaging winds. There are two types of downburst, the “macroburst” and the “microburst”. A macroburst is a downdraft of air with an outflow

diameter of 2.2 nautical miles, or greater, with damaging winds that last from 5 to 20 minutes. Such occurrences are common in the summer but only rarely hit towns or airports. On occasion, embedded within the downburst, is a violent column of descending air known as a “microburst”. Microbursts have an outflow diameter of less than 2.2 nautical miles and peak winds lasting from 2 to 5 minutes. Such winds can literally force an aircraft into the ground.

- **Volcanic ash:** a major, but fortunately infrequent, threat to aviation is volcanic ash. When a volcano erupts, a large amount of rock is pulverized into dust and blasted upwards. The altitude is determined by the severity of the blast and, at times, the ash plume will extend into the stratosphere. This ash is then spread downwind by the winds aloft in the troposphere and the stratosphere. Of greater concern is the volcanic ash that is ingested by aircraft engines at flight level. Piston-driven engines can fail due to plugged air filters while turbine engines can “flame out” and stop working. That was the case of Eyjafjallajökull in 2010, when it created an ash cloud that led to the closure of most of the European IFR airspace from 15 until 20 April 2010. This meant (Figure 5.31) the disruption of some 100,000 flights and 10 million passenger journeys during these days producing huge economic losses and setbacks.

Figure 5.31 - Traffic in Europe before and during the April crisis [10]

This set of hazards for aviation could become into tragedies if they are not found out with enough time in order to mitigate their impact or to avoid them by setting other routes to be flown. In this manner, phenomena occurred near airports and that affect its operation should be early detected, either through forecasts or actual sighting, in order to implement the appropriate measures, such as advice airplanes to land at another airport.

On the other hand, phenomena occurred along the route that will be followed by the aircraft should be detected before aircraft departs from the airport or far enough from the hazard meanwhile the aircraft is airborne.

In conclusion, these predictive measures lead to the need to develop the current systems and radars used to set both weather and hazards forecasts.

Reference State in 2010

Since the beginning of aviation, weather and its related hazards have been a key factor during air traffic operations, producing uncountable number of incidents and accidents. These events related to meteorology have also produced uncountable delays in aircraft operations, being one of the main reasons which aircraft cannot take-off or land.

In this context, many studies related to these hazards have been carried out along last decades. As example, the National Aviation Safety Data Analysis Centre (NASDAC), which is a part of the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), issued a Review of Aviation Accidents Involving Weather Turbulence in the United States [11], analysing the accidents occurred during 1990s. In this document, data was extracted from the National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB) Aviation Accident/Incident Data System. The NTSB is the official U.S. repository of aviation accident data and causal factors.

This study explained that, from 1992 to 2001, there were 4326 weather accidents out of a total of 20332 accidents that occurred in the United States, setting a 21,3% of total. Of these 4326 accidents, 509 were cited as turbulence weather events which nearly 23 percent of these turbulence-related accidents resulted in fatal injuries to the occupants of the aircraft. The cause or factor most often in the general aviation accidents was downdraft meanwhile in the air carrier accidents was clear air turbulence.

Figure 5.32 - Comparison of weather accidents to weather turbulence accidents 1992-2001 [11]

As can be noticed in the Figure 5.32, the number of weather accidents showed a slightly tend to decrease but it also remained approximately steady over the years, which induces to think that no measures or not enough measures were taken in order to make the number of accidents decrease. Additionally, the following Figure 5.33 shows the percentages of each cause or factor related to weather hazards, describing that the most often causes from 1992 to 2001 were wind and visibility.

Figure 5.33 - Total weather accidents by phenomenon from 1992 to 2001 [11]

Another study called Weather-related Aviation Accident Study 2003-2007 was issued by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) in 2010 [12]. This document reveals that, from 2003 to 2007, there were 8657 aviation accidents which weather was a cause or contributing factor in 1740 accidents setting a 20,1% of total. If this figure is compared with the 21,3% of weather accidents out of total reported from 1992 to 2001, it can be realized that a slightly decrease occurred as it is displayed in the following Figure 5.34:

Figure 5.34 - Weather-related accidents from 1992 to 2007 in the US [12]

Concerning the percentages of each cause or factor related to weather hazards, the following Figure 5.35 shows that the most often causes from 2003 to 2007 were also wind and visibility as in the previous period.

Figure 5.35 - Total weather accidents by phenomenon from 2003 to 2007 [12]

As wind has contributed about 50% of every weather-related accident from 1992 to 2007, it was important to study where on the route these problems had happened to the aircraft. The following Figure 5.36 shows that most of the occurrences had happened during landing at the destination airport (57,7%). Therefore, it is usual to think that different measures to mitigate the impacts of the wind in the operation should be implemented.

Figure 5.36 - Wind accidents by phase of flight from 2003 to 2007 [12]

Progress Up-to-Now

The decreasing streak in number of weather-related accidents have continued along the last few years until reaching historical minimum in 2011. This was explained in the Wake and Weather Turbulence Report issued by Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) in 2016 [13].

According to the NTSB, 19575 aviation accidents occurred in the United States from 2002 to 2013. During this timeframe, weather was identified as a cause or contributing factor in 2983 accidents (15.23%). If this number is compared with the previous percentages, it can be noticed that the number of accidents have considerably decreased in the last few years as it is shown in the following Figure 5.37:

Figure 5.37 - Weather-related accidents in the US from 1992 to 2013 [13]

However, even though the number of accidents due to the weather has steadily decreased until the present time, it is necessary to put into context these accidents in terms of severity. Related to that, covering the period between 2002 and 2013, the following events have been reported:

Figure 5.38 Weather events by worst injury aboard [13]

Assessing the numbers in Figure 5.38, almost half of the events had no consequence for passengers but nevertheless the high percentage of fatal injury cannot be disregarded.

Therefore, it is necessary to find the right measures to turn these fatal events into no consequence events. Besides, and even more important, it is necessary to focus on continuing to decrease the number of weather-related accidents through new developments either aircraft, ground systems and equipment or detection methods and avoidance strategies. This means that more investments within this field are necessary.

As an example of the type of technology available to detect and predict weather related hazardous situations, nowadays in the United States, the ground equipment consists of the Next Generation Weather Radar System (NEXRAD) and Terminal Doppler Weather Radar (TDWR) networks [14]. The Next Generation Weather Radar (NEXRAD) system (Figure 5.39) currently comprises 160 sites throughout the United States and selected overseas locations, using the Weather Surveillance Radars–1988 Doppler (WSR-88D).

WSR-88D systems are modified and enhanced during their operational life to meet changing requirements, technology advances, and improved understanding of the application of these systems to real-time weather operations. These new technologies included:

- Mid-Volume Rescan of Low-Level Elevations (MRLE);
- Supplemental Adaptive Intra-Volume Low-Level Scan (SAILS);
- Enhanced Velocity Azimuth Display Wind Profile (EVWP);
- Automated Volume Scan Evaluation and Termination (AVSET);
- Two-Dimensional Velocity Dealiasing Improvement Algorithm.

Figure 5.39 - NEXRAD system network [15]

On the other hand, the Terminal Doppler Weather Radar (TDWR) network is a Doppler weather radar system (Figure 5.40) operated by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), which is used primarily for the detection of hazardous wind shear conditions, precipitation, and winds aloft on and near major airports situated in climates with great exposure to thunderstorms in the United States [14].

TDWR was developed in the early 1990s in order to assist air traffic controllers by providing real-time wind shear detection and high-resolution precipitation data and, as of 2014, there

were 45 operational TDWR radar systems in major metropolitan locations across the United States and Puerto Rico.

Figure 5.40 Terminal Doppler Weather Radar at Charlotte Airport [14]

Comparing the TDWR to the WSR-88D, the range resolution of the TDWR is finer than what is available in the Weather Surveillance Radar, 1988 Doppler (WSR-88D), or any other FAA radar that has weather channel capability. The TDWR utilizes a range gate resolution of 150 m for Doppler data. It has a resolution of 150 m for reflectivity data within 135 km and 300 m from beyond 135 km to 460 km. By contrast, the WSR-88D employed by the National Weather Service, FAA, and Department of Defence has a maximum range gate resolution of 250 m for Doppler and 1 km for surveillance data.

The angular (azimuth) resolution of the TDWR is nearly twice what is available in the WSR-88D. Each radial in the TDWR has a beam width of 0.55 degrees whilst the average beam width for the WSR-88D is 0.95 degrees.

Summarizing, the Terminal Doppler Weather Radar (TDWR) is a high quality, dedicated meteorological surveillance radar usually deployed near of the larger airports and it is a great supporting feature to the WSR-88D Radar.

In addition, regarding the airborne operation, deteriorating weather conditions are frequently the cause of changes in flight objectives, and the pilot needs to know quickly where the weather is better and what to do to get there. Related to that, it is necessary an Aviation Weather Information (AWIN) system (Figure 5.41) which consists of, a means for distributing the weather products to the users, and a means to present the information to the users.

Figure 5.41 - Block diagram of an AWIN system [16]

However, pilots need more than just weather information for in-flight decision making. This includes aircraft capabilities, pilot capabilities, and information on flight-path-relevant terrain, obstacles, air space restrictions, and traffic. For example, a light windshear or other weather disturbance reported by an aircraft on approach can be used to alert following aircraft and divert them to another airport before the windshear becomes more hazardous. Data links are needed to exchange information between airplanes and ground stations and, in the same manner, aircraft-to-aircraft links may be needed for timely exchange of in situ weather reports. Information from on-board sensors may be passed to ground-based weather systems for incorporation in updated forecasts and reports that can be subsequently transmitted to aircraft in flight. Data-link weather information systems are intended to provide information for long-term strategic planning and to augment on board sensors (Figure 5.42) such as weather radar and lightning detectors.

Figure 5.42 - Cockpit radar display of turbulence [16]

In conclusion, further efforts in this field should be done, such as developing the current systems aboard and improving the communications aircraft-ground and aircraft-aircraft via data link.

Predictions Up-to-2025

By far, the largest cause of air traffic delay in the US airspace is weather. According to FAA (Figure 5.43) data, weather caused 69% of system impacting delays (> 15 minutes) over the six years from 2008 to 2013.

Figure 5.43 - Causes of air traffic delay in the National Airspace System (US)

While weather is the largest cause of delay (i.e., too much demand for the impacted resources), volume alone (too much demand, even with unconstrained resource capacity) also accounts for 19% of delay. Equipment failure (1%) and runway unavailability (6%) account for smaller portions of the delay, and the final category "Other" accounts for the remaining 5%. These delay statistics include Air Carrier, Air Taxi, General Aviation, and Military classes of aircraft.

The portion of delay due to weather represented nearly 10 million minutes of delay in 2013. Delays translate into real costs for the operators and passengers. Currently, the cost to the air carrier operators for an hour of delay ranges from about \$1,400 to \$4,500, depending on the class of aircraft, and whether the delay is taken on the ground or in the air. If the value of passenger time is included, the cost goes up an additional \$35 per hour (personal travel) or \$63 per hour (business travel) for every person on board [11]. The Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) has determined two thirds of this is preventable with better weather information.

As example, if an en route flight encounter a thunderstorm, aircraft can safely fly over thunderstorms only if their flight altitude is well above the turbulent cloud tops. The most intense and turbulent storms are often the tallest storms, so en route flights always seek to go around them. If a busy jet route becomes blocked by intense thunderstorms, traffic will reroute into the neighbouring airspace, which can become overcrowded if the flow is not managed.

In the United States, in the case of a large-scale weather impact, a Severe Weather Avoidance Plan (SWAP) may be put in place to completely relocate demand to another part of the country. The Planning team's strategic placement of Airspace Flow Programs (AFPs) with reduced hourly flow rates allows airlines to prioritize and plan which of their scheduled flights they will route through the restricted airspace. Ground Delay Programs (GDPs) are also used to temporarily hold aircraft at their departure airports to reduce the number of flights coming into an impacted area.

As an example, on September 11, 2013, an approaching cold front caused a broad region of rapid storm development in the New York Centre airspace. An Airspace Flow Program was set about one hour before the weather impact quickly increased, as a way of reducing flow, but west coast traffic bound for New York was already en route. Very few flights could get through the weather-impacted airspace, and many of them were routed northward to avoid the weather. However, the weather continued to progress northward, making for increasingly long reroutes. Even though the New York airports remained clear of weather, the flights bound for New York couldn't get there on time.

As result, there were 69 diversions (meaning aircraft had to land at alternate airports), and 72 taxi-backs (meaning the aircraft pushed back from the gate, ready to take off, but there was no available airspace and they had to return). In addition, there were 55 airborne holding events, and almost 600 departure and arrival cancellations.

In addition to the issues that weather can trigger, stakeholders including airlines, aircraft manufacturers and organizations are concerned that anticipated increases in air traffic over the next 5-15 years will result in crippling convective weather season delays. Therefore, optimizing air traffic management (ATM) to minimize delay in the complicated network environment of airspace requires integrated Weather-ATM decision support tools that explicitly consider airspace structure, network impacts, weather forecast uncertainty, and pilot preferences for weather avoidance.

For example, regarding the pilot decision making on weather avoidance, a critical first step in the translation of weather forecast into air traffic impacts is a validated model for airspace that pilots will seek to avoid. In research funded by NASA Ames Research Centre, Lincoln Laboratory developed an en route Convective Weather Avoidance Model (CWAM1) that outputs three-dimensional weather avoidance fields. The probabilistic Weather Avoidance Fields (Figure 5.44) identify regions of airspace that pilots are likely to avoid due to the presence of convective weather [12].

Figure 5.44 - Weather Avoidance Fields example [12]

The model used Corridor Integrated Weather System (CIWS) Vertically Integrated Liquid (VIL) and echo top fields and National Lightning Detection Network (NLDN) data to predict aircraft deviations and penetrations. The statistical results showed that the difference between flight altitude and the radar storm top was the most important factor in explaining pilot deviations. The second most important factor was the precipitation intensity.

A second study (CWAM2) extended the analysis to additional Centres and included several additional deviation predictors. The additional predictors captured information about storm growth and decay, vertical structure and weather type (convective or non-convective). Even with all the additional information, the difference between flight altitude and radar storm top was again the top predictor of pilot deviation to avoid convective weather [12].

Most deviation prediction errors occurred for flights that encountered echo tops near the flight altitude, for which pilots can legitimately make different choices. The following Figure 5.45 illustrates two flights on the same route at roughly the same flight altitude, 10 minutes apart. The first pilot deviates widely to avoid the weather, while the second flies extremely close to the high storm tops. The model correctly predicted the second pilot's behaviour, but not the first.

a) 17:37 - 33 kft. flight altitude

b) 17:47 - 36 kft. altitude

Figure 5.45 - Deviation prediction example [12]

A third CWAM study (CWAM3) is currently being planned. It will be the first to include operational information, such as time of day (daylight, twilight, and night), aircraft type, airline, airspace congestion, etc., as potential predictors of deviation. Lincoln Laboratory is also investigating the visual cues available in the cockpit to gain a better understanding of which aspect of the weather the pilot considers hazardous [12].

Summarizing, during the following years research programs will focus on facilitating the decision-making to the professionals involved in the aircraft operation, such as pilots and air traffic controllers, during the en route phase through better forecasts and real time deployments of weather situation in the cockpit.

Evolutionary Progress Up-to-2050

During the flight in en route area, aviation is only disrupted marginally by weather phenomena. But during start and landing, it is very sensitive to those effects. Especially fog, snow and wind can disrupt the operations with even a low intensity. This weather impact will increase in future. Past has shown that particular airports, operating at their capacity limit, are affected by bad weather phenomena. Due to the expected increase in aviation, more and more airports will operate in this area close to their overall capacity, and therefore, they will be more affected by weather. But especially high-density airports transfer delay to the next day as they do not have the capacity to reduce accumulated aircraft queues during regular operations.

Looking at the expected development for aviation, it can be stated that the influence of weather on aviation will increase in future. The reason here is not primarily the climate change, but the prognosis for growth in worldwide air traffic.

The effects of climate change for air traffic can be hardly foreseen, as there are many overlapping effects, which can offset or accumulate. Below you can find some examples [13]:

- A reduced number of fog situations leads to avoidance of higher separation and finally in higher yearly capacity;
- An increased number of thunderstorms result in more temporary closure of airspace or airport and so in a lower yearly capacity;
- Increasing temperatures reduce the necessity for de-icing procedure, resulting in shorter turn-around times and hence in an increase of capacity;
- More sandstorms in the Mediterranean region reduce the visibility, what leads to an increase in separation and so in a loss of capacity.

But due to the expected growth in aviation, an increasing number of airports will operate near their capacity limit and hence will be more sensitive to disturbances by weather phenomena. An increase of the capacity by airport extension programs is especially in Central Europe very difficult due to environment restrictions and the noise awareness within the vicinity of an airport. Therefore, technical and procedural developments are needed to face this challenge and maintain the high standards of safety and quality in air travel.

For example, NextGen weather vision is focused on providing multiple user common weather picture, consistent and reliable weather information and an improved weather information and data storage approach containing observation and forecast data enabling NextGen dissemination capabilities (called the 4-D Data Cube).

A Net-centric capability is envisioned for NextGen, and it is referred to as "Network Enabled": an information network that makes information available, securable, and usable in real time, information may be pushed to known users and is available to be pulled by others and weather information sharing is two-way. This contains a "virtual" repository with no single physical database or computer: conceptually unified source distributed among multiple physical locations and suppliers, of which the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) is the leading data supplier.

Comparing the situation nowadays to the new requirements by NextGen, the differences are the following (Table 5.3):

Today	New requirements by NextGen
Not integrated into aviation decision support systems (DSS)	Totally integrated into decision support systems (DSS)
Today's requirements can lead to inconsistent weather information	Updated requirements/Nationally consistent
Low temporal resolution (for aviation decision making purposes)	High temporal resolution

Disseminated in minutes	Disseminated in seconds
Updated by schedule	Updated by events
Fixed product formats (graphic or text)	Flexible formats

Table 5.3 - New requirements by NextGen [14]

Following this guideline, FAA recommendations for weather information display in the cockpit are:

- Provide integrated display of weather data.
- Incorporate decision-making aids referenced to a specific pilot and flight profile.
- Emphasize hazardous weather directly relevant to flight profile (per known pilot prioritizations).
- Indicate reliability of forecast information (i.e. probabilities associated with specific forecasts).
- Provide access to lower levels of detailed data without full-time display of same.

If we talk about Europe position, NextGen and SESAR project were compared in 2008 to identify similarities and differences of both projects with regards to weather. The following excerpt seems to be correct at present as well.

The primary difference between SESAR and NextGen concerning weather is the manner in which information is acquired. In NextGen, a centralized government-run weather service is anticipated, while in SESAR the information will be derived from a variety of traditional sources. A more net-centric solution would be to allow each carrier to be able to choose whatever information is available from certified sources to provide maximum safety.

In the case of SESAR, the information will be derived from a variety of (traditional) sources including an increased reliance on remote sensing systems, aircraft derived data and satellite-based weather information. With enhanced digital communications services, the provision of Meteorology (MET) information will encompass ground-based and potentially airborne automation systems and human users.

On the other hand, NextGen foresees weather as moving from a stand-alone display to an integrated decision-making element. A primary objective of NextGen is the establishment of a single authoritative weather service available to all systems communicating within the network. While little is said about how this service will be run, a great detail is provided on what type of service will be available. The service will draw data from traditional weather reporting systems, aircraft and other sensors in route including UAVs specifically deployed for weather collection, commercial weather services which will augment the system at the basic provision rate and presumably at premium rates as a choice of individual carriers and aircraft and potentially airborne automation systems and human users as well as from weather national service.

Furthermore, it is also important to consider pilots' requirements about weather information [14]:

- Access to information has to be continuous and it has to be available on the ground and in the air, from early pre-flight planning maybe days in advance until the flight is completed.
- Information content has to be displayed in easy to grasp, i.e. graphical form.
- Weather graphics shall make use of colour to highlight important phenomena.
- Information transfer technologies shall have a role to play, like the internet, which should deliver access to a pan-European portal of weather information. This shall be extended to include information for all areas of the world as far as it can be provided.
- Real-time advanced radar and satellite pictures with flight path added, continuously updated forecasts that have 3 hours or less between forecast times.
- Pilot-selectable, specialized weather information for special situations, i.e. tropical systems, high winds, volcanic eruptions, winter weather or fog.
- Playback capability for all information.
- Wireless devices shall support laptops, tablets, eFBs that pilots might use.

Thinking about how climate change will affect until 2050, it is inevitable to talk about the main uncertainties in climate projections: internal variability of the climate system that exists even in the absence of any external forcing; uncertainty in radiative forcing due to future emissions of greenhouse gases and aerosols; and model uncertainty.

Based on the EWENT project results using the six Regional Climate Model (RCM) simulations, the frequency of snowfall events (Figure 5.46) is projected to decrease 1-5 days in southern Europe, with changes in the frequency of snow days increasing progressively northward, to 10-20 days in Scandinavia compared to 1971-2000. The sign of change is consistent among all six RCMs, except in the Mediterranean and the western part of the continent. Contrary to the general decrease in snow days, the probability of extreme snowfall (> 10 cm) increases over large areas of Scandinavia and north-eastern Russia (1-5 days/year). This increase is partly due to the anticipated increase of total precipitation in the future but also due to warmer temperatures, since heavy snowfall tends to occur close to near-zero degrees Celsius. As shown in the upper limit maps, some models indicate a more robust increase in the frequency of 10 cm and especially 20 cm snowfall/day for several central and eastern European countries. The anticipated decrease in snowfall and frozen precipitation would have a positive impact on road, rail and air transportation reducing the cost of maintenance in many European countries; however in the Nordic countries, where heavy snowfall is already one of the most common disruption factors, it seems to become a more severe phenomenon [13].

Figure 5.46 - Multi-model mean, upper and lower limit of changes in annual snowfall days from 1971-2000 to 2041-2070 exceeding (A) 1 cm, (B) 10 cm and (C) 20 cm based on six RCM simulations [13]

Concerning warm days (mean temperature above 25°C), they will become (Figure 5.47) more prevalent by the 2050s. Scandinavia will experience 5 more warm days/year and Southern Europe 30-40 more days/year. In western and central parts of the continent, the projections suggest warm days will become more frequent by 20-30 days/year. This change implies that mid-latitude regions may experience as many days with heat waves by 2070 as the Mediterranean countries do in the present climate. As for the frequency and spatial variation of days above 43 °C, more countries will be affected than nowadays, with most of south and southeast Europe experiencing extreme heat waves, their number increasing by 5 days/year. Some of the climate models indicate an increase of 20 days/year for the Mediterranean countries [13].

The projected increase in the duration and intensity of hot days will have a negative impact on transportation and infrastructure during the summer months, especially in those countries which already experience high temperatures.

Figure 5.47 - Multi-model mean, upper and lower limit of changes in annual heat-spells days from 1971-2000 to 2041-2070 exceeding (A) 25 °C, (B) 32 °C and (C) 45 °C based on six RCM simulations [13]

Additionally, the simulated cold extremes (Figure 5.48) decline in occurrence substantially by 2070 over the whole continent, most strongly over Northern Europe. The decrease in the frequency of frost days (0 °C) varies between 20-30 days/year in Northern Europe and decreases gradually towards Southern Europe, with a decrease of 1-5 days/year. Most of the six models agree on the amplitude of change over land. This implies that Finland, Sweden and Norway are likely to experience as many frost days in the 2050s as some mid-latitude countries (such as the Baltic countries, Poland and Ukraine) do in the current climate [13].

Figure 5.48 - Multi-model mean, upper and lower limit of changes in annual cold-spell days from 1971-2000 to 2041-2070 exceeding (A) 0 °C, (B) -7 °C and (C) -20 °C based on six RCM simulations [13]

Concerning other meteorological hazards such as precipitation extremes, wind extremes or blizzards, they are more difficult to assess due to the large variation in the results among the models. For example, precipitation extremes are expected to increase by 1-5 days/year over Europe except the Mediterranean, where no significant change or a sporadic decrease is expected. On the other hand, wind extremes are expected to decrease over the Atlantic and Mediterranean Sea but a slight decrease or no significant change in either direction is expected over the continent.

In conclusion, future systems related to weather forecasts as radars and other systems related to weather information streaming as data link should be developed considering future meteorological conditions, which it is expected to be quite different than current conditions.

Possible or Predictable Breakthroughs

The following breakthroughs could be expected:

- Development of new technologies concerning radars throughput.
- Improved connectivity air-ground and air-air allowing predictive decision-making.
- More complete and more accurate forecasts due to new technologies.
- Improved meteorological predictive models.
- Integration of outputs from meteorological models and cockpit and ground radars.

Identification of Gaps

Looking at the expected development for aviation, it can be stated that the influence of weather on aviation will increase in the future. The reason here is not primarily the climate change, but the prognosis for growth in worldwide air traffic.

The growth of air traffic will lead to the saturation of the entire air traffic network, containing both airports and airspace. Airports will operate near their capacity limit and hence they will be highly sensitive to disturbances caused by weather related phenomena, just the same case as airspace. If any disturbance occurs, it could drive into the generation of severe delays which would spread throughout the entire air traffic network affecting the different stakeholders. In order to make the air traffic network resilience to disturbances and hence improve its throughput, research must be focused on developing the current atmospheric models, so that it would help to produce more accurate forecasts, both short and long-term.

Moreover, the effects of climate change for air traffic can be hardly foreseen, as there are many overlapping effects, which can offset or accumulate. For example, a reduced number of fog situations would lead to avoidance of higher separation and finally in a higher capacity. On the other hand, an increased number of thunderstorms would result in more temporary closure of airspace or airport and finally in a lower capacity. In this manner, as it is likely that climate change forecasts are not enough accurate, stakeholders and governments should focus on the new technology that will allow air traffic operators to handle any change relative to today's situation.

Considering the trend of increasing regionalization and globalization in response to user's needs for globally harmonized and seamless services, it is recognized the need for the meteorological community to respond to the associated shift in modes of service delivery. These must include the development of new business models, utilization of the latest information technologies and scientific research, harnessing new and innovative methods of service delivery and being able to leverage a higher level of regional and international cooperation to bridge existing and future gaps.

One of the key gaps that should be considered is the cooperation between stakeholders, which must be improved in order to fulfil the goals set for the future. Currently, several projects related to that are being carried out. It is the case of the Aircraft Met Data Relay (AMDAR) which consists in collecting, processing, formatting and transmitting meteorological data to ground stations via satellite or radio links. This meteorological data is collected using existing aircraft on-board sensors, computers and communications systems.

The World Meteorological Organization (WMO) global AMDAR system (Figure 5.49) now (May 2017) produces over 700,000 high-quality observations per day of air temperature and wind speed and direction, together with the required positional and temporal information and with an increasing number of humidity and turbulence measurements being made. The data collected is used for a range of meteorological applications, including, public weather forecasting, climate monitoring and prediction, early warning systems for weather hazards and, importantly, weather monitoring and prediction in support of the aviation industry [6].

Figure 5.49 - AMDAR overview [6]

In this context in which a global and interrelated network is the main goal, issues may arise concerning the physical management of the information (including meteorological information) as a system-wide information management (SWIM) will underpin the future ATM system. This will require appropriate governance arrangements to be developed, including data management policies for both the providers and consumers of the information within SWIM.

Furthermore, understanding the requirements for the integration of the meteorological information into the ATM decision-making processes in support of trajectory-based operation (TBO) will be crucial. Entering into an increasingly automated decision-making environment will require respective automation of the MET information generation and sharing and will require a close dialogue with users. One of the problems related to a highly-automated, data-rich digital environment that could show up is that National Meteorological Services (NMHSs) may lose contact with the end-users, e.g. pilots, relative to the situation today. Similarly, with quality a global concern, feedback from the users may be lost. As a consequence, mechanisms to ensure that effective interfaces and interactions between provider and consumer can be sustained will need to be studied [7].

Therefore, if technical and procedural developments are not carried out properly, it could turn into a difficult situation in order to reach the proposed objectives and also in order to maintain the high standards of safety and quality in air travel.

KEY TOPIC T5.2 - INTEGRATION OF UNMANNED AIRCRAFT IN MANNED AIRSPACE

Goal 16 was defined in Flightpath 2050 as “The European air transport system operates seamlessly through interoperable and networked systems allowing manned and unmanned air vehicles to safely operate in the same airspace”.

Comparing both Flightpath 2050 and SRIA goals it can be realized that the goal has been set in the safety framework which makes sense because, although Unmanned Aircraft System (UAS) represent an infinite world with multiple applications still to be explored, they are also coming up strongly as a new risk area. Contextualizing, Unmanned Aircraft System (UAS), of which the Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) is the airborne component, comprise two fundamental types [17]:

- Remotely-Piloted Aircraft Systems (RPAS), a class of UAS which has a 'pilot' operating the Remotely-Piloted Aircraft (RPA) from a Ground-Control Station (GCS).
- UAS with no remote pilot, or autonomous air vehicles.

These Unmanned Aerial Vehicles constitute a new threat in the European airspace as demonstrated by the occurrence of several incidents involving conventional aircraft and UAVs. As example, in the 2016 Annual Safety Report (Figure 5.50) issued by EUROCONTROL [18], which relies on data received from the Member States, the highest number of reports amounts to over 40 events in 2015; hence, in order to reduce the number of incidents related to RPAS, it is necessary to contribute to the seamless accommodation and integration of RPAS into the European ATM.

Figure 5.50 - RPAS related occurrences in 2015 [18]

Benchmarks

RPAS have been instrumental in providing new capabilities for European defence and have demonstrated significant growth as a consumer leisure product. At the same time, they are offering public safety and security authorities' new capabilities much in the same way they have for the military and are transforming commercial businesses. A core component to these

new capabilities and transformations is the collection of data from strategic vantage points that have been either inaccessible or too expensive to be economically viable today. This core area of data processing is being extended to include the efficient transport of urgently needed goods within a local community or industrial site with longer term aspirations to transform large commercial vehicles for both cargo transport and also, someday, passenger transport [17].

Related to the stated above, Europe is not alone in this race: United States (US) and China are two key States that are significantly investing into technology and innovative businesses that currently exceed the level of total European investments. In particular, the US is the leader in producing defence drone systems – followed by Israel – and China not only is the leader in producing leisure units that tend to be more and more used for professional purposes but is also becoming the leading exporter of high-end armed military drones that face US export restrictions. Therefore, Europe should focus on developing the use of drones in as many sectors as possible since UAS will create significant benefits that should be pursued in the following years.

In addition, it is expected that commercial and professional users demand drones in both rural and urban settings. Examples of some of the most influential missions, in terms of the potential number of drones and economic impact, include the following [17]:

- Agriculture sector where over 100000 drones are forecasted to enable precision agriculture to help drive increased levels of productivity that are required.
- Energy sector where close to 10000 drones limit risk of personnel and infrastructure by performing preventative maintenance inspections.
- Public safety and security where a forecasted fleet of approximately 50000 drones would provide authorities like police and fire forces the means to more efficiently and effectively locate endangered citizens and assess hazards as they carry out civil protection and humanitarian missions.
- Delivery purposes where there is potential for a fleet of nearly 100000 drones to provide society with some kind of urgent service capabilities, such as transporting emergency medical supplies, and “premium” deliveries. This is the case of different companies such as Amazon or Google. Related to this, many studies are currently carrying out: as example, in 2016 Airbus signed a contract with the Civil Aviation Authority of Singapore (CAAS) allowing them to test an UAV parcel delivery service on the campus of the National University of Singapore (NUS) under its project “Skyways”. This project (Figure 5.51) aims to provide efficient delivery of small packages using UAVs.

Figure 5.51- "Skyways" project developed by Airbus

In this case, the UAV is a fully autonomous octocopter that carries air transport containers located on its underside and flies an equally fully automated route called "aerial corridors" landing on a designated landing pad where it is automatically unloaded and then the customer receives a delivery notification on their smartphone saying their parcel is ready for picking up at the parcel station.

Projects like "Skyways" are interesting because they could help to evolve the regulatory framework for self-piloted aircraft systems operations if the outcomes demonstrate that "Skyways" and associated infrastructure can safely operate over the National University of Singapore.

Figure 5.52 - Applications by region based on media attention [17]

Further actions taken at the European Union level will need to occur rapidly given the pace of global development in drones, especially as the US and China are already (Figure 5.52) the leaders in different forms of production and investing more heavily than the European Union. One example of this is the UAS Traffic Management (UTM) system that is currently being developed by NASA in the US. This system has been described properly in Benchmarks for Goal 4.

Much of what still needs to be done include technology (detect and avoid, Datacom), air traffic management, security & cyber reliance along with the availability of authorized & safe testing environments. As a main finding of the study and based on the expectations of the market to unlock demand and global competitiveness, these improvements need to be completed within a window of opportunity limited to the next 5-10 years. Completion within such a time span requires that an ecosystem is created at European Union level around both technology and regulation to ensure a proper "home" for drones that brings all key public and private stakeholders together [17].

Regarding research and development, European Union funding levels need to be re-assessed to stimulate this emerging marketplace and establish a European level ecosystem. Based on expectations of the market, an estimated total of at least EUR 200 million in additional R&D over the next 5-10 years is required to address remaining gaps related to Very Low Level (VLL) activities that will represent the majority of future drone operations. Required additional investments should be supported by a mix of both public and private stakeholders reinforcing

the importance of a European level ecosystem for R&D. This same mix of stakeholders will also be needed to ensure fast implementation of comprehensive regulation. Speed will be essential for Europe to obtain a global leadership position, especially as the value in services remains in the early stages of development in all markets. It is therefore also critical that R&D coordination at European Union level results in leveraging and bringing together numerous initiatives that are presently fragmented across Member States and industry stakeholders [17].

One of the keys in this subject is the technology related to air traffic management in such a way that the demand of UAVs on all areas of airspace highlights the critical nature of air traffic management. UAVs will create new forms of traffic, especially (Figure 5.53) at very low levels of airspace with high demand in densely populated areas where risk levels will increase. As a result, appropriate new and adapted procedures along with the development of technology related to the management of airspace are a "must-have" for safely accommodate the growth of UAVs. Besides, the absence of a pilot on board the aircraft raises the question of how to detect and avoid other traffic, or objects, and how to handle dangerous situations. Airborne collision avoidance systems can protect unmanned aircraft from damage, but they are not designed to deal with denser traffic. This is comparable to the situation with road traffic: As long as there are just a few vehicles on the road, the driver is able to control the situation and avoid other vehicles or obstacles; but the denser traffic becomes, the more traffic control in the form of, for example, traffic lights is needed [19].

Figure 5.53 - UAVs operations by altitudes [19]

Related to that, conventional air traffic management cannot be applied to unmanned aircraft. It relies on voice communication between air traffic controllers and pilots, and on radar detection. Larger drones may be equipped with voice recognition/speech synthesis radio and have a significantly larger radar cross-section. However, many drones are too small, and operate too close to the ground, for radar to be of any use. Current airspace management and air traffic flow management systems are not predicted to have the capabilities to handle the type of operations relevant to drones. In addition, the forecasted traffic density of drones is far beyond the capabilities of current air traffic management systems, which were never designed to handle large amounts of dense heterogeneous traffic with widely varying performance characteristics [19].

In this context, Member States of the European Union should be at the forefront of this matter, developing the UTM system that allow UAVs to fly joining manned aircraft and also implementing the regulatory framework regarding the integration of UAS into a busy airspace as it is European airspace.

Besides, it is important to set the differences between the UTM concept and the UTM system [19]:

- On the one hand, the UTM concept is a complex system in which several stakeholders contribute to ensure the required safety level of UAS operations, i.e. is a system of stakeholders and technical systems collaborating in certain interactions and according to certain regulations, to maintain safe separation of unmanned aircraft, between themselves and from ATM users, at very low level, and to provide an efficient and orderly flow of traffic.
- On the other hand, a UTM system is a concrete technical implementation comprising software, the necessary infrastructure for running the software and the drones themselves, all contributing to the achievement of UTM. This UTM system should cover the needs of both RPAS and autonomous unmanned aircraft and also consider all sort of UAS operations: VLOS (Visual Line of Sight), EVLOS (Extended Visual Line Of Sight) and BVLOS (Beyond Visual Line Of Sight).

As it can be noticed, the most likely stakeholders of an UTM system could be composed of national aviation authorities, supranational institutions, drone pilots, operators, drone owners, conventional aviation pilots, conventional ground, rail or sea traffic, law enforcements, emergency services, drone manufacturers or UTM service providers. This cluster of stakeholder's evidences that the UTM domain will have to deal with different and heterogeneous organizations that should address this issue as a solid and collaborative group.

Figure 5.54 - Example of an UTM system [19]

Related to the Figure 5.54, each UTM system can be modelled as a set of functional blocks in mutual interaction in order to accomplish the system mission. This proposal is a logical breakdown not aimed at constraining possible deployments, which may vary in the physical architecture according to the specific deployment case. The breakdown is rather aimed at highlighting important information exchanges, inputs for service, and data protocol definitions [19].

Another possible breakdown is the one proposed by NASA, which shows (Figure 5.55) how a UTM system will be deployed in the United States and which has been described in Goal 4.

Figure 5.55 - NASA UTM system [19]

Reference State in 2010

Drones have been used since long time ago, as demonstrate the first prototypes which date from XIX century. These first steps of the UAVs addressed to develop them for military and security issues during the XX century, in such a way that they were used in different wars such as the Second World War or the Cold War.

However, since not so long ago -about 20 years ago- governments and private stakeholders started to try to extend their range of action to a civilian application. Thus, stakeholders had to consider the new concepts for a civilian application: whilst the ultimate goal in military application is completion of mission, the ultimate goal in civilian application is safety. That means that in military application aircraft could crash but only after mission is completed, nevertheless in civilian application aircraft could never crash. Consequently, a technology development was needed for UAVs civilian application due to different specifications meant different systems.

Focusing on the European Union, several projects about UAVs were carried out during the first years of the XXI century within the Fifth Framework Programme. This Fifth Framework Programme set out the priorities for the European Union's research, technological development and demonstration (RTD) activities for the period 1998-2002.

Some of these projects are explained below [20]:

- **UAV-NET:** this project addressed a Thematic Network on the subject of advancing the utilization of UAVs into the civilian commercial sphere UAVs have proven their capability within the military fields. The many civilian applications addressed in this project were environmental monitoring, communications relays, law enforcement surveillance, earth observation, etc. where the benefits of UAVs were only beginning

to be understood. The Thematic Network served as a forum for information exchange, for setting new policies and for launching activities in critical technology research and technology platform validation studies at the next stage.

- **CAPECON:** this project (Figure 5.56) aimed to advance the utilization of safe and low cost Unmanned Air Vehicles (UAVs) in the civilian commercial sphere. CAPECON surveyed in-depth applications of potential users and produced safety and cost assessments. It also compared different aerodynamic configurations and it was defined possible civil UAV configuration ready for engineering development. This project was a research synthesis of critical technologies, configuration design, simulation and cost appraisal methods, aimed at the design and production of safe and commercially viable, civilian UAVs. The project also focused on configurations and technologies suited to High and Medium Altitude Long Endurance (HALE and MALE) missions and also to Rotary UAVs. At that moment, the commercial potential for the civilian use of UAVs was largely untapped; hence CAPECON aimed to enable the EU to gain a leading role in this emerging technology.

Figure 5.56 - UAVs studied in CAPECON Project

- **USICO:** the main goals of this project (Figure 5.57) was to improve operational capability and safety of UAVs. Related to that, the scope of work gathered the following issues:
 - Recommendations for UAV system airworthiness certification procedures and standards.
 - Recommendations for UAV operations regulations.
 - Technology for see and avoid.
 - Proposals for research into image recognition and sensors and adapted ADS-B technology.

- Flight simulation of UAV ATC/ATM process. For example, USICO simulated a civil UAV safely flight in Frankfurt airspace using the concepts developed by the USICO project.

Figure 5.57 - USICO simulation in Frankfurt airspace

Progress Up-to-Now

During the last decade the disruptive concepts related to UAVs systems and manufacturing were developed in such a way that the civil use of UAVs has sharply increased. Nowadays, besides the different uses of UAVs such as public safety, deliveries, surveillance, weather monitoring, and agriculture and so on, it is usual to know someone who owns a drone for leisure. As a result, the number of drones within European Union has multiplied over the last 2 years.

These new users of airspace are generating new conflicts which have shown up during the last few years. Concerning that, EASA analyse in its Annual Safety Reviews the occurrences related to UAS in the European airspace and, in the 2017 Annual Safety Review [21], the outcomes show that most of the occurrences are related to either airspace infringements that occasionally lead to a near collision with an aircraft or issues with controlling the RPAS's flight path.

In this manner, the analysis of UAS occurrences in the European Central Repository (ECR) identified 606 occurrences (Figure 5.58) of all severity levels for the last 5 years, of which 37 had been classified as accidents, and fortunately none of them involved fatalities. The collection of data on UAS occurrences is still in its infancy and there is still a lot of work to be done to ensure the correct application of taxonomy terminology related to UAS. This work should be done due to the fact that the increase in the number of non-fatal accidents and serious incidents demonstrate the rapid development of drone operations [21].

	Fatal Accidents	Non-Fatal Accidents	Serious Incidents
2011-2015 average	0	2.6	0.3
2016	0	15	7
% difference	=	470% ↑	2230% ↑

	Fatalities	Serious Injuries
2011-2015 average	0	0
2016	0	0

Figure 5.58 - Key statistics about UAS accidents and serious incidents from ECR occurrence database [21]

The Figure 5.59 shows the development of reported UAS occurrences for the last 5 years. These occurrences, observations and sightings come mostly from pilots flying commercial aircraft owing to it is rare that UAS pilots report the occurrences that they encounter concerning UAS operations. As can be noticed from the Figure 5.58, the difference in terms of percentage between both periods of time is extremely high. Moreover, this yearly growth of occurrences can also be perceived in the following figure 5.59 in which data from European Central Repository and additional data reported to EASA from several European operators have been used.

Figure 5.59 - UAS reported occurrences per year 2012-2016 [21]

Fortunately, most of these occurrences have not been classified as accidents as can be seen in the following Figure 5.60. However, a further effort is necessary in order to decrease the large number of incidents and accidents reported during the last few years.

Figure 5.60 - UAS accidents and other occurrences during 2012-2016 [21]

An additional study has been carried out based on the available data containing altitude information. It can be noticed in the following Figure 5.61 that when the drones are spotted the manned aircraft is most often in the area from 0-6000 feet above the ground and the distance from the aircraft to the drone is from 0-1000 feet. This reflects the main range of drones, which can reach different altitudes but most often they usually operate in low-altitude airspace, hence a regulatory framework that take into account an environment where both unmanned and manned aircraft coexist should be implemented.

Figure 5.61 - Aircraft altitude vs distance from drone at the time of detection 2010-2016 [21]

Regarding the most severe incidents reported during the last years, three key risk areas have been set [21]:

- The first one is the aircraft upset: most of the accidents are related to drone pilots losing control of the drone as demonstrate the fact that 50% of the RPAS accidents are related to such incidents. These incidents usually result in a damage and most often a destruction of the aircraft.

- The second one is the airborne collision: even though there are very few occurrences where actual collisions between a drone and a manned aircraft happen, the risk is considered to be substantial and, with a steady exponential increase of unmanned aircraft of all sizes and shapes, it is vital to monitor this area closely and to work on solutions that prevent actual collisions.
- The third one is the obstacle collision in flight: drones used in aerial work operations and in space constrained areas are susceptible to higher collision risk than manned aircraft.

Therefore, it is evident that further regulations should be developed and implemented as soon as possible in the European Union. These regulation frameworks should regard the control of the UAS flight path, use of automation and also regard airspace infringement and airborne separation, which is a hard task due to the fact that nowadays smaller drones do not have transponders on board.

Predictions Up-to-2025

Today's evolution of UAVs framework depends on technology, ATM, regulations and societal acceptance. The increase of automation up to potential of robotics in the sky is not brand new, however more robust technology is still required before many applications are commercially viable and accepted. Additionally, regulation and societal concerns related to privacy and safety remain constraints for some applications already feasible from a technical perspective.

In terms of regulation, a new framework around the operations of drones should be proposed by the European Union as a common basis to harmonize regulation across Europe and enable more applications. Related to that, European Member States have already been at the forefront of regulation with over 15 Member States holding legislation related to drones. Included in this legislation are initial permissions for beyond visual line of sight (BVLOS) drone operations that are critical for many of these operations to be economically viable opportunities. Examples of such BVLOS permissions include Spain allowing BVLOS for drones under 2 kg and France allowing these flights for drones under 2 kg with no lateral limitation and additionally for drones under 25 kg that operate within 1 kilometre (km) of the remote pilot. The above examples begin to indicate the remaining opportunity for harmonization across States in order to unlock future potential [15].

Even though EU countries have been at the forefront of legislation, regulation still limits the extent to which drones can operate on their own and the ease of to which operations can expand across countries using the same drones and certifications. Critical parts of the evolving regulation will be the extent to which drones can be operated BVLOS, in populated areas or/and without a dedicated pilot per each drone (i.e. allowing a single pilot to operate or monitor more than one drone at the same time).

Furthermore, societal worries on privacy and accidents create an additional barrier that drones must overcome in order for regulators to allow flights in populated areas. These concerns over safety are magnified by the fact that drones are bringing aviation capabilities to a group of new users. The inexperience of these users in aviation framework increases the number of issues that regulators must consider.

Traffic management solutions associated to required drone technologies (e.g. detect and avoid, datalink, geofencing) are key enablers for safety, and it is essential that they demonstrate together safety performance in-line with the high standards of the aviation industry. The ability to address how drones will be safely integrated into European airspace and also how cybersecurity threats will be mitigated, will be factors in determining the pace at which the industry will grow over the coming years.

Additional technology advancements will also be important to increase the value that drones generate for end users. Big Data analytics related to services such as industrial preventative maintenance, precision agriculture and research purposes are still in their early phases of development and must continue to evolve for drone's applications to successfully transform businesses and processes. Components and systems related to engines, propulsion and batteries will be needed to achieve required levels of reliability and durability performance that commercial users demand. High-precision navigation, like that in development as part of the EU's Galileo and EGNOS satellite navigation systems, could also be considered for drones to improve reliability and support their integration in non-segregated airspace [15].

The progression of regulation, ATM procedures, technology and societal acceptance will likely continue to take shape rapidly, both in Europe and in other global markets. It is therefore necessary that Europe helps to develop the stated above through facilitating to set the regulatory framework and also investing in the projects carry out by the stakeholders.

Evolutionary Progress Up-to-2050

The role of drones is likely to expand still for many years, thus driving the need to understand mission types that are being established today and also those yet to come. Different sectors could illustrate the opportunity that drones have to transform how businesses operate, to increase Europe's global competitiveness, to provide new jobs and to deliver both economic and environmental benefits. These sectors, shown together with some of societal benefits that drones may generate within each, are the following [15]:

- **Agriculture:** Drones could help to enable precision agriculture that will be critical to meet productivity needs for Europe and support greener farmer practices that are a focus of the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) of 2020.
- **Energy:** Drones may reduce a variety of risks including to personnel performing hazardous tasks, to the environment by properly maintaining assets and to the infrastructure overall by limiting the amount of downtime to Europe that already is a heavy importer of resources and pays higher energy prices than other regions.
- **Public safety and security:** Drones could be used by a variety of authorities to better assess and monitor hazardous situations, complete search and rescue missions, gather evidence for investigations and detect other crises.
- **E-commerce and delivery:** Urgent packages, including medical supplies, could be completed in a fraction of the time and online retailers could benefit from increased accessibility in both urban and remote areas.

- **Mobility and transport:** The infrastructure of today, i.e., railways, may be monitored and kept secure and future forms of passenger aircraft could someday operate safely without the requirement of on-board pilots.

These many applications will lead (Figure 5.62) to a sharply increase of the number of drones in the following decades as forecasts show. Overall, in terms of order of magnitude, military defence assets are expected to increase from high hundreds to multiple thousands, leisure units from close to 1 million to approximately 7 million and, finally, government and commercial units from multiple thousands to hundreds of thousands. Leisure unit growth is expected to mature in the near term with defence and the government and commercial growth will continue out through 2050. These numbers can be seen in the following Figure.

Figure 5.62 - Total fleet size forecast (current through 2050) [15]

As can be seen, the largest increase will correspond to leisure drones, which will operate at very low levels of the airspace. It is expected a continued annual unit growth for another 3 years that would increase the total from just over 1 million units sold to nearly 7 million (with annual sales exceeding a million units). The recent history of action-based cameras, led by GoPro, provides a comparable case to highlight these expectations, especially given filming and imaging are a leading driver of consumer usage. GoPro is expected to reach maturity of its annual unit sales this year after a period of 9 years of growth, of which the first 6 were a near identical match to drones (see the following Figure 5.63). After 2-5 more years of annual sales growth in drones, the total consumer base should remain relatively stable for a significant period.

Figure 5.63 - Comparison of growth in leisure drones to GoPro action cameras [15]

Talking about the demand forecast classified by mission type, the use of drones for local surveying that is mostly within visual line of sight (VLOS) has the potential to increase rapidly as result of energy infrastructure inspections (solar farms, wind turbines, power plants, dams, refineries, oil platforms), public safety and security (police and fire response using in-vehicle units), mining and construction (both quarries and industrial construction sites with the potential for residential surveying in future), insurance (property inspections) and media (new coverage) among other. Together there is estimated potential for over 100.000 drones by 2035 and 2050. These drones have a relatively low regulation hurdle to overcome as many of these operations can be performed within visual line of sight. However, as exemplified by police and fire missions, these drones will need to be able to fly in densely populated areas to reach this forecasted potential.

Beyond visual line of sight capabilities yield even greater potential. For mapping and surveying alone, 180.000 drones are estimated for 2035 with fixed wing drones being the primary operating type. This includes agriculture remote sensing of crops and livestock, inspection of power line, pipeline, and railway networks that currently require expensive helicopters. In the future they could be used by public authorities to operate drones directly from each station and could complement or replace VLOS units carried in vehicles. Media drones used to cover traffic conditions or sporting events such as cycling are also opportunities along with use at larger construction and mining sites and for conducting new forms of research by universities and other institutes.

The majority of light load drone missions are also expected to operate beyond visual line of sight with 90.000 drones forecasted by 2035 mostly for delivery purposes and flying at low altitudes. This includes emergency medical deliveries, lightweight industrial deliveries (e.g., from a port to a vessel or transfer of tools across a large industrial construction site) and completing traditional forms of delivering parcels and couriers to businesses and consumers.

Agriculture chemical spraying and seeding represents a smaller portion, approximately 25.000, of the estimate for light load drones flying at these low altitudes.

More complex certified drones are expected primarily in public safety and security and mobility sectors. Drones with longer endurances and flying well above 150 meters are expected for border security, maritime surveillance and other environment assessments (e.g., forestry and national park surveillance). As a result, they will likely be acquired by national and regional authorities and represent a low volume (a fleet size close to 100 units in total which could reach a few hundred over the time). These capabilities are likely to be in the form of technology transferred from the military.

Complex certified drones also include remotely piloted or highly automated aviation capabilities for today's aircraft fleet, including rotorcrafts and commercial airlines. As stated above, public acceptance will be essential along with ensuring robustness of the technology which is likely to come from the military. A gradual shift towards systems with no pilot on board over multiple decades is expected to occur according to the evolution of the society with regards to automation. Therefore estimates (Figure 5.64) are inclusive of optionally piloted systems. Approximately 10.000 units are estimated in 2050 on the basis of the market starting first for cargo aircraft sometime after 2030 and then for human transport at earliest 2035, representing a lag of at least 10 years after the launch of fully autonomous self-driving vehicles anticipated for 2025 [15].

Figure 5.64 - Demand outlook by type of mission [15]

The potential for drones across many different settings in the years to come has considerable implications for airspace management. Future forms of optionally piloted and unmanned aircraft for mobility purposes are estimated to represent approximately 20% of the future fleet meaning that air traffic management would need to account for millions of such flights in controlled airspace by 2050. The safe integration of these drones in ATM will also need to

include ground operations particularly in airports where automated taxiing capabilities are required.

Possible or Predictable Breakthroughs

Enabling successful safe operations beyond visual line of sight are the core of commercial and government market potential and this will require the availability of a variety of technologies. Further, many of these technologies will require multiple forms to account for the various types of missions being performed at very low levels and also in controlled and uncontrolled airspace (i.e., different development to prevent a collision with a static building than a collision with a fast travelling manned aircraft). Several of these technologies are suggested to require European level support to effectively bring them to market in context of the global marketplace. This set of technologies is further detailed below individually [15]:

- **Detect and avoid** (D&A) capabilities are seen as a key enabler for drone operations in all classes airspace and are expected to have a positive impact on safety and social acceptance. This technology depends on the flight rules: in IFR the D&A system performs the collision avoidance function against cooperative and non-cooperative traffic, whilst in VFR/VLL drones will need to be able to detect and avoid cooperative and non-cooperative traffic and multiple types of obstacles (power lines, buildings, trees, birds etc.). Although some investments to develop solutions supporting the safe integration of drones in non-segregated airspace have been made, it still requires large investments to bring performances to the required level. Lower levels of investment in detect and avoid for very low level operating drones are also impacted by the remaining gap of a clear vision on the future concepts of operations and regulatory framework, making it risky to invest and difficult to align players towards industry standards and hence the development of appropriate solutions.
- **Datacom and spectrum** issues are critical to enable BVLOS and long endurance surveying missions to happen in safe conditions. Appropriate datalinks are necessary for command and control (C2) as well as potentially for communication with air traffic control (ATC) or future forms of VLL drone management. The biggest challenges when it comes to datalinks are the identification, allocation and protection of the necessary spectrum. Also to ensure that safety is not compromised by interruption of links, or that there are redundant or alternate links.
- **Security and cyber resilience** is a priority area of development to mitigate the risk that drones could be subjected to malicious or accidental takeovers of datalinks leading to accidents, theft or deliberate use of the aircraft to damage infrastructure or hurt civilians. Those issues could have a severe negative impact on public acceptance. Private initiatives are exploring potential solutions such as digital identification, but clear concepts of operations, requirements and standards are needed to drive research into a more advanced and coordinated phase.
- **Human factors and training** will need additional R&D efforts to ensure that the situation awareness for pilots of drones matches that of pilots in cockpits. Additionally, there will be a requirement to manage the transition from remotely piloted drones to more automated drones that are only monitored. In order to achieve those goals, effective solutions

regarding contingency, failure management etc. will need to be put in place. Harmonization of the operator's environment is likely to lead to more appropriate training and higher safety. Training and qualification is an underlying topic that requires immediate action from the EU to provision new, well trained pilots. Achieving EU-wide accepted pilot licenses would accelerate the creation of drone service companies.

- **Validation and demonstration** will be important to increase public acceptance of drone operations and will support the regulatory work. Although some validation exercises are performed at national level, broader authorized and safe testing environments to perform integrated demonstrations involving different systems (manned and unmanned operating simultaneously) will be needed. In addition to that, EU level coordination on the allowance to let some pioneer applications operate will be of high importance. Indeed, pioneer applications that would be allowed under a risk-based logic would enable the collection of data and observations to further refine concepts of operations and regulation while increasing public acceptance.
- **Air traffic management (ATM)** is a critical area that requires further research and development. All previously mentioned R&D topics depend on how ATM will integrate drones in all classes of airspace. The basic principles of drone traffic management as defined by the concepts of operations will lead to precise requirements on which industry standards will be developed, thereby assuring a strong basis for future investments and partnerships across private industry players and public member states and stakeholders.

Identification of Gaps

Leisure drones, while increasing dramatically in number, are still on average only flown for a few hours annually. Beyond visual line of sight (BVLOS) operations, including above the very low level (VLL), may impact all classes of airspace and have a much greater impact on the airspace than leisure drones given they will likely fly multiple hours a day. This is expected to be especially true in the long term for delivery and public safety & security drones operating in urban environments.

Unmanned aircraft, including station-operated beyond visual line of sight drones, will need to safely operate alongside manned aviation and delivery drones in dynamically changing locations. In total, all operations that are primarily performed at very low levels are estimated to represent the majority of flight time to be accounted for and thus will require additional technology to support safe operations.

In order to maintain high levels of safety similar to manned aviation, multiple technology areas should be taken into account, which are highly aligned to these same categories as detect & avoid, datacom & spectrum, human factors, security & cyber resilience and validation & demonstration are all included and represent direct synergies with ATM.

The issue is that in the lower levels of airspace, i.e. uncontrolled airspace and very low-level airspace, the road to safe integration of drones is even more challenging and currently less addressed than in controlled airspace. Drones in those types of airspace will need to be able to cope with non-cooperative air traffic, multiple sorts of obstacles and aircraft operating under visual flight rules (VFR). The safe integration of unmanned aviation at those lower levels

is likely to require a new drone management system and approach (i.e. unmanned aircraft traffic management (UTM)). The exact shape of this drone management system is yet to be defined and will likely require EU level coordination and harmonization of all stakeholders.

Furthermore, European Union support is necessary to create a competitive drone market able to improve connectivity, growth and jobs just as has been done in EU aviation. Related to that, boosting innovation and regulation in a manner that matches or outpaces that of the global drone marketplace needs harmonization and coordination. The numerous initiatives on drones remain fragmented across industry participants and Member States such that it is important that increased coordination and pooling is urgently put in place. Facilitating cooperation and public private co-developments is a role which has to be orchestrated at the EU level and it will be critical to develop an ecosystem that welcomes the full range of relevant public and private stakeholders.

Overall, from a technological standpoint, most developments need to occur over the next 5 to 10 years. The improvement of security & cyber resilience as well as improved datacom & spectrum and a deeper understanding of human factors are key R&D areas that will reinforce safety and hence public acceptance of drones. On top of that, privacy and security as well as regulation awareness to attain social acceptance should be addressed. The next five years however will be crucial to unlock a majority of the market potential while assuring that Europe remains globally competitive. If Europe has difficulty allowing for technically mature missions at an efficient pace, capabilities will be more likely to develop abroad and export their expertise to Europe at a later stage thereby limiting economic potential locally. Success during these next 5 years can only occur with immediate actions and support at an EU level to the required drive investment and regulatory support [8].

KEY TOPIC T5.3 – PASSENGER AND LUGGAGE SCREENING AT AEROPORTS

Scope of the Goal

Comprehensive and unobtrusive security measures		
Goal 17: Efficient boarding and safety measures allow seamless security for global travel with minimum passenger and cargo impact. Passengers and cargo pass through security controls without intrusion		
Comparison with 2017 SRIA document	Why	Lacks
Coherent	Both the SRIA document and the report mark that security must be addressed continuously during operations to ensure the safety of staff and passengers and continuity of service. This must be achieved while maintaining system safety as well as performance, with acceptable levels of capacity and delay.	Security must be supported by intelligence that provides the information necessary to develop a comprehensive and detailed catalogue of threats and system vulnerabilities. Tools such as a security radar or a horizon scanning will be needed to automate detection of aviation incidents, gathering of associated information, and forensic analysis

Table 5.4 – ACARE/SRIA security targets

Benchmarks

Today's security measures as passenger and baggage security screening has as a consequence delays and queues, which are the most frequent sources of traveller dissatisfaction. Therefore, the ACARE goal for the future is to achieve the minimum of delay, intrusion and disruption in the implementation of safety measures, through the use of the most appropriate equipment and airport architectures.

One of the current initiatives which has as an objective to improve the passenger experience and to strengthen security is the project called Smart Security, a joint initiative of the International Air Transport Association (IATA) and Airports Council International (ACI). This project defines a future where passengers proceed through security checkpoints with minimal inconvenience, where security resources are allocated based on risk, and where airport facilities are optimized. This will be achieved through the implementation of new technologies and processes that will result in the following benefits:

- Security improvement.
- Better passenger experience.
- Operational efficiency improvement.

New technologies

Conventional X-ray scanners and metal detectors are the standard security methods used nowadays but they imply delays and troubles for passengers. Advanced screening technologies (Figure 5.65) will allow for effective threat detection while reducing the burden for passengers. Some solutions proposed to improve security measures are the following ones:

- Passenger screening: security scanners which are increasingly being adopted by airports can improved security and passenger experience outcomes, since they have the capacity to detect concealed items on the body regardless of the substance and the ability to facilitate a targeted search. These security scanners together with automated decision support algorithms could help the security officers to carry out better and quicker inspections of passengers and, at the same time, respecting better their privacy.
- Cabin baggage screening: new technologies which are currently in development such as Dual/multi-view X-rays and Computed Tomography (CT) could help operators to examine in a more accurate way the cabin baggage. For example, Dual/multi-view X-rays assist provides images of multiple angles of the same bag while the CT capacities include the ability to produce 360-degree images from the bag, which will allow to have a better view of its content.
- Alternative measures: alternative screening methods could enhance the overall effectiveness of the security checkpoints, while at the same time support operational efficiency and an improved passenger experience. Some of these new alternative methods are the Explosive trace detection (ETD) or the Explosive detection dogs (EDD). On the one hand, ETD equipment can detect trace amounts of explosives on a person, their clothes or their belongings. This detection capabilities as well as their portability makes ETD a passenger friendly, especially because these devices allow a process less intrusive. On the other hand, Dogs can be used to detect passengers who may be

carrying or have recently been in contact with explosive materials. They offer several advantages such as a more operational flexibility than fixed screening equipment and, in addition, they are usually considered more unobtrusive than other security measures.

Figure 5.65 - Technologies for Comprehensive and unobtrusive security measures

New Procedures

Until now, most risk-based decisions regarding the checkpoint have focused on assessing the risk of a particular item but considering all passengers as equals. Therefore, the risk-based differentiation concept is introduced, which focuses its attention on “the person” in the assessment of threats, instead of focusing on the items risk. As a result, based on a reasoned process of selection, different people would be screened in different ways. For example, people who have been identified as low risk people will have a quicker screening process while people identified as high-risk people will have a slower screening process since additional measures will be applied to them.

Five examples ‘risk categories’ are illustrated in the diagram below (Figure 5.66), where the majority of passengers could be considered as ‘normal risk’. Some passengers will require enhanced search while a small proportion will not be allowed to fly or will be exempt from screening.

Figure 5.66 - Operational procedures for Comprehensive and unobtrusive security measures

In this way, passenger would undergo to some kind of “risk filter”, which would classify them into higher or lower risk passengers. Therefore, the higher risk passenger would be submitted to additional screening measures prior to travel. These filters could be based on population-based data (category of passengers or journey) or based on individual passenger data. Data collection can start prior to the booking of a trip for known travellers, through check-in and baggage acceptance right up to the screening process. Each touch point by the passenger provides an opportunity to collect additional data, which may be used in the analysis of risk. As the technology increases, new automatic screening methods could be used to detect behavioural anomalies and to collect data. This information could be digitally transferred to a security officer who will ensure that the passengers with a major risk are submit to additional security measures. Selection procedures such as these would not inhibit the passenger’s journey through the airport and the passenger would not be aware of them.

➤ Benefits

Taking into account that, on average, passengers spend 20 minutes waiting in line to get to the security screening checkpoint, this new technologies and procedures could significantly reduce these waiting times.

In addition, new technologies would allow to process about 360 passengers per hour while conventional procedures such as X-ray metal detectors can process about 150 passengers per hour.

Reference State in 2010

The attempted sabotage liquid explosives of Northwest Airlines Flight 253 on 25th December 2009 and the thwarted plot to sabotage two cargo aircraft in October 2010 with improvised explosive devices concealed in freight shipments at airports in the United Arab Emirates and the United Kingdom lead to relevant ICAO actions on 2010.

In 2010 ICAO finalized a new comprehensive strategy for enhancing aviation security worldwide (ICASS ICAO Comprehensive Aviation Security Strategy) and the 37th Session of the ICAO Assembly unanimously adopted the Declaration on Aviation Security in light of the continuing threat to civil aviation. Annex 17 to the Chicago Convention was updated and strengthened to reflect the mayor risk and concerns to aviation, particularly in relation to staff screening, security equipment capabilities, hazardous substances in liquids, aerosols and gels (LAGs), cyber threats and air cargo. In January 2010 ICAO Secretariat established a database on the secure Aviation Security (AVSEC) website in order to disseminate information on acts of unlawful interference (AUI) in an efficient and effective manner, instead of distributing these data by way of an annual print summary. Following the attempted sabotage on 25 December 2009, ICAO used the secure Aviation Security (AVSEC) Point of Contact (PoC) Network to communicate information and recommendations to participating States, numbering 99 members at the time.

Historically, airport security measures have focused on checkpoint screening using magnetometers to detect metallic weapons on passengers and X-ray systems to examine carry-on items. However, these measures result in wait times and queues, which are one of the main reasons of traveller dissatisfaction. These methods have changed little since they were first implemented but new initiatives are emerging with the purpose of improving screening effectiveness through the deployment of new technologies. The objective is to enhance and strengthen security measures in order to detect efficiently threats as the entry of dangerous items on commercial aircraft but allowing freedom of movement for passengers. To that purpose, there have been several advances in technology screening during recent years.

These advanced technology aims to achieve the following benefits:

- Enhancing detection devices capability;
- Improving efficiency in security checkpoints;
- Preserving passenger privacy and dignity.

With these objectives, several advanced passenger and baggage screening technology begun to be deployed in 2010, such as Advanced Technology (AT) X-ray, Bottled Liquid Scanners (BLS), Advanced Imaging Technology (AIT), Chemical Analysis Devices (CADs), and Explosive Trace Detectors (ETD). These technologies (Figure 5.67) allow to detect explosive threats and prohibited items on passengers and their baggage but preserving their privacy and dignity while increasing their safety.

Advanced Technology X-ray (AT): They are penetration X-ray based technologies that are used to screen carry-on luggage. They provide an enhanced view of a bag's contents through

improved image resolution. AT X-ray creates multiple views/angles, clearer and more detailed images of baggage than traditional single view X-ray.

Advanced Imaging Technology (AIT): AIT is a new imaging capability that will be used to inspect a passenger's body for concealed weapons (metal and non-metal), explosives, and other prohibited items. In addition, the AIT offers operators the opportunity to review anomalies on an individual, to determine if a hand wand and/or physical pat-down inspection is required. However, passenger privacy concerns raised related to this kind of equipment because this technology can provide a whole-body image that can reveal anomalies underneath passenger clothing. As a result, passengers show displeasure because these devices display highly personal details of their bodies. In order to ensure passengers privacy, the officer viewing the image is in a separate room and never see the passenger being screened while the officer attending to the passenger never see the image.

Bottle Liquid Scanner (BLS): BLSs are hand-held or table-top devices which are used to discriminate explosive or flammable liquids from common, benign liquids carried by passengers. BLSs were introduced because X-ray systems were unable to distinguish liquid explosives from common liquids. The devices analyse substances within a container, measuring particular characteristics of the content's and distinguishing between benign and hazardous liquids in a matter of seconds.

Chemical Analysis Devices (CAD): CADs are portable systems that can be used to identify a range of chemical agents and explosives threats. These devices are used to assess suspicious substances in the possession of passengers traveling through the security checkpoints.

Explosive Trace Detectors (ETD): They are used to examine articles, analysing their content for the presence of potential explosive residue. A swab is used to collect samples, which are then analysed for traces of explosives residue. The first joint meeting of the International Explosives Technical Commission (IETC) and the Ad Hoc Group of Specialists on the Detection of Explosives (AH/DE) reviewed progress made in testing, implementing and deploying advanced security screening technologies, including body scanners. The explosives experts concluded that trace detection technology continues to play an important role in airport screening and noted that further research to validate when and how this technology can be used for air cargo is under way in many States.

Figure 5.67 - Security technologies in 2010.

The common ICAO, AITA and ACI workshop on the next generation screening process for passengers and cabin baggage in Geneva in 2010 in collaboration reviewed planned and ongoing initiatives for developing a “**checkpoint of the future**” that will improve passenger flow as well as provide effective security. In particular, it examined how certain elements, such as the use of passenger data for identifying high-risk passengers, might be incorporated in the screening process. The Declaration on Aviation Security urged Member States to increase cooperation to ensure the early detection of threats and dissemination of information on threats to civil aviation. Collection and transmission of advance passenger information (API) and passenger name record (PNR) data are recognised as facilitators, while acknowledging the importance of protecting passengers’ privacy. In 2010 more than 180 States had issued machine readable passports (MRPs) in conformity with ICAO specifications by 1 April 2010, and another five States achieved compliance by year’s end.

Progress Up-to-Now

Since 2010, there have been advances in passenger and baggage screening through the development of new technologies and the improvement of the processes. Firstly, there have been enhances in existing checkpoint and checked baggage screening technologies, such as Advanced Imaging Technology, Advanced Technology X-Ray, Enhanced Metal Detectors, Explosives Detection Systems, and Explosives Trace Detection to increase detection capabilities and efficiencies. However, traditional threats to aviation security remain and new types of threats are emerging. As a result, passenger and baggage screening must adapt to face the

evolving threats and changes. For that reason, in addition to enhancing existing technologies, it has invested in new technologies such as automation and the use of risk-based algorithms to screen passenger more efficiently and quicker. Through this type of initiatives which are currently in development, security and overall traveller experience is improved, by expediting physical screening for passengers who are considered lower risk to aviation security.

The existing technologies which has been updated and enhanced are the following ones:

- **Advanced Imaging Technology:** This technology allows to screen safely passengers for metallic and non-metallic items, such as weapons, explosives and other objects concealed under layers of clothing. There have been improvements in this technology since 2010, as for example images with more quality, enhanced detection capabilities and false alarms rates reduced. However, there are still some airports that do not have this technology deployed, which can be considered a system vulnerability because these airports can be used as entry points.
- **Advanced Technology X-Ray:** These systems detect threats in carry-on baggage, by providing a high definition x-ray image of its content. This technology is deployed in most airports. Enhancements in Advanced Technology X-Ray include updating software or adding an infrared operator sensor and a queuing conveyor.
- **Boarding Pass Scanners:** a new technology that allows reading two-dimensional barcodes located on boarding passes. These systems reduce the need for manual verification of boarding passes and also validates the authenticity of the passenger's boarding pass at the security checkpoints using bar code readers and encryption techniques. The system temporarily captures and displays the photograph from the passenger's ID, helping security officers to compare the photo of the person carrying the ID. If the encoded data on the passenger's ID match with the data on the boarding pass, the passengers are allowed to fly.
- **Bottled Liquids Scanners:** they can discriminate explosives or flammable liquids from common, benign liquids carried by passengers. Efforts are dedicated to developing capabilities that detect a broader range of threats, enable the screening of opaque containers, and detect smaller quantities of liquid explosives.
- **Enhanced Metal Detectors:** these devices are used for locating potential metallic threats on a person where Advanced Imaging technology is not deployed. Some advances in this technology are intended to improve threat detection and discrimination capabilities, assuring at the same time passengers' privacy and dignity.
- **Explosives Trace Detectors:** the detection capability of these devices has been enhanced, allowing a better operational performance and the ability to detect new threats. They are employed in checkpoint and checked baggage screening for traces of explosives. Transportation security officers swab a piece of carry-on or checked baggage, or a passenger's hands, and then place the swab inside the unit to analyse it for the presence of potential explosive residue.

Passenger screening statistics

Thanks to the technological improvements in passenger screening developed in recent years, the number of passengers screened has improve as it can be seen in the next Figure 5.68:

Million passengers screened per year

Figure 5.68 - Million passengers screened according to TSA statistics

In addition, baggage screening has also improved from 432 million checked bags in 2015 to 466 million checked bags in 2016.

KEY TOPIC T5.4 – EXPANDED USE OF PROTECTED COMMUNICATIONS

Scope of the Goal

High –bandwidth data resilient to cyberattacks		
Goal 19: The air transport system has fully secured global high bandwidth data network, hardened and resilient by design to cyber-attacks		
Comparison with 2017 SRIA document	Why	Lacks
Coherent	In both documents it is pointed that one of the main concerns in the future will be cybersecurity. In addition, technological advances may also introduce new vulnerabilities. Therefore, it will be required an aviation system that is resilient by design to the possible attacks.	Security must be supported by intelligence that provides the information necessary to develop a comprehensive and detailed catalogue of threats and system vulnerabilities. Tools such as a security radar or a horizon scanning will be needed to automate detection of aviation incidents, gathering of associated information, and forensic analysis.

Table 5.5 – SRIA Targets for cyber-resilience

Benchmarks

Cyber-attacks on the aviation industry are becoming a matter of concern. The 2012 report by the British Centre for the Protection of National Infrastructure (CPNI) highlighted that the interface and interdependence inherent to ICT-use has raised the vulnerability of aircraft and aviation systems. This is because the aviation encompasses one of the most integrated and complex information and communications technology (ICT) systems from the development and construction of aircraft to communications and navigation instruments, along with all the thousands of connections that link the various parts of an airport.

As in other fields, the digitalisation and placement online of such complex instrumentation have introduced considerable problems associated with cyber security. As a result, due to the on-board and ground computer systems, navigation systems and the use of complex data networks, cyber-attacks and data breaches are perceived to be growing threats for the aviation sector. With increasing inter-connectivity which is expected in the future, the system will be more vulnerable and exposed to multiple points of attacks. Ensuring secured aviation systems and staying ahead of the possible threats requires that the aviation sector establishes a cyber security culture, sets measures to strengthen the defence system and develops mitigation/prevention strategies for the threats identified.

Figure 5.69 summarizes aviation's information and communications technology (ICT) environment. Simply stated, ICT is pervasive across the aviation ecosystem, from designing and developing aircraft, to flight operations, maintenance, communications, navigation, and air traffic management.

Figure 5.69 - ICT technologies in civil aviation. Source: American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, A Framework for Aviation. Cybersecurity, August 2013, p. 8, <http://www.aiaa.org/aviationcybersecurity>.

Therefore, in order to face the future cyber-attacks, firstly, it would be necessary to identify the multiple threats that could compromise aviation security as well as to identify the systems

which could be vulnerable to attacks. Then, it would be required to develop strategies in order to mitigate the threats identified. The following are some of the main threats identified in cybersecurity:

- Phishing threats: phishing is a type of security attack that attempts to obtain sensitive/valuable information such as usernames, passwords and credit card details, often for malicious reasons.
- Jamming attacks: an attacker could alter the projection and mapping of airplanes or delete their position from the radar screen. This type of attack could have serious consequences as the hackers could compromise the accuracy of data provided to the aircraft management, such as speed, location and direction of nearby airports and other planes.
- Remote hijacking: Security gaps in communication technologies used in the aviation industry could allow hackers to remotely attack/control the flight and on-board systems. Cyber criminals could attack critical systems such as flight controls, engine and fuel systems, surveillance systems, etc.
- DDoS attacks: Distributed-denial-of-service attacks are attempts to make an online service unavailable by overwhelming it with traffic from multiple sources and cause a denial of service for users of the targeted resource. The flood of incoming messages, connection requests or malformed packets to the target system could result in a crash of the platform, thereby denying service to legitimate users or systems.
- Wi-Fi-based attacks: there are vulnerabilities in the on-board system that could allow hackers to use the on-board Wi-Fi signal or inflight entertainment system to hack into the plane's avionics equipment and disrupt or modify satellite communications.

Currently, there is no common vision, or common strategy, goals, standards, implementation models, or international policies defining cybersecurity for commercial aviation. Ensuring a secured aviation system and staying ahead of evolving ICT threats is a shared responsibility, involving governments, airlines, airports, and manufacturers. The aviation community is working on the development of a framework to offer an approach to increasing the effectiveness of cybersecurity for aviation. To achieve the 2050 goal of an air transport system **fully secured global high bandwidth data network, hardened and resilient by design** to cyber-attacks a triple approach is needed that encompass the **technological, operational and societal/human dimension** of the problem as indicated in the figure 5.70:

Figure 5.70 - Technological, operational and societal/human dimension of goal 19 Benchmarks

From a **technological dimension**, the following benchmarks must be achieved:

- **Establish common cyber standards for aviation systems:** Although aviation system is now one of the most complex ICT and control systems in the world, yet there is not a recognized common vision, or common strategy, goals, standards, and practices to further safeguard aviation against the evolving cyber threats. Application of common standards or practices can help provide mitigation, including against insider threats. For example, applying common encryption standards for aviation communications could reduce the risk of interference for future enhancements to the system.
- **Understand the threat and the risk** by identifying the elements of the aviation system that need protection; determining how to protect these elements with systems and standards and understanding the timeliness required for responding to threats.
- **Strengthen the defensive system** including: (1) hardening the Internet backbone, including IPS malware detection and prevention; (2) securing power sources; (3) adding public-key infrastructure (PKI) or other encryption technologies; and (4) technology and procedural upgrades to critical systems. Long-term solutions may require architectural changes to aviation's networks and control systems.

Define and agree on design principles: The internet design principles, that all nodes are known and trusted are no longer valid for aviation. Aviation must define design principles for its networks and control systems that consider the evolving nature of the cyber threat. This would include identifying architectures and design principles that help us protect our systems and platforms against known attack methods, defining quality assurance standards for critical systems, and ensuring that aviation systems are resilient against unknown threat scenarios.

From an operational dimension, the following benchmarks must be achieved:

- **Communicate the threats and assure situational awareness** by establishing a protected forum for industry and government information exchange on current and emerging cyber threats to the commercial aviation system and creating secure mechanisms to extend information exchange to the international community.
- **Provide incident response** able to provide the aviation community with a means to mitigate evolving threats.
- **Define operational principles:** These principles focus on the operational principles of systems after they are deployed in the field. This would include operational standards and best practices that mitigate threats to our systems and platforms to assure its resiliency. Items to consider would be system upgrades and patches, the timeliness of system changes, decisions on when to upgrade or retire obsolete systems, maintenance practices, access control, and personnel processes such as credentials, training, and inadvertent human errors that expose vulnerabilities that can aid an attacker.

From a **social/human dimension**, the following benchmarks must be achieved:

- **Establish a cyber security culture:** The same disciplined approach that created aviation's safety culture (i.e., a common vision and strategy, clear goals, common understanding, a collaborative risk-based decision-making model, non-punitive reporting structures, open communication of failures, training, etc...) must also be applied to securing cyber systems across the air transportation system.
- **Ensure that government and industry work together to coordinate national aviation cybersecurity strategies, policies, and plans. This will imply:** (1) Establish a private/public cyber partnership that includes "business continuity elements" for the aviation sector; (2) Establish policies for the near- and long-term development for cybersecurity; (3) Define accepted international rules of behaviour; (4) Consequences for bad behaviour must be enforced; (5) Governments need to move cybersecurity to a high priority on the diplomatic agenda.

On top of that it would be necessary to conduct necessary research and development on technical and operational assets. The aviation community, government and academia need to define and conduct necessary research and development to support the design and operational principles for enhancement to the aviation system. This would include:

1. Creating secure network architectures, including methods for maintaining secure data transfer, isolating critical data, and effectively recovering from attacks;
2. Determining system vulnerabilities;
3. Improving attack detection, and (4) improving forensics technology.

Reference State in 2010

In 2010 aviation stakeholders start to realise the need to create a common framework for cybersecurity in aviation and start to construct a holistic approach to this problem. Current European response to this threat although considers the extension and streamline of regulation, but first focusses on understanding the risks and building a holistic, coherent, affordable and adaptable response, and then establishing mitigating measures. The most relevant initiatives at that moment are summarized hereafter from different perspectives.

A. Legislative and Regulatory Developments

➤ ICAO

ICAO's Annex 17 to the Convention on International Civil Aviation, Security – Safeguarding International Civil Aviation against Acts of Unlawful Interference, sets minimum standards for aviation security worldwide and creates a global policy and legal framework. ICAO Aviation Security Manual (Doc 8973) provides guidance, including on minimum measures to protect critical information systems against unauthorised access and use. In 2010 Annex 17 was updated and strengthened to reflect the mayor risk and concerns to aviation, in particularly cyber threats. In 2012 a new Annex 17 Recommended Practice 4.9 recognizes cyber- attacks as a distinct threat to the aviation industry that needs attention.

In 2010 ICAO finalized a **new comprehensive strategy for enhancing aviation security worldwide (ICASS ICAO Comprehensive Aviation Security Strategy)** that recognize cyber-attacks on aviation systems, including Air Traffic Management systems as a new and evolving threat to aviation. The **Diplomatic Conference on Aviation Security**, held in Beijing from 30 August to 10 September 2010 **criminalizing the act of cyberattack on air navigation facilities**.

➤ The Digital Agenda for Europe

The European Commission launched in March 2010 the Europe 2020 Strategy 1 to exit the crisis and prepare the EU economy for the challenges of the next decade. Europe 2020 sets out a vision to achieve high levels of employment, a low carbon economy, productivity and social cohesion, to be implemented through concrete actions at EU and national levels. The Digital Agenda for Europe is one of the seven flagship initiatives of the Europe 2020 Strategy, set out to define the key enabling role that the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) will have to play if Europe wants to succeed in its ambitions for 2020.

In the Digital Agenda for Europe, the Commission committed itself to **establishing a CERT for the EU institutions**, as part of the EU's commitment to a reinforced and high level EU Networking and Information Security Policy in Europe. In August 2010 the Commission requested four cyber-security experts known as the "Rat der IT Weisen" to make recommendations on how to set up such a CERT. Their report was finalised in November 2010.

The Digital Agenda also calls on all Member States to establish their own CERTs, paving the way to an EU-wide network of national and governmental Computer Emergency Response Teams by 2012 (see IP/11/395). The EU's Council of Telecoms Ministers adopted conclusions on 27th May 2011, confirming this objective.

AT the Digital Agenda Commission also committed to:

- Present in 2010 measures aiming at a reinforced and high-level Network and Information Security Policy, including legislative initiatives such as a **modernised European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA)**, and measures allowing faster reactions in the event of cyber-attacks, including a CERT for the EU institutions;

- **Present measures, including legislative initiatives, to combat cyber-attacks against information systems by 2010**, and related rules on jurisdiction in cyberspace at European and international levels by 2013.

B. Standardisation Activities

➤ ECAC

ECAC Study Group on Cyber Threats to Civil Aviation was settled in 2009. Since then it has been recognised their valuable contribution on Cybersecurity in Aviation, notably the works of its Study Group on Cyber Security in Civil Aviation, including the updated **ECAC Doc 30**; as well as its **Vulnerability assessments on cyber security** since 2011.

The Group has also achieved international outreach with provisions on cyber security in ICAO Annex 17, sharing of information with ICAO and common Europe-USA paper at ICAO Assembly.

C. Services

➤ CERT-EU

After a pilot phase of one year and a successful assessment by its constituency and its peers, the EU Institutions have decided to set up a permanent Computer Emergency Response Team (CERT-EU) for the EU institutions, agencies and bodies **on September 11th, 2012**. The team is made up of IT security experts from the main EU Institutions (European Commission, General Secretariat of the Council, European Parliament, and Committee of the Regions, Economic and Social Committee). It cooperates closely with other CERTs in the Member States and beyond as well as with specialised IT security companies. CERT-EU will gradually extend its services, on the basis of the requirements of its constituency and taking into account the available competencies, resources and partnerships.

In recent years, CERTs have been developed in both private and public sectors as small teams of cyber-experts connected to the internet that can effectively and efficiently respond to information security incidents and cyber threats, often on a 24-hours a day-7days a week basis.

Progress Up-to-Now

Aviation cyber-security is a fast-moving topic and a very dynamic area with strong political and technical involvement by many players. As consequence, the last years have seen many developments in this domain, proposed and actual. Latest developments in terms of legislative and regulatory changes, standardisation activities, pan-European research and development, etc. are updated and summarised hereafter. However, the dynamism of this area makes the shelf life of any analysis limited. The most relevant initiatives until now are summarized hereafter from different perspectives.

A. Legislative and Regulatory Development

➤ ICAO

The last updates of ICAO's Annex 17 and ICAO Aviation Security Manual regarding cybersecurity were in 2014.

The 39th ICAO Assembly, held in September/October 2016, included (item 16) a progress report on the global aviation security policy framework and implementation of the ICAO Comprehensive Aviation Security Strategy (ICASS), including developments in risk assessment, innovation and cyber-security. Cyber-security was also expected to be addressed in other relevant items, such as RPAS (Item 33). The General Assembly passed a high-level resolution on cyber.

The Working Group on Threat and Risk has added cyber-security to the Risk Context Statement which should be used by all ICAO members to inform their national risk assessments. This includes a specific risk matrix for ATM.

➤ FAA

FAA has revised its cyber security strategy recently. The five components of the strategy include – improved governance model, continued improvements to the protection and defence of the FAA mission, data driven risk management approaches applied to cyber, focus on building cyber workforce and enhanced collaboration with external partners. The regulatory side of FAA is targeting its improvements via a **program named Aircraft Systems Information Security/Protection (ASISP)** – examining potential gaps and improvements via a risk-based framework.

For ATM systems, FAA is currently focused on cyber resilience and has an active effort underway to characterize threats to the mission (service threads vs. individual systems). This effort will create and maintain a **National Airspace level threat model** to help FAA prioritize its cyber related activities investments. FAA has also ramped up its operational exercises to include more realistic scenarios and has increased its participation in national level cyber exercises. To this end, a **cyber-test facility was established in 2015** to facilitate more comprehensive tests and exercises.

➤ European Union

The **General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR)** applies to personal data and imposes additional legal obligations on data processors, stipulates that Data Protection Impact Assessments and risk assessment and mitigation, along with prior approval of the DPA for high risks. Data protection law is extended to all foreign companies processing data of EU residents, and a single set of rules is introduced for all EU Member States.

In July 2016 the **Network and Information Security (NIS) Directive (2016/1148)** was adopted, establishing minimum standards for Member States and operators of critical national infrastructure. It implies risks assessment and adoption of appropriate measures to ensure a secure and trustworthy environment; mandatory reporting of any incident seriously compromising the networks and information systems. Member States shall establish effective Computer Emergency Response Teams (CERT) and designate one or more competent authorities, which will be part of a secure European-wide electronic data interchange network to allow the sharing of cybersecurity related information especially for incident reporting.

In **October 2016, a new unit (A5) in DG MOVE dealing with all security aspects in transport has been established** integrated Maritime Security (former A4) and Aviation Security (former A2).

➤ EASA

In November **2015 EASA has developed a Cybersecurity Roadmap** that identified 4 main objectives: Situational Awareness, Readiness & Resilience, Reactiveness, and Cyber-Security Promotion. Since then, EASA is working on its implementation and a number of initiatives to better address cybersecurity risks in aviation improving resilience and fostering built-in security:

- EASA has been tasked to facilitate a **Strategic European Coordination Platform** including representatives of key industry stakeholders, Member States and EU Institutions.
- EASA is supporting the creation of a **European Centre for Cybersecurity in Aviation (ECCSA)** and providing the initial operational capabilities in collaboration with CERT-EU, to promote voluntary information sharing and expert collaboration.
- EASA is undertaking a **gap analysis of all Implementing Rules**. These are started to identify areas of action.
- It is expected that EASA will release a **Notice of Proposed Amendment (NPA) for a single, horizontal rule by the end of 2017**. This will be followed by an opinion sent to the European Commission by the end of 2018, and a rule in force by end of 2019.
- **Negotiations on the EASA Basic Regulation** is on-going and it might give EASA the competency to address cyber-security although it is noteworthy that the European Council proposal does not address cyber-security and the Parliament proposal considers cyber-security as one additional source of concern for Safety
- **EASA has also joined the FAA in the information-security Aviation Rulemaking Advisory Committee (ARAC)**. The FAA tasks the ARAC to provide advice and recommendations concerning a full range of aviation-related issues, in this case information/cyber-security. However, this is focused on aircraft cyber-security and does not address ATM, since in the US ATM systems are of federal interest only.

➤ High Level Conference Cybersecurity in Civil Aviation Krakow 8-9 November 2017

The Conference discussed the progress achieved for aviation ground systems, including institutional set-up, legislation advancement, risk assessment methodology, cybersecurity promotion, research activities, commitments and resources devoted to cybersecurity. All this in order to establish a ground for the future European strategy for Cybersecurity in Aviation and the Cybersecurity Road Map that will define the future actions that have to be undertaken at European level in order to ensure a secure environment for aviation covering the cyber-space.

B. Standardisation Activities

➤ CEN

It has published in 2014, **EN 16495** Information security for organisations supporting civil defining guidelines and general principles, structured in line with ISO 27002, for the implementation of an information security management system.

➤ EUROCAE

The Eurocae sub-group from WG-72 (Aeronautical Information Systems Security) is producing a **Process Specification for the security accreditation of ATM systems** throughout the lifecycle of data exchanged between aircraft and ATM systems: this includes the creation, origination, storage, transmission, processing and decommissioning of data. It will address the design of a security accreditation method for ground ATM systems analogous to airworthiness certification. The scope will have a broad approach focusing on safety, operational and economic impact.

➤ ECAC

An **ECAC Study Group on Cyber Threats to Civil Aviation is updating Document 30 ('Doc. 30') to better address cyber-risks**. Doc. 30 builds upon ICAO Annex 17 and can define higher standards. Amendments to the overarching principles in Chapter 14, and prescriptive annexes, as well as supporting guidance material are expected to be developed and included within the **ECAC Aviation Security Handbook** within the next couple of years.

➤ Industry High-Level Group (IHLG)

In **2014**, ICAO, ACI, CANSO, IATA and the International Coordinating Council of Aerospace Industry Associations (ICCAIA) signed a **Civil Aviation Cybersecurity Action Plan** aimed at more effective coordination across all stakeholders to effectively respond to cyber challenges. Since then there has been progress with:

- **Sharing of best practices:** IHLG organisations has identified key practices and guidance, to be held on an ICAO-based dedicated cyber security web-page. There is a recognition that specific guidance for different entities may be appropriate, with overarching guidance at the ICAO level (drawing on international standards such as ISO/IEC 27002).
- **Developing a common set of terms:** The IHLG identified a number of existing glossaries and have facilitated sharing those among the aviation community through the cyber portal established by ICAO.
- **Preparing civil aviation against future challenges:** The IHLG agreed a common set of key messages such that a consistent view could be presented publicly. Many efforts were also made to promote the cyber-security topic as a priority.
- **Proposing a declaration for the ICAO 39th Assembly:** The IHLG proposed a declaration intended to consolidate and align cyber-related policy statements and directions to facilitate defining general objective. This was scheduled for the end of September 2016.

➤ ACI World Cybersecurity Task Force (2015)

The Task Force was initially set up with the focus of enhancing cyber-security information-sharing between airports and industry partners; educating airport management and information technology staff on cyber-security issues; representing ACI's interests with other organisations who are also concerned with the growing risks posed by cyber-terrorism in the air transport industry. The taskforce has also developed the **IT Airport Cybersecurity Benchmark**, a web-based system addressing the specific information security needs of the airport community. It is aligned to ISO/IEC 27002 controls.

➤ ASD Civil Aviation Cyber Security Task Force

The **Task Force was launched in October 2015 with** the goals of developing an ASD position on civil aviation cyber-security and coordinating ASD inputs to external bodies on the subject. International work has been through the ICCAIA and has contributed to ICAO's Assembly and AVSEC Panel, including the IHLG declaration (see above). European work to-date has centred on coordinating with, and providing input to, EASA (especially on the Basic Regulation and cyber-security roadmap) and ECAC. High-level objectives for the manufacturing industry and for operators have been developed. The Task Force was set up as a temporary entity so in autumn 2016 decisions will be taken on whether to extend and on any future work programme.

➤ CANSO ATM Security Working Group

CANSO has an ATM Security Working Group (ASWG) that address all aspects of security, including cyber-security. The third ASWG meeting was held in December 2015. A working paper on cyber-security was presented to the fifth ICAO EURNAT EUR/NAT Aviation Security Group (ENAVSECG) in May 2016. Ongoing activities within CANSO Vision 2020+ include:

- Security promotion, awareness and Just Culture
- ATM security human factors in the whole ATM lifecycle
- Identification of Security standards and best practices applicable to ATM environment in the light of sustainability and regulatory compliance
- Audit and oversight issues
- ADS-B Working Group activities for secure surveillance

2016 has also seen cooperation between CANSO and NEASCOG (NATO-EUROCONTROL Security Coordination Group).

In 2017 CANSO and EUROCAE commit on the joint development of aviation industry standards, with particular focus on ATM, USAS and Cyber security.

C. Functions and Services

➤ European Centre for Cyber Security in Aviation

One of the enablers identified in the EASA Cyber-Security in Aviation project and roadmap is the European **Centre for Cyber Security in Aviation (ECCSA)**. ECCSA's mission is to provide information and assistance to European aviation manufacturers, airlines, maintenance organizations, air navigation service providers, etc. in order to protect the critical elements of the system such as aircraft, navigation and surveillance systems, datalinks, airports, etc. ECCSA will cover the full spectrum of aviation. ECCSA's capabilities will be rolled out with a stepped

approach, providing during the first implementation phase, 2017 – 2018, the following services:

- A public website reporting cyber security news and ECCSA initiatives,
- Open Source Intelligence services for members,
- A collaboration platform for members to exchange sectorial cyber security information.

➤ Aviation-ISAC

The Aviation Information Sharing and Analysis Centre (A-ISAC) is a US / Boeing led membership group for relevant security information sharing for the aviation sector. It combines both industry and government participants to share timely and actionable information pertaining to threats, vulnerabilities, incidents, etc. In addition, it aims to foster cooperation and provide best practices and educational awareness. Membership is open to European organisations, and Airbus will be an “anchor” member to address European issues and engagement with the government, when needed.

➤ EU-Aviation ISAC (EA ISAC)

A similar initiative to the Aviation-ISAC has been proposed by Airbus and Lufthansa, with informal discussions considering its formal launch. Discussions between the US and European efforts on potential collaboration are ongoing with a meeting held in September 2016 on the Aviation-ISAC’s European strategy. NDA and MoU are being drafted to frame the EA-ISAC activities.

D. Research and Development Activities

Civil aviation cybersecurity research and development activities are currently fragmented across national and EU funding sources. The latest High-level conference on cybersecurity in civil aviation has suggested EU institutions to ensure a high level of priority of aviation-relevant subjects in the next Research Framework Programme (FP9).

These different perspectives must be coherent and complementary: civil aviation cybersecurity must be fully integrated in the EU Research agenda in order to increase efforts to develop technologies and competencies at European level.

A more coordinated research and development work programme needs to be implemented with short-term flexible research activities. EU commitment should serve for development activities to improve the safe operation of the civil aviation transport system, whilst research and development activities for business continuity could remain within the existing funding instruments. As part of this strategic vision and master plan, EASA needs to be involved to ensure there is a good link between science, innovation development, deployment and policy.

➤ European ATM Master Plan

The 2015 Edition of the Master Plan makes explicit reference to cyber-risks to ATM. A risk identified within the Master Plan is that the deployment of SESAR solutions leads to unaddressed cyber-security vulnerabilities. The mitigations identified were to (a) ensure efforts on ATM cyber-security are coordinated and assess policy options for strengthening cyber-

security and resilience, and (b) establish principles and processes for ensuring cybersecurity and resilience are included appropriately within the SESAR R&D work programme.

The draft 2016 Deployment Programme both refines the specific Families related to SWIM cyber-security and reports on the identified cyber-security requirements to be considered in the deployment of each Family, having specific regard to the potential cyber-threats linked to the increased connectivity associated to the full PCP deployment. The SDM is of the opinion that some components of some families are particularly exposed to cyber-security risks and that stakeholders should take appropriate action to mitigate them. The Commission also requested to the SESAR Deployment Manager to consider cyber-security requirements at project level in the Deployment Programme by proposing guidance material.

➤ SESAR 2020

The SESAR 2020 multi-annual work programme identified cyber-security as a research topic to address. PJ19 (Content Integration) coordinates cyber-security activities and guidance provided across all projects, by the appointment of Security/Cyber-Security ATM Focal points in each project. Each SESAR solution shall develop a security case to demonstrate that self-protection and collaborative support has been correctly addressed. As part of this, projects will undertake security risk assessments and identify resulting security requirements – both include the cyber dimension. SESAR has develop a study on the research and development (R&D) needed to ensure ATM cyber security that sets out the elements needed to introduce a holistic approach to cyber-security. In addition, the SJU are currently developing a cyber-security strategy to clarify what will be delivered as part of SESAR's output regarding cyber-security and the 'securability' of SESAR solutions. It will define the responsibilities of the SJU in the frame of the whole system - and service - lifecycle. Topics such as the role of operational mitigations to system vulnerabilities are likely to be addressed. The strategy is expected to be published in Q4 2016.

➤ ACARE Security Sub-Group

In June 2015, at the request of the EC, a dedicated security sub-group was created within the WG/4 (Safety & Security) of the Advisory Council for Aviation Research and Innovation in Europe (ACARE). It accounts for both the evolution of technology as well as radical changes or 'technology shocks'. It has identified objectives for operators and manufacturers as well as short term, medium and long-term challenges.

➤ GAMMA

The Global ATM Security Management Project (GAMMA) is a European research project (2013-2017) whose goal is to develop solutions to emerging air traffic management vulnerabilities backed up by practical proposals for the implementation of these solutions. During 2016 the focus has moved towards translating the GAMMA concept into a set of prototypes to validate in exercises. The Security Management Platform (SMP) prototype represents the central instantiation of the GAMMA concept as it is the security information sharing platform which lies at the heart of the GAMMA proposal for managing ATM security in Europe.

➤ EUROCONTROL Agency Research Team (ART)

A dedicated ART Workshop on 'ATM Security and Cybersecurity' was held in Q1 2016, giving a broad overview of different areas of activities within the field.

➤ European PPP on Cyber Security ECS

The European Commission has signed on July 2016 a PPP with the private sector for the development of a common approach and market on cybersecurity. The Aim of this partnerships is: 1) Foster cooperation between public and private actors at early stages of the research and innovation process in order to allow people in Europe to access innovative and trustworthy European solutions (ICT products, services and software). 2) Stimulates cybersecurity industry, by helping align the demand and supply sectors to allow industry to elicit future requirements from end-users, as well as sectors that are important customers of cybersecurity solutions (e.g. energy, health, transport, finance). 3) Coordinate digital security industrial resources in Europe. The EC will invest up to €450 million in this partnership, under its research and innovation programme Horizon 2020 for the 2017-2020 calls (4years). Cybersecurity market players are expected to invest three times more.

➤ FAA

FAA is in the process of leveraging useful research in cyber defence and resilience conducted by partner agencies in the US Federal government. The research focus areas are – cyber resilience, self-adaptive systems, data analytics for cyber, and design assurance in mixed-trust environments.

The following Figure 5.71 summarizes the progress achieved up to now in this goal.

Figure 5.71 - Progress achieved up to now in goal 19.

Predictions Up-to-2025: Existing Technologies and Evolutionary Progress Up-to-2025

In the next years, the measures which are used nowadays to screen passengers and baggage are expected to be enhanced and strengthened in order to improve efficiency and security. The enhanced capabilities include the ability to detect an expanded set of threat materials with higher detection probabilities, lower false-alarm rates, and faster throughput rates, all at lower lifecycle costs, resulting in less impact to airport operations and the passengers. In addition, these advances will allow each year to screen more an increase number of passengers and baggage per hour.

The existing technologies which will be updated and enhanced in the next years are the following ones:

- Advanced Imaging Technology;
- Advanced Technology X-Ray;
- Boarding Pass Scanners;
- Bottled Liquids Scanners;
- Enhanced Metal Detectors;
- Explosives Trace Detectors.

The main types of scanning and detection devices currently deployed by European and international airports are based on traditional X-ray technologies as well as EDS and ETD detection systems. Therefore, these technologies are developed, and their maturity level achieved is number 9. However, not all of them have been deployed in all airports. Therefore, it is still necessary to expand this technology on a global scale, especially at large airports.

As time passes, the detection capabilities of these security measures will improve as well as their efficiency. For example, in case of baggage screening, the primary detection component are the explosives detection systems. These systems provide imaging, screening, and detection capabilities through x-ray technology to identify possible threats and create images of the bag contents.

Explosives detection systems technologies are categorised into three different groups:

- High-speed: Throughput ~ 900 bags per hour;
- Medium-speed: 400 ~Throughput < 900 bags per hour; and
- Reduced-size: 100 <Throughput< 400 bags per hour.

At this time, only reduced-size and medium-speed have been deployed while high-speed is in development. Therefore, in short-time horizon all the explosives detection systems will be faster, allowing a higher performance.

However, despite enhances in the existing measures, it will reach a point in which these measures achieve a limit, so that it cannot be possible to increase the number of passengers screened. In that moment, it will be necessary to develop new technologies that allow an important breakthrough.

Possible or Predictable Breakthroughs: Emerging Technologies

As it was mentions before, the existing technologies will be enhanced and updated in order to improve airport security and efficiency. However, these current measures will achieve a limit sometime, in which the number of passenger screened cannot be improved. Taking into account that during the past years the passenger flow at airports has increased significantly, it is expected that in the future that

number increases. For that reason, it is necessary to evaluate new technologies and capabilities in order to maximize threat detection and efficiency. Some examples of the emerging trends in technology are the following ones:

Biometrics

One of the main emerging technologies is the biometric identification, which is being considered as an alternative to traditional access control methods.

The implementation of biometrics at airports would simplify, streamline and enhance the passenger travel process, including border controls and security, while reducing costs. For example, by implementing biometrics screening it could be possible to remove the hassle of checking identification documents for both travellers and airport security personnel, instead of carrying all the documents to pass through airport security (ticket, passport, etc.).

Traditionally, there are two ways to authenticate that a person is who that person claims to be: 1) by something one knows (a password, a PIN); 2) and by something one has (a key, an ID card, a token); and 3) by something that one is (a biometric, such as a fingerprint). Items such as keys and PINs can be compromised, and, for that reason, a new identification method arises: biometric identification, such as a fingerprint. Biometric represents the most secure and convenient authentication tool because it cannot be borrowed, stolen, or forgotten.

Biometric identification is a technology that verifies a person's identity through his or her fingerprints, facial features or other physical characteristics. However, before the ability to access authentication systems is granted to a person, that person's data must be pre-recorded, or "enrolled" into the database. Users "enrol" by having their biometric information (fingerprint, iris pattern or face) scanned by the system.

Therefore, biometric systems use a person's unique physical characteristics to verify a person's identity. This could all be accomplished several methods that can quickly identify a person and automatically approve his or her progression through the normally onerous process of getting on an airplane:

- Biometric face recognition systems (Figure 5.72) will collect data from the users' face and store them in a database for future use. It will measure the overall structure, shape and proportion of features on the user's face such as: distance between eyes, nose, mouths, ears, jaw, size of eyes, mouth and other expressions.
- Finger print is the low cost and widely accepted technology. Fingerprint-based systems match passengers to their bags at check-in. Their index finger scan is then stored in the passenger register, matching it to the details on the baggage tag.
- Iris recognition systems will scan the iris in different ways. It will analyse over 200 points of the iris including: rings, furrows, freckles, the corona and other characteristics. After recording data from each individual, it will save the information in a database for future use in comparing it every time a user wants to access to the system.

One of biometrics technology which is used in security systems recently is DNA biometrics since, it is impossible to fake this characteristic because each person's DNA is unique.

Biometric technology (Figure 5.72) has many advantages such as: improved security and effectiveness, reduced fraud and password administrator costs and ease of use. Even though the biometrics security system still has many concerns such as information privacy, physical privacy and religious objections, this new technology will improve security processes at airports.

Figure 5.72 – Biometric Face recognition system

➤ CT Scanners

Other new technology that could improve airport security screening is computed tomography (CT) scanning (a similar technology to what is used for scans in hospitals).

A CT scan (Figure 5.73) creates a full 3-D image by rotating a narrow band of x-rays around whatever it's inspecting, and digitally compiling the result into a multi-coloured image that gives a lot more data. The results are nuanced and detailed, and the screener can change the colours or contrast to make certain materials stand out. It could be also possible to manipulate the image with pinch and zoom gestures to get a good look from every angle.

The benefit of CT technology in general, is that passengers could keep laptops and liquids in the bag when they reach the checkpoint.

Another difference between CT scanners and other X-ray scanner solutions is the amount of data they can collect: the conventional equipment doesn't collect as much data as CT equipment. So, a spinning source in a relatively similar amount of time will collect much more data about what it's looking at compared to a conventional X-ray, which may have just one, two or three cameras that are taking a photo.

This type of technology would provide a better customer experience, in terms of shortening waiting times and allowing for faster processing through the checkpoint, while maintaining the highest levels of security.

Figure 5.73 – Computer tomography scanning creates 3-Dimension Image

Facial Scanning

Other future technologies that would improve security at airports is using facial recognition software (Figure 5.74) to identify ticketed passengers. This face scanning technology would replace traditional boarding passes, by scanning own face and comparing it with the photo of own passport. These systems would allow video surveillance to match faces to a database of previously identified individuals.

However, there is some concern about how accurate these new procedures will be. Apparently, the facial recognition technology doesn't recognize all people with the same accuracy. White women and black people aren't as easily recognized as white men, meaning there could be some mismatching of identities. Some are also concerned that this is crossing the line in terms of passenger privacy.

Figure 5.74 – Facial recognition software

Behavioural Analytics

Essentially, this is software that continuously scans surveillance video feeds for suspicious behaviour. These techniques focus (Figure 5.75) on analysing the passengers' intentions and emotions, instead

of analysing the content of carry-ons. Speedier and less intrusive than metal detectors, these systems would improve efficiency to the airplane boarding process. Therefore, with this type of systems it could be possible to detect a person's reaction to certain stimuli by reading body temperature, heart rate and respiration, signals a terrorist unwittingly emits before he plans to commit an attack.

Figure 5.75 – Behavioural analytics

Integrated Security System

Airports present a particular security challenge due to its operational complexity, because they are composed of a huge number of subsystems, people, technology, and interest groups involved. Due to its challenging environment, the information and data that flows in this system must be accurate, intelligent, quick, and easy to understand to make decisions and share between all the actors involved. In addition, it is necessary to develop methods to protect infrastructure, equipment, and especially the passengers. One of the possible measures foreseen for the future is to create (Figure 5.76) an integrated security system, so that all the airport security systems are integrated, such as video surveillance cameras, alarm systems, intrusion detection devices, and object tracking systems, closed-circuit television, and other sensor systems. All the data provided by these systems would improve situational awareness and enable quick response to any emergency. In this way, the huge volumes of information provided by the several systems could be storage and shared to all actors in real time, allowing a great increased in detection capabilities and efficiency within the airport security measures. Moreover, integration efforts will reduce the number of screening procedures required for each passenger and they will allow to increase passengers flow. The systems which are necessary to be integrated are shown in the next Figure 5.77:

Figure 5.76 - Communication and Coordination among security subsystems, people, and all involved parties

Figure 5.77 - Integrated security system

It is important to highlight that all the new technologies mentioned before are in **the first level of maturity**, since all of them are not still in development, so they are in the concept phase.

Projection and Identification of Gaps

As it was mentioned before, the existing technologies will be enhanced and updated in order to improve airport security and efficiency. However, it will reach a point in which these measures achieve a limit, in which the number of passenger screened cannot be improved. From that moment, it will be necessary to introduce new technologies and capabilities in order to maximize efficiency. Taking this into account it can be estimated the trend that this sector will follow in next years in terms of number of passengers screened as indicated in the Figure 5.78:

Figure 5.78 – Prediction of the growth in the number of passengers to be received at airports.

KEY TOPIC 5.5 – GUIDELINES FOR CYBER PROTECTION AND SECURITY

Reference State in 2010

The state of the art within Europe was reviewed in **Cyber Europe 2010 (CE2010)** – the first pan-European exercise on Critical Information Infrastructure Protection. It was organized by EU Member States, facilitated by the European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA) and supported by the Joint Research Centre (ENISA, 2011).

The objective of the exercise was to trigger communication and collaboration between countries in Europe to try to respond to large-scale attacks. During the CYBER EUROPE 2010 exercise, experts from the participating public bodies of European countries worked together to counter simulated attempts by hackers to paralyze the Internet and critical online services across Europe.

The simulation exercise was based on a fictitious scenario on a fictitious Internet interconnection infrastructure, with a limited number of Internet Interconnection Sites (IIS1) between countries. During the exercise, Internet connectivity between European countries was gradually lost or significantly reduced, requiring cooperation between Member States to avoid a total network crash.

The key findings of CE2010 were as follows:

- The planning phase of the CYBER EUROPE 2010 exercise benefited from the interaction among the participants, which allowed the interests and concerns of all parties to be taken into account and enabled a fruitful and highly appreciated exercise.

- Member States should continue to work on the points of contact that were established during the exercise and to establish a solid European CIIP-network. The consolidation of trust between MS and partners should be a continuing objective.
- The exercise increased in several ways the understanding of how cyber incidents are handled, both on a European level (between Member States) and on a national level (between players). It is, however, worth mentioning that the artificiality of the scenario limited this scope of understanding to a certain extent. A more realistic scenario could lead to a deeper insight of how cyber incidents are handled.
- The exercise accentuated the necessity to be able to establish and locate relevant points of contact within Europe. Since each country is organized differently, it is very important to know who to contact in case of an incident or, more generally, who is able to answer a specific question.
- The exercise demonstrated the need for efficient communications, leading not only to greater understanding, but also illustrating the differences in structure between Member States. How to achieve efficient communication will need more gathering of requirements and analysis work.

Progress Up to Now

A Worldwide Perspective on the Aviation Sector

With the development of new technologies such as internet, the global aviation industry is subject to a new and growing type of threat coming from cyberspace. As in the other industries, cyber threats purposes are for example the robbery of information, political actions, make profit, or simply weaken one stakeholder of the industry (Duchamp et al, 2016).

The global aviation industry has many layers overseeing the safety of all the stakeholders involved, from aircraft manufacturers to the passenger boarding a flight. Overall, these different actors can be classified into 4 categories:

- One international organization: The International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), part of the UN. It codifies the rules of investigation internationally and designs international civil aviation Standards and Recommended Practices in collaboration with its member states.
- Governments: National investigation organizations, virtually security agencies that investigate on behalf of countries involved in the accident. France's Bureau d'Enquêtes et d'Analyses (BEA) or the USA's National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB) are the main examples of such organizations. On top of ICAO's guidelines, they may develop additional safety standards (for example, the NTSB developed smoke detectors in aircraft toilets).
- Trade organization of airlines: International Air Transport Association (IATA) oversees standards at industry level and is directly in contact with most of the world's airlines.
- Manufacturers of aircraft and security systems: Many large corporations such as Boeing, Dassault, Thales, Honeywell, etc. They constantly update their systems to face new threats with the advice of the different boards described above.

Because of its complexity and its weight in the economy, breaking the aviation industry's security constitutes a great challenge for hackers and terrorists. Moreover, this industry relies more and more on information and communication technology (ICT). As an industry that is well known for providing one of the safest type of transportation, it is mandatory for all its stakeholders to understand the risks and to prevent any malicious events for the good of the industry, the economy, the population and the environment.

The aviation sector is not immune to the cyber security risks that have been critical issues for all the other industries. Modern aircraft are very complex systems that rely on many transponders to communicate their position to air traffic control. It's quite difficult to hack all systems at once, including the on-board radios and the Aircraft Communications Addressing and Reporting System (ACARS), used to send messages or information about the airplane rather than voice transmissions. Consequently, "an attacker with a deep knowledge of the plane's system could intentionally cause serious problems with its normal operation" (Paganini, 2014). Major cyber-security incidents in the aviation sector strengthen this observation, and the threat is not as recent as one might think.

In her research paper, security specialist Ruben Santamarta exposed the backdoors and remote control of SATCOM aviation radios, reaching the rather alarming conclusion that "the current status of the products [we] analysed makes it almost impossible to guarantee the integrity of thousands of SATCOM devices" (Santamarta, 2014).

It is not just navigation systems that have been subject to cyber-attacks. An attack on the internet in 2006 forced the US Federal Aviation Administration to shut down some of its air traffic control systems in Alaska. In July 2013, an attack led to the shutdown of the passport control systems at the departure terminals at Istanbul airport, causing many flights to be delayed. Finally, an attack that possibly involved malicious hacking and phishing targeted 75 airports in the USA in 2013. These are just a few examples among many more, but they justify the needs to prevent such threats that could lead to dramatic consequences.

Communication between people and devices, the rise of computing performance, price erosion and software developments are all ingredients shared by all the industries that enhance the necessity to consider seriously the cyber threats in the aviation sector. Indeed, aviation security remains a critical topic despite all the investments and measures that have been made, especially when the examples above point out that this threat is not a new trend at all.

One of the major explanation for this new type of threat in this sector is the greater use of computer-based systems: sophisticated air navigation systems, on-board aircraft control and communication systems, airport ground systems including flight information and security screening, day-to-day data management systems.

In the same time, cyber threats have been developed regardless of the industries but in relation with technologies: computer viruses, malicious attacks, etc. Because of an increasing number of travellers, the creation of new modern airports, the introduction of more complex aircraft, the use of IT and advanced computer-based systems, the risks will increase considerably with time. In addition to this, it is important to consider the digitalization of the sector with electronic ticketing for example or the goal of reducing costs by the reduction of manpower for example.

Like any other industry, it is possible to consider two types of cyber security breaches:

1. "Opportunistic": the goal is to exploit mistakes made by internal users like employees using the IT systems with the purpose of causing inconvenience and nuisance to any entity involved in the aviation ecosystem
2. "Calculated and premeditated": it concerns any malicious attacks to disrupt operations or threaten lives. This category is critical as terrorism are fully aware of the potential of technologies and cyber-attacks.

Then, like in the other industry, we can mention different factors that would influence the cyber security strategy:

- There are more and more interactions between people, devices and services. This increase and diversity in the interactions make the paths of attacks less and less predictable
- Innovation and cost reduction made by the ecosystem transform non-existent or unavailable technologies into common goods. Moreover, software is more and more used to provide effective solutions and digital experience to the workers of this industry and passengers. Consequently, this evolution exposes more and more internal and external systems to potential threats.

For example, a report from the NASA (2009) highlights the rise of software complexity in all industries:

- Flight software lines of code has increased 10 times in ten years
- From 1960 to 2000, functionality provided by software to pilots has grown from 8% to 80%

Moreover, despite this new complexity, the aviation systems seem not to be prepared. Indeed, since the creation of the first aviation network, the systems ran isolated and were designed more for high availability than for security.

With the rise of software complexity in the aviation sector, software security cannot be totally guaranteed. This is the reason why it is important to handle vulnerabilities in this sector, to deploy software updates to prevent any attacks and of course to test regularly the security of critical systems.

With the complexity and the high number of stakeholders in this industry, the number and the origins of breaches could be substantial. In the same way, establishing the stakeholder accountable for a breach or an attack could be difficult. Some previous cases in the aviation sector have led to some observations. For example:

- When a vulnerability or a breach is discovered, vendors do not always address or fix it;
- No stakeholder would accept to be accountable for a breach or a vulnerability: the suppliers blame each other, the main manufacturers such as Airbus or Boeing blame the suppliers, the airplane operators blame the manufacturers and so on;
- Critical systems and cabin systems on airplanes are not isolated properly from external threats
- The principal internal communication protocol, Avionics Full Duplex (AFXD), had poor security solutions implemented.

As cyber-attacks against the aviation industry have increased considerably, setting the cyber security as a major concern, all 4 categories of industry stakeholders as pointed out earlier worked together to address these cyber threats.

The major efforts made by these stakeholders are the following:

- With the increase of cyber-attacks in all the industries and the increase of computer-based solutions used, ICAO encourages better and stronger collaboration between all the stakeholders to identify as many threats and risks as possible.
- ICAO organized a discussion to define responsibilities on cyber security for the aviation industry.

- ICAO would like to encourage countries to implement strong cyber security strategy and management. The goal is to implement more policies and measures to prevent any cyber-attacks that could lead to dramatic consequences. This recommendation by the ICAO includes crisis management and business resilience.
- More and more countries started to work on cyber security few years ago.
- More and more airports started to implement measures to secure any IT systems already exposed. They also started to consider upstream the cyber security issues for the future projects.
- With safety as a top priority, IATA conducts yearly audits mandated by governments and provides airlines with a cyber-security toolkit that has a traditional risk assessment approach.
- Finally, manufacturers have made some efforts as well: for instance, Boeing implemented additional security measures on the 777 aircraft to prevent on board hacking of critical computer systems (Federal Register, 2013)

Although a lot of efforts have been made, there still exist a lot of issues to be addressed.

➤ Cyber Europe 2012

On 4 October 2012 more than 500 cyber-security professionals across Europe participated in Cyber Europe 2012, the second pan-European Cyber Exercise. The exercise built on extensive activities at both the national and European level to improve the resilience of critical information infrastructures. As such, Cyber Europe 2012 was a milestone in the efforts to strengthen cyber-crisis cooperation, preparedness and response across Europe (ENISA, 2012).

Cyber Europe 2012 had three **objectives**:

1. Test the effectiveness and scalability of mechanisms, procedures and information flow for public authorities' cooperation in Europe.
2. Explore the cooperation between public and private stakeholders in Europe.
3. Identify gaps and challenges on how large-scale cyber-incidents could be handled more effectively in Europe.

Twenty-nine EU (European Union) and EFTA (European Free Trade Association) Member States were involved in the exercise; 25 of them participated actively in the exercise, while the other four were involved as observers. In addition, several EU Institutions participated. Following up on a key recommendation of Cyber Europe 2010, the private sector actors took part in this exercise. Cooperation between public and private players took place at the national level, while public authorities also cooperated across borders.

Cyber Europe 2012 resulted in the following **recommendations**:

- Cyber Europe 2012 proved valuable in enhancing pan-European cyber-incident management. It is therefore important to continue the efforts and further develop the European cyber exercise area. EU Member States and EFTA countries should cooperate towards new pan-European and national cyber exercises in order to enhance transnational cyber-incident management. The Good Practice Guide on National Exercises, developed by ENISA, provides additional support in this area.

- Future cyber exercises should explore inter-sectoral dependencies and be more focused on specific communities.
- Cyber Europe 2012 provided an opportunity for international-level cooperation and strengthening of the European cyber-incident management community. To foster international cooperation, it is essential to facilitate exchange of good practices in cyber exercises, lessons learned, expertise and the organization of conferences. This will ensure a stronger community that is able to tackle transnational cyber-crises.
- EU Member States and EFTA countries should further improve the effectiveness, scalability of, and familiarity with, existing mechanisms, procedures and information flows for cooperation of public authorities in Europe. Lessons learned from Cyber Europe 2012 provide an excellent starting point.
- All stakeholders in the area of international cyber-crisis cooperation need to be trained on the use of procedures in order to know how to adequately work with them.
- The involvement of private sector organizations as players was of added value to this exercise. Therefore, EU Member States and EFTA countries should consider the involvement of the private sector in future exercises.
- The European cyber-incident management community could be strengthened with input from other European critical sectors (e.g. health, transportation) that are relevant to the handling of large-scale crises.

➤ Cyber Europe 2014

In May 2014, a European-wide cyber warfare exercise - The Cyber Europe 2014 (CE2014) - was organized by the Crete-based European Union Agency for Network and Information Security (ENISA). Representatives of 200 organizations and some 400 cyber security professionals from all the EU member states and those in the EU Free Trade Space (ENISA, 2014).

The event was designed to simulate unrest and political crisis at a pan-European level, and to test cyber security response across public and private sectors. The objective of this first phase was to analyse how the events escalate and de-escalate, to understand these processes at all technical, operational, and strategic levels, as well as to understand the related public affairs issues linked to cyber threats.

The exercise, however, came in for stinging criticism. The main concern was fundamental problems of inter-governmental communication and disparate incident response standards across borders. Also, some believed that the war games might have done little more than act as a communication exercise. Cross-border crises are hard to conceive especially if they are multi-sector, because different sectors will have different vulnerabilities. These war games were not designed to test whether they all had defences that were up to the job of combating the latest malware, only the older recognized malware.

However, the 2014 war game was a step up from previous years with more technical demands of the participants than previously. This was a valuable exercise with as many as 16 different types of case studies, but any real attack would have surprises no-one expected, and the key question of any war game would be how to prepare for the 'unexpected'.

CE2014 demonstrated that strong cross-border cooperation was necessary for the EU member states, and the public and private sector. This kind of cooperation between the EU and EFTA countries was crucial for the strengthening of cross border, transnational cyber-incident management.

A report on CE2014 concluded with five key **findings**:

1. Cyber Europe exercises, as well as any cooperation activity at European level during real cyber crises, build upon existing relations between Member States. ENISA and the Member States will continue to invest in trust building activities to maintain and further develop existing trust.
2. ENISA and the Member States should further develop the operational procedures which drive the cooperation activities during a cyber crisis, taking into account existing and future cooperation frameworks, to bring these procedures to a maturity level similar to those found in other sectors such as civil protection and aviation.
3. ENISA and the Member States will seek further integration with national and regional activities.
4. ENISA will address future Cyber Europe activities as a program containing both trainings as well as small and large-scale exercises, in order to provide a better experience and achieve greater impact.
5. Lastly, ENISA will further develop the Cyber Exercise Platform to offer a richer experience to both players and planners, as well as to support the organization of national and regional exercises, fostering the development of a cyber exercise community.
6. Cyber Europe 2016

Cyber Europe 2016 was the fourth pan-European cyber crisis exercise organised by the European Union Agency for Network and Information Security (ENISA). Over 1 000 participants working mostly in the ICT sector, from public and private organisations from all 28 Member States of the European Union and two from the European Free Trade Association (EFTA), joined in a programme of activities ranging from training sessions and communication checks to technical competitions and cooperation exercises. The exercise simulated a realistic crisis build-up over an actual period of 6 months, culminating in a 48 hours event on 13 and 14 October 2016 (ENISA, 2017).

Cyber Europe 2016 was based on three pillars essential to the successful mitigation of large-scale crises caused by cybersecurity incidents: cooperation at national and international levels and sound cybersecurity capabilities.

First, the exercise fostered cooperation between targets of simulated cybersecurity incidents, security providers and national authorities, shedding light on national-level public–private and private–private cooperation. Participants had to follow existing business processes, agreements, communication protocols and regulations to mitigate effectively the situations presented to them. Such mechanisms were not always in place for all participants, which hindered the overall ability to reach full EU-level situational awareness. The EU network and information security directive identifies many of the associated shortcomings and proposes measures that ENISA and Member States are already implementing to improve the situation.

Second, Cyber Europe 2016 helped participants understand how cybersecurity authorities would cooperate with each other and EU bodies in the event of a large-scale crisis. Undoubtedly, crisis cooperation at EU level is very much maturing and improving. Most, if not all, Member States have come to realise the importance of sharing structured information across national borders. With the active support of ENISA, they have leveraged the benefits of EU-level situational awareness for their

own crisis management activities. Yet despite such progress, Cyber Europe 2016 highlighted, as previous exercises did, the absence of a cooperation framework at EU level for crises stemming from cybersecurity incidents, officially endorsed cooperation procedures or a centralised hub. The creation of the EU CSIRTs Network and the European Commission initiative to publish a crisis cooperation blueprint in 2017 are excellent developments in that regard. They will surely benefit from the detailed findings in this report.

Last, the exercise offered countless opportunities for participants to enhance their cybersecurity capabilities, from their technical and operational expertise to their capacity to handle crisis communication. Organisational and individual cybersecurity preparedness and capabilities in the EU were excellent overall. Technical expertise, business continuity and crisis communications procedures were of a high standard. Nevertheless, the vision required to link technical- and operational-level response activities to strategic crisis management mechanisms was sometimes lacking, which proved detrimental to fostering crisis exit strategies supporting decision-making.

Additionally, many lessons were learned from the use of the prototype platforms developed by ENISA to support cooperation at EU level; they will reflect positively on the development of the EU-level crisis cooperation infrastructure financed by the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF).

A report on CE2016 concluded with these key **findings**:

Participating organisations responded adequately to most challenges they faced during the exercise. Cybersecurity experts employed in a wide array of sectors in the EU demonstrated high levels of expertise and appetite to resolve complex cybersecurity issues. Their ability to cooperate in the most difficult times is an important finding.

No participant questioned the essence of cyber incident cooperation at EU level. Rather, all actors focussed their efforts on lifting the remaining barriers. Such cooperation was particularly insightful and led to a full understanding of all facets of the crisis within a few hours, which supported the swift mitigation of a simulated large-scale attack against EU interests. In particular, the EU Cyber Standard Operational Procedures helped to provide EU-level situational awareness and structured cooperation activities.

The exercise in itself proved to be an excellent opportunity to increase individual and collective knowledge in the field of cybersecurity. Participants developed skills, procedures and relationships. Most importantly, they reiterated their appreciation in the exercise series: 99% indicated interest to participate in the next exercise.

Innovation and transformation were at the heart of Cyber Europe 2016. From a product, process, rhetoric and service perspectives, the exercise planning team, composed of Member States and ENISA representatives, pushed established boundaries to transform the EU cybersecurity society. The European Union Ombudsman underlined this joint effort in March 2017 with an award for excellence in innovation and transformation.

Participants repeatedly asked for more opportunities to test their technical skills regularly against a variety of advanced scenarios. Many were grateful for the multiple options offered by ENISA to involve media, legal and financial policy experts and hope for more to come as leaders across the EU realise that cybersecurity goes beyond information security.

The Cyber Crisis Cooperation Platform prototype developed by ENISA provided numerous insights into technical means supporting EU-level cooperation. These will be of paramount importance in order to ensure the buy-in from Member States in such a cooperation platform, currently under development.

The Cyber Exercise Platform proved to be a powerful tool to plan, conduct and evaluate the exercise. In particular, the simulated environment developed by ENISA supported the crisis build-up in a realistic fashion with an unprecedented emphasis on written and visual storytelling.

Cyber Europe 2016 resulted in the following **recommendations**:

1. Following their revision, the operational procedures which drive the cooperation activities during a cyber crisis should be endorsed by the CSIRTs Network established by the Network and Information Security Directive. Training opportunities on the use of these procedures and tailored exercises should be offered regularly.
2. An EU-level cyber crisis cooperation framework is currently being developed by the European Commission. It should build upon these findings to develop interconnections between cooperation mechanisms, identify and empower key actors, from CSIRTs to law enforcement, and set a clear vision for the future of EU cyber response.
3. Future Cyber Europe should focus on cooperation activities on technical and operational topics. Other options should be pursued to offer training and exercise opportunities on a variety of other topics increasingly associated with cybersecurity. In particular, ENISA should support EU-wide capacity building on cyber crisis communication.

➤ Research Findings Elsewhere

Problem: despite the fact that lack of security of commercial-grade multi-million ADS-B technology has been widely covered by previous academic studies, and more recently by the hacking community, the fundamental architectural and design problems of ADS-B have never been addressed and fixed. As noted by Costin and Francillon (2012), it has been demonstrated that a low-cost hardware setup combined with moderate software effort is sufficient to induce potentially dangerous safety and operational perturbations via the exploitation of missing basic security mechanisms such as message authentication. Also, given the efforts in terms of time and money invested so far, it is unclear why such mission-critical and safety-related protocol does not have a security chapter in the main requirements specifications document.

Approach: raising awareness among the academic, industrial and policy-making sectors on the fact that critical infrastructure technologies such as ADS-B require real security in-place in order to operate safely and according to the requirements.

Directions for future research: not identified

Problem: recently, as a result of the rapid increase in air traffic, the construction of the CNS/ATM next-generation ATC system has been accelerated. To ensure the safe navigation of more aircraft in

limited air space, CNS/ATM has to predict accurate traffic flows on the basis of flight plans and accurate positioning of aircraft. ADS-B is able to provide accurate navigation information, such as the location, altitude, and identification information of aircraft; consequently, it is the core technology in CNS/ATM. However, the transmission of ADS-B data between ADS-B sensor and ATC is carried out in an unencrypted (or unprotected) communication channel; therefore, it is vulnerable to security threats such as spoofing, eavesdropping, and data modification (Lee et al 2014).

Approach: the ideal method of countering this security threat toward ADS-B would be to issue X.509 certificates to all planes and provide a certificate-based security service, but this is difficult in reality. As proposed by Lee et al 2014, a more realistic approach would be to protect the ADS-B data transmitted between the ADS-B sensor and ATC. In the proposed method, the ADS-B sensor is identified using SPKI four tuple certificates and further authorized to transmit ADS-B data to ATC using SPKI six tuple certificates. An authorized ADS-B receives symmetric keys from ATC and utilizes them to encrypt the ADS-B data. It is believed that application of this method to the next-generation ATC system could facilitate an effective response to the security threats to ADS-B data transmitted between ADS-B sensors and ATC, such as spoofing, eavesdropping, and data modification.

Directions for future research: implementing the proposed security framework, improving it through validation at the laboratory level, analysing the benefits of application to CNS/ATM, and performing tests to link the actual data with an ATC system in operation.

Problem: securing ADS-B and preventing attackers from exploiting its open-text open broadcast nature in order to launch attacks against ATC operations.

Approach: a novel intrusion detection system operating with minimal overhead and demonstrating promising performance values (Kacem et al 2016).

Directions for future research: not identified

Problem: although simulation can support the operation of critical infrastructures in various levels and applications, it is easy to overlook the difficulties involved in setting up the simulation testbed with enough fidelity and level of realism to ensure its effectiveness in supporting these activities.

Approach: a system based solely on open source tools and designed to support activities that cannot be conducted in the real environment. Current features are already powerful enough to perform a variety of studies, including the one presented in ADS-B, which has been a much-discussed topic in the literature recently (Monteiro et al 2016).

Directions for future research: developing an automatic pilot module to comprehend voice commands, execute the instructions of controllers and reply to the orders using voice synthesizers.

Problem: with the increase in the number of UAVs in the sky, the need for the UAV traffic management arises. Unmanned air traffic management system (UTMS), especially in the urban airspace, could be considered as a critical infrastructure, which – if disrupted – can lead to severe monetary losses and even casualties. As a computerized system, UTMS is susceptible to cyber-attacks

ranging from cyber vandalism to cyber warfare. An emphasis on building security into products counters the all-too-common tendency for security to be an afterthought in development. Addressing existing vulnerabilities and patching security holes as they are found can be a hit-and-miss process.

Approach: using the “secure by design” philosophy to systems engineering when the system is designed from the start to be secure. This approach contrasts with less rigorous approaches including security through obscurity, security through minority and security through obsolescence, which have proven themselves to be ineffective (Sidorov et al 2017).

Directions for future research: not identified

Problem: cyber security does not fully comprise technological solutions and is actually a three-fold notion based on technology, people, and processes. People are considered one of the most influential factors in cyber security. They could knowingly or unknowingly compromise systems, could wilfully or by negligence violate protocols, and might not be aware of consequences of their actions from the point of view of cyber security.

Approach: approaches to human resources management and personnel education need to be designed with cyber security in mind. Moreover, processes are required to ensure sustainable cyber security. Internal processes of the organization need to be designed to include technology maintenance, security incident response actions, security incident information management, self-adjustments in view of changes in cyber threat landscape, etc. It is also important to ensure that people and processes are connected with every process having a manager as the authority for reinforcing the process. Properly designed and setup technology takes care of all the heavy lifting in ensuring cyber security: encryption, resiliency, fool-proofing, filtering, reducing human factor, etc. (Sidorov et al 2017).

Directions for future research: not identified

Problem: the need for increased surveillance due to increase in flight volume in remote or oceanic regions outside the range of traditional radar coverage has been fulfilled by the advent of space-based Automatic Dependent Surveillance – Broadcast (ADS-B) Surveillance systems. ADS-B systems have the capability of providing air traffic controllers with highly accurate real-time flight data. ADS-B is dependent on digital communications between aircraft and ground stations of the air route traffic control centre (ARTCC); however, these communications are not secured. Anyone with the appropriate capabilities and equipment can interrogate the signal and transmit their own false data; this is known as spoofing. The possibility of this type of attacks decreases the situational awareness of the airspace concerned.

Approach: designing a secure transmission framework to prevent ADS-B signals from being spoofed. Three alternative methods of securing ADS-B signals can be evaluated: hashing, symmetric encryption, and asymmetric encryption. Research is needed to determine the security strength of the design alternatives. Feasibility criteria can be determined by comparative analysis of alternatives. Economic implications and possible collision risk can be determined from simulations that model the airspace concerned (Amin et al. 2014).

Directions for future research: not identified

Problem: a space-based system plays a vital role within national critical infrastructures. They are being incorporated into energy distribution software, advanced air-traffic management applications, rail signalling systems, etc. Unfortunately, these infrastructures are susceptible to a broad range of security threats; the end users of communications, location sensing and timing applications often fail to understand these infrastructures. Potential cyber-attacks may overthrow many of the safety assumptions that support the condition of critical space-based services. These safety assumptions are based on standard forms of hazard analysis that ignore cyber-security considerations. This is a significant limitation when, for instance, security attacks can simultaneously exploit multiple vulnerabilities in a manner that would never occur without a deliberate enemy seeking to damage space-based systems and ground infrastructures. Moreover, it is unclear how to represent and reason about the safety concerns that are created by the diverse security threats to GNSS architectures, including jamming, spoofing and the insider threat to ground based systems. Such concerns invalidate many of the assumptions that support the provision of critical services.

Approach: identifying attack scenarios that justify the allocation of additional design resources so that safety barriers can be strengthened to increase the flexibility against security threats. One approach would be to extend the application of argumentation techniques such as GSN from safety-related applications to represent security argumentation. The ultimate goal would be providing an integrated, risk-based approach to the identification of attack scenarios that can help assess the resilience of safety cases to security threats (Sharma et al. 2016).

Directions for future research: not identified

Problem: security of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) against cyber-attacks is an important yet challenging problem. Since most cyber-attacks happen in erratic ways, it is difficult to describe them systematically. Deception attacks (or false data injection attacks), which are performed by tampering with system components or data, are not of particular concern if they can be easily detected by the system's monitoring system. However, intelligent cyber attackers can avoid being detected by the monitoring system by carefully design cyber-attacks. The main objective then is to investigate the performance of such stealthy deception attacks from the system's perspective.

Approach: investigating three kinds of stealthy deception attacks according to the attacker's ability to compromise the system. Based on the information about the dynamics of the system and existing hypothesis testing algorithms, one can derive the necessary and sufficient conditions under which the attacker could perform each kind of attack without being detected (Kwon et al. (2013).

Directions for future research: using the conditions under which the deception attacks successfully bypass the monitoring system, one could not only evaluate the vulnerability level of a given CPS, but also develop secure system design methodologies against stealthy deception attacks.

Problem: currently UAVs are used for a wide range of missions such as border surveillance, reconnaissance, transportation and armed attacks. UAVs are presumed to provide their services at any

time, be reliable, automated and autonomous. To fulfil their missions, UAVs need to collect and process data. The amount and kind of information enclosed make UAVs an extremely interesting target for espionage and endangers UAVs of theft, manipulation and attacks (Hartmann and Steup 2013).

Approach: developing a scheme for the risk assessment of UAVs based on the provided service and communication infrastructures. The components to be analysed could be the type of communication system, data storage, sensor system, environmental factors, and fault handling mechanisms. Risk can then be defined as the result of the product of the susceptibility of an UAV, the probability of occurrence of a specific attack on a component's vulnerability, and the severity of the attack.

Directions for future research: not identified

Problem: current autopilot systems for UAVs were not built with cyber security considerations taken into account and are thus vulnerable to cyber-attack. To develop a cyber secure autopilot architecture, a study is needed on potential cyber threats and vulnerabilities of the current autopilot systems. The ultimate goal would be to build a controller the current UAV autopilot system making it robust to cyber-attacks (Kim et al, 2012).

Approach: to attain the goal, one needs to develop a more sophisticated and accurate model to simulate the GPS attack coupled with a sensitivity study. Then, one needs to develop a collision avoidance algorithm for the ADS-B attack scenario and carry out a numerical analysis on simulated multiple aircraft.

Directions for future research:

- One should focus on more sophisticated attacks that utilize multiple points of attack or multiple methods.
- One should also evaluate possibilities for a coordinated attack where the attacker uses several attacks in a certain manner to induce more effective faults into the autopilot system.
- One should consider possibilities for the disguised attack where the attacker can mask an attack to induce a false reaction from the autopilot in order to remedy the attack.
- A purely analytical approach could also bring valuable insights; for instance, certain Kalman filtering algorithms might be vulnerable to a special form of induced error in measurements which cannot be detected.
- There is an acute need for developing metrics for cyber-attacks; until now a metric for measuring either likelihood or a damage potential of cyber-attacks on a UAV autopilot does not exist.
- Algorithms for detecting cyber-attacks need to be developed.

Predictions up-to-2025 and evolutionary progress up to 2050

Blockchain technology

Although maturity of blockchain technology is still relatively low and the technological know-how is still concentrated to a small group of blockchain users in the world, blockchain technology (more

globally known as distributed ledger technology or DLT) is becoming more and more extensively accepted as the best unbreakable solution for securing Internet communications.

Findings show that while there were only a small number of companies active in the enterprise DLT (distributed ledger technology) space in 2013, interest in 'blockchain technology' quickly grew in 2014 with a significant increase in the number of companies providing DLT service. 2015 was the year that the DLT industry took off in terms of new entrants, with the number of start-ups growing by 108% over 2014 (Hileman & Rauchs, 2017). According to his study existing DLT deployment plans: 15% of OPSIs (Other Public Sector Institutions) plan to deploy DLT-based applications this year, and another 23% plan to do so within the next two years; the timetable for central banks is more conservative than for OPSIs (most of their deployment plans consider periods longer than 10 years).

There are however several drawbacks and limitations previously described (throughput, latency, size and bandwidth, possibility of a 51% attack, wasted resources, usability, versioning, hard forks, multiple chains and scalability), that made its application in aviation, air transport and air traffic management uncertain, and that will be required further research in the coming years. It is expected that when more Blockchain solutions are taken in use with larger numbers of users, it will trigger the need to conduct more research on the challenges and limitations, particularly in topics related to scalability, security and privacy

In 2017 a few companies start to design applications of Blockchain in the aviation industry:

- Aeron (<https://aeron.aero/#en>) is working on the development of a smart blockchain based solution called "airline in a pocket". It includes a pilot's application that is used by a pilot for personal flight logging. A company application that collects and verifies data from aircraft operators, maintenance organizations, flight schools and fixed base operators. In case of any mismatch in data between any Aeron data source with either the Air Traffic Control, pilot, or operator, aviation authorities can quickly detect and eliminate the problem. Aviation authorities can also detect any pilots operating with an expired license. As a consumer, or flight school student, you have access to the verified global database through aerotrips.com. The project is expected to be fully available within two years.
- The BASTONET project (www.bastonet.com), based on the Ethereum network, seeks to engineer the blockchain use in the airline and travel industry, in booking and ticketing processes of airlines, and in transfer of data and value within the network in association with other airline services like air cargo movement, crew management, passenger data transfer and aircraft maintenance scheduling, loyalty programs, etc.
- Airbus has been working to identify several business challenges worth addressing with blockchain. These include instances of a high cost of trust, a slow process but time-sensitive interactions, compliance issues, high overhead cost for data reconciliation and multiple parties with whom to share data. Ideas that emerged as viable use cases include 3D printing and the applicability of blockchain to distributed manufacturing at a local level; keeping identity, achievements and certificates attached to each pilot is immutable data; dispute management in which complex transactions can obscure the fact that money is unnecessarily blocked; and quality process tracking, which would benefit from greater transparency and an early-warning trigger system.
- The Blockchain.aero Consortium is promoting the concept of Proof-of-flight protocol and McFly token based on blockchain technology to speed up on the air taxi market, (invoice,

charge and land), as a way to use eVTOLs and other infrastructure elements (pads, chargers, maintenance and repair shops) and pay for that use. They full service is expected to be deployed by 2020. This technology is envisaged as an enabler that pave the way for the introduction of global single passenger tokens, as blockchain technology offers us the potential to provide a new way of using biometrics. It could enable biometrics to be used across borders, and at all airports, without the passenger's details being stored by the various authorities.

All these previous applications addressed individual not interconnected aspect of the aviation an air transport industry not involve in real time operation. All represents individual company's initiatives to take advantage in the short term of the blockchain technology as a way to get contact with it, in a safe and profitable manner.

In 2017 SITA has published research on blockchain technology FlightChain, conducted with British Airways, Heathrow, Geneva Airport, and Miami International Airport. FlightChain was designed as a private permissions blockchain—using Ethereum and Hyperledger-Fabric—which stores flight information and uses a smart contract to reconcile any conflicting data. During the trials conducted between British Airways, Geneva Airport, Heathrow and Miami International Airport, FlightChain handled and stored more than two million flight changes. The project has demonstrated that blockchain is a viable technology to provide a single source of truth for data for airlines and airports, specifically for real-time flight information.

Blockchain is also being explored as a way to address drone cybersecurity by keeping a high-speed, assured ledger of airspace activity and information regarding the drone and its operator and distributing it to all appropriate parties.

Some initiatives are also been put in place to apply blockchain to secure VoIP (<https://www.dyrnan.com/enterprise/>), that if prove to be efficiency might be also translated to the aviation domain for real time pilot controller communication. In 2017 the first pioneer of blockchain-based VoIP service was born: EncryptoTel, a company that raised \$3 million during a crowd funding campaign (another sign of blockchain's significance) and is expected to launch by the summer of 2018. The company is promising a secure VoIP and B2B blockchain communications infrastructure for its service. According to EncryptoTel, a hosted PBX provider available to anyone in the world, users of different hosted PBX sources can start and accept encrypted VoIP calls while also get access to popular messenger applications.

An effective adoption of blockchain as a standard in the industry will required a more coordinated and regulated approach, based on shared standards and solid agreement between the stakeholders involved. The development cycle of these blockchain applications is around two years. The development of real-time aviation application build upon standards and stakeholders agreement will be subject to the longer development cycles of the aviation, considering that for this purpose the technology has been validated in lab and in other environments (TRL4) but it still to be validated in relevant environment (TRL5).

As with many emerging technologies, there are still concerns in the market regarding the security and reliability of blockchain. The development of standards and regulations for blockchain has a role to play in establishing market confidence and supporting the eventual commercial implementation of blockchain technology. Australia will host the first international blockchain standards meeting for

ISO/TC 307 in April 2017. JWS will publish further updates as new developments in the standards and Australian law relating to blockchain arise. These standards are recognized temporal and are not applicable to aviation by itself. It has to be considered that the full cycle of standards development will still be accomplished in aviation after the technology have achieved TRL 9 (system proven in an operational environment) for critical safety aviation real time applications

➤ Future of ATM cybersecurity

The reliance of future ATM on wireless networks and interfaces, implementation of Internet Protocols and VoIP for air to ground communications will make it more vulnerable to malicious attack unless enough protections are including in the system design. SESAR and NextGen will radically increase the 'attack surface' for any future malware (Johnson). Neither of SESAR nor NEXTGEN have define appropriate security standards at both physical and logical. In 2015, separate reports were published looking at the vulnerability of both the NextGen and SESAR systems to cyber -attacks and how best to protect against them. Both NextGen and SESAR are introducing a computer system named System Wide Information Management (SWIM), which will handle all ATM information including aeronautical, flight, aerodrome, meteorological, air traffic flow, and surveillance. Both reports note that introduction of SWIM, which represents a more interconnected ATM system that operates through an Internet Protocol (IP) network, means there are increased cyber security risks.

Moreover, the inherent vulnerabilities of the Radio frequency-based ATM technologies' have not been sufficiently addressed not overcome by the future ATM (such as those of unencrypted ADS-b, Radio Aids, etc.). The current ADS-B system openly transmits sensitive aircraft information over a shared link, allowing flight information to become available to everyone with the right ADS-B equipment.

To avoid these limitations some authors (Atanasov & Chenane , 2013) recommend:

- Authentication mechanism to be introduced on NextGen/SESAR to reduce the complexity of detecting malicious actors,
- Use of a combination of secret keys and secret numbers will allow the communication between aircraft to aircraft and aircraft to ground to be authenticated,
- Use of digital certificates, message validation to reduce the risk of malicious activities on the aircraft infrastructure. Digital certificates should be implemented at different phases of operation, when the aircraft is parked on the ground or when it is airborne. In addition, they can be embedded in an individual device of the aircraft network or one common digital certificate can be used for the entire network. Defining common criteria to implement and manage digital certificates on an aircraft can be of a great benefit to the airline industry allowing the lifecycle process of the digital certificate to be closely and carefully inspected and maintained.

More than a dozen wireless technologies are currently used by air traffic communication systems during different flight phases. From a conceptual perspective, all of them are insecure as security was never part of their design. Recent contributions from academic and hacking communities have exploited this inherent vulnerability to demonstrate attacks on some of these technologies. The International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), EUROCONTROL, and the FAA have started planning for further upgrades of the current communications systems and are seeking to develop new data links.

Specifically, L-band Digital Aeronautical Communications System (L-DACS) and Aeronautical Mobile Airport Communications System (Aero-MACS) are supposed to replace the current VHF system. Since these systems can provide much higher data throughput comparing to the existing data links, some of the applications currently provided by other technologies could also utilize these new technologies one day. Thankfully, L-DACS and AeroMACS have begun to at least consider the issue of wireless security and some corresponding designs are already included by the specifications or will be in the future.

Unfortunately, L-DACS is still in the very early specification phase and in line with typical technological cycles in aviation will not be deployed before the 2030s (International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), 2013). Furthermore, since its specification is not finished – many parts are up in the air and there are still competing proposals – they could strongly benefit from an immediately increased awareness about security concerns in aviation, which we aim to provide with our work.

AeroMACS takes the form of a profile of IEEE 802.16- 2009 (IEEE Std 802.16-2009, 2009), known as WiMAX. It intends to provide a surface data link for use at the airport, allowing ATC, airlines, and airports to communicate with the aircraft (Fistas, 2016). It has line-of-sight range of up to 3 km per cell and uses commodity radios to communicate. While the current standards include cryptography, making it a serious step forward, AeroMACS will not solve the security problems currently found in aviation. Besides the prevalent issue of long deployment time frames (the beginning of deployment is not projected before the middle of the next decade), many security questions such as the protection of management frames are still undecided (SESAR, 2014). Most importantly, AeroMACS will only be able to replace current data links on the ground and in the immediate vicinity of an airport, leaving the vast amount of air traffic communication unprotected. AeroMACS is further along in the development cycle compared to L-DACS, with test deployments going on at some airports around the world. However, at the time of writing, many of the necessary avionics standards and specifications were still in the planning phase. Thus, it was not possible to include it in our survey but, like L-DACS, it should see strong input from the security community as soon as possible.

Possible or Predictable Breakthroughs

- The prospect of quantum computing and the post quantum cryptography.

Although not yet in existence, but theoretically viable, the vision of quantum computing and its capacity to decrypt secure network traffic captured and archived today²¹, raises concerns about the long-term robustness of encrypted solutions, including blockchain applications. The achievement of quantum computing may destabilize all these technologies and applications.

Currently, the lead developer of quantum computing technology is Google. They expect to have a 49-qubit quantum computer this year⁶. For hardware, **the key metric in the roadmap for quantum computer is building scalable qubits with 2-qubit gate errors below 0.1-0.2%** (Martinis, 2015). For software, a new "quantum-supremacy" test that can demonstrate the exponential power of a quantum processor by checking its output with a classical computer, which is intractable for even the world's most advanced classical supercomputer beyond 42-50 qubits will be described. The aim of

²¹ [2] "The quantum clock is ticking on encryption – and your data is under threat", Wired 2016, <http://www.wired.co.uk/article/quantum-computers-quantum-security-encryption>

google is to perform this experiment in the next 2 years. Google's quantum computer roadmap plans commercialisation of the technology in 5 year and IBM is feeling similarly optimistic.

Now that Google and other companies involved in quantum computing have mastered much of the fundamental science behind creating high-quality superconducting qubits, the big challenge facing these firms is scaling these systems and reducing their error rates. Alan Ho, engineer in Google's quantum AI lab, predicts that it will be 2027 before we have error-corrected quantum computers, so useful devices are still some way off.

The projection by the experts is that in the 2030s, there will be quantum computers significantly better than super computers today, but they most likely won't be accessible to governments and companies until the 2040s. Eventually at 2050s they'll shrink down to a size and cost viable for consumer use.

Besides this long-term projection for quantum computing, the magnitude of concerns is enough for researchers across the world to the study of new methods for online encryption and the hiding of messages, known as **Post-Quantum Cryptography**.

Researchers add complexity to the algorithms that encode our messages while hackers attempt to break them. For now, researchers are able to outpace the majority of these malicious attempts. However, quantum computing would compel the use of keys so long that most public key systems in use today would not be practical. This necessitates a complete redesign of the algorithms involved in online encryption.

There is currently no standard of encryption against a quantum computing attack. But there are known quantum-safe algorithms.

The U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology, which in December 2016 launched a [post-quantum crypto project](#) designed to identify quantum-resistant public-key cryptographic algorithms. It has been recognized by the experts that full transition to cryptograph alternatives takes a long time (possibly > 10 years) in any industry, and these times will be much higher in aviation because of the high level of interoperability and standardization.

➤ Quantum Communications

Quantum communication is a field of applied quantum physics closely related to quantum information processing and quantum teleportation. It's most interesting application is protecting information channels against eavesdropping by means of quantum cryptography.

The most well-known and developed application of quantum cryptography is quantum key distribution (QKD). QKD describes the use of quantum mechanical effects to perform cryptographic tasks or to break cryptographic systems.

Quantum communication encryption is secure against any kind of interception because information is encoded in a quantum particle in such a way that it will be destroyed as soon as the system detects any intrusion attempts. The principle of operation of a QKD system is quite straightforward: two parties (Alice and Bob) use single photons that are randomly polarized to states representing ones and zeroes to transmit a series of random number sequences that are used as keys in cryptographic communications. Both stations are linked together with a quantum channel and a classical channel. Alice generates a random stream of qubits that are sent over the quantum channel. Upon reception

of the stream Bob and Alice — using the classical channel — perform classical operations to check if an eavesdropper has tried to extract information on the qubits stream. The presence of an eavesdropper is revealed by the imperfect correlation between the two lists of bits obtained after the transmission of qubits between the emitter and the receiver. One important component of virtually all proper encryption schemes is true randomness which can elegantly be generated by means of quantum optics.

Recently China has taken one more step forward towards achieving success in Quantum communication technology and launched the World's 1st 'Hack-Proof' Quantum Communication Satellite into orbit aboard a Long March-2D rocket in order to test the fundamental laws of quantum mechanics at space. The satellite, dubbed Quantum Science Satellite, is designed to develop a 'Hack-Proof' communications system in this age of global electronic surveillance and cyber-attacks by transmitting uncrackable encryption keys from space to the ground. But if successful, the QUESS satellite would vastly expand the range of un-hackable communication to long distances as well.

KEY TOPIC T5.6 – THE BLOCKCHAIN PROCESS AS AN EXAMPLE OF CYBERSECURITY

Airport transportation systems are cyber-physical systems that serve passengers, air traffic system under supervision of human controllers or unmanned. It is forecasted that the volume of these operations will grow more than recent years. Therefore, cyber-physical system will become more important to work uninterrupted and secure. According to Sampigethaya and Poovendran (2013) aviation information systems contain physical components, including electronics, hardware, infrastructure, and humans which use digital computing, storage, software, or data networking to generate, process, present, and consume data. However, the increasing density of these interactions between physical and cyber systems warrant a surgical consideration of cyber-physical interactions and potential performance risks from cyber and physical threats. Authors demonstrated 'cyber' layer benefits for helping future aircraft, airports, and freight movement systems to overcome 21st century challenges.

In another study Johnson (2012) studied air traffic management systems safety for developing a technology roadmap and proposed the extreme need on raising awareness about the potential threats to safety-related systems amongst regulators and senior management. He stressed that without greater strategic leadership there would be security breaches that might leave major vulnerabilities.

It is well-known that there is a great amount of studies regarding Industry 4.0 and Internet of Things applications. Furthermore, same vulnerability problems arise on these issues also. Hence, it is thought to create an analogy and mention about a growing research trend on Blockchain technologies.

Globalization become more reasonable with the developments in network technologies and internet. In this age, digital platforms changing the business models and whole society by enabling connected structure via cloud-based systems (Kushida et al., 2011; Pon et al., 2014; van Alstyne et al. 2016). This perspective can enable a light-weight financial system, inter-organizational record-keeping and multiparty data aggregation (Greenspan, 2016).

One of these technologies is Blockchain which is accepted as a general-purpose technology (GPT) today like steam engine, electricity, and the internet examples (Catalini and Gans, 2016). GPTs typically lead to subsequent innovation and productivity gains across multiple industry verticals, sustaining

new technological paradigms and economic growth for multiple years (Bresnahan and Trajtenberg, 1995; Helpman and Trajtenberg, 1998; Rosenberg and Trajtenberg, 2001; Moser and Nicholas, 2004; Basu and Fernald, 2007). According to Naughton (2016) Blockchain technology will be the most important IT invention of our age.

When the historical background of Blockchain examined it can be seen that Satoshi Nakamoto proposed Bitcoin as an electronic payment system based on a decentralized peer-to-peer network, without the need for an intermediation in a White paper published in 2008 (Nakamoto, 2008). The Blockchain platform is created for Cryptocurrency exchange by Nakamoto but it is not mentioned in the report (Mattila, 2016). However, the technology used in Blockchain gives insights many other scholars with different application areas today. Underlying technology came with Bitcoin is Blockchain which is a protocol and widely acknowledged as a major breakthrough in fault-tolerant distributed computing, after decades of research in this field.

Briefly Blockchain can be defined as a distributed ledger that contains all transaction executed in the Bitcoin network. This technology described with three words as disintermediated, censorship-resistant, and tamper-proof (Seppala et al., 2016). The ledger network is open, and participants do not need to trust each other to interact. All transactions are verified and recorded by the nodes of the network through cryptographic algorithms, without supervisors, central authority, human intervention, and any other third-party organizations. The reliability of network is provided by the majority of nodes even some of them dishonest or malicious. For making human intervention or controlling authority unnecessary verification is performed by a mathematical mechanism called proof-of-work. Proof-of-work systems runs by "mining"²² and "mining" does not serve the purpose of verifying transactions, but of building a credible commitment against an attack. Consensus about the true state of a distributed ledger therefore emerges and becomes stronger as time (and blocks) go by. If a bad actor wanted to reverse a past transaction it would have to spend a disproportionate amount of resources to do so. This is the result of the bad actor not only having to outpace the growth rate of the legitimate chain, but also of having to recompute all blocks after the one that is being manipulated. Since the network always takes the longest, valid chain as the true state of the ledger (i.e. as the "consensus"), the task of altering a past block of transactions and imposing it on the rest of the network becomes increasingly difficult as the chain is extended. As a result, in proof-of-work systems, a blockchain is only as secure as the amount of computing power dedicated to mining it. This generates economies of scale and a positive feedback loop between network effects and security: as more participants use a cryptocurrency, the value of the underlying token increases (because the currency becomes more useful), which in turn attracts more miners (due to higher rewards), ultimately increasing the security of the ledger.

Main idea of Blockchain protocol is decentralization and permission-less attendance. However, there are different blockchains as permissioned, private, public etc. The steps of Blockchain protocol can be demonstrated in the Figure 5.79:

²² Mining: Nodes in the network compete to solve a mathematical puzzle that requires the consumption of computing power. Once the puzzle solved the new block of transactions is accepted by the network and committed to the Blockchain. The network nodes which is called miners rewarded with newly generated coins.

Figure 5.79 - Blockchain Process

(Source: <https://blockgeeks.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/09/infographics0517-01-1.png> Access Date: 19.10.2017)

It is clear with the explanation of blockgeeks.com that blockchain process is paperless, disintermediated, unaltered, reliable and free. These characteristics make this system more popular especially for reducing transaction costs at first. These costs are; the cost of verification and the cost of networking (Catalini and Gans, 2016). By using blockchain protocol, for the first time in history value could be reliably transferred between two distant, untrusting parties without the need of a costly intermediary.

However, Blockchain technology has also some technical challenges and limitations that have been identified. Swan (2015) presents seven technical challenges and limitations for the adaptation of Blockchain technology in the future:

Throughput: The potential throughput of issues in the Bitcoin network is currently between 4 to 7 tps (transactions per second) and it is limited when compared to VISA and PayPal.

Latency: To create sufficient security for a Bitcoin transaction block, it takes currently roughly 10 minutes to complete one transaction. To achieve efficiency in security, more time has to be spent on a block, because it has to outweigh the cost of double spending²³ attacks. Bitcoin protects against double spending by verifying each transaction added to the block chain, to ensure that the inputs for the transaction have not been spent previously. This makes latency a big issue in Blockchain currently. Making a block and confirming the transaction should happen in seconds, while maintaining security. To complete a transaction e.g. in VISA takes only a few seconds, which is a huge advantage compared to Blockchain.

²³ Double-spending is the result of successful spending of money more than once.

Size and bandwidth: At the moment, the size of a Blockchain in the Bitcoin network is over 100GB (December 2016 - <http://www.coinfox.info/news/6700-bitcoin-blockchain-size-reaches-100-gb> Access Date 19.10.2017). When the throughput increases to the levels of VISA, Blockchain could grow 214PB in each year. The Bitcoin community assumes that the size of one block is 1MB, and a block is created every ten minutes. Therefore, there is a limitation in the number of transactions that can be handled (on average 500 transaction in one block). If the Blockchain needs to control more transactions, the size and bandwidth issues have to be solved.

Security: The current Blockchain has a possibility of a 51% attack. In a 51% attack a single entity would have full control of the majority of the network's mining hash-rate and would be able to manipulate Blockchain. To overcome this issue, more research on security is necessary.

Wasted resources: Mining Bitcoin wastes huge amounts of energy (\$15million/day). The waste in Bitcoin is caused by the Proof-of-Work effort. There are some alternatives in industry fields, such as proof-of-stake. With Proof-of-Work, the probability of mining a block depends on the work done by the miner. However, in Proof-of-Stake, the resource that is compared is the amount of Bitcoin a miner holds. For example, someone holding 1% of the Bitcoin can mine 1% of the "Proof-of-Stake blocks". The issue with wasted resources needs to be solved to have more efficient mining in Blockchain.

Usability: The Bitcoin API for developing services is difficult to use. There is a need to develop a more developer-friendly API for Blockchain. This could resemble REST APIs.

Versioning, hard forks, multiple chains: A small chain that consists of a small number of nodes has a higher possibility of a 51% attack. Another issue emerges when chains are split for administrative or versioning purposes.

Beyond these limitations according to Yli-Huumo et al. (2016) scalability is also an issue that needs to be solved for future needs. Therefore, to identify and understand the current status of research conducted on Blockchain, it is important to gather all relevant research. It is then possible to evaluate what challenges and questions have been tackled and answered, and what are the most problematic issues in Blockchain at the moment.

Due to the fact that the maturity of blockchain technology is still relatively low, the technological know-how is still concentrated to a small group of blockchain users in the World. However, in a decade the Blockchain platform has been approved with its bespoke characteristics. Hence, the idea behind it make the technology became widespread and it can be envisioned that the perspective will have potential to be improved with these common applications. For today there are many application areas of Blockchain and here some of them are mentioned.

As an irreversible and tamper-proof public records repository for documents, contracts, properties, and assets, the blockchain can be used to embed information and instructions, with a wide range of applications from private to public (Atzori, 2015). The most popular application is smart contracts which can be described as tamper-proof, self-executing and automatically enforceable. Based on Mattilla et al. (2017) American cryptographer Nick Szabo published an article in which he outlined the concept of smart contracts in 1994 at first. However, because of the immature technology and IT infrastructure at that time the idea couldn't have opportunity to be applied. Beyond Szabo's smart contract definition today smart contracts are accepted as a set of promises in a digital form including protocols within which the parties perform on these promises. Blockchain technology enable smart

contracts to be programmed and embedded to the system easily. Moreover, it can be envisioned that these smart contract systems may be improved with self-execution and self-enforcement to be fully automatized in autonomous organizations. With these improvements in smart contracts it is envisioned to reach Decentralized Autonomous Organization/Corporations/ Societies (DAOs/DACs/DASs). In this concept, self-sufficient agents derived from artificial intelligence and capable to execute tasks without human involvement, for which the blockchain can provide additional functionality. DAOs operate independently of their developers. In their structure, humans are moved from the centre of the organization to its outskirts, as the system is used to organize human activity algorithmically. An open organization based on smart contracts may solve the problem of bad leadership or issues with the transparency of the organization. However, if left unregulated and ungoverned, errors in the programming code may prove to be very harmful or even dangerous. The DAO is in development stage and so it reveals new types of risks. The organizational character of The DAO in itself raises the question of, for instance, the distribution of liability for damages within such new types of applications. In addition, it involves ties to the question of determining the correct legal entity in economic activity based on new models of co-operation, as is the case with The DAO. Hence, developing technology is not only adequate for making the application common, but also social side should be handled with a holistic perspective.

Smart property concept is another application area and applied to digital ownership of tangible and intangible assets. By the way it can change the patent system with a distributed perspective and can democratize the triadic perspective. By embedding patent system into blockchain, idea-owners do not need third-party approval but need acceptance by nodes in the network. The execution of instructions by a cryptographic code with protection of participants against risks of fraud and a significant reduction of management overheads. Because of the remarkable advantages related to automation, transparency, auditability and cost-effectiveness, the blockchain may represent a disruptive innovation for many varieties of contracts and business activities.

Decentralized voting system may be demonstrated as an important application area for blockchain for public administration field. Tamper-proof ballots and election results can create transparency and strengthen democracy. Due to the fact that blockchains can be designed to be public yet anonymous, anyone can easily verify the voting outcome and also check that their own vote has been taken into account accordingly, while still maintaining ballot secrecy. Blockchain technology can therefore help to reduce corruption in political systems and act as a safeguard against rigged elections.

Blockchain technology may be used in improving IoT with smart, censorship-resistant, tamper-proof, and disintermediated data interchange. This may add value to industry 4.0 applications also with same technology perspective.

Another market may be music industry for applying Blockchain technology. According to report of Middlesex University (2016), Blockchain technology could revolutionize the music industry with a networked database for music copyright information, fast payments, transparency in the chain and Access to alternative sources of capital. As can be seen in the application examples, the idea behind blockchain technology, which may be called as a paradigm, has been becoming popular evolutionary.

Because of these evolutionary improvements in Blockchain, Swan (2015), described blockchain technology as "fundamental for forward progress in society as Magna Charta or the Rosetta Stone". Again, based on Mattila (2016) blockchain technology is shifting society in two aspects. Firstly,

blockchain technology enables directly and reliable transactions of any assets over the internet between any parties by providing censorship-resistant, disintermediated, tamper-proof digital platforms (Mattila & Seppälä, 2015; Mattila, 2016). Secondly, for enterprise- and industry- level systems, blockchain technology is providing efficiency gains on top of existing structures by removing the constant need for actively intermediated data-synchronization and concurrency control by a trusted third party (Mattila, 2016; Mattila et al., 2016). Therefore, blockchain platform can be described as more democratic and equal for all nodes in the network. Main idea is accepting all parties sharing the same platform without having privileges and no third-party that will provide ones these privileges. So, blockchain technology can enable all the participants to produce a platform together in a distributed manner, without having to trust each other in almost any capacity (Seppälä & Mattila, 2016; Mattila, 2016).

It is thought that the potential of Blockchain regarding security, smart contract structure and peer-to-peer network design may be applied for improving the Aviation cyber-physical systems. It can be proposed that research studies may be directed to understand the sub-systems to apply blockchain logic to aviation industry in future.

Chapter 6 – Prioritizing Research, Testing Capabilities and Education

The continuation of the success of the European aeronautics sector in the long term requires a joint research strategy (section 6.1), implemented through industry-research-academia cooperation (section 6.2), with access to test and development facilities (section 6.3) the whole supported by a steady influx of young talent (section 6.4).

6.1 European Research and Innovation Agenda

****Flightpath 2050 goal 20: “European research and innovation strategies are jointly defined by all stakeholders, public and private, and implemented in a coordinated way with individual responsibly”.***

Aviation is recognized as one of the top five advanced technology sectors in Europe. Thus, it is generally acknowledged that research infrastructures are extremely important to the aviation industry and the scientific community working on aeronautics. Europe has the world’s leading research infrastructure covering the entire aviation system from wind tunnels through simulation facilities to test aircraft. Industrial customers (i.e. aircraft manufacturers) make commercial use of facilities for developing and enhancing their products during limited test periods. This contributes towards making the facilities available for scientific research to other users who need them for limited periods of time. This situation benefits the numerous research projects conducted under national or EU programmes on both fixed and rotary wing aircraft and is conducive to improving basic knowledge (of such matters as flow stability, transition, wakes, vortices and the combustion process) through tests directly funded by research establishments to improve fuel efficiency and reduce noise.

European research is defined, organised and funded in a coherent and coordinated, dynamic and agile way avoiding duplication and inefficiency. It is prioritised towards initiatives resulting from strategic roadmaps defined and agreed by all European stakeholders, satisfying actual needs (industry pull) and potential future demands (technology push). The start of the EU aeronautics programme in the framework programme FP2 with a budget of 36 M€ and its steady growth one hundred-fold to a budget of 3.6 B€ in H2020 testifies to the success and growing importance of this initiative. It was pioneering in supplementing without duplication national, bilateral and multilateral cooperation on an occasional basis among larger nations, by a systematic cooperation accessible to all EU member states, bringing more talent to the European pool. The growth of the aeronautics program has seen a shift from (i) basic, to (ii) industrial, (iii) demonstration and (iv) integration activities. This growth should be considered as an efficient element of integral European transport system growth that “provides completely safe, secure and sustainable mobility for people and goods”. A single European transport area should ease the movements of citizens and freight, reduce costs and enhance the sustainability of European transport. Technological innovation can achieve a faster and cheaper transition to a more efficient and sustainable European transport system by acting on three main factors: vehicles’ efficiency through new engines, materials and design; cleaner energy use through new fuels and propulsion systems; better use of network and safer and more secure operations through information and communication systems. The synergies with other sustainability objectives

such as the reduction of oil dependence, the competitiveness of Europe's transportation (aviation, automotive, railway and maritime) industry as well as health benefits, especially improved air quality in urbanistic conglomerates, make a compelling case for the EU to step up its efforts to accelerate the development and early deployment of clean vehicles (aircraft, cars, trains, etc.).

On a separate track the European Research Council (ERC) has sponsored high-quality research in basic science, including mathematics and physics, with some underrepresentation of engineering. Fundamental and applied research in various scientific disciplines (such as fluid mechanics, materials, structures and systems) and the development of sub-components and components (like engines) and aeronautical end-products (including fixed-wing aircraft and rotorcraft) has always been associated with extensive design, computation, testing, optimisation and validation activities. This complex process calls for the systematic use of various research facilities, such as aerodynamic wind tunnels, combustion and structural test beds, material elaboration apparatus, clusters of small computers (or conversely high-end super-computers), air traffic management and air traffic control simulators, flight simulators, and research aircraft. These facilities, used for different disciplines and specialities, differ greatly in their size and range of application but are often linked to one another through a complex immaterial network that transforms basic scientific knowledge into competitive products while integrating environmental, safety and security requirements. Formal pan-European networks have been established to improve overall efficiency by exchanging best practices and progressively specialising in fields of application. Examples are AT-One for Air Traffic Management, DNW, and ESWIRP for wind tunnels.

The gap between the Joint Research Initiatives (JRI) "Clean Sky" and "SESAR" focused on industrial application and the ERC focused on fundamental research needs to be filled by a Basic Research Programme (BRP). The call for "exploratory research" ideas in SESAR is a first step towards filling the void in basic research and needs to be expanded and extended to all areas of aeronautics. Both Joint Undertakings (JUs) Clean Sky and SESAR ensure the medium-term competitiveness of the European aeronautical sector; the supply of new ideas and prospects to ensure longer term competitiveness depends on a Basic Research Program linking the human resources of academia, industry and research establishments.

6.2 Industry-Research-Academia Clusters

****Flightpath 2050 goal 21: "Creation of a network of multi-disciplinary technology clusters based on collaboration between industry, universities and research institutes"***

The creation of these technology clusters could be the result of 3 initiatives, two ongoing and one to be restored from the past:

- A – The (iii) demonstration and (iv) integration activities existing in the JUs Clean Sky and SESAR;
- B – The fundamental research in mathematics, physics and engineering existing in the ERC;
- C – Restoring the (i) basic and (ii) industrial research that existed in the aeronautics programme since the beginning and lapsed with increasing scale.

European research and innovation strategies are jointly defined by all stakeholders, public and private, and implemented in a coordinated way with individual responsibility. This involves the complete innovation chain from blue sky research up to technology demonstration. A network of multi-

disciplinary technology clusters has been created based on collaboration between industry, universities and research institutes (EREA, PEGASUS, XNOISE, FORUM-AE, etc.). The sector is organised to sustain the full research and innovation chain. This includes mechanisms for small and medium enterprises (SMEs) to link with higher tier suppliers without any penalty for sub-contracting. Research work with achieved previously maturation in its TRLs is continued and intensified with particular emphasis on medium and high levels which are specifically focused on improving components for existing aircraft. Fundamental aeronautics research is coherent with more applied research and makes use of the European Research Council's scheme. In the short-term, attractive and efficient research instruments are put in place, which ensure continuity between research on promising breakthrough concept, their validation by focused RTD actions and finally their demonstration in an integrated environment.

The basic research programme in C may be a relatively modest budget item (up to 100 M€) but it can have a major effect on long-term competitiveness by linking A and C. It would be possible to imagine the clusters around any or all of the 14 main aeronautical technologies: flight physics, aerodynamics, propulsion, structures, materials, production, control, avionics, telecommunications, computation, electrics, noise, emissions and operations.

Harmonisation between technology evolution in aviation and in other correlated sectors enables spin-in from and cross-fertilisation with innovations in other sectors, such as communications (mobile web, travel search engine providers). It also incentivises the aeronautical world to be more adaptive to the very fast evolution of IT technologies (c.f. the current aeronautical evolution on 10-year time scale versus IT technology evolution on a yearly time scale).

The contribution of the EU aeronautics programs from FP2 to the present deserves special focus (Key Topic T6.1).

KEY TOPIC T6.1 – EU AERONAUTICS PROGRAMS SINCE FP2

The aerospace industry is characterized by a high R&D intensity, technological complexity, long product life cycles, and so on. To support the huge costs associated to the development of new products in this demanding industrial sector, the European Union has funded numerous transnational, collaborative R&D projects, within the European Framework Programmes (FPs). The proposals are submitted by self-organized consortia composed by at least two independent legal entities established in different EU Member States and an associated State. Since their initiation in 1984, seven FPs have been launched, and continued in the 8TH EU FP, named Horizon 2020, launched in 2014 (Table 6.1)).

General statistics on the funded aerospace R&D collaboration network						
	FP2	FP3	FP4	FP5	FP6	FP7
	1987 - 1991	1990 - 1994	1994 - 1998	1998 - 2002	2002 - 2006	2007 - 2013
European Framework Programmes						
Number of projects	390	714	241	196	255	217
Number of participants	2171	4066	2301	2385	3899	2791
Average number of participants per project	5,6	5,7	9,5	12,2	15,3	12,9

Table 6.1 - General information concerning the aerospace sector funded from FP2 to FP7 in the time period 1987 to 2013. Source: D. Guffarth, M. J Barber, (2013): The European aerospace R&D collaboration network, FZID Discussion Paper, No. 84-2013.

In order to analyse the main fields of interest such researches carried out within the EU framework programs, Guffarth et al., by consulting the EUPRO database²⁴, have inspected 2013 projects dedicated to the aerospace sector and mapped each of them into one or more of 25 thematic categories as shown in Table 6.2. Moreover, Figure 6.1 illustrated the fraction of the projects funded during each FP that can be associated to the different categories. A more uniform distribution among the different categories is can be noticed in the early FPs. Four categories have increased the relative importance from FP4 until FP7: SAT (satellite and space topics), RSY (quality and safety systems, non-destructive detection and repair systems, maintenance and their facilities), OMP (optimization of manufacturing processes and supply chains, existing product improvements) and SIM (simulation, numerical models, computer-aided systems for air traffic management or aerodynamic application).

Thematic Categories	
Code	Thematic explanation
AER	Aerodynamic, flows and aero thermic
ALO	Alloys and coatings, glazed materials and paints
CEG	(technical) ceramic and glasses
CHE	Chemical processing (incl. petrochemicals)
COM	Composite materials
ELE	Electric and electronic (incl. cables and conductors)
FCH	Fuel cells, batteries, liquid hydrogen, cathodes and membranes
FOR	Forming, moulding, winding, sintering and grinding
LIT	Rare-earth materials (e.g. lithium)
LSO	Lasers, sensors and optics
MET	Metals (steel, aluminum, copper, titanium,...)
MIN	Mining (incl. all auxiliaries)
OMA	Other materials (e.g. rubber, leather, resins, wood, concrete, biomaterial,...)
OMP	Optimizing manufacturing processes, production and products (incl. cost reduction)
OTH	Others
PLA	Plastics and polymers
REC	Recycling and environmentally friendly product improvements and processes
ROB	Robotic systems, e.g. for production, inspection, ...
RSY	Quality and safety systems (incl. repair systems, non-destructive detection, maintenance, etc.)
SAC	Sawing and cutting
SAT	Satellites and space topics
SIM	Simulation, numerical models, computer-aided systems, informatics
SUR	Surfaces
TXT	(technical) textiles
WEL	Welding, soldering, brazing

Table 6.2 - Thematic categories used to classify the EU funded projects related to the aeronautic sector. Source: D. Guffarth, M. J Barber, (2013): The European aerospace R&D collaboration network, FZID Discussion Paper, No. 84-2013²⁵.

A significant observation which can be resumed by relating the data in Figure 6.1 with the historical development of the aeronautic industry concerns the composite material sector (COM).

²⁴ EUPRO database is developed and maintained by Austrian Institute of Technology, Innovation Systems Department by standardizing raw data on EU FP research collaborations collected from the CORDIS database

²⁵ D. Guffarth, M. J Barber, (2013) : The European aerospace R&D collaboration network, FZID Discussion Paper, No. 84-2013, <http://nbn-resolving.de/urn:nbn:de:bsz:100-opus-9038>

It can be noted that projects belonging to this category were among the most relevant in FP2 and FP3 which have been in place between the mid-1980s to the mid-1990s. During this period many R&D efforts have been devoted to the development of new composite materials in response to the aircraft manufacturers demand to reduce its weight in order to decrease fuel consumption and increase the airplane flight range.

It has to be reminded that until the mid-1990s the amount of composite materials employed was around 10% of the total aircraft weight and limited to non-structural parts. This percentage has sensibly increased up to the actual figures. In fact, both the Boeing 787 and the Airbus A350 recently introduced in the aircraft market (in 2011 and 2015, respectively) are now composed with about 50% in weight of carbon fibre reinforced materials. This evidences that there has been an industrial application of such new technology has nearly 20 years lag with respect to the research and development phase.

The most relevant topics of FP4 concerning efficiency and optimization of aircraft design and procurement costs, (OMP and RSY in Table 6.2) were continued in FP5. In addition, specific goals concerning the reduction of aircraft noise and climate impact become of greater importance thus, explaining the increase of AER and REC categories. During the exploitation period of FP5, the improvement of aircraft operational capability is put in evidence by the increased number of projects dedicated to computer-aided systems (SIM).

In FP6, the significant percentages associated to categories like space (SAT), satellite-based information services (LSO) and data information models (SIM) signalled the growing importance recognized by the EU to the Galileo project, and to satellite telecommunications. As it concerns the aeronautic sector, the most relevant efforts have been associated to safety and security (RSY), cost reduction (OMP), improvement of the environmental impact with regard to emissions (REC) and noise (AER and OMP).

Within the FP7 the EU strategy concerning aerospace has been concentrated on the reduction of emissions and alternative fuels (REC), air traffic management (SIM), safety and security (RSY) and efficient aircraft production (OMP).

Figure 6.1 - Thematic development of EU-funded aerospace R&D projects. Source: D. Guffarth, M. J Barber, (2013): The European aerospace R&D collaboration network, FZID Discussion Paper, No. 84-2013.

Participation by Country

The graphs shown in the Figure 6.2 provides a synthetic description of the relative involvement of the different EU countries in the FP projects. In particular, the diameter of the nodes is associated to the overall number of participants per country, whereas the links between the nodes provide the number of connections between the regions: the thickness of the links indicates the amount of connections within the different FPs. Such graphs illustrate the evolution of the involvement of the EU countries from a more uniform distribution in FP2 and FP3 towards a more concentrated one in FP5-FP7. Such change may be reasonably associated to the previously discussed evolution of the relative importance of the different categories and to the identification of a less fragmented and more specialized cooperation network.

Figure 6.2 - The European aerospace R&D collaboration network; Source: D. Guffarth, M. J Barber, (2013): The European aerospace R&D collaboration network, FZID Discussion Paper, No. 84-2013.

Participation by Section: Industry, Research, Academia.

As it concerns the organization types participating to the EU funded projects the following categories can be considered: IND (industry), EDU (education and science facilities, like universities), ROR (research organizations, like the Fraunhofer Gesellschaft), GOV (government and other public authorities) and OTH (all other organizations).

In the Figure 6.3 illustrates the relative weight of such different organizations within the FP projects is illustrated. As it concerns the industry IND, It can be noted that there is a presence between 50-60% almost constantly from FP2 to FP5. In FP6 and FP7 a decrease to 45% and 38% respectively can be noticed. An opposite trend, closely related to the thematic development discussed before, is visible

for the scientific organizations EDU and ROR since their shares, nearly constant from FP2 to FP5 with a percentage <40%, increased to 45% in FP6 and 53% in FP7. In particular, such trend is related to the rising relevance of topics like satellite and space, environmental impact in FP6 and FP7 which demands for a more prominent scientific effort and long development phase.

As indicated in [1] on the average by considering all FPs, “an industrial actor participated in a mean number of 3.2 projects, with a standard deviation of 14.6, a research organization in 3.0 (11.1) projects, and a university in 2.6 (6.1) projects. Over all organization types, the fluctuation seems to be high, since they participate on average in about three projects over 26 years. The enormous variation indicates strong heterogeneity within the different types”.

Figure 6.3 - Relative shares of the different organization types to aerospace EU funded projects.

Source: D. Guffarth, M. J Barber, (2013): The European aerospace R&D collaboration network, FZID Discussion Paper, No. 84-2013.

6.3 Test, Simulation and Development Facilities

****Flightpath 2050 goal 22:“ Identification, maintenance and ongoing development of strategic European aerospace test, simulation and development facilities. The ground and airborne validation and certification processes are integrated where appropriate”.***

Research and development infrastructure is an indispensable tool to achieve a decisive competitive edge in developing sustainable aviation products and services that meet the needs of EU citizens and society. Appropriate core capabilities are available and accessible. Infrastructure and the associated workforce are vital assets, which are maintained and further developed in a focused, efficient and cost-effective manner. Suitable access to these facilities enables knowledge transfer across Europe and facilitates continuity from blue sky research to innovation in products and services for the benefit of Europe. Strategic aviation infrastructure is of the highest quality and efficiency, providing the basis for world-class research and competitive product development while supporting education. It ranges from wind tunnels via iron and copper birds up to experimental aircraft and simulation capabilities for in-flight and airport operations. Infrastructure is organised in a network for the best usability of all

stakeholders. The data quality and operational efficiency of European aviation infrastructure helps industry to minimise risks and development costs and helps society to determine the impact of aviation in benefits such as fast transport as well as in penalties such as impact on the atmosphere.

The days of duplication or multiplication of major aerospace test facilities are long gone, as shown by some good examples of the last few decades: (i) the joint Dutch-German aero-acoustic wind tunnel DNW; (ii) the joint British-French-German cryogenic pressurized wind tunnel ETW; (iii) the choice of CIRA to build an icing wind tunnel and an atmospheric re-entry simulation facility not existing elsewhere in Europe on a comparable scale. The rationalization of smaller scale test facilities has diminished duplication and it may be time to look at updates, upgrades and new needs.

There is large-scale co-operation in science, code development and high-power computing. The main topics of this include:

- Improved and validated fluid dynamics, aerodynamic control, combustion, noise and thermal modelling based on high performance computation, covering all needs for the aircraft and its engines, external and internal.
- Methods and tools facilitating evaluation of aircraft and engine configurations.
- Results from demonstration, allowing to assess not only improvements in vehicle development but also to verify and validate new modelling techniques.

An European aeronautical facility programme would logically consist of the following steps:

- List by industry and certification authorities of the test facilities needed for the foreseeable future and their appropriate specifications;
- comparison with the inventory of existing facilities in Europe to identify the needs (i) already met; (ii) to be met by upgrades or (iii) requiring new facilities;
- To devise a funding and implementation plan, associating each test facility with one or more technology clusters (section 6.2).

6.4 Young Talent and Women in Aviation

****Flightpath 2050 goal 23: Students are attracted to careers in aviation. Courses offered by European universities closely match the needs of the aviation industry, its research establishments and administration and evolve continuously as those needs develop.***

The aviation community is committed to lifelong learning and continuous education thus promoting interest in the sector and stimulating innovation. Europe's students are attracted to careers in aviation and perform highly. Courses offered by European Universities are academically challenging and adapted continuously to support and match the evolving needs of the sector research (establishments) and administrations. Educational policies across the EU motivate students to pursue further studies in science, technology and mathematics to ensure a steady supply of talent for a first-class work force. The aviation community engages actively with European students from the earliest age. Higher education is based on the adaptation of curricula based on the evolution of knowledge, language and (soft) skill requirements derived from ICAO. The curricula are designed based on a common understanding of the balance between multi-disciplinary and in-depth knowledge, such as, for example, common language recommendations, the T-shaped professional and the Conceive-

Design-Implement-Operate (CDIO) philosophy. This ensures that scientists of the future are capable of integrating interdisciplinary skills of a technological, human and social nature. Also more detailed requirements such as inclusion of a flight test, hands-on experience, and a minimum amount of essential, aeronautics related knowledge are included.

The aviation sector in Europe will need a vast pool of human resources (Key Topic T6.2). The distribution by tasks may be comparable in Europe and the United States (Key Topic T6.3).

KEY TOPIC T6.2 – HUMAN RESOURCES NEEDED BY THE AERONAUTICAL SECTOR IN EUROPE

The Goal 23 – Young talent and women in aviation is mentioned and analysed by several key institutions in the field of aeronautics, as presented below:

Flightpath 2050 - Goal 23:

“Students are attracted to careers aviation. Courses offered by European universities closely match the needs of the aviation industry, its research establishments and administration and evolve continuously as those needs develop. Lifelong and continuous education in aviation is the norm.”

The attraction of young talent to aviation can be enhanced by:

- Demonstrating the progress in aerospace vehicles of all types: airliners, helicopters, fighters, launchers, satellites, rockets and drones;
- Highlighting the multidisciplinary nature of aerospace engineering as a synthesis of advance technologies with working opportunities throughout Europe.

The pool of young talent can be enlarged by promoting greater participation of women in aviation through dissemination of opportunities and successful case histories.

The best form of alignment of university courses with the needs of industry and research establishments is the joint research activities that point to the same future and link academic staff to the places where their students are going to be employed, creating synergies and longer-term links.

The cooperation among the IMT, EREA and PEGASUS in general and the technology clusters are further elements in the alignment of education, research and industry.

2017 SRIA

The SRIA challenge relevant for the Goal 23 is dedicated to: Infrastructure and Skills – aiming to ensure the preservation of Europe’s research infrastructure requirements and encourage a sustained flow of competent, trained and motivated people.

ACARE has laid down the plan to establish a” fully integrated European aviation education system which will deliver the required high-quality workforce, with the skills and the motivation to be able to meet the challenges of the future. This requires a harmonised and balanced approach covering the entire scope from attracting talents over primary and secondary education to apprenticeship, academia and lifelong professional development”. ACARE settles three action actions relevant for this analysis, indicated in the Table 6.3:

- Action Area 5.6 – Provide world-leading education in aviation;

- Action Area 5.7 – Stimulate the involvement of stakeholders in education;

- Action Area 5.8 – Make aviation attractive to ensure inflow into educational programmes.

Action Areas	Target State 2050	Desirable Progress
5.6 - Provide world-leading education in aviation	European aviation education is world-leading, providing excellent support to the aviation sector. Programmes are harmonised with European accreditation schemes and a chartered aerospace engineer qualification.	By 2025, the means for harmonisation across European aviation education should be defined, with implementation following shortly after. European accreditation should be in place in 2035. As well, the qualification of chartered aerospace engineer should also be available.
5.7 - Stimulate the involvement of stakeholders in education	Industry and research establishments are fully involved in educational programmes ensuring that students are better prepared for a career in aviation. Industry is reaping substantial benefits from this collaboration, which extends to apprenticeships and life-long learning.	Internships, placements and subject matter for masters and doctoral students; staff exchanges; greater number of industry-funded university chairs
5.8 - Make aviation attractive to ensure inflow into educational programmes	The image of the aviation sector is positive and attractive. Sufficient number of people flow into the educational programmes and choose a career in aviation. This supports European aviation as world leader.	Awareness programmes for schools should be in place from 2020 onwards By 2025 there should be a system of grants for outstanding students who wish to join aviation programmes from within and beyond Europe. A European XPRIZE in aviation should also be organised in 2025.

Table 6.3 – Status relative to the ACARE Goal 23.

Analysing the scope in both Flightpath 2050 and SRIA it can be stated that both proposals are coherent and SRIA is complementary to the FP 2050. SRIA analyses several keys aspects and areas to be promoted until 2050. We can highlight the following:

- **Ensure a large inflow of talent into aviation educational programs:**
 - From primary through secondary to high education;
 - Attract talent from outside Europe;
 - Attract people from other sectors to pursue a career in aviation
 - Outreach to the general public.

- **Retain professionals at later stage** – keeping them motivated and updated in terms of knowledge and skills.
- **Gender balance** – attract female students and encourage greater participation of women in conferences, events and competitions.

In terms of measures to be taken, the following are highlighted:

- **Implementation of awareness programmes:**
 - Careers must be visible attractive and progressive, with LLL possibilities and flexibility to change disciplines inside the sector.
- **Organisation and promotion of scholarships, grants and prizes;**
- **Promote diversity in types of education and training:**
 - Degree programmes must be interesting, appealing, of high quality and supported by modern facilities. Harmonised curriculum; Europe-wide standard for aviation education; Links with outstanding education institutes worldwide.
 - Professional education and re-training opportunities should be available on-line and on-site.
 - Include in the programmes the 21st Century skills – problem solving, critical thinking and creativity.

ICAO also addresses shortage of skilled aviation professionals. In 2009, ICAO also strongly addressed the shortage of skilled aviation professionals. The analyses made at that time highlighted that:

Statistics

- In the next 20 years, airlines will have to add 25,000 new aircraft to the current 17,000-strong commercial fleet
- By 2026, 480,000 new technicians **will be needed** to maintain these aircraft and over 350,000 pilots to fly them
- Between 2005 and 2015, 73% of the American air traffic controller population is eligible for retirement.

The underlying problem **was presented and simply stated in the following way:** “the demand for aviation professionals will exceed supply”.

Factors that explain it include:

- **wholesale retirements in the current generation of aviation professionals;**
- **aviation professions not attractive enough to potential candidates;**
- **competition with other industry sectors for skilled employees;**
- **training capacity insufficient to meet demand;**
- **learning methodologies not responsive to new evolving learning style;**
- **accessibility to affordable training;**
- **lack of harmonization of competencies in some aviation disciplines, and**
- **Little awareness by the “next generation” of types of aviation professions available.**

ICAO stated then that solutions should be globally-harmonized in nature and include human resource planning tools, accredited training and educational programmes adapted to the next generation, and wide-ranging cooperation among concerned stakeholders. Therefore, ICAO established the **Next Generation of Aviation Professionals Taskforce (NGAP)**, consisting of 29 representatives from industry, education and training providers, regulatory bodies and international organizations. Near-

term objectives define included to: inventory human resources planning data; identify and support initiatives to reach out to the next generation; and, find ways to harmonize training regulations. The Task Force also envisaged to support initiatives relating to the next generation of aviation professionals.

The NGAP initiative was “launched to ensure that enough qualified and competent aviation professionals are available to operate, manage and maintain the future international air transport system. This is critical as a large contingent of the current generation of aviation professionals will retire, access to affordable training and education is increasingly problematic, and aviation competes with other industry sectors for highly skilled professionals. The lack of harmonized competencies in some aviation disciplines and a lack of awareness by the 'next generation' of the types of aviation jobs available further compounds the problem”.

Under this initiative several actions are in place, as presented in the Figure 6.4 below:

NGAP actions timeline since 2009

Figure 6.4 – NGAP: New generation of Aviation Professionals task force.

As for the recent NGAP developments/actions by NGAP (2016 – 2017) we can mention the following:

- Established as ICAO Programme, inclusion in GANP & GASP, Assembly Resolution;
- Outreach activities and communications including:
 - Website; Newsletters; Training Reports
 - Inclusion in Global and regional training conference programmes
 - Collaboration with IPTA to promote best practices for pilot careers
- Supported Dream Soar Initiative
- NGAP Global Summit & Model ICAO Forum
- New Fundamentals of the Air Transport System course
- New Aviation Training and Education Directory
- Updated aviation personnel forecasts
- New CBT manuals and regional workshops

Reference State in 2010

In 2010, the skills shortages were a forthcoming threat and worries about skills shortages were widespread at a global scale in aviation. Red flags were raised by ICAO, IATA, ACARE, ...

In Europe, clearly, there were no guarantees that it would be possible to keep up with the changing world in a way that allowed the maintenance or increase of its technological position, as the demand for professional engineers and technicians was expected to grow in all levels of the value chain. Most of the worries about skills shortages were directed mainly at engineering related careers. As well known that the major demographic trend in Europe is characterised by an aging population and declining younger age cohorts. In 2010 the industry employment was already assisting to a concentration of age structures in the middle age range (35-50 years) and experiencing lower recruitment rates of youngsters – in part due to longer education and training periods – but also due to broad use of early retirement schemes. This demographic tendency, in addition with lower proportions of qualified young people who were (and are) choosing for mathematics, physics and engineering careers was (is) a concern for the aerospace industry, not only in Europe but in all mature industrialized economies. Europe AI also faces challenges posed by the emerging economies who accessed the aircraft market and are not confronted neither with the problem of an ageing society nor a decreasing interest in STEM study programmes. The longstanding dimension of the declining labour supply is also heightened by the circumstance that regional mismatches in the labour market cannot easily be adjusted. Cultural, linguistic, and legal differences among European members challenge companies' desires to move work and employees between countries. It was clear the need for education and training to coordinate multiple cultural traditions and institutions and make them work across borders, to develop transparent and recognised training courses and graduates. It's also relevant to mention that for the European AI is difficult to take advantage of the global market for highly skilled employees, since European characteristics - less open societies and language barriers – make Europe, in general, less attractive than the US, and most Member States are more restrictive.

Nevertheless, and as mentioned above, the labour shortages on the engineering level are not only a European but also a US concern. In 2014, in a study made by GAO (US Government Accountability Office), the analysis found mixed evidence about a current or possible future shortage of aviation professionals. There has been a steady decline in the number of engineering graduates in the US since

a peak in the mid-1980s, but as the USA can rely on immigrants, the situation there is different. Aerospace engineers experienced a low unemployment rate—the most direct measure of a labour shortage—and increases in employment suggested that a shortage may exist. Until 2010, around half of all engineers with PhDs in the US workforce under the age of 45 were foreigners. Data provided less support for a shortage of aircraft mechanics; while the occupation has had a low unemployment rate, both employment and earnings have stayed about the same, suggesting that demand for this occupation has not outstripped supply. Industry and government are taking some actions to attract and retain qualified individuals in these occupations, but employers GAO interviewed remain concerned about future needs. GAO found that most of these employers had some challenges hiring personnel with the skills employers were seeking at the wage they offered. Employers reported taking a variety of actions, but few were raising wages. Several US agencies—the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and the Departments of Defence (DOD), Education, Labour (DOL), and Veterans Affairs—developed programs that assisted individuals interested in aviation careers. For example, in academic year 2011–2012, Education disbursed approximately \$1.6 billion in federal grants to students majoring in related fields. Still, most employers and stakeholders stated that maintaining a qualified workforce was difficult (Figure 6.5), in part because of a perception that fewer people are interested in aviation careers.

Figure 6.5 – Need for aviation professionals in the US

Since then, some initiatives were already put in place. Workforce mobility assumed a growing importance for the European AI. National cluster units and the new European Aerospace Cluster Partnership (EACP) established opportunities to develop and expand transnational education and training programmes. The Hamburg Qualification Initiative (HQI), or the PEGASUS (Partnership of a European Group of Aeronautics and Space Universities) are examples of successful transnational cooperation. The HQI has established an exchange in the field of training between the aviation clusters of Hamburg and the French aerospace valley of the regions Midi-Pyrénées (Toulouse) and Aquitaine (Bordeaux). The programme has evolved from the exchange of trainees to integrated transnational vocational training courses. The PEGASUS alliance created with the purpose to optimise the higher education services offered in the best interest of Europe both in terms of continuing to attract the best students and also to offer highly relevant educational and research programmes, also evolved to include also an industry and research alliance is also pursuing the interest to promote excellence and recognition seal of European aerospace Universities.

Actual Status

The skills shortage is no longer a looming threat; it is a stark reality that many countries are facing.

Initiatives Worldwide to Attract Young Talent to Aerospace

The "Australian Youth Aerospace Association" (www.ayaa.com.au) is composed and animated by young students from Aerospace and organises a set of activities that aim to engage and attract youth to aerospace related careers. Among the initiatives we can highlight the following:

- Aerospace Futures: a 3 days conference dedicated to expose university students to opportunities in aerospace industry. In this conference, students have the opportunity to be aware of the latest developments in AI; to better know the organisations involved in AI; to discover job opportunities in AI.
- AYA Forum: is a 5 days interactive conference dedicated to secondary students that aims to showcase the Aerospace Industry. Through this forum students have the opportunity to gain a clear understanding of the pathways available for them after the high school.
- RocketProjet: this action allows students to become rocket engineers for a day. It showcased both the theoretical and practical applications of modern rocketry.
- Australian Undergraduate week: a 5 days event is organised and includes hands-on space engineering activities; dissemination of PhDs and internships activities.

Women

The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) in the United States has two programmes that focus on attracting female talent. Through the NASA/Girls Scouts of the USA partnership, NASA scientists provide training sessions, led by NASA scientists, for girl scouts. Some 100 000 girls have participated in these sessions until May 2016. Under the "NASA G.I.R.L.S" programme, female NASA professionals provide online lessons in STEM fields to girls selected through a competitive process. Surveyed countries support many other programmes that foster interest in STEM careers, but these are not specifically targeted to women. Some countries also support initiatives to attract interest among male students in female-dominated professions. Germany, for example, funds a nation-wide network and information platform to support gender-sensitive career and life orientation for boys through the programme "New Paths for Boys and Boys' Day". The programme provides information and material to education and social work professionals, career advisers, human resource teams, education and training specialists, and parents. Nationwide conferences and meetings are also organised to facilitate exchanges between researchers and practitioners.

The aerospace and defence sector is characterized by strong volume growth with an estimated production of 25,000 aircraft in the next 20 years. That's way, the industry must attract qualified engineers and skilled blue-collar workers, as well as pilots and technicians. *According to Alix Partners (It's All About People, The Battle for Talent in the Aerospace and Defence Industry, January 2013)* European aerospace and defence industry is expected to require at least 12 500 engineers yearly²⁶. The demand for highly skilled people is expected to increase dramatically. For example, the number

²⁶ <https://legacy.alixpartners.com/en/Publications/AllArticles/tabid/635/articleType/ArticleView/articleId/466/Its-All-About-People.aspx>

of U.S. jobs that require complex interactions involving a high level of judgement has grown three times as fast as employment in general.

The International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) estimates that 350 000 new pilots and 480000 new technicians will be needed to keep these planes operational²⁷.

Current Situation

Europe

According to Aerospace and Defence Industries Association of Europe (ASD), employment in 2015 looks like:

- Aeronautics 552 000 employees;
- Space 38 000 employees²⁸.
- Statistics data form 2016 are not yet available.

USA

More detailed statistics are available from the United States Department of Labour, Bureau of Labour Statistics (Table 6.4).

HOUSEHOLD DATA
ANNUAL AVERAGES

18. Employed persons by detailed industry, sex, race, and Hispanic or Latino ethnicity
[Numbers in thousands]

Industry	2016				
	Total employed	Percent of total employed			
		Women	Black or African American	Asian	Hispanic or Latino
Aircraft and parts manufacturing	729	22.4	6.0	8.8	12.9
Aerospace product and parts manufacturing	73	15.0	3.2	3.6	17.7

Table 6.4 – Aviation Employment in the US; Source: <https://www.bls.gov/cps/cpsaat18.htm>

And the United States Department of Transportation (Table 6.7):

CATEGORY	2016	2015	2014	2013	2012	2011	2010	2009	2008	2007
Pilot--Total	39	39	39	39	40	41	42	36	37	35
	187	287	322	621	621	316	218	808	981	784
Student 1/	15	14	14	14	14	14	14	8 450	9 127	9 559
	971	580	369	405	643	683	767			

²⁷ <https://icao.int/Newsroom/Pages/ICAO-Addresses-Shortage-of-Skilled-Aviation-Professionals.aspx>

²⁸ Aerospace and Defense Industries Key Facts & Figures 2016

CATEGORY	2016	2015	2014	2013	2012	2011	2010	2009	2008	2007
Recreational (only)	15	16	16	17	16	18	12	13	20	17
Sport	223	211	192	174	152	135	118	98	79	64
Private 2/	10	11	11	11	12	12	13	14	15	13
	009	339	652	909	456	927	566	322	015	694
Commercial 2/	6 081	6 587	6 685	6 911	7 536	7 956	8 175	8 289	8 083	7 101
Airline Transport 2/	6 888	6 554	6 408	6 205	5 818	5 597	5 580	5 636	5 657	5 349
Flight Instructor Certificates 4/	6 848	6 669	6 521	6 386	6 371	6 350	6 359	6 362	6 293	6 232
Remote Pilots 7/	793	NA								
Non-Pilot-Total	187	183	174	166	160	155	150	147	144	138
	914	259	000	294	452	918	019	052	968	452
Mechanic 5/	6 536	8 419	8 151	7 917	7 729	7 487	7 215	6 980	6 740	6 524
Repairmen 5/	1 822	2 289	2 278	2 288	2 307	2 278	2 312	2 335	2 284	2 193
Parachute Rigger 5/	540	811	763	712	697	683	655	633	615	594
Ground Instructor 5/	4 772	5 907	5 889	5 869	5 853	5 880	5 894	5 860	5 785	5 726
Dispatcher 5/	3 615	4 503	4 326	4 115	3 930	3 744	3 530	3 381	3 230	3 087
Flight Navigator	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Flight Attendant 6/	169	159	150	143	138	134	128	126	124	118
	170	703	941	701	223	114	646	034	419	426
Flight Engineer	1 458	1 626	1 651	1 691	1 712	1 731	1 766	1 828	1 894	1 901

Table 6.5 - Estimated Active Women Airmen Certificates Held December 31, 2007-2016. Source: Excel file 2016-civil-airmen-stats_US Dep of Transportation https://www.faa.gov/data_research/aviation_data_statistics/civil_airmen_statistics/

Note: The term airmen include men and women certified as pilots, mechanics or other aviation technicians. This table (Table 2) represents data for females only. Data in the Pilot Categories does not directly correspond to the same category in Table 1 as glider and/or helicopter and/or gyroplane certs are not broken out separately. Data in the Non-Pilot Categories as well as Flight Instructor Certificates does directly correspond to the same category in Table.

- 1/ In July 2010, the FAA issued a rule that increased the duration of validity for student pilot certificates for pilots under the age of 40 from 36 to 60 months. This resulted in the increase in active student pilots to 14,767 from 8,450 at the end of 2009.
- 2/ Includes those with an airplane and/or a helicopter and/or glider and/or a gyroplane certificate.
- 3/ Glider and lighter-than-air pilots are not required to have a medical examination.
- 4/ not included in total.
- 5/ historically, numbers represented all certificates on record. No medical examination required. In 2016, Federal Regulation required that airmen without a plastic certificate no longer considered active. Therefore, starting with 2016, those airmen with a paper certificate only were excluded.
- 6/ Flight Attendants first reported in 2005.
- 7/ Remote pilot certification started in August 2016. These numbers are not included in the pilot totals.

NA Not available. Prior to 1995 repairmen were included in the mechanic category. Recreational certificate first issued in 1990. Sport certificate first issued in 2005

Potential Solutions

Potential solutions may be:

1. Recruiting more creatively - improving recruiting process by institutionalising a close cooperation between industry and science to attract talents:
 - Airbus is using Twitter accounts to talk to potential recruits and is holding international recruitment days where candidates are quickly down-selected from several hundred applicants²⁹.
 - Rolls-Royce supports PhD students, 25% of the graduates are recruited and many more remain in the network³⁰.
2. Acting globally - companies globalise their activities to attract the largest pool of talent while similarly benefitting from lower cost and international work-sharing:
 - Boeing Design Centre in Moscow, to benefit from the local pool of talents³¹;
 - Airbus innovation units in Bangalore and Delhi (India), to benefit from the local pool of talents³².
3. Improving the working environment - companies focus on improving the working environment:
 - UTC Re-Empower Program supporting experienced professionals returning to work after a career break³³.
 - BAE Systems has created an "Assignment Panel", a clearing-house of openings in the company, so employees do not need to leave in order to find new challenges³⁴.
 - Northrop Grumman has implemented highly structured rotation system where top talents spend their first two years on four rotations, supported by a mentor³⁵.
4. Improving knowledge transfer from experienced to young employees - companies actively seeks opportunities to improve the knowledge transfer from older to younger employees. They use rotation programs as a lever to transfer knowledge and systematically offer part time work for older people (e.g. BAE Systems has established a very aggressive mentoring programme to ensure that knowledge is being passed down from one generation to another³⁶).
5. Improving number of college graduates who have studied science, technology, engineering and mathematics. A good example of that kind action, undertaken by an aviation company's cluster, is Aviation Valley Association Education Support Foundation³⁷. The foundation main goal is popularizing science and education, developing scientific interests as a means for attractive discoveries and experiences. Some of the most important actions and projects conducted by the foundation:
 - **The Children's Technical University** includes activities for primary school pupils. These include interactive lectures, conducted using scientific experiments, aid, and

²⁹<http://www.industryweek.com/recruiting-retention/boeing-and-airbus-fight-hell-aerospace-engineers>; access: December 2017

³⁰<http://www.indianexpress.com/news/airbus-plans-innovation-unit-in-india/967419>; access: December 2017

³¹<http://www.boeing.com/news/frontiers/archive/2005/september/mainfeature1.html>; access: December 2017

³²<http://company.airbus.com/careers/jobs-and-applications/vacancies-in-india.html>; access: December 2017

³³http://www.utc.com/Careers/Work-With-Us/Pages/ReEmpower_Program.aspx; access: December 2017

³⁴Economist Intelligence Unit 2011, Talent strategies and the competitiveness of the US aerospace and defence industry, p. 8

³⁵<http://www.northropgrumman.com/careers/Students-Entry-Level/Pages/default.aspx>; access: December 2017

³⁶<https://www.baesystems.com/en-uk/our-company/corporate-responsibility/working-responsibly/investing-in-our-people/diversity-and-inclusion/developing/perfect>, access: December 2017

³⁷<https://dolina-wiedzy.pl/fundacja/>; access: December 2017

exhibits. The topics of the lectures are adjusted to the age of the pupils. Topics from the fields of chemistry, physics, mathematics, civil engineering, biology, aeronautics and every other scientific subject related to the Technical University. Classes are taught by academic staff, industry specialists, students, and other institutions offering institutions. Actions are conducted full-time in Rzeszow, Mielec, Debica, Ustrzyki Dolne and part-time (The Travelling Children's Technical University).

- **Flying Physics Project** - demonstrative physics lessons for middle school pupils held a few times a month in selected schools with the approval of the respective principal. Teachers are grouped in two-person teams that are didactically and substantively prepared. During the demonstrations, scientific exhibitions are used that are used to confirm the theoretical material present during a multimedia presentation.
- **Suggestion Project** - demonstrative physics lessons held for teenagers of secondary schools. They are conducted twice a month in selected schools with the approval of the respective principal. Topic that combine physics and aviation are conducted by two teachers working in team that have the knowledge and ideas for interesting lessons, which can be a great foundation of knowledge, and it serves as a way to better prepare for the Matura exam.
- **Company and science picnics** - The foundation participates in several scientific events, during which it presents scientific exhibitions. This called the experiment zone, in other words experiment stations that can be used to conduct simple experiments with the help of organizers and volunteers. In the experiment zone, there are also play stations dedicated for young children.
- **CEKSO Operator Training Centre and CEKSO 2 project** - In 2005, the Aviation Valley Association established a program that intended to increase accessibility of professions related with the aerospace industry. The task of CESKO was coordinating training in technical in the Subcarpathian Voivodeship to suit the realistic needs of industry and creating a world class Operating Training Centres in the long term. Cooperating under the CEKSO framework permits more extensive analysis of issues regarding implementing: new production management tools, new production technologies, and continuous improvement tools. Practical Training Centres, in accordance with their statutes, educate young future employees by appropriating the forms and educational contents to the employment needs of Aviation Valley companies. The institutions also train adults in the form courses to meet the needs of companies.

In 2015 new actions, named CEKSO 2, were being implemented. The main principle is shortening the adaptation period of professional graduates and increasing their skills to adapt to the ever-changing needs of aerospace company through:

- Modifying secondary school curriculums;
- Creating motivators for teachers and students;
- Preparing teaching staffs.

Chapter 7 – Long Distance Air Travel

The long-range airliner market is dominated by the Airbus-Boeing duopoly (section 7.2) that arose at the end of a long competitive period in which Airbus steadily gained ground (section 7) starting from a newcomer status. The possibility of other competitors emerging in the long-range air transport market (Russia, China, Ukraine or cooperation) is also considered (section 7.3). The long-range airliner routes are fed by regional airliners that have a significant market of their own (section 7.4). Europe is strongly competitive not only on long-range and regional airliners but also in other categories like business aircraft (section 7.5) and helicopters (section 7.6).

7.1 The Growing Airbus Challenge to Boeing

Airbus as a newcomer to the airline market started with the A300 by filling an empty niche: the short-haul wide body aircraft (subsection 7.1.1). A further advance in competitiveness was achieved with the increased use to electronics in the forward-facing crew cockpit (FFCC) of the A310 that reduced flight crew from three to two (subsection 7.1.2). An even more significant innovation in the A320 as the first fly-by-wire airliner in the world that was countered by Boeing with an improvised second-generation B737 that managed to compete only through the trick of “grand-father rights” (subsection 7.1.3). The fourth stage of the Airbus challenge with the twin-engine A330 and four-engine A340 pair was met head-on by the Boeing 777 (subsection 7.1.4). Airbus decided it had to challenge the remaining Boeing monopoly, the jumbo market of the B747, but the A380 as the world’s largest airliner has had a troubled development and market history (subsection 7.1.5). Boeing took advantage of Airbus troubles with the A380 to launch a new challenge in another sector with the 787 to which Airbus responded late but successfully with the A350 and A330neo (subsection 7.1.6). Since the A350 was designed to outperform both the Boeing 787 and 787, Boeing reacted with the stretched 777X out of reach of further A350 developments, threatening both the Boeing 747 and Airbus A380. The Bombardier temerary challenge with the C-series to companies 10 times larger, together with development delays, lead to the massive success of the second-generation Airbus A320neo and to the late but still successful response of the third-generation Boeing 737max (subsection 7.1.7). This strong competition has been highly profitable to both members of the duopoly.

7.1.1 The Airbus A300 and the Wide-Body Short-Range Niche

Just before the Airbus entered the airliner market there were two disjointed sectors:

- Small single-aisle short-range narrow bodies up to 190 seats and 6 000 km range;
- Large double-aisle long-range wide bodies up to 450 seats and 14 000 km range.

Airbus identified a niche for short high-density routes: the A300 twin-aisle wide body carrying up to 300 passengers up to 8 000 km. Boeing arrogantly both dismissed (i) this Airbus niche market as non-existent and (ii) the A300 as another government aeroplane doomed to failure. Although ultimately proved utterly wrong, both these charges could not be easily dismissed at the time and were actually the statement of two major challenges.

As for European ‘government’ aeroplanes versus American ‘commercial’ successes:

- The Sud-Aviation Caravelle and British Aircraft Corporation One-Eleven were the pioneer twin jets, although the market came to dominate by the later entries from the Douglas DC-9 and Boeing 737;
- The Hawker Siddeley Trident was the first tri-jet but the market was subsequently dominated by the later entry into market of the Boeing 727;
- The Vickers VC10 was a pioneer four-engine aircraft with pioneer Rolls-Royce Conway turbofans, but like the Convair CV-880/990 it lost market position to the Douglas DC-8 and Boeing 707/720.

As for 'government' versus 'commercial' airliners:

- The private venture De Havilland Comet was the first jet airliner and a commercial failure due to structural fatigue problems unknown at the time;
- Before Boeing sold the first commercial Boeing 707 it had several years of development funded by the U.S. Air Force that had ordered hundreds of similar KC-135 in-flight refuelling tankers.

The Franco-German initiative to develop the Airbus A300 was met by the British government with the demand to use a new Rolls-Royce high by-pass ratio (HBPR) turbofan, the RB 207. This was similar in configuration but distinct from the RB 211 under development at the time, whose composite fan failures ultimately lead to the bankruptcy of both Rolls-Royce and Lockheed, followed by their rescue respectively by the British and United States governments. Airbus refused developing at the same time a new aircraft (A300) and a political engine (RB 207) and opted for an American well-proven engine, the General Electric CF6. The British still participated in the A300 with Hawker building the wing as a 'private' partner 'supported' by the government. The Airbus decision to choose the existing General Electric CF 6 over the new Rolls-Royce RB. 207 was proof that the A300 was not a 'government aeroplane' and that Airbus had the courage to resist political pressures and aim squarely at the market ensuring its success.

7.1.2 The A310 and the Forward-Facing Crew Cockpit (FFCC)

Although the A300 achieved a 10% market share Boeing refused to consider it in its market projections, allowing Airbus to strike the next coup unchallenged. At the time the airliner cockpits consisted of large arrays of mostly duplicate analogue flight instruments facing the pilot and co-pilot plus large side panel(s) with system instruments facing the flight engineer; since the flight navigator had been dispersed earlier, at this time was the minimum flight crew was 3. Airbus proposed the introduction of multi-function electronic flight displays capable of showing different information at different stages of flight or in different circumstances, such as system diagrams in the case of a failure or emergency; together with a much-increased level of automation this would allow the flight engineer and his side panels to be dispensed with, hence the publicity kind designation forward facing crew cockpit (FFCC). The elimination of the flight engineer was rather controversial, and it did not escape anyone that the ultimate motivation was to reduce flight crew costs from 3 to 2. Nevertheless, the electronic flight instrument displays were an innovation to stay providing a much more flexible way of selecting among a wide array of information and the increased efficiency of the A310 added to the market penetration of the A300 reaching 20%. Still Boeing continued to refuse the inclusion of Airbus in its market projections, making the third stage of the Airbus challenge, the A320, the rude awakening.

7.1.3 The A320: The First Fly-by-Wire Airliner

The introduction of fly-by-wire technology from fighters in the first airliner allowed the A320 to be designed with a smaller tail plane area, less cruise trim drag and a higher efficiency. Boeing initially dismissed the A320 diffidently as the 'wonder plane' until realizing that it made the existing B737 uncompetitive. Boeing rushed to upgrade the 737 into a second generation with some limitations. For example, the lack of ground clearance below the wing limited the diameter of the turbofan engine used and required a non-circular flat-bottomed nacelle; the short nacelle pylon also caused transonic flow problems. After all the possible modifications Boeing realized the second generation 737 could still not compete with the A320 and resorted to a certification trick: "grandfather rights". It claimed that the second-generation Boeing 737 only had to meet certification rules holding at the time of the first generation and need not comply with current certification rules that applied to new aircraft like the A320. As consequence, the Boeing 737 could seat more passengers in a cabin smaller than that of the A320 by benefiting from outdated emergency evacuation standards. The granting of grandfather rights to the second-generation Boeing 737 by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) drew considerable criticism from outside the United States as a poorly disguised protectionist measure, and it was eventually agreed internationally that this would not be repeated in the future. Even with extensive redesign and the unfair economic advantage of carrying more passengers in a smaller cabin, the second-generation Boeing 737 struggled against the all-new A320, and Airbus reached a 30 % market share. The fourth stage of the Airbus challenge, the A330/A340, no longer benefited from the disdain or complacency of Boeing, that by now realized it had serious rival, and had to compete on merit rather than by tricks like «grandfather rights».

7.1.4 The A330/A340 and the Family Commonality Concept

The Boeing family of airliners consisting of the short haul 737 and medium haul 757 single aisle and wide body medium range 767 and long range 747 was a mixed bunch of designs with different ages and standards preventing economies of scale in crew training and maintenance tasks across different types. The more recent and up-to-date Airbus range besides consisting of models competitive individually against their Boeing counterparts had the additional advantage of commonalities requiring less maintenance infrastructure and shorter crew retraining across a mixed fleet. Airbus followed conventional belief (A) that long overwater flights required four engines, an assumption that may have been its only questionable choice and would haunt it since to this day. The fourth Airbus challenge (B) shared the fuselage cross-section of the A300/A310 in the twin engine medium range A330 and four engines long range A340, using different wings with the same gross weight capability that would later enable the A330neo. The A330/A340 completed the Airbus family started with the A300/A310 and continued with the A320 and enabled a 40 % market share. Contrary to the past Boeing had shaken off its former complacency and was back in its best competitive talent.

The earlier Boeing complacency was supported by the demise or decline in the marked of its main American competitors:

- The Convair CV-880/990 transcontinental four jets lacked the transoceanic range potential of the Boeing 707, and were the last Convair airliners:
- The failure of the carbon fibre fan in the Rolls-Royce RB.211 engine without a titanium fan alternative led to the end of the (Lockheed L-1011) Tristar as the last Lockheed airliner.

- McDonnell Douglas was limping along in a survival mode with low production rates of the DC-9/DC-10 and derivatives, surviving on spares revenue from existing fleets, which was doomed to decline.

The success of Boeing over Douglas was a testimony to boldness and innovation.

- The Boeing 707 held the lead over the Douglas DC-8 up to the series 50, until the DC-8-60 series stretch from 190 to 260 passengers gave a 25 % seat-mile advantage that could not be matched;
- Boeing countered with the first jumbo, the 747 that needed a new factory and did not fit existing airports, and made a success out of gambling on its existence;
- Douglas countered with the DC-10 as a wide body tri-jet, and cancelled the DC-8-60 series because it was too much of an internal competition;
- The decline of the DC-10/MD-10 versus B747/B767 and DC-9/MD-80 versus the B737/B757 allowed Boeing to take-over its last American competitor;
- The Boeing attempt to salvage the McDonnell Douglas MD-80/90 as a Boeing 717 was an abysmal failure, since no airline wanted an aircraft having nothing in common with the Boeing family except the name;
- Airbus had vowed not to make an aircraft smaller than the A319, but did an A318 to counter the B717, and managed relatively modest but still better sales than its rival.

By now the only significant remaining Boeing rival in the world airliner market was coming from an unexpected quarter: the Europe of government aeroplanes had spun a truly market oriented competitor: Airbus. NASA complained that a complacent Boeing was no longer interested in new technologies, which were not needed for the sole market leader. All changed as Boeing decided to counter head-on the Airbus A330/A340, focusing on its two weak points (A) and (B) above.

Boeing made the bold assumption that twin-engine aircraft could fly overwater over the whole world, including both the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans. The realization that modern turbofan engines seldom failed in cruise lead to the prospect of extended overwater flights more than 90 minutes away from the nearest airport. ETOPS allowance increased steadily from 90 minutes to over 3 hours allowing almost unrestricted transatlantic and transpacific flights. With ETOPS Boeing needed only one twin-engined B777 to counter the A330/A340 pair.

With the benefit of the hindsight of coming later Boeing add to (A) the further gauntlet (B) choosing a wider fuselage cross-section than that the A330/A340 'inherited' from the A300/A310. The larger capacity of the B777 versus the A340 had this time Airbus scrambling back to the drawing board with the A340-600. Bound to the same cross-section as the A300/A310/A330 all that Airbus could do was to increase the length of the fuselage to the airport limit; the A340-600 had the longest fuselage of any airliner and was the first whose flying qualities were affected by the elastic modes of the fuselage. The A340-600 was almost a totally new aircraft relative to earlier A340 variants, and the large effort and expenditure in its development served only to prolong its life for some years. The end of production of the A340 left the airliner market only with twins except for the old B747 and new A380 still based on the belief that 4 engines were needed for long overwater flights.

7.1.5 The A380 the World's Largest Airliner

The initial rationale for the Airbus A380 was quite compelling:

- Airbus had reached a 40 % market share and was competing with Boeing on every sector except the jumbo aircraft;
- Boeing was using its 'jumbo monopoly' selling a B747 for twice the price of a B767, collecting profits to finance the rest of the range;
- In order to reach 50 % or parity Airbus had to challenge Boeing in every sector, breaking its last monopoly with the jumbo aircraft.

As the world's largest airliner the A380 was not short of challenges:

- Its size and weight were well beyond the minimum weight per passenger of an airliner at about 350 seats;
- As a consequence, the A380 had 30 novel weight saving features, like 4,000 psi hydraulics instead of the 3,000 psi standard up to then;
- Given the larger number of in-flight entertainment systems for passenger seats with different arrangements for each airline the replacement of copper wires by aluminium wires was one of the 30 significant weight savings.

This apparently innocuous change was the start of a far-reaching chain of events:

- The aluminium wires could not be bent to the same small radius as copper wires, leading to installation problems that were reported late;
- The Airbus method of sending fully equipped sections for final assembly maximizes added value partners (the opposite of Boeing);
- The arrival of unfinished sections at final assembly caused a production bottleneck with a large number of workers brought in from other factories;
- The rate of expenditure would have bankrupted Airbus in two years unless a new strategy was adopted;

The detailed redesign of elements of the A380 was not helped by another contrast:

- All Airbus partners used the CATIA design software developed by Dassault;
- Except its former Aerospatiale rival that used software from a firm in Seattle, the home of Boeing.

The Airbus A380 is certainly the most spacious and probably the most comfortable airliner flying. It is not only the largest airliner ever but also one of the most sophisticated. It did upstage the Boeing 747, which was in any case undermined by the Boeing 777 as an in-house rival.

7.1.6 The Sonic Cruiser, B787 and A350

Boeing recognized that the market could not support two jumbos, and thus decided not to develop a direct rival to the A380. The Airbus troubles with the A380 were an opportunity not to be missed to strike back in another sector. The Boeing counter, the 'sonic cruiser' was a daring and brilliant design: it managed to have a fuselage of constant cross-section while obeying the area rule for low shock wave drag by clever blending with the canard fore plane and main wing. It was capable of cruising

efficiently at Mach 0.95 versus Mach 0.85 for a conventional airliner, but sales may depend more on attractive economics than brilliant engineering. Boeing argued in vain that a 10-12% decrease in flight time in long-haul routes would allow more daily flights with the help of shorter turn around at airports. Airlines were not convinced, and Boeing brought along as a fall back the 7E7: a conventional design using the advanced technologies of the sonic cruiser, like a composite fuselage, to reduce cost. The 7E7 was the preferred choice every airline and became the Boeing 787. The B787 gained the largest order book of an airliner in history before its first flight. Boeing predicted that the 787 would be the its quickest development and certification programme in recent times with entry into service 3 years from start-up. This optimism was not supported by a development period more than twice as long, with perhaps not surprising problems in the production of the single barrel all composite fuselage. After entry into service, the Boeing choice of a type of lithium-ion battery with high energy density for low weight, turned out to cause battery fires that were cured by a redesign adding weight. Notwithstanding the usual development hurdles the Boeing 787 is a considerable success, this time helped by the reluctance of Airbus to offer a matching competitor.

Saddled with the A380 issues Airbus could hardly cherish another totally new aircraft development. In contrast with the past, when Boeing was slow or inadequate in its responses, this time it was Airbus that delayed a competitive answer. The initial Airbus argument that the A330 was an already available B787 competitor did not convince airlines. The reluctant further developments of the A330 were not too well received either, although the second generation A330neo later proved to be a moderate market success. When Airbus finally accepted the reality that nothing short of a new clean sheet design would convince airlines, the A350 was the resulting clever design 'splitting' the B787 and B777:

- Larger than the B787 with comparable cost;
- Comparable in size to the B777 with lower cost.

This clever killing of two rabbits with a single stroke drew the predictable matching reaction from Boeing;

- a – Trying to improve the competitiveness of the 787;
- b – Stretching the 777 to a second generation 777X beyond the growth potential of the A350.

The move (b) meant that the B777X effectively superseded the B747 and also brought the world's largest twin airliner in stronger competition with the A380 as the world's largest airliner and nearly sole remaining four engine type. Concerning move (a) the reengining of the Airbus A330 as the second generation A330neo proved after all that a cheaper to buy and cost-effective to operate aircraft could be rapidly developed as an alternative to the B787. The A330neo was inspired by the success story of the A320neo.

7.1.7 The Bombardier C-series, Airbus A320neo and Boeing B737max

The third and fourth largest airliner manufactures in the world, Embraer of Brazil and Bombardier of Canada, are about one-tenth of the size of the two world leaders, Boeing of America and Airbus of Europe. Only the brave or the foolish would try to bridge a gap of one order of magnitude. Embraer has wisely stayed below the Airbus-Boeing market, perhaps scraping it at the lower end, without ever venturing into a direct challenge. Bombardier claimed it was not trying to compete with Airbus or Boeing but in fact tried to do just that with the C-series. The main advantage of the Bombardier C-series was a new generation of geared turbofans from Pratt & Whitney; this advantage would easily

disappear if the same engine was adopted by the A320 or B737. The PW1200 geared fan had the development problems and delays of its own and comparable performance was achieved by the Snecma/General Electric LEAP engine, which used advanced technology in a more conventional design to come to market earlier. Not only the Bombardier C-series lead in engines was lost, but also the lead in time was compromised by development problems delaying entry into service. The Bombardier C-series was completely upstaged by the rival developments of the Airbus A320neo and Boeing B737max, and the acquisition of a majority in the C-Series by Airbus marked the end of adventurous challenge. In fact, the reactions of Airbus and Boeing to the Bombardier C-series were somewhat different.

Airbus would not let the Bombardier C-series erode the A320 market; bearing in mind the first generation A320 was relatively modern and efficient, a second generation reengining in the A320neo would completely upstage the challenger and consolidate its market. The A320neo was a runaway success, collecting orders at a rate never seen before, and forcing Boeing to enter the fray with the third generation B737max. Boeing was understandably reluctant to go into a third generation of the B737:

- The first generation was by now over 50 years old;
- The second generation had struggled against the first generation A320 with the help of grandfather rights;
- Without the help of grandfather rights, a third redesign of the B737 would be an even greater struggle against a second generation of the newer Airbus A320.

The Boeing decision to counter the new A320 with a second generation B737 rather than a new design came back to haunt it again with the third generation B737 versus the second generation A320. For example, the low ground clearance of the flat-bottomed nacelle of the second generation B737 could only become a more difficult problem with the increased diameter of more recent higher by-pass ratio engines. Boeing was well aware that the engine under the wing of the third generation B737 would have a smaller diameter and lower by-pass ratio than for the second generation A320. This shortfall in engine efficiency would have to be compensated in other areas like aerodynamics, yet Airbus would hardly be left behind in any area and allow Boeing to recover its weaker starting position. The preference of Boeing was to let some years pass to design an all new single-aisle replacement for the B737. For this reason, Boeing did not feel it necessary to counter immediately the Bombardier C-series, but after the runaway success of the Airbus A320neo it had no choice but to join the fray. Just Airbus had been reluctant to launch the A350 to counter the B787, Boeing was reluctant to launch the third generation B737max against the second generation A320neo. In both cases there was no choice, with the A350 recovering only partially the order book lost to the B787, and similarly the B737max trying to narrow the initial gap to the A320neo.

In addition, the gap between the third generation of the old B737 and the second generation of the not so old A320 neo, created another market impact:

- The A320neo has enough stretch potential into the A321neo, which is an effective replacement for the Boeing 757, still used on long thin routes;
- The lack of stretch potential in the B737 max means there is no fast and cheap alternative and requires a new middle of the market (MoM) aircraft.

Although Boeing has toyed with the idea of a MoM, which is what it would have liked to do instead of the 737max, the prospects are challenging. A new aircraft can be amortized only if it at least a 10 % improvement in fuel consumption to lower direct operating costs. This is unlikely to be achieved bearing in mind that the A320neo and B737max use state-of-the-art engines and a new engine generation might be needed. The development of a new middle of the market aircraft would be costly and time consuming, and it is questionable if the market left unfulfilled would allow a break even. Boeing is at last having to live with the consequences of soldiering for too long with the B737 and may after all not have gained much from the trick of grandfather rights in the long term; it would be doing better now with a less old design. Airbus is benefiting from a more recent A320 design that was an inevitable consequence of being a newcomer to the market. However, with a production lifetime of 10 years longer than the 8 years of the A320, the B737 still has a larger number of units sold, although the gap may reduce in the future. This sets the background for the current status of the Airbus versus Boeing competition in the airliner market (section 3.2).

7.2 The Current Status of the Airbus-Boeing Competition

The situation is different in the single-aisle narrow body (subsection 7.2.1) and twin-aisle wide body (subsection 7.2.2) market leading to an approximate balance with Airbus leading the former and Boeing the latter. Both Airbus and Boeing are in the healthy situation of having the largest order books in history and face challenges in achieving higher production rates (subsection 7.2.3). The profits may be invested (section 7.2.4) in evolutionary developments of existing aircraft (section 7.2.5) or in totally new designs that will require years of maturation to incorporate new technologies (subsection 7.2.7). When the new designs (section 7.2.6) come perhaps 10 or more years away they may still be the ultimate evolutions of the tube-and-wing configuration (subsection 7.2.8) rather than the more radical concepts (like flying wings or joined wings) that may require an intermediate stage of large-scale demonstrators (subsection 7.2.8).

7.2.1 Single-Aisle or Narrow-Body Market

The prompt and decisive response of Airbus to the Bombardier C-series challenge lead to a large order book for the A320neo as the second generation A320. The delays and hesitations of Boeing to commit to the third generation B737max lead to a response only when there was a large gap to recover. Boeing proposed the third generation B737max to avoid the risk of losing traditional and faithful airline customers. This customer base amounted to a substantial backlog reducing but not closing the gap to the A320neo. The stretched A321neo dominates the long, thin route market, without a clear match in the B737 family, so this part of the gap is not readily closed. Boeing would need an all-new Middle of the Market aircraft that might come too late to an already partially filled market, with questionable profitability. A bold and risky decision to develop the MoM aircraft by Boeing may be necessary to remain a strong supplier of narrow bodies in competition with Airbus. The Airbus lead in the orders of narrow bodies may be balanced by a Boeing lead in wide bodies, with higher unit values compensating the smaller number to lead to comparable profitability.

7.2.2 Twin-Aisle or Wide Body Market

The situation here was the reverse of the A320neo lead over the B737max, with Boeing amassing a large backlog of B787 orders before Airbus replaced its evolved A330 plans by an all new A350. The A350 effectively targeted the B787 offering higher capacity for comparable cost. And the second generation reengineered A330neo proved after all that it also had a market as a lower cost B787

competitor. The double pronged counterattack with the A350 and A330neo allowed Airbus to narrow the gap to the B787, helped by the development delays of the latter to reduce the effects of a late response. The A350 had the second task of matching the B777 capacity at lower cost, which it did at the then status. But Boeing could hardly be expected to sit still and let two of its products be challenged by a single Airbus product. The second generation stretched 777X moved beyond the stretch potential of the A350, and at the risk of killing the already moribund B747, sharpened the challenge to the A380. The prospects of a second-generation Airbus A380neo look at least as challenging as those of the Boeing MoM aircraft: both could come too late at a too high development cost to break even.

7.2.3 Production Ramp-Up to Meet Large Order Books

One point that Airbus and Boeing share is their biggest order books in history, to the extent some sceptics point to historic risk of a collapse of the order bubble. This time around with a backlog of several years and a steady growth of air transport, it hard to see how a calamity of such scale could occur. An unlikely big decline in the airliner market would have several years of production as a cushion and large-scale cancellations do not seem to fit airline plans. Rather the reverse, the industry is still trying to recover from an unexpected order boom. Tom Enders, the CEO of Airbus said, that if some years ago someone suggested a production rate of 30 A320 per month he would have thought this was outright foolishness; but now Airbus is aiming at 60 A320 per month and even at this rate will take several years to fulfil its current backlog. Although many orders are the 'nice to have problem' it does pose many challenges, not only at expanding the final production line but also with suppliers: some may be wary of growing oversize, especially when Boeing tries to squeeze lower prices. Others may see expansion plans limited by access to credit. In some cases, Airbus has bought suppliers mainly to ensure that they have the resources to deliver the required quantities.

7.2.4 Continued Competition Through Evolutionary Developments

A heavy workload in increasing final production rates and shoring up the supply chain to much higher outputs leaves Airbus and Boeing with little spare capacity for major all-new designs. The current aircraft are selling at unprecedented rates so there is no need or incentive to come up with radical improvements. A radical improvement might require much more efficient engines; but the reengineered second and third generation aircraft already rely on the latest and most advanced technology, so there is little scope for major improvement in a few years. Besides the engine manufactures are enjoying an order boom in proportion to that of airframe manufactures: Snecma and General Electric have challenges similar to Airbus and Boeing in increasing the final production rates and shoring up the supplier base; in spite of problems with the geared fan at Pratt & Whitney and the 'self-limitation' of Rolls Royce to wide body engines, neither seems to be in a less than healthy state. With both airframe and engine manufacturers busy to fill order books, incremental improvements are the feasible option, waiting for major progress that could take 5 to 10 years to mature to enable new designs.

However, both Airbus and Boeing face challenging situations, at opposite ends of the market: (i) Airbus with the A380; (i) Boeing with a middle-of-the-market aircraft (MMA) to complement the B737max (section 7.2.6)

7.2.5 The Prospects of the Airbus A380

Apart of the B747 as freighter, the A380 is the last four jet airliner on the market. The economic disadvantage relative to long-range wide-body twins is exacerbated by retaining an older generation of less efficient engines. Two flights of the B787/A350 carry as many passengers as a single A380 flight at comparable or lower cost, with greater flexibility of schedule but using twice as many airport slots. The A380 would require the thrust of 3 existing engines sizes for the B777/A350 but this is not a feasible configuration. The development of a new twin engine configuration would require much larger engines than those currently available. Retaining four new engines would imply development costs that engine suppliers may not shoulder due to limited market prospects. A more favourable prospect would arise if the new engine(s) developed for the new Boeing MMA twin-aisle twin-engine aircraft proved suitable for reengining the four-engine A380; this might be feasible later than the Boeing MMA entry into market and might involve considerable development cost, that a limited market might or might not justify.

The A380 may survive in an unmodified or modestly changed form for several years, at a modest and marginally economic or uneconomical production rate based on orders from a few airlines that value two of its unique characteristics:

- The passenger preference for its large lounge-like cabin with high levels of comfort;
- The ability to make the most of a limited number of slots at congested airports by carrying the highest possible number of passengers in the largest available airliner.

Airbus may be betting that the last factor will ultimately lead to a resurgence of the A380 orders, as air traffic grows faster than the runways and slots at major hubs, and airlines may have to exploit more fully whatever slots are available to them, by using the largest available aircraft.

7.2.6 The Boeing Middle-of-the-Market Aircraft (MMA)

The challenges that Boeing faces at the small capacity end of the market with the B737 Max are, if anything, more serious than the Airbus prospects with the A380. For a start the A321neo stretch beyond the capacity of the B737 to which Boeing must respond in order to continue to compete in the long thin routes. Boeing may have brought another challenge to itself by opposing the "subsidized" sales of the Bombardier C-Series in the United States. The cost-free acquisition of majority rights in the C-Series leaves Airbus with a formidable and comprehensive line-up of the state-of-the-art airliners in the 100-300 seat range:

- The Bombardier C-Series is optimised for 100-150 seats and is a good alternative to the slow selling A319 shrink of the A320;
- The A320neo remains a strong and efficient contender for the 150-200 seats;
- The A3201neo dominates the long thin routes with 200-250 seats with its stretch potential;
- Beyond 250 seats the A330neo has a competitive price and good economy.

The link with Airbus benefits Bombardier C-series in several ways:

- Not only in circumventing possible United States protectionism by having final assembly at the Airbus facility in America;
- Also, because the Airbus clout can bring suppliers prices to levels that Bombardier would not be able to obtain, making the C-Series more competitive in capital cost;

- The Airbus sales and support network and the integration in a product line ranging all the way up from 100 seats gives a dimension to the C-Series that Bombardier could not hope to achieve on its own.

Thus, even after the confirmed failure of the Boeing attempt to block some C-Series sales in the United States, Bombardier has every good reason to pursue and cherish the Airbus tie-up that is beneficial to both, and hard to match by Boeing, that has no choice but to try.

Against the formidable line-up of the C-Series/A319/A320neo/A321LR/A330neo Boeing has only the third generation of B737 that manages to compete in the 130-200 seat range, leaving an important slice of the market for the replacement of the B757/B767, currently used on long thin routes, almost unchallenged to Airbus. The expected reaction to the Airbus-Bombardier link with a Boeing-Embraer link is predictable but not equally effective:

- The Embraer E2 Series does not go beyond 120 seats compared with 150 seats of the Bombardier C-Series;
- This leaves Boeing with the challenge to cover the 100-300 seat range with the existing B737max below 200 seats and the new MMA above.

While it is inevitable that Boeing must launch an MMA the challenges it faces are considerable:

- In order to differentiate from Airbus offerings and compensate late arrival to market it could be a twin-aisle, but this adds cost;
- Unless the Embraer E2 range is stretched beyond 120 seats covering the lower part of the 100-300 seat range, means soldiering along with B737max and waiting 5-7 years at least for the entry to market of the MMA.
- To recover the investment in a new MMA, airlines need a 10% increase in efficiency that will require a new engine for which all major suppliers (General Electric/Snecma, Pratt & Withney and Rolls-Royce) will be competing;
- The development time and time to market of a totally new clean sheet Boeing MMA will give Airbus plenty of opportunity to upgrade its current range at lower cost to try to reduce the market impact of its rival;
- If Boeing succeeds in putting the MMA beyond the nearly exhausted potential of the A321LR, Airbus can still, with the benefit of hindsight, decide to develop an all new aircraft possibly superior in at least some aspects.

Overall, Airbus should be able to keep an upper hand in the 100-300 seat airliner market until significant new technologies are implemented. In any case the healthy and still growing order books of both Airbus and Boeing, if they can rise to the challenge of increased production, bring revenues to do more than evolutionary developments. Both Airbus and Boeing have the financial resources and engineering talent to keep up their healthy competition to the benefit of airlines and their passengers.

7.2.7 The Promise of Radical New Configurations

Recent years have seen a growing interest in configurations distinct from the classical tube-and-wing of current airliners dating back to the vision of Sir George Cayley in the mid XIX-th century. The sometimes called radically new configurations like flying wings or joined wings were envisioned about 80 years ago in the period between the two world wars, though use has been sporadic until recently.

The Northrop Grumman B-2 Spirit stealth flying wing bomber and a variety of drone (UAV-Unmanned Air Vehicle) designs have proved the viability of these concepts in several contexts. However, airliner design is subject to a long list of technical, certification, economic and operational requirements that extend beyond military and drone requirements. The case of the flying wing serves as an illustration of this point. There are clear advantages:

- The higher lift-to-drag ratio can lead to a reduction of 20 % in fuel consumption and emissions;
- The large internal volume of the thick wing provides plenty of passenger and cargo space;
- The choice of overwing engine nacelles, or flush or buried engines, or distributed propulsion would reduce noise at airports.

All these benefits do not come without challenges, some of which can erode the final result:

- The engine nacelles in the accelerated airflow above the wing are affected by compressibility effects at lower speeds than underwing nacelles, and could reduce cruise speed for the same drag;
- The engines at the rear top of the wing would lie in a thick boundary, whose ingestion could cause stall or operating problems, that could become more serious for flush or buried engines;
- Distributed propulsion raises issues of transmission of power, like high pressure losses in ducted flows or resistive dissipation of high-electric currents;
- The top mounted rear engines create a large pitch down moment opposing rotation at take-off, requiring large lift and angle-of-attack and a long undercarriage to avoid tail scrapes;
- the trimming of the large pitch down moment in cruise with upward deflection of trailing-edge control surfaces would reduce lift and lower lift-to-drag ratio benefits;
- The wide fuselage would place most inboard passengers far from the windows whereas outboard passengers would have large displacements in roll manoeuvres;
- The certification requirement of emergency evacuation in darkness from one random side of the fuselage in 90 seconds is more difficult to meet in a wide and short cabin than in a long and thin one;
- The easy isotropic pressurization of a cylindrical fuselage does not apply to a flying wing that must be either divided into tubes or need extra bracing or both.

This sample of issues shows that it is not a straightforward conclusion to decide on the overall benefits of new aircraft configurations, although they will inevitably come, sooner or later.

7.2.8 The Next Generation and One After

Given the current large order backlog of modernized aircraft and the time to mature further significant advances in technology, the next generation in technology may not come in less than 5-10 years' time, with market competition making the Boeing MMA the most likely all new aircraft no sooner than 2022. It will be a tube-and-wing aircraft, a configuration whose potential is far from exhausted, since it is possible to incorporate several improvements. On the other hand, the radical transition to a new configuration could be too risky an experiment in a market-oriented product. A half-scale demonstrator of a new configuration like a flying wing or joined wing might be useful to:

- Convince industry that all design trade-offs have been mastered and a reliable design data base has been created;

- Allow certification authorities, service providers, airlines, airports and maintenance organizations to prepare for upcoming changes;
- Familiarize and educate the public about upcoming progress out of past precedent.

The prospect of an evolved tube-and-wing next generation and a flying wing generation to follow may depend on a major effort for in-flight validation of the latter in parallel with development of the former. The precursor half-for full-scale Boeing flying wing aircraft could arise out of a NASA experimental aircraft programme or a tanker/transport aircraft for the US Air Force or a combination of both. In this case Europe should not fall behind and must support a comparable flying wing demonstrator.

7.3 The Regional Jet and Turboprop Market

The regional jet (subsection 7.3.1) and turboprop (subsection 7.3.2) market cannot be separated from the long-distance air travel (sections 7.1-7.2) because it acts as its feeder at major hubs, besides serving also shorter routes. It is also an important market for Europe, much more accessible to other entrants (subsection 7.3.2) than the Airbus-Boeing duopoly of giants. The link Airbus-Bombardier on the C-Series and the possible counter Boeing-Embraer on the E-Series imply a tie-up between regional and long-range jet airliners.

The reduction of the number of competing suppliers, from 4 to 2, may not please airlines, since it could extend the Airbus-Boeing duopoly from long-range to regional jets.

7.3.1 The Embraer E170/E190 Family of Regional Jets

Embraer has recognized the limits of an order of magnitude difference to Airbus and Boeing by staying below their markets and at most scraping the bottom end. It has avoided the risky challenge of the Bombardier C-series and used new geared fan engines later in the development cycle with reduced risk. As consequence, Embraer has built a steady and stable market share, evolving from regional turboprops to regional jets, in a relatively smooth and orderly transition. The misfortunes of the Bombardier C-series lead to some neglect or underfunding of other activities, and thus Bombardier could not disturb significantly Embraer inroads in the regional jet market, although it has a larger order book. The Airbus majority share in the C-Series strengthens very much the Bombardier position; it remains to be seen what effect the Boeing-Embraer talks will have, when a conclusion is reached.

7.3.2 The ATR42/72 Family of Regional Turboprops

The ATR42/72 family is the survivor of the European offer of regional airliners, following the demise of Dornier, rundown of British Aerospace models, end of SAAB 340 production and concentration of CASA on military transports. The revival of the ATR42/72 is due to the superior economics of turboprops over jets, with modest compromise on flight time due to lower speed on short routes. The Italian side of ATR has in the past advocated an extension to the 100-seats; a view apparently not shared by the French side. A basic question is whether the size of the market would justify the development cost and lead to break even in an acceptable time scale. Some speculate Airbus could fear that a hypothetical ATR100 would compete with the modest selling A319 or erode the bottom of the vast A320 market. The Airbus-Bombardier deal on the C-Series and a more cautious approach on the Leonardo side may lead to a focus on updates to the ATR42/72 rather than stretched or new aircraft.

Another explanation is that Airbus may not wish to follow the unsuccessful example of the Boeing acquisition of Canadair regional aircraft ending in a sale to Bombardier after years of losses. It appears that the large corporate structure of Airbus and Boeing is well suited to the design and production of long-range single and twin aisle jet liners, but not cost-effective at the one-tenth smaller scale of regional aircraft best left to smaller industry groups. The other contenders in the regional aircraft market include Japan, Russia, China and Ukraine, and are considered next in the broader context of potential competitors in the airline market.

7.4 Potential Competitors in the Airline Market

The Soviet Union had alternatives to offer in every airline market sector (subsection 7.4.1), although the closed and sheltered nature of its clients made a difficult transition to the post-soviet partial collapse of the Russian aircraft industry. Japan's experience in contributing substantially to the design and production of Boeing airliners, has led to the design of complete regional aircraft, with no signs of higher ambition (subsection 7.4.2). That ambition clearly exists in China but may need foreign collaboration more likely from Russia than from Ukraine (subsection 7.4.3).

7.4.1 The transition from Soviet to Russian Airliners

The closed monolithic posture of the Soviet Union required that there must be an airliner in every sector, to be also used by satellite countries and support mostly politically motivated exports of:

- The Tupolev Tu-104/124/134 twin jets;
- The Tupolev Tu-154 tri-jet;
- The Ilyushin IL-62 four jet;
- The Ilyushin IL-86 widebody;
- The Yakolev IL-42 regional jet;
- The Ilyushin IL-38 regional turboprop.

The Tupolev Tu-144 Konkorskii never entered airline service. All others in the list above were produced in some numbers and operated over the years without having to face the competition of western airliners. The collapse of the Soviet Union led to an abrupt change, with Russian airlines buying western airliners that were more efficient and reliable, besides having much better after sales support. The poor record of Soviet era aircraft for reliability and inadequate spares support was only made worse by the near collapse of the former Soviet civil aircraft industry.

The former military aircraft industry survived better the collapse of the Soviet Union and transition to the Russian Federation, mainly through the Sukhoi family Flanker fighter variants, that gathered enough export orders to overcome the decline of the home military market. Its former fighter house rivals Mikoyan-Gurevich fared worse with limited sales of the Mig-29 Fulcrum and Mig-25/31 Foxbat/Foxhound relying mainly on the home market. The outcome of the reorganization of the former Soviet into the 'new' Russian aircraft industry was that:

- Mainly civil design bureaus like Tupolev, Ilyushin and Yakovlev tried to soldier on the basis of updated Soviet era designs that were not too competitive to start with;
- Of the predominantly military design bureaus only Sukhoi had the market and resources to lead the consolidation and rationalization;

- As consequence, Sukhoi became the leader in new civil aircraft designs in the Russian federation, an area in which it had never participated in Soviet times.

There is no hint of doubt of the ability of Sukhoi to design most types of competitive military or civil aircraft if the resources, engines and avionics are available. The Sukhoi regional aircraft was a limited success, but hardly better could be expected in the circumstances. The Sukhoi last civil challenge, a competitor for the Airbus A320neo/Boeing B737max was, at least on paper, an impressive design, matching the western aircraft in most respects, and perhaps having some edge in some areas by virtue of a clean sheet design versus second/third generation redesigns. However, a long series of factors dim commercial prospects for this impressive initial effort:

- Only one prototype was shown whereas several would be needed a certification program;
- There was no evidence of a production line let alone a complete chain;
- The maturity of Russian made systems was an open question;
- The Russian occupation of Crimea and interference in Ukraine cast doubts on the supply of western systems;
- This included western engines and avionics for which Russia has no equivalents;
- The 'Russification' of engine and avionics technologies to western standards would be costly and slow;
- The western sanctions and low oil prices reduced the Russian budget for all sectors, including aviation;
- The militaristic and aggressive Russian policy gives priority to military over civil aviation;
- Given the cuts in military aircraft development and production it would be surprising indeed if civil aviation would fare any better;
- Even if a fully Russianized aircraft could be produced the necessary spares support for exports might not be credible.

It appears that Russia will have to make do with updated obsolete soviet types with limited export potential or failing that rely on western airliners or slowly develop more modern types in collaboration with China.

7.4.2 Japan`s Market Captive to Boeing

The large trade surplus of Japan relative to the U.S. has led to a long-standing policy of the Japanese government to keep the airline industry aware of the patriotic duty to buy Boeing. Not content with having a sizeable captive Japanese market, Boeing has subcontracted to Japanese industry the design, development and production of major parts of its aircraft. It has been mentioned that up to 40 % of the B787 development was financed by Japan. It is clear that, in these circumstances Japan is most unlikely to launch a Boeing competitor, and will instead continue to blend in, share and finance Boeing designs, keeping Airbus out of the Japanese market. The Japanese ambitions for the design of complete civil aircraft are thus limited to regional airliners. The Nanc YS-10 twin turboprop was an example in a distant past stretching to the current Mitsubishi MRJ-110. The Japanese have maintained a significant research effort in supersonic airliner design in the hope of become a full partner if such a project ever sees the light of the day after the memory of Concorde.

7.4.3 China`s Turboprop and Turbojet Certification Hurdles

China is well aware of the value of the aircraft industry. When the EU considered taxes or sanctions against Chinese 'dumping' practices, there was a reminder that "a single jet airliner is worth 200 million t-shirts". There is an Airbus A320 final assembly line in China using entirely imported components. When Airbus proposed sourcing locally some components the Chinese airlines rejected the idea. Embraer planned business jet production in China; however, the Chinese government taxed components imported for the Phenom business aircraft, making the whole operation unprofitable; Embraer had to scrap the production plan at a loss. These two opposite events show the Chinese government emphasis on local production and airlines mistrust of the same.

The Chinese have developed a turboprop and a jet regional airliner plus a single-aisle competitor to the A320/B737. The flight tests of prototypes have dragged on for years without certification being achieved. When asked about these long-delayed development programmes Chinese officials reply that their efforts are much younger than the decades of Airbus and Boeing experience. In desperation China has asked Rockwell-Collins to help it certificate its 3 civil airliners, as if this could be a job for an avionics company alone. The Chinese lag behind most in engine technology. The engineer that developed the first Chinese military engine for the J-10 fighter received the highest decoration of the country, although the power plant appears to be rather unreliable, not boding well for the next developments of civil engines.

The Chinese difficulties in certifying its three civil aircraft, if and when eventually overcome, could lead to a significant change in the local and global market:

- The Chinese domestic market is large enough to support airliner development on its own;
- The availability of Chinese aircraft, say a single-aisle airliner, could partially close the local market for the A320/B737;
- A Chinese aircraft in this class would use western engines and avionics, so the advantage of low labour rates on final cost could be small;
- It cannot be excluded that the Chinese would promote exports by the use dumping or subsidies as they have been accused in the past on lower value products;
- The focus of Chinese trade in Asia, Africa and South America and its lack of concern with local ethics could increase penetration of those markets;
- Even if unable to compete on fair terms in Europe and North America, the Chinese could significantly erode the Airbus and Boeing markets.

The hardest sector for the Chinese to crack is wide body airliners, requiring cooperation with Russia or Ukraine.

7.4.4 China`s Path Towards Wide-Body Airliners

The Chinese are clearly very far from being able to produce a wide body airliner, both from the airframe and propulsion points-of-view. The signature of a Sino-Russian agreement at the highest head-of-state level to jointly develop a wide body airliner demonstrates the high priority in both countries not to depend on Airbus and Boeing and to compete with them. This agreement could be seen as a partnership of Russian aviation technology and Chinese finance and market. The available Russian wide body technology is the update Ilyushin IL-86 converted to IL-96 with engines less efficient and reliable than western engines; it's not really competitive now and would be less in the

future. Besides the former Soviet experience with large aircraft was with Antonov military transports powered by Ivchenko high by-pass ratio engines both located in Ukraine, outside Russia now. The logical step of a Chinese approach to Ukraine would be most welcome for all sorts of reasons ranging from political, to economic, financial and technical. The pair Antonov Aircraft/Ivchenko Progress engines has long record of producing some of the largest aircraft and engines at the time:

- the Antonov An-12 Cub was the standard Soviet tactical transport, as the Lockheed C-130 Hercules in the U.S. and Transall C-160 in Europe, and is currently produced in China;
- The Antonov An-70 with its contra-rotating propfan pioneered 20 years ago the technology now used in the Airbus A400M Atlas;
- The Antonov An-22 Antei was a four-turboprop large transport that preceded the An-124 Ruslan as a rival to the Lockheed C-5 Galaxy and Boeing C-17 Globemaster in the US.:
- By growing the An-124 from 4 to 6 underwing engines the payload was increased from 150 to 250 tons in the single prototype of the An-225 Mryia, that with a gross weight of 600 tons is the world's heaviest aircraft.

The tale of Antonov and Ivchenko after the collapse of the Soviet Union was a complex one:

- The close links between the Russian and Ukrainian aircraft industries meant that Russia remained an important but reluctant client, trying to do without Ukrainian products whenever possible;
- The 20-years lead of the An-70 was lost in protracted development of an Ukrainian aircraft and engine that Russia did not want to fund or depend on;
- Antonov/Ivchenko explored their smaller regional aircraft but this was a limited source of revenue;
- The An-124 Ruslan operated by Dnieper airliners become a leader in worldwide air transport of outsize loads, for example in United Nations humanitarian missions;
- The annexation of Crimea and Russian military intervention in the Donbass area was the final strain in soured relations, and a loss to both sides;
- Russia lost a part of its aviation supply chain that it would be costly and long to replace;
- Ukraine had to replace facilities lost in the Donbass region and look for new markets.
- The Ukrainian recovery strategy has succeeded in at least in the production of regional aircraft in Saudi Arabia;
- License production of the An-225 in China has been reported in the press.

The latter would be a heaven's send that could allow China to overcome all its current limitations:

- Its military transports are based on the Antonov An-12 equivalent to the C-130 Hercules and Ilyushin Il-76 equivalent to the C-141 Starlifter; it lacks a strategic transport like the Lockheed C-5 Galaxy and Boeing C-17 Globemaster and is behind the Airbus A400M Atlas.
- The An-225 will give China the world's largest military transport aircraft and a power projection capability worldwide to exceed Russia and Europe and rival the US;
- Ivchenko can provide not only the engines for the An-225, but also for Chinese fighters, helicopters and other aircraft;
- The availability of a full range of modern engines gives the Chinese time to develop their own with less dependence on Russia or the west.

The news of licence production of the AN-225 in China has not been confirmed.

Instead the focus has returned to cooperation with Russia on a CR-929R wide-body with a range of 7 500 mm with 270 passengers. The designation CR-929R indicates the Chinese intent:

- The Chinese 'C' to follow the Airbus 'A' and the Boeing 'B';
- The 929 wide body to follow the 919 narrow body family;
- The 'R' in CR-929R for collaboration with Russia.

China had tried to buy the troubled Bombardier C-Series program which could have paved the way for the long relayed C919 certification. This was prevented by the cost-free acquisition of a majority stake by Airbus in the C-Series that was a master stroke in several aspects:

- It prevents Chinese access to western airliner design and certification expertise;
- It extends the Airbus range down to 100-150 seats with an alternative to the slow selling A319;
- It compounds the challenge that Boeing faces with the B737max and future MMA.

Thus, China may have to rely on cooperation with Russia on the CR-929R wide body which may not help with the certification of the C-919 and ARJ21.

7.5 The Business Jet Market and Supersonic Prospects

The business jet market extends from the largest airliners customized for heads of state to private aircraft flown by their owners (subsection 7.5.1). The next civil supersonic transport following Concorde (subsection 7.5.2) could be a supersonic business jet (subsection 7.5.3). Hypersonic or orbital travel (subsection 7.5.4) would be farther into the future.

7.5.1 A Wide Range of Business Jets and Fractional Ownership

A small fraction of Airbus and Boeing airliner production goes into business jets, mainly in two groups:

- At the upper end the wide bodies like the A380 and A340, and B747 and B777 customized for heads of state, royal families and wealthy individuals;
- -At the lower end the corporate narrow bodies like the A320 and B737 used to transport several company officials from and to the closest airports independently of airline schedules.

Just below in size the top rank of dedicated business jets by Gulfstream aviation can have comparable speed, range and comfort in a narrower fuselage and costs that are not much lower than single-aisle airliners. The main European competitor Dassault keeps a family of efficient long and medium range Falcon series business jets. Smaller regional business jets are produced by other manufacturers like Cessna with the extensive Citation range. Embraer has entered the market at the low end with the Phenom series, going gradually up in scale. This contrasts with its arch-rival Bombardier established for a longer time as supplier of high-end large business jets, some doubling as regional jetliners. Some models like the Learjet, Hawker and Aero have changed ownership several times. At the very low end some low-cost business jets are supposed to be flown by their owners. The general trend is in the opposite direction of fractional ownership with an aircraft or a large fleet shared by several owners. This may amount to flight by the hour including aircraft, engines, flight crew, maintenance and other

costs. The successor to the first supersonic airliner Concorde (subsection 7.5.2) could come in another category as a supersonic business jet (subsection 7.5.3).

7.5.2 The Unsurpassed Technical Achievements of Concorde

Although it was designed in the 1950s, first flew in the 1960s and ceased airline operations in the last century, Concorde as the first supersonic airliner remains an unsurpassed achievement in many areas:

- Its ogival wing combines high sweepback angle at the root and tip for high speed flight with lower sweepback in the middle for greater span for low speed flight;
- The highly swept delta wing was tested at low speed in the specially designed Handley Page H.P.115 experimental aircraft, to check that it had acceptable flying qualities;
- The ogival wing was tested at high-speed up to Mach 2.2 in another experimental aircraft, the BAC 221 itself an extensive redesign of the Fairey Delta FD.2;
- The choice of a Mach 2.08 cruising speed was made to stay below the heat barrier and allow the use of a special aluminium alloy in the structure;
- The Bristol Siddeley Olympus engine grew in thrust from 4.5 tons in the series 100 in the Avro Vulcan Mk.1/Handley Page Victor Mk.1 bombers, to 9 tons in the 200 series of the Mk.2 bombers, to 13.6 tons in Concorde augmented to 16.2 tons with afterburning;
- Supersonic cruise did not require afterburning and careful aerodynamic design gave the same range in subsonic as in supersonic flight;
- Afterburning was used only on take-off and landing, with the high angle-of-attack requiring a droop nose, and flying at the 'back' of the power curve, that required special pilot training and skill;
- Sophisticated multi-ramp air intakes were needed to match the airflow to the engine over a wide range of speeds from twice the speed of sound to stalling speed;
- The motion of the centre of lift changing between subsonic and supersonic flight required fuel transfer to keep pitch trim, thus adding another flight critical system;
- The passenger payload was only 8% of the gross weight giving little margin for weight growth in the development of such a complex aircraft.

Technical excellence does not always equate to market success, and Concorde faced many other challenges:

- The development cost of one billion pounds for each partner country Britain and France could never be recovered;
- Only 16 aircraft were produced, 8 each for Air France and British Airways, with no further orders;
- The flights were always full of passengers willing to pay higher fares for the privilege of flying at twice the speed of sound in a unique aircraft instead of flying first class in a more conventional airplane;
- The sonic boom limited supersonic flight to overwater routes in the Atlantic, with acceleration and deceleration bins of shock wave concentration in inhabited areas in the English Channel and near Newfoundland in Canada;
- Flights between London/Paris and New York/Washington took half the time of other aircraft;
- Flights to the Middle East had similar range at mostly subsonic flight with less time benefit;
- Paris-Conakry was also possible but not transpacific routes.

- The Concorde needed high jet exhaust speeds for supersonic flight leading to higher at take-off and landing noise than for subsonic aircraft.

New York La Guardia airport created a noise monitoring point, and millions waited for the next Concorde operation to break the noise limit and leading to a ban to use the airport. A special bank manoeuvre after take-off was developed, so that the noise limit was not exceeded at the measuring point, and the demonstrators returned home with nothing to complain about. The achievements of Concorde can be seen by comparing with its attempted rivals, starting with the Tupolev Tu-144 Konkordski. Its designs betrayed the role of industrial espionage in Britain and France, yet it was a failure: it needed afterburning for supersonic flight, was short on range, never carried passengers and only performed some mail carrying flights between Moscow and Alma Ata. A more ambitious competitor was the US SST (Super Sonic Transport) funded by Congress. It would carry 300 passengers across the Pacific Ocean (instead of 108 passengers across the Atlantic Ocean) and fly at Mach 2.7 above the heat barrier (instead of Mach 2.08 below the heat barrier) requiring titanium instead of aluminium for the structure. The Boeing swing-wing design won over the Lockheed highly swept delta wing, raising some eye brows when Boeing changed to the configuration of its rival after winning the contest. With the prospect of a 2.7 billion-dollar development cost being exceeded the U.S. Congress finally voted to terminate the program.

The cancellation of the U.S. SST left Concorde as the sole supersonic transport in existence and in the foreseeable future, allowing some discriminatory targeting of its unique features. Yet Concorde operated reliably and profitably over the Atlantic routes until suffering an accident that was not its fault. A piece of debris left on the runway by a preceding aircraft was hit by the undercarriage, projected towards the wing, puncturing a fuel tank, and causing a fire leading to a fatal crash. The protracted investigation that followed proved nothing wrong with the original design. The operations ceased not for lack of willing fare paying passengers, but because of the difficulties of maintaining an old aircraft, with the few surviving examples cannibalized for spares. The preferred name of the aircraft was "Concord" for the British and "Concorde" for the French, and in the compromise "Concorde" the last "e" was supposed to stand for "Europe". Whether British, French or European the Concorde was a magnificent technical achievement but not a commercial success, perhaps explaining why decades have passed debating a successor that is yet to appear.

7.5.3 The Supersonic Business Jet?

The prospects for a commercial supersonic aircraft look dim:

- The sonic boom would prevent flight overland, leading only overwater routes, with the transatlantic market small and the transpacific market requiring more range;
- The overall number of aircraft, perhaps a few hundred, could hardly cover the high development cost of a supersonic airliner and a dedicated engine.

The feasibility of a supersonic transport probably depends on taking economics out of the equation. The supersonic business jet could be the right market niche with time saved and perhaps exclusive status prevailing over operating costs. Yet the supersonic business jet still faces the same challenges as Concorde. Research on sonic boom reduction has led to long-nose configurations delaying the formation of the N-shaped shock wave and leading to lower ground over pressures. Depending on the level of ground overpressure allowed by certification authorities' supersonic flight at about Mach

1.5 might be possible overland at sufficient altitude. The main stumbling block may be the lack of a suitable engine:

- The existing supersonic engines were designed for combat aircraft that fly hundreds of hours per year, and have a design life of about 5000 hours;
- With civil aircraft flying up to 3000 hours per year the durability of military engines is clearly inadequate;
- Converting a subsonic civil engine to supersonic would mean an almost total redesign at a cost possibly not justified by the small niche market involved.

Of all aircraft manufacturers Dassault Aviation would be best placed to design and produce a supersonic business jet:

- it has decades of experience with supersonic jet fighters;
- it has a complete range of high-end efficient business jets;
- it has researched the critical aspects of a supersonic business jet.

Yet Dassault has never come forward with a supersonic business jet proposal, perhaps because there is no suitable power plant. Several start-ups, some of which never produced even a light plane, have come and gone with supersonic business jet and small airliner designs that change configuration halfway into oblivion.

Some of the supersonic business jet or small airliner start-ups or stalwarts have sought or claimed the cooperation of major airframers like Airbus, Boeing or Lockheed with various agreements and timescales.

7.5.4 Hypersonic, Sub-Orbital and Orbital Transport

As speed increases several factors become more acute:

- The cost may grow faster than speed;
- The time saved is less in absolute terms;
- The technology and operating conditions become more severe.

To illustrate the point of reduction of travel time:

- Propeller driven airliners in the early post-war years would take over 10 hours to cross the Atlantic and might require a refuelling stop;
- jet airliners flying directly at twice the speed halve the travel time from 12 to 6 hours, that is a significant absolute time saving of 6 hours;
- Flying at twice the speed of sound in Concorde halves the flight time cross the Atlantic to 3 hours, yet this smaller absolute time saving comes at considerable cost and complexity.

Substantial time savings at speeds higher than transonic airliners could still apply to very long flight to the antipodes of the earth, such as Europe to Australia in 20 hours direct or with 2 or 3 stops. A Concorde successor flying at twice the speed of sound over very long ranges would halve travel time to 10 hours. A hypersonic aircraft powered by a supersonic combustion ramjet at Mach 6 would take 3 hours and a rocket orbiting a passenger capsule with atmospheric re-entry would take less than 1

hour. However, the operation would no longer be from nearby airports, adding to ground travel time. The cost also increases significantly with the technical challenges and passenger fitness might become an issue. All these problems will have ultimately to be solved for space exploration by mankind.

7.6 Helicopters, Convertibles, Drones and Fighters

The helicopter market is one of Europe's major successes with Airbus helicopters a world leader and Agusta-Westland competing with Boeing-Vertol, Bell and Sikorsky (Lockheed-Martin) from the U.S. as well as Mil and Kamov from Russia (subsection 7.6.1). The strong U.S. investment in greater hot-and-high and high-speed capabilities must be matched if Europe wants to maintain long term market share (subsection 7.6.2). The lack of coordination in drones that made Europe a market for U.S. and Israeli vehicles is the bad example not to be followed and to be corrected (subsection 7.6.3). The existence of competing European designs like the fighters does no harm as long as they satisfy European needs, reach the market and earn exports (subsection 7.6.4).

7.6.1 Stability and Volatility of the Helicopter Market

The helicopter market has some stable elements like search-and-rescue, emergency medical evacuation and law and order protection. Other elements are more volatile and vulnerable to large fluctuations:

- Off-shore oil exploration is more intense in periods of high oil prices, and can run down quickly if prices fall;
- Wars in inhospitable places, like hot and dusty Iraq, and high, hot and dusty Afghanistan place high demands on helicopters due to the lack of safe ground infrastructure or alternative means of transport.

The helicopter market expanded due to:

- The wars in Iraq and Afghanistan leading to high demand for rotorcraft due to the lack of local infrastructure to support rapid mobility on the ground and the risks with the proliferation of roadside bombs;
- The high oil prices fostering the off-shore oil prospecting and exploration supported by medium and heavy helicopters.

The decline in military operations in Iraq and Afghanistan and the reduction in oil exploration due to the lower oil prices, caused a reduction of both the military and civil helicopter markets, that are slowly recovering.

7.6.2 Greater Hot-and-High and High-Speed Capabilities

Faced with reducing order books the American helicopter industry is pressing the US government mostly through the armed forces to end decades of stagnation in helicopter technology, as the focus was on the production of existing types and derivatives. The aim is to replace production contracts by contracts to develop new helicopters that can then be produced as replacements for the existing vast fleets, even if on a reduced scale of less than one-on-one. The promises of increased performance focus on:

- Greater hot-and-high capabilities, overcoming the degradation of existing helicopters in those conditions, by using more powerful propulsion and rotor systems.
- The greater power can also be used to increase speed, range and shorten reaction time.

Although these developments are driven by the military, the results in improved performance will come to the civil market sooner rather than later.

Europe must match the U.S. efforts if it wants to keep its leading position in the world helicopter market. Safran Helicopters is introducing a new family of turboshaft engines to compete with the advances made in two military U.S. programs. The Airbus X-3 has gained the world helicopter speed record, showing that Europe does not lack the technology or ingenuity. However, the massive resources being put into high-speed helicopters and convertibles in the U.S. leave no room for complacency: the advances there must be matched on this side of the Atlantic in a competitive or cooperative but coordinated program.

7.6.3 The European Market for Foreign Drones

An example not to be followed is the case of UAV (Unmanned Air Vehicles) or drones for short. There is no shortage of technology as proved in the UK-only Taranis program, the German Talarion, the Italian Hammerhead and the multi-national Neuron led by Dassault. None has reached production with Europe buying Global Hawks, Reapers and Predators from the U.S. and Herons and others from Israel. In the meantime, the reluctance of the United States to export armed drones has allowed China to take a leading position as the supplier of such systems in Asia and the Middle East. The strong efforts made by the Chinese to develop a wide range of almost state-of-the-art drones and the willingness to export them at unbeatable prices gives a market advantage that will be difficult to challenge. There are a number of MALE (Medium Altitude, Long Endurance) programs involving Britain, France, Germany, Italy and Spain. They are at an early stage with no guarantee that leadership and nationalism issues have been resolved. It is those issues that have left Europe with several prototypes and no production, buying instead from abroad. It is essential to have either one common or several competitive programs that go beyond studies and prototypes into production.

7.6.4 The Eurofighter/Rafale/Gripen Competition

The existence of several European rivals is not a problem as long as they all reach production, meet European needs and gain exports. An example is the fighter market where the (1) Eurofighter Typhoon, (2) Dassault Rafale and (3) Saab Gripen have been competing in Europe and around the world. Having two comparable aircraft (1, 2) and a cheaper alternative (3) increases the choice of customers and results in greater overall market penetration. Competition does not exclude selective cooperation for mutual benefit; all three aircraft use similar AESA (Active Electronically Scanned Antenna) radar technology and employ the Meteor BVRAAM (Beyond Visual Range Air to Air Missile) in a world leading combination that has been brought into service by Sweden in the Gripen, ahead of France in the Rafale and Britain (Germany/Italy/Spain) in the Eurofighter.

The key topics considered next are:

- Long-range air transport (T7.1 and T7.2);
- Airliner and Business Jet Markets (T7.3 and T7.4);
- Helicopters (T7.5 and T7.6).

KEY TOPIC T7.1 ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF THE LONG-RANGE AIR TRANSPORT

Historically, long-haul traffic has grown faster than short-haul, growing 3.4% per year since 2000 while the growth in short-haul has been 2.5% for the same period. Today's long-haul network serves a variety of market needs. People may choose to fly from a world's economic centre to another, fly to a more secondary airport or seek for a connection between smaller locations. Nonstop and connecting traffic contributes to different extents to an airport's long-haul traffic volume.

Figure 7.1 shows the year-on-year evolution of long-haul and short-haul traffic in terms of offered seats and gives an idea about how the traffic has evolved during the past years:

Figure 7.1– Long-haul vs short-haul traffic evolution
Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

The long-haul traffic future growth is related to a wide range of parameters that will be analysed in detail in following sections:

- Demand;
- Cost;
- Users;
- Operators and manufactures.

T7.1.1 Demand

In the future, long-haul flights will be operated by larger aircraft to serve the higher numbers of passengers demanding travelling long-distance. In addition, it is expected more demand from emerging countries such as China or India as a result of their growing economy.

T7.1.1.1 Passengers Demand

According to IATA, passenger numbers are expected to reach 7 billion by 2034 with a 3.8% average annual growth in demand (2014 baseline year). That is more than double the 3.3 billion who flew in 2014 and exactly twice as many as the 3.5 billion expected in 2015.

The five fastest-increasing markets in terms of additional passengers per year over the forecast period will be China, the US, India, Indonesia and Brazil. (See figure 7.2).

Figure 7.2– Top ten passengers’ markets

Source: IATA Air Passenger Forecast Shows Dip in Long-Term Demand

In addition, passengers demand by regions will also experiment a great change, as indicated in Figure 7.3:

- Asia-Pacific will see an extra 1.8 billion annual passengers by 2034, for an overall market size of 2.9 billion. In relative terms, it will increase its size compared to other regions to 42% of global passenger traffic, and its annual average growth rate, 4.9%, will be the joint-highest with the Middle East.
- The North American region will grow by 3.3% annually and in 2034 will carry a total of 1.4 billion passengers, an additional 649 million passengers a year.

- Europe will have the slowest growth rate, 2.7%, but will still cater for an additional 591 million passengers a year. The total market will be 1.4 billion passengers.
- Latin American markets will grow by 4.7%, serving a total of 605 million passengers, an additional 363 million passengers annually compared to today.
- The Middle East will grow strongly (4.9%) and will see an extra 237 million passengers a year by 2034. The UAE, Qatar and Saudi Arabia will all enjoy strong growth of 5.6%, 4.8%, and 4.6% respectively. The total market size will be 383 million passengers.
- Africa will grow by 4.7%. By 2034 it will see an extra 177 million passengers a year for a total market of 294 million passengers.

**Global air passengers by region
(% of total flows)**

Figure 7.3– Global Air Passengers by region
Source: IATA Air Passenger Forecast Shows Dip in Long-Term Demand

T7.1.1.2 Urban Growth

Air traffic growth is much related to population growth, which in turn is related to economic growth. Nowadays, more than half of world’s population, 3.5 billion people, live in urban centres. By 2030, it is expected that 59% (5 billion people) will live in cities. During the next two decades, developing countries as China or India will absorb a significant additional urban population, 900 and 600 million city dwellers respectively.

Rates of urban growth in developing countries have been higher than that of developed countries. Cities have become the main driver of globalization and the engine of economic growth. They have

quickly transformed their economies through international trade, attracting large multinational corporations, international media and foreign tourism. The rise in urban population has led to an increase economic growth, which is a key driver for aviation. Most urban growth is projected to take place in the southern part of the world, with different degrees of urbanisation. For example, urban populations are expected to grow significantly in India, China and Indonesia. By 2030, more than half of the population of China and Indonesia and about 40% of the Indian population will live in cities.

As these countries continue growing, it will be necessary to have access to quick and efficient connections. Air transport will be the ideal solution, minimizing time, the impact on land use and cost to government. Therefore, air transport will become a vital part of these emerging countries by providing access to global markets and facilitating the connection of people worldwide, enabling increased foreign migration and international tourism.

In 2010, emerging countries such as Brazil, Russia, India and China (BRIC countries), together accounted for 69% of world population, about 5 billion people, which explain the growth it is predicted over the next two decades. In the future, these countries together with other emerging economies will contribute an impressive 56% of the 2010-2030 world economic growth. (See figure 7.4).

Figure 7.4 – Top 10 urban countries
Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

T7.1.1.3 Long-range Routes and Traffic Flows

Forty years ago, 76% of the world’s traffic flew from, to or between North America, Western Europe and Japan. Today, this tendency has changed as more people can benefit from aviation advantages as consequence of growing economies.

In 2010, the 57% of the traffic was centred on other parts of the world. This does not mean that the original regions as Europe or North America have not been continued growing, they have, almost doubling their traffic over the forecast period. Finally, in 2030 it is expected that the 70% of the traffic volumes will be between expanding regions.

Today, the long-haul market is dominated by three main traffic flows (see figure 7.5). The air-bridges over the Atlantic and the Pacific Ocean, as well as links between Europe and Asia, account for two thirds of worldwide long-haul traffic. With anticipated traffic growth over the next 20 years the clear majority of long-haul traffic will remain concentrated on these three dominant flows (see figure 7.6).

Figure 7.5 – RPK share of Trans-Atlantic, Trans-Pacific and Europe-to-Asia traffic flows on total long-haul traffic, 2010

Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

Figure 7.6 – RPK share of Trans-Atlantic, Trans-Pacific and Europe-to-Asia traffic flows on total long-haul traffic, 2030

Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

In particular, the trans-Atlantic market has undergone a growth of 50 % in the last 15 years, as it can be seen in figure 7.7.

Figure 7.7 – Passenger Traffic between Europe and US
Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

On the other hand, traffic between emerging countries is forecast to grow at 6.2% annually, and will represent a growing share of air traffic, from 29% of world traffic in 2016 up to 40% by 2036. The highest growth in long-haul traffic market is expected within the triangle of Africa, Asia-Pacific and the Middle East.

The Popular Republic of China will be the main contributor to new long-haul routes in the Asia-Pacific region, which will lead world traffic by 2030, becoming this dynamic region the world's largest air travel market. For instance, traffic within the Asia-Pacific region will represent 25% of total traffic in twenty years, up from 19% in 2010. The main flows will connect China to South-East Asia, the Indian subcontinent and the Middle East.

The long-haul sector between Europe, the Middle East and Africa is dominated by traffic between Europe and Middle east, where again most of the route openings are expected, notably between the U.A.E. hubs and more secondary cities in Europe.

Finally, the Trans-Pacific will enjoy the strongest growth out of the big three long-haul flows. The main reason is the increasing weight of RPK (Revenue Passenger Kilometres) traffic to China, which will reach similar dimensions as traffic to Japan. The newest non-stop route openings are forecast between Europe and Asia, despite strong competition coming from connections via the Middle East hubs.

In figures 7.8 and 7.9, it can be seen the main flows with more volume of air traffic in 2010 and 2030.

Figure 7.8 – Share and volume of 2010 RPKs
Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

Figure 7.9 – Share and volume of 2030 RPKs
Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

Finally, the figure 7.10 shows the flows in which it is expected the fastest growth.

Figure 7.10 – Top 20 fastest growing flows over the next 20 years
 Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast, Growing Horizons 2017-2036

T7.1.1.4 Long-range Destinations

There are cities that traditionally are centres of air transport demand, due to their socio-economic weight within a certain region. These cities, such as Tokyo, New York and London, are vital points for world trade; they are also big population centres with an enormous appeal far beyond their borders. These cities, in most of cases, serve as a connection hub and, in addition, they are places where people want to start and finish their journey that above all contributes to their weight and importance in the world long-haul network. Other points, whilst not being major population centres, are very significant as aviation centres, such as the cities and airports in United Arab Emirates and large European and U.S. transfer hubs. All these destinations are part of the long-haul network, which serves to connect flights from all over the world. Today, there are 39 cities from a total of around 350 that have a monthly throughput of at least 10,000 long-haul passengers per day and they absorb the 90% of the world’s long-haul traffic. They serve as the pillars of the global long-haul network, serving as essential network crossroads and as the source of massive air transport demand. They are called aviation mega-cities.

Today, more than 90% of long-haul passengers travel either on a route between two Aviation megacities or on a route having one of them as route start point, connecting point or end point.

Figure 7.11 – Long haul direct routes between the world’s 2010 Aviation Mega-cities
 Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

By 2030, 87 cities around the world will have passed the threshold of 10,000 daily passengers, to become aviation mega-cities (Figure 7.11). The emerging regions of the world, including Latin America, Africa, the Middle East and Asia will contribute an additional 29 long-haul traffic hubs, as their economic power and wealth grows passenger traffic within these regions. Cities in Australia, Europe and North America will also benefit from a sustained long-haul traffic growth, adding a further 19 aviation megacities. However, in the next 20 years, slightly more than half of the global long-haul air transport centres will be in emerging economies. The number of cities that are considered as key gateways for long-haul flights will more than double over the next 20 years.

Nevertheless, long-haul traffic will remain highly concentrated on a relatively few number of points. In numerical terms: the 2010 top 20 long-haul gateway cities handled 55% of world long-haul traffic. Despite network evolution, the top 20 of 2030 will still account 50% of traffic. In the same way, the top 100 cities account for more than 90% of long-haul traffic, in 2010 as well as over the next 20 years.

Figure 7.12 – 2030 cities with more than 10,000 daily long-haul passengers
 Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

T7.1.1.5 Long-Range Network Forecast

World air traffic will grow at an average rate of 4.8% per year over the next two decades. This additional traffic volume will be accommodated on the existing route network as well as on new routes. Airbus forecasts that more than 700 new city-pairs will be added on the long-haul market over the next 20 years. This will grow today's long-haul network of about 1,600 city links by more than 40%. However, as traffic will grow twice as fast as the network, most growth will be accommodated on the world's existing city pairs. No more than 15% of 2030 passenger traffic will be on routes that are not served today, that is to say, new routes. Therefore, the 85% of 2030 long-haul traffic will still be accommodated on the 2010 network. The Figure 7.13 illustrates this forecast.

Figure 7.13 – Evolution of long -haul traffic
Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

T7.1.1.6 Touristic Destinations

In the following figure 7.14, it can be found the main touristic destinations in 2015, with China leading the list.

Figure 7.14 – Top 10 most visited cities in 2015
Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast, Growing Horizons 2017-2036

T7.1.1.7 Business Travel Trends

Business travels expenditure by US and European passengers have adjusted to austerity following the financial crisis and slow to recover the old spending habits; in contrast to Asia business passenger's travels expenditures, that trend growth, as indicated in the following figure 7.15.

Figure 7.15 – Total business travel expenditures 2005-2023

Source: Oxford economics

A variety of mechanism have contributed to this adjustment:

- Western companies have introduced sophisticated tools to control business expenses.
- Use of technological alternatives such as videoconferencing.
- More business trips are being planned by employees themselves or at least in-house rather than via an agent.
- Employee's empowerment by making more cost-effective decisions and/or decisions more suitable to their precise individual circumstances.
- Changes in corporate travel policies declining the yield on such travel (downshifting from business class to premium economy/economy, shorter hotel stays, changing to restricted fares or other means, etc.).

However, the effect has not been so dramatic for the long-haul segment. Premium air traffic data from IATA7 shows that long-haul (intercontinental) premium traffic recovered quicker from the financial crisis - particularly that connecting advanced to emerging markets. This difference might be explained by the fact that emerging market growth is helping to propel the latter.

As results of this later crisis several trends have consolidated:

- Emergence of the 'Premium Economy' travel class, especially in medium-haul 6-8 hours journeys.
- Certain airlines have reinforced business class to retain or recapture business class passengers.

Regarding the future evolution of the business sector, **it seems that Asia will drive future growth in business travel**. North East Asia alone will account for 42% of the growth in global outbound business travel expenditure over the next decade, with South East Asia accounting for a further 13%.

In particular, China is also rapidly reaching the US as the largest domestic market for business travel (see figure 7.16). European and North American business travellers will become less important globally, in proportion, but they will still be a third of outbound business travel between them and

will increase their business travel to emerging markets. European business travellers are expected to be around 15% of future global revenue growth over the next decade, and North America 7% (See figure 7.17).

Figure 7.16 – Domestic business travel expenditure (% of global total domestic business expenditure)
Source: Oxford economics

Figure 7.17 – Regional share of global growth in business travel expenditure (2013-2023)
Source: Oxford economics

A special reference needs to be done to the role of videoconferencing in this sector, as a supplement but not a replacement for business travels. Room for growth in both, videoconferencing and business travel, is expected over the next decade, in the context of globalisation and emerging markets.

T7.1.2 Cost

T7.1.2.1 Ticket Costs

Long-haul routes are highly attractive; in the United States they account for about 40 percent of mainline operating revenues and over 90 percent of operating profits (See figure 7.18).

Figure 7.18 – Long Haul portion of mainline revenues

Source: McKinsey & Company: Annual reports; US Department of Transportation

Normally, total ticket costs are much higher in long-haul flights than in short-haul flights (Figure 7.19). This is mainly because the impact of fuel cost, but also because taxes, fees, and surcharges are considerably higher on long-haul routes.

Figure 7.19 – A short life in long haul for low-cost carriers

Source: McKinsey & Company

T7.1.2.2 Costs of Operation

Normally, the cost categories of a flight include pilot, cabin crew, fuel, airframe maintenance, engine maintenance and others. The next figure 7.20 illustrates the approximate share of airplane operating costs that can be attributed to these various categories for a long-haul flight.

Figure 7.20 – Cost per flight for a long-haul service

Source: <http://www.tourism2025.org.nz/tourism-2025-archive/grow-sustainable-air-connectivity-2/>

Figure 7.21 – Cost per flight time

Source: Long Haul Carriers in the modern low-cost world, Nathan Agnew

As it can be seen in the previous images, the fuel consumption is the main cost component of a long-haul flight, as it must travel a great distance and, therefore, more fuel is needed. Fuel represents approximately 50 percent of the total LH trip cost, for every carried tonne of fuel, 0,5 tonnes of fuel will be burnt to carry it. Figure 7.22 illustrates the potential fuel savings predicted by Airframe- and Engine-manufacturer. The Airframe- and Engine-Manufacturer predict for the short-term Fuel burn savings of 2 percent to 4 percent, with new technologies in the long term, estimated fuel burn savings are predicted to be in the region of 10 percent to 12 percent. To buy a new aircraft and recover the capital investment, an airline requires a reduction of fuel consumption per passenger of at least 10%. This is the minimum gain in efficiency for a new generation of aircraft.

Figure 7.22 – Potential fuel savings predicted by Airframe- and Engine-manufacturer (short and long term are disregarded).

Source: Airline profiler

Figure 7.23 represents the fuel consumption per distance for various long-range aircraft. As can be seen, the Boeing B787 is today one of the most fuel-efficient airplanes, therefore it is very likely that the carriers (both mainlines and low cost) will prefer to operate with this type of aircraft or similar (e.g. Airbus 350, Airbus A330 Neo, revamped B737 or A320 an extended range A321).

Figure 7.23 – Fuel consumption per distance

Source: Airline profiler

The next figure 7.24 illustrate the breakdown of the cost of operation for the today most fuel-efficient airplane, the Boeing 787-8, as operated by different companies, a conventional air-carrier, a low-cost

carrier and a charter air-carrier. The figure highlights the possible range of cost per available seat and kilometre and allows to identify where cost saving will might be possible.

A look at the operating economics of the 787-8 highlights cost differences.

Line item	Mainline 247 seats ¹ 3,200 nautical miles (nm); 740 km/h block speed 85% load factor		Low-cost carrier 291 seats ¹ 3,200 nm; 740 km/h block speed 85% load factor		Charter 291 seats ¹ 3,200 nm; 740 km/h block speed 95% load factor		Unit
	\$/BH ²	Input cost	\$/BH	Input cost	\$/BH	Input cost	
Aircraft/insurance	2,467	879,000	2,467	879,000	2,467	879,000	\$/month BH/day
Fuel	4,386	1,700	4,386	1,700	4,386	1,700	Gallons/BH \$/gallon
Maintenance	855	855	855	855	855	855	\$/BH
Cockpit	544	300,000	411	300,000	411	300,000	Salary/year/crew, \$ Benefit load, % Training cost/year/crew, \$ BH/month/crew
Cabin crew	390	32,000	310	32,000	310	32,000	Salary/flight attendant/year, \$ Benefit load, % Cabin crew/aircraft Training cost/year/crew, \$ BH/month/crew
Hotel accommodation	167	200	125	150	125	150	\$/crew member
Airport/navigation	831	2,000	661	1,500	679	1,500	\$/turn, aircraft \$/leg, landing and navigation \$/passengers, handling
On board	524	20	310	10	173	5	\$/passengers
Sales and distribution	918	35	310	10	104	3	\$/passengers
General and administrative	315	12	155	5	69	2	\$/passengers
Total cost \$/BH	11,396		9,989		9,579		
CASK³	6.2		4.6		4.4		

¹Seat counts based on announced configurations by carriers fitting the respective archetype.

²Block hour.

³Cost per available seat kilometer.

McKinsey&Company | Source: Aircraft Commerce; annual reports; Boeing; US Department of Transportation, Form 41; International Air Transport Association; International Civil Aviation Organization; pprune.org; McKinsey analysis

Figure 7.24 – Operation cost differences among companies for a B-787-8

Source: Airline profiler

T7.1.2.3 Fuel Prices Evolution

Oil price is an important consideration in aircraft forecasts as result of its impact on economic activity, and the resulting impact it has on demand for aviation. From aviation’s perspective, crude oil prices and economic activity are closely correlated: strong and developing economic activity increases demand for oil, which has a positive impact on crude oil prices. Conversely, an exogenous increase of crude oil prices has a negative impact on economies, through inflation and a negative shock on global demand.

Air transport is generally more impacted than other sectors by increases of crude oil prices, as fuel currently represents more than 30% of airlines operating expenses. In recent years, the jet fuel price

has undergone a decline, allowing improving the airline profitability during the period. Airlines had an operating result of \$58.3 billion in 2016.

However, in the short to medium term, forecasts suggest that oil and jet fuel prices will recover over time, although may not reach soon the peak levels of the past.

Figure 7.25 – Fuel prices forecast
Source: Boeing Market outlook 217-2036

T7.1.2.4 Costs in Relation with Distance

In addition, there is a relation between the flights costs and the distance costs increase as the distance increases because carries more fuel weight relative to pay level. Therefore, as long-haul flights must travel a greater distance, their operating costs are higher, which can be seen in the following images Figure 7.26 and 7.27 respectively for short and long-haul flights.

Figure 7.26 – Short-haul trip costs
Source: Aircraft trip cost parameters: A function of stage length and seat capacity, William M. Swan, Nicole Adler

Figure 7.27 – Long-haul trip costs

Source: Aircraft trip cost parameters: A function of stage length and seat capacity, William M. Swan, Nicole Adler

T7.1.3 Manufacturers

As Airbus and Boeing are the main manufacturers of long-haul aircraft, in this section it is analysed how their fleets will evolve in the future:

T7.1.3.1 Airbus Fleet

According to Airbus, the world's fleet of passenger aircraft will grow from 15,000 at the beginning of 2011 to nearly 31,500 by 2030.

Some 19,165 new deliveries (Figure 7.28) will be single-aisles for domestic and intra-regional flows. As many as 6,500 twin-aisle passenger aircraft will be required to serve the existing, mainly international markets created largely by growth on existing city pairs, flows from and within emerging markets and the addition of new routes. Around 1,300 very large passenger aircraft will be needed to link the world's major aviation hubs. It should be no surprise that 45% of the new deliveries of very large passenger aircraft will be delivered to the airlines in the Asia-Pacific region.

Figure 7.28 – New passenger aircraft demand in 2030
 Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

In addition, the Airbus forecast predicts that the greatest demand for passenger aircraft will come from airlines in the United States and the Popular Republic of China. North American and European airlines’ will both receive 22% of the total, with Asia-Pacific’s airlines forecast to take 34% of new deliveries. In addition, the world’s airlines will require nearly 5,000 smaller aircraft, either jet or turbo-prop (with 20 to 100 seats) to serve regional demand, especially in the US and Europe. In the following figures 7.29 and 7.30 it can be seen the new passenger aircraft deliveries for aircraft with more of 100 seats.

Passenger aircraft demand		
1	USA	5,389
2	PRC	4,041
3	Germany	1,038
4	India	1,019
5	UK	938
6	UAE	813
7	Brazil	701
8	Russia	689
9	Australia	609
10	Ireland	588

Figure 7.29 – Top ten countries in 20-year new passenger aircraft deliveries
 Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

	2011-2020	2021-2030	2011-2030	% of world deliveries
Asia-Pacific	4,259	4,901	9,160	34%
Europe	2,918	3,032	5,950	22%
North America	2,667	3,234	5,901	22%
Latin America	961	1,067	2,028	8%
Middle East	1,044	838	1,882	7%
Africa	542	559	1,101	4%
CIS	464	435	899	3%
World demand	12,855	14,066	26,921	100%

Figure 7.30 – New passenger aircraft deliveries by region
Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

In addition, it is expected that in the future the number of very large aircraft will increase, which are the most used in long-haul routes. These aircraft are designed to meet demand efficiently by minimising seat costs in both fuel and CO₂. By 2030, the number of this category of aircraft will be around 1,300 units flying globally. Given the projected growth in Asia, both economic and air passenger traffic growth, the regions demographics, urbanisation trends and the dense traffic flows between Asia and Europe and North America, it is unsurprising that the region's airlines will take 45% of these aircraft over the next 20 years. It is expected that in 2030 10 of the 20 largest very large aircraft airports will be in Asia-Pacific.

One example of this type of aircraft is the A380, which is becoming a common sight at the world's most important hubs, already serving 12 of the top twenty international airports. The predictions for very large aircraft are more optimistic than those of Boeing that does not have a direct A380 competitor with the B777 gaining more orders.

Figure 7.31 – A380 network
Source: Airbus Global Market Forecast 2011-2030

T7.1.3.2 Boeing Fleet

According to Boeing, the fleet growth will undergo a significant increase, with the following deliveries by category, shown in Figures 7.32 and 7.33.

Figure 7.32 – Aircraft deliveries by category in 2015
Source: Boeing Market outlook 2015-2035

Figure 7.33 – Aircraft deliveries by category in 2035
 Source: Boeing Market outlook 2015-2035

If both years are compared, it can be seen a great increase (Figure 7.34) in aircraft deliveries, from 22,510 airplanes deliveries in 2015 to 45,240 airplanes deliveries in 2035.

Figure 7.34 – Aircraft deliveries
 Source: Boeing Market outlook 2015-2035

Therefore, the long-term forecast shows that it is expected a need for more than 45,000 new deliveries, with the clear majority of demand (32,200 units) in the single-aisle category, which represents the 70 percent in the share of new deliveries. In addition, 9,100 new wide body airplanes will be delivered, which will allow airlines to serve new markets more efficiently than in the past.

Moreover, consistent with air travel demand growth trends, Boeing expects (Figure 7.35) that by 2035, approximately 40 percent of all new airplanes will be delivered to airlines based in the Asia region. An additional 40 percent will be delivered to airlines in Europe and North America combined, with the remaining 20 percent delivered to the Middle East, Latin America, CIS and Africa.

Figure 7.35 – Aircraft deliveries by region
Source: Boeing Market outlook 2015-2035

T7.1.4 Long-Range Air Transport of Passengers

In relation to the growing demand for air travel, the following figures are established, according (Figure 7.37) to Airbus GMF (Global Market Forecast) data:

- Revenue Passenger Kilometres (RPKs) grew 6.3% in 2016, as compared to 2015, according to ICAO figures which were preliminary at the time of writing.
- This represents an impressive 3.7 billion passengers carried by air in 2016.
- Over half of the world's tourists who travel across international borders each year are transported by air.
- Air passengers benefited from **oil prices** which remained relatively low, with airlines able to choose between stimulating the market through lower yields and therefore **ticket prices**, and their margins.
- Air traffic continues to prove its resilience to slow economic growth by outperforming global GDP, demonstrating the world's appreciation of the benefits aviation brings.
- For the next 20 years, the Airbus GMF forecasts a 4.4% global annual air traffic growth, despite some downward revision of future economic growth by a number of forecasters in several regions of the world. According to some predictions, the first decade will enjoy a 4.9% increase per year, with 4.1% average annual growth for the last decade, a lower figure but growth in those years based on absolute traffic numbers higher than today.
- One source of information is the Airbus GMF forecast. As an example, the GMF 2000 forecast continues to track the long-term trend and our latest forecast, despite significant market perturbations in the years following its production.

Figure 7.36 – Airbus GMF predicting long term demand
Source: Airbus GMF 2017

Furthermore, the following results are shown in the traffic forecast for 2036:

- Asia-Pacific will lead world traffic by 2036, with a threefold increase in the traffic serving this region by the end of the forecast period.
- Traffic between emerging countries is forecast to grow at 6.2% per annum, and will represent a growing share of air traffic, from 29% of world traffic in 2016 up to 40% by 2036.
- Domestic China will become the largest traffic flow before the end of the forecast period. Domestic Chinese traffic is forecast to almost quadruple, with Domestic USA increasing by 50% from an already high base.
- The three major flows connecting Western Europe are all expected to develop: Western-Europe – USA, Intra-Western Europe and Western-Europe – Middle East forecast to grow 1.8, 1.6 and 2.5 times respectively.
- Amongst the Top 20 traffic flows, 50% will involve Asia-Pacific and 25% will involve the Middle East.

T7.1.4.1 New Routes Demand (“Ultra-long-range”)

Improved long-range economics are making the opening of new routes possible, as well as the resumption of old ones. So, improved fuel efficiency is therefore essential to the feasibility of ever longer air routes and this is exactly what the aircraft manufacturing industry has been delivering.

The state-of-the-art Airbus A350-900ULR (where the last three letters stand for "ultra-long range") has a range of 8,700 nautical miles (over 16,000 Km).

It's this aircraft that Singapore Airlines is planning to use to re-launch the New York route that it previously operated with a comparatively thirstier four-engine Airbus A340-500.

It'll have competition in the form of the up-and-coming Boeing 777-8, whose first delivery is expected in 2020. This new ultra-long-range version of the popular "triple seven" will replace the Boeing 777-200LR, that's currently in use on Qatar's Doha to Auckland route.

Meanwhile, the smaller Boeing 787-9 combines an impressive range of over 7,600 nautical miles (14,000 kilometres) with operational costs low enough to enable the launch of less busy long-haul routes which were deemed uneconomic in the not-so-distant past.

Advances in aircraft manufacturing make it possible to operate profitably some very long-distance routes that were previously unthinkable. This is due to the growing global demand for air travel; since as more people fly, more city pairs meet the demand threshold required to support direct connections.

Technological improvements are also having an effect on ETOPS regulations, which set constraints on twin-engined aircraft routings by imposing a limit of maximum flight time to the closest airport in case of diversion.

With aircraft like some A350 being ETOPS-compliant for up to 370 minutes, a whole bunch of new direct routings across the oceans becomes possible, particularly in the Pacific region and across the Southern Hemisphere.

Better long-range aircraft economics should also provide the definitive impulse to the development of a global long-haul **low-cost** airline sector. It's in this context that AirAsia X, the Malaysian airline that pioneered long-haul low-cost flights in Asia, has announced its intention to have another go at the **European market**. It tried some years ago with four-engined A340 aircraft, but dropped the flights, citing low profitability. Now AirAsia X is planning to resume them as soon as it receives new Airbus A330neo airplanes, a reengined, more fuel-efficient version of this popular wide-bodied aircraft type.

Meanwhile the Boeing 787 Dreamliner has found favour with Scandinavian carrier Norwegian. With a dozen 787s in service and 20 more on order, Norwegian is leveraging the aircraft to develop a long-haul **low-cost operation out of its European bases**.

An important point to keep in mind are the long-haul travellers. The most obvious limitation is the amount of time economy class passengers are willing to sit still in a cramped cabin. Also, the effects of lack of humidity become noticeable after three hours of flight.

Despite the industry working hard to devise improved ergonomic aircraft seat designs, this is an area where pretty much the only way to get straightforward relief is to get an upgrade. Traveling in economy may have its silver lining, though.

T7.1.4.2 User Expectations for Ultra-Long Range

User expectations for long and ultra-long-haul flights will play an essential role in the development of this market. Key aspects of these expectations are discussed hereafter:

- **Saving time for business & increasing productivity:** Ultra-long-haul is perceived, by the business travel community, as a great occasion to increase productivity and available working hours. With one or two layovers, the journey from Singapore to New York can take between 24 and 30 hours with one or two intermediate stops. Professional travellers argue that direct air route will always be preferable as reduced unproductive hours on connections, and also improve traveller rest that is not interrupted by layovers. This argument can also be applicable for leisure flights, as traveller will always to enjoy maximising its holiday time at destination instead on intermediate airports at layovers.

- **Passenger's endurance:** Perhaps the only remaining challenge that ultra-haul flights have to overcome is how to guarantee passengers health and comfort during such large number of hours on board. A new area of technological solutions is gaining relevance and becoming a differentiation strategy for big manufacturers as new technology will be needed to make the experience of long flights more endurable for passengers. For example, carbon-fibre-reinforced composites — such as in the Boeing 787 and the forthcoming Airbus A350-900ULR — that are not vulnerable to corrosion, permits a higher cabin humidity and higher internal cabin pressure, probably the most important factors for passenger comfort. After extensive 18-hours endurance tests at different pressures inside a mock aircraft cabin at the University of Oklahoma, Boeing has settled the 787-optimal cabin pressure equivalent to that at 6,000 ft. above the sea level, instead of the 8,000ft at conventional older aircraft.
- **Pilot health risks:** The risks of flying such long distances also distress the pilot's health. The effect of long-haul routes on pilot circadian rhythm (body clock) disruption, sleep and fatigue has not been studied, nor the risk of greater exposure to radiation. Adapted crew in flight rest facilities must be provided on board ultra-long aircraft. New needs appear regarding health, such to provide special cupboard to store any unexpected fatality on board (as introduced by Singapore Airlines in its fleet of A340-500).
- **Economic sustainability:** Until now, the strategies of operator to support the airline's higher fuel and staff costs in ultra-long-haul services, has been to stand upon high premium travellers, predominantly business travellers, willing to pay a premium for a nonstop flight. For example, the longest Singapore Airlines route, initiated in 2004 with both business and economy seats, was adapted 4 years later to uniquely business-class. The trade-off between health and comfort vs occupancy rates for economy cabin might be one of the key point for the economic profitability of ultra-long-haul operations. There seems to be a clear willingness from passengers to pay slightly more for an ultra-long-haul flight without an intermediary stop. The trade-off between this additional extra payment, the length of the flight and the evolution of the principal cost of operation will determine the progress of this new market segment.

T7.1.5 Specific long-haul business models

The long-haul market envisages various specific models of operation which utility and variability are disused hereafter.

- Intermediate Stop Operation – ISO;
- Low Cost Business Model for Long-Haul Sectors – LHLC (Long-Haul Low-Cost);
- Ultra-Long-haul operation – ULTRA LH;
- Supersonic flights.

T7.1.5.1 ISO Intermediate Stop Operation

Intermediate Stop Operation is a model of operation that face the exploitation the long-haul market based on the use of medium range aircraft and intermediate stops in the route.

The economic interest of this model of operation for the airlines is closely related to a specific range of aircraft segments, travel distances and routes. Some studies³⁸ have shown the effect of splitting long-range routes into two segments (analysed for medium size and large wide bodies, represented by two specific payloads of 30,000 and 50,000 kg, and the splitting respecting geographic and commercial constraints). According to research:

- **ISO potential fuel savings below a certain threshold**, about 7,000–10,000 km, depending upon the detour factor, **are negligible or, even, negative**.

In routes serving very distant city pairs, with little or no detour (deviation) and almost even splitting (such as London–Sydney via Calcutta or New York– Melbourne via Honolulu), ISO fuel savings can be as high as 20%. However, in more common circumstances, ISO can scarcely cut the fuel bill by 7–10%.

Considering the overall DOC (Direct Cost of Operation) the results are less positive than considering only pure fuel savings, because it is necessary to account for the extra flying time. Extra flying time brings also extra airplane depreciation, insurance and maintenance; as well as extra crew time required.

Direct Cost of Operation (DOC) will only be smaller than for the baseline nonstop flight for very long routes, above 12,000 km (6,500 NM). However, for these very long distances, the psychological effect of the stop and waiting time at the intermediate airport has a significant negative effect on the passengers. This is a serious issue of comfort now that new aircraft development allows flying very long distances without any stop, at very low operating cost.

In the best case considered, for R $\frac{1}{4}$ 15,000 km without detour and perfect route splitting, the economic saving is about 10%. In a future scenario with higher fuel prices or new taxes on fuel, the savings due to ISO would increase up to 12–13%. This saving can hardly justify the operation of this fleet for this very long market.

- **Implementation of intermediate stops is not always possible** from a logistic point of view.

Intermediate stop operations can be easily scheduled in the Northern Hemisphere, since it contains the clear majority of the population and of the land masses with suitable airports. Although, even with these favourable conditions, there will still be problems and problematic routes, such those linking North America to South East Asia due to the scarcity of adequate airports across the Pacific Ocean.

However, the Southern Hemisphere, with the endless uninhabited Pacific Ocean and Antarctica, poses unbeatable troubles for commercially viable ISO.

All these together, means that ISO are more interesting from the point of view of fuel savings and environmental impact, than on pure economic terms. In view of the new long-range aircraft, highly competitive in terms of efficiency and fuel composition this model does not seem to be a sustainable model for long –haul, but more a residual operation for medium range companies. It

³⁸ Proc IMechE Part G: J Aerospace Engineering 227(2) 394–404, IMechE 2012 DOI: 1177/0954410011429766. Cost-range trade-off of intermediate stop operations of long-range transport airplanes. Rodrigo Martinez-Val, Emilio Perez, Cristina Cuerno and Jose F Palacin

is not therefore expected that this model will stand for a great share of the long and ultra-long market in the future.

T7.1.5.2 Low Cost Business Model for Long-Haul Sectors

Low-Cost airliner has created a very successful model for short and medium flights, however the realization of low budget for long-haul flights had many failed attempts until now.

Low-Cost Carriers (LCCs) that succeeded in short and medium haul profited from structural and hard-to-match cost advantages; markets with significant latent demand; and a unique value proposition that appealed to a wide range of customers. The mixture of these features has permitted LCCs to continuously under-price mainline airlines, limit retaliation, and build a loyal customer base. However, this model is difficult to replicate on long-haul routes, due to the specificities of this type of operation; that poses serious limitations to the development and consolidation of a LCC model in the long-haul market. While long-haul market offers significant margins for a lower-priced, mainlines have the opportunity to capture it, impairing LCC to become factual new entrants in the long-haul market.

At the same time, it is true that a new concept of operation is necessary for these routes. This model, still to be developed, will have to consider the specificities of the long-distance operations, emerging aviation technologies and information technology, demand and supply –driven, flexible networks and aircraft management. On top of all that, it should be focused on customer comfort service providing a mix of premium and comfort classes.

The feasibility of Low-Cost for long-haul Sectors will depend mainly on the ability of the Airlines to control the operating expenses. Table 7.1 illustrates the areas LCC have demonstrated ability to influence in the short and medium range.

Cost Factors	Ability to Influence
Manpower	Possible
Air Fares	Possible
Air Traffic Management	Not Possible
Airport, Navigation, Taxes and Fees	Not Possible
Airport Handling	Possible
Cabin Design, Seat Configuration	Possible
Fleets and Aircraft Composition	Possible
Fuel Consumption, Saving Measurements (Weight reduction, winglets, airframe modifications, air traffic, etc.)	Possible
Fuel, Oil	Not Possible
Leasing Cost	Possible
Maintenance	Possible
Marketing Sales	Possible
Passenger Services	Possible
Stimulating Traffic	Possible
Technical Aircraft and Engines Improvements	Not Possible
Routes and Destinations	Possible

Table 7.1 – Areas current LCC have demonstrated ability to influence in the short and medium range

In short haul operation, LCCs combine lower input costs with higher productivity to achieve a 25 to 50 percent cost advantage over their mainline rivals. However, the operating economics associated with long-haul flights are different. More optimistic estimates of the cost savings potential, if current Low-Cost Concept will be adapted for Long-Haul Sectors, are indicated on the figure 7.37. Optimistic forecasts in the short term indicate that the long-haul low-cost sector will likely again double in size over the next two years and surpass a 1% share of global capacity. The fastest expansion is likely to come in Europe, driven by Norwegian, Level and Air France's Buzz. Scoot and AirAsia X are also expected to focus on expanding in Europe over the next few years – in part a response to their new European based competitors and partially driven by the fact routes to Australia and North Asia are starting to become saturated.

Figure 7.37 – Estimated cost savings potential, if current Low-Cost Concept will be adapted for Long-Haul Sectors

A simple cost model shows that in long haul, half of the potential unit-cost advantage for long-haul LCCs is from higher seat count, produced by shrinking the premium cabins and making the economy sections denser. As consequence, the 26% cost differential between LCCs and mainlines might be reduced to a slight 13 percent when seat density turns equivalent among them. The other half of the potential cost advantages comes from input costs, which are less flexible in long haul (figure 7.38). For instance, on long-haul flights, fuel's share of direct operating costs grows from 30 to 50 percent.

¹Cost per available seat kilometer.
²Long-haul.
³Seat counts based on announced configurations by carriers fitting the respective archetype.
⁴Low-cost carrier.

McKinsey&Company

Figure 7.38 – CASK for Boeing 787 in 8 hours flight
 Source: McKinsey & Company

Considering long-haul flights, the potential savings can be located mainly in the following areas:

- **Productivity:** e.g. Aircraft type, Load factors, Fuel Consumption, Manpower;

- **Performance:** e.g. Passengers traffic, Punctuality, Aircraft Utilization;
- **Operational:** e.g. Airports, Air Traffic Management, Handling, Routes, Destinations.

Key aspects of these potential savings are discussed here after.

- **Increasing Load Factors and Seat Densities.** Most of the gains of LCC come from high seat densities. However, this does not seem to be a differentiating factor actor between LCC and Network Airlines in the long-haul market. High Passenger Load Factors and dense Eco cabins Seat-Configurations on long haul sectors is already implemented by conventional airlines (Figure 7.39 and Table 7.2). Moreover, the Eco-Seating or Single Class Concept is increasing, business class seating is reduced and expanded by Premium Economy. The First-Class Concept is strongly reduced, and many airlines re-considering the concept or even cancel the service completely.

Figure 7.39 – Load factors in long haul operations

Airline	Seat Pitch in cm	Seat Width in cm	Airline	Aircraft	Eco-Seats	Ratio to total number of seats
AirAsia X	81	43	AirAsia X	A330	365	97%
British Airways	79	45	British Airways	B777	227	82%
Cathay Pacific	83	45	Cathay Pacific	B777	268	79%
Emirates	84	46	Emirates	B777	236	81%
Japan Airlines	80	45	JAL	B777	279	75%
Jetstar	79	46	Jetstar	A330	268	86%
Lufthansa	86	44	Lufthansa	A330	165	75%
Norwegian	78	44	Norwegian	B787	259	89%
Qantas	82	44	Qantas	A330	271	90%
Scoot Airlines	81	48	Scoot	B777	329	82%
Singapore Airlines	81	44	Singapore Airlines	B777	255	89%
TAM	82	44	TAM	B777	272	75%
United Airlines	80	44	United	B777	218	82%

Table 7.2 – Seat pitch, width and utilization of flight cabin by Network Airlines and Low-Cost Carrier

- **Airframe, Aerodynamic improvements, reducing fuel consumption.** High cost reduction in LH operation will come from the utilization of aerodynamic improved airframes and more economical engines. Potential savings expected in these areas have been discussed in previous sections.

For long-haul flights the aircraft efficiency and a lean airline fleet will play an important role. But due to the long aircraft production periods it might take years for a Low-Cost Airline to

build up an adequate fleet with enough number of aircraft to serve the required destinations with sufficient frequencies. Boeing and Airbus are working flat out and have a long waiting list for the single-aisle B737max and A320neo and twin-aisle B787/B777X and A350/A330neo, plus the A321LR for long thin routes pending competition from the Boeing MMA.

- **Passenger traffic, Punctuality and Aircraft Utilization.** On long Haul sectors, network carriers are already achieving a significant performance in high aircraft utilization, in average 13-15 hours aircraft utilization and over 80 percent punctual flights. The possibilities increasing flight rotations are minimum, because long-haul flights need longer turnaround times for boarding, loading, servicing and fuelling. Longer duty hours can become in conflict with duty time regulations. Flying to less congested secondary airports will not be so easy, because the necessary infrastructure; and therefore, to operate on primary international airports will not gain any savings.
- **Limits to latent demand.** LCCs' ability to drive demand by lowering prices has contributed significantly to their success in short haul, however, there may be limitations to this approach in long haul:
 - Total ticket costs are higher in long haul, and cross-elasticity of demand (that is, the ability to buy some other substantial item that a household might need or want) plays a role.
 - Cross-elasticity with other modes of transport, such as rail and bus, is limited, so the reduces the opportunity to steal travellers from other modes is reduced.
 - Low fares are already available in most markets. Sixth-freedom¹ options are priced significantly lower than their point-to-point alternatives and widely available.
 - In many leisure markets, LCCs already exist in different forms: holiday/charter carriers serving price-sensitive travellers on leisure routes (for example, Corsair and Thomson) have a particularly strong market influence in Europe; scheduled carriers catering to the visiting-friends-and-relatives passenger segment are especially prevalent on routes with strong ethnic ties, such as the Iberian Peninsula and Latin America.

If the Low-Cost Carriers must gain market shares directly from the network airlines, because they have no evasive options, Low Cost traffic will take place (Figure 7.40) mainly between North America and Europe. Probably between Southeast Asia and Europe it will start again, attempts in the past failed (Oasis Hong Kong Airlines).

Figure 7.40 – Load factors in long haul operations
Source: Airline Profiler

T7.1.5.3 Ultra-Long-haul Operation – ULTRA LH

More efficient new generation of aircraft, in particular, extended-range aircraft models Airbus A350-900ULR and Boeing 777-8, are helping to create a new marker in the long-range sector. These fuel-efficient technologies and cheaper oil are favouring the return of ultra-long flights, of about 19 hours non-stop flight.

Modern aircraft manufacturing technologies make it possible to operate profitably very long-distance routes. Technological improvements have overcome the limitations of maximum flight time to the closest airport in case of diversion, imposed by ETOPS regulations on route flown by twin-engine aircraft. The advent of aircraft such as the A350, ETOPS-compliant for up to 370 minutes, open the door for new direct oceanic routes, particularly in the Pacific region and across the Southern Hemisphere. Technological and economic challenges of long-haul flying are being already tackled.

While we may have to wait a few more years for passenger flights that reach 22 hours, there are a number of ultra-long-haul flights already in operation:

- From March 2018, Singapore Airlines plans to fly an Airbus A350-900ULR non-stop flight between Singapore and Newark airport near New York.
- With its the new venture Project Sunrise, Qantas will challenge Boeing and Airbus to deliver an aircraft capable of flying regular direct services like Sydney to London, Brisbane to Paris and Melbourne to New York non-stop by 2022 as has already been shown feasible.
- The longest flight in the world is operated by Qatar Airways, using a Boeing 777-200LR to fly the 18-hour trip between Doha in Qatar and Auckland. Gulf airline Emirates flies to New Zealand 's biggest city from Dubai using an Airbus A380 in an 18 hours flight.
- United Airlines Dreamliner's fly from Los Angeles to Singapore in 17 hours and 55 minutes.
- The longest flight to Hong Kong is by American Airlines. Its service from Dallas is scheduled to take 16 hours and 55 minutes. From Hong Kong to Dallas, the flying time is 14 hours and 25 minutes.

At the same time global demand for air travel keeps growing, and where more city pairs are reaching the demand threshold required to support direct connections.

It is probable that all these previous factors, together with new and better long-range aircraft economics and business models, will provide the definitive impulse to the development of a global long-haul low-cost airline sector.

The only remaining limitation to the development of this sector is coming now for the physiological challenges, particularly the one posed by the amount of time economy class passengers will accept to spend in a confined cabin.

Industry is working on improved ergonomic aircraft seat designs, but at his moment those improvements will not be enough for very long-distance comfort, the human body cannot be comfortable in the same position for a long time. Other factors affecting the well-being of people in indoor spaces need further improvement, such as the lack of humidity that becomes noticeable after three hours of flight; the lower air pressure in the cabin also for longer periods; the soothing effect of illumination during long flights, or how diet can influence the well-being and behaviour of passengers during long flights.

T7.1.5.4 Supersonic Flights

The Concorde, which operated at supersonic speeds since 1973, closed operations in 2003 due to difficulties in supporting an old airframe and lack of spares. There has been little private-sector investment since then. The ban responded to concerns about noise pollution and negative environmental impacts. However, over the past four decades, technical advances in engine design suggest that it is now feasible to produce less noisy supersonic jet engines. Moreover, some research suggests that the environmental impacts were overstated, although the sonic boom remains an issue.

To ensure a proper noise standard, initial levels can be established that are comparable to those societies already tolerates. A standard set at 85–90 decibels, for example, would be no different from lawnmowers, motorcycles, and kitchen blenders.

Aircraft speeds have stagnated over the past 40 years; the time required to fly from Los Angeles to New York or across the Atlantic Ocean are no different than they were in 1977. Addressing sonic boom concerns in the form of a standard instead of the current ban may go a long way toward achieving the economic gains of commercial supersonic travel.

Commercial supersonic flight has not been altogether forgotten as Boeing and Airbus as well as start-ups Boom or Spike Aerospace have all signalled supersonic ambitions. The advance in efficiency is made possible by a breakthrough aerodynamic design, state-of-the-art engines, and advanced composites. Long flights are a barrier to travel. That's why companies like Boom are trying to remove that barrier, turning 8-hour redevies into 3-4-hour daytime flights. Excruciating 16-hour journeys become easy overnights.

Figure 7.41– Flight NYC- London in 3h 15min instead of 6h 30min

Source: Boom supersonic website

This company has created prototypes to demonstrate the efficiency of supersonic flights, like XB-1 Supersonic Demonstrator. The XB-1 demonstrates the key technologies for efficient supersonic flight: advanced aerodynamic design, light-weight materials that can withstand supersonic flight, and an efficient super-cruise propulsion system. Engineering development of XB-1 ("Baby Boom") is proceeding rapidly, with aerodynamics defined, systems ground tested, and initial structural components in fabrication. Vehicle assembly starts shortly, with first flight planned for next year. They are grounded in physics and push technology to new heights.

About the prices, they are seeking the holy grail of the plane which can go to Mach 1 (the speed of sound; 768mph) and up to Mach 1.6 (instead of Mach 2.1 for Concorde) but do so with operational costs leaping to levels that large multinational will accept for their top executives.

Spike Aerospace is another rider in this most forward-thinking of races. This Boston-based company is currently developing the S-512 Supersonic Jet and has claimed that it could be flying by the end of the decade. This will be a 12-18 seat commercial plane that will reportedly be able to reach Mach 1.6 (about 1,100mph), although will largely be a luxury steed aimed at the private jet market.

Airbus, meanwhile, has set up a partnership with the Nevada-based Aerion Corporation, in the hope that a marriage of the latter's technological nous and the former's business clout and economic muscle may yet give birth to the new Concorde. Elsewhere, the European giant's key American rival Boeing is also looking to craft a supersonic solution. Japan has kept a steady research program on supersonic commercial flight.

T7.1.6 Impact on ACARE Goals

The following Table 7.3 shows how the long-haul travel could have an impact on the ACARE goals as well as the improvements that will be required:

Challenges	Goals	Action Area	Impact in LR	Improvements
Challenge 1: Meeting societal and market needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Air traffic management system (at least 25M flights). 2. Ground infrastructure. 3. Mobility. 4. Door-to-door within 4 hours. 5. Flights arrive within 1 min off the planned arrival time. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Understand customer, market and societal expectations and opportunities. - Design and implement an integrated, intermodal transport system. - Develop capabilities to evaluate mobility concepts, infrastructure and performance. - Provide travel management tools for informed mobility choices. - Deliver mobility intelligence: journey information, data and communication. - Provide tools for system and journey resilience, for disruption avoidance and management. - Evolve airports into integrated, efficient and sustainable air transport interface nodes. - Design and implement an integrated information, communication, navigation and surveillance platform. - Develop future air traffic management concepts and services for airspace users. - Human factors and automation support, autonomy and resilience. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -It will depend on business and tourist class. - ULR: aspects to improve - Low cost LR: competitiveness with traditional companies. - Advanced navigation technologies using new sensors. - Network congestion. -Selection, training and qualification of long-haul crews. - A single ticket, valid for the entire journey will be more complicated to be achieved. -Information shared between airports: processes, time, etc. -Connectivity between airports. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Users' needs will be different in long-haul routes: punctuality, comfortability, health conditions. - New markets such as ultra-long range, low cost long-haul. -Regulatory framework in crew conditions: maximum number of hours, medical inspections. - Competitiveness of emerging markets and low-cost carriers. - Interoperability requirements and standards more complex due to a larger scale. -System robustness and resilience to face disruptions. - More accurate systems. -Better connectivity and integration. - Ground and air infrastructure availability and capacity. - Tools that allow passenger to be informed of the flight situation: scales, delays, direct flights
Challenge 2: Maintaining and extending industrial leadership.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. The whole European aviation industry is strongly competitive. 7. High profiles in motivation process. 8. Streamlined systems engineering. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Increase competitiveness in product industrialisation. - Develop high-value manufacturing technologies. - Embed design-for-excellence in the product lifecycle. - Secure continued and focused investment. - Exploit the potential of operations and maintenance, repair and overhaul (MRO). - Develop innovative and optimised testing. - Establish new business/enterprise models and initiatives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digitalisation and big data, supported by cybersecurity measures. - Aviation industrialisation in the future must focus on high-value technologies. - By 2050, industrialisation should benefit from access to a full set of production data and capabilities. - European aviation industry will extend its industrial leadership while meeting the essential societal challenges of climate change and security. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Access to a full set of production data and capabilities of different production sites. - Constantly increasing competition means that airlines must maximise the operating time of their fleet, reduce operating costs and minimise the number of unscheduled flight cancellations. - European airline industry increased airport efficiency and capacity and is developing new services and products. - New models. - The use of tools for automated analysis and design.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lead the development of standards. - Streamline certification. 		
<p>Challenge 3: Protecting the environment and the energy supply</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 9. 75% reduction in CO2 emissions in 2050. 10. Aircraft movements are emission free when taxing. 11. Designed to be recyclable. 12. Europe like a centre of excellence. 13. Environmental action plan. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Develop air vehicles of the future: evolutionary steps. - Develop air vehicles of the future: revolutionary steps. - Increase resource use efficiency and recycling. - Improve the environmental performance of air operations and traffic management. - Improve the airport environment. - Provide the necessary quantity of affordable alternative energy. - Understand aviation’s climate impact. - Adapt to climate change. - Develop incentives and regulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the mid-term: new engine options or other system changes. - In long- term: more radical concepts and technologies. - On-board aircraft systems must support new operations and air traffic management concepts for reduction of emissions and noise. - New designs, new energy sources and capabilities of operations. - New operational concepts based on multiple aircraft/fleet interaction. - The increasing availability and use of (RPAS) must be carefully managed. - The use of environmentally-friendly chemicals need to be generalized at airports. - Aviation as a global business has a strong need for internationally harmonised rules, in terms of both design and operational requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Airframes: lightweight materials. - Propulsion: higher thermal and propulsive efficiency and new lightweight structures and high-temperature materials for engine cores. - Health monitoring must apply to all elements. - An eco-design approach - The operational gains resulting from these research activities will induce a reduction of between 250kg and 500kg of fuel (800kg to 1600kg of CO2) per flight - 5-10% of the total). - Specific research for the airport environment will permit significant improvement in air quality and reduction of noise annoyance at European airports. - Use of recycling materials in order to achieve less environmental impact - Optimised trajectories that minimize fuel burn as well as noise and CO2 emissions

<p>Challenge 4: Ensuring safety and security</p>	<p>14. European air traffic system has less than one accident/10M aircraft.</p> <p>15. Risks properly mitigated.</p> <p>16. Manned and unmanned vehicles operate safely in the same airspace.</p> <p>17. Efficient boarding and security measures.</p> <p>18. Resilience to external and internal threats.</p> <p>19. High –bandwidth data resilient to cyberattacks.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborate for safety. - Optimise human and organisational factors for safety. - Build and exploit safety intelligence. - Ensure operational safety. - Design, manufacture and certify for safety. - Collaborate for security. - Engage aviation personnel and society for security. - Build and exploit security intelligence. - Ensure operational security. - Design, manufacture and certify for security. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intermodal safety governance is aimed at the future. - Europe will operate an air transport system in which safety governance and practice is effective, able to keep up with and stay ahead of a rapidly changing environment. - Ensuring the highest degree of safety. - Gathering, processing and exploiting the data will provide vital information that will make the air transport system safer. -Ensuring high levels of operational safety is the culmination of all safety efforts. - Early warning and alerts will facilitate incident prevention and response system-wide, thereby maintaining security across the entire aviation spectrum. - Real-time security capability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Human factors will be essential in long-haul to ensure safety as the flights will be longer: it is necessary to change crews considering fatigue, flight hours, etc. -Crew must be trained adequately to long-haul requirements. -Improve survivability of people in long-haul flights. -Improvement of data exploitation for the benefit of safety. -Analysing the great amount of data to identify safety hazards. -All the processes inside the airports must be safe. -A safety radar is required to detect safety hazards such as weather events, one of the main disruptions in long-haul flights. -High level of maintenance will be required to ensure safe operations. -It is necessary compatible risk management methods between regions. -Monitor staff and passengers to detect erratic behaviours and security threats.
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<p>Challenge 5: Prioritising research, testing capability and education</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 20. European research and innovation agenda. 21. Industry- Research-Academia clusters. 22. Test, simulation and development facilities. 23. Young talent and women in aviation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Maintain awareness with an effective technology watchtower. -Develop an inclusive research strategy covering the entire innovation chain. -make the right investment choices with robust selection processes. -Develop and maintain state-of-the art test infrastructure. -Establish sustainable network of operators for test infrastructure. -Provide world-leading education in aviation. -Stimulate the involvement of stakeholders in education. -Make aviation attractive to ensure inflow educational programmes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The technology watchtower will promote harmonisation of evolutions in aviation with other relevant sectors. -New processes are needed to help capture and import technology from other sectors. - Systematic feedback from exploitation and operations into early research will ensure more effective technology development and reduce waste. - Develop metrics and goals to support the selection of projects and investments. - The aviation sector needs a coordinated and shared approach to the development, maintenance and operation of a broad range of infrastructure. - A dynamic network of operators of strategic European test infrastructure will ensure up-to date, relevant equipment, efficiently operated. - Workforce with excellent education. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -European aviation industry will be a support to SMEs with key knowledge and visibility of emerging technologies. - Engaging all stakeholders in a common approach will ensure that future trends are properly accommodated. - The network will bring together the expertise of all major operators and serve as the counterpart to potential users in discussions on future needs and trends. - Utilisation of the dynamic network will increase and redundancy will be reduced. - European aviation education will remain world-leading and provide excellent support to the aviation sector. - Involving industry and research establishments in educational programs will ensure that students are better prepared for a career in aviation. - Development and investment of new infrastructure required for simulation and virtual testing
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Table 7.3– ACARE Goals

KEY TOPIC T7.2 COMMERCIAL AND BUSINESS AVIATION

T7.2.1 Introduction

Related to the air traffic evolution, which include the long-haul trips, the growth of air traffic has suffered remarkable variations in the past and it is likely to also suffer remarkable variations in the future. As can be seen in the following figure 7.42, the air traffic has grown steadily through the years, but it also had decreasing periods, coinciding with economic recessions and security issues as World Trade Centre attacks in 2001.

Figure 7.42– Evolution of European IFR flights (1990-2023)
Source: EUROCONTROL Annual Report 2016

However, there has been a positive trend during the last three years, in which a 2% annual growth has been reached in 2016. Based on this positive trend, even though it is not expected that previous annual growth rates (about 6%) are reached, it is expected that air traffic continues growing as much as new technologies are able to accommodate the future demand. In this context, the successful introduction of UAVs within the current air traffic network, based on manned aircraft, will be the key factor to reach the traffic goals set for 2050.

According to what is stated in the document Challenges of Growth 2013 by EUROCONTROL, the most-likely scenario for 2035 is based on moderate economic growth, with regulation reconciling the environmental, social and economic demands to address the growing global sustainability concerns, following closely the current trends. In this context, EUROCONTROL states that there will be 14.4 million flights in Europe in 2035, 1.5 times more than in 2012 (see following Figure 7.43). That is an average of 1.8% increase per year, around half the historic rate from the 1960s to the peak of 2008. Traffic growth will slow down from 2025 as markets mature, economic growth decelerates and as the capacity limits at airports increasingly become an issue.

Figure 7.43 – EUROCONTROL scenarios for 2035
Source: Challenges of Growth 2013 - Task 4

However, contrary to the 2035 forecast, there is not a “most-likely” scenario identified for 2050 (Figure 7.44). Whilst Scenario C represents a common view of an extension to the current existing environment, it is not appropriate to identify a most-likely scenario over this extended time horizon when there is so much scope for uncertainty. Therefore, the forecast states a variable of IFR flights from 26,1 million in the best case to 10,5 million in the worst case.

Figure 7.44 – EUROCONTROL scenarios for 2050
Source: Challenges of Growth 2013 - Task 7

In this context, and considering EUROCONTROL forecasts, three different scenarios are proposed:

- First scenario (Figure 7.45): a low but steady growth occurs, establishing almost a 1% annual growth. This forecast agrees with the slow but sustained development of the air traffic framework, both of technological and regulatory framework. This growth would allow to accommodate only part of the future demand.

Figure 7.45– IFR traffic forecast - scenario 1

- Second scenario (Figure 7.46): the growth is not steady over the years and it presents decreasing periods due to issues that are likely to occur, such as economic recessions or the unviability to accommodate the demand based on the technology developed in the next decades. This forecast set a 1.25% overall annual growth rate and it would allow to accommodate only part of the future demand.

Figure 7.46 - IFR traffic forecast - scenario 2

- Third scenario (Figure 7.47): the following figure shows the optimal growth that would allow the accommodation of the expected demand within the air traffic network. This forecast set a 2,7% overall annual growth rate, reaching the 25 million flights in 2050.

Figure 7.47 – IFR traffic forecast - scenario 3

T7.2.2 Airline Traffic

Focusing on long-haul trips, the demand for them is characterized by its elasticity, mainly owing to that ticket prices for long-haul flights are very high and, therefore, these flights decrease the most during the economic downturns.

During the last few years Europe's economy has grown (Europe's GDP grew by 1.9% in 2015), thus Europe's air travel market has remained strong, including long-range travel. For example, air passenger flows grew by 15% between 2010 and 2015 in connections between North America and European Union. The routes between these two continents are traditionally one of the most profitable ones, thus it is unsurprising such a big growth.

However, the highest growth rate since 2010 was observed in passenger flows between Europe and the Near & Middle East (+49%) due to the strong expansion of Middle Eastern carriers. In contrast, North Africa's share in passenger flows decreased by 21% during 2010-2015, mainly driven by a series of multiple terrorist attacks and political instability in many of North African countries.

As can be seen in the following figure 7.48, approximately 54% of the total passengers from/to Europe were related to long-haul flights in 2015. The main destination was North America with almost a 20% of share, whilst Middle East set almost a 13% of share with the highest growth rate.

Figure 7.48 – Air passenger flows in 2015. Shares and historic evolution from/to Europe (EU28)
Source: Annual Analyses of the EU Air Transport Market 2016

Concerning airlines, its operations in Europe continue to evolve with the launch of new ventures, routes and business models. Perhaps the most striking strategic development in Europe during the last few years has been the rapid rise of the low-cost long-haul (LCLH) business model. For example, Norwegian Air Shuttle continues to expand its low-cost long-haul carrier operations, adding bases in Paris and Barcelona for service to North America and recently initiating the first low-cost service from London to Singapore. As a response to that, network airlines are establishing LCLH operations in their LCC subsidiaries: Lufthansa subsidiary EuroWings is expanding the LCLH operations it initiated last year, Level from International Airlines Group began operations during past June, and Air France-KLM's Boost has announced plans to initiate LCLH operations in 2018. The North Atlantic has been a primary flow for LCLH service additions to and from Europe, with Norwegian, EuroWings, Level, Iceland-based LCC Wow air, Canadian LCC WestJet, and Air Canada LCC subsidiary Rouge increasing their LCLH service between Europe and North America by over 250 peak operations per week during summer 2017 [1].

European operators have been on the forefront of this trend, with 96 long-haul routes introduced since 2012 (the most of any region). The introduction of more efficient aircraft has helped European carriers both to improve their load factors, but also to increase their RPKs (Revenue Passenger Kilometres) and ASKs (Available Seat Kilometres) as they fly routes of longer length.

Focusing on the future, intercontinental traffic is further impacted by the general tendency of network airlines to focus less on short-haul point-to-point traffic, while increasing hub operation. In this context, South and South East Asian destinations are expected to benefit from Middle Eastern airlines, which are expanding their transfer traffic from European airports, via Middle Eastern hubs to these markets. European network carriers in contrast, largely focus on long-haul operations to North, Central and South American regions.

As can be seen in the following figure 7.49, air traffic flows within Europe are projected to increase by 3.2% between 2016 and 2035. Intra-European traffic development is particularly driven by the continuous expansion of low-cost short-haul point-to-point traffic. On the other hand, long-haul traffic is expected to present a higher growth than short-haul traffic as traffic to South America is expected to increase by 5.3% or traffic to Middle East is expected to increase by 5.4%.

Figure 7.49 – Air traffic flows from/to Europe growth projections for 2016-2035
Source: Annual Analyses of the EU Air Transport Market 2016

T7.2.3 Business Jet Traffic

Firstly, business aviation should be put in context. Business flying is defined by International Business Aviation Council (IBAC) as “that sector of aviation which concerns the operation or use of aircraft by companies for the carriage of passengers or goods as an aid to the conduct of their business, flown for purposes generally considered not for public hire and piloted by individuals having, at the minimum, a valid commercial pilot license with an instrument rating” [2]. Different subdivisions are inherent in this definition:

- Commercial: “The commercial operation or use of aircraft by companies for the carriage of passenger or goods as an aid to the conduct of their business and the availability of the aircraft for whole aircraft charter, flown by a professional pilot(s) employed to fly the aircraft”. [2]
- Corporate: “The non-commercial operation or use of aircraft by a company for the carriage of passengers or goods as an aid to the conduct of company business, flown by a professional pilot(s) employed to fly the aircraft”. [2]
- Owner Operated: “The non-commercial operation or use of aircraft by an individual for the carriage of passengers or goods as an aid to the conduct of his/her business”. [2]

Corporate and owner operated subdivisions are located within general aviation, which is defined as “all civil aviation operations other than scheduled air services and non-scheduled air transport operations for remuneration or hire” [2]. The position of these subdivisions within general aviation can be seen in the following figure 7.50.

Figure 7.50 – Business aviation within aviation network

In this context, business aviation is the third largest market segment in Europe, after the traditional scheduled and low-cost segments. While being a much smaller market segment in comparison with commercial air travel, it nevertheless has a significantly positive economic impact as it generates jobs and, indirectly, stimulates commerce. Compared to the main market segments, business aviation flies from smaller airports, and is characterized by a very large number of routes focusing on city pairs where there is no daily scheduled service.

Business aviation has suffered variations along the years (Figure 7.51) at the same time as air traffic has changed and it has contributed to the total growth of flights in Europe. At the beginning of 21st century, business aviation suffered a rapid expansion from 2002 to 2009, when it suffered a sharp 14% contraction and it went back to around 2005 levels. This 14% contraction in 2009 was the largest percentage decline of the major market segments in Europe: all-cargo and charter came close with declines of 13%. As a result, the market share of business aviation fell back from its peak of 7.7% of flights in 2007 to 6.9% in 2009. In fact, business aviation began to contract sooner than the rest of the industry, which managed a little growth in 2008. [3]

Figure 7.51 – Annual business aviation flights in Europe 1997-2009
Source: Business Aviation in Europe 2009

However, it recovered in 2010 (+5%) and 2011 (+2.4%) but declined again by 1.2% on average between 2012 and 2015 (Figure 7.52). Therefore, over the last 10 years, the market share of business aviation has fluctuated around 7% of all flights (variations between 7.7% in 2007 to 6.7% in 2016) which states that business aviation is being a steady sector in Europe.

Figure 7.52 – Business aviation growth along the years
Source: Business aviation: An expanding sector

Concerning the recent trends and upcoming challenges, the sector started to show promising signs of strength at the end of 2016, which was confirmed by 6% growth recorded during the first quarter of 2017, compared to the same period in 2016. This is mainly due to a robust increase in flows within Europe, with France and UK contributing most to this growth, in such a way that Eurocontrol forecasts an average annual growth rate of +2.3% for the period 2017-2023.

One of the key factors for the growth of business aviation is the evolution of its fleet in Europe. Whilst business aviation set negative growth rates since 2012, the European fleet has maintained positive growth rates during the last few years, reaching more than 3000 aircraft in 2014 as can be seen in the following figure 7.53.

Figure 7.53 – European business aviation fleet 2010-2014
Source: EBAA Annual Review 2014-2015

This growth has allowed to the European fleet to maintain its position as the second biggest in the world behind the United States, hoarding around 18% of the total global fleet. It can be also stated that large category of business aircraft has suffered a growth during the last decade, as show the following figure 7.54. This means that an increase of long-range operations has occurred.

Figure 7.54 – Industry deliveries (units), large category in yellow
 Source: Bombardier business aircraft market forecast 2016-2025

Fleet forecasts show that it will continue to grow in the following years. For example, Bombardier has forecasted a total of 8300 deliveries until 2025 (starting in 2016), which are divided in 3100 deliveries of light aircraft, 2800 deliveries of medium aircraft and 2400 deliveries of large aircraft. Although the number of deliveries of large aircraft will be the lowest one, taking into account the retirements of the old aircraft, large aircraft will set the highest growth percentage in the following years. The following figure 7.55 illustrates how, whilst the light aircraft market share decreases, the large aircraft market share increases which means that long-haul trips within business aviation will grow in the next decade.

An important factor in business aviation has been the growth of traditional or shared ownership and leasing.

Figure 7.55 – Business aviation fleet 2015 vs 2025

T7.2.4 Airline Fleets

Firstly, prior to stating any conclusions, it is necessary to compare current air traffic figures with future air traffic situation.

During 2017 there were more than 10 million IFR flights within ESRA08 (EUROCONTROL Statistical Reference Area). These IFR movements can be split into internal flights, departures and arrivals (e.g. respectively going to or departing from a non-ESRA country) and overflights (e.g. flights for which both departure and arrival aerodromes are outside the region). The figures for each subdivision of IFR flights are collected in the following Table 7.4.

Departures	1.087.220
Arrivals and Departures	1.087.562
Internal	8.075.186
Overflight	143.256
Total	10.393.224

Table 7.4 – IFR movements in 2017 (ESRA08). Source: STATFOR

It is adequate to gather both arrival and departure flights in other to establish a classification, differencing between flights from/to Europe and flights within Europe. In this manner, internal flights are those that are carried out within Europe, whilst arrival flights, departure flights and overflights are those that are carried out from/to Europe or from/to another country or continent different to Europe. The percentages corresponding to each part are shown in the following figure 7.56.

Figure 7.56– IFR movements in 2017

As can be seen, internal flights hoard most of IFR movements (78%) whilst flights with origin or destination out of Europe, in which most of them can be considered as long-distance flights, gather 22% of overall.

As well as global air traffic, it is also expected a growth of the number of long-distance flights in Europe. For example, it is forecasted (Figure 7.57) 14,4 million of IFR flights in 2035 [2], within

which the short-haul flights are expected to decrease up to 69% and medium and long-haul flights are expected to grow up to 31% [4].

Figure 7.57 – IFR movements in 2035

On the other hand, it is necessary to compare the previous figures with fleet forecasts. For example, Boeing states (Figure 7.58) that there were approximately 22,510 jet airplanes in service in 2015, a number that is expected to double over the next 20 years to an in-service fleet of 45,240 airplanes. To achieve that, 39,620 new airplanes will be needed owing to that 5,620 airplanes that are in service nowadays will be maintained in service [5].

Figure 7.58 – Boeing fleet forecast 2015-2035
Source: Current Market Outlook 2016-2035

If the number of aircraft is split into categories (single aisle and widebody), it can be seen in the next figure that (Figure 7.59) 22% of overall were correspondent to widebody in 2015. This means that the percentage of widebody aircraft is exactly the same as the percentage of arrivals, departures and overflights of IFR movements in 2017. This connection between both

IFR movements and aircraft shows that nowadays both are growing together and that the offer meets the demand for long-range aircraft.

Figure 7.59 – Aircraft classified by type in 2015

On the other hand, Boeing forecasts that, from the 45.240 airplanes that will be in service in 2035, 23% of them will correspond to widebody aircraft, which means that the share for any type of aircraft will be pretty similar to nowadays (see figures 7.59 and 7.60). If this became true, it could mean that there was a big difference between the expected percentage of medium and long distance IFR movements (31%) and the expected percentage of widebody aircraft (23%). This difference could mean that offer cannot meet the demand for long-range aircraft in the future and, hence, it could become a problem for the development of long-haul flights.

Figure 7.60 – Aircraft classified by type in 2035

T7.2.5 Business Jet Fleets

Regarding business aviation, as previously seen in IFR movements, it also can be split into internal flights, departures and arrivals and overflights. From 10 million IFR flights in 2017, less than 1 million were business aviation flights (6,87%) as can be seen in the following Table 7.5.

Arrivals	52.534
Arrivals and Departures	52.255
Internal	602.754
Overflight	6.357
Total	713.900

Table 7.5 – Business aviation movements in 2017 (ESRA08). Source: STATFOR

In this case, medium and long distance mean the 16% of business aviation flights whilst short distance average the 84% of business aviation flights as can be seen in the following figure 7.61.

Figure 7.61 – Business aviation flights in 2017

Comparing the percentages of each type of flight with percentages of each type of business aviation fleet, it can be stated that long distance flights are carried out using large aircraft and also using part of total of medium aircraft, which have a range of 30%-45% of global coverage. This means that nowadays, as business fleet is maintaining positive growth rates since several years ago, there is no problem as the offer meets the demand of business aviation aircraft.

Figure 7.62 – Business aviation fleet in 2015

Concerning the evolution of business aviation, it should be considered whether the supply of aircraft will meet the demand for them, since a difference, both in excess and in defect, between supply and demand can mean not to reach the expected growth. For example, since 2007 the fleet has grown faster than the traffic (see figure 7.63) and if the trend continues as the last years, it would be questionable for the sustainability and margins of the sector, since it would lead to a form of overcapacity in which supply would outweigh demand.

On average, it would mean that the asset would be used less, while its depreciation would remain almost unchanged compared to a scenario where the aircraft was used intensively.

Figure 7.63 – Fleet growth vs Traffic growth

Source: EBAA Annual Review 2014-2015

T7.2.6 Airliner Market

As was seen in the last section, there might be a difference among the expected growth of air traffic and the expected growth of fleet within long distance sector. In this manner, there might

be a shortfall of long-range aircraft from now until 2035, when it is expected that medium and long distance flights account for 31% of all flights [6] whilst long-range aircraft are expected to account for 23% of the entire fleet, according to Boeing forecasts [5].

Although this difference of percentages may seem excessive, it is necessary to clarify that the percentage of 31% correspond to those flights covering distances longer than 2000 km. Long-haul aircraft tend to be used in routes longer than this, say over 3 000, 4 000 or 6 000 Km, so the definition should be viewed with caution. This means that, part of medium distance flights, which cover distances between 1500 and 4000 km [7], are included within this percentage. Therefore, although the difference between percentages is significant, the part concerning long distance flights is lower than it could seem.

Focusing on the growth of the fleet, which it is expected to be composed of 23% of widebody aircraft and 77% of single aisle aircraft in 2035, it is interesting to address the economic impact that it will drive globally. Even though the number of widebody aircraft will be significantly lower than single-aisle aircraft, widebody aircraft will account for about half of the total market value as forecasts carried out by Airbus and Boeing show.

For example, whilst Boeing forecasts 41030 deliveries with a billing of US\$ 6,1 trillion [1] for the next 20 years, Airbus forecasts 34166 new deliveries with a billing of US\$ 5,1 trillion [8] for the same period. Despite of the difference between companies for both number of deliveries and its billing, the most important factor is how the billing is split between types of aircraft. In this manner, the following figures show how each company expect each segment of aircraft market.

Figure 7.64 – Billing by type of aircraft forecasted by Boeing

On the one hand, Boeing forecasts (Figure 7.64) that 45,62% of total billing will correspond to widebody aircraft, which means that the airlines will spend around US\$ 2760 billion on widebody aircraft. Therefore, if the difference between the percentage of long-distance traffic and the percentage of long-range aircraft became true, it would result in a shortfall of revenue

that aircraft manufacturers could have reached if the offer had met the actual demand of widebody aircraft. In economic terms, this would result in the non-income of up to US\$ 944 billion.

Figure 7.65– Billing by type of aircraft forecasted by Airbus

On the other hand, Airbus forecasts (Figure 7.65) that almost 53% of total billing will correspond to widebody aircraft, this is translated into airlines spending around US\$ 2700 billion on widebody aircraft which is pretty similar to the figure forecasted by Boeing (US\$ 2760 billion). In this case, if the difference between the percentage of long-distance traffic and the percentage of long-range aircraft became true, it would result in the non-income of up to US\$ 924 billion.

As can be noticed, while Boeing set a higher billing for the single-aisle aircraft market, Airbus set a higher billing for the widebody aircraft market. This is owing to the difference of the number of aircraft forecasted to be delivered by 2035: Boeing forecast a total of 41030 deliveries, divided into 31900 typically single-aisle aircraft and 9130 typically twin-aisle aircraft whilst Airbus forecasts a total of 34166 deliveries, divided into 24807 typically single-aisle aircraft and 9359 typically twin-aisle aircraft. The fact that the percentage of widebody aircraft billing is different for each company (see figures 7.64 and 7.65) is mainly due to the difference of the number of single-aisle aircraft forecasted for each company (31900 vs 24907). Indeed, both companies set a similar number of widebody aircraft (9130 vs 9359) and, hence, the forecasted income are also similar (US\$ 2760 billion vs US\$ 2700 billion).

As both companies forecast a similar number of widebody aircraft to be delivered, the gap between revenue and possible non-income is also similar (US\$ 944 billion vs US\$ 924 billion). However, the most important thing about this figure is the fact that in becoming true, it would mean a potential economic growth of 34% not achieved due to, although it is expected the manufacturing of over 9000 widebody aircraft, it would be necessary more than 12000 widebody aircraft in order to cover the medium and long distance traffic (31% out of total traffic) forecasted for 2035.

T7.2.7 Business Jet Market

Contrary to what was seen in the previous section, business aviation has experienced a growth of its fleet higher than the growth of its traffic during the past years, according to EBAA Annual Review 2014-2015. However, EUROCONTROL forecasts an average annual traffic growth rate of +2.3% for the period 2017-2023 which will drive into the decrease of the difference of growth rates between fleet and traffic. If this average growth rate remains constant, business aviation will reach 850282 flights by 2025. Comparing fleet and traffic data from 2015 with forecasted data for 2025, it can be seen (Figure 7.66) that an excess number of aircraft is likely to occur.

In this manner, during 2015 there were 677340 business aviation flights in Europe according to STATFOR data, which were carried out with a fleet of 1435 airplanes, according to Bombardier data. As there will be 850282 flights by 2025, and it is expected a fleet of 2835 airplanes, the result would be an excess number of aircraft for that traffic forecast.

Figure 7.66 – Business aviation fleet in Europe 2015-2025
Source: Bombardier business aircraft market forecast 2016-2025

In economic terms, this excess number of aircraft would translate into a waste of US\$ 37.2 billion. This waste of money would occur due to both manufacturing and maintenance costs associated to the fact that a high number of aircraft would be manufactured which would result in the excess fleet that would be inactive. It could also devalue existing aircraft in the second-hand market.

T7.2.8 Desirable Future Evolution

Firstly, long distance traffic situation should be put in context. The cluster of short, medium and long distance flights shape the global air traffic network and, within it, long range flights have a fundamental role due to they allow the connections between continents in such a way that displacements of people and goods from one part of the world to another are possible in a few hours, whilst in other modes of transport, as maritime transport, the same displacements have a duration of days.

Similarly, since we are part of a globalized world in which the speed of connections with countries far away is increasingly important, long range traffic is a key factor for the development of air traffic. Likewise, all the measures designed to allow the development of air traffic will have a direct impact to long distance traffic.

Therefore, measures designed to achieve the increase of airspace capacity, the reduction of the environmental impact of air traffic and the reduction of air traffic management costs are necessary. Some of these measures address the development of equipment, systems and procedures which would allow, for example, improve the flexible use of airspace which would optimize the available airspace for commercial operations. On the other hand, other measures address the development of aircraft systems which would allow, for example, to reduce separation minima, always taking into account the main principles of any air navigation system: accuracy, availability, continuity and integrity. A clear example of the previous part is the Performance-Based Navigation (PBN). As states the PBN Navigation Strategy 2016 by FAA, PBN comprises RNAV and RNP and describes an aircraft's ability to navigate in terms of performance standards. On the one hand, RNAV enables aircraft to fly on any desired flight path within the coverage of ground- or space-based navigation aids, within the capability of the aircraft equipage or a combination of capabilities. On the other hand, RNP is RNAV with the addition of on-board performance monitoring and alerting capability. A defining characteristic of RNP operations is the ability of the aircraft navigation system to monitor the navigation performance it achieves and inform the pilot if the requirement is not met during an operation. The performance requirements of PBN for a particular airspace are communicated to pilots through navigation specifications published in navigation charts. Common PBN specifications include RNAV 1, RNAV 2, RNP 0.3, RNP 1, as well as RNAV (GPS) and RNAV (RNP) approaches, as can be seen in the following figure 7.67.

Figure 7.67 – Various PBN procedures are used at each phase of flight
Source: FAA PBN Navigation Strategy 2016

The main advantages are that PBN framework enables a safer and more efficient design of airspace and procedures within the airspace by [9]:

- Segregating traffic between airports, arrival and departure paths, and routes in close proximity.
- Increasing efficiency of sequencing, spacing and merging when integrated with communication, surveillance and controller decision support tools.

- Allowing for reduced divergence between departure operations, resulting in increased departure throughput.
- Providing safe access to airspace near obstacles and terrain.
- Improving access to airports during poor weather conditions, especially for general aviation (GA) operations.
- Reducing pilot-controller voice communication by using text-based messages, allowing controllers more time to plan or handle emergencies and abnormal situations.
- Providing pilots with vertical guidance, resulting in more stabilized approaches and landings.
- Reducing flight track distance, fuel burn and emissions due to more direct flight paths and optimized vertical descent profiles.
- Improving predictability to better inform airline operators for schedule and gate management.
- Reducing reliance on and investment in ground-based navigational aids and the conventional procedures dependent on them.

As an example of the benefits of PBN navigation procedures, non-radar track separation was reduced from 100 nautical miles (NM) to 30 NM laterally and longitudinally using RNP 4 procedures over the Atlantic and the Pacific, as can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 7.68 – Reduced spacing has substantially increased the capacity of non-radar oceanic environments

Source: FAA PBN Navigation Strategy 2016

Likewise, technological improvements and increases in operator equipment will continue to enable new worldwide PBN applications instead of conventional procedures. This transition from conventional procedures to PBN procedures increases predictability, reliability and flight efficiencies while continuing to ensure safe operations. As PBN capabilities evolve and emerging advancements in surveillance and communication become widely available in Europe, it is vital that aviation stakeholders continue to innovate and integrate navigation technologies [9].

However, these improvements may not be enough to match the expected growth of air traffic and it is possible that available capacity becomes a bottleneck. In this manner, constraints can become true both at airports (regarding runways, terminals or processes saturation) and in air traffic management (regarding en route sectors and TMAs saturation).

Therefore, proper measures should be taken in order to predict and solve these bottlenecks before they arise, hence research and development will be essential for aviation industry. In that case, European Union should provide institutions, companies and other stakeholders with the tools needed for a successful development.

KEY TOPIC T7.3 AIRLINER MARKET

T7.3.1 Introduction

Our age of globalization is unique in that it is now far cheaper and faster than ever to transport people, which has made it possible to travel back and forth between distant places as never before. This is the direct consequence of the expansion in air travel. Of course, it was possible to travel long distances before air travel, but the cost was so high and travel time so long that few actually did, and those who did, for the most part, would not travel frequently. Now, for the first time in human history, the whole world is effectively connected in a global network that enables a constant flow of people between countries and continents far apart.

The technological evolution of commercial airplanes enabled greater and greater distances to be covered: from the Boeing 707, which started flying transatlantic routes in 1958, to the Boeing 747 ("Jumbo Jet"), which enabled, for instance, the route between San Francisco and Sydney which, at just under 7500 miles, became in 1976 the longest regularly scheduled non-stop flight in the world.

The Boeing 747-400 started commercial operations in 1989; by 1990 there had already been over 100 units delivered, and the 747-400 went on to become the best-selling subset in the 747 family, with more than 1400 units delivered. A few years later, in 1993-94, Airbus introduced its A330 and A340 models, which made the company into a serious competitor for Boeing; the A330/A340 have combined to sell more than 1800 units. Finally, in 1995, the Boeing 777 family went into operation, eventually delivering nearly 1500 planes. These plane models made ULH flights substantially cheaper, because they combined long ranges with much improved fuel efficiency. The 747-400 family was about 20% more fuel-efficient than the preceding best-selling family of twin aisle planes, from the early 1970s, and the 777 pushed that gain further to a total of about 30%.

The number of long-haul flights (above 4500 miles) goes up sharply right after 1989, and this is largely pushed by the range below 6000 miles. This is in turn driven by Boeing aircraft, matching the introduction of the 747-400. Airbus then enters the long-haul market in 1993, exactly as the A330 and A340 come into the picture, and the increase in its presence is overwhelmingly in the below- 6000 range as well.

The introduction of the Boeing 747, in 1970, brought about the era of "ultra-long-haul" (ULH) commercial aviation. There is no single definition of what constitutes ULH, but a common

practical one singles out flights that take longer than 12 hours. Given customary speeds, a 12-hour flight translates into about 6000 miles, corresponding to the distance between London or Paris and Tokyo. The distinction is apparent in the range of modern commercial aircraft by Airbus and Boeing: there is a set of aircraft models designed to fly up to 4000 nautical miles (about 4600 miles), and another designed to fly at least 6000 miles. The crucial import of the ULH distinction is not in the technical feasibility of flights by different kinds of aircraft – in fact, the shorter-haul planes cannot fly the 9-12 hours range anyway.⁶ Instead, the 12-hour threshold is meaningful because of its impact on the cost of a given flight, as very long flights impose requirements on the availability of pilots and crew. For instance, the US Federal Aviation Authority (FAA) had required since the 1950s that a two-pilot crew could fly at most 12 hours within a 24-hour period: flights above that limit require at least three pilots and an additional flight crew member (“double augmentation”), as well as “adequate sleeping quarters” on the plane. Similarly, European regulators adopted in 1991 a daily maximum of 13 hours for a flight crew member’s “flight duty period” working in a basic (“un-augmented”) crew. Since the regulator also imposed that pre- and post-flight duties included in that period could not be less than one hour, there would necessarily be additional crew in any flight of more than 12 hours. The cost patterns documented by the US FAA show that, for long-haul planes (wide-body, 300-plus seats) in passenger air carriers, crew corresponds to about 36% of non-fuel costs (11% of total costs). On top of that, additional crew and sleeping quarters imply less space and weight available for carrying payload, thus reducing revenue potential.

T7.3.2 Foreseen Development of the Long-Range Air Transport Demand

Demand for air transport is the driver for traffic growth. Demand is heavily influenced by the economy and demographic evolution. The growth of air transport exhibits a strongly positive trend, even though this is inhibited to some extent by various factors, such as environmental concerns, infrastructure, perceived inconvenience, and so on. In the presence of these constraints, however, the evidence indicates that overall demand does not reduce, but instead adapts - and spreads. As constraints influence demand, then so, in turn, demand influences supply. If air traffic growth is constrained (e.g., by capacity limits or regulation and/or by price increases), then demand changes and supply adapts and restructures.

The development of competition between airlines, which followed air transport deregulation, coupled with more efficient and less costly aircraft technologies, has brought about the democratisation of air transport. Tourism is an important contributor to air transport growth. About 69% of air journeys made by Europeans are leisure trips. Demand for leisure-driven air transport will probably continue to grow.

Regarding the characteristics of air travel demand in 2025, a recent study has identified the following trends (Eurocontrol, 2009):

- increase in the level of air travel demand for the purpose of Visiting Friends and Relatives;
- increase in the level of air travel demand for retired people;
- increase in the demand for individualised travel;
- use of travel as a way to escape from the very fast rhythm imposed by society;

- increases in air fares or regulatory measures limit supply levels and reduce demand for air travel.

Long-term demand analysis requires further exploration and monitoring of several societal indicators (Eurocontrol, 2009):

- total cost of travel, including the cost of living at destination;
- household consumption of leisure air travel;
- holiday departure rates according to socio-professional categories;
- number of retired and emigrated people impacting the number of trips for the purpose of Visiting Friends and Relatives (VRF);
- opposition between environmental issues and the emergence of "the right to travel".

Professional mobility, second to tourism and leading to migration flows, remains an important driver of air transport demand. Moreover, professional mobility is supported by the EU as a channel for developing the future European economic model.

Emerging economies attract business activities, which act as a catalyst for more transport and travel movements until levels of wealth begin to reach toward those in developed nations. In the future, there is likely to be very strong growth along these lines, comparable with the doubling of air traffic every 20 years as observed in the West. The areas with outstanding growth are Asia (especially China and India), Russia, and Latin America. These are emerging economies seeking access to the same travel modes and behaviours as the developed countries. This may lead to significant growth in demand, especially for long-haul connections, that is, unless environmental constraints impede this growth.

The main macro-economic trend is the exceptional growth over the past four years. Global GDP increased by 4% yearly. This represented an annual 8% growth in global air transport demand. From 2008 onward, following the "sub-prime" crisis, global GDP growth will slow slightly to stabilise at around 3% for the next five years (forecast made early 2008). This equates to a 6% growth in global air transport demand. This figure has actually been the standard for the last 60 years. Air transport growth over the long-term, then, has exhibited a stable trend, even though economic stagnation and recession. Although economic forces have exerted a negative impact on demand in special circumstances (for instance, the 1970s oil crisis and 1991 terrorist attacks) traffic is seen, historically, to rebound after negative events.

T7.3.3 Long-Range Air Transport Cost

T7.3.3.1 Aircraft

An aircraft can operate on different ranges. According to the ICAO definition, the long-haul flights are the flights on routes longer than 4 000 km (ca. 2160 NM). However, it is generally assumed that long-haul flights are carried out on routes longer than 6,000 km (ca. 3 240 NM). Aircraft that can handle such routes are mainly produced by two world leaders in the aircraft production: the AIRBUS consortium and the Boeing Company. Table 7.6 contains a summary of the long-range aircraft currently in service, indicating the maximum capacity of each type,

number of aircraft currently in use and the approximate unit cost. The payback-range characteristic of three classes of airliners appears in the Figures 7.69 – 7.71).

Some of the aircraft not included in the table have a range close or a little greater than 3200 NM. This is their maximum range. However, aircraft rarely fly on routes with a length close to their maximum range, therefore it was assumed that they do not fly on long-haul distances.

Type	Max. Seating no.	Max. range, nm	In service/in order (2016)	No. of operators	Unit Cost Million USD
Airbus A300-600(R)	298	4 150	23	9	N/A
Airbus A310-200/300	280	4 350	35	15	N/A
Airbus A330-200	380	7 250	501/42	91	238.5
Airbus A330-300	440	6 100	619/99	71	264.2
Airbus A340-200	300	8 000	2	3	87 (1989)
Airbus A340-300	440	7 400	120	33	238 (2011)
Airbus A340-500	375	9 000	5	8	261.8 (2011)
Airbus A340-600	475	7 900	72	10	275.4 (2011)
Airbus A350-900	366	9 700	36/564	39	317.4
Airbus A380-800	853	8 200	195/124	19	445.6
Boeing 737-7	170	4 200	0/60	-	90.2
Boeing 757-200	228	3 995	357	63	65 (2002)
Boeing 767-200/200ER	255	6 385	19	23	N/A
Boeing 767-300/300ER	350	5 500	481	84	197.1
Boeing 767-400ER	375	5 365	37	2	N/A
Boeing 787-8	291	7 355	304	41	224.6
Boeing 787-9	290	7 635	141/432	41	264.6
Boeing 787-10	330	6 430	0/153	9	306.1
Boeing 777-200	440	4 240	70	10	N/A

Type	Max. Seating no.	Max. range, nm	In service/in order (2016)	No. of operators	Unit Cost Million USD
Boeing 777-200ER	313	7 065	363	49	277.3
Boeing 777-200LR	317	8 555	55	12	313.8
Boeing 777-300	550	5 045	53/3	10	N/A
Boeing 777-300ER	396	7 370	669/126	40	339.6
Boeing 777-8	355	8 700	0/53	-	371
Boeing 777-9	406	7 600	0/243	-	400
Boeing 747-400(ER)	500	7 635	187	43	N/A
Boeing 747-8I Intercontinental	581	7 730	32/9	5	379.1

7.6. Long-range aircraft

Figure 7.69 Narrow-body Payload-range (single class cabin configuration) (Leeuwen, 2016)

Figure 7.70 Narrow-body payload-range (dual class cabin configuration) (Leeuwen, 2016).

Figure 7.71 Widebody payload-range (dual class cabin configuration) (Leeuwen, 2016).

Figure 7.72 Widebody payload-range (triple class cabin configuration) (Leeuwen, 2016).

T7.3.3.2 Fuel

One of the main factors affecting the economic efficiency of air transport is the amount of fuel consumed. The indicator showing the amount of fuel consumed is fuel efficiency expressed in fuel/passenger-km.

The analysis compares the fuel efficiency of newly delivered aircraft on two metrics, namely fuel per passenger-kilometre and ICAO's metric value (MV). The fuel/passenger-km metric denotes the amount of fuel burned per passenger-km flown, as measured from the departure gate to arrival gate ("block fuel"). This metric includes all fuel consumed for taxi, take-off, cruise, approach, and landing.

ICAO's metric value (MV) was developed within ICAO's Committee on Aviation Environmental Protection (CAEP) as part of the effort to establish a CO₂ emission standard for new airplanes. The most important difference from the fuel/passenger-km metric is that MV considers only the cruise performance and ignores other flight phases of an aircraft such as landing, take-off, and climb.

Figure 7.73 presents historical changes in fuel efficiency for commercial jet aircraft from 1960 to 2014, with the 1968 value as the baseline, using both fuel/passenger-km and ICAO's metric value. The figure shows that the average fuel burn of new aircraft fell approximately 45% from 1968 to 2014, or a compounded annual reduction rate of 1.3%. But the rate of reduction varied significantly. During periods of rapid improvement such as the 1980s, fuel efficiency improved by 2.6% annually due to the aggressive adoption of new technologies and efficient aircraft design principles. In contrast, little net improvement was seen during the 1970s.

Reductions in average aircraft fuel burn slowed noticeably after 1990 and largely halted around 2000. After 2010, average fuel efficiency began to accelerate on both metrics and has now returned to the long-term average improvement of 1.1% per annum on a fuel/ passenger-km basis. Acceleration in improvement rate is expected in the foreseeable future due to the introduction of new, more efficient aircraft designs such as the A320neo, 737 MAX, and 777X. Over the long term, fuel efficiency improvements on the fuel/passenger-km and ICAO's cruise fuel metric were found to be comparable. Periodic deviations between the two are partly attributable to the fact that the ICAO metric provides limited crediting for improved structural efficiency (e.g., the use of lightweight materials).

ICAO estimates the potential for a 40% improvement in fuel efficiency for new single-aisle and small twin-aisle aircraft in 2020 relative to 2000 levels. This goal was compared with a fuel burn trend projection of new single-aisle (SA) and small twin-aisle (STA) aircraft types under ICAO's metric value plotted by the year they enter service (EIS). Figure 7.74 presents this comparison, showing a 12-year time lag between the projected fuel burn improvement and the time needed to reach ICAO's goals.

Figure 7.73 Average fuel burn for new commercial jet aircraft, 1960 to 2014 (1968=100) (Kharina et al., 2015).

Figure 7.74 New single-aisle and small twin-aisle jet aircraft metric value vs. ICAO fuel burn technology goals (Kharina et al., 2015).

There are several expected drivers of the recent trends in new aircraft efficiency. One is fuel cost. Figure 7.75 overlays the trend in real jet fuel prices (EIA, 2015), normalized via the Consumer Price Index to 2015 values, from 1975 to January 2015 over the average fuel burn data (fuel/passenger-km metric) from Figure 7.73. Figure 7.75 highlights the high volatility of jet fuel prices, especially in the last decade.

Figure 7.75 Average fuel burn for new commercial jet aircraft and real jet fuel prices (2015 dollars) (Kharina et al., 2015).

Over the long term, aircraft average fuel burn trends are largely driven by the introduction of new, more efficient aircraft types. Within an aircraft type, there are limited means of reducing fuel burn through the introduction of incremental improvements in technology; prominent examples include Performance Improvement Packages (PIPs) that are incorporated into Airbus and Boeing's products over the course of their production lives.

The average fuel burn trend assuming annual improvement on all aircraft types after their EIS dates follows the original trend quite closely, with gaps widening in the 1970s and narrowing back in the 1980s, and again widening in the late 2000. In fact, the annual average fuel burn reduction for the sensitivity analysis between 2010 and 2014 falls to 0.9%, lower than the annual improvement for the trend assuming no annual improvement (1.1%).

T7.3.3.3 Fuel Price

Over the long-term, the biggest concern for the air transport industry is the cost of fuel. Profitability, reduced costs and return on investment are the key factors that govern organisations like Airbus, Boeing, and the airlines. For the financial well-being of a commercial air transport operator, fuel cost is the greatest issue, as this represents the main part of its operating costs. This depends on fuel price and fuel burn. Ever since its beginning, air transport has been fuelled by oil derivatives.

Alternatives to fossil fuel were known and tested some 20 to 30 years ago. There has been hydrogen- and natural gas-fuelled aircraft. None of these innovations are remembered, despite being potentially more economical than the current aircraft operations. Nonetheless, the search for alternative fuel will probably affect other modes of transport before air transport.

Demand and availability of oil will be important factors for air transport evolution as these drive fuel prices. The oil price will increase as, in the long-term, oil demand is likely to increase faster than supply. Oil price is not yet driven by scarcity. Global oil reserves for the next 80 years are probably greater than the estimations, and oil availability does not mean actual physical limitations for air transport. After all, air transport accounts for 3% of global fuel consumption, and if doubled would still only represent 6%.

T7.3.3.4 Ticket Price

Today, the cost of air travel may well be at its lowest ever. Competition between airlines is driving ticket prices down, which, in turn, sustains air transport growth. The ATM community is creating an increasingly efficient system. Airlines are becoming far more efficient in the way they operate their businesses; and they have reduced overhead costs significantly.

However, fuel price and tax increases may well drive prices up again. We are probably at the bottom of the curve of disposable air ticket prices, without knowing where air ticket prices will be 20 years from now. In Europe, the political signs are that air travel is considered too cheap; this could potentially have a strong negative impact on demand.

In the long term, a quick economic analysis using the elasticity of demand to GDP and ticket-price (which will increase because of oil) shows that even with very conservative assumptions

but taking into consideration the demography which plays an important role in the growth of air transport, we can still expect a 2.5% growth per annum until 2025.

- elasticity of demand to ticket price is -0.5 (i.e., if the price reduces by 1% then demand increases by 0.5%). This is a reasonable assumption, since, in general, such elasticity is deemed to be -0.4 in the long term.
- elasticity of demand to GDP is 0.8. This is an appropriate value for developed economies. In China, however, the value would be nearer 2.0.

Let us consider a scenario where the oil price goes from USD 50 in 2005 to USD 200 in 2025 (USD in constant value). This is seen as a realistic hypothesis because the oil price will remain driven by demand rather than by scarcity.

We can then make a projection of how much ticket prices could increase by 2050.

- Take a ticket price of 100 in 2005, 25% of this covers fuel cost, i.e., 25.
- In 2025, fuel cost is multiplied by four. There is a slight decrease due to productivity gains (-0.5% per year). The ticket price is then 167.5.

Assuming that global GDP increases annually by 4% between 2005 and 2015, the annual increase between 2015 and 2025 is 3%, and global GDP is then multiplied by two in 2025. In this hypothesis, the growth in demand by 2025 would represent a 34% increase, i.e., 1.5% per year. If demography is included, this would go up to 2.5% per year. This is far from the commonly accepted 4% per year. The hypotheses are therefore pessimistic, but still they indicate that demand will grow.

T7.3.4 Aircraft Manufacturers and Operators

T7.3.4.1 Manufacturers

There were 2,375 net commercial aircraft orders in 2015, down 30% on the previous years' orders. Airbus secured 1,100 new orders in 2015, down 37% on 2014 when over 1,700 orders were placed. Boeing on the other hand secured 840 new orders during 2015, a 45% reduction on 2014 (1,527 orders).

Narrow body airliners represented in Figure 7.76 close to two-thirds of total orders, although orders for these types were sharply down on previous years. Airbus secured 900 of these orders, mainly for the A320neo, while Boeing recorded 550 orders, most of them for its new 737 Max.

Despite this slowdown in new orders, both Airbus and Boeing have strong order backlogs and are increasing production rates to meet the long-run demand from airlines.

Figure 7.76 Airliner Orders 2005-2015

Airbus and Boeing delivered 1,366 aircraft in 2015, with Boeing delivering a higher share globally and, in all regions, apart from Latin America and the Middle East. Of these deliveries, 46% were to airlines in the Asia-Pacific region.

Looking forward, between 2016 and 2035 growth in air travel demand is expected to result in delivery of between 33,070 (Airbus forecast) and 37,340 (Boeing forecast) new commercial jet aircraft (excluding regional jets). Airbus and Boeing broadly agree on the level of demand for wide-body aircraft, but Boeing sees greater demand for narrow-body aircraft, and only one-third of the number of very large aircraft.

T7.3.4.1 Airlines

We know which types of aircraft will be operating in 2020. There will be no major technological breakthrough until then. As an example, for long-haul, the planes used 20 years from now may be the A380 and the B777, the A350 and the B787. The A380 and the B777 are part of the logic of substantial flows between large airfields supported by the hub system. The A350 and the B787 were conceived with the development logic of the long-haul point-to-point system as an alternative to the hub system. This is based on the idea that 13 Chinese capitals will constitute marketplaces of more than 10 million inhabitants. These capitals are bound to deal directly with European capitals independently of one another. Flying farther and faster with a quick turn-around time is a factor that contributes to efficient aircraft operation. There are two factors to consider when designing and building aircraft: size and speed. For the construction of large aircraft, like the A380, a good case for the economic justification is needed. Contrary to the Hub and Spoke concept, the concept of point-to-point, such as Lyon to Salt Lake City, emphasises speed and distance. The large market between hubs, e.g., Paris and New York, emphasises size and distance. The two modes of operation will probably co-exist. Business development might not be based on frequency anymore, but on a strategy of «productive» growth using larger aircraft. However, the macro-economic trend of a 6% growth in the

demand for worldwide air transport over the next five years is a concern, because this implies that most of the large European hubs will be saturated in the future.

Concentration of legacy airlines will continue. This will reduce competition, which is often detrimental to the environment and to the economic performance of the operators: several departures at the same time for the same destination, small modules, and high frequencies, more fuel usage, and more space utilised. The air transport model evolves toward a trust of three worldwide alliances between three European and three American poles: American Airlines alongside British Airways, United Airlines alongside Lufthansa, and Delta North West alongside Air France. At the moment, intra-American flows, intra-European flows, and European-American flows represent 54% of worldwide flows. Airlines from other parts of the world will probably enter some of these three alliances.

KEY TOPIC T7.4 BUSINESS JET MARKET

T7.4.1 Introduction

According to the General Aviation Manufacturers Association (GAMA) 2016 General Aviation Statistical Databook & 2017 Industry Outlook, Textron Aviation (Cessna Aircraft) delivered in 2016 178 business jets, Bombardier Business Aircraft came 2nd at 163, Embraer Executive Jets sold 117, Gulfstream Aerospace sold 115, Dassault Falcon Jet sold 49, Honda Aircraft Company sold 23, ONE Aviation Corp. (prev. Eclipse Aero) sold 8, while Boeing Business Jets sold 4 and Airbus Corporate Jets sold 1.

T7.4.2 Leading Business Jets Manufacturers in 2016

According to the GAMA world leading business jets manufacturers are:

Textron Aviation (Cessna) – is the general aviation business unit of the Textron group. It was formed in March 2014 following the acquisition of Beech Holdings which included the Beechcraft and Hawker Aircraft businesses. The new business unit includes also the Textron-owned Cessna. The company sells Beechcraft and Cessna branded aircraft. While no longer selling new Hawker airplanes, Textron Aviation still supports the existing Hawker aircraft fleet through its service centres.

<http://txtav.com/>

Bombardier Business Aircraft, as part of Bombardier Inc. – it is the world's third-largest aircraft manufacturer. The company's involvement with aircraft started with its acquisition of Canadair in 1986. Bombardier makes a wide range of jets to suit different purposes. The Learjet series is made up of light jets capable of carrying around eight or nine over short distances, whilst the popular Global 6000 – previously known as the Global Express XRS – can carry almost twice as many passengers and is able to make much longer journeys. The company newest aircraft are the follow on to the highly successful Global 5000/6000, with the Global 7000/8000 scheduled to enter service in 2017/2018. The company currently offers: Learjet 70 and 75, Challenger 350 and 650, Global 5000, 6000, 7000, 8000.

<https://www.businessaircraft.bombardier.com/en/aircraft>

Embraer Executive Jets - Brazilian-based Embraer entered the aerospace market making reliable turboprops. The Legacy 600, available as a shuttle version with 16-37 seats and an executive version with 10-16 seats, flew for the first time in 2001. With the Legacy continuing to cement its reputation as an immensely popular mid-sized aircraft, in 2006 Embraer embarked on a tour across the US to showcase mock-ups of its new Phenom 100 business jet as well as the Phenom 300. The following year the Phenom 100 entered service, just three months before the much larger Lineage 1000, which achieved FAA Certification in 2009.

Having started off in the business by building executive versions of airliners in the early 2000s, Embraer are now aiming to have a model in each of the size and weight categories. First came the Phenom 100 and Phenom 300, but Embraer soon closed the gap between the Phenom 300 and the Legacy 650 with the introduction of the mid-size Legacy 450 and Legacy 500. Embraer decided to give the aircraft the Legacy name rather than the Phenom name to give the new range the feel of the larger aircraft family.

<http://www.embraerexecutivejets.com/en-us/pages/compare-aircraft.aspx>

Gulfstream Aerospace - Although Gulfstream has developed a number of popular medium-sized business jets, such as the G200 and G450, the Georgia-based company has built its reputation almost entirely from building large business jets. Having always specialised exclusively in corporate aircraft, Gulfstream Aerospace grew out of Grumman Aircraft Engineering Co., a manufacturer of military aircraft. Gulfstream's biggest coup came part way through 2014 with the simultaneous introduction into the market of two new models. Long talked about as the mysterious sounding 'P42', Gulfstream managed to keep both the G500 and G600 secret until the day they launched. During the launch at the manufacturers Savannah home-base, Gulfstream wowed many by having the G500 taxi into view under its own power. The company currently offers: Gulfstream G650ER, G650, G600, G500, G550, G280.

<http://www.gulfstream.com/>

Dassault Falcon Jet – Dassault has produced a number of medium-sized business jet models as well as the larger Falcon 7X, which features three engines and has a range of almost 6,000 nautical miles. Dassault's latest models, the Falcon 5X and Falcon 8X were introduced in 2013 and 2014 respectively, but whilst the Falcon 8X is a one meter stretch of the 7X with an additional 500 nm range, the 5X is a clean sheet design that could become the platform for later, larger models.

<https://www.dassaultfalcon.com/en/Pages/Home.aspx>

Honda Aircraft – Honda Aircraft Company is a wholly owned subsidiary of American Honda Motor Co., Inc. Founded in 2006, Honda Aircraft's world headquarters is located in North Carolina. The HondaJet is Honda's first commercial aircraft, incorporates many technological innovations in aviation design (e.g. Over-The-Wing Engine Mount (OTWEM) configuration that improves performance). The OTWEM improves fuel efficiency by reducing aerodynamic drag, cabin sound, minimizes ground-detected noise. The HondaJet is powered by two highly fuel-efficient GE Honda HF120 turbofan jet engines. The HondaJet is a light, seven seats jet, with a range of 1,223 nautical miles and 422 knot cruising speed.

<http://www.hondajet.com/>

Boeing Business Jets - All three versions of BBJ remain popular types of aircraft amongst private jet owners and operators, and between 1996 and 2014, there were a total of 164 aircraft delivered to customers. The company's latest development came in August 2011 when the Boeing board approved the launch of the 737MAX series of aircraft, almost a year after Airbus launched the A320neo family that the 737 competes with. Designed to replace the current in-production series of 737 airliners, the BBJ versions of the aircraft were finally launched in April 2014 with an order from an undisclosed customer for a single BBJ MAX 8.

Like Airbus Corporate Jets, Boeing Business Jets are often used by heads-of-state, governments and corporate clients, and because of a great number of airlines operate Boeing aircraft, it is easy to find maintenance.

<http://www.boeing.com/commercial/bbj/>

Orders and deliveries include all BBJ, BCA and BDS Aircraft delivered new into VIP service since 1996 appear in Table 7.7

Orders & Deliveries	737	BBJ	MAX	757	767	777	787	747-4	747-8	TOTAL
Orders	16	169	17	5	8	11	15	3	11	255
Deliveries	16	163	0	5	8	11	12	3	11	229
In Service	15	159	0	5	8	8	4	3	6	208

Table 7.7 Source: <http://www.boeing.com/commercial/bbj/#/aircraft/overview/>

Airbus Corporate Jets - Airbus has besides the two main manufacturing facilities, one at Toulouse and the other in Hamburg, also one in China and one in the U.S. The most popular business jets built by Airbus are corporate ACJ318, ACJ319neo, ACJ320neo and ACJ321. These versions typically seat between 15 and 50 passengers. Airbus Corporate Jets are often used by heads-of-state, governments and corporate clients, and because over 300 airlines operate Airbus aircraft, it is easy to find maintenance.

<http://www.airbus.com/aircraft/corporate-jets.html>

ONE Aviation Corp. (prev. Eclipse Aero) - formed in 2015 to merge the aircraft manufacturers Eclipse Aerospace and Kestrel Aircraft. The new company initially produced the Eclipse 550, which had been in production at Eclipse Aerospace, and intends to complete certification of the Kestrel K-350. In March 2017 the company announced that Eclipse 550 production would end to concentrate production on the new Eclipse 700 model of the aircraft.

<https://www.oneaviation.aero/>

Reference state in 2010 and progress up-to-now

According to the General Aviation Manufacturers Association (GAMA) worldwide business jet shipments by manufacturer in years 2010-2016 are given in Table 7.9:

Company	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Airbus Corporate Jets	15	10	9	6	5	4	1
Boeing Business Jets	12	8	12	7	10	11	4
Bombardier Business Aircraft	150	182	179	180	204	199	163
Cirrus Aircraft	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Dassault Falcon Jet	95	63	66	77	66	55	49
Embraer Executive Jets	145	99	99	119	116	120	117
Gulfstream Aerospace Corp.	99	99	94	144	150	154	115
Honda Aircraft	0	0	0	0	0	2	23
ONE Aviation Corp.	0	0	0	0	12	7	8
Textron Aviation (Beechcraft)	73	52	32	6	0	0	0
Textron Aviation (Cessna)	178	183	181	139	159	166	178
SUM:	767	696	672	678	722	718	661

Table 7.8 Source: 2016 General Aviation Statistical Databook & 2017 Industry Outlook

The worldwide business jet shipments by manufacturer and type of aircraft in years 2003-2016 is presented in the Table 7.9.

	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Airbus	0	0	9	11	13	11	13	15	10	9	6	5	4	1
Airbus Corporate Jet (all models)	0	0	9	10	12	9	11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ACJ318	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	2	2	1	0	1	0
ACJ319	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	6	6	4	1	1	0
ACJ320	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	1	0	0	4	1	0
ACJ321	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0	0	0
ACJ330	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
ACJ340	-	-	-	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Avcraft (prev. Fairchild)	9	9	1	0										
Envoy 3	9	9	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Boeing Business Jets	7	3	4	13	7	6	6	12	8	12	7	10	11	4
Boeing Business Jet	4	2	3	12	7	3	3	4	8	2	5	3	4	1
Boeing Business Jet 2	3	1	1	1	0	1	0	2	0	2	1	2	1	0
Boeing Business Jet 3	-	-	-	-	-	2	1	4	0	0	0	0	1	0
Boeing 737-800	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
Boeing Business Jet 747	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	0	0	0	0
Boeing Business Jet 767	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Boeing Business Jet 777	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	2	0	0	0	1	1	1
Boeing Business Jet 787	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	4	4	0
Bombardier Business Aircraft	70	130	188	213	224	247	173	150	182	179	180	204	199	163
Learjet 31A	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Learjet 40/XR	-	17	21	26	57	48	33	16	24	24	1	-	-	-
Learjet 45/XR	17	22	28	30	57	48	33	16	24	24	1	-	-	-
Learjet 60/XR	12	9	18	15	23	26	13	12	19	15	10	1	0	-
Learjet 70/75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	18	33	32	24
Challenger 300/350	1	28	50	55	51	60	33	29	37	48	55	54	68	62
Challenger 604/605	24	29	36	29	35	44	36	38	43	34	32	36	25	26
Global 5000	-	4	17	18	46	52	51	49	53	54	62	80	73	51
Global 6000/Express	14	20	13	22	46	52	51	49	53	54	62	80	73	51
CL 850/870/890	-	1	5	18	12	17	7	6	6	4	2	0	1	0
Cirrus Aircraft	0	3												
SF50	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3
Dassault Falcon Jet	49	63	51	61	70	72	77	95	63	66	77	66	55	49
Falcon 50EX	8	5	5	5	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Falcon 900C	3	3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Falcon 900EX	6	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Falcon 900DX	-	-	2	4	10	4	1	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
Falcon 900EX EASy	4	14	16	16	18	19	17	17	1	-	-	-	-	-
Falcon 900LX	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	11	7	11	8	-	-
Falcon 2000	12	11	6	6	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Falcon 2000DX	-	-	-	-	-	3	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Falcon 2000EX	16	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Falcon 2000EX EASy	-	19	21	30	33	24	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Falcon 2000LX	-	-	-	-	-	-	23	30	20	22	8	-	-	-
Falcon 2000LXS	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	18	-	-
Falcon 2000S	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12	13	-	-
Falcon 7X	-	-	-	-	6	21	32	41	31	37	43	27	-	-
Falcon 2000S/2000LXS/900LX/7X/8X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	55	49
Embraer	13	13	20	27	36	38	122	145	99	99	119	116	120	117
Phenom 100/E	-	-	-	-	-	2	97	100	41	29	30	19	12	10
Phenom 300	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	26	42	48	60	73	70	63
Legacy 450	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	12
Legacy 500	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	20	21
Legacy 600/650	13	13	20	27	36	36	18	11	13	17	21	18	12	9
Lineage 1000/E190 Head of State	-	-	-	-	-	-	5	5	3	2	4	3	3	2
Shuttles (ERJs and E-Jets)	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	3	0	3	4	0	0	0
Emivest (prev. Sino Swearingen)	0	0	0	1	1	0	2	0						
SJ30-2	-	-	-	1	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gulfstream Aerospace Corporation	74	78	89	113	138	156	94	99	99	94	144	150	154	115
G100/150 (prev. IAI Astra)	24	22	26	42	59	68	19	24	21	11	23	33	34	27
G200 (prev. IAI Galaxy)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
G300/350/400/450 (prev. GVI/GVSP)	50	56	63	71	79	88	75	75	78	83	121	117	120	88
G500/G550 (prev. GV/GVSP), G650	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Honda Aircraft Company	0	2	23											
HA-420 HondaJet	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	23
ONE Aviation Corp. (prev. Eclipse Aero)	0	0	0	1	98	161	0	0	0	0	0	12	7	8
Eclipse 500	-	-	-	1	98	161	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Eclipse 550	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12	7	8
Textron Aviation (Beechcraft)	100	115	141	140	162	160	98	73	52	32	6	0	0	0
Premier I/A	29	37	30	23	54	31	16	11	11	3	-	-	-	-
Hawker 400XP	24	28	53	53	41	35	11	12	1	-	-	-	-	-
Hawker 750	-	-	-	-	-	23	13	5	7	-	-	-	-	-
Hawker 800XP	47	50	58	8	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	-
Hawker 850XP	-	-	-	56	35	15	3	1	0	-	-	-	-	-
Hawker 900XP	-	-	-	-	32	50	35	28	22	17	-	-	-	-
Hawker 4000	-	-	-	-	-	6	20	16	10	12	6	-	-	-

Table 7.9 Source: 2016 General Aviation Statistical Databook & 2017 Industry Outlook, GAMA

	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016
Textron Aviation (Cessna Aircraft)	196	181	247	307	388	466	289	178	183	181	139	159	166	178
CE-510 Citation Mustang	-	-	-	1	45	101	125	73	43	38	20	8	8	10
CE-525 Citation CJ1	22	20	14	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CE-525 Citation CJ1+	-	-	4	25	34	20	14	3	2	-	-	-	-	-
CE-525 Citation M2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12	46	41	38
CE-525A Citation CJ2	56	27	23	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CE-525A Citation CJ2+	-	-	-	36	44	56	21	17	15	19	15	2	-	-
CE-525B Citation CJ3	-	6	48	72	78	88	40	20	22	21	15	6	-	-
CE-525B Citation CJ3+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	23	25
CE-525C Citation CJ4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	19	48	44	33	28	33	29
CE-550 Citation Bravo	31	25	21	18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CE-560 Citation Encore	21	24	13	12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CE-560 Citation Encore+	-	-	-	-	23	28	5	5	4	-	-	-	-	-
CE-560 Citation Excel	48	23	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CE-560 Citation XLS	-	32	64	73	82	72	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CE-560 Citation XLS+	-	-	-	-	-	8	37	22	27	31	31	22	21	19
CE-680 Citation Sovereign	-	9	46	57	65	77	33	16	19	22	5	-	-	-
CE-680 Citation Sovereign+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	8	28	18	11
CE-680A Citation Latitude	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	16	42
CE-750 Citation X	18	15	14	12	17	16	7	3	3	6	-	-	-	-
CE-750 Citation X+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9	6	4
Total Number of Airplanes	518	592	750	887	1,137	1,317	874	767	696	672	678	722	718	661
% Change	-23.4%	14.3%	26.7%	18.3%	28.2%	15.8%	-33.6%	-12.2%	-9.3%	-3.4%	0.9%	6.5%	-0.6%	-7.9%
Total Billings for Airplanes (\$M)	8,616	10,404	13,161	16,555	19,347	21,948	17,443	18,000	17,235	17,108	21,058	22,015	21,877	18,353
% Change	-17.4%	20.7%	26.5%	25.8%	16.9%	13.4%	-20.5%	3.2%	-4.2%	-0.7%	23.1%	4.5%	-0.6%	-16.1%

Table 7.9 (continuation) Source: 2016 General Aviation Statistical Databook & 2017 Industry Outlook, GAMA

The latest data from the GAMA shows that there was a slight increase in business jet deliveries in the third quarter of 2017 when compared to the same period 2016. Overall the industry delivered 138 aircraft in the third quarter 2017 (137 in the same period in 2016).

Figure 7.77 Source: GAMA

Highlights during the quarter (Figure 7.77) include the continuing success of the Challenger 350 (13 deliveries) and the Citation Latitude (also 13 deliveries). At the smaller end of the scale, the Citation M2 just reached double digit deliveries for the first time this so far in 2017. The light jet delivery contest won Embraer with nine Phenom 300s versus the six HondaJets. In large cabin business jet sector, Gulfstream continued its dominance with a mixture of 21 G450s, G550s and G650s delivered.

Overall, despite the lower quarter on quarter numbers, deliveries for the first nine months are up by 1.4%.

Two new aircraft:

- Gulfstream was able to deliver a single G500 into its demonstration team (however this will now take place in the first quarter of 2018),
- Pilatus Aircraft delivered the first Pilatus PC-24, but the certification for the type is on-track, with the first customer aircraft for US fractional operator PlaneSense almost completed.

T7.4.3 Market Forecast

According to **Bombardier Business Aircraft Market Forecast 2016-2025** in 2015, the business jet industry was stable, having been supported by the developed economies. As the emerging economies return to strong growth levels during 2016 to 2017, world GDP were forecasted to reach 3% growth, translating into higher order intake and stronger business aviation activity.

Bombardier Business Aircraft (Table 7.11) forecasts 8,300 new business jet deliveries (representing \$250 billion USD in industry revenues) from 2016 to 2025 in the Light, Medium and Large aircraft segments.

Business jets in region	Fleet in 2015	Deliveries	Retirements	Fleet in 2025
North America	10 355	3 930	1 390	12 895
Europe	1 435	1 530	130	2 835
Latin America	2 015	790	305	2 500
Greater China	405	700	10	1 095
CIS	595	400	15	980
Middle East	410	350	30	730
Asia Pacific	435	200	50	585
South Asia	155	200	10	345
Africa	380	200	60	520
	16 185	8 300		22 485

Table 7.10 Source: Bombardier Business Aircraft Market Forecast 2016-2025

North America, Europe, Latin America and Greater China will be the largest markets for business aircraft over the next 10 years

Figure 7.78 Source: Bombardier Business Aircraft Market Forecast 2016-2025

North America (Figure 7.79) will account for greatest number of new business jet deliveries between 2016 and 2025 with 3,930 aircraft. Europe remains the second largest market with 1,530 deliveries between 2016 and 2025.

According to *Honeywell's Global Business Aviation Outlook*, released on 8th October 2017, global economic and political uncertainty, combined with low commodity prices and stiff competition from the used-jet market, will restrain new aircraft deliveries. Mr. Ben Driggs, President Aftermarket Sales, Americas, Honeywell Aerospace, said "*Declining used aircraft prices, continued low commodity prices, and economic and political uncertainties in many business jet markets remain as near-term concerns for new jet purchases*". He also pointed "*(...) there are several new and exciting aircraft models coming to market which will drive solid growth in new business jet purchases in the midterm and long term.*"

Honeywell estimates up to 8,300 new business jet deliveries (valued at \$249 billion) will take place in the next 10 years.

Other highlights of the report estimated:

- Large-cabin airplanes will account for about 57% of new business jet deliveries and 85% of revenue in the next five years;

- Russia, India, and China have seen a significant drop in demand for new business jets, while Brazil is a "bright spot";
- Asia, as a whole, has seen a significant drop in business jet demand due to increasing regional tensions;
- The Middle East and Africa forecast for new sales is down, due to low oil prices;
- Europe saw an 11% decline in new business jet purchases in 2017 compared to the previous year due to sluggish economic growth, concern about Brexit, and political turmoil;
- North America, which accounts for 61% of global demand for new business jets, is expected to see a 9% reduction in new business jet purchases to roughly the same levels as 2014 and 2015;
- In the used-jet market, asking prices declined about 7% this year and are still falling. Used jet inventory has dropped, but sales remain soft.

"We expect roughly similar delivery levels in 2018 compared with 2017," Mr. Ben Driggs said.

KEY TOPIC T7.5 HELICOPTERS AND LONG-HAUL OPERATION

T7.5.1 Current Utility of Helicopters

The smaller the size of the helicopter, the smaller the fuel tank, and naturally the reduced distance it can travel. For those serious about owning a helicopter and integrating this method of travel into their day to day planning, it's essential to not have to think about fuel stops every hundred or so miles.

A typical mid-range design will be able to fly for 2.5 hours at 135 knots, for 300-350 miles (500/560 Km) without refuelling. To put that into perspective, that kind of speed and fuel efficiency will get you from London to Paris in 90 minutes. A larger model, like the Sikorsky S92 can seat up to 16 people and reach 160 mph for over 600 miles.

Just like planes, helicopters must abide by a similar set of rules laid out by the Civil Aviation Authority, also bad weather can result in blanket bans on helicopter flights if the conditions are deemed too unsafe. Even the best-outfitted helicopters have their access restricted when conditions are at their worst.

T7.5.2 Technological Evolution

Helicopters were once billed as an alternative to fixed-wing aircraft, especially as a short-haul airliner; but noise, vibration and fuel-efficiency got in the way.

When helicopters first appeared in our skies in the 1950s, they were touted as the transport of the future; an aircraft which could take off and land in a car park or the roof of a building and fly us high above our traffic-clogged streets.

Congested roads and airways would be a thing of the past, the thinking went. Fleets of helicopters could whisk us safely and efficiently to our destinations. But helicopters proved to

have their drawbacks. They are much less fuel-efficient than planes. They are noisy, and vibrations make them uncomfortable to travel in.

In the meantime, fixed-wing aircraft won out. Conventional planes can carry larger loads faster and further than helicopters, and in more comfort for passengers. But they require long runways and therefore, bigger airports.

At London's Heathrow, for instance, a plane uses the runway every 30 seconds or so. Airports like these are bad neighbours; noisy and polluting and have to be situated some way outside city centres, adding to travel time. And we need more and more of them.

If helicopters can be re-designed, then they might provide an alternative, cutting congestion and opening the skies to us all.

Nowadays, NASA designers are using tilt-rotor technology to design a machine that will carry around 90 passengers and travel 1,000 miles (1,600km).

The Large Civil Tilt Rotor (LCTR) looks like a plane, but with two huge rotors at the end of each wing instead of small propellers. For take-off and landing those rotors are parallel to the ground just as in a helicopter. Then during flight, they swivel forwards to act like huge propellers. The LCTR is designed to work using existing infrastructure. That means it could use airports, but not clog up runways. Short and medium-length trips could be taken on a tilt-rotor, leaving just the long-haul flights using large fixed-wing aircraft.

The Agusta tiltrotor demonstrates at a smaller scale the technology of the larger V-22 developed to the military.

Another major drawback of helicopters has been their speed, or rather lack of it. Compared to fixed wing aircraft, helicopters are the snails of the sky.

The limit for a conventional helicopter, big rotor on top, small rotor at the back, is somewhere in the region of 170-190 knots (315-350km/h or 185 to 220 mph). The LCTR is designed to fly at 300 knots (555 km/h), which is a significant increase in speed. New technologies and designs will increase speeds above 400Km/h that have already been demonstrated.

The way conventional helicopters are built makes it almost impossible for them to fly very fast. Their spinning blades slice through the air and work like the wings of a plane, generating lift. Unlike wings, however, the blades don't provide equal lift on both sides. As a blade on one side moves forward, a blade on the other side is moving backwards. When a helicopter starts to speed up, this difference becomes more serious. Air passing over the blade moving in the same direction as the helicopter travels faster than it does over the opposite blade. It is a problem known as retreating blade stall

But with radical redesign, helicopters are capable of being speed demons. Sikorsky, a helicopter maker based in Florida, held the record for the fastest helicopter flight, until recently beaten by Airbus. Its X2 concept flew at over 250 knots (460 km/h) in 2010. The X2 uses two counter-rotating rotors, meaning two rotors stacked on top of each other, spinning in opposite directions. That means there is an equal amount of lift being generated on each side.

Another advantage of the design is that engineers can remove the tail rotor, which is needed to stop the helicopter spinning around. That gave them extra room for a propeller at the back. Other helicopter's configurations can provide similar performance.

Advances in computing and 'fly-by-wire' flight systems have made the craft much easier to fly, and the proof of the design is in the world speed record. The double rotors mean no retreating blade stall, and a much smoother and quieter ride. Now the team is working on a next generation helicopter incorporating the technology, in order to get safety, efficiency and comfort.

T7.5.2.1 Kind of Helicopters

- Civil helicopters (Figure 7.79). They are designed to fly safely in all types of situations at the lowest possible cost. From single- and twin-engine light and medium rotorcraft, to those in the eleven-ton-class.

Figure 7.79 – Civil helicopters (H125, H130, H175)
Source: Various manufactures

- Military helicopters (Figure 7.80). They are for transport, armed scout, utility, attack, combat rescue, naval, maritime and special operations.

Figure 7.80 Military helicopters (H145M (Airbus), AS565 MBe (Airbus))
Source: Various manufactures

- Corporative helicopters (Figure 7.81). The Dedicated Private and Business Aviation Helicopter.

Figure 7.81 - Military helicopters (H145 (ACH), (ACH) Latest model)
Source: Various manufactures

T7.5.2.2 Helicopters in The Future

The conventional design of a helicopter is based on the use of a main rotor motor for the lift and a tail rudder, on which an anti-torque rotor works that prevents it from turning on itself. Although the advantages of vertical take-off and landing are obvious, this design limits the maximum speed, since above 160-170 knots blades become unstable and stall. This is due to the difference in lift of the blade that advances against that is trailing and the high speed that is reached at the tip of the blade.

There are several helicopter types in service with coaxial rotors, or interlaced rotors, which do not use the anti-torque rotor because the main doubles cancel their own torque.

Another approach is the tilt-rotor V-22 Osprey convertiplane developed by Bell and Boeing, which is an example of the combination of a helicopter and an airplane, which is what the military seeks.

It offers the capacity of landing and vertical take-off of one and the high speed of the other, being its main characteristic that the wings of which have at the ends two engines that tilt along with the rotors, which vertically allow to take off and land like a helicopter, but in horizontal they act like those of a conventional plane.

Sikorsky helicopters are used by the five branches of the Armed Forces of the United States, as well as by international armed forces and commercial companies in 40 nations), launched the development of a tactical helicopter prototype, called S-97 that subsequently made real. It consists of a combination of cutting-edge technologies, as it employs a one-piece fuselage made of composite materials, fly-by-wire control system and active systems for vibration reduction. The first one of fly-by-wire is a helicopter made by the European multinational NH90.

The configuration is of cabin with two seats side by side and identical command posts; it also has a compartment to accommodate up to six soldiers, weapons and fuel.

Figure 7.82 Military helicopters (S-97 "Skyrider")

Source: Various manufactures

The features are the following: cruising speed of 405 km / h, maximum of 440 and a service ceiling of 3,000 m. In addition to greater speed, the composite rotor configuration provides greater manoeuvrability and autonomy and allows to reduce the turning radius. A particular characteristic is that the tail propeller can be used to brake the device, by generating thrust in the opposite direction to the gear.

The "Skyrider" (Figure 7.83) has an estimated cost of 15 million dollars per unit.

These models have been improved and for the future a parallel model to the American one is proposed, called Advanced Concept Engine (ACE), according to which the options are evaluated to develop a new high-performance engine, which can be installed in both the current helicopters as in those that emerged from the Future Vertical Lift (FVL) program. It is estimated that this program will be ready by 2035. Participating companies include GE Aviation and ATEC formed by Honeywell and Pratt & Whitney.

In Europe Airbus helicopter and Agusta have high-speed helicopter concept as advanced as the United States, and the main European helicopter engine supplier, the former Turbomeca now part of Safran delivers equally competitive turboshafts.

KEY TOPIC T7.6 HELICOPTERS AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

In comparison to studies concerning airplanes less references concerning the impact of helicopters on environment are available. Therefore, the gas emissions due to helicopter operation is even more difficult to assess than for airplanes. A methodology to define a metric for assessing the gas emitted by the helicopters in operation has been proposed by Eurocopter [7]. In particular, the metric is obtained on the basis of the consumed fuel volume, or mass of emitted CO₂ reproducing the specificity of rotorcraft operational aspects. It is quite evident that the helicopter traffic is only a few percent of the entire air transportation and hence also the correspondent contribution is a very small fraction (about 1%) of the global CO₂ emission associated to air transport.

The CO₂ emission rate is not published by engine suppliers nor by helicopters manufacturers. Moreover, due to peculiar capability to hover of the helicopters as required in rescue or medical missions, the fuel consumption cannot be obtained from the average consumed fuel per km and travelled distance. In addition, the fuel consumption may depend on the atmospheric conditions. Therefore, a metric dependent on hourly consumed fuel is more appropriate than the evaluation based on kilometric fuel consumption. Such dependence is illustrated in Figure 7.84 where the hourly fuel consumption at take-off under three different atmospheric conditions (See Level International Standard Atmosphere, SL ISA+20, 1500m ISA+20) is presented for four types of helicopters: one Light Single motor (like for example, AIRBUS H130, BELL 505, ENSTROM 280FX, LEONARDO SW 4, ROBINSON R44 II, ...), one Light Twins (like AGUSTA WESTLAND AW 109, AIRBUS H135, EUROCOPTER EC 135, ...) one Medium Twins (like AIRBUS H160, Bell 214ST, EUROCOPTER AS332, SIKORSKY S76 C++, ...) and one Heavy Twins helicopter (like AIRBUS H225, BOEING CH47, EUROCOPTER EC 225, SIKORSKY H92, ...).

The results are represented with respect to those concerning the helicopter with Light Single engine. It can be observed that the consumed fuel does not exhibit appreciable variability with weather conditions. Moreover, as it concerns the consumed fuel, the medium twins require 1.5 times the amount of fuel of a light single motor helicopter, whereas the heavy twins exhibit a consumption figure of about 3.5 times that of the reference single motor.

Figure 7.83

Source F. Verlut ; N. Dyrła, N., 2010, "Definition by Eurocopter of a green metric to assess gas emitted by helicopters in operation", DSpace - Digital Repository, <https://dspace-erf.nlr.nl/xmlui/browse?value=Verlut%2C+F.&type=author>

In order to evaluate the consumption a typical profile in terms of time percentages spent for each phase of the helicopter mission has been defined. The considered phases include the specific characteristics of a helicopter i.e. the hover phase, the Best Endurance Speed (V_{be}), characterizing the observation ability from above and a forward flight condition at given speed. In particular, in order to have a greater uniformity between different helicopter types a speed of 120 knots (about 220 km/h) is considered. In Figure 7.85 the results concerning different time distribution for four types of helicopters (Light Single, Light Twins, Medium

Twins, and Heavy Twins) is depicted. The average fuel consumption has been computed taking into account varying distribution of the different phases.

As can be evidenced by the results shown in Figure 7.85 the different mission profile does not influence significantly the fuel consumption for all helicopter type.

In order to fix a metric to compare helicopter consumption the counter-part of transported persons adopted for aircraft should be chosen. By considering that helicopters may transport both persons or loads, a valid solution can be the fuel consumed divided by the useful load, so that the metric is expressed in terms of kilogram fuel per hour per kilogram of useful load. In particular, the following expression is adopted for useful load, UL:

$$UL = \text{Min} (MTOW - EW - \text{Pilot}; MTOW - mAGW)$$

where:

- MTOW is the Maximum Take-Off Weight given in the flight manual;
- EW is the Empty Weight standard given mostly in the Tech Data;
- mAGW is the Minimum Approved Gross Weight given in the flight manual.

Figure 7.84

Source F. Verlut ; N. Dyrła, N., 2010, "Definition by Eurocopter of a green metric to assess gas emitted by helicopters in operation", DSpace - Digital Repository, [https://dspace-erf.nlr.nl/xmlui/browse?value=Verlut%2C+F.&type=author](https://dspace.erf.nlr.nl/xmlui/browse?value=Verlut%2C+F.&type=author)

An emissions scale can be defined to rank current and future helicopters. In particular, helicopter emissions are classified with a letter on a scale from A+, which represents long-term high efficiency objectives (according to ACARE and Clean Sky goals), to E (less efficient models). The proposed scale is shown in Figure 7.86. The second column of the Table represents the fuel consumption, the third column shows the emitted CO2.

	Green Metric (kg fuel / h / 100kg UL)	Green Metric (kg CO ₂ / h / 100kg UL), <i>approximate</i>
A+	≤ 9	≤ 28
A]9; 12]]28; 37]
B]12; 15]]37; 47]
C]15; 18]]47; 56]
D]18; 21]]56; 65]
E	> 21	> 65

Figure 7.85 Classification of helicopters on the basis of emissions

Source F. Verlut ; N. Dyrła, N., 2010, "Definition by Eurocopter of a green metric to assess gas emitted by helicopters in operation", DSpace - Digital Repository, <https://dspace-erf.nlr.nl/xmlui/browse?value=Verlut%2C+F.&type=author>

Chapter 8 – Emerging Aviation Technologies

Aeronautics is a leader in the introduction of new technologies in many sectors, with 'spin-offs' to other industries, both transport (cars, ships, trains) and consumer (electronics, services, etc.). The aerodynamic shapes, strong and lightweight structures and other technologies pioneered in aeronautics find applications in cars, high-speed trains and other vehicles. Aeronautics was the pioneer in anti-skid braking systems (ABS) and head-up displays (HUDs) long before their use in cars. The first microcircuits appeared in rugged, light and small computers in ballistic missiles at a time when similar computing power required a large air-conditioned room. The example of microelectronics shows how the widespread adoption of a technology turned aeronautics into a relatively small user facing obsolescence issues. Satellite navigation demonstrates the special needs of aeronautics compared with a wide range of other users. The inverse process of 'spin-in' from other sectors into aeronautics is as important as the direct process of 'spin-off'; specific technologies developed in other sectors can contribute to sustain the relentless progress in aeronautics, which is the main driver for the renewal of aircraft fleets. For example, the capital investment in a new airliner can only be recovered if there is a gain efficiency of at least 10% relative to a preceding generation; in other sectors of aeronautics gains in various measures of performance, new capabilities and improved availability and operability are decisive factors for fleet renewal.

8.1 Electric and Conventional Propulsion

Electric propulsion can take several forms, including solar powered aircraft (8.1.1), battery or fuel-cell driven propulsion (8.1.2) and the use of gas turbines as generators of electricity (8.1.3). Electric propulsion is currently more effective for small vehicles, with light payloads like miniature sensors; long-range transportation of a large number of passengers or heavy cargo will rely for some time to come on conventional propulsion (4.1.4) that still has a considerable development potential on its own and as part of hybrid systems.

8.1.1 Solar Powered Aircraft

Solar powered aircraft offer the ultimate promise of environmentally clean operation for long periods of days, months or years as long as the on-board equipment does not fail. They raise the prospect of an alternative to satellites, operating at an altitude of about 20 km above cloud cover, well below the satellite orbits above 200 km. They could loiter in a desired geographical region as an alternative to geostationary satellites 36 000 km above the earth. The closer distance of solar powered aircraft to receivers and users on the ground compared with satellites would enable lower emission power and less atmospheric signal degradation by staying below the ionosphere. All this promise is an incentive to face the considerable challenges of implementation.

The power of solar radiation is 1.4 kW/m^2 at the top of the earth atmosphere, possibly reduced at the surface by cloud cover and other atmospheric effects; it is also reduced by the angle of incidence. Thus, a propulsive power of 2 MW will require a wing area of at least 140 m^2 covered with solar panels assuming the ideal conditions of orthogonal incidence without cloud cover

and 100 % energy conversion efficiency. Electric motors can have an efficiency of more than 92 % and distributed propulsion with many small motors along the span is also aerodynamically efficient in accelerating the flow and generating lift over all sections of the wing. A slender wing with large aspect ratio of span to chord also reduces drag making the most of the limited propulsive power available.

Some of the solar energy collected during daylight must be stored in batteries to enable continued flying at night. Batteries have relatively low power to weight ratio. The weight of batteries and electric motors adds to the total weight of a solar powered aircraft that is minimized using a light weight structure; for a wing with large span this may entail some structural flexibility and vulnerability to aero-elastic effects. The solar powered aircraft fly above cloud cover at an altitude of about 20 km, and the limited power available typically restricts speeds to a range of 40 to 120 km/h. Stratospheric winds easily reach speeds of 100-200 km/h.

The solar powered aircraft acting as a transmission or relay station over a limited geographical area must fly in a racetrack pattern, with upwind, side wind and downwind legs. A strong stratospheric wind of 200 km/h for a solar powered aircraft flying at 100 km/h implies along the racetrack: (i) a relative headwind 300 km/h that may overcome the strength of a lightweight structure; (ii) a relative tailwind of minus 100 km/h that could stall the aircraft; (iii) a sidewind that could cause considerable drift from the intended trajectory. Also, large aerodynamic forces on a light weight structure can result in coupled motions difficult to control or even catastrophic oscillations.

Solar powered aircraft may be limited to not too unfavourable atmospheric conditions even at the high loitering altitude of about 20 km above cloud cover in low density air. The transit from the earth to loiter altitude and the flight back to base imply crossing denser layers of the atmosphere with possible cloud cover. The limited power available may imply a slow climb to loiter altitude, and the limited structural strength may limit dive speed in descent. The flight endurance based on the battery power available, typically half a day, will limit the time of flight under cloud cover. Atmospheric storms in the denser air at lower altitudes may subject the structure to excessive loads.

In combination all the preceding factors imply that the operation of solar powered aircraft requires careful consideration of atmospheric conditions, to the extent that they can be predicted. The achievement of round the globe flight by a solar powered aircraft is proof that success is possible. On the other hand, a sequence of hops over a period of months with long intervals at the most favourable atmospheric conditions is very different from all-weather round-the-clock operation to rival satellites. The weight and speed limitations do not prevent solar powered aircraft from being effective platforms for lightweight sensors. The transportation of larger loads over longer distances at higher speeds leads to power requirements that can be satisfied by other options.

8.1.2 Battery-Powered Aircraft

One of the main limiting factors in the design of solar powered aircraft is the low power-to-weight ratio of batteries that also affects other forms of transport. It will improve gradually

over the years with the efforts directed at applications such as electric cars; since the operation of batteries depends on electro-chemical effects very large improvements over a short time like in electronics cannot be expected. Progress in batteries is linked to materials and will benefit many sectors like consumer appliances.

The use of batteries is most effective in aircraft for low weight, small payload and limited endurance and speed. For a small drone with lightweight sensors electric propulsion based on batteries or fuel cells is an attractive near silent option. For light planes battery power allows training flights lasting a fraction of an hour but is limited in endurance as a means of transport over longer distances. The Airbus and other developments show that a vertical take-off and landing electrically powered taxi is feasible. For larger transport aircraft other sources of electric power are needed, such as gas turbines.

8.1.3 Turbine-Driven Electric Propulsion

The power-to-weight ratio of lithium-ion batteries is currently up to 250 Wh per kg, or 4 kg per kW. For a large airliner needing 60 MW power for propulsion this would mean a prohibitive 240 tons weight of the battery pack. For long-range high-speed aircraft carrying hundreds of passengers or tens of tons of cargo the gas turbine remains the power source of choice; it can drive an electric generator providing power to distributed electric motors with high power conversion efficiency and good aerodynamic efficiency. The main issue then becomes one of transmission of tens of MW of power in an aircraft from the electric generator driven by the gas turbine to the electric motors distributed over the span of the wing (and possibly elsewhere).

Tens of megawatts of electrical power translate to currents of thousands of amperes at thousands of volts. The very high voltages require special equipment and can pose challenges of electromagnetic interference and electrical discharges. Very large currents over normal conductors lead to high dissipation by the Joule effect, hence significant power losses; these power losses take the form of heat that is difficult to dissipate in an aircraft. The electric power transmission without electric resistance has been demonstrated by superconductors operating at very low temperatures close to absolute zero. Creating such cryogenic conditions is known for mostly for rockets rather than aircraft. Room temperature superconductors have been demonstrated on a limited scale.

The prospects for an Airbus or Boeing type electric transport aircraft could thus be summarized as: (i) gas turbine(s) driving electric generator(s) feeding distributed electric propulsion; (ii) power transmission via superconductors with zero electric resistance and dissipation. While this is a somewhat distant prospect, progress in the electrification of aircraft will continue, with the attraction of replacing multiple systems (hydraulic, pneumatic, etc.) by a single electric architecture. The installed power of the order of 2 MW in the Boeing 787 and Airbus A350 matches the next Airbus electrical experimental aircraft: a British Aerospace 146 regional jet airliner with one of the four engines replaced by a 2 MW hybrid propulsion unit.

8.1.4 Developments in Conventional Propulsion

Conventional propulsion still has a bright future on its own and as part of hybrid systems as a mean to power long-range large-payload high-speed aircraft with plenty of development

potential ahead. The Safran road map for conventional aircraft propulsion shows that the development potential is far from exhausted. Taking as baseline in 2016 the LEAP turbofan engine with a by-pass ratio (BPR) of 11, by 2025-2030 ultra-high-by-pass-ratio (UHBPR) of 15 could lead to a reduction of specific fuel consumption (SFC) of 5-10% compatible with noise reduction. By 2030-2035 a BPR of 30 can be achieved with a counter-rotating open rotor bringing a reduction of specific fuel consumption (SFC) of 15%; by choosing blade numbers and other design choices the ultra-high by-pass-ratio (UHBPR) open rotor could meet current noise standards but could struggle against stricter rules foreseeable in the future. The boundary layer ingestion configuration around 2040-2045 would reduce the SFC by 25%, assuming inlet flow distortion problems are solved; the evolution towards buried engines would bring major engine noise reduction, possibly below aerodynamic noise. Reducing the latter too could achieve the ultimate aim of an aircraft inaudible outside the airport perimeter. This desirable environmental feature could be preserved in a subsequent hybrid propulsion system, with buried turbine(s) driving electrical generator(s) and small distributed electric motors. Some propulsion components have been among the first aeronautical applications of additive manufacturing (section 8.2).

8.2 Additive Manufacturing

Additive manufacturing has several attractive features: (i) since it consists of adding layers it does not waste material, unlike such processes like milling that carve a part out of a larger block; (ii) it allows the manufacture of large complex specimens that would otherwise have to be built-up of smaller parts with junctions. At present additive manufacturing also has limitations: (i) it is a slow process more suited to laboratory use or limited production of prototypes than to large scale high-rate serial industry; (ii) the surface smoothness is dependent on the number of layers that cannot be excessive, thereby requiring subsequent operations to ensure a better finish. If the limitations of additive manufacturing can be overcome there are promising prospects: (i) producing parts locally and as needed instead of transporting them from large stocks in a warehouse; (ii) coupled with digital imaging and sensing producing replicas and replacements for damaged parts already out-of-stock or unavailable. These features will become more useful as widens the range of materials suitable for additive manufacturing and their physical properties. Additive manufacturing is one of the contributors to more efficient production (section 8.3).

8.3 Efficient Production

Industrial sectors like automotive have taken the lead in efficient production relative to aeronautics due to a combination of factors including: (i) much higher production rates (tens of thousands instead of tens) per month justify a larger investment in automation; (ii) less long-lead production items allow short start-to-finish production cycles (hours instead of months); (iii) smaller numbers of simpler parts with less stringent quality standards facilitate higher throughput. There are also counter-factors that favour aeronautics: (i) higher added value justifies bigger investments in quality and efficiency; (ii) large order backlogs if they are achieved give a measure of long-term stability. Some of the key concepts of efficient production read across production volume, value and rate and include: (i) just-in-time delivery avoiding large and costly static inventories; (ii) work planning that maximizes human

motivation and efficiency; (iii) the right mix of automation and human intervention. The more complex world of aeronautics compared with other sectors provides opportunities for cross-fertilization in new technologies and their efficient utilization and management.

The next stage in the evolution towards efficient production is known as “4.0” and in a topic of major interest (Key Topic T8.1).

KEY TOPIC T8.1 EFFICIENT PRODUCTION 4.0

T8.1.1 Introduction

Based on the increase and advance of digitalization within the factories, the conjunction of internet and oriented technologies in the area of “smart” machines and sensors, another new and essential industrial revolution named Industry 4.0 has been born. The term *Industry 4.0* refers to the combination of several major innovations in digital technology, all coming to maturity right now, all poised to transform the energy and manufacturing sectors. These technologies include advanced robotics and artificial intelligence; sophisticated sensors; cloud computing; the Internet of Things; data capture and analytics; digital fabrication (including 3D printing); software-as-a-service and other new marketing models. Advanced digital technology is already used in manufacturing, but with Industry 4.0, it will transform production. It will lead to greater efficiencies and change traditional production relationships among suppliers, producers, and customers - as well as between human and machine. Nine technology trends form the building blocks of Industry 4.0. (Figure 8.1).

Figure 8.1 - Nine foundational technology advances powering transformation Industry 4.0

T8.1.2 Nine Technologies Transforming Industrial Production

T8.1.2.1 Big Data and Analytics

Analytics based on large data sets where it optimizes production quality, saves energy, and improves equipment service. In an Industry 4.0 context, the collection and comprehensive evaluation of data from many different sources - production equipment and systems as well as enterprise - and customer - management systems - will become standard to support real-time decision making.

Big data arose due to the emergence of three major trends. First, it has become economical to generate a broad kind of data, due to inexpensive storage, sensors, smart devices, social software, multiplayer games, and the Internet of Things. Second, it has become inexpensive to process huge amounts of data, due to progresses in multicore CPUs, solid state storage, cloud computing, and open source software. Thirdly, not just database administrators and developers, but many more people (such as decision makers, domain scientists, application users, journalists, and ordinary consumers) have become involved in the process of generating, processing, and consuming data.

Currently the aviation industry adopts on Condition/Preventive maintenance procedures due to its operational efficiency and it depends upon the failure mode calculations made after testing a part under circumstances. These conditions may fluctuate depending on the external factors/human errors which may result in the variation in the life time of components in turn reducing the operational efficiency of the aircraft.

A study by FAA states that during a year jet engine generates data equivalent to 20TB. Basically, most of this data is not used for any of the analytics purpose since this data is unstructured. Big data analytics can be used to predict the fault in the component by analysing data obtained from various sensors and account of the specific component attached to an aircraft or fleet in which it is present.

Commercial airline manufacturers are extending their digital products in a range of ways. A typical aircraft has millions of parts. The amount of data output is immense and is increasing rapidly with a new generation of aircraft. Legacy aircraft used to capture 125+ flight parameters. The Airbus A320, for example, produces 20,000 data parameters but the latest A350 has 400,000 and a data output of some 250GB per flight. Boeing 787 captures more than 1000 flight parameters with some reports claiming half a terabyte of data per flight. This explains the big data explosion in aviation. This data is being used to improve flight operations, safety and efficiency, enhance the passenger experience and deliver better predictive and customised maintenance.

Apart from flight data, a large amount of data gets generated in repair shops, inventory systems and by various regulatory organizations as well. Analysing such big data can help in improving flight safety, reducing operational delay, better inventory management of spares, predictive maintenance of various equipment on board, improving fuel economy of the fleet etc. Honeywell Aerospace has been a pioneer in providing flight data solutions for predictive maintenance of parts through its tools and data sources like PTMD (Predictive Trend

Monitoring and Diagnostics). Its focus is to leverage latest tools and technologies in big data analytics space to improve these predictive maintenance offerings. Using big data and analytics infrastructure, Honeywell Aerospace have enabled analysis of large data from ACMS (Aircraft condition monitoring systems) and various repair databases and found outliers and hidden trends in the data.

T8.1.2.2 Autonomous Robots

Manufacturers in many industries have long used robots to tackle complex assignments, but robots are evolving for even greater utility. They are becoming more autonomous, flexible, and cooperative. Eventually, they will interact with one another and work safely side by side with humans and learn from them. These robots will cost less and have a greater range of capabilities than those used in manufacturing today.

Robots improve the productivity favouring the savings on production and eliminating problems of lack of qualified manpower. Robots improve the quality of work by taking over dangerous, tedious and dirty jobs that are not possible or safe for humans to perform. The high performance, low investment cost and most of all the adaptability of robots makes them the perfect choice for an efficient and easy automation solution. In this way, special software developed for robotics helps to improve the repeatability and the accuracy of robots' positioning. This feature contributes to meet the requirements of manufacturing aviation. Due to be known as very conservative, the aerospace industry usually uses successful assembly methods that have already been proven to work in the past. But, in the past couple of years, the general attitude, in terms of assembly tasks, has really started to change in the aerospace industry. Aircraft manufacturers tend to use robotics on some manufacturing applications to perform tasks that require precision and rigidity on big parts. Investments with robots on aircraft manufacturing can be beneficial when the payback is feasible.

For example, KUKA, European manufacturer of robotic equipment, offers autonomous robots that interact with one another. These robots are interconnected so that they can work together and automatically adjust their actions to fit the next unfinished product in line. High-end sensors and control units enable close collaboration with humans. Similarly, industrial-robot supplier ABB is launching a two-armed robot called YuMi that is specifically designed to assemble products (such as consumer electronics) alongside humans. Two padded arms and computer vision allow for safe interaction and parts recognition.

Boeing was an early adopter of robots for painting aircraft and has facilities around the globe that deploy drilling and fastening robots on its aircraft assembly lines.

Boeing worked closely with KUKA Systems to develop an advanced automated manufacturing process for its wide-body commercial airliners. Called Fuselage Automated Upright Build (FAUB), the robotic production line assembles the forward and aft fuselage sections of the Boeing 777 jetliner. Several aspects of this robotic assembly line make it unique.

Traditionally, the riveting process is done manually with mechanics positioned on both sides of the fuselage, performing repetitive movements that place considerable strain and impact stress on their shoulders, arms and hands. In a costly and time-consuming process, the massive

fuselage must be rotated so mechanics can ergonomically access the riveting locations. In the FAUB workspace, the fuselage remains “upright” throughout the entire build. Because unlike humans, robots can work at any angle.

According to Boeing, the process also simplifies the build by using determinant assembly (part-to-part indexing) for panel and floor indexing. Determinant assembly provides for a quicker process by using features of the parts, such as drilled holes, to quickly align components without requiring additional tooling or fixtures.

Workers begin the build by loading and assembling the floor beams and frames, and then synchronous robots work on the fuselage panels, both longitudinal and circumferential splices. Working from both sides of the fuselage, KUKA robots work in pairs to concurrently drill and countersink holes, insert fasteners, and complete the riveting.

KUKA Systems also developed the multifunctional end effector for the robot, which clamps the different material layers that make up the fuselage, and then drills, fills and bucks – all with one end-of-arm tool.

The FAUB production line is in residence at Boeing’s mammoth factory in Everett, Washington. The aircraft manufacturer is currently using the process at a low rate of initial production. When at full rate, several pairs of KUKA robots will work in tandem installing approximately 50,000 fasteners per fuselage.

According to Boeing, the first 777 assembled with the FAUB process was delivered in December 2015. The robotic assembly system will be drilling, filling, and bucking the fuselages of the new Boeing 777X aircraft when it enters production in 2017. With FAUB, fuselage sections will be built using automated, guided robots that will fasten the panels of the fuselage together, drilling and filling the more than approximately 60,000 fasteners that until today were installed by hand.

Boeing reports that the new automated process helps with areas that cause the greatest ergonomic issues, but expects that other residual benefits will follow, including quality, cost and flow. Quantifiable performance metrics will be made public when production reaches full rate, which is anticipated at 2018.

Composite materials have been integral to the aviation industry for some time now. Coveted for their structural strength and lighter weight compared to metallic materials, composites contribute to better fuel efficiency and reduced airplane emissions. AFP (automated fibre placement) processes use computer-guided robotics to lay up one or several layers, called tows, of carbon-fibre tape onto a mould to create a composite aerostructure.

The aerostructures manufacturer currently uses custom automation, or large gantry systems with multi-axis heads, for AFP processes on composite parts for the Airbus A350 XWB and Boeing 787 jetliners. But the use of robots for AFP is an area of interest.

To fabricate the composite parts of the giant wings of Boeing’s 777X, Mukilteo-based engineering firm Electroimpact has designed and built a new generation of robotic machines

that haven't been previously shown to outsiders. Those are 30-foot-tall, 3-D printers, each costing tens of millions of dollars.

Precisely placing layer upon layer of carbon-fibre strips infused with epoxy resin, one of these AFP machines builds up the 777X's composite wing skin, producing single piece 110 feet long and 20 feet across at the widest end near the fuselage.

Using these technologies of Making the skins and spars of such a giant wing in single full-length pieces is new. It should reduce the cost of manufacturing and save some weight because there are no joins.

Using a wholly different method, the composite wing spar of the 787 is made in three sections by Mitsubishi Heavy Industries in Japan. In the U.K., Airbus supplier GKN uses AFP machines to fabricate the spars of the A350 wing, also in three sections.

T8.1.2.3 Simulations

In the engineering phase, 3-D simulations of products, materials, and production processes are already used, but in the future, simulations will be used more extensively in plant operations as well. These simulations will leverage real-time data to mirror the physical world in a virtual model, which can include machines, products, and humans. This allows operators to test and optimize the machine settings for the next product in line in the virtual world before the physical changeover, thereby driving down machine setup times and increasing quality.

For example, Siemens and a German machine-tool vendor developed a virtual machine that can simulate the machining of parts using data from the physical machine. This lowers the setup time for the actual machining process by as much as 80 percent.

Increasingly, simulations have been used in industrial operations, from the engineering phase, products' modelling and definitions of materials and production processes. Simulations compare on real time data the physical world with a virtual model, which includes machines, products and people. This allows operators to test and optimize the machine settings for the next product on production in a virtual environment before changing to the physical condition, thus reducing the down time of machine setup and increasing the quality of the products. It consists in a virtual integration on production shop floor, including equipment, products, planning, data and efficiency of operation. Digital manufacturing is also used to detect fails and interruptions of the production in order to reduce downtime, based on a virtual machine that can simulate the whole process.

T8.1.2.4 Horizontal and Vertical System Integration

Most of today's IT systems are not fully integrated. Companies, suppliers, and customers are rarely closely linked. Nor are departments such as engineering, production, and service. Functions from the enterprise to the shop floor level are not fully integrated. Even engineering itself - from products to plants to automation - lacks complete integration. But with Industry 4.0, companies, departments, functions, and capabilities will become much more cohesive, as cross-company, universal data-integration networks evolve and enable truly automated value chains.

The setting for vertical integration is the factory. A factory owns several physical and informational subsystems, such as actuators and sensors, control and production management, manufacturing, and corporate. Vertical integration refers to the integration of the various IT systems at the different hierarchical levels in order to deliver an end-to-end solution. In the field of production and automation engineering and IT, horizontal integration refers to the integration of the various IT systems used in the different stages of the manufacturing and business planning processes that involve an exchange of materials, energy and information both within a company (e. g. inbound logistics, production, outbound logistics, marketing) and between several different companies (value networks). These new value creation networks are real-time optimized networks that enable integrated transparency and offer a high level of flexibility.

For instance, Dassault Systèmes and BoostAerospace launched a collaboration platform for the European aerospace and defence industry. The platform, AirDesign, is a scalable collaboration platform available as a service on a high-security, private cloud or on-premise. It consists of a neutral workspace for advanced OEM (Original Equipment Manufacturer) and partner PLM (Product Lifecycle Management) collaboration, design and manufacturing. Considered the next generation platform for collaboration and exchange, it has been designed to integrate all the key industry players, from OEM to small and medium business enterprises.

AirDesign drastically reduces operational costs for all partners through a single infrastructure, common exchange methods, open standards and easy access, all without adversely impacting existing information systems. All the primary European OEMs jointly requested and defined this platform in order to facilitate exchanges, support their suppliers' ecosystems and generate new opportunities with services.

T8.1.2.5 The Industrial Internet of Things (IoT)

Today, only some of a manufacturer's sensors and machines are networked and make use of embedded computing. They are typically organized in a vertical automation pyramid in which sensors and field devices with limited intelligence and automation controllers feed into an overarching manufacturing-process control system. But with the Industrial Internet of Things, more devices - sometimes including even unfinished products - will be enriched with embedded computing and connected using standard technologies. This allows field devices to communicate and interact both with one another and with more centralized controllers, as necessary. It also decentralizes analytics and decision making, enabling real-time responses.

Bosch Rexroth, a drive-and-control-system vendor, outfitted a production facility for valves with a semi-automated, decentralized production process. Products are identified by radio frequency identification codes, and workstations "know" which manufacturing steps must be performed for each product and can adapt to perform the specific operation.

The IoT concept can be defined as the use of internet technologies. It covers the wireless connection, micro-electromechanical systems, software and Apps. This approach has helped the linkage between Operational Technology (OT) and Information Technology (IT) allowing unstructured machine-generated data to be analysed for monitoring that will orient improvements on production systems. Every "thing" will soon be networked. Even today,

almost every electronic device is able to communicate with the Internet. Digitization is triggering rapid developments in any area and digitally networked processes in Industry 4.0 will make it possible to manufacture products at a low cost in a manner that is more flexible, energy-efficient, resource-saving and customized. Thus, aviation manufacturing has looked for solution in order to integrate robots, systems and devices by tablets and smartphones via Apps.

GE credits itself for coining the term "Industrial Internet of Things" in 2012 and describes it as "the network of a multitude of devices connected by communications technologies that results in systems that can monitor, collect, exchange, analyse, and deliver valuable new insights like never before." GE is one of the companies that founded the Industrial Internet Consortium to accelerate the development, adoption, and widespread use of interconnected machines and devices, intelligent analytics, and people at work.

A fine example of General Electric's appetite for industrial innovation is the development of the core Integrated Vehicle Health Management application (IVHM) for GE Aviation. From medical imaging, to aircraft engines, energy and rail monitoring, GE and its affiliates monitor hundreds of thousands different devices, including ten thousand of engines.

GE's IVHM application now provides 24/7 worldwide wireless connection to aircraft health status in the broadest sense – including prioritized alerts and analysis of airframe, systems, and engines. The latter can be bought, leased and financed by General Electric Aviation Services (GECAS) from various companies, including GE, CFM, Rolls-Royce, Pratt & Whitney, IAE and Engine Alliance. GECAS offers short-term leases ranging up to one year, and operating leases up to a term of 20 years. The company provides the largest and most diverse pool of spare engines in the marketplace.

The many benefits of GE Aviation's IVHM application that keep increasing include: reduced unscheduled and scheduled maintenance; reduced return to service time; reduced overall operations and maintenance costs; automatic data downloads for Flight Operational Quality assurance (FOQA) and health; quick identification of fleet-wide issues; improved aircraft availability and technical support; ever new insights to aircraft operation and performance.

Through this comprehensive web-based aircraft health management service, GE made it possible for operators to monitor fleet trends and detect and predict anomalies earlier and with greater confidence.

An aircraft engine used to be just one of many parts and slowly became a commodity. To counter that trend, Rolls Royce packed its engines with sensors allowing for real-time data analytics to improve performance and safety. The company launched "Engine Condition Monitoring" that sends real-time engine performance metrics when the plane is mid-air to one of the company's R&D centres. The data can be analysed instantly, and any concerns will be communicated to an airline before the plane reaches its destination. The company operates hundreds of terabytes of data allowing it to compare engine performance across different flights, leading to more efficient solutions. For instance, Rolls Royce Trent 7000 engine allows Airbus's A330 to be 14% more fuel efficient.

Rolls Royce also makes flights safer and more predictable. Traditionally, any irregularities in engine performance during a flight would trigger a full inspection upon landing, leading to delays. With data analytics, Rolls Royce can assess in real-time if a plane is safe for another journey or if it needs to undergo maintenance. It can also predict which maintenance actions need to be taken ahead of time to limit travel disruptions. Finally, comparing data across journeys allows to capture early-warning signs, decreasing potential risks.

Airbus is planning to use the concept of the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) to improve its internal manufacturing process. The French OEM wants its future manufacturing process to be driven by the intersection of people, data and intelligent machines.

T8.1.2.6 Cybersecurity

Many companies still rely on management and production systems that are unconnected or closed. With the increased connectivity and use of standard communications protocols that come with Industry 4.0, the need to protect critical industrial systems and manufacturing lines from cybersecurity threats increases dramatically. As a result, secure, reliable communications as well as sophisticated identity and access management of machines and users are essential.

Such a promising development is not without a degree of risk. Transitioning from silo-based operations to the open model of Industry 4.0, with its interconnected industrial systems and the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), means opening the door to systems with an intrinsically low level of security. The associated risks may be considerable, ranging from commercial data confidentiality (manufacturing secrets, intellectual property theft, etc.) to protection of people and property in relation to critical activities.

To allow industry to benefit from the most innovative technologies, Thales offers a complete range of solutions and services to support the secure end-to-end digital transformation of production systems. Thales solutions encompass data acquisition directly on the shop floor (via secure IIoT solutions), data processing and display at human-machine interface level, secure cloud storage and Big Data analytics for predictive maintenance and other applications. With this full range of capabilities, Thales is helping to improve industrial processes by integrating leading-edge technologies that are "Secure by Design".

T8.1.2.7 The Cloud

Companies are already using cloud-based software for some enterprise and analytics applications, but with Industry 4.0, more production-related undertakings will require increased data sharing across sites and company boundaries. At the same time, the performance of cloud technologies will improve, achieving reaction times of just several milliseconds. As a result, machine data and functionality will increasingly be deployed to the cloud, enabling more data-driven services for production systems. Even systems that monitor and control processes may become cloud based.

Vendors of manufacturing-execution systems are among the companies that have started to offer cloud-based solutions.

T8.1.2.8 Additive Manufacturing

Companies have just begun to adopt additive manufacturing, such as 3-D printing, which they use mostly to prototype and produce individual components. With Industry 4.0, these additive-manufacturing methods will be widely used to produce small batches of customized products that offer construction advantages, such as complex, lightweight designs. High-performance, decentralized additive manufacturing systems will reduce transport distances and stock on hand.

For instance, aerospace companies are already using additive manufacturing to apply new designs that reduce aircraft weight, lowering their expenses for raw materials such as titanium.

For example, at the Airbus's Innovation Cell, the parts produced on Stratasys machines weigh 30–55% less than traditionally manufactured parts, reduce raw material used by 90%, and cut total energy used in production by up to 90% compared to traditional methods. The production has reduced the total weight on each aircraft by up to one ton. By 2018, Airbus expects to print about 30 tons of metal parts every month. Similarly produced components are also included within in-service jetliners in the A300/A310 family.

The airline industry itself is making the move to additive manufacturing process because the printing method delivers absolutely consistent results. Parts are identical and meet very stringent specifications. The same goes for the materials used to make the parts. As that example illustrates, it's a new world for manufacturers and for the companies - and consumers - that depend on them.

T8.1.2.9 Augmented Reality

Augmented-reality-based systems support a variety of services, such as selecting parts in a warehouse and sending repair instructions over mobile devices. These systems are currently in their infancy, but in the future, companies will make much broader use of augmented reality to provide workers with real-time information to improve decision making and work procedures.

For example, workers may receive repair instructions on how to replace a particular part as they are looking at the actual system needing repair. This information may be displayed directly in workers' field of sight using devices such as augmented-reality glasses.

Another application is virtual training. Siemens has developed a virtual plant-operator training module for its Comos software that uses a realistic, data-based 3-D environment with augmented-reality glasses to train plant personnel to handle emergencies. In this virtual world, operators can learn to interact with machines by clicking on a cyber-representation. They also can change parameters and retrieve operational data and maintenance instructions.

Augmented Reality (AR) is defined as an integration of digital information with the user's environment in real time. It uses the real world and overlays virtual information on top of it to perform the augmentation. Digital data can be input to visual or sound condition. When applied to visual, 3D digital objects are loaded and rendered within the physical world often using a display device like a tablet or smartphone. Numerous advancements in AR have

enhanced the feasibility of using AR in many applications. The advantages and benefits of AR have been widely applied by important aircraft manufacturers in global market.

An important industrial application of AR is already used by Airbus. The solution of digital tools has been developed to assist the aircraft production process. This AR solution was named MiRA (Mixed Reality Application) by Airbus. MiRA is designed to reduce the inspection time of tens of thousands brackets that hold hydraulic pipes and wire bundles in place in the plane, and late discoveries of damaged, wrongly positioned or missing brackets. This application increases the productivity in production lines by using AR to scan parts and detect errors on structures. For example, on A380 aircraft, MiRA contributes to a time reduction of 80 % for inspection of brackets in the fuselage. Saving could be got due to integration of AR with a tablet and a special pack containing sensor and software. Also, other gains related to discoveries of damages, wrongly positioned or missing brackets have been reduced by 40 %. A specific application of AR technology has been used on Airbus factories. On the shop floor, tablets and sensors are installed inside the aircraft fuselage in order to track the position of parts and relate them to full-scale CAD models of the real. So, this allows downloading an image of the part in the area where they are working to ensure that they have fixed it correctly. Location tags attached inside the fuselage interact with the sensors to allow the visualization of the tasks from any work location. Another saving is the reduction of the time to inspect brackets inside an A380 fuselage, which hold systems such as hydraulics pipes.

MiRA technology has been developed by Airbus Group Innovation. Mira is now in use on the A320, A380, A350 XWB, A400M production lines in French, German, and Spanish Airbus plants. Inspection time for the 60,000 to 80,000 brackets in the A380 fuselage has dropped from three weeks to just three days.

Digital MockUp (DMU) is another concept that allows the description of a product, usually in 3D, for its entire life cycle. DMU is enriched by all the activities that contribute to describing the product. At Airbus GPure system is used to prepare the Catia DMU of plane sections to inspect. This GPure automation process selects and optimises the necessary parts with their context for a given inspection scenario and adapts them by adding SAP metadata used by MiRA to assist the operator using its tablet PC in the plane under assembly.

8.4 Telecommunications

Telecommunications is a major innovation and growth sector in modern societies that becomes readily embedded in aeronautics technologies and the services they provide, including navigation and air traffic management, on-board monitoring and preventive maintenance, flight safety and security, etc. The expanding flow of information risks saturating the frequency spectrum and forces the trend to higher frequencies to achieve larger bandwidths and data rates. The larger flow of information can also create vulnerabilities if the content is corrupted or interrupted by unintentional failures or interferences or calculated or malicious actions.

The progress in telecommunications supports not only flight operations but also earlier stages of aircraft design and production. Nevertheless, one of the main applications of telecommunications in aeronautics remains air traffic management (Key Topic T8.2).

KEY TOPIC T8.2 TELECOMMUNICATION IN ATM

T8.2.1 Current Status

Since the first steps in aeronautics in the 20th century, telecommunications have played a key role within this field; this is due to the fact that air traffic is based on the use of telecommunications in such a way that most of its applications within this field were introduced decades ago. Nowadays telecommunications still play a key role within current air traffic network and it is expected to continue occupying its position as its core.

Telecommunications allow the provision of air navigation services, both those services addressed to provide to aircraft's positioning and guidance capacity and those services that allow to carry out their movement in the presence of other aircraft in a safe, efficient and effective way. Thus, the cluster of air traffic management (ATM), communication, navigation and surveillance (CNS), meteorological (MET) and aeronautical information (AIS) services are called air navigation services. Likewise, ATM services are divided into three different services: air traffic flow management (ATFM), airspace management (ASM) and air traffic services (ATS) which are composed in turn by air traffic control (ATC), flight information services (AIS) and alert services (AL). Telecommunications are the core of this network in such a way that they allow, as example, communications air to air, air to ground, ground to ground, as well as aircraft navigation or surveillance through the application of radio frequencies. Thereby, available communication and surveillance systems are essential for the correct functioning and effectiveness of air traffic control services as well as equipment based on radio waves is essential for the correct aircraft navigation.

As the numbers of equipment's and applications that use radiofrequency is large, radio spectrum is close to being saturated. Thus, there are specific areas of the spectrum whose frequencies are reserved for aeronautical radio-communication and radio-navigation services. These areas are classified by bands, according to International Telecommunication Union (ITU) and Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) criteria. The following colours have been used to classify the radiofrequencies usages within aviation network:

- Red: ATM Infrastructure – Communication
- Green: ATM Infrastructure – Surveillance
- Blue: ATM Infrastructure – Navigation
- Purple: Avionics and Airborne equipment

Bands	Frequency spectrum	Aviation usages	Types of services
LF & MF	130 – 535 kHz	Non-Directional Beacon (NDB)	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service

Bands	Frequency spectrum	Aviation usages	Types of services
HF	2850 – 22000 kHz	Air-ground communication (HF voice and data)	Aeronautical Mobile (Route) Service
	3023 & 5680 kHz	Search and Rescue	Aeronautical Mobile (Route) Service
VHF	74.8 – 75.2 MHz	Marker Beacon	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service
	108 – 117.975 MHz	VOR/ILS localizer GBAS/VDL Mode 4 (voice and data)	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service Aeronautical Mobile (Route) Service
	117.975 – 137 MHz	Air-ground and air-air communications (VHF voice and data)	Aeronautical Mobile (Route) Service
	121.5, 123.1 & 243 MHz	Emergency distress frequency	Aeronautical Mobile (Route) Service
UHF	328.6 – 335.4 MHz	ILS glide path	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service
	406 – 406.1 MHz	Emergency locator transmitter (ELT)	Mobile-Satellite Service
UHF or L	960 – 1164 MHz	Distance Measuring Equipment (DME) TACAN LDACS (for datalink) LDACS (for Alternative-PNT)	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service Aeronautical Mobile (Route) Service
	978 MHz	Universal Access Transceiver (UAT)	Aeronautical Mobile (Route) Service
	1020 – 1040 MHz 1080 – 1100 MHz	Secondary Surveillance Radar (SSR) 1090 Extended Squitter ADS-B Airborne collision avoidance system (ACAS)	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service
	1164 – 1215 MHz	DME/Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service/Radionavigation-Satellite Service
	1215 – 1400 MHz	Primary Surveillance Radar (PSR)	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service
	1525 – 1559 MHz	Satellite Communications (FANS/ATN Baseline 1 and 2)	Mobile-Satellite Service (space-Earth)
	1559 – 1610 MHz	Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS)	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service/Radionavigation-Satellite Service
	1610 – 1626.5 MHz	Satellite Communications (IRIDIUM)	Aeronautical Mobile-Satellite (Route) Service (space-Earth, Earth-space)

Bands	Frequency spectrum	Aviation usages	Types of services
	1626.5 – 1660.5 MHz	Satellite Communications (FANS/ATN Baseline 1 and 2)	Mobile-Satellite Service (Earth-space)
UHF or S	2700 – 3300 MHz	Primary Surveillance Radar (PSR) Meteorological RADAR	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service Radionavigation Service/Radio Location Service
	3400 – 4200 MHz	Satellite Feeder Links to ATS Services in Africa	
SHF or C	4200 – 4400 MHz	Radio Altimeter Wireless Avionics Intra-Communications (WAIC)	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service
	5000 - 5250 MHz	Microwave Landing System (MLS) UAS CNPC*/Airport Surface Communication (AeroMACS)	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service Aeronautical Mobile (Route) Service/Aeronautical Mobile-Satellite (Route) Service
	5350 - 5470 MHz	Airborne weather radar	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service
SHF or X	8750 - 8850 MHz	Airborne Doppler radar	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service/Radio Location Service
	9000 - 9500 MHz	Precision Approach Radar (PAR)/Airborne weather radar/ASDE	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service/Radionavigation Service
SHF or Ku	13.25 - 13.4 GHz	Airborne Doppler radar	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service
	15.4 - 15.7 GHz	PAR/Airborne weather radar/ASDE	Aeronautical Radionavigation Service/Radio Location Service
SHF or K	24.25 - 24.65 GHz	ASDE	Radionavigation Service
SHF or Ka	31.8-33.4 GHz	ASDE/Airborne radar	Radionavigation Service

Table 8.1 - Aviation radiofrequency usages
Source: Aviation Usages of Frequency Spectrum [1]

* UAS CNPC: Unmanned Aircraft System Command and Non-Payload Communications

T8.2.2 Future Outlook

What can be noticed from Table 8.1 is that radio frequencies related to aviation network fill a wide area within radio spectrum that results in its almost saturation. However, this is not a recent issue due to that most of radio-based equipment was introduced along the 20th century; thereby radio spectrum dedicated to aviation started to be saturated long time ago. For example, the very first radio equipment began to be used in the late 1920s when weather updates and request help with navigation were transmitted through radio by two-way communications. At the same time, began the use of radio for navigation through radio marker

beacons and 4-course radio range systems. During the next decade, the 1930s, the VHF omnidirectional radio range (VOR) started to operate helping pilots to navigate by instrument and it has become a primary NAVAID for decades owing to it has been globally used to define routes and support approach procedures. Likewise, the instrument landing system (ILS) was selected by ICAO as primary landing aid in 1946 and, after seventy years of successful operations and many improvements, it is still the most common precision approach and landing system used at airports.

As a consequence of the growth of air traffic and, likewise, of the growth of the number of NAVAIDs, the need for a higher number of radio channels was identified due to the congestion of radio spectrum. Thus, the saturation in the VHF frequency spectrum required for ground-air communication services forced stakeholders to reduce the separation between channels from 25 kHz to 8,33 kHz. This change in the frequency assignment has managed to increase the number of available channels in VHF band of aeronautical communications, which has allowed the creation of new control sectors and has contributed to increase the air traffic management capacity. It all started in 1999, when some 30 states within the ICAO EUR region enforced mandatory carriage of 8,33 kHz radios above FL245 and, after that, the European Commission (EC) undertook to regulate the implementation of VHF 8.33 kHz in European airspace below FL245 down to FL195. The last effort in this field was carried out by the Single Sky Committee in 2012, when a new regulation extending the requirements for the 8.33 kHz spacing of the air-ground voice channel below FL195 was approved.

In this manner, the future scenario of communications relies on the use of the Aeronautical Mobile Satellite Service (AMSS) through the use of communications satellites SATCOM as well as the use of data link via VHF and HF. Basically, data link is a method for connecting one location to another in telecommunications, in order to transmit and receive digital information. However, in aeronautics data link is a generic term encompassing different types of data links systems and subnetworks as is shown in the following Figure 8.2.

Figure 8.2 - Data Link System Overview

Source: FAA [5]

Data link is being widely spread within aviation framework due to it facilitates specific Air Traffic Management (ATM) operational functionalities such as Context Management (CM), Controller Pilot Data Link Communications (CPDLC), Data Link Flight Information Service (DFIS), Automatic Dependent Surveillance – Addressed (ADS-C) or Automatic Dependent Surveillance – Broadcast (ADS-B). For example, CPDLC is a means of communication between controller and pilot, using data link for Air Traffic Control (ATC) communications in which messages from an aircraft to the Air Traffic Service Unit (ATSU) may follow a standard format or may be free text unlike messages from a controller which usually follow a standard format and require a response from the pilot.

One of the goals is that all of this comes together on ground through a much more efficient, modern and global Aeronautical Telecommunication Network (ATN). ATN is an internetwork that permit ground, air-ground and avionics data subnetworks to exchange digital data for the safety of air navigation and for the regular, efficient and economic operation of ATS. Nowadays, the system has constraints as it is terrestrial based and not available over oceanic and remote continental areas and, besides, ATN is in limited use in Europe and it is not available in the US domestic airspace. However, communications via data link are already being used in certain airports and airspaces, allowing the obtaining of:

- Pre-departure clearances (PDC);
- ATIS information (D-ATIS);

- VOLMET information (D-VOLMET);
- Oceanic clearances (OCL).

It is expected that VHF communications still are an important communication way between aircraft and air traffic controllers in terminal areas, whilst it is expected that direct links replace HF communications between aircraft-satellite-ACCs (Airspace Control Centres). Thus, radio communications are expected to be maintained in service mainly for critical messages such as vectors to avoid traffic or landing clearances at congested airports as well as it is expected that it is a support for data link. Likewise, digital communications allow a link ground-air more direct and effective which results in a benefit in the data exchange between operators, aircraft and ATS centres, in a relief in the voice channels congestion and in a substantial decrease in odds of making a mistake. All of this results in a better air traffic management.

On the other hand, traditional navigation has been based on the use of nav aids located on ground (VOR, NDB, ILS, DME) and autonomous (INS). Nav aids provided the backbone of global air navigation system since they were introduced during the 20th century, and its development has been linked to development of electronics. At present, nav aids infrastructure is under a transition phase since the introduction and development of Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) that results in the change of nav aids scene. Due to this, many of the nav aids currently working are expected to be replaced by satellite-based systems.

The future of air navigation is determined by Performance-Based Navigation (PBN) future deployment which will allow to limit the use of nav aids on ground only for certain airspaces. According to PBN Navigation Strategy 2016 by FAA, PBN comprises Area Navigation (RNAV) and Required Navigation Performance (RNP) and describes an aircraft's ability to navigate in terms of performance standards. On the one hand, RNAV enables aircraft to fly on any desired flight path within the coverage of ground- or space-based navigation aids, within the capability of the aircraft equipment or a combination of capabilities. On the other hand, RNP is RNAV with the addition of onboard performance monitoring and alerting capability. A defining characteristic of RNP operations is the ability of the aircraft navigation system to monitor the navigation performance it achieves and inform the pilot if the requirement is not met during an operation. Common PBN specifications include RNAV 1, RNAV 2, RNP 0.3, RNP 1, as well as RNAV (GPS) and RNAV (RNP) approaches. In this manner, RNAV navigation allows to fly any route specified by the user with the least possible constraints since there is no need to fly over the nav aids on ground. This is due to RNAV is based on the use of Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) with the support of augmentation systems based on satellites (SBAS), on ground (GBAS) and onboard (ABAS), which allow to fulfil the minimum requirements to operate as unique navigation system. Concerning the future, it is expected that by 2030 PBN procedures and flexible routing are the standard method of navigation during normal operating conditions. Related to that, the number of VORs and ILSs will be gradually reduced as result of rationalization. Additionally, due to increased and evolving training on PBN procedures and the evolution of decision support tools for the ATC and pilot community, automation tools and operations will be tightly integrated.

Thus, satellite-based navigation is likely to become an essential element due to it will transform air traffic management because it will allow to attain the full implement of RNAV navigation.

Besides, its precise time reference is expected to be used in surveillance and communications strategic applications. Therefore, within GNSS network, the development and deployment of GALILEO system will be essential for the European Union owing to GALILEO has been designed to fulfil all the required features for aviation users hence it can be widely used, unlike GPS which is hardly certifiable. In this manner, GALILEO will be more accurate and reliable than GPS and it will also inform users about possible system failures (integrity).

8.5 Cybersecurity

The increasing reliance on computer systems tied by telecommunications links multiplies the entry points for disruptive and malicious intrusions. Aeronautics needs no less and perhaps more than many other sectors to implement security measures such as: (i) isolation of safety critical systems as far as it is possible to avoid external links; (ii) access protocols able to foil would be intruders through multiple layers that need not be complex; (iii) independent full-time monitoring of the network to locate local anomalies and prevent their spread; (iv) permanent updating of the list of risks to avoid being surprised by a new form of hacking; (v) general intelligence of security risks, actors and critical time periods; (vi) ability to isolate, re-configure and re-quality compromised systems in the shortest possible time scale; (vii) sufficient redundancy and alternative paths to restore lost capabilities. It is known that: (i) the only unbreakable code is that used only once; (ii) there is no 100% safe protection of software by software. Cybersecurity is and is likely to remain a game of constantly staying on top of new threats.

Cybersecurity is a major concern for air traffic management (Key Topic T8.3) but also in other sectors of aeronautical activity, including airline activities (Key Topic T8.4).

Cyber-vulnerabilities have been exposed at industry and government level, even in the largest aerospace programmes, like the F-35 Lightning II – Joint Strike Fighter Programme:

- Industrial espionage has used small sub-contractors with modest security resources to access up the supply chain to main contractors.
- Intergovernmental meetings among the representatives of participating nations have had uninvited, invisible “guests” from other nations.

These kinds of security breaches can compromise major systems, forcing large scale and costly redesigns.

KEY TOPIC T8.3 CYBERSECURITY IN ATM

T8.3.1 Current Status

Cybersecurity is a relatively new component of aviation security. Putting in context, aviation security consists in safeguarding civil aviation against acts of unlawful interference and this objective is achieved by a combination of measures and human and material resources. However, from an historical point of view, aviation security refers to unlawful physical acts like hijack of aircraft, destruction of an aircraft in service, hostage-taking on board an aircraft or at airports, introduction on board an aircraft or at an airport of a weapon or hazardous device

intended for criminal purposes, use of an aircraft in service for the purpose of causing death, serious bodily injury or serious damage to property or the environment, and so on. Unlike the previous unlawful acts, cybersecurity is about the prevention of and/or reaction to deliberate malicious acts undertaken via cyberspace to either compromise the system directly or wherever systems play a key role. While there is no standard definition of cyberspace it refers to the domain of information flow and communication between computer systems and networks and includes physical as well as purely virtual elements. Airport and ATM cybersecurity is aimed at limiting the effects of such cyber-threats and the impact on airport organization and operations and the overall ATM network.

Cybersecurity has become a real issue for aviation, driven by different factors such as the increasing interconnectivity of ATM which means that the impact of an attack may extend across a growing number of interconnected systems; the increased reliance on integrated data which means a high potential for operational disruptions if connectivity is lost; the migration toward common and Commercial Off The Shelf (COTS) components, underpinned by industry standard protocols such as Internet Protocol (IP), with published vulnerabilities which means that more people will have the technical background to launch attacks and more people will have access to core infrastructures through extended supply chains; and new methods of attack stemming from either criminal activities and/or state sponsored actors, of increasing levels of sophistication. In summary, aviation cyberattack surface is growing due to more interconnected systems [2].

In order to ensure the identification of appropriate preventive security measures, the level of threat should be continually reviewed, and risk assessments carried out, taking into account international, national and regional situations and environments. In this manner, whenever a specific threat exists, selected and predetermined preventive security measures should be applied, commensurate with the associated risk assessment and the nature and severity of the threat. Therefore, as cyber issue has been identified as an important risk for aviation security, it should be treated with the same importance as any other threat that affects aviation security [3].

As well as in air transport, cyberattacks are multiplying in many sectors causing serious issues. These include industries like banking, retail, health insurance or online businesses in which, according to ZDNet opinion, the cost of data breach could reach \$2 trillion by 2019. This will be due to cyberattacks will continue to grow in number, cost and sophistication in the future.

Aviation can learn from other sectors about this issue, trying to develop a strong network where cyberattacks odds are reduced to minimum and where cyber-related disruptions in operations are avoided. If these disruptions are not avoided, successful cyberattacks can cost up to tens of million dollars through immediate direct cost due to service interruption for hours or days and indirect cost for investigation and "clean" rebuilding of the system.

One of the keys to fight successfully against cyberattacks is to identify the potential cyber-attackers. The main potential aviation threat actors are shown in the following Figure 8.3:

Figure 8.3 - Potential aviation threats actors
Source: THALES [4]

The potential cyber attackers that are shown in the previous Figure 8.3 can be explained as follows [2]:

- Insiders like employees, contractors, etc., who have legitimate access to sensitive information, either by accidental or deliberate misuse (e.g. when threatened by terrorists).
- Hacktivists, who have a cause to fight for such as political or ideological motives.
- Hackers or virus writers, who find interfering with computer systems an enjoyable challenge.
- Business competitors and foreign intelligence services interested in gaining an economic advantage for their companies or countries.
- Cyber-criminals, who are interested in making money through fraud or from the sale of valuable information.
- Terrorists, who are interested in obtaining and using sensitive information to launch a conventional attack.
- Organized crime, who are interested in obtaining financial reward or ransom in exchange for not provoking cancellations or flight disruptions.
- State cyber-forces, who have large amount of resources at their disposal, state backing and are very highly skilled.

T8.2.2 Future Outlook

As today's cyber threat actors such as hackers, cyber criminals, hacktivists and terrorists are focused on malicious intent, the theft of information, profit and disruption, the safety and security of the global aviation system could become vulnerable to attacks on its information and data systems.

As one of the most complex and integrated systems of information and communications technology (ICT) in the world, the global aviation system is a potential target for a large-scale cyberattack, or for attack on one or some of its elements in which possible impacts of a cyberattack range from endangering the safety of an aircraft to affecting operational reliability, financial health and business continuity. With the continual and rapid integration of new technologies, the aviation industry is becoming increasingly inter-connected and reliant on systems and, as technologies rapidly evolve, however, so too do the threats [6].

Although it is difficult that an airplane is hijacked or taken over by cybersecurity-related means any time soon due to regulators and manufacturers take care of that even before a new aircraft is designed, the airline's brand and business continuity are threatened by cybersecurity breaches. For example, it is quite easy for a random attacker to compromise the web page that passengers use to check in and, while such an attack won't have any impact on flight operations, the consequences would end up in the media with very dramatic headlines and such news would have a deep effect on passengers' trust in the operator and in aviation. This could cause a loss of confidence, which would lead to a loss of revenues. Without the appropriate cybersecurity measures in place for this evolving threat, the industry may be at risk. Therefore, it is imperative that the industry maintain the highest levels of confidence in aviation in order to keep growing and to avoid any setback related to cyberattacks [7].

Likewise, ensuring a secure aviation system and staying ahead of evolving cyber threats is a shared responsibility, involving governments, airlines, airports, and manufacturers. It is critical that all of these members adopt a collaborative, risk-informed decision-making model to set goals and define a cybersecurity framework and a roadmap to strengthen the aviation system's resilience against cyberattacks. This roadmap should be driven by a common vision, strategy and different economic from safety-related concerns, and address all security matters including knowledge, prevention, detect, respond, and recover. The industry should also take other successful collaborative government-industry teams as an example for designing aviation cyberspace security solutions, such as the Commercial Aviation Safety Team (CAST) that developed a risk management model to reduce commercial aviation fatalities and initiated new government and industry safety initiatives [8].

In this manner, the cybersecurity framework should be based on common principles such as [8]:

- Establish common cyber standards for aviation systems: organizations such as National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), International Organization for Standardization (ISO), and others are working with critical infrastructure providers to develop information security and cyber protection standards for critical infrastructure. Constructive participation in these activities is important to ensuring that aviation's unique requirements are considered when developing the standards.
- Ensure a cybersecurity culture: the same discipline that achieved aviation's high safety standard should also be applied to developing a common vision, common strategy, goals, and definitions, and a common framework and roadmap for addressing the evolving threats.

- Understand the threat: the aviation community should have a common understanding of the actors and their motivations and intents to efficiently plan the defence against them. Adversaries are thinking outside the box to plan cyberattacks and stakeholders should do the same to stop them.
- Understand the risk: to manage cyber risk, it is imperative that the industry identify the elements of the aviation system that need to be protected. The aviation system is a large and complex international entity with multitudes of stakeholders. It will take time and a disciplined process to understand the interactions of the system and its weaknesses.
- Communicate the threats and assure situational awareness: it is important that government and industry share threat and mitigation data to increase the speed at which threats are mitigated across the aviation system. As aviation cyber threats are also global in nature, there should be mechanisms in place to exchange data with the international aviation community.
- Provide incident response: the aviation community should also understand the timeliness required for responding to threats. Different events dictate different response times. For example, a change to a ticketing system may happen quickly as a software patch, whereas a change to aircraft software requires significantly more testing, certification, and approvals. Timely processes, methods, and standards for responding to an attack should differentiate the needs of each aviation subsystem.
- Strengthen the defensive system: the industry should also protect the elements of the aviation system with systems and standards. This requires protecting the interfaces between major subsystems as well as the subsystem.
- Define design principles: the design principles underlying the development of the Internet create opportunities for adversaries. As the cyber domain continues to grow, aviation should define design principles for its networks and control systems that consider the evolving cybersecurity threat and ensure no silent failures. This would include identifying architectures and design principles that protect critical systems and platforms against known attack methods and to ensure that aviation systems are secure by default and are resilient against unknown threat scenarios.
- Define operational principles: these principles focus on the operational aspects of systems deployed in the field. This would include a strong cyber culture, operational standards and best practices that mitigate threats in order to ensure resiliency.
- Conduct necessary research and development: the aviation community should focus its resources on researching and developing appropriate design and operational principles, such as: creating secure and resilient system architectures, including methods for maintaining secure data transfer, isolating critical data, and effectively recovering from attacks; or improving attack detection.
- Ensure that government and industry work together: establish a government and industry framework to coordinate national aviation cybersecurity strategies, policies, and plans. This would include: establishing policy for near and long-term cybersecurity development; defining accepted international rules of behaviour; enforcing consequences for bad behaviour; and positioning cybersecurity as a high priority on the diplomatic agenda.

Additionally, recommendations from ICAO Annex 17 (Security) about cyberterrorism should be adopted as a reference to set the cybersecurity framework. For example, it is stated that each Contracting State should, in accordance with the risk assessment carried out by its relevant national authorities, ensure that measures are developed in order to protect critical information and communications technology systems used for civil aviation purposes from interference that may jeopardize the safety of civil aviation. It is also stated that each Contracting State should encourage entities involved with or responsible for the implementation of various aspects of the national civil aviation security programme to identify their critical information and communications technology systems, including threats and vulnerabilities, and develop protective measures to include, security by design, supply chain security, network separation, and remote access control, as appropriate.

In conclusion, the appropriate authority should ensure that there are procedures in place to identify and assess cyber risks to civil aviation. This should include all relevant stakeholders, for example intelligence agencies, control authorities and industry in that country. On the basis of that analysis they should ensure that appropriate measures are in place to mitigate the likelihood of those threats occurring, recognize them when they occur and respond to and therefore limit the consequences of such attack [3].

KEY TOPIC T8.4 CYBERSECURITY IN AIRLINERS

T8.4.1 Introduction and Reference Zone

This theme will regard the cybersecurity issue for all European states, not one in particular but will also give an inside about USA's vision and countermeasures against the attacks.

Civil aviation is the safest transport mode in the world, and it is probably also the most interconnected system of information and communication technology. Cyberattacks are increasing in quantity and in sophistication, with points of attack spanning the entire industry chain: new technologies, extension of connectivity, use of Commercial Off The Shelf (COTS) solutions and their ever-quicker integration in the aviation industry (e.g. in the field of Air Traffic Management) increase the risk and impact of threats to these critical assets, whilst attackers become more numerous, adaptive and far-reaching.

Maintaining the high levels of security in civil aviation therefore urgently requires the development of an effective comprehensive framework addressing all aspects of the aviation system. Regulators, operators and manufacturers have to work together based on a collaborative, risk-based model through a strong framework to address direct threats and at the same time increase the system's resilience against future attacks.

Aviation security = Safeguarding civil aviation against acts of unlawful interference. This objective is achieved by a combination of measures and human and material resources.

In order to ensure the identification of appropriate preventive security measures, the level of threat should be continually reviewed, and risk assessments carried out, taking into account international, national and regional situations and environments.

Whenever a specific threat exists, selected and predetermined preventive security measures should be applied, commensurate with the associated risk assessment, and the nature and severity of the threat.

“Cyber” issue is identified (Figure 8.4) as a new risk for aviation security.

Figure 8.4 – Cyber risks to aviation

T8.4.2 Current Status and Future Prospects

The aviation industry is important to the global economy. In 2013, the air transportation network carried over 48 million tons of freight and over 2.6 billion passengers. Its global economic value was estimated at 2.2 trillion dollars (AIAA, 2013). Any (cyber)-attack in this industry would result in important social and economic consequences.

With the development of new technologies such as internet, the global aviation industry is subject to a new and growing type of threat coming from cyberspace. As in the other industries, cyber threats purposes are for example the robbery of information, political actions, make profit, or simply weaken one stakeholder of the industry.

The global aviation industry has many layers overseeing the safety of all the stakeholders involved, from aircraft manufacturers to the passenger boarding a flight. Overall, these different actors can be classified into 4 categories:

- **One international organization:** The International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO), part of the UN. It codifies the rules of investigation internationally and designs international civil aviation Standards and Recommended Practices in collaboration with its member states.
- **Governments:** national investigation organizations, virtually security agencies that investigate on behalf of countries involved in the accident. France’s Bureau d’Enquêtes et d’Analyses (BEA) or the USA’s National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB) are the main examples of such organizations. On top of ICAO’s guidelines, they may develop additional safety standards (for example, the NTSB developed smoke detectors in aircraft toilets).

- **Trade organization of airlines:** International Air Transport Association (IATA) oversees standards at industry level and is directly in contact with most of the world's airlines.
- **Manufacturers of aircraft and security systems:** many large corporations such as Boeing, Dassault, Thales, Honeywell... They constantly update their systems to face new threats with the advice of the different boards described above.

Because of its complexity and its weight in the economy, breaking the aviation industry's security constitutes a great challenge for hackers and terrorists. Moreover, this industry relies more and more on information and communication technology (ICT). As an industry that is well known for providing one of the safest type of transportation, it is mandatory for all its stakeholders to understand the risks and to prevent any malicious events for the good of the industry, the economy, the population and the environment.

Online attacks are on the rise resulting in headline-grabbing stories. In the last few years, we've witnessed data breaches across multiple industries including banking, retail, health insurance, and online-only businesses. The financial impact alone is staggering. The cost of data breaches globally could reach \$2 trillion by 2019. Another study estimates that 2014 cybercrime losses cost businesses about \$400 billion annually. Inevitably, cyber threats will continue to grow in number, cost, and sophistication. Consider the greatly expanded use of cloud and mobile devices. Businesses are embracing these tools to connect their internal staff and operations. They're also accelerating usage to connect externally—with strategic partners, customers, and a multitude of other third parties. These efforts are serving to enhance efficiencies, collaborations, and competitiveness. But along with these benefits, new vulnerabilities have emerged. Mobile devices create more entry points for hackers by dispersing data. The cloud, where data are aggregated, makes data more accessible. And these sources of risk are continuing to expand quickly. To mitigate the threats, companies will need to reassess all facets of their business and establish internal protocols to effectively manage them. Furthermore, as businesses aggregate and analyse more data on customers and processes, the data become increasingly valuable and a more attractive target for hackers. This double-edged sword applies to technology as well. While improved technology allows businesses to better understand and target their customers, advances in technology also provide hackers with more sophisticated technology with which to perpetrate attacks.

For the airline industry, cybersecurity risk is top of mind. According to our survey, 85 percent of airline CEOs expressed concern about this risk versus 61 percent of CEOs in other industries, a difference of 24 percentage points. As in other industries, airlines are concerned with the theft of sensitive customer or company data. But an added threat for airlines is that technology is being used to improve the connectivity of flight operations systems with ground crews and air traffic systems. While this enhanced communication and integration is essential to the improvement of financial and operational performance, it does provide more opportunities for those seeking to exploit these advances. So as airlines increasingly adopt advanced technologies, they must also upgrade security procedures to allow for safe innovation. Overall, security procedures to date have been effective, safely integrating the many technological advances introduced to aircraft and airlines. Yet the industry continues to see major technological advances that contribute to the complexity of protecting data and assets. Two of these are tablet-based electronic flight bags (EFBs) and the installation of in-

flight entertainment and Wi-Fi connectivity systems (IFEC). EFBs are particularly popular with pilots as they have taken the place of heavy binders that pilots used to carry onboard. Yet a recent survey revealed that many airlines do not have a targeted plan in place to safeguard the security of EFBs. On-board IFEC systems are proliferating. Currently, they are physically segregated from cockpit systems.

Nevertheless, these systems greatly increase the number of connections, vendors, and technologies involved, which in turn creates more hacking opportunities. The threats posed by EFBs and IFECs need to be managed holistically, with airlines closely cooperating with other carriers, hardware and software providers, aircraft OEMs, and other industry stakeholders. Another potential cyber issue for the airline industry is the Federal Aviation Administration's (FAA) modernization of air traffic control, notably the Next Generation Air Transportation System or NextGen. The current system is 40 years old and relies on radar, which provides limited connectivity. NextGen seeks to improve network efficiency by using GPS (global positioning system) that is software based and connected to the Internet. While it's widely accepted that this transition is needed to modernize our air traffic control systems, the General Accounting Office has voiced concern that implementing a system with Internet connectivity brings with it greater threats to security.

As real-time aircraft connectivity continues to evolve, providing information where and when it's needed to optimize airline operations and the customer experience, it not only increases the number of opportunities for attacks, it potentially makes them more damaging. The industry is making significant investments and taking important steps to address cybersecurity, calling for increased oversight from boards of directors as well as third-party providers. The FAA has "convened a private meeting" to examine the security of aircraft systems, which at the very least is an acknowledgement of the need for industry-wide approaches and standards. Tony Tyler, the head of the International Air Transport Association, or IATA, has publicly stated that regulators have to work with airlines to develop a global security system that adopts "an end-to-end risk-based approach." IATA's position is that the industry can effectively deal with most attacks by focusing efforts on prioritizing and allocating resources to protect the airlines' most valuable assets.

In the interim, without any uniform industry standards in place, each airline has to consider how to reduce the risk of a cyber-attack and how to deal with one when it happens. Regardless of how a cybersecurity strategy is formulated, the airline's board has to support the strategy and ensure that it is coordinated across all departments in the organization. A cybersecurity strategy includes methods to prevent, detect, and react to attacks as well as a mechanism for capturing learnings. Feedback collected at each stage should be incorporated into the overall security program to make attacks more difficult to execute successfully. While prevention methods are not fool proof, an airline's first security goal is to try and stop attacks from occurring, both on the ground and in the air. Once an attack occurs, airlines must detect the attack as quickly as possible and isolate the intrusion. And then airlines must react quickly and efficiently to minimize the damage and reduce the risk of future incidents. As we have seen in many industries, this involves extensive analysis of the potential vulnerabilities across an organization's internal operations, supply chain, and strategic partner network.

The United States of America have a firm opinion related:

"America must also face the rapidly growing threat from cyber-attacks...our enemies are also seeking the ability to sabotage our power grid, our financial institutions and our air traffic control systems. We cannot look back years from now and wonder why we did nothing in the face of real threats to our security and our economy." - President Obama, 2013 State of the Union Address

All the developed countries around the globe are seeking a strong collaboration and are committed to develop a synergy to protect against cyber-attacks and protect their assets.

T8.4.3 Evolutionary Progress. Predictions

What constitutes an effective defence plan? There are several key elements: Oversight at the board level and building a security culture

A cybersecurity program has to rest on a risk-based framework that addresses risks across the airline including back-office IT, maintenance, operations, and consumer facing systems because failure in one area can affect others. Management, employees, and the board must become more cyber aware as breaches can occur as a result of small lapses in procedure. But security awareness training is not enough. Airlines need to incorporate cyber awareness into the security culture, embedding cybersecurity into the organizational fabric. Below are specific examples of the roles various functions need to play:

- Procurement: looks for the counterfeit parts that may have come unwittingly from providers
- Maintenance: considers the security maturity of MRO partners and potential points of ingress;
- Operations: considers enhanced digital security measures needed to fly safely to high-risk destinations;
- Marketing: examines the value of consumer information and guards against identity theft and exploitation of awards programs;
- Information technology: modernizes infrastructure and implements security monitoring and remediation protocols that establish resiliency for flight operations;
- Management: sets the tone at the top and appropriately communicates to the broader enterprise and its trading partners;
- Board: ensures operational cyber risk is put in context of other carrier risks and is properly resourced.

Proactive approach that sets priorities

Since it's too expensive to protect all assets from all threats, airlines need to prioritize—assets, threats, and threat perpetrators. On assets, they must recognize their protection obligations, identify associated digital assets, and focus aggressively on protecting those assets most valuable and critical to the organization. On threats, airlines need to prioritize and categorize the kinds of threats they are facing, both those known currently and those projected to emerge over the next few years and recognize the signs of an attack early on. On perpetrators, they

need to look at the players that are most threatening, a list which can include nation states, organized crime, and terrorists.

Airlines cannot do this by themselves: the risks are too numerous and diverse—and constantly changing. They need to avail themselves of all existing tools, public and private, that can help mitigate risk. In the United States, the NIST Cybersecurity Framework supports businesses in critical infrastructure industries including transportation. In addition, the Department of Homeland Security established the Critical Infrastructure Partnership Advisory Council (CIPAC) for aviation as a public-private partnership to address the cyber risks affecting the industry. To augment this industry sector insight with carrier-specific threats, many airlines subscribe to threat intelligence services that inform them about the latest threats. Airlines then can model different scenarios to determine optimal prevention approaches. Real-time feeds from these services are fed into security operations procedures so they can be dealt with. Many carriers are also harnessing the power of the cloud and big data to model and monitor evolving and new cybersecurity threats. Using these new technologies allows airlines to scale protection efforts across their organization and increase the sensitivity of their prevention programs. Additionally, some companies perform periodic penetration assessments. These are generally commissioned by senior management to evaluate the strength of security and monitoring procedures.

Support international standards

There are no international standards for cybersecurity design and testing, which is widely acknowledged to be an issue. The US, Europe, and the International Air Transport Association (IATA), a trade association of the world's airlines, have begun initiatives to address the lack of standards. Last year, the US Federal Aviation Administration, or FAA, established a new industry working group to provide guidance on how to improve cybersecurity on e-enabled aircraft. The European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) held a workshop to address cybersecurity. IATA has also called for better sharing of airline cyber threats among governments and airlines worldwide and asked governments around the world to take a more active stance in improving cybersecurity. Airlines can do their part by supporting efforts to build international standards. While industry associations establish standards, airline CISOs could form informal alliances to discuss leading practices in the industry and how best to implement those practices. These peer-to-peer interactions can lead to focused discussions on specific threat areas.

Address supply chain risks

It's critical that airlines and their external partners (such as OEMs, MROs, IFEC [in-flight entertainment and communications] providers) collaborate on threats and response techniques to share best practices to increase the knowledge base. But, in addition, airlines have to monitor partners' operations for potential security breaches and manage the access of users to different systems. In particular, smaller companies tend to have less stringent security protocols and invest less than their larger counterparts in security measures. To mitigate risk, airlines have to ensure their vendor contracts include audit clauses and specified testing procedures.

Cybersecurity capabilities. Beyond these broad strategic approaches to cybersecurity, airlines need to consider the technologies and processes that can strengthen their programs to deal with today's threats. Some of those tools are described below:

Threat intelligence

Airlines must gather both external and internal threat intelligence from multiple sources including third-party vendors, subscription feeds, and agencies as well as system event and log information. This information can then be correlated and fed into a 24 x 7 x 365 security operations centre (SOC) to help identify and prioritize threats. It's also key that airlines get involved at an industry level, so they can raise awareness of threats among colleagues. One such organization, the Aviation Information Sharing and Analysis Centre (A-ISAC), helps constituents better prepare for and manage sector-specific threats, vulnerabilities, and incidents. Other organizations that can provide intelligence include federal agencies, such as the FBI and the Secret Service, and industry consortiums, such as ISACA (Information Systems Audit and Control Association) and CERTs (Community Emergency Readiness Teams).

Identity and access management

Identity and access management (IAM) is often overlooked as a legacy capability, yet it provides a suite of functionality that authenticates and authorizes employees, partners, and customers to access airline applications and systems. IAM systems may cover many functions: ecommerce, ticket purchase, loyalty redemption information, and concourse applications to generate boarding passes, and also enable collaboration between airlines and governmental agencies, such as the Department of Homeland Security, and communication with MRO partners. There are a few capabilities within IAM. One is privileged access management (PAM) that is meant to protect against the use of generic and shared IDs. The system includes capabilities for enforcing, controlling, and managing privileged access to systems; logging, monitoring, auditing, and certifying privileged access; and reporting violations. Another variation is multifactor authentication (MFA), which has been adopted by leading airlines that have moved beyond a 'passwords only' approach. It requires more than one method of authentication from independent categories of credentials to verify a user's identity and is usually comprised of something you know (e.g., password), something you have (e.g., token) and something you are (e.g., biometric). MFAs restrict access to an airline's Internet and employee portals as well as key enterprise systems. Adaptive authentication solutions add an additional layer of security. They assess the risk associated with each authentication attempt/transaction by requesting additional attributes that help to verify identity. With basic password authentication, systems are vulnerable to attackers exploiting credentials that were compromised elsewhere.

In the airline industry, several carriers have been hit with millions of dollars in fraud related to unauthorized redemption of miles and points by rogue attackers. The full value of adaptive authentication comes from establishing normal behavioural patterns of users and populations and then detecting anomalies by applying contextual data about the user, endpoint, transaction, or asset to make a risk-based authorization decision (e.g., logging in from a new geographic location).

Data protection/encryption

Leading airlines use encryption and tokenization technologies to help protect customer and employee information, including payment cards, national IDs, passport numbers, and bank accounts. This is particularly critical in today's digital environment with widespread use of social media and online applications. One example of a dynamic regulatory environment recently, the European Commission proposed changes to its privacy laws to strengthen and unify data protection for individuals in the EU. It also addresses export of personal data outside the EU. More importantly, it stated that the penalties and fines for the most egregious violations could be up to four percent of an organization's revenue.

Design/application security

Leading airlines are embedding security requirements from the 'ground up' and not as an afterthought, starting with the design of secure applications and products. According to NIST, it is 6.5 times more expensive to find and address an application flaw in development than during design, 15 times more expensive during testing, and 100 times more expensive during production. In the past, efforts may have been limited to regulated or commercial applications that were in scope for SOX 404 or the payment card industry (PCI). However, this left mission critical operational systems for ground and aircraft operations as well as MROs and other third parties out of scope for security. The threat landscape that airlines face has moved beyond the theft of data such as payment cards and towards the operational resiliency and integrity of all systems. Furthermore, any products and services that are developed for the crew, ground operations, and customers must consider security as a key functional requirement in today's landscape.

Security awareness

Whether it's the tampering of concourse devices, activity within the cabin (e.g., plugging into USB ports), or corporate espionage, awareness is often the front-line defence against threats. All airline employees, not just the physical and information security departments, have to share in that awareness and understand their roles and responsibilities in preventing cyber-attacks. A good analogy for the depth of cultural integration required is the way that environmental safety regulations have become ingrained in the factory culture. For example, workers understand they need to wear certain footwear on a production floor for safety reasons and would almost certainly stop someone from wearing open-toed sandals. In the factory, policy and heightened awareness have been woven into the fabric of the culture through tone at the top, organizational campaigns, and incentives as well as penalties. A similar cultural commitment is needed on the cyber front. For example, phishing attacks are still one of the most effective attack vectors used by adversaries; they are very easy to exploit and can yield significant returns even if just one target takes the bait. In such an attack, an employee is targeted to open an email link, which then downloads malware that infects the IT environment of the entire organization. Recently, executives have been the target of these types of attack because of their access to sensitive data. It's easy to see how one unwitting employee or executive can lead to significant damage.

T8.4.4 Identification of Gaps

When dealing with a cyber incident, organizations often discover that there were signs of an intrusion long before the breach was identified. In our experience, advanced threat actors often maintain remote access to the target environment for 6-18 months before being detected. During this time, an attacker has the opportunity to identify critical systems, locate valuable data, and execute the most devastating attacks. Early detection, along with a clearly defined set of operational processes to quickly address an attack, is vital to reducing the consequences. This is true for all industries, including the airlines.

The objectives of today's advanced cyber threats are typically to steal desired data and maintain access to the environment for as long as possible. Over the past decade, in all industry sectors, cyber intrusion activity targeting multinational companies has increased significantly. Any company with proprietary data perceived to be of economic value—or involved with national security and critical infrastructure, such as aviation—has increased from a potential to a likely target.

When compromised organizations conduct incident post-mortem analyses, they usually discover that their monitoring processes and tools are lacking. They may not have a holistic view of systems and data across the enterprise and they may not include needed alerts, rules, and workflow to detect or communicate threat scenarios. In fact, we see that many current tools only perform basic pattern matching and counting and fail to correlate data across multiple systems and between seemingly disconnected events.

Part of the challenge of detecting security breaches is keeping up with the constantly evolving set of threat actors, targets, and vectors. Detection protocols have to be one step ahead of the latest hacking techniques. Another problem is that while external threats get more play in news headlines, insider threats can be much more difficult to diagnose and costly to remediate.

Companies also face a financial challenge: When it comes to cyber strategy, it is often more difficult to obtain funding for detection efforts than for prevention. Preventative measures, such as encryption and access control, are often tangible and, as a result, easier for management and employees to understand and support.

Detection, on the other hand, is a moving target with generally unknown actors, uncertain penetrations, and unpredictable timing. Since attacks are so varied, it can be hard to build a leading-edge detection system. Airlines face an additional burden in that they have extensive third party networks. And for all industries there is little concrete regulatory guidance other than the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST).

Include detection in cyber programs

The leading airlines that include detection as part of their cyber programs have built comprehensive coverage of their network, data, and endpoints (Figure 8.5). They're able to react so quickly to attacks that response times are virtually instantaneous. This ability to move decisively and swiftly not just limits losses, but also prevents the intruder from temporarily

pausing the attack and hiding elsewhere in the enterprise’s networks only to attack in a different fashion at a later date.

Figure 8.5 – Measures against cyberattack

While cyber detection has to be tailored to meet the specific needs of each airline, these tools cannot simply log and aggregate data points—they have to intelligently correlate the data to identify an intrusion (Figure 8.6). In addition, next generation cyber security defence programs include other essential capabilities such as those discussed below:

Figure 8.6 – Further measures against cyberattack

Companies in the aviation industry face yet another challenge. A key trend is increasing interconnectedness, whether it's between aircraft and ground control stations, airlines, airports and other aviation stakeholders, or between dispersed field-deployed assets. This same interconnectedness that provides operational efficiencies simultaneously introduces further risk to commercial passenger airlines. From billing and reservation systems to aircraft engine telemetry, aviation companies have broad networks that not only provide multiple high-value targets for attackers, but because of their interconnections open up multiple avenues of penetration into an airline's core systems. A recent example of the danger inherent in interconnections with third parties occurred in the attack on an organization's air-conditioning vendor, which then allowed hackers to penetrate the corporate network. While there's no going back on interconnectedness—it is a factor in today's world—every airline has to address the risk of third-party networking and the potential weakness of points of intersection.

Compounding the challenge of implementing and maintaining an effective cyber detection program are the many seismic changes in the airline industry in recent years that add to

complexity (Figure 8.7). Below are some changes we've seen that alter the way airlines operate and make it more difficult to detect cyber threats:

- Growth in the volume and types of data created by new-model airframes, engines, and components;
- Increased focus on capturing, mining, and using passenger shopping and travel preferences and behaviours;
- Proliferation of increasingly advanced and interconnected assets among aircraft, airports, airline network operations and dispatch, and other stakeholders in the travel ecosystem;
- Increased dispersion of data collection points, geographically and physically;
- Increase in the number of vendors that tap into and use airline data to improve operations, passenger management, and other core airline functions;
- Reliance on potentially insecure legacy applications and platforms that support core aircraft operational activity.

Figure 8.7 – Data Streams vulnerable to cyberattack

Since airlines can pay a particularly heavy toll for not having effective cyber detection tools, they've become much more proactive in developing tools as part of their cyber programs. According to the latest Airline IT Trends Survey from SITA², 91 percent of airlines are planning to invest in cyber programs over the next three years, up from 47 percent in 2013. The study also shows a large increase in the number of airlines that think they are prepared for the common types of cyber threats: 48 percent compared with 17 percent three years ago.

T8.4.5 Current Status of Relevant Technologies

Efforts have been made but not enough

As seen in the previous section, it is important to consider the rise of software complexity in the aviation sector. Indeed, software complexity is increasing, and software security cannot be totally guaranteed. This is the reason why it is important to handle vulnerabilities in this sector, to deploy software updates to prevent any attacks and of course to test regularly the security of critical systems.

With the complexity and the high number of stakeholders in this industry, the number and the origins of breaches could be substantial. In the same way, establishing the stakeholder accountable for a breach or an attack could be difficult. Some previous cases in the aviation sector have led to some observations. For example:

- When a vulnerability or a breach is discovered, vendors do not always address or fix it
- No stakeholder would accept to be accountable for a breach or a vulnerability: the suppliers blame each other, the main manufacturers such as Airbus or Boeing blame the suppliers, the airplane operators blame the manufacturers and so on
- Critical systems and cabin systems on airplanes are not isolated properly from external threats
- The principal internal communication protocol, Avionics Full Duplex (AFXD), had poor security solutions implemented

As cyber-attacks against the aviation industry have increased considerably, setting the cyber security as a major concern, all 4 categories of industry stakeholders as pointed out earlier worked together to address these cyber threats.

The major efforts made by these stakeholders are the following:

- With the increase of cyber-attacks in all the industries and the increase of computer-based solutions used, ICAO encourages better and stronger collaboration between all the stakeholders to identify as many threats and risks as possible (Lim, 2014);
- ICAO organized a discussion to define responsibilities on cyber security for the aviation industry;
- ICAO would like to encourage countries to implement strong cyber security strategy and management. The goal is to implement more policies and measures to prevent any cyber-attacks that could lead to dramatic consequences. This recommendation by the ICAO includes crisis management and business resilience;
- More and more countries started to work on cyber security few years ago;
- More and more airports started to implement measures to secure any IT systems already exposed. They also started to consider upstream the cyber security issues for the future projects;
- With safety as a top priority, IATA conducts yearly audits mandated by governments and provides airlines with a cyber-security toolkit that has a traditional risk assessment approach (IATA, 2015).

Figure 8.8 – Example of an initiative on cybersecurity

- Finally, manufacturers have made some efforts as well: Boeing implemented additional security measures on the 777 aircraft to prevent on-board hacking of critical computer systems (Federal Register, 2013).

Cybersecurity initiatives are taken by various organizations, e.g. EASA (Figure 8.8). A good example of cross-stakeholder collaboration is the National Transportation Safety Board, the US government agency that investigates and provides recommendations on accidents that occurred in all forms of transportation. The processes in place in this agency are “more focused on figuring out what went wrong than in laying blame or assigning liability”, and takes into account the perspective of all stakeholders involved in the accident to make conclusions. Many experts in the US have been recommending that the government develops a similar agency with a focus on cybersecurity in transportation, a quest that may have found its answer in the 2016 Cybersecurity standards for aircraft to improve resilience act, or the Cyber AIR act (Wolff, 2016).

Although a lot of efforts have been made, there still exist a lot of issues to be addressed (Figure 8.9).

Figure 8.9 – Future initiatives on cybersecurity

T8.4.6 Advantages and Limitations

Cyber Security Challenges for the Aviation Industry

As the aviation industry is known for providing one of the safest types of transportation, it is mandatory for the stakeholder to consider seriously the cyber threats if they want to preserve the efficiency, security and resilience of their systems. Moreover, underestimating these new types of threats would lead to a drop in the number of users as people would be looking for a safe transportation network. To deal with these threats and to maintain a high degree of confidence, stakeholders would need to continue the efforts made to date.

To strengthen its cyber security, the aviation industry could consider some of the propositions made by experts and agencies globally. The following suggestions seem to be the most appropriate:

The aviation industry has to evolve and to introduce strong systematic tests against cyber threats in addition to the compliance testing already implemented. The latter does not imply security and is managed internally by experts in compliance and availability testing. Internal security testing is then disregarded because of internal constraints and a lack of expertise. It is more than important to test all the components independently and the complete systems by external experts. These experts would have the advantage to be independent, less constrained, unbiased, creative, and more than anything else expert in breaking systems.

- The aviation industry is made up of traditional isolated systems that are more and more connected and exposed (AIAA, 2013). Like in other industries, for any project it is important to:
 - Assess the needs and the allowance for these external links;
 - Ensure that security processes are implemented;
 - Ensure that vulnerabilities can be addressed quickly;
 - Be aware that security updates might break current certification. The choice of expose and connect isolated systems implies to consider a new environment.
- Critical systems should be tested by external and independent companies that have a real expertise in cyber security.
- Provide high security for critical communication systems such as the radio. This security should ensure strong authentication, confidentiality, integrity and availability. Any other unprotected communication systems should be considered as potentially compromised. Finally, it is important to check that critical and non-critical systems are isolated.
- Any company in the aviation industry should raise awareness among all the employees on the importance of considering seriously cyber threats. It is important to set up a real cybersecurity culture in the critical entities of this industry.
- Every company in the aviation industry should assess its needs in term of cyber security. These companies should be aware of their vulnerabilities and implement some measures to reduce them. Like any other industry, the aviation sector should consider seriously cyber security like they do for HR, Finance, operations and so on. The companies of this industry should have a deep understanding of the threats and the risks. Who are the attackers? What are their motivations? How will they attack? What should be protected in priority?
- Implement stronger internal policies and plans within the company. Indeed, as companies rely more and more on computer-based systems, interact more and more with other companies or people such as passengers, it is mandatory to strengthen internal policies and plans.
- It would be important to implement also recovery plan and to increase resilience.
- Governments should set up some regulations and norms in term of cyber security.

All these recommendations might be already implemented today but it is interesting to note that they are shared with the other industries. The aviation industry might be more cyber-secure nowadays, it should continue to strengthen its systems as technologies evolve constantly, so do the threats.

T8.4.7 Proactive Measures

Airlines have long had to deal with many operational disruptions, such as unplanned aircraft maintenance, adverse weather, business system faults, and other unplanned events that cause delays and cancellations. The need to address issues that impede day-to-day operations can push aside other types of threats, especially cyber-related ones, which may appear at first glance to be innocuous. However, even a relatively low-impact attack may indicate a vulnerability that can lead to a more serious and expansive intrusion.

A clear indication that incident response processes are not working is that very few (or no) attacks are detected. Highly mature, global organizations should expect to see hundreds of successful (not blocked at the firewall nor remediated by antivirus software) low-impact attacks in a year and, perhaps, dozens of more serious attacks annually.

How can an airline create an effective cybersecurity incident response plan?

Define Parameters and Protocols

Many organizations are uncertain about how to define a cyber incident, how to respond, and how to measure potential impact. This creates a dangerous opening. If an enterprise fails to mount an effective reaction to an incident, an intruder has time to penetrate more deeply into the organization's network and cause greater harm. With detection time averaging 6-18 months, slow reaction has become a widespread problem.

Airlines are no different from other organizations: All cyber incidents must be contained and mitigated as quickly as possible. But not every incident requires a full-court press. It's essential to implement a framework for categorizing the severity of an attack and its potential impact on the organization. IT and cybersecurity professionals should develop a matrix that labels attacks on a graduated scale such as high, medium, and low impact. The matrix should specify financial exposure, number and type of systems involved, and a clear plan for which stakeholders, internally and externally, should be notified.

For example, the matrix should define when the CIO must be notified, or under what circumstances the legal team must be notified. In that way, the right leadership will be alerted at the right time and for the appropriate level of risk. Often, this kind of clear protocol can prevent a small problem from becoming much larger and ensure that large problems get the attention they require as quickly and efficiently as possible.

Not everyone in the organization needs to be made aware of every incident. In fact, an effective incident response process can limit the number of people involved. Different triage protocols should be considered for major/minor incidents, including notifying the appropriate business units, enacting (or not) a crisis public relations strategy, and coordinating notification efforts. Generally, the most severe incidents should receive the widest coverage, which can run counter to an organization's tendency to de-emphasize such incidents.

The vast majority of incidents tend to be of very low severity. However, it's essential for airlines to establish regular metrics around these incidents. By identifying, documenting, and analysing low-risk vulnerabilities, senior leaders may come to see that a particular intrusion type or exploited vulnerability is actually having a broader negative impact on the organization than previously understood. Metrics help establish patterns that can be more useful than just viewing incidents in isolation and highlight new opportunities for improvement, cost savings, and risk reduction.

Create response structures

Large organizations tend to have three distinct types of incident response structures. One, the primary focus of IT operations, involves information technology incidents, where the

breakdown of some portion of the IT eco-system creates a potential business impact. The second structure is centred on crisis management incident response to deal with natural disasters or other events that can cause major disruption. The third structure concerns cyber incident response processes. These structures should work together to ensure that all incidents are captured.

Some airlines use their IT operations incident framework for cybersecurity incidents. However, IT operations cannot adequately address the severity of a cyber incident because it focuses on glitches in IT systems. In a cyber incident, all IT systems could be functioning while millions of customer records are being exfiltrated for further exploitation. For that reason, it's important to develop an incident severity matrix/framework that takes into account the possibility that standard IT processes may appear to be operating normally although an attack is in progress.

Establish regional capabilities

For airlines that have a global footprint, allocating and integrating resources from global geographic regions is an important part of the cybersecurity incident response plan. It's unrealistic to expect a team in the US to fully counter a threat in Asia. In many cases, criminal groups wait to launch their most devastating attacks when an organization has the fewest people available to deal with it; or when they have the greatest chance of blending in with business-as-usual operations. With timeliness often a critical factor in incident response protocols, airlines should incorporate regional capabilities to deal with incidents promptly.

Develop the three-legged stool

Successful cyberattacks are not just an IT problem, they are a business problem that requires a holistic corporate response. Three of the most common stakeholder groups in an incident response plan include (Figure 8.10) information or cyber security, legal, and corporate communications. While there can be additional groups involved in an incident response plan, any serious plan has to involve strong, focused participation from a core team. A best practice is to form a working group with permanent representatives from these three groups who are responsible for creating, reviewing, updating, and incorporating lessons learned from cyber incidents.

When an incident occurs, a single leader should be appointed from one of the three core groups to serve as the focal point of the response. Generally, in highly mature organizations, information security is the first to recognize an incident and leads the initial response. If the immediate technical impact is quickly mitigated, continuing activities may focus on legal liability. At that point, leadership is likely to shift from information security to legal. That shift should be explicitly noted by the larger team, so that the role of leader is always clear to those involved. The lack of a single leader can lead to confusion, delay, and disconnected communications among team members, resulting in increased risk.

Figure 8.10 – Departments involved in cybersecurity

Adequately fund and staff

There is often a large level of investment in prevention activities and technology, but considerably less in detection and response. As a result, these functions are often under staffed, or staffed without the appropriate skill sets. Large organizations should create at least one position dedicated to incident response who has the requisite talent and experience. This is a particularly critical role in the airline industry, given the various threat vectors an attacker can take, and the potentially high stakes of an incident.

Even with a dedicated incident response role, organizations generally have to rely on third-party retainer services for specialized capabilities, such as cyber forensics and breach investigation support. These third-parties need to be integrated into an organization's cyber program to ensure that, as third-party resources change, new team members are familiar with the organization's history and practices.

Simulate and practice

Airlines can use simulation exercises to help them prepare for cyber incidents by walking through plans and procedures. These exercises can serve as part of a broader strategy for practicing how to move swiftly and effectively in response to an attack. Typical simulations include working through the severity matrix (minor, serious, and major incidents) and proper notifications; collecting forensic data to help determine the nature of the event; coordinating communications, including the groups that are part of the three-legged stool; and discussing backup plans and restoring actions.

Capture lessons learned... and apply them

Once an incident is dealt with, the natural tendency is to move on by the organization. But leading organizations have a structured lessons-learned process that allows them time to review and update protocols and tactics: What went well? What didn't? How can efforts be improved? What specific actions should be taken and by whom? The answers to these

questions help strengthen prevention strategies and lead to an improvement in airline cybersecurity.

To illustrate this further, consider that cybersecurity was not a concern when airline legacy systems were established. As a result, these core business systems can present significant vulnerabilities; many possess high-value data, but do not have the safeguards in place to defend against modern threat techniques and technologies. But as legacy systems are upgraded or replaced, airlines can simultaneously incorporate new security measures.

As airlines become increasingly connected across internal operations and with their supply chains, creating a more open environment, it increases the probability that information will be compromised. If that occurs, an airline has to look for points of possible entry and close the loopholes—actions that are increasingly hard to do as system architectures integrate more and more new technologies and systems with existing legacy mainframes that are too entrenched to replace. Not only can these disparate systems be attacked, but the integration points themselves create other vulnerabilities.

To close the loopholes, airlines must “capture” and then “apply” learnings. Often, “apply” is much more difficult to execute than “capture.” One way to deal with this problem is to incorporate learning into a metrics program. By tracking and implementing specific improvements identified during lessons-learned, an airline can build a body of knowledge to help it deal with the next incident.

Report threats

While airlines are primarily concerned with their own security, they recognize they are part of a larger aviation ecosystem. This community can play a critical role in providing a countervailing force against organized cyber hacking. If an attack is successful in penetrating one airline, the same kind of attack is likely to be used (or is simultaneously being used) against other airlines.

The aviation industry has an organization dedicated to the sharing of threat information and response and recovery coordination known as A-ISAC (Aviation Information Sharing and Analysis Centre). The ISAC network was established by the US government to help support and protect private-sector organizations that are part of the country’s critical infrastructure. In an ISAC, members can share information anonymously for the mutual benefit of their industry. This proactive sharing helps airlines understand the current threat environment and identify and respond to attacks.

To date, most of threats to the airline industry have focused on obtaining customer data. However, airlines have also been subject to attacks on corporate information, physical systems, and operational disruption. According to an official at the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), aviation systems were subject to approximately 1,000 attacks each month. Ransomware attacks are becoming much more frequent. Criminal organizations are placing an enormous burden on all legitimate businesses competing in the global environment. With the increasing and expanding threats to airlines and aviation, a key way to blunt their

effectiveness is to share information with other members of the industry, forming a collective mechanism for self-defence (Figure 8.11).

Examples

The intentions exist among hackers and the attacks happen.

Figure 8.11 – Intent in safety and security

Miami International (MIA) – 20.000 hack attempts per day

LA Area Airports:

- 2.900.000 hacking attempts in one year;
 - 60.000 cases of internet misuse;
 - Attacks on network baggage systems via malware.
- In June 2015, a Polish aircraft with hundreds of passengers aboard was grounded at the Warsaw airport for about five hours. Airline officials believe it was likely caused by a Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attack. In this kind of attack, an organization's system becomes overloaded by a flood of communication requests, so that it can no longer carry out normal functions.
 - In a 2015 report, the Government Accountability Office (GAO) called for the Federal Aviation Administration to develop "a more comprehensive approach to address cybersecurity" as it embraces next-generation technology. The GAO noted that the aviation regulatory agency had adopted measures to protect its air-traffic control system from cyber intruders. However, it stated that "significant security-control weaknesses remain that threaten the agency's ability to ensure the safe and uninterrupted operation of the national airspace system."

- Aviation Administration to develop “a more comprehensive approach to address cybersecurity” as it embraces next-generation technology. The GAO noted that the aviation regulatory agency had adopted measures to protect its air-traffic control system from cyber intruders (Figure 8.12). However, it stated that “significant security-control weaknesses remain that threaten the agency’s ability to ensure the safe and uninterrupted operation of the national airspace system.”
- The non-profit Centre for Internet Security (CIS) reported a few years ago that 75 US airports were impacted by an Advanced Persistent Threat (APT) attack, including two where the computer systems were compromised. APT hackers are foreign groups with the resources of a nation-state or other large organization behind them. The CIS said it issued a cyber alert to its members after identifying phishing emails and certain kinds of suspicious network traffic.

Figure 8.12 – Cases of Aviation Cyberattack

How does it work?

Cybercrime – tactics, techniques and procedures:

- Malware injection;
- Phishing campaigns;
- Social engineering;
- Mobile malware;
- Physical theft of hardware.

Malware Infection Techniques

- Phishing – widespread email – lots of victims;
- Spear-phishing – targeted email aimed at a few victims;
- Drive by download – tricking search engines (Google, Bing, Yahoo, etc.) to display links to malicious content;
- Fake Anti-virus software – alarming user with false infection warning, tricked into downloading software;
- Pharming/DNS Re-direction – modifying user PC or DNS provider to send traffic to malicious servers;
- Drive-by email – opening email or preview panel.

Mobile malware

- Malware infections of mobile smartphones increased more than 780% from 2011 to end of 2012
- 99% of the mobile malware available specifically targeted Android devices
- Over 6,000 new pieces of Android malware per month in the latter half of 2012
- The largest category of mobile malware in 2012 was SMS Trojans masquerading as legitimate apps. All were designed to target bank accounts

Where cyber criminals come from...

- Nation State Actors – Highly Sophisticated – *state and corporate secrets*;
- Criminal Rings – Organized crime focused on cyber – *money driven*;
- Hacktivists – Cyber criminals with a 'cause' – *political causes*;
- Script Kiddies – Up and comers – *making a name for themselves*.

Location and Risk

- Hand-Held Devices;
- Laptops;
- Desktops;
- Servers/Databases;
- Web Applications;
- POS Equipment;
- Thumb Drives;
- The Cloud – SaaS.

Back to the Basics

- Poor handling of user names and passwords
- Clicking on links from disguised sources
- Mobile malware
- Downloading suspicious software

Cybersecurity is a people problem, not a technology problem.

How to counter act?

“Cybersecurity has become a cost of doing business for airports. All airports can afford it; it is a matter of how much and what sacrifices they are willing to make.”

The Usual Suspects

- Desktops;
- Servers;
- Network devices;

Threat Landscape:

Airports

- Flight Information Systems (FIDS);
- Airfield lighting controls;
- Heating and ventilation systems;
- Baggage handling systems;
- Access control devices;
- Other mission-critical systems that rely on digital technology.

Interconnectivity

- Airlines;
- Concessionaires;
- Tenants;
- Vendors;
- Passengers;
- Anyone who is connected to the airport's network.

Essential Practices

- Identify vulnerabilities and prioritize based on potential impact of a successful attack;
- Adopt countermeasures;
- Hire/Assign a CISO:
 - Incident response team;
 - Threat assessments;
- Audit human and computer behaviour.

8.6 Big Data

Since the advent of mankind knowledge has been limited by several factors: (i) the accurate observation of facts; (ii) the rational identification of their causes; (iii) the definition of effective strategies; (iv) their implementation in the right time frame. Modern technology has advanced most of these fields: (i) a variety of sensors improve situational awareness; (ii) merging sensor data minimizes errors of interpretation; (iii) decision aids and simulations improve predictive capabilities; (iv) computing and automation implement processes at a rate beyond human capabilities. All these activities give an increased access to data, compound the problem of digesting it and increase the benefits of successfully doing so. Modern telecommunications,

data storage and computing can process the large amounts of data gathered to put it to good use. A fast-growing field is to use on-board monitoring of aircraft systems for preventive and on-condition maintenance avoiding long and costly interruptions of service; another is to use operational data to guide design choices for higher reliability and lower cost. At the next level individual aircraft operations can be monitored to improve fleet level efficiency at the scale ranging from an airline to the air traffic management (ATM).

Some of the multiple uses of big data are considered in more detail next (Key Topic T8.5). The processing of big data may use cognitive (Key Topic T8.6) and quantum computing (Key Topic T8.7) and artificial intelligence (section 8.7).

KEY TOPIC T8.5 BIG DATA

With the digitization of most of the processes, emergence of different social network platforms, blogs, deployment of different kind of sensors, adoption of hand-held digital devices, wearable devices and explosion in the usage of Internet, huge amounts of data are being generated on continuous basis. Applications as Internet has changed the way businesses operate, functioning of several sectors and lifestyle of people around the world. Today, this trend is in a transformative stage, where the rate of data generation is very high, and the type of data being generated surpasses the capability of existing data storage techniques. These data carry a lot more information than ever before due to the emergence and adoption of Internet.

Over the past two decades, there has been a tremendous growth in data. This trend can be observed in almost every field. According to a report by International Data Corporation (IDC), a research company claims that between 2012 and 2020, the amount of information in the digital universe will grow by 35 trillion gigabytes.

In the mid-2000s, the emergence of social media, cloud computing, and processing power (through multi-core processors and GPUs) contributed to the rise of big data. As an example, in December 2015, Facebook had an average of 1.04 billion daily active users, 934 million mobile daily active users, available in 70 languages, 125 billion friend connections, 205 billion photos uploaded every day 30 billion pieces of content, 2.7 billion likes, and comments are being posted and 130 average number of friends per Facebook user.

Understanding the great amount of data can help organisations to make informed decisions and provide competitive advantage. In past years, organisations used simple data analysis techniques that helped them to plan and take decisions. However, due to the increase in the size of data especially the unstructured form of data, it has become almost impossible to process these data with the existing storage techniques.

Storage and retrieval of vast amount of structured as well as unstructured data at a desirable time lag is a challenge. Some of these limitations to handle and process vast amount of data with the traditional storage techniques led to the emergence of the term Big Data. Big Data is about how these data can be stored, processed, and comprehended such that it can be used for predicting the future course of action with a great precision and acceptable time delay.

The current and emerging focus of big data analytics is to explore traditional techniques such as rule-based systems, pattern mining, decision trees and other data mining techniques to develop business rules even on the large data sets efficiently. It can be achieved by either developing algorithms that uses distributed data storage, in-memory computation or by using cluster computing for parallel computation. Earlier these processes were carried out using grid computing, which was overtaken by cloud computing in recent days.

- Grid computing: it is a means of allocating the computing power in a distributed manner to solve problems that are typically vast and requires lots of computational time and power. It works on the principle of voluntary basis, where the users share their computing and memory resources to be used by others. In this setting, the goal is to access computers only when needed and to scale the problems in such a manner that even small computers can contribute to the grid. Every computer that is connected to the Internet and wants to become a part of the grid is considered a node in an extremely large computing machine. The main advantage of this computing technique is that it offers an opportunity to harness unused computing power. There are several applications which are using this technology such as weather, astronomy, medicine, multi-player gaming, etc. However, this technology has several disadvantages such as financial, social, legal and regulatory issues.
- Cloud computing: It has its roots from grid computing and other related areas like utility computing, cluster computing and distributing systems, in general. Cloud computing refers to the concept of computing at a remote location with control at the users end through a thin client system, computer or even mobile phones. Processing, memory, and storage will be done at the service providers' infrastructure. Users need to connect to the virtual system residing at some remote location, which might run several virtual operating systems on physical servers with the help of virtualisation. It supports all sorts of fault tolerant features like live migration, scalable storage, and load balancing. Cloud computing also suffers from similar drawbacks of grid computing like data location, data replication, data segregation, security threats, regulatory compliances, recovery issues, long-term viability, high dependency on the Internet for accessing the remote virtual machine, different laws of different countries, investigative support, etc.

In the following image (Figure 8.13), it can be seen a map of the future of big data technologies with an array of emerging technologies that are reaching new levels of diversity, resilience, and adoption:

Figure 8.13 - Big data technologies
 Source 1: TechRadar™: Big Data, Q1 2016

T8.5.1 Definition and Dimensions

The term big data has been defined in different ways, but there is not a specific definition. For example, in 2010, Apache Hadoop defined big data as “datasets, which could not be captured, managed, and processed by general computers within an acceptable scope”. Following this, in 2011, McKinsey Global Institute defined big data as “datasets whose size is beyond the ability of typical database software tools to capture, store, manage, and analyse”. In addition, International Data Corporation (IDC) defines “big data technologies as a new generation of technologies and architectures, designed to economically extract value from very large volumes of a wide variety of data, by enabling high-velocity capture, discovery, and/or analysis”.

On the other hand, Academicians define big data as huge size of unstructured data produced by high-performance heterogeneous group of applications that spans from social network to scientific computing applications. The datasets range from a few hundred gigabytes to zettabytes that it is beyond the capacity of existing data management tools to capture, store, manage and analyse.

However, in addition to defining big data, there is a need to understand how to make the best use of this data to obtain valuable information for decision making.

Initially, big data was characterized by the following dimensions, which were, often, referred as 3V model:

- Volume: it refers to the magnitude of the data that is being generated and collected. The data volume is growing ever faster and, in the future, as the storage capabilities increase, it will be possible to store and capture data more efficiently.
- Velocity: velocity refers to the rate of generation of data. Traditional data analytics is based on periodic updates (daily, weekly or monthly). With the increasing rate of data generation, big data should be processed and analysed in real or near real time to make informed decisions. The time role is a critical factor.
- Variety: Variety refers to different types of data that are being generated and captured. They are within the category of unstructured data, which cannot be organised using a pre-defined data model unlike the structured data. Examples include video, text, and audio.

Later, one more dimension have been added:

- Veracity: Coined by IBM, veracity refers to the unreliability associated with the data sources. There is a need to differentiate the reliable data from uncertain and imprecise data and manage the uncertainty associated with the data.

T8.5.2 Sources of Big Data

The data can be captured from different sectors such as astronomy, agriculture, industry, etc. In addition, Internet of Things (IoT) has become one of the main sources of data. The following Table 8.2 summarises the various types of data produced in different sectors:

Sector	Data produced	Use
Astronomy	Movements of stars, satellites, etc.	To monitor the activities of asteroid bodies and satellites.
Financial	News content via video, audio, twitter and news report	To make trading decisions
Healthcare	Electronic medical records and images	To aid in short-term public health monitoring and long-term epidemiological research programs
Internet of Things (IoT)	Sensor data	To monitor various activities in smart cities
Life sciences	Gene sequences	To analyse genetic variations and potential treatment effectiveness
Media/Entertainment	Content and user viewing behaviour	To capture more viewers
Social Media	Blog posts, tweets, social networking sites, log details	To analyse the customer behaviour pattern
Telecommunications	Call Detail Records (CDR)	Customer churn management

Transportation, Logistics, Retail, Utilities	Sensor data generated from fleet transceivers, tag readers and smart meters	To optimise operations
Video surveillance	Recordings from CCTV to IPTV cameras and recording system	To analyse behavioural patterns for service enhancement and security

Table 8.2 - Sources of data

Source: Big Data: Challenges, Opportunities and Realities, Bhadani and Jothimani, 2016

T8.5.3 Big Data Value Chain

Value Chain, the concept introduced by Porter (1980), refers to a set of activities performed by a firm to add value at each step of delivering a product/service to its customers. In a similar way, data value chain refers to the framework that deals with a set of activities to create value from available data. It can be divided into seven phases: data generation, data collection, data transmission, data pre-processing, data storage, data analysis and decision making.

- Data generation: The first step of the big data value chain is the generation of data. Normally, data is generated from various sources that include data from blogs, tweets, etc.
- Data Collection: in this phase, the data is obtained from all possible data sources. The most commonly used methods are log files, sensors, web crawlers and network monitoring software.
- Data Transmission: Once the data is collected, it is transferred to a data storage and processing infrastructure for further processing and analysis.
- Data Pre-processing: The data collected from various data sources may be redundant or inconsistent. For that reason, in this phase the data is pre-processed to improve the data quality required for analysis. This also helps to improve the accuracy of the analysis and reduce the storage expenses.
- Data Storage: The big data storage systems should provide reliable storage space and powerful access to the data.
- Data Analysis: Once the data is collected, transformed and stored, the next process is data exploitation or data analysis, by defining a set of metrics for a particular problem taking as a base the collected and transformed data as well as selecting the suitable architecture and the appropriate algorithms.
- Decision Making: Based on the analysis of the data collected and results obtained, the next step is to take informed decisions and plan for necessary actions

T8.5.4 Technologies for Analysing Big Data

Tools that are being used to collect data encompass various digital devices (for example, mobile devices, camera, wearable devices, and smart watches) and applications that generate enormous data in the form of logs, text, voice, images, and video. In order to process these data, several researchers are coming up with new techniques that help better representation of the unstructured data, which makes sense in big data context to gain useful insights that may not have been envisioned earlier.

- Not only Structured Query Languages (NoSQL): It is the most commonly used database query language. The data is stored in a data warehouse using dimensional approach and normalized approach. NoSQL stores and manages unstructured data and it allows the scalability of data. Few examples of NoSQL databases are HBase, MangoDB, and Dynamo.
- Hadoop: In 2005, an open source Apache Hadoop project was conceived and implemented on the basis of Google File System and Map Reduce programming paradigm. Apache Hadoop is a software framework that supports distributed applications under a free license. It allows applications to work with thousands of nodes and great amounts of data.
 - Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS): HDFS is the fault-tolerant, scalable, highly configurable distributed storage system for a Hadoop cluster. Data in the Hadoop cluster is broken down into pieces by HDFS and are distributed across different servers in the Hadoop cluster. A small chunk of the whole data set is stored on the server.
 - Hadoop MapReduce: It is a software framework for distributed processing of vast amounts of data in a reliable, fault-tolerant manner. It is divided in two phases: The Map phase, in which the workload is divided into smaller sub-workloads, which are assigned to the Mapper, and it processes each unit block of data to produce a sorted list of pares. Then, in the Reduce phase, the previous list is analysed and merged to produce the final output which is written to the HDFS in the cluster.

The following Table 8.3 summarizes the big data capabilities and the available main technologies:

Big data capability	Primary Technology	Features
Storage and management capability	Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS)	Open source distributed file system, Runs on high-performance commodity hardware, Highly scalable storage and automatic data replication
Database capability	Oracle NoSQL	Dynamic and flexible schema design, Highly scalable multi-node, multiple data centre, fault tolerant, ACID operations, High-performance key-value pair database
	Apache HBase	Automatic failover support between Region servers, Automatic and configurable sharing of tables
	Apache Cassandra	Fault tolerance capability for every node, Column indexes with the performance of log-structured updates and built-in caching
	Apache Hive	Query execution via MapReduce, Uses SQL-like language HiveQL, Easy ETL process either from HDFS or Apache HBase
Processing capability	MapReduce	Distribution of data workloads across thousands of nodes, Breaks problem into smaller sub-problems
	Apache Hadoop	Highly customizable infrastructure, Highly scalable parallel batch processing, Fault tolerant

Data integration capability	Oracle big data connectors, Oracle data integrator	Exports MapReduce results to RDBMS, Hadoop, and other targets, Includes a Graphical User Interface
Statistical analysis capability	R and Oracle R Enterprise	Programming language for statistical analysis

Table 8.3 - Big data capabilities and main technologies

Source 2: Big Data: Challenges, Opportunities and Realities, Bhadani and Jothimani, 2016

T8.5.5 Software Tools

There are several tools that allow processing and analysing data. Many new languages, frameworks and data storage technologies have emerged that supports handling of big data:

- R: is an open-source statistical computing language that provides a wide variety of statistical and graphical techniques to derive insights from the data. It has an effective data handling and storage facility and supports vector operations with a suite of operators for faster processing. A huge number of packages supports R and it is available on Windows, Linux, and Mac platforms. It is a good support for reading and writing in distributed environment, which makes it appropriate for handling big data, but its main challenges are the memory management, speed and efficiency.
- Python: is yet another popular programming language, which is open source and is supported by Windows, Linux and Mac platforms. Libraries such as NumPy, Scikit, and Pandas support some of the popular packages for machine learning and data mining for data pre-processing, computing and modelling. Python is very user-friendly and great for quick analysis on a problem.
- Scala: is an object-oriented language and it is becoming popular programming tool for handling big data problems. It requires java virtual machine environment.
- Apache Spark: is an in-memory cluster computing technology designed for fast computation, which is implemented in Scala. It uses Hadoop for storage purpose as it has its own cluster management capability. It supports R, Map Reduce, SQL, data streaming, graph processing algorithms and machine learning algorithms.
- Apache Hive: is an open source platform that provides facilities for querying and managing large datasets residing in distributed storage. It is similar to SQL and it uses Map Reduce for processing the queries and supports developers to plug in their custom mapper and reducer codes.
- Apache Pig: is a platform that allows analysts to analysing large data sets. It is a high-level programming language, called as Pig Latin for creating MapReduce programs, that requires Hadoop for data storage. The Pig Latin code is extended with the help of User-Defined Functions that can be written in Java, Python and few other languages.
- Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2): is a web service that provides compute capacity over the cloud. It gives full control of the computing resources and allows developers to run their computation in the desired computing environment. It is one of the most successful cloud computing platforms.

T8.5.5 Applications of Big Data

Big data have great applications in several sectors, which are described below:

Healthcare:

Data analysts obtain and analyse information from multiple sources to gain insights. The multiple sources can be various: electronic patient record, clinical decision support system including medical imaging, physician's written notes and prescription, pharmacy and laboratories, etc. The integration of clinical, public health and behavioural data helps to develop a robust treatment system, which can reduce the cost and at the same time, improve the quality of treatment. Data obtained from sensors are monitored and analysed for adverse event prediction and safety monitoring.

In addition, obtaining information from external sources such as social media helps in early detection of epidemics and precautionary efforts. For example, after the earthquake in Haiti in January 2010, analysis of tweets helped to track the spread of Cholera in the region.

Telecommunication

Through data analysis such as demographic data (gender, age, marital status, and language preferences), customer preferences, household structure and usage details, it can be possible to improve the quality of service and customers experience, modelling their preferences and offering a relevant personalized service to them. This is known as targeted marketing, which improves the adoption of mobile services and reduces churn. Companies' analyses data to identify the call patterns to offer different plans to customers. The services are marketed to the customers through a call or text message and their responses are recorded for further analysis.

In addition, telecom companies are working towards combating telecom frauds since traditional fraud management systems are not efficient in detecting new types of fraud. In order to overcome the limitations of traditional fraud management system, real-time data are being analysed to minimize the losses due to fraud. For example, Mobileum Inc., one of the leading telecom analytics solution providers, is working towards providing a real-time fraud detection system using predictive analytics and machine learning.

Financial Firms

Currently, capital firms are using advanced technology to store huge volumes of data. However, increasing data sources like Internet and Social media require them to adopt big data storage systems in addition to the need real-time processing of data. Capital markets are using big data in preparation for regulations, anti-money laundering, fraud mitigation, pre-trade decision-support analytics including sentiment analysis, predictive analytics and data tagging to identify trades.

Retail

Evolution of e-commerce, online purchasing, social-network conversations and recently location specific smartphone interactions contribute to the volume and the quality of data for data-driven customization in retailing. By observing behaviour and purchasing patterns of customers, nowadays, e-commerce firms use this data analysis to segment and target the customers as well as to track the flow of clients and recommend products in real time.

In addition, analytics help the retail companies to manage their inventory. For example, Stage stores, one of the brand names of Stage Stores Inc., which operates in more 40 American states, used to analytics to forecast the order for different sizes of garments for different geographical regions.

Marketing

Marketing analytics helps the organizations to evaluate their marketing performance, to analyse the consumer behaviour and their purchasing patterns, to analyse the marketing trends which would aid in modifying the marketing strategies like the positioning of advertisements in a webpage, implementation of dynamic pricing and offering personalized products.

New Product Development

Analysing data sources, both internal and external can allow understanding the customers' requirement for a new product, gathering ideas for new product as well as understanding the added feature included in a competitor's product. Proper analysis and planning during the development stage can minimize the risk associated with the product, increase the customer lifetime value and promote brand engagement. For example, Ribbon UI in Microsoft 2007 was created by analysing the customer data from previous releases of the product to identify the commonly used features and making intelligent decisions.

Banking

The investment worthiness of the customers can be analysed using demographic details, behavioural data, and financial employment. The concept of cross-selling can be used here to target specific customer segments based on past buying behaviour, demographic details, sentiment analysis, etc.

Energy and Utilities

Consumption of water, gas and electricity can be measured using smart meters at regular intervals of one hour. During this interval, a huge amount of data is generated and analysed to change the patterns of power usage. The real-time analysis reveals energy consumption pattern, instances of electricity thefts and price fluctuations.

Insurance

Personalized insurance plan is adapted for each customer using updated profiles of changes in wealth, customer risk, home asset value, and other data inputs. Recently, the insurance

companies collect driving data of customers such as miles driven, routes driven and time of day, by using sensors in their cars. Comparing individual driving pattern and driver risk with the statistical information available such as peak hours of drivers on the road develops a personalized insurance plan. This analysis of driver risk and policy gives a competitive advantage to the insurance companies.

Education

With the advent of computerized course modules, it is possible to assess the academic performance in real time. This helps to monitor the performance of the students after each module and give immediate feedback on their learning pattern. It also helps the teachers to assess their teaching pedagogy and modify based on the students' performance and needs. Behavioural patterns such as students that require special attention or those students who can face challenging tasks can be predicted.

As an example, the following image (Figure 8.14) shows the main sectors, which have been described previously, in which big data have applications:

Figure 8.14 - Big data applications

Apart from the sectors mentioned previously, big data analytics has a great amount of applications that can be used in many other sectors, such as aviation, construction, meteorology and material sciences.

T8.5.6 Applications of Big Data in Aviation

The new generation of aircraft generate a lot of data from multiple sources (Figure 8.15): flight tracking data, passenger information, airport operations, aircraft information, weather data, airline information, market information and air safety reports besides health and usage monitoring systems (HUMS) of engines and other components. In the following image, it can be seen examples of data sources from the aviation industry:

Figure 8.15 - Aviation industry data sources

Some of these data can be obtained through thousands of sensors and sophisticated digitalised systems that are installed on board an aircraft. The newest generation of jets can collect, with each flight, more than 30 times the amount of data the previous generation of wide-bodied jets produced. Although currently only about one-tenth of the global fleet is made up of these technologically advanced aircraft, it is expected that in a decade this number will increase to the double. By 2026 (Figure 8.16), annual data generation should reach 98 billion gigabytes, or 98 million terabytes, according to a 2016 estimate by Oliver Wyman. By then, the newest generation aircraft will be spewing out between five and eight terabytes per flight, up to 80 times what older planes today generate.

Exhibit 1: Data generated from projected global fleet
 In 2026, the global fleet will generate 98 exabytes of data (That's 98 million terabytes or 98 billion gigabytes)

Figure 8.16 - Data generated form aircraft fleet

Source 3: Oliver Wyman, MRO Survey 2016

Due to this great amount of data, IA and big data analytics will be essential in the future in order to process all this data and extract useful information in real time, since this capacity is very limited nowadays. With hundreds of planes, thousands of flights, and millions of employees and passengers, there is now too much data and too many variables for humans to sort through fast enough to fix problems or even prioritise potential threats. While much of this activity today is mostly reactive, the next step will be for aviation to proactively avoid some of the delays, congestion, and inefficiencies that annoy passengers and keep the global industry at single-digit profit margins.

Using big data analytics to process efficiently the great amount of data from different sources can have several applications on aviation:

Optimising operations

With all the data provided by the newest aircraft, it could be possible to optimise fuel consumption, crew deployment and flight operations. In addition, maintenance could be improved by anticipating parts that need to be replaced, air congestion could be reduced, flight routes could be altered in advance of take-off in order to avoid adverse weather conditions and passengers could be kept informed about schedules and options from the minute they leave their home for the airport. These improvements would make aircraft easier to maintain and more efficient. It also may reduce crew fatigue with more precise scheduling and fill in gaps from anticipated pilot shortages. Moreover, the data could help with the next generation of aircraft by providing information about new ways to improve systems design and performance.

Cost

The new connectivity and advanced analytics also mean savings for airlines; Oliver Wyman's estimate is between 2 percent and 2.5 percent of total global operating costs, which translates

to something between \$5 billion and \$6 billion annually. However, it may take several years, even a decade, to achieve these possibilities. In addition, it could be possible to improve overall fuel cost (not just the consumption) taking into account energy prices, when/where to refuel, optimal flight and taxi paths as well as when/how much to hedge for the fuel

Maintenance

For aviation companies, delays and cancellations are a huge and expensive problem. Up to 30% of the total delay time is due to unplanned maintenance. Advanced analytics rationalize, predict and streamline maintenance, helping aviation clients increase maintenance efficiency, improve the health of their fleet, and reduce delays and cancellations. This predictive maintenance approach can also help improve areas like supply chain optimization, inventory allocation and planning, aircraft reliability improvement and operation and schedule planning.

Therefore, the benefits are:

- Reduced maintenance cost and improved aircraft availability through optimization of the maintenance program.
- Reduced maintenance turnaround time through efficient troubleshooting.
- Reduced parts inventory requirements through integrated supply chain and planning

Weather forecasting

All the data provided by aircraft can be used to predict adverse weather events before they occur. This can have a great impact as flights are incredibly sensitive to weather and knowing future weather events can lead to fewer grounded flights, costly delays, and even danger.

Safety

It is expected that global air traffic increases in the next 10-15 years and, for that reason, the number of accidents will correspondingly increase if nothing is done to improve it. Therefore, new and efficient ways for improving air safety need to be explored.

Due to the vast amount of data produced and collected every day in aviation, valuable information cannot be discovered with traditional analysis method. For example, the reports developed once an accident or incident has happened are an example of the data collected, including several information such as aircraft descriptions, pilot age, pilot experience, operators, time of day, weather, and the factors contributing to the accident (or incident). These reports include both structured and narrative fields. The structured data can be analysed easily using queries from databases and running their results through graphic tools. Among narrative data the situation is totally different. There were no tools to analyse textual data until data mining tools have been developed. Data mining is a broad field of data science, which has had a great development in recent years. Data mining was developed to make predictions on future data based on patterns found in collected data.

Data mining could be used to improve aviation safety by analysing all the data collected from the reports and searching for patterns and anomalies that indicate potential incidents and hazardous situations before they happen. However, this method presents several limitations.

For example, the task requires some knowledge of what should be searched for and found and, therefore, it is necessary to find a method to determine the relevant and important data. In addition, as the data included in reports is overly generalised, it is difficult to identify unknown patterns, and, in consequence, data mining usually discover known trends.

KEY TOPIC T8.6 COGNITIVE COMPUTING

The machines of tomorrow, cognitive systems, will forever change the way people interact with computing systems to help people extend their expertise across any domain of knowledge and make complex decisions involving extraordinary volumes of fast-moving Big Data.

The cognitive systems are a category of technologies that uses natural language processing and machine learning to enable people and machines to interact more naturally to extend and magnify human expertise and cognition. These systems will learn and interact to provide expert assistance to scientists, engineers, lawyers, and other professionals in a fraction of the time it now takes. Far from replacing our thinking, cognitive systems will extend our cognition and free us to think more creatively. In so doing, they will speed innovations and ultimately help build a Smarter Planet.

Cognitive computing refers to systems that learn at scale, reason with purpose and interact with humans naturally. Rather than being explicitly programmed, they learn and reason from their interactions with us and from their experiences with their environment. They are made possible by advances in a number of scientific fields over the past half-century and are different in important ways from the information systems that preceded them.

The success of cognitive computing will not be measured by Turing tests or a computer's ability to mimic humans. The Turing test, developed by Alan Turing in 1950, is a test of a machine's ability to exhibit intelligent behaviour equivalent to, or indistinguishable from, that of a human.

It will be measured in more practical ways, like return on investment, new market opportunities, diseases cured, and lives saved.

T8.6.1 The History of Computing and the Rise of Cognitive Features

To understand the future of cognitive computing, it is important to place it in historical context (Figure 8.17).

- a. **The Tabulating Era (1900s - 1940s).** The birth of computing consisted of single-purpose mechanical systems that counted, using punched cards to input and store data, and to eventually instruct the machine what to do (albeit in a primitive way). These tabulation machines were essentially calculators that supported the scaling of both business and society, helping us to organize, understand, and manage everything from population growth to the advancement of a global economy.
- b. **The Programming Era (1950s - present).** The shift from mechanical tabulators to electronic systems began during World War II, driven by military and scientific needs.

Following the war, digital “computers” evolved rapidly and moved into businesses and governments. They performed if/then logical operations and loops, with instructions coded in software. Originally built around vacuum tubes, they were given a huge boost by the invention of the transistor and the microprocessor, which came to demonstrate “Moore’s Law,” doubling in capacity and speed every 18 months for six decades. Everything we now know as a computing device — from the mainframe to the personal computer, to the smartphone and tablet — is a programmable computer.

- c. **The Cognitive Era (2011 -).** The potential for something beyond programmable systems was foreseen as far back as 1960, when computing pioneer J.C.R. Licklider wrote his seminal paper “Man-Computer Symbiosis.” Much of modern computing is based on Licklider’s research and insights:

“Man-computer symbiosis” is an expected development in cooperative interaction between men and electronic computers. It will involve very close coupling between the human and the electronic members of the partnership. The main aims are: to let computers facilitate formulate thinking as they now facilitate the solution of formulated problems, and to enable men and computers to cooperate in making decisions and controlling complex situations without inflexible dependence on predetermined programs...

Preliminary analyses indicate that the symbiotic partnership will perform intellectual operations much more effectively than man alone can perform them.” - J.C.R. Licklider, “Man-Computer Symbiosis,” March 1960 Licklider knew that cognitive computing would be a necessary and natural evolution of programmable computing, even if he didn’t yet know how it would be accomplished. Fifty years later, massively parallel computing and the accumulation of oceans of structured and unstructured data would lay the groundwork for cognitive computing.

Figure 8.17 - Computing's evolution

Source 4: IBM Computing cognition and the future of knowing, Dr John E. Kelly III

T8.6.2 Watson

In February 2011, the world was introduced to Watson, IBM's cognitive computing system. It was the first widely seen demonstration of cognitive computing. Watson's ability to answer subtle, complex, pun-laden questions made clear that a new era of computing was at hand. Watson has tackled increasingly complex data sets and developed understanding, reasoning and learning that go far beyond deciphering (Figure 8.18). Indeed, the goal of cognitive computing is to illuminate aspects of our world that were previously invisible, patterns and insight in unstructured data, in particular, allowing us to make more informed decisions about more consequential matters.

The true potential of the Cognitive Era will be realized by combining the data analytics and statistical reasoning of machines with uniquely human qualities, such as **self-directed goals**, **common sense** and **ethical values**. This is what Watson was built to do and is in fact already doing.

T8.6.3 Applications of Cognitive Computing

- Economic area: Banks are analysing customer requests and financial data to surface insights to help them make investment recommendations. Companies in heavily regulated industries are querying the system to keep up with ever-changing legislation and standards of compliance.

In a global economy and society where value increasingly comes from information, knowledge and services, this data represents the most abundant, valuable and complex raw material in the world. And until now, we have not had the means to mine it effectively.

- Health area: oncologists are testing ways in which cognitive systems can help interpret cancer patients' clinical information and identify individualized, evidence-based treatment options that leverage specialists' experience and research. Computer science is going to evolve rapidly, and medicine will evolve with it. This is co-evolution.
- Aeronautical area: there are many applications in the field of aeronautics (Figure 8.19), of which the following stand out:
 1. Turbulence detection. Turbulence, especially that caused by thunderstorms (convectively-induced turbulence) has been hard to detect by traditional meteorological sensing methods. With **IBM Watson**, carriers are developing an intelligent detection system that combines IoT (Internet of Things) sensor data, billions of data points from The Weather Company and real-time updates from nearby pilots.
 2. Aviation Maintenance. The company IBM has taken Maximo's 30 years of maintenance/EAM experience and has combined it with IBM's 50+ years of aerospace experience (Apollo, Space Shuttle, & Sabre) and created **Maximo for Aviation**. It addresses the need for a highly configurable, easily upgradeable, web-built enterprise application for aviation maintenance.
 3. Help the pilot to develop a problem with a hydraulic system in flight. The pilot can simply describe the situation in spoken, natural human language. Watson can

interpret the problem logically and then review the technical materials relevant to a solution. It could then make a series of recommendations to the pilot.

4. Reduce delays at airports. Using advanced content analytics, Watson can examine a plane's maintenance history and recommend probable causes and solutions to maintenance issues. How and where would it be integrated into flight control systems?
5. Communicate with the customers on travel and add-on travel services such as; a hotel, rental car, and even restaurant suggestions. One key area where Watson can help airlines is through real-time personalization and offers. Watson can provide real-time personalization of price and offers by estimating a customer's propensity-to-pay and response to offers. To do this, Watson learns about the customer, their journey, and the various product attributes.
6. A new technology dubbed **R3** designed to better predict and manage air traffic volume as well as deliver more real-time information about an aviation event. R3 stands for responsive, reliable and real-time and created at IBM's Watson research lab. The joint project was designed to coordinate more flights in the same airspace. The air traffic issue is a big one considering that flight traffic is expected to double or triple by 2025.
7. This picture shows how Watson IoT platform and **Weather Company** data can be used to integrate sensors and mobile clients. With advances in avionics and the availability of cheap computing resources such as Raspberry Pi, a simple ground station may be easily built. Once configured, ground stations can be replicated using Docker to be able to cover large areas.

Figure 8.18 - Watson IoT platform and Weather Company data
Source 5: IBM DeveloperWorks

8. One of the major goals of researchers at NASA's Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) is to remotely control vehicles for extra-planetary exploration, rather than manually manoeuvring vehicles or programming robotic sequences in advance and letting them run.
9. Another application of cutting-edge Virtual Reality (VR) tech in space exploration currently in use is testing new vehicles in virtual space before building prototypes in physical space (Figure 8.20). Additionally, VR helps the crews prepare for obstacles they may encounter on missions. This is especially useful in orbital trajectory planning where pilots can practice manoeuvring certain flight paths according to the actual physics of space, but from the safety of a space-like digital environment. VR training is also handy to help prep for day-to-day life in space.
10. Researchers at NASA's Armstrong Flight Research Centre have started exploring the possibility of employing IBM Watson as a flight operations advisor. In this role, NASA flight crews would leverage Watson's ability to crunch large amounts of aviation data that come in from any number of devices to help with rapid decision-making. By tasking Watson with the heavy research needed to quickly identify and respond to unforeseen circumstances in-flight, NASA hopes to offload the brunt of real-time research usually performed by both in-flight and ground crews on the cognitive computer. In a not-too-distant future cloud-based cognitive computer like Watson could just as easily be our new co-pilots.

Figure 8.19 - Aeronautical applications of cognitive computing

Figure 8.20 - NASA Virtual reality and cognitive computing, Wired Brand Lab
Source 6: IBM Internet of Things blog

Some very complex problems like Air Traffic Management (ATM) still defy computing tools. IBM famously failed in the 1980s a large contract of 6.3 B\$ from FAA (Federal Aviation Administration) to automate ATM in the US; this was before the advances in cognitive computing that are now contributing to model parts of the ATM system.

KEY TOPIC T8.7 QUANTUM COMPUTING

Quantum computers are incredibly powerful machines that take a new approach to processing information. Built on the principles of quantum mechanics, they exploit complex and fascinating laws of nature that are always there, but usually remain hidden from view. By harnessing such natural behaviour, quantum computing can run new types of algorithms to process information more holistically. This extraordinary scaling will advance the state of the art in software verification and validation, cryptography, drug discovery, machine learning, cyber security, finance and many other areas where innovation is bounded by the limits of high-performance computing.

In quantum computing, a **qubit** (short for "quantum bit") is a unit of quantum information, the quantum analogue to a classical bit. Qubits have special properties that help them solve complex problems much faster than classical bits. One of these properties is superposition, which states that instead of holding one binary value ("0" or "1") like a classical bit, a qubit can hold a combination of "0" and "1" simultaneously. When multiple qubits interact coherently, they can explore multiple options and process information in a fraction of the time it would take even the fastest non-quantum systems.

T8.7.1 Aeronautic Application

Artificial Intelligence (AI) could be described as the attempt to make machines think like humans. It is an idea that is more than 70 years old, and Airbus has long had AI applications (Figure 8.21). Airbus Helicopters has been using an artificial neural network since 2005 to adjust its rotor blades.

Figure 8.21 - AI and airspace

Source 7: Airbus

But now, with IBM Watson, it can process huge volumes of data and discover new, previously unknown root causes by establishing correlations that a human would never come up with. For example, Watson determined the precise relationship between the temperature and early wear of brakes. This is a completely new finding, which will allow Airbus to develop prognostics that help airlines avoid delays.

According to experts, the potential of AI for Airbus can be best illustrated using the A350 XWB as an example: the aircraft has some 50,000 sensors on board and collects 2.5 terabytes of data every day. If you let AI loose on this data, then problems and correlations can be recognised faster, and aircraft maturity can be achieved more quickly. In addition, developers inside the Airbus Group are already working on the next steps; for example, they are exploring ways in which AI can help make **UAVs** and passenger aircraft even safer.

It is very likely that we will see self-flying parcel delivery UAVs in the next ten years. Moreover, if passenger planes can fly more safely with AI on board, they will be doing the same before long.

A further area where deep learning has made considerable progress is in image recognition. However, they are working on it to get the error rate of identification of these objects lower.

T8.7.2 Airbus & Quantum Computing

Rather than building a quantum computer itself, Airbus is working with academia and IT companies to define the algorithms needed to utilise the immense power of the new technology.

The company could potentially use quantum computers in digital modelling and simulation, such as the airflow over its airliners' wings or a complete airframe to improve efficiency (Figure 8.22) as a method of implementation of CFU (Computational Fluid Mechanics).

Figure 8.22 - More efficient designs of aircraft with quantum computers

Source 8: Airbus's quantum computing brings Silicon Valley to the Welsh Valleys, The Telegram

Being able to see airflows at this level of detail would allow the companies to squeeze every fraction of efficiency out of a design, potentially cutting fuel consumption, reducing drag and improving lift. In addition, the ability to simulate new ideas at the atomic level could also speed up development of other aircraft, including helicopters, structures and even materials.

Airbus is also sponsoring PhDs in quantum computing to help attract highly skilled people into the field. The quality of results depends both on the validity of physical models and ability to compute them accurately.

8.7 Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence has steadily developed as an academic discipline since dedicated languages like LISP and PROLOG have gained wide acceptance. Artificial Intelligence is based on a learning process whereby a large pool of repetitive experience induces a number of operating rules, procedures or interpretations. As such AI is suited to repetitive frequent events and less able with to cope with isolated exceptional occurrences. The advent of big data can provide AI with the vast pools of information needed to implement learning algorithms. The competition towards autonomous or self-driving cars is one of the impetus for AI aiming to learn the habits and preferences of the individual by reference to sensor and monitoring data.

The adoption of AI techniques in one transport sector like automotive will eventually spread to other sectors like aeronautics. One of the most frequent claims about AI is that it can prevent accidents and is potentially safer than humans. In fact, this may be a double-edged sword: (i) AI is at its best in repetitive well monitored situations for which it is trained to act without failure or the variability of humans; (ii) AI can hardly cope with unpredictable situations it was not trained for where human ingenuity could do better. Thus, the scope and domain of

application of AI needs to be carefully defined to stay within its learning experience. AI developed for a well signalled road may not work on an unmarked road.

Aircraft accidents are extremely rare events for which it is difficult to train, that are best avoided by strict safety precautions, and failing those survival may depend on imaginative human action. AI could potentially be applied to all aspects of aeronautics: (i) least critical and already in use with moderate success is in fault diagnosis as part of preventive maintenance or failure detection; (ii) its extension to the pilot cockpit would likely be more controversial still than autonomous or self-driving cars in roads and city streets; (iii) its application to air traffic management (ATM) would be a step beyond full automation, which is not considered feasible at present. The application of AI in aeronautics may be gradual starting to prove itself in simpler non-safety critical situations for which other independent checks are available.

The multiple implications of artificial intelligence in the aeronautical sector (Key Topic T8.8) can be best understood from its historical evolution (Key Topic T8.9).

KEY TOPIC T8.8 IMPLICATIONS OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Artificially intelligent systems currently utilize computers to emulate various faculties of human intelligence and biological metaphors. They use a combination of symbolic and sub-symbolic systems capable of evolving human cognitive skills and intelligence, not just systems capable of doing things humans do not do well. Intelligent systems are ideally suited for tasks such as search and optimization, pattern recognition and matching, planning, uncertainty management, control, and adaptation [1].

Artificial intelligence methods are applied to these control problems in which the control object cannot be adequately described by the equations of dynamics, such as differential equations, finite differences, transfer functions etc. The impossibility of adequate, accurate description can lead to failures, malfunctions, and other problems, which cannot be obtained in advance and can be assessed only in real time operation. Thus, the intelligent control must be able to receive the information about the object, the destabilizing effect of varying operating conditions, to form conclusions, make decisions, and to stabilize the control and train.

Intelligent System (IS) applications have gained popularity among aerospace professionals due to the ease with which several of the IS tools can be implemented. In addition to this ease of implementation, IS has been shown to solve difficult problems more efficiently.

Intelligent systems are software-intensive systems that are loosely patterned after human abilities associated with learning and reasoning during adaptive planning and problem solving. In aerospace systems and system-of-systems (SoS), intelligent systems typically take the form of autonomous systems, associate systems, or aiding systems. IS are characterized by facilities for knowledge acquisition and understanding, model-driven and evidence-based reasoning, adaptability, ability to transform data into compiled knowledge, and various forms of machine learning including supervised, unsupervised, semi-supervised, and reinforcement learning [2].

Aerospace techniques intellectualization is a current problem of scientific and technical research. This is expressed in extension and improvement of many functions of aircraft control and taking the human operator out of the control loop through the use of artificial intelligence.

Aerospace technology intellectualization will result in [3]:

- Effective solving navigation tasks without dispatchers and navigator assistance. The concept of 4-d navigation and free flights (out of fixed routes);
- Carrying out profound diagnostics and workability recovery without ground services participation, during both flight and pre-flight;
- Implementation of a number of other complex facilities requiring intelligent support.

Intelligent support aims to reduce information overload, to deliver automation of aviation complex control, to supply a crew with situational awareness, to help making decision in a complex environment.

Intellectualization of aerospace systems is the constructive way to improve safety of aerospace system operation, due to the fact that the human factor is often a reason of flight incidents and accidents.

In aerospace engineering, IS come into play in a variety of mission contexts [4]. They take the form of autonomous systems for performing tasks that tend to be hazardous or that humans perform poorly [5,6]. Examples of such tasks are monitoring infrequent stimulus (i.e., low probability but potentially high consequence events), monitoring high density events that exceed human cognitive processing ability, and operating in hazardous environments [5,6]. They take the form of associate systems to offload humans in tasks that are generally performed by humans [7]. They take the form of aiding systems for routine tasks, tasks that require perfect recall of information (e.g., viable options for a known decision situation), and tasks that require looking ahead to assess future outcomes, under different assumptions, before making decisions.

The role of humans in IS has a major impact on system architecture design and algorithm selection. When the role of the human is central to IS (i.e., human is not expected to be replaced by automation in the foreseeable future), the architecture needs to capitalize on the strengths of the human and machine respectively while circumventing their respective limitations. The primary emphasis needs to be on joint human-machine system performance. On the other hand, if the human role is not central to IS (i.e., the human is likely to be replaced by automation in the foreseeable future), then the architecture needs to be driven by performance and applicable non-functional requirements such as solution scalability, cybersecurity, resilience, and affordability.

Future intelligent systems technologies can provide increased adaptive and autonomous capabilities at all levels of autonomy. At the lowest level of autonomy, adaptation through closed-loop control and prognostics enables aerospace systems to be more resilient and intelligent by automatically adjusting system operations to cope with unanticipated changes in system performance and operating environment. At mid-level of autonomy, planning and scheduling provide capabilities to perform automatic task allocation and contingency

management to reduce human operator workloads and improve situational awareness and mission planning. At high levels of autonomy, automated reasoning and decision support systems provide higher degrees of intelligence to enable aerospace systems to achieve autonomous operations without direct human supervision in the loop.

Adaptive systems are an important enabling feature common to all these levels of autonomy. Adaptability is a fundamental requirement of autonomous systems that enable a wide range of capabilities at the foundational level.

Capabilities of adaptive systems include:

- Learning and optimizing system behaviours to improve system performance and safety;
- Intelligent use of resources in aerospace processes;
- Estimate aerospace system's long term and short-term behaviours.

Machine learning techniques are commonly used in many adaptive systems. These techniques sometimes employ neural networks to model complex system behaviours. The use of multi-layer neural networks can result in non-determinism due to random weight initialization. Non-deterministic behaviours of these adaptive systems can cause many issues for safety assurance and verification and validation.

A future research goal is to develop simplified adaptive systems that reduce the introduction of non-determinism. Despite the potential benefits of neural network applications in adaptive systems, real world experiences through recent flight research programs seem to suggest that simplified adaptive systems without neural networks may perform better in practice than those with neural networks. Simplified adaptive systems may have other advantages in that they may be easier to be verified and validated, and there are some existing adaptive control methods that can be applied to assess the stability margins and performance of those systems.

Computational intelligence (CI) is the study of the design of intelligent agents where an agent is an entity that reacts and interacts with its environment. An intelligent agent refers to an agent that adapts to its environment by changing its strategies and actions to meet its shifting goals and objectives. The methodologies making up Computational Intelligence mostly fall under the areas of fuzzy logic, rough sets, neural networks, evolutionary computation, and swarm intelligence.

The ability to bring high-performance and efficient control to difficult problems with a far less intimate study of the physics behind the system, and thus fewer, if any, unrealistic mathematical assumptions and constraints is the highlight of the CI tools.

The success of CI tools in limited applications opens up the imagination and enables us to boldly envision a wide variety of future aerospace applications involving numerous interactions between teams of humans and increasingly autonomous systems. An additional advantage of this class of hybrid CI approaches is that while the exploration of the solution space utilizes stochastic parameters during the learning process, once the learning system converges to a solution, the subsequent decision-making is deterministic which lends itself far better for verification and validation.

Traditional aerospace missions or scenarios tend to limit themselves when it comes to concerns about autonomous decision-making in uncertain large-scale problems. Operational doctrine development and technology advancement need to go hand-in-hand as they are far more coupled in an increasingly complex aerospace environment. A simulation-based effort may be required to enhance the “daring” and to develop the confidence in the development of operational doctrines. This calls for interaction between the user and engineering communities that traditionally do not exchange much in terms of early research and exploration of ideas and exploitation of potentially powerful computational intelligent tools [8].

KEY TOPIC T8.9 EVOLUTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

In recent years, there have been several emerging technologies, which have provided benefits to various fields. However, there are several emerging trends which are expected to have a great development in the following years, and other technologies which are currently being developed and has a great potential. In the following image, it can be seen the Gartner Hype Cycle for Emerging Technologies (Figure 8.23) for the year 2017, in which the emerging technologies trend, which are expected to have a great development, are shown:

Figure 8.23- Gartner Hype Cycle for emerging Technologies
Source 9: Gartner (July 2017)

As it can be seen in the previous picture, some of the emerging technologies which are expected to have a great development in the future are Artificial Intelligence (T8.8 – T8.9), Big

data (T8.5) analytics, Quantum computing (T8.6) and Cognitive Computing (T8.7). Artificial Intelligence is considered next in more detail, starting from an historical perspective.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a commonly employed appellation to refer to the field of science aimed at providing machines with the capacity of performing functions such as logic, reasoning, planning, learning, and perception. Nowadays, the term AI encompasses the whole conceptualisation of a machine that is intelligent in terms of both operational and social consequences.

Current AI technologies are used in many fields such as driving, aviation, medicine and personal assistance and image recognition. An example are the vehicles known as autonomous cars. These vehicles are equipped with accurate cameras and sensors, which enable recognition of their three-dimensional environment and provides the ability to make intelligent decisions on manoeuvres in variable, real-traffic road conditions. Another example is the Alpha-Go, developed by Google Deepmind, to play the board game Go. Last year, Alpha-Go defeated the Korean grandmaster Lee Sedol, becoming the first machine to beat a professional player and recently it went on to win against the current world number one, Ke Jie, in China.

However, current AI technologies are limited to very specific applications. One limitation of AI, for example, is the lack of "common sense", that is to say, the ability to judge information beyond its acquired knowledge. A recent example is the AI robot Tay developed by Microsoft and designed for making conversations on social networks. It had to be disconnected shortly after its launch because it was not able to distinguish between positive and negative human interaction. AI is also limited in terms of emotional intelligence. AI can only detect basic human emotional states such as anger, joy, sadness, fear, pain, stress and neutrality. Emotional intelligence is one of the next frontiers of higher levels of personalisation. True and complete AI does not yet exist. At this level, AI will mimic human cognition to a point that it will enable the ability to dream, think, feel emotions and have own goals. Although there is no evidence yet, this kind of true AI could exist before 2050, nevertheless the computer science principles driving AI forward are rapidly advancing and it is important to assess its impact, not only from a technological standpoint, but also from a social, ethical and legal perspective.

T8.9.1 History of AI

The following image (Figure 8.24) shows a timeline, which highlights the most relevant events of AI since 1950. The blue boxes represent events that have had a positive impact on the development of AI while the red boxes represent those events with a negative impact.

Figure 8.24– AI Timeline
 Source 10: Artificial intelligence and robotics, UK-RAS network

The evolution of AI to date, has endured several periods since the term AI was coined in the Dartmouth Conference of 1956. Before that, there were already advances in cybernetics and neural networks, which started to attract the attention of both the scientific communities and the public. During the 1960s, computers of the time could solve algebra and geometric problems, as well as speak English. These advances were received with optimism, however, in the 1970s the field of AI endured fierce criticism and budgetary restrictions, as AI research development did not match the overwhelming expectations of researchers. As a result, investment in AI by major agencies such as DARPA, the National Research Council and the British Government had an abrupt end and the field was stagnated for the next 10 years.

From 1980 until 1987, there was a revival of the field as AI programmes, called “expert systems”, were adopted by companies and knowledge acquisition became the central focus of AI research. At the same time, the Japanese government launched a massive funding program on AI, with its fifth-generation computers initiative. However, due to the difficulty of updating and reprogramming the expert systems, in addition to the high maintenance costs, they were displaced by new desktop computers developed by Apple and IBM, which had gradually improved their speed and power. In the 1990s, the new concept of “intelligent agent” emerged. An agent is a system that perceives its environment and undertakes actions that maximize its chances of being successful. The concept of agents conveys, for the first time, the idea of intelligent units working collaboratively with a common objective. This new paradigm was intended to mimic how humans work collectively in groups, organizations and/or societies. Intelligent agents proved to be a more polyvalent concept of intelligence. In the late 1990s, fields such as statistical learning from several perspectives including probabilistic, frequentist and possibilistic (fuzzy logic) approaches, were linked to AI to deal with the uncertainty of decisions. This brought a new wave of successful applications for AI, beyond what expert systems had achieved during the 1980s.

From 1997 to 2000, the field of AI was progressing behind the scenes, as no further multi-million programs were announced. Despite the lack of major funding the area continued to progress, as increased computer power and resources were developed. New applications in specific areas were developed and the concept of “machine learning” started to become the cornerstone of AI. Since 2000, with the success of the Internet and web, the Big Data revolution started to take off along with newly emerged areas such as Deep Learning. Great advances were also made in computer vision, improving visual perception, increasing the capabilities of intelligent agents and robots in performing more complex tasks, combined with visual pattern recognition. All these paved the way to new AI challenges such as, speech recognition, natural language processing, and self-driving cars.

In the following years, it is expected that the rise of AI-as-a-service platforms, with lower barriers to entry, will allow companies to scale cognitive solutions in a zero-marginal cost setting and reshape industry dynamics. Moreover, while it is hard to predict the specific AI technology adoption paths over the next 10 to 15 years, the overarching impact themes are easier to envision, with AI technologies creating and changing the value proposition across all domains (Figure 8.25). Products and services will compete based on hyper-personalized,

cognitive features. Firms will leverage AI to process customer preferences in real time, so as to rapidly scale personalized products and services, as consumers become brand agnostic and more willing to pay for hyper-personalized offerings. Organizations will also become efficient hierarchies (companies typically face a trade-off between efficiency of scale and hierarchical nimbleness). Large global firms and institutions, with economies of scale that have never been unleashed due to the complex coordination required, will benefit from AI; they will use AI applications to rapidly assess, predict and simulate decisions across silos, spans and layers. Industrial companies are moving rapidly into the AI domain, investing in R&D around the “industrial internet”. Analytics is being deployed for asset performance management and operations optimization, AI is improving safety and accessibility in the automotive industry and intelligent scheduling software is being adapted to real-time production variability. AI systems are enabling new levels of production system optimization, such as predictive maintenance and improved quality management. Natural language processing can be adopted to create task-specialized personal assistants, as well as platforms for conversational technologies that can be provided as a service and integrated in various applications. Computer vision capabilities enhance visual navigation for self-driving cars as well as 3D scanning. Pattern recognition can identify customer preferences and be deployed to aid drug

discovery. AI reasoning and optimization technologies are penetrating the value chain in various industries, such as the automotive sector, and currently inform 75% of consumer picks on Netflix. AI is used to optimize the multi-robot fulfilment system in Amazon warehouses.

Figure 8.25 - Development of AI and its future state

Source 11: Technology and Innovation for the Future of Production: Accelerating Value Creation

T8.9.2 Financial Impact of AI

It has been well recognised that AI amplifies human potential as well as productivity and this is reflected in the rapid increase of investment across many companies and organisations.

These include sectors in healthcare, manufacturing, transport, energy, banking, financial services, management consulting, government administration and marketing/advertising. The revenues of the AI market worldwide, were around 260 billion US dollars in 2016 and this is estimated to exceed \$3,060 billion by 2024. This has had a direct effect on robotic applications, including exoskeletons, rehabilitation, surgical robots and personal care-bots. The economic impact of the next 10 years is estimated to be between \$1.49 and \$2.95 trillion. Therefore, IA is a sector with a great potential of development, as in can be seen in the next image (Figure 8.26):

Figure 8.26 - Venture capital investment in AI technology worldwide
 Source 12: Artificial intelligence and robotics, UK-RAS network

As a result, there is a huge potential for economic growth and, for that reason, major technological firms are investing into applications for speech recognition, natural language processing and computer vision. For example, companies such as Google, Microsoft, Apple, Amazon or Facebook made between 2014 and 2015 26 acquisitions of companies developing AI technology, totalling over \$5 billion cost.

In 2014, Google acquired DeepMind, a London-based start-up company specialising in deep learning, for more than \$500M and set a record of company investment of AI research to academic standard. One of the achievements of DeepMind was in developing AI technology able to create general-purpose software agents that adjust their actions based only on a cumulative reward. On the other hand, IBM has developed a supercomputer platform, Watson, which has the capability to perform text mining and extract complex analytics from large volumes of unstructured data. To demonstrate its abilities, IBM Watson, in 2011, beat two top players on 'Jeopardy!', a popular quiz show, that requires participants to guess questions from specific answers. This achievement has had a significant impact on the performance of web searches and the overall ability of AI systems to interact with humans. In 2015, IBM bought AlchemyAPI to incorporate its text and image analysis capabilities in the cognitive computing

platform of the IBM Watson. The system has already been used to process legal documents and provide support to legal duties. Experts believe that these capabilities can transform current health care systems and medical research.

Research in top AI firms is centred on the development of systems that are able to reliably interact with people. Interaction takes more natural forms through real-time speech recognition and translation capabilities. Robo-advisor applications are at the top of the AI market with a globally estimated 255 billion in US dollars by 2020. There are already several virtual assistants offered by major companies. For example, Apple offers Siri and Amazon Alexa, Microsoft offers Cortana, and Google has the Google Assistant. In 2016, Apple purchased Emotient, a start-up using artificial-intelligence technology to read people's emotions by analysing facial expressions and DeepMind created WaveNet, which is a generative model that mimics human voices.

Recently, OpenAI, a non-profit organisation, has been funded as part of a strategic plan to mitigate the risks of monopolising AI. OpenAI has re-designed evolutionary algorithms that can work together with deep neural networks to offer state-of-the-art performance. It is considered to rival DeepMind since it offers similar open-source machine learning libraries to TensorFlow, a deep learning library distributed by Google DeepMind. Nevertheless, the big difference between the technology developed at OpenAI and the other private tech companies, is that the created Intellectual Property is accessible by everyone.

The following Table 8.4 shows the major companies which invest in IA:

	Technology/Platforms	AI applications of significant impact
Google DeepMind	Search engine, Maps, Ads, Gmail, Android, Chrome, and YouTube	Self-driving cars: Technology that allows a car to navigate in normal traffic without any human control.
	Deep Q-network: Deep Neural Networks with Reinforcement Learning at scale.	AlphaGo: The first computer program to beat professional players of Go. DQN: Better than human-level control of Atari games through Deep Reinforcement Learning. Wavenet: Raw audio form impersonating any human voice
IBM	Manufacturer of computer hardware and software Hosting and consulting services Cognitive Computing	Deep Blue: First computer program to defeat world champion chess player Watson: Won top players on 'Jeopardy!', a popular quiz show.
Facebook	Social Networking Service	Applied Machine Learning: Spot suicidal users Human Computer Interaction: Image Descriptions for Blind Users
Apple Inc.	Computer hardware and software Consumer electronics Online services	Siri: AI Virtual Assistant Self-driving car: AI technology that could drive a car without human interaction.

	Technology/Platforms	AI applications of significant impact
Amazon	Cloud Computing Online retail services Electronics	Alexa: AI virtual assistant Amazon AI platform: Cloud software and hardware AI tools
Microsoft	Developing, manufacturing and licensing computer hardware and software Consumer electronics	Microsoft Azure: Cloud services Cortana: AI virtual assistant

Table 8.4 - Major companies in AI
Source 13: Artificial intelligence and robotics, UK-RAS network

As it can be seen in the next image (Figure 8.27), China and the United States dominate investments in artificial intelligence. European companies including ABB, Bosch, BMW and Siemens are investing in AI, but overall Europe is behind in external Ai investment, which totalled 3\$ to 4\$ billion in 2016, compared with 8\$ to 12\$ billion in Asia and \$15 to \$23 billion in North America.

Figure 8.27 - Artificial intelligence investment in 2016
Source 14: McKinsey & Company

T8.9.3 Hardware of AI

According to Gordon Moore’s prediction, the number of transistors, in a dense integrated circuit, doubles approximately every two years. This prediction has been accurate for several decades and has been used in the semiconductor industry to guide long-term planning. Today, his prediction is still valid, and the number of transistors is increasing even if, after 2005, the frequency and the power started to reduce, leading to a core scaling rather than a frequency improvement. In the future, experts believe that revolutionary technologies may help sustain Moore's law. One of the key challenges will be the design of gates in nanoscale transistors and

the ability of controlling the current flow as, when the device dimension shrinks, the connection between transistors becomes more difficult.

Figure 8.28 - History of general-purpose CPUs: Evolution of main characteristics
Source 15: Artificial intelligence and robotics, UK-RAS network

Modern machines combine powerful multicore CPUs (Figure 8.28) with dedicated hardware designed to solve parallel processing. GPU and FPGA are the most popular dedicated hardware commonly available in workstations developing AI systems.

- A GPU (Graphics Processing Unit) is a chip designed to accelerate the processing of multidimensional data such as an image. A GPU consists of thousands of smaller cores, intended to work independently on a subspace of the input data that needs heavy computation. Repetitive functions that can be applied to different parts of the input, such as texture mapping, image rotation, translation and filtering, are performed at a much faster rate and more efficiently, through the use of the GPU. A GPU has dedicated memory and the data must be moved in and out in order to be processed.
- FPGA (Field Programmable Gate Array) is a reconfigurable digital logic containing an array of programmable logic blocks and a hierarchy of reconfigurable interconnections. An FPGA is not a processor and therefore it cannot run a program stored in the memory. An FPGA is configured using a hardware description language (HDL) and unlike the traditional CPU, it is truly parallel. This means, that each independent processing task is assigned to a

dedicated section of the chip and many parts of the same program can be performed in simultaneously

While a GPU is designed to perform efficiently, with similar threads on different subsets of the input, an FPGA is designed to parallelize sequential serial processing of the same program.

T8.9.4 Subfields and Applications of AI

AI is a diverse field of research and it is composed of many subfields, few of them include:

- Neural Networks;
- Evolutionary and Genetic Computing;
- Vision Recognition;
- Robotics;
- Expert Systems;
- Speech Processing;
- Natural Language Processing;
- Machine Learning.

T8.9.4.1 Neural Networks

The study of Neural Networks (NNs) began with an aim to replicate the thought process of a human brain. It refers to a huge network of data sets which are interconnected and continuously sending data to each other. Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is a computational structure intended to mimic biological neural networks. It is composed of a large number of highly interconnected processing elements called neurons. The mass of an interconnection is a quantity that states the strength of the associated interconnection. The foremost representative of ANNs is their capability to study. Normally, An ANN is configured for a specific application, such as pattern recognition or data classification.

An Artificial Neural Network is specified by:

- Neuron model: the information-processing unit of the NN,
- An architecture: a set of neurons and links connecting neurons. Each link has a weight,
- A learning algorithm: used for training the NN by modifying the weights in order to model a particular learning task correctly on the training examples.

Some of their applications are:

- Character Recognition: Character recognition has become very significant as handheld devices are becoming gradually popular. Neural networks can be used to recognize handwritten characters.

- Image Compression: NNs can receive and process huge amounts of information at once, building them beneficial in image compression. With the cyber explosion and many sites using more images on their sites, using neural networks for image compression is useful.
- Stock Market Prediction: Now a day, the stock market is becoming extremely complicated. Several factors weigh in whether a given stock will go raise or fall on any given day. Meanwhile neural networks can inspect a proportion of information quickly and grouping it all out; they can be used to forecast stock prices.
- Medicine, Security, and Loan Applications
- Weather forecasting: Neural networks are nowadays being used for predicting weather conditions. Past data is provided to the neural network, which then analyses the data for patterns and predicts the future weather conditions

T8.9.4.2 Genetic Computing

In environment, evolution is mostly resolved by natural selection or various individuals competing for resources in the environment. Those individuals that are well adapted are more likely to survive and disseminate their genetic material. The encoding procedure for genetic information (genome) is done in a way that confesses asexual reproduction, which outcomes in children that are genetically identical to the parent. Sexual reproduction allows some exchange and restructuring of chromosomes, producing offspring that contain a grouping of information from each parent. This is the recombination operation, which is often named to as crossover because of the way strands of chromosomes cross over during the exchange. The assortment in the population is achieved by mutation operation procedure. The Genetic computing imitate this process in order to solve difficult problems.

Some of the applications of genetic computing are:

- Automotive Design: Use of Genetic Systems to both select compound materials and aerodynamic shapes for race cars and consistent means of shipping (including aeronautics) can return groupings of best materials and best engineering to deliver faster, more fuel efficient and harmless vehicles
- Robotics: Genetic algorithms can be encoded to search for a range of optimal designs and machineries for each specific use, or to return results for absolutely new types of robots that can achieve multiple tasks and have more universal application.
- Evolvable Hardware: Hardware applications are electronic circuits which are created by genetic algorithm computer prototypes which will use stochastic (statistically random) operators to progress new patterns from old ones. Consequently, genetic algorithms would enable self-adaptation and self-repair.
- Optimized Telecommunications Routing: the genetic algorithms have been developed that will allow for dynamic and anticipatory routing circuits for networks telecommunications. They are being developed to enhance placement and routing of cell towers for good coverage and comfort of switching.
- Invention of Biomimetic: Biomimetic is the term which indicates the development of technologies encouraged by designs in nature. Programmers of genetic algorithms are

working on applications that not only to analyse the natural designs themselves for a return on how they work, but also join natural designs to create something entirely new that can have unforeseen applications.

- Code breaking and Encryption: For the security front, genetic algorithms can be used both to create encryption for data as well as to break the codes.
- Computerized Molecular Design: The genetic algorithms are used to help in the understanding of protein folding, evaluating the effects of substitutions on protein functions, and to identify the binding attractions of several designed proteins industrialized by the pharmaceutical industry for better treatment of special infections.

T8.9.4.3 Vision Recognition

Computer Vision is the science and technology of gaining models, sense and control information from visual data. Computer vision can be divided into computational vision and machine vision. Computational vision takes to ensure with simply recording and exploring the visual acuity and trying to recognize it. Machine vision has to do with by means of what is found from computational vision and relating it to profit people, animals, environment, etc.

In several computer vision applications, the computers are pre-programmed to solve a certain task, but techniques based on learning are now becoming gradually common. Examples of applications of computer vision include systems for:

- Monitoring processes, e.g., Industrial robot;
- Collaboration, e.g., as the input to a device for computer-human interaction;
- Military, e.g., discovery of enemy soldiers or vehicles and missile guidance;
- Automatic inspection, e.g., in industrialized applications;
- Agriculture process, e.g., optical sorting;
- Navigation, e.g., by an autonomous vehicle or mobile robot;
- Modelling substances or surroundings, e.g., medical image analysis;
- Support of visual effects design for cinema and broadcast, e.g., camera tracking.

T8.9.4.4. Speech Recognition

Speech recognition is one of the most innovative conceptions of electrical engineering and computer science. Essentially, speech recognition or computer speech recognition is nothing more than the approach of transforming a speech signal into the sequence of words, by the help of different systems and procedures.

Speech recognition is also stated as ASR (Automatic Speech Recognition), STT (Speech to text) or just computer speech recognition. Artificial intelligence is one of the most developing and effective techniques, which supports faultless and exact speech recognition.

AI is widely used in different areas, including prosaic signals and traffic lights, robotic household gear, conservation systems and homemade security, healthcare robotics, credit card trades, cell phones (smart phones), and video games.

- Automated identification - Australia's 8th largest insurers, ahm Health Management is effectively using speech biometrics to allow present account holders to speak to customer service representatives rapidly and securely. The company has registered more than 20,000 customers' voiceprints.
- Removing IVR menus - By announcing Natural Language Speech Recognition (NLSR), universal insurance company Suncorp substituted its original push button IVR, supporting the customer to just say what they wanted.

T8.9.4.5. Robotics

Robotics could be an area where AI can be very beneficial. It includes mechanical, generally computer-controlled devices to accomplish tasks that necessitate extreme accuracy or monotonous or dangerous work by people. These robots also increase the efficiency, as they do not need any break while working thus overcoming the inherent disadvantage of tiredness in humans.

Some of the robotics applications are the following ones:

- Galaxy Robotics - Improvement of robot systems for amorphous, uneven territory based on biologically enthused inventive kinetic energy perceptions
- Subaquatic Robotics - Development of schemes for user provision in remote-controlled underwater vehicles
- Rechargeable Mobility - Conceptions for electric vehicles, battery charge technologies, and the group of vehicle data. Prototypes for intellectual, environmentally sound, and integrated urban mobility are created.
- Logistics, Production and Consumer (LPC) - Novel systems are established which will improve handling and planning tasks, fast, self-learning image recognition and classification to identify construction faults.
- Search and Rescue (SAR) & Security Robotics - Robots will be technologically advanced to support rescue and security personnel, mission planning and independent navigation.

T8.9.4.6. Expert systems

The first extent of Artificial Intelligence application is expert systems, which are AI suites that can create resolutions, which generally necessitate human level of proficiency. Expert systems are possibly the furthestmost simply implemented and maximum extensively used AI technology. Therefore, expert systems are machines that are trained to have total expertise in specific areas of interest. They are developed to solve the problems in niche areas. These systems use statistical analysis and data mining to solve these problems by deducing the solutions through a logical flow of yes-no questions. An expert system is made up of three parts:

- Knowledge base: It stores all the information, rules, data and relationships that are needed by the expert system to have total expertise in its area of interest

- Inference engine: It seeks information from the knowledge base on being presented with a query, analyses it and responds with a solution or recommendation in the way a human expert would
- Rule: It is a conditional statement that links the given conditions to the final solution

A software package called DENDRAL, developed at the Stanford Research Institute in 1965, was the ancestor of expert systems. Considerably like a human chemist, it could investigate information about chemical compounds to define their molecular construction. The advanced suite called MYCIN was developed in the mid-1970s and was proficient of serving physicians in analysis of bacteriological infections. It is regularly denoted as the first real expert system.

The spell-checking efficacy in our word processor is an expert system. It takes the role of a checker by evaluation a set of sentences, testing them against the known spelling and linguistic rules, and constructing propositions of probable modifications to the writer. Expert systems, shared with robotics, carried about computerization of the engineering process which enhanced production rate and reduced errors. A typical association line that required hundreds of persons in the 1950s now merely requires ten to twenty persons who handle the expert systems that do the work. The inventors in manufacturing mechanization are Japanese automobile industrialists such as Toyota and Honda, with up to 80% automation of the industrialized process.

The most advanced expert systems, like several other innovative technologies, are used widely in army applications. An example is the F-22 Raptor, an aircraft of the U.S Air Force. The pointing supercomputer on the team the Raptor precedes the role of a radar controller by inferring radar signals, detecting a target, and testing its radar signature against known opponent types deposited in its database.

T8.9.4.7. Natural Language Processing

Natural-language-processing software package use AI to let a user to communicate with a computer in the user's natural language. The computer can both recognize and reply to instructions given in a natural language. The penalty area of Natural Language Processing (NLP) is to plan and construct a computer system that will investigate, recognize, and produce natural human-languages. Usages of NLP comprise machine transformation of one human-language text to another; group of human-language text such as literature, booklets, and universal explanations; interfacing to additional systems such as databases and robotic systems accordingly facilitating the use of human- language type commands and enquiries; and accepting human-language text to provide a summary or to appeal conclusions. One of the easiest jobs for a NLP structure is to parse a sentence to govern its syntax. A more difficult assignment is defining the semantic meaning of a sentence. One of the most challenging tasks is the analysis of the framework to determine the exact meaning and associating that with other text.

Applications of Natural Language Processing (NLP):

- Spelling amendment, syntax checking;
- Enhanced search engines;

- Information mining;
- Psychoanalysis, Harlequin passions;
- Innovative interfaces;
- Speech appreciation (and text-to-speech);
- Negotiation Systems (USS Enterprise on-board computer);
- Machine transformation (Babel fish).

T8.9.4.8. Machine Learning

Machine learning programs identify patterns in data and adjust program actions consequently. For instance, Facebook's News Feed changes according to the customer's private communications with other consumers. If a customer regularly tags a friend in snapshots, writes on his wall or likes his/her links, the News Feed will display more of that friend's movement in the user's News Feed due to assumed closeness.

Some of the applications of machine learning are the following:

- Face detection in Mobile Camera: Usually Cameras can automatically snap a photo because of developments in machine learning methods.
- Face recognition: An efficient program can identify an individual from a picture. We can find this feature on Facebook for mechanically tagging people in snapshots where they appear. An advancement in machine learning is additional accurate auto-face group software.
- Image classification: The major application of deep learning is to improve image classification or image categorization in applications such as Google photos. Google pictures would not be possible without advancements in deep learning.
- Speech recognition: Enhancements in speech recognition systems have been made possible by machine learning explicitly deep learning.
- Google: Google is a front-runner in this area because machine learning is a precise important component to its primary advertising and search businesses.
- Anti-virus: Machine learning has been used in Anti-virus software to improve discovery of malicious software on computer procedures.
- Anti-spam: The machine learning can also be used to train best anti-spam software systems.
- Genetics: In machine learning, the classical data mining or clustering algorithms such as agglomerative clustering are used in genetics to give assistance find genes associated with a particular disease.

In the next Figure 8.29 as an example, the main applications of AI are presented, which have been described in the previous points:

Figure 8.29 - AI applications

T8.9.5 Applications of AI in Aviation

Some existing AI use cases in aviation include:

- Flight management computer systems used in some aircraft to assist the pilot with information and for handling purposes.
- Computer systems behind the autopilot feature to steer the aircraft along a predefined trajectory without the need of pilot intervention.
- Computer systems supporting automated aircraft cabin pressurization to ensure the cabin environment is safe and comfortable for passengers.
- Analysis and prediction of passenger behaviour/demand.
- Seamless airport security processes, through facial recognition and biometrics.
- AI providing support to the optimization of revenue management, route network, fleet management, and pricing strategies.
- Self-flying planes.
- Autonomous airport processes, e.g. ground handling, loading, fuelling, cleaning, and aircraft safety checks.
- Autonomous in-flight services.
- AI assistants: responding to customer inquiries and responding to voice commands for domestic airline flight info and ticket availability through interactions using natural language.
- Facial Recognition: Facial recognition technology is being used to perform customer identity verification and to match passengers to their luggage through kiosks.

- Airplane simulators are already using AI in order to process the data taken from simulated flights. One example is aircraft warfare where computers are able to come up with the best success scenarios in these situations as these machines can create strategies based on the placement, size, speed and strength of the forces and counter forces.

T8.9.6 Applications of AI in Aviation

In recent years, artificial intelligence technologies have developed dramatically due to improvement in the processing capacity of computers and the accumulation of big data. However, the results of current artificial intelligence technologies remain limited to specific intellectual areas, such as image recognition, speech recognition, and dialogue response. That is, current AI is a specialized type of artificial intelligence which develop the intellectual work carried out by each area of the human brain; they are only a substitute and do not perform all of the functions of the human brain. In other words, AI has not been able to cooperate with whole-brain functions such as self-understanding, self-control, self-consciousness and self-motivation.

Despite all the IA benefits and advantages, there are still many problems to overcome before its widespread applications.

- Intelligence as a multi-component model: A machine to be called “intelligent” should satisfy several criteria that include the ability of reasoning, building models, understanding the real world and anticipate what might happen next. The concept of “intelligence” is made of the following high-level components: perception, common sense, planning, analogy, language and reasoning.
- Large datasets and hard generalisation: After extensive training on big datasets, today machines can achieve impressive results in recognising images or translating speech. These abilities are obtained thanks to the derivation of statistical approximations on the available data. However, when the system must deal with new situations when limited training data is available, the model often fails. We know that humans can perform recognition even with small data since we can abstract principles and rules to generalise to a diverse range of situations. The current AI systems are still missing this level of abstraction and generalisability.
- Black box and a lack of interpretation: Another issue with the current AI system is the lack of interpretation. For example, deep neural networks have millions of parameters and to understand why the network provides good or bad results becomes impossible. Despite some recent work on visualising high-level features by using the weight filters in a convolution neural network, the obtained trained models are often not interpretable. Consequently, most researchers use current AI approaches as a black box.
- Robustness of AI: Most current AI systems can be easily fooled, which is a problem that affects almost all machine learning techniques.

Despite these issues, it is certain that AI will play a major role in the future. As the availability of information grows, humans will rely more and more on AI systems to live, to work and to

entertain. Therefore, it is not surprising that large tech firms are investing heavily on AI related technologies. In many application areas, AI systems are needed to handle data with increasing complexities. Given increased accuracy and sophistication of AI systems, they will be used in more and more sectors including finance, pharmaceuticals, energy, manufacturing, education, transport and public services. In some of these areas they can replace costly human labour, create new potential applications, and work along with /for humans to achieve better service standards. Advances in AI will also play a critical role in imitating the human brain function. Advances in sensing and computation hardware will allow to link brain function with human behaviour at a level that AI self-awareness and emotions could be simulated and observed in a more pragmatic way. Recently, quantum computing has also attracted a new wave of interest from both academic institutions and technological firms such as Google, IBM and Microsoft.

8.8 New Materials

Progress in materials has been a key to advances in aeronautics since its birth at least in two areas: (i) strong and light structures able to withstand flight and landing loads without demanding more than the essential lift and incurring excessive drag; (ii) high-temperature turbine blades of jet engines subject to rotational and aerodynamic loads combined with heat fluxes. The evolution from wood and canvas, to aluminium and high-strength alloys and to composites has allowed the design of larger and faster aircraft without proportional increases in empty weight, and with larger payload and fuel fractions. High-strength materials able to withstand high temperatures include alloys and ceramics and apply to all hot sections of engines, structures subject to their exhaust and high-speed flight beyond the heat barrier at Mach 2-3. The contribution of materials and structures to progress in aeronautics has been steady and gradual, e.g. a 10-30% weight saving replacing a metal wing or fuselage by a full composite one. The prospect of structures having a fraction of their current weight is brought by nanotube developments.

The development of new materials is driven both by the pull of aviation needs (Key topic T8.10) and by the progress of technologies (Key Topic T8.11). Materials research is closely related to the structures employing them (Section 8.9).

KEY TOPIC T8.10 AVIATION NEEDS OF NEW MATERIALS

T8.10.1 Introduction

Constant pressure for fuel efficiency is forcing aerospace manufacturers to find ways to incorporate new or previously impractical to machine materials. Forty years ago aluminium

dominated the aerospace industry - as much as 70% of an aircraft was made of it. Aluminium was used in any part of a plane, from the fuselage to main engine components. Materials such as titanium, graphite, fiberglass or composites and alloys were also used, but only in very small quantities.

T8.10.2 New materials

Currently typical airplane is constructed as little as 20% pure aluminium and most of the non-critical structural material consist of even lighter-weight carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRPs) and honeycomb materials. Also, for engine parts and critical components, there is a simultaneous push for lower weight, increase strength and higher temperature resistance. Those changes are made in the aim of reducing the cost of aerospace manufacture, improving fuel economy through efficiency and light weighting. "The materials used must be lightweight, of course, but they also need to be rigid and strong enough to withstand intense mechanical stress. They also need to withstand impact from hailstones and bird strikes in the case of engine parts" said Jean-Pierre Poitevin, Vice President of Safran Composites, Safran Tech's R&T centre³⁹.

T8.10.3 Metal Alloys

Standard aerospace aluminium (6061, 7050, 7075) and traditional aerospace metals, like nickel 718, titanium 6Al4V, or stainless 15-5PH still have applications in aerospace, but currently are ceding territory to new metal alloys and components, designed to improve cost and performance (Figure 8.30). Some of those materials, aren't new for the industry, rather are new to practical production application, as machine tools, tooling technology and insert coatings have sufficiently advanced to tackle difficult-to-machine alloys.

Figure 8.30 – Metal Alloys used in Aircraft

Source: The Challenge of New Materials in the Aerospace Industry, Gerould Young, 2013, Boeing Company

³⁹ <https://www.safran-group.com/media/aerospace-materials-future-20170925>

In some fields aluminium is re-introduced to aerospace application in new alloys, especially in cases where the move to carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) has proved cost prohibitive or unsuccessful. Reappearing aluminium alloys are titanium aluminide (TiAl) and aluminium lithium (Al-Li), for example, which have been around since the 1970s. Similar to nickel alloy in its heat-resisting properties, TiAl retains strength and corrosion resistance in temperatures up to 600°C. But TiAl is more easily machined, exhibiting similar machinability characteristics to alpha-beta titanium, such as Ti6Al4V. TiAl has the potential to improve the thrust-to-weight ratio in aircraft engines because it's only half the weight of nickel alloys. Case in point, both low-pressure turbine blades and high-pressure compressor blades, traditionally made of dense Ni-based super alloys are now being machined from TiAl-based alloys. General Electric uses TiAl low-pressure turbine blades on its GEnx engine, the first large-scale use of this material on a commercial jet engine – in this case in the Boeing 787 Dreamliner.

Another aluminium alloy is weight-saving Al-Li, in which the addition of lithium strengthens aluminium at a lower density and weight. Al-Li alloys' high strength, low density, high stiffness, damage tolerance, corrosion resistance and weld-friendly nature make it a good choice in commercial jetliner airframes. Airbus is using AA2050, Alcoa is using AA2090 T83 and 2099 T8E67. The alloy can also be found in the fuel and oxidizer tanks in the SpaceX Falcon 9 launch vehicle. The alloy is used extensively in NASA rockets.

Another new metal to aerospace is Titanium 5553 (Ti-5553), exhibiting high strength, light weight, and good corrosion resistance. Major structural components that the previously used stainless steel alloys are perfect application points for this titanium alloy.

T8.10.4 Composites

Originally being used for only light structural pieces or cabin parts, composites are now increasingly being used for functional components such as engines, wing skins, and landing gear. Composites provide increased fuel efficiency because of their light weight, and are easy to handle, design, and repair. Composites are at least two materials with different properties that are combined to work together while remaining separate to a certain degree.

Due to their ability to be formed into complex shapes, composites reduce the number of heavy fasteners and joints which would be needed for metallic parts. Therefore, can be shaped into a one-piece part. Pre-formed composite components are replacing overall assemblies because industry leaders are using one-piece designs whenever they can (Figure 8.31). These designs are ultimately safer because they have fewer potential failure points.

Platform	Percent Composites	Total Wt (lbs)	Approx Composite Wt (lbs)	Approx Delivery Rate	Wt (lbs/Month)	# Delivered	Total Wt Composites Delivered (lbs)
C-17	8%	277,000	22,714	1.5		218	4,951,652
B-2	High					20	
F-18 c/d	10%	24,700	2,470			1,450	3,581,500
777	10%	300,000	30,000	7	210,000	1066	31,980,000
F-22	20%	31,700	6,340	6		339	2,149,260
F-18 e/f	18%	30,500	5,490	4	21,960	500	2,745,000
V-22	43%	33,140	14,250	1	14,250	160	2,280,000
787	50%	250,000	125,000	5	625,000	130	16,250,000
Total					871,210		63,934,360

Figure 8.31 - Use of composites in different Boeing's aircraft

Source: The Challenge of New Materials in the Aerospace Industry, Gerould Young, 2013, Boeing Company

The Douglas DC3 had a take-off weight of about 25,200 pounds with a passenger complement of about 25. With a maximum payload range of 350 miles, that's about 3 pounds per passenger mile. The Boeing 787 Dreamliner has a take-off weight of 550,000 pounds carrying 290 passengers. With a fully loaded range of over 8,000 miles, that's roughly ¼ pound per passenger mile - 1100% better⁴⁰. Also, Dreamliner has General Electric (GEnx-1B) and Rolls Royce (Trent 1000) engine options, and both use composites extensively. In GEnx-1B composite are even used in the fan blades. In the Dreamliner power plant, composites are used for the first 5 stages of the 7-stage low-pressure turbine.

⁴⁰ <https://www.thoughtco.com/boeings-787-dreamliner-820385>

Figure 8.32 – Production Rate of Materials for aircraft programmes

Source: *The Challenge of New Materials in the Aerospace Industry*, Gerould Young, 2013, Boeing Company

T8.10.5 Sandwich Materials

Core materials refer to the central component of a sandwich construction. Usually a sandwich structure consists of two relatively thin, stiff and strong faces separated by a relatively thick lightweight core, for instance, honeycomb, balsa or foam cores. The purpose of sandwich structure is to achieve a stiff and simultaneously light component. Depending on the purpose the materials can vary, however the most important characteristics for sandwich structures are:

- They are lightweight compared to metallic;
- Have high stiffness;
- Cost effective compared to other composite structures.

When considering using core materials for specific applications, the production technology used for the sandwich structure is crucial, for example, wet-layup, prepreg, infusion, etc.

Honeycomb is a core used to build sandwich structure. The honeycomb, flex cores and nomex are sandwiched between two carbon skins with the purpose of creating a very stiff and strong

structure. The aluminium honeycomb, for instance, is available in different aluminium grades with specific material properties and thus can be applied as required. The trend of its usage in the aerospace segment for aircraft components is increasing. The honeycomb sandwich structures is very light and a wide variety of materials can be used (e.g. carbon, paper, aluminium, etc.). Additionally, the core has a high strength to weight ratio and a very good compressive strength. The sheets of honeycomb can be available in different thicknesses and densities and can be deformed to follow the shape of the tool where the component will be laminated. The major disadvantages of honeycomb cores are price and corrosion.

T8.10.6 Foams

Composite metal foams (CMF) is a metal that is similar to a foam sponge. Heat travels slower in air than in metal, that's why CMFs are very heat resistant. According to digitaltrends.com: "a piece of steel-steel CMF (2.5x2.5x.75 inches) was able to withstand eight minutes of 800oC heat before the entire piece of foam heated up". Standard steel would heat up in half that time. Other studies show that CMFs have incredible high-velocity impact resistance and can effectively protect against radiation. Impressively, an inch-thick piece of CMF can stop a bullet⁴¹. In tests, the bullet only left an indentation of 8mm, which is much less than the 44 mm armour indentation limit which is set by the National Institute of Justice⁴². CMF can be used for aircraft or space-based vehicles, which need to be protected from bits of debris traveling at high speed.

Polymethacrylimide (PMI) belongs to the family of closed cell foams and is mainly used in high tech sandwich construction, for instance in combination with prepreg systems. The material is produced by mixing methacrylic acid and methacrylonitrile monomers. Due to its good mechanical properties, the foam core material can be processed in an autoclave, so they can cope with high pressure without collapsing. As a consequence of the overall costs involved and its performance characteristics, PMI has been used in higher performance composite parts including helicopter rotor blades, ailerons and stringer profiles in pressure bulkheads. Generally speaking the foam core material PMI is used in the aerospace industry in a variety of structural sandwich application in either commercial, military and general aviation aircraft, satellites and helicopters.

Polymethacrylimide main advantage:

- Lightweight;
- Strength;
- Stiffness;
- High dimensional stability;
- High fatigue life⁴³.

The main disadvantage of PMI is cost - in comparison to other foam cores it is very expensive.

⁴¹ <https://www.digitaltrends.com/cool-tech/composite-metal-foam/>

⁴² <https://eastbaymfg.com/new-materials-being-used-in-the-aerospace-industry/>

⁴³ <http://altairenligheten.com/in-depth/sandwich-structures/>

The industry continues to march toward components of lighter weight, increased strength, and greater heat and corrosion resistance. The mix of materials in aerospace will continue to change in coming years with composites, freshly machinable metals, and new metals increasingly occupying the space of traditional materials (Figure 8.32).

According to Gerould Young, Director Materials & Fabrication Technology from Georgia Institute of Technology:

- optimization will continue to increase number of materials;
- materials improvements are vital to aircraft performance improvements;
- discovery is only a small part of materials development;
- computational materials & manufacturing tools will speed decision making;
- new material development must have:
 - reduced qualification and certification costs and schedule;

T8.10.7 References

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KEY TOPIC T8.11 ADVANCES IN AERONAUTICAL MATERIALS

Constant pressure for greater fuel efficiency is forcing aerospace manufacturers to find ways to incorporate new and existing materials that had once been considered impractical to machine. Forty years ago, when aluminium dominated the aerospace industry, was considered to be novel, lightweight, and inexpensive. In fact, as much as 70% of an aircraft was made of aluminium at that time. Other new materials such as composites and alloys were also used, including titanium, graphite, and fiberglass, but only in relatively small quantities. Readily available, aluminium was used everywhere from the fuselage to main engine components.

Nowadays, however, only about 20% of aluminium is used to build a typical jet. Most of the non-critical structural material – panelling and aesthetic interiors – now consist of even lighter-weight carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRPs) and honeycomb materials. Meanwhile, for engine parts and critical components, there is a simultaneous push for lower weight and higher

temperature resistance for better fuel efficiency, bringing new or previously impractical-to-machine metals into the aerospace material mix.

Aerospace manufacturing is unique among other volume manufacturing sectors, and this is especially true of aerospace engine manufacturing. The engine is the most complex element of an aircraft, houses the most individual components, and ultimately is an important factor in fuel efficiency. The advent of lean-burn engines, with temperature potentials as high as 3,800°F (2,100°C), has helped drive demand for these new materials, as well as cooling techniques like in-blade flows. Considering that the melting point of current super alloys is around 3,360°F (1,850°C), the challenge becomes finding materials that will withstand higher temperatures.

To meet these temperature demands, heat-resistant super alloys (HRSAs), including titanium alloys, nickel alloys, and some non-metal composite materials such as ceramics, are now being brought into the material equation. These materials tend to be more difficult to machine than traditional aluminium, historically meaning shorter tool life and less process security.

There's also a high process risk in machining aerospace parts. Because margins for error are small at 35,000ft cruising altitude, tolerances in aerospace are more precise than almost any other industry. This level of precision takes time. Longer machining times are required for each component, and more time per part makes scrap relatively expensive, when factoring in time investment. Also, compared to other industries, aerospace component orders often consist of short run quantities and long lead times, rendering scheduling for productivity, throughput, and profitability difficult.

Unlike any other industry but oil and gas, which also has high temperature, pressure, and corrosion requirements, aerospace materials themselves impact component design. Design for manufacturability (DFM) is the engineering art of designing components with a balanced approach, taking into consideration both component function and its manufacturing requirements. This approach is being applied more and more in aerospace component design because its components must accomplish certain loads and temperature resistances, and some materials can only accommodate so much. Material and component designs truly drive one another, as opposed to one following the other. This give-and-take relationship between material and design is a particular consideration when investigating next-generation materials. Aerospace manufacturers are a breed apart for all these reasons. It's not surprising that their assortment of materials is unique.

Standard aerospace aluminium – 6061, 7050, and 7075 – and traditional aerospace metals – nickel 718, titanium 6Al4V, and stainless 15-5PH – still have applications in aerospace. These metals, however, are currently ceding territory to new alloys designed to improve cost and performance. To be clear, these new metals aren't always new, some having been available for decades. Rather, they are new to practical production application, as machine tools, tooling technology, and insert coatings have sufficiently advanced to tackle difficult-to-machine alloys.

Even though the amount of aluminium is declining in aircraft, its use is not completely disappearing. In fact, aluminium is coming back, especially in cases where the move to CFRP has been cost prohibitive or unsuccessful. But the reappearing aluminium is not your father's aluminium. Titanium aluminide (TiAl) and aluminium lithium (Al-Li), for example, which have

been around since the 1970s, have only been gaining traction in aerospace since the turn of the century.

Another re-introduction of aluminium to aerospace is found in weight-saving Al-Li, specifically designed to improve properties of 7050 and 7075 aluminium. Overall, the addition of lithium strengthens aluminium at a lower density and weight, two catalysts of the aerospace material evolution.

Titanium 5553 (Ti-5553) is another metal that is reasonably new to aerospace, exhibiting high strength, light weight, and good corrosion resistance. Major structural components that need to be stronger and lighter than the previously used stainless steel alloys are perfect application points for this titanium alloy. Nicknamed triple 5-3, this has been a notoriously difficult material to machine – until recently. Extensive research and development has been devoted to making the metal practical to machine, and triple 5-3 has recently proven to be very predictable with machining consistency similar to more traditional titanium alloys like the aforementioned Ti6Al4V. The variances in the two materials require the use of different cutting data to obtain similar tool life. But once an operator has proper parameters set, triple 5-3 machines predictably. The key with triple 5-3 is to run a bit slower and optimize the tool path and coolant system to achieve a good balance of tool life and tool security.

Some structural pieces, like fasteners, landing gear, and actuators, require raw strength, with lightweight properties being less of a priority. In such cases, Carpenter Technology Ferrium S53 steel alloy has provided mechanical properties equal to or better than conventional ultra-high-strength steels, such as 300M and SAE 4340, with the added benefit of general corrosion resistance. This can eliminate the need for cadmium coating and the subsequent related processing.

Composite materials also represent a growing piece of the aerospace material pie. They reduce weight and increase fuel efficiency while being easy to handle, design, shape, and repair. Once only considered for light structural pieces or cabin components, composites' aerospace application range now reaches into true functional components – wing and fuselage skins, engines, and landing gear.

Also, important composite components can be formed into complex shapes that, for metallic parts, would require machining and create joints. Pre-formed composite components aren't just lightweight and strong, they reduce the number of heavy fasteners and joints – which are potential failure points – within the aircraft. In doing so, composite materials are helping to drive an industry-wide trend of fewer components in overall assemblies, using one-piece designs wherever possible.

While CFRPs represent the lion's share of composite material in both cabin and functional components, and honeycomb materials provide effective and lightweight internal structural components, next-generation materials include ceramic-matrix composites (CMCs), which are emerging in practical use after decades of testing. CMCs are comprised of a ceramic matrix reinforced by a refractory fibre, such as silicon carbide (SiC) fibre. They offer low density/weight, high hardness, and most importantly, superior thermal and chemical resistance. Like CFRPs, they can be moulded to certain shapes without any extra machining,

making them ideal for internal aerospace engine components, exhaust systems, and other “hot-zone” structures – even replacing the latest in HRSA metals listed earlier.

Metallic and composite materials alike continue to be developed and improved to offer ever-increasing performance, whether that’s lighter weight, greater strength, or better heat and corrosion resistance. Accelerating this evolution of new materials, advances in machining and cutting technology give manufacturers unprecedented access to materials previously deemed impractical or too difficult to machine. New material adoption is happening exceptionally quickly in aerospace, requiring DFM-minded interaction between material characteristics and component design. The two must be in balance, and one can’t really exist outside of the context of the other.

Meanwhile, one-piece designs are continuing to reduce the number of components in overall assemblies. In general, this bodes well for composites in aerospace, which can be formed instead of machined. A variation of this trend exists in metallic structures, as more components are conditioned in forgings to get to near-net shape, reducing the amount of machining. Elephant skins, roughed-in shapes, and thin floor sections all reduce material costs and the total number of components, but setup and fixturing continue to be challenges. Some manufacturers are turning to waterjet and other technologies to reduce or eliminate raw stock materials in need of removal. Still, difficulties exist in work holding, surface finish, and CAM tool paths. But designers, machinists, engineers, and machine tool/cutting tool partners are developing new solutions to keep the evolution churning forward.

The mix of materials in aerospace will continue to change in coming years with composites, freshly machinable metals, and new metals increasingly occupying the space of traditional materials. The industry continues to march toward components of lighter weights, increased strengths, and greater heat and corrosion resistance. Component counts will decrease in favour of stronger, near-net shapes, and design will continue its close collaboration with material characteristics. Machine tools builders and cutting tool manufacturers will continue to develop tools to make currently unviable materials machinable, and even practical. And it’s all done in the name of reducing the cost of aerospace manufacture, improving fuel economy through efficiency and light weighting, and making air travel a more cost-effective means of transportation.

8.9 Nanotechnologies and Nanotube Structures

There is intense research on nanotechnologies, several of which have been proposed for aeronautics, such as micro sensors, micro actuators; some of the technologies already exist in larger scales like fluidics or piezoelectric structures or actuators with morphing capabilities to change wing, air foil or control surface shapes. A particular focus is given next to the prospects and implications of nanotube structures. Nanotube structures have a fraction of the weight of the conventional structures they replace, because they are mostly hollow and consist of strategically placed nanotubes to have the same strength with a much smaller amount of material. Nanotube structures are very challenging in at least three respects: (i) they are difficult to produce since the nanotube distribution must be correct, and the tendency of nanotubes to cluster undermines total strength; (ii) the binding of nanotubes to other materials is difficult;

(iii) the passage from laboratory fabrication of nanotube structures to industrial series has not been made.

Assuming that the challenges in economic serial production of nanotube structures can be overcome, their impact on aeronautics could be as significant as metallic structures, jet engines or composites. The possible revolution in aeronautics made by nanotube structures can be assessed in two cases: (a) load carrying large passenger or cargo aircraft; (b) sensor platforms with need only for small payload.

In the case (a) say of a large airliner a nanotube structure with a fraction of the weight of a conventional structure would imply that most of the take-off weight would be passengers/cargo and fuel. Assuming that 20% of the weight of a current aircraft is passengers/cargo, 30% fuel and 50% structure, with a nanotube structure weighting 1/5 or 10%, the take-off weight minus fuel would be 30% less weight means less lift, less drag, less thrust and less fuel. Thus, the fuel load could probably be halved to 15% for a total take-off weight of 45% compared with a conventional aircraft with the same payload-range. Halving the weight, lift, drag and thrust would halve fuel consumption, cost and emissions and reduce noise.

In the case (a) of an airliner or cargo aircraft the benefit of a structure having a fraction of the weight is limited by the fixed payload weight. In the case (b) of a sensor aircraft with a light payload say 10%, fuel might be 30% and structure 60% of the total take-off weight. A nanotube structure with 1/5 of the weight would be 12% or 22% take-off weight not including fuel. Contemplating an aircraft with one-third of the weight, lift, drag, thrust and fuel consumption the total take-off weight would be 32% of a conventional aircraft for the same mission.

In rough terms the replacement of a conventional by a nanotube structure would reduce the weight of an aircraft for the same mission to one-half for a passenger/cargo airplane and to one-third for an observation drone. This would have multiple benefits: (i) improved economics through lower fuel cost; (ii) less emissions due to lower fuel consumption; (iii) less demand for aviation fuel or alternative sources, reducing from 10% of world needs to less than 5%; (iv) less engine noise at airports due to lower thrust; (v) less airframe noise due to less lift and lower landing weight; (vi) easier to reach silent operation outside airport boundaries.

The weight saving of nanotube structures could be used alternatively: (b) to increase the fuel load of an observation drone for much greater range and/or speed; (a) to increase the payload-range of a passenger or cargo aircraft. One of the main limitations of the design of structures is their own weight, such as the bending moment at the root of a wing of large span. A nanotube wing would be a fraction of the weight for the same span with a smaller bending moment at the root and lighter wing box structure. Or more interesting the same wing root bending moment would allow a larger span and better lift-to-drag ratio within aero elastic limits. Thus, the large weight benefits of nanotube structures could be used in several ways to increase aircraft efficiency.

Nanotube structures (Key Topic T8.1.3) are just one of multiple areas of aeronautics in which nanotechnologies can have a major impact (Key Topic T8.12).

KEY TOPIC T8.12 RELEVANCE OF NANOTECHNOLOGIES TO AERONAUTICS

There are few industries where the applications of nanotechnology are as clearly beneficial as in the aerospace industry. The primary development goals match almost exactly with the advantages offered by using various nanomaterials in the place of traditional bulk metals like steel. The aerospace industry is one of the most important heavy industries in the world. Countless companies rely on the ability to ship products and people around the world with the speed that can only be achieved by air.

Along with this huge economic value, however, comes huge consumption, and one of the largest carbon footprints on the planet relative to the size of the market. For this reason, the major drivers in current aerospace R&D are towards lighter construction materials and more efficient engines - the overall goal being to reduce fuel consumption and carbon emissions associated with air travel and air freight. The significant interest in nanotechnology for the aerospace industry is justified by the potential of nanomaterials and nanoengineering to help the industry achieve this goal.

Bulk metals with some nanoscale structure are already widely used in aircraft manufacturing. It is now well known that nanostructured metals - exhibit considerably improved properties compared to their counterparts with microscale or larger grain structure. This is particularly noticeable for properties which are crucial for materials used in aircraft - primarily yield strength, tensile strength and corrosion resistance, coupled with low density which helps keep the total weight of the aircraft down.

Various nanomaterials have been used as filler materials to enhance the properties of structural and non-structural polymers used in aircraft construction. The most commonly used nanomaterials include nano-clays, carbon nanotubes, nanofibers, and graphene. Carbon nanotubes, in particular, have been shown to give excellent advantages when used as fillers in various polymers, due to their exceptional stiffness, toughness, and unique electrical properties.

Nanocomposites typically have superb weight-to-strength ratios, and enhanced resilience to vibration and fire, making them ideal for use in the aviation industry. The properties of the nano-fillers, like the conductivity of nanotubes, for example, can create interesting opportunities for multifunctional materials. The properties of polymers enhanced by nanomaterial fillers are so well-tuned to the requirements of aircraft manufacturers, that they are, actually, being used to replace some of the metals used in the airframes. This obviously brings along huge weight savings, and often cost savings as well.

Another major trend in the materials used in aircraft is towards nano-coatings to enhance the durability of metals. In particular, magnesium alloys, which are far lighter than steel or aluminium, are prone to corrosion, due to the high chemical reactivity of magnesium. Coatings can help prevent corrosion, but the type typically used contain chromium complexes which are a highly toxic pollutant. Materials used for these novel anti-corrosion nano-coatings include silicon and boron oxides, and cobalt-phosphorous nanocrystals.

Nano-coatings are also now being used on turbine blades and other mechanical components which must withstand high temperatures and friction wear. Tribological coatings can drastically lower the friction coefficient and improve resistance to wear - this greatly improves the efficiency of the engines. Many nanostructured and nanoscale coating materials have been suggested as possible friction modifying agents, such as carbides, nitrides, metals, and various ceramics.

To conclude, the drive for lighter and more efficient air vehicles has led to the rapid adoption of nanotechnology in aerospace manufacturing. The main roadblock, as with many industries looking to adopt nanotechnology, is caused by uncertainty over the environmental and health and safety implications of these materials. Whilst nanomaterials can often be less toxic than the current materials used, the effects of long-term exposure to these novel materials are still uncertain. The potential of nanotechnology in the aerospace industry cannot be denied, however. Outside of airframe and component materials, nanotechnology applications have been found in lubricants, fuel, adhesives and many other areas. Nanotechnology is also helping engineers to create vehicles with the necessary properties to endure the harsh conditions of space. Large scale manufacture of nanomaterials with repeatable, certifiable properties is also challenging, since some laboratory techniques do not scale up readily. For example, the tendency of nanotubes to cluster reduces their potential benefit in strength-to-weight ratio.

KEY TOPIC T8.13 DEVELOPMENTS IN NANOTUBES

Composite components based on Carbon Nano Tubes (CNT) offer improved corrosion resistance and lighter weight, which improve fuel efficiency and reduce carbon dioxide emission in airplanes. The Figure 8.33 depicts and shows an overview of the actual use of composites which now constitute more than 25% of the Airbus A380 and 50% of the Boeing 787 aircraft. The panelling and aesthetic interiors, consists of these new materials which reduce the overall weight of the plane by as much as 20 percent compared to aluminium-bodied planes.

Gulfstream has incorporated increasing levels of composite materials into its aircraft design. In 2007, Gulfstream initiated the Advanced Composites Research and Development program to exploit the advantages of composite structures. In 2012, this program was expanded to include new forming processes, additive manufacturing (3-D printing) and green technologies to its research and development activities.

Figure 8.33 - The use of composites in Airbus A380

Source: X. Zhang et al. Recent advances in the development of aerospace materials. Progress in Aerospace Sciences 97 (2018) 22–34 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paerosci.2018.01.001>

One problem to be faced when using polymer nanocomposites is the low electrical conductivity. In fact, airplanes get struck by lightning frequently. Modern composites are reinforced with conductive metal fibres or metal screen in order to conduct away lightning currents. However, these solutions add additional weight which partially reduce the advantage related to the use of the composite systems. For this reason, a relevant research topic for nanostructured materials is focused on the improvement of the electrical conductivity.

Another issue involved in the application of CNT is depicted in the Figure 8.34 which illustrates a way to bond composite layers leading to a material substantially stronger and more resistant to damage than other advanced composites. Carbon nanotubes having a diameter of about 10 nanometres (nearly a million times smaller than the carbon fibres adopted to reinforce the polymeric resin adopted in aeronautic composite structures), exhibit a surface area 1000 times larger than that of carbon fibres leading to a better bonding with the polymer matrix. The technique integrates a scaffold of carbon nanotubes within a glue-like polymer matrix. The nanotubes are vertically aligned and transferred onto a sticky, uncured composite layer. This structure is repeated to generate a stack of 16 composite plies.

Figure 8.34 - Method to reinforce the composite systems adopted to manufacture structural parts of airplanes; Source: <https://phys.org/news/2016-08-methodcarbon-nanotubes-airplane-lighter.htm>

The resulting composite material is able to withstand 30 percent more force before cracking. Finally, the strength enhancements suggest this material will be more resistant to any type of damaging events or features hence good candidate as new composites to improve aircraft structural performance.

With respect to such issues, European Union (EU) has promoted progress by supporting research efforts. In particular, through the funding of several large-scale 'flagship' projects in micro-nano-manufacturing EU, has provided an impulse for some substantial improvements in aircraft design, development, verification and validation processes.

In this regard, during FP7 several relevant projects were developed of new nanomaterials to improve different aspects connected to the challenges of the FlightPath2050. The main project objectives and results are summarized in the sequel.

Iapetus - Innovative Repair of Aerospace Structures with Curing Optimization and Life Cycle Monitoring Abilities

- (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/91015_en.html)
- Project ID: 234333
- Funded under: FP7-TRANSPORT
- Dates: From 2009-06-01 to 2012-12-31, closed project
- Total cost: EUR 3 342 226,23; EU contribution: EUR 2 339 595
- Coordinated in: Spain
- Topic(s): AAT.2008.1.1.2. – Aerostructures; AAT.2008.1.2.2. - Maintenance and Disposal
- Funding scheme: CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project

In IAPETUS two novel methodologies to repair a crack or a defect in an aircraft structure has been developed. The team used a multi-functional repair solution that includes innovative materials, i.e. smart composite repair patches made of a carbon fibre (graphite) epoxy system with matrix materials containing carbon nanotubes, which improves homogeneity of thermal and electrical properties to facilitate homogeneous heating. The innovative features derived

from their novel curing methodologies, i.e. conductive heating (relies on passage of electrical current) and induction heating (relies on application of a magnetic field through the electrically conductive carbon nanotubes). Moreover, by means of a sensor technology, which they developed such as wireless impedance monitoring and infrared thermography, the team developed a new generation of adhesives with carbon nanotube additives for improved control of thermal expansion and higher electrical and thermal conductivity. The composite developed by the team of this project provides better solution to repair the composite with reduced time and costs and is able to ensure continuous health monitoring. In this way, should a defect appear, maintenance will be timely and cost-efficient while ensuring the safety of airline passengers.

POCO - Carbon Nanotube Confinement STRATEGIES to develop Novel Polymer Matrix Composites

- (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/88797_en.html)
- Project ID: 213939
- Funded under: FP7-NMP
- Dates: From 2008-11-01 to 2012-10-31
- Total cost: EUR 8 234 036,40 EU contribution: EUR 5 524 450
- Coordinated in: Spain
- Topic(s): NMP-2007-2.1-1 - Nanostructured polymer-matrix composites
- Funding scheme: CP-IP - Large-scale integrating project

The main objective of the POCO project was to get innovative polymer composites filled with Carbon Nano Tubes (CNT) with tailor-made and superior properties for application in different industrial sectors including aeronautics. In particular, the project was focused on the selection of the best combination (according to the application) of the polymeric matrix and CNT, the study of the interface CNT/polymer characteristics and the determination of the most suitable approaches for chemical functionalization of CNT in order to achieve a proper dispersion of the nanotubes into the polymer matrix during processing and an optimization of the performance. According to the reports, the project has achieved different strategies of functionalisation, alignment and positioning of CNTs, with the use of ionic liquids (ILs) as a strategy to disperse and functionalise CNTs. Moreover, successful nano-structuring and confinement of functionalised CNTs in the correlating phase block copolymers (BCs) as well as nano-structuring of thermosetting matrices was also achieved. Different properties of CNTs and nanocomposites were studied together with the influence of CNTs as a nucleating agent for crystallinity of semi-crystalline matrices. The main problems for the processing of carbon-fibre-reinforced polymer (CFRP) epoxy composites containing CNTs by means of different strategies has been also dealt with. However, these promising results would require further upscaling of the devices and processes to be applied at industrial level.

SARISTU - Smart Intelligent Aircraft Structures

- (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/100047_en.html)
- Project ID: 284562
- Funded under: FP7-TRANSPORT Smart Intelligent Aircraft Structures

- Dates: From 2011-09-01 to 2015-08-31, closed project
- Total cost: EUR 50 712 428,33 EU contribution: EUR 32 434 311
- Coordinated in: Germany
- Topic(s): AAT.2011.4.4-3. - Integrated approach to smart airframe structures
- Funding scheme: CP-IP - Large-scale integrating project

The SARISTU project aims at reaching a reduction of the manufacturing and operational cost of civil airliners and an enhancement of aerodynamic performance by the use of a combination of technologies based on self-sensing structures and nanocomposites. In particular, the shape adaptation (morphing) of some parts (e.g. winglet) of the external wing is addressed on a full-size by considering integrated shape sensing system to ensure optimal control of the aerodynamic surface and failure tolerance and robustness. The integration of different materials including CNT-based nanocomposites for the wing may lead to a 6 % reduction in drag, meaning that less fuel is needed. Moreover, an elastic connecting element for closing the gap between the flap and the fixed aircraft has been developed. Such innovative elastic component is based on a resin containing carbon nanotubes. The nanocomposite systems developed in this project may lead also to a weight reduction up to 3 % when compared to traditional materials.

IASS - Improving the Aircraft Safety by Self-Healing Structure and Protecting Nanofillers

- (https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/103705_en.html)
- Project ID: 313978
- Funded under: FP7-TRANSPORT
- Dates: From 2012-09-01 to 2015-08-31
- Total cost: EUR 3 270 839; EU contribution: EUR 2 397 266
- Coordinated in: Italy
- Topic(s): AAT.2012.3.4-2. - Maintenance
- Funding scheme: CP-FP - Small or medium-scale focused research project

The main objective of IASS Project was to develop multifunctional self-healing composite for aeronautic applications. The multifunctional composite systems are developed with the aim of overcoming serious drawbacks of the composite materials and in particular the low electrical conductivity, the rather weak impact damage resistance and the poor flame resistance.

The IASS project aimed at developing all functionalities integrated in a single material able to face such important requirements of structural materials for primary structures in aeronautics. The strategy to achieve such goals relies on the use of nanotechnology for the production of new, high performance structural multifunctional materials. In order to obtain high mechanical and electrical performance, the IASS consortium led by a group of the University of Salerno (UNISA, Italy) selected multi-wall carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). These nanomaterials were embedded inside an epoxy matrix with a particular formulation which has proven to be very effective for improving nanofiller dispersion due to a decrease in the viscosity. In addition, it

has been found that the so obtained nanocomposite system is able to reduce the moisture content, which is a very critical characteristic for aeronautic materials.

As an outcome of the IASS project multifunctional carbon fibre reinforced panels (CFRPs) have been manufactured using the multifunctional resin. CFRPs (impregnated using the resin with all functionalities integrated) have been manufactured by Resin Film Infusion (RFI) using a unusual technique to infuse a nano-filled resin into the carbon fibre dry preform. In this process, a dry carbon fibre preform is placed in a vacuum bag and the resin is injected from an edge of preform while in the other is venting the vacuum so the resin flow through the length of the preform. The scheme of the RFI is depicted in Figure 8.35, whereas, in Figure 8.36 the steps for the preparation of the laminates is illustrated. In particular, the edges of the preform are sealed to force the resin to flow only through the thickness (Figure 8.36A). The laminate is covered by a porous film and a distribution medium to allow to the resin to escape from the upper side and a breather media to receive the excesses of the resin (Figure 8.36B). Finally, the obtained compound is placed in a vacuum bag and the laminate is transferred into the autoclave (Figure 8.36C).

Figure 8.35 - Approach to Resin Film Infusion adopted in IASS project
Source - L. Guadagno et al. RSC Adv., 2015, 5, 6033, DOI: 10.1039/c4ra12156b

Figure 8.36 - Steps for the preparation of laminates adopted in IASS project
"Source - L. Guadagno et al. RSC Adv., 2015, 5, 6033, DOI: 10.1039/c4ra12156b

Flat panels have been produced and tested with respect to all functionalities. An optical picture of the manufactured panels (30 x 30 cm) is shown in Figure 8.37.

7 PLYS (BIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBERS FABRIC)

Figure 8.37 - Optical image of the CFRP panel with the epoxy based MWCNT composite developed in IASS project; Source - L. Guadagno et al. RSC Adv., 2015, 5, 6033, DOI: 10.1039/c4ra12156b

The electrical conductivity was found to be about $2 \times 10^4 \text{ S/m}$ in the direction parallel to the fibres and greater than 3.0 S/m in the direction orthogonal to the fibres. These values are among the highest values available for nanofilled resins impregnating carbon fibres. The panels also revealed enhanced flame resistance properties (Ignition time about 81 s). Furthermore, due to the auto-repair ability, a significant decrease in the fatigue crack growth rate by approximately 80% was found.

Prepreg with modified and charged epoxy resin have also been developed. The fabrication of the aeronautical prepreg demonstrators was carried out following the aeronautical standards I+D-P-233 from Airbus ("Manufacture of composite structures with carbon fibre"). Two final demonstrators have been produced: a flat panel with three T shape stringers, manufactured by infusion, and a curved panel with two omega shape stringers, manufactured by ad hoc prepreg.

In successive works, the researchers of UNISA have also proposed to integrate within the CFRP panels also a stress sensor obtained with the same MWCNT-loaded composites able to detect stress levels and small damages. The Figure 8.38 shows the relation between the mechanical behaviour (i.e. σ , left vertical axis) and the normalized change of electrical resistance (i.e. $\Delta R/R_0$, observed in tensile stress as function of the axial strain (ϵ) and vs. time for cycling tension loading of nanocomposites.

Figure 8.38 - a) Mechanical behaviour; b) normalized change of electrical resistance
 Source - L. Vertuccio et al. "Piezoresistive properties of resin reinforced with carbon nanotubes for health-monitoring of aircraft primary structures", Composites Part B 107 (2016) pp. 192-202, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2016.09.061>

Looking ahead, in order to reach and retain the global leadership and the competitiveness of European Aeronautics and pave the way on achieving the demanding goals of the Flightpath 2050 for Aeronautics, the continue development of innovation and breakthrough nanotechnologies represents an indispensable need. The results obtained so far represent the reference to measure the future achievements.

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Chapter 9 – Cooperation Beyond Europe's Borders

There are a few areas of aeronautics of common interest to the worldwide community, including education, research, industry, airlines, airports, service providers and ultimately passengers and travelling public, and the governments and the national and international institutions representing them. Some of these areas that clearly justify cooperation beyond Europe's borders are Air Traffic Management (ATM), harmonized certification rules, environmental effects, safety and security, fair trade and open markets and are considered next.

9.1 Air Traffic Management

Air traffic is expected to continue to grow at a rate of 2 to 7% per year depending on the region of the world. It is generally agreed that the main potential limitation to this continuing growth is the capacity of the air traffic system including airports and Air Traffic Management (ATM). Airports are a local issue, although with far reaching geographical implications in the case of major hubs. ATM is a global issue in the sense that it should function seamlessly worldwide, over continents and across oceans, and in densely, sparsely or uninhabited regions.

The air traffic is densest in Europe and the north-eastern corridor of the US. Past experience in these areas has shown that when traffic approaches the available capacity there is a combination of entirely undesirable consequences: (i) departure and arrival delays that cause passenger dissatisfaction and can hinder business activities; (ii) aircraft in flying holding patterns awaiting permission to land and take-off queues of airplanes waiting to gain access to a runway; (iii) associated with (ii) there is an increase in fuel consumption, and also increased pollution and noise, precisely near the airport areas where these issues are more sensitive; (iii) the economic losses are not just increased fuel costs and lost revenues for airlines but also the loss of valuable time for passengers and business travel.

Through advances in technology and procedures ATM in Europe and the US has mostly managed to stay ahead of the growth of air traffic, but not by a wide margin all the time, so that there are still occasional delays and the overall challenge remains. This challenge is recognized at a political level as testified by the large programs SESAR in Europe and NextGen in the US that are under some pressure to provide evidence of results and progress in the quest to keep air traffic capacity ahead of air transport growth and avoid the risk of massive flight delays and cancellations.

Progress in ATM is more marked in Europe and the US both because of the market pull of having the densest air traffic in the world and by the market push of being able to provide the most advanced relevant technologies, such as radars, navigation and communication systems, satellite links, equipment for Air Traffic Control (ATC) centres and control towers, including operator consoles and other hardware and operating systems incorporating sophisticated software. The market for ATM equipment and services is considerable and not to be

underestimated compared with the market for aircraft and airlines services, since they are all complementary and interdependent.

The situation is simpler in the US which as a single nation has the same procedures and compatible equipment under the auspices of the FAA that is both the only Air Navigation Services Provide (ANSP) and also the certification authority. In Europe: (i) there is a division in ATM sectors affected by national borders; (ii) the national ANSPs coordinate their activities through Eurocontrol and operate a diversity of hardware and software ;(iii) the membership of Eurocontrol is wider than that of the European Union and does not coincide with the certification authority (EASA) which groups the national certification authorities. The Single Sky is a given in the US and work in progress in Europe. Despite all these factors Europe betters the US in most ATM performance metrics like timeliness of flights and achieves the same or higher safety standards.

While there is healthy and desirable competition in the supply of ATM equipment and systems, the requirement for seamless operation over continents and across oceans should be preserved. Also, many of the basic technologies are common and it is their implementation in commercial products that is competitive. The seamless integration of SESAR and NextGen across the Atlantic Ocean is as good example of the need for and benefits of cooperation and coordination among the two world leaders in ATM technology. The benefits will be felt worldwide since the same issues of seamless air transport apply across national borders and the Pacific and Indian Oceans, and major suppliers of hardware are Europe and the US.

Considering the likely and needed progress in ATM (Key Topic T9.1), a comparison can be made between the two largest programs in the world (Key Topic T9.2): SESAR in Europe and NextGen in the US.

KEY TOPIC T9.1 EVOLUTION OF ATM IN EUROPE AND ELSEWHERE

T9.1.1 Steps Toward the Single European Sky (SES)

The Single European Sky (SES) initiative was launched in the beginning of the present century by the European Commission, mainly driven by important delays in aviation operation in Europe by the end of the 19th century. In other words, its primary goal was and is still to meet future capacity and safety needs through different tools, mainly legislation framework and research.

The first step taken was a legislative package drafted by the European Commission at the end of 2001 which was adopted by the European Parliament and Council in March 2004, since which the European Union has gained competences in air traffic management (ATM) and the decision-making process has moved away from an intergovernmental practice to a common European framework.

The legislative package adopted in 2004 comprised four basic regulations, which addressed the reinforcement of safety and air navigation services. The regulations provided the framework for the creation of additional capacity and for improved efficiency and interoperability of ATM system in Europe. These four basic regulations were [1]:

- Framework Regulation (EC N° 549/2004), which addresses the framework for the creation of the Single European Sky.
- Service provision Regulation (EC N° 550/2004), which addresses the provision of air navigation services in the Single European Sky.
- Airspace Regulation (EC N° 551/2004), which addresses the organization and use of airspace in the Single European Sky.
- Interoperability Regulation (EC N° 552/2004), which addresses the interoperability of the European air traffic management (ATM) network.

These four regulations formed the SES I Package, and the result of its implementation was the insufficient progress in key areas hence deep modifications were needed. The key areas that needed to be developed were, mainly [2]:

- Performance review of service providers: The Framework Regulation foresaw Performance review of Air Navigation Service Providers (ANSP) in which data gathering and benchmarking were expected to commence in 2008 in order to form a solid basis for future development of the Single Sky initiative.
- Peer review of supervisory authorities: it was foreseen in order to ensure a uniform level of safety and even application of the Common Requirements. With the completion of the first Certification exercise by the NSAs in July 2007, the peer review was established with first visits in early 2008.
- Transparency of charging: the first review under the Common Charging Scheme Regulation was expected to guarantee a greater transparency for the determination, imposition and enforcement of charges for air navigation services.
- Airspace design: the mandate process to Eurocontrol was initiated on a number of draft Regulations related to airspace such as the establishment of a European Upper Flight Information Region (EUFR), airspace classification in the lower airspace or common principles for route and sector design. In this manner, progress in all three areas was slow and the Commission studied alternative mechanisms.
- Functional Airspace Blocks (FABs): a key element of SES was the establishment of Functional Airspace Blocks (FABs), which were foreseen as the mechanisms for ensuring maximum capacity and efficiency of the air traffic management network.

Back in 2007, SES did not deliver the expected results in some important areas. In general, the FAB approach was not producing the benefits hoped for in terms of improved flight efficiency, cost reduction and "defragmentation". It was recognized that the creation of FABs was a new challenge and suffered from significant technical and organizational difficulties, sovereignty, particularly concerning Member States responsibilities and associated liability for their airspace and the involvement of the military remained an issue. Besides, even though legislation had powerful tools to improve performance through: designation of service providers; unbundling of services; use of economic incentives; setting of user charges; changes in route structure; establishment of FABs; rationalization of infrastructure; etc., Member States did not make sufficient use of them to improve cost or operational efficiency of service provision [2].

In this manner, the SES II Package was defined in 2009 through Regulation EC N° 1070/2009 in which the main aim was to increase the overall performance of the air traffic management

system in Europe, based on the insufficient progress in key areas from the start of the SES I Package, as explained above. Thus, the Commission adopted and implemented extensive and exhaustive implementing legislation in which more than 20 implementing rules and community specifications (or technical standards) were adopted by the European Commission in order to ensure the interoperability of technologies and systems [3]. Therefore, with the SES II Package, a step forward was made towards establishing targets in key areas of safety, network capacity, effectiveness and environmental impact.

This SES II Package was intended to accelerate the realization of the SES and its benefits with high-levels goals to achieve by 2020 relative to 2005. To achieve these goals the European Parliament established a framework of five pillars (Figure 9.1) based on technology, safety, performance-based regulation, airports and human factors. This framework is based on an integrated approach towards safety by the extension of the competencies of the EASA in the field of aerodromes, air traffic management and air navigation services, through the establishment of a joint undertaking (JU) on research & development, the SESAR JU (SESAR standing for the Single European Sky ATM Research). A Network Manager for the European ATM network has been created, while an independent Performance Review Body (PRB) supports the Commission in the development and management of the SES performance scheme in which Functional Airspace Blocks (FABs) have a key role to play [3].

Figure 9.1 - SES implementation five pillars
Source: A Blueprint for the Single European Sky by IATA

Each one of these five pillars will help to achieve the overall SES objectives through a holistic approach and they are specifically explained below [4]:

Technology Pillar

The Single European Sky ATM Research (SESAR) program has been a strong focus for many stakeholders across the industry. More than €2 billion has been committed to the development phase and is estimated that around 3,000 people are currently engaged in this unprecedented research and development effort to improve ATM efficiency. The encouraging results of this development phase have demonstrated that new concepts are feasible however the benefits will be much delayed and at a reduced level than originally planned. Additionally, SESAR deployment will only deliver a portion of the SES high-level goals and, if the technology

component is not deployed in synchronization with the other pillars, it will lead to further waste and non-delivery of benefits.

Safety Pillar

To date the SES, I and II packages focused on making progress in areas of safety and clarified the respective roles of regulators, supervision authorities and service providers. The evolution of the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) to cover ATM and airports is also an important step towards the supervision of safety across the entire air transport supply chain. However, at this point, it is considered that EASA must improve its cost-efficiency. Importantly, it is lacking some of the necessary resource capability in order to effectively perform new responsibilities, especially with respect to appropriately experienced and skilled professionals. Reporting and transparency are also insufficient. For example, it is concerning that in the PRR for the 2011 calendar year, that 12 European Civil Aviation Conference states did not submit safety template data to the Eurocontrol Safety Regulation Commission.

Legislative Pillar

The legislative pillar consists of three components which have close interrelationships; the Performance Scheme, the FABs and the Network Manager.

Performance Scheme

The Regulation established that a Performance Scheme should be set up to improve the performance of air navigation services and network functions as much as the scheme aims to ensure that capacity is increased. As a result, flights will be significantly less delayed, saving unnecessary costs for airlines and passengers. In addition, the environmental impact of air traffic will be reduced due to more efficient and shorter flight paths. Air travellers should benefit from a punctual, greener and more cost-efficient mode of transport with a maintained or even enhanced level of safety. In this manner, the scheme should include Community-wide performance targets on the key performance areas of safety, environment, capacity and cost-efficiency. National plans ensuring consistency with this as established by this Regulation and Community-wide performance targets must be defined, and moreover periodic review, monitoring and benchmarking of air navigation services and network functions should be conducted to ensure that targets are met. The Regulation also establishes reference periods (periods of validity and application of Union-wide performance targets and the performance plans): the first reference period, known as RP1, covered the calendar years 2012-2014, the current one, RP2, includes the calendar years 2015-2019 and RP3 will start in 2020 and subsequent periods will cover five calendar years.

As example of monitoring, en route ATFM delay has changed along the past years (see Figure 9.2). At the beginning of RP1, the average delay was lower than the target set for 2012 (0.63 vs 0.7) and, although the target has been even more restrictive every year, the average delay was also lower than the target in 2013 (0.54 vs 0.6). However, since 2014 until now, the average en route ATFM delay has been higher than the target set and, even worse, the average delay has continued increasing until set the maximum difference in the current year (1.07 vs 0.5).

Therefore, as an increasing trend is underway, air traffic stakeholders should implement mitigating measures in order to chase the fulfilment of the targets for each reference period during the following years.

Figure 9.2 - En-route ATFM delay (RP1-RP2) (min/flight)

Functional Airspace Blocks

The FABs are a vital foundation element of the SES, designed to rationalize European ATM. There are currently 9 FABs established as can be seen in the following Figure 9.3:

Figure 9.3 - Functional airspace blocks (FABs)
Source: EUROCONTROL

The establishment of Functional Airspace Blocks (FABs) is a key mechanism of the Single European Sky (SES) and represents the framework established by Member States to enable this increased cooperation and integration leading to a more rational organization of airspace and service provision poised to meet the performance expectations of the airspace users and that of the European Union through its performance scheme [5]. In this way, route design has seen an increase in operational efficiency, however, major technical, cultural and industrial challenges still need to be addressed. Most European ANSPs continue to develop their own ATM systems and their own training capability, which leads to difficulty in standardizing EU-wide service delivery, inhibits staff mobility and adds significantly to overall costs.

Network Manager

The Network Manager function was established at the beginning of 2012. The function has a governance structure supportive of airspace user needs and will be a useful tool to drive the implementation of SES operations towards increased performance. However, there are also some unresolved matters that relate to the on-going EUROCONTROL network technology research and development. To ensure the effectiveness of this role, the SES regulation should explicitly state that the Network Manager has the authority to enforce coordinated actions by ANSPs. Additionally, the Network Manager role needs to be strengthened to ensure that it can rationalize the network and identify opportunities for service quality improvement by FABs.

Airports Pillar

The need to better integrate airport processes with airspace management using a standardized approach is evident if the capacity goals of the SES are to be realized and we are not to continue wasting €2.35 billion in additional costs attributable to the airport and associated terminal airspace.

Human Factors Pillar

Of all the pillars, the least tangible progress has occurred with respect to the human factors and social issues involved in SES implementation. It is well recognized that this is a challenging area and will take commitment and diligence by ANSP management and staff to work through this transition. Without a successful human factors element to this transition, the SES will result in the deployment of new technology that will not be fully utilized and not deliver the anticipated benefits. A clear focus on better planning the engagement with ANSP staff is needed.

In conclusion, the experience gained with SES I since 2004 and SES II since 2009 has shown that the principles and direction of the SES are valid and warrant a continuation of their implementation. However, the initiative is experiencing significant delays in its implementation, notably in the achievement of the performance goals and the deployment of its basic elements (such as functional airspace blocks (FABs) or National Supervisory Authorities (NSAs)).

In 2009, when adopting the SES II Package, the legislator decided that SES II would be done in two stages and invited the Commission to come back to do an alignment of SES and EASA

regulations after the initial set of EASA implementing measures and audit experiences concerning ANS was in place. A recast of the legislative package was therefore already foreseen, primarily aiming at simplifying and clarifying the border line between EASA and SES legal frameworks.

The process of recast also gives the opportunity to assess the effectiveness of the existing legal provisions in the light of the lack of timely implementation of the SES initiative. This process of revision of the SES legal framework, known under the abbreviation of SES 2+, is intended to accelerate the implementation of the reform of air navigation services without departing from its original objectives and principles.

The purpose of the SES 2+ Package is to introduce improvements in oversight of rules, the performance scheme, the customer focus of the service providers and in overall performance. In addition, the SES 2+ Package will simplify the legislation by eliminating certain overlaps in the existing framework. Concerns have been raised about several overlapping areas existing in the SES framework and there is also a need to clarify the roles of the various actors at EU-level. This alignment between the four SES Regulations and the EASA Basic Regulation, is a purely technical adaptation measure already required by the legislation. Due to the extent of overlap between the Regulations, a recast of the remaining parts of the four SES Regulations into one is a logical consequence of that adaptation [6].

T9.1.2 Comparison of SESAR with NextGen

Within Single European Sky framework, particularly on the technology side, Single European Sky ATM Research (SESAR) Programme supports the technological development in order to provide advanced technologies and procedures with a view to modernizing and optimizing the future European ATM network. These technological solutions are aimed to increase the performance of Europe's ATM system and moreover they contribute to the implementation of the Single European Sky. This modernization and harmonization of ATM systems are expected to be achieved through the definition, development, validation and deployment of innovative technological and operational ATM solutions.

Figure 9.4 - SESAR main pillars
Source: SESAR webpage

As one of its pillars (Figure 9.4), SESAR is defined in the European ATM Master Plan which is the agreed roadmap that connects ATM research and development activities with deployment

scenarios to achieve the SES performance objectives. These development and validation activities are carried out by SESAR Joint Undertaking (SJU) and they are deployed through Common Projects. All three of these pillars (definition, development and deployment) are components of a virtual lifecycle that actively involves the stakeholders and the Commission in different forms of partnerships.

While the SES packages (I and II) were defined, two SESAR programs were also established. These SESAR programs are named SESAR I and SESAR 2020.

The Programme for SESAR 2020 is structured into three main research phases, beginning with Exploratory Research, then is further expanding within a Public-Private-Partnership (PPP) to conduct Industrial Research and Validation then further exploits the benefits of the PPP in Demonstrating at large Scale the concepts and technologies in representative environments to firmly establish the performance benefits and risks.

On the other hand, the Next Generation Air Transportation System (NextGen) is the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA)-led modernization of the United States' air transportation system to make flying even safer, more efficient, and more predictable, according to NextGen webpage.

In this manner, NextGen is composed of a comprehensive suite of upgrades, technologies and procedures that improve every phase of flight and enable aircraft to move more efficiently from departure to arrival. For example, one of the most important goals in NextGen is to use satellite technology to enhance navigation and surveillance, deploy digital systems for communication, and improve information management. Since the first demonstrations, trials and initial deployments of new systems and procedures, national airspace system (NAS) operators and users are benefiting from NextGen.

Globally, each one of these development programs (SESAR and NextGen) are focused on the specific problems that each region has. On the one hand, SESAR is mainly focused on the technological development that allows to set a common framework for the entire European Union from a holistic point of view. This common framework is intended to remove the fragmentation present in European aviation (for example each Member State has its own supervision authorities and air navigation service providers) in such a way that the functioning is as uniform as possible in the whole EU regardless of the Member State where the service is provided. On the other hand, the United States are not as fragmented as the European Union (the US only has a unique air navigation service provider) hence its development program is focused on improving the performance through new technologies that allows to reduce delays produced in its airspace and airports and also to increase its capacity.

Likewise, these differences between SESAR and NextGen make sense if the US and Europe ATM-related operational performance is compared. For example, according to 2010 data (see Figure 9.5), some areas are pretty similar and other areas are too different. In this manner, with similar sized airspace (11.5 million km² for Europe, 10.4 million km² for the US), a comparable number of airports (450 in Europe for 509 in the US) and with very similar service levels, the US ATM system is able to manage 67% more flights (15.9 million flights in the US compared to 9.5 million flights in Europe) with less air traffic controllers (14600 in the US for 16700 in

Europe) and 38% less staff (35200 in the US for 57000 in Europe). The main drivers behind such difference is the fragmentation of the European ATM system as there were 38 ANSPs in Europe (for only one in the US) and 63 en-route centres in Europe (for 20 in the US).

Figure 9.5 - 2010 U.S./Europe Comparison of ATM-Related Operational Performance

Source: A Blueprint for the Single European Sky by IATA

Comparing to more recent data, 2010 figures have remained almost undisturbed through the years. Therefore, while the US and the European ATM system are operated with similar technology and operational concepts, there is still a key difference: the US ATM system is operated by one single service provider (ANSP) which uses the same tools and equipment, communication processes and a common set of rules and procedures. However, even though ATFM and ASM in Europe are provided and coordinated centrally by the Network Manager, at the ATC level the European system is much more fragmented, and the provision of air navigation services is still largely organised by State boundaries [7].

In total, there are 37 different en route ANSPs of various geographical areas which have been operating different systems under slightly different sets of rules and procedures, and also different tools and equipment.

Therefore, as since 2004 the Single European Sky (SES) initiative of the European Union aims at reducing this fragmentation, SES 2+ Package is also addressing these issues.

Thus, the first problem addressed in SES 2+ Package is the insufficient efficiency of air navigation due to ANS provision remains relatively inefficient in terms of cost and flight efficiency as well as the capacity offered. The main issues to be solved are the shortcomings in setting up and enforcing the performance scheme, ineffective supervisory authorities and the disproportionately high amount of support staff in the service providers.

The second key problem addressed in SES 2+ Package is a fragmented ATM system. The European ATM system consists of 27 national authorities overseeing in total over a hundred Air Navigation Service Providers (ANSPs) – en route, approach and aerodrome providers-, with the associated variance in systems, rules and procedures. There is a large amount of additional costs caused by the fact that Europe has a large number of service providers, each procuring

their own systems, mostly training their own staff, creating their own operating procedures and being limited territorially to providing services in a small airspace. To overcome fragmentation, the SES has introduced the ideas of cross-border Functional Air Blocks (FABs) and the centralised Network Manager to run certain network level services. However, FABs and the Network Manager still remains too weak hence developments should be carried out in these areas [6].

T9.1.3 The World Market for ATM Equipment

Firstly, ATM service and infrastructure have to be differentiated. The ATM service is organized through a certain form of supply chain: most of service providers are state-owned companies which buy systems (radar stations, navaid stations, control centres, communication systems) from equipment suppliers. These systems form a cluster of tools that help to provide air traffic management (ATM) thereby they are considered as part of the ATM infrastructure.

From an economic point of view, international rules set up by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) prevent the transformation of the ATM service into a real market. In this manner, a state is not authorized to raise money in selling the access to its sky in such a way that it can only ask airlines to pay for the services given to their aircraft passing through its sky: communication, surveillance, navigation, airspace design, control and flow management.

To be able to deliver the service, air navigation service providers (ANSPs) have to be equipped. Providing ATM service requires different equipment such as radars to determine the position of the aircraft, navaid stations to help aircraft knowing exactly where they are, communication systems to secure exchanges between controllers and pilots, avionics systems, and so on. However, new technologies are allowing that exchanges between controllers and pilots are partly automated and managed by satellites (via datalink), moreover nowadays aircraft usually navigate using their position obtained by satellite instead of ground navaid stations (via performance-based navigation), thereby the equipment market is also adapting to new technologies [8].

In this context, the ATM equipment market is "small" in the sense of that equipment development and manufacturing companies are few so everybody in the market knows everybody. Some of the main companies involved are: BAE Systems Plc, Northrop Grumman Corp., Indra Sistemas SA, Thales SA, Intelcan Technosystems Inc., Frequentis and so on.

Some of these companies are focused on specific equipment. For example, Toshiba only manufactures PSRs, SSRs, VORs and DMEs whilst Frequentis is focused on communication and information systems. On the other hand, other companies are focused on a wide market. This is the case of Thales or Indra. For example, the last one manufactures many systems such as digital voice communications control system, signal multichannel recorders, DVORs, DMEs, ILSs, integrated ATC automation systems, ACC, APP and TWR simulators, PSRs, 3D Radars, monopulse SSRs, SMRs, ADS-B ground stations and so on [9].

As ATM equipment is made of complex systems in which connections, electronics and reliability are key factors, its development and manufacturing entail many complications and usually needs an important investment from the company hence it is difficult to enter in the

market for new interested companies. Thus, some segments of the market are run by what seems to be a duopoly. This is the case of the ILS systems in whose market two companies are the main suppliers in the world: Indra and Thales. On the one hand, Thales have sold more than 700 ILS systems worldwide whilst Indra have sold more than 1200 ILS systems worldwide.

KEY TOPIC T9.2 COMPARISON OF SESAR WITH NEXTGEN

T9.2.1 Introduction

For both the SESAR and NextGen, the change to operations includes shared situational awareness for more collaborative decision making and trajectory-based operations for safer, more efficient airspace utilization. This requires transforming the procedures and regulations as well as the organizations' fundamental concepts and technologies. Net Centric Operations allow migrating functionality among actors and facilities to improve the efficiency of the system as a whole but requires that basic tenets be changed. In the case of ATM, this means changing the paradigm from extrapolating the aircraft intent based on radar data to the aircraft explicitly sharing it.

SESAR

Supporting the entire ATM system, and essential to its efficient operation, is a netcentric, System Wide Information Management (SWIM) environment that includes the aircraft as well as all ground facilities. It will support collaborative decision-making processes, using efficient end-user applications to exploit the power of shared information. Interoperability between civil and military systems will also be a key enabler to enhance the overall performance of the ATM network.

Fundamentally, SESAR operational concepts place the business trajectory at the core of the system, with the aim to execute each flight as close as possible to the intention of the user. This is seen as a move from airspace to trajectory focus while introducing a new approach to airspace design and management. The collaborative planning will continuously be reflected through a common shared Network Operations Plan (NOP). Integrated airport operations will contribute to capacity gains and reduce the environmental impact. New separation modes will allow for increased capacity. Using these new integrated and collaborative features, humans will be central in the future European ATM system as managers and decision-makers.

SESAR has set the definition of the initial 2025 performance targets. ATM performance covers a broad spectrum represented by the 11 ICAO **Key Performance Areas (KPA)**. The KPA targets represent initial values (working assumptions), subject to further analysis and validation. Most KPAs are interdependent and will be the basis for impact assessment and consequent trade-off analysis for decision-making.

The 11 KPAs are as follows: Capacity, Cost-Effectiveness, Efficiency, Flexibility, Predictability, Safety, Security, Environmental Sustainability, Access and Equity, Participation, Interoperability.

Those that are highlighted, below, are the KPAs that SESAR sees as directly linked to the achievement of the proposed SESAR Vision.

Capacity:

A 3-fold increase in capacity, while reducing delays on the ground and in the air (en route and airport network), is necessary to be able to handle traffic growth well beyond 2030. The ATM system is to accommodate a forecasted 73% increase in traffic by 2030 from the 2015 baseline, while meeting the targets for safety and quality of service.

Cost-Effectiveness:

2030 Target: Halve the total direct ATM costs. The ATM Performance Framework provides a common basis to ensure the effectiveness of the ATM system through a dynamic relationship between European States, institutions and regulations ("Institutional and Regulatory Framework"), and all aircraft operators, air navigation service providers and airports working in partnership to match the targets ("Business Management Framework").

Safety:

To improve safety levels by ensuring that the numbers of ATM induced accidents and serious or risk bearing incidents decrease. The traffic increase to up to 2030 requires an improvement factor of 3, and for the long term a factor of 10 to meet the threefold in traffic.

Environment:

As a first step towards the political objective to enable a 10% reduction in the effects flights have on the environment by emission improvements through the reduction of gate-to-gate excess fuel consumption, minimizing noise emissions and their impacts for each flight to the greatest extent possible, minimizing other adverse atmospheric effects to the greatest extent possible.

NextGen

NextGen is focused on ATM System Transformation via trajectory-based operations with an emphasis on user needs. It endeavours to increase efficiencies and decision making to account for growing demand and diversity of airspace participants and eliminate limitations caused by human decision making based on verbal communications. Transformation is enabled through distributed decision making, international harmonization, optimized division of human/automation roles, net-enabled probabilistic weather, integrated into automated decision tools, environmental sustainability, integrated safety management systems, and layered adaptive security. NextGen establishes principles and definitions of desired end-states in the varying domains associated with these services. This chapter does not discuss specific implementations or standards or methodologies of achieving these end-states or adhering to these principles.

T9.2.2 Net Centric Commonalities

NextGen

While the NextGen Concept of Operations uses different language to discuss desired performance improvements, the intent is very similar to the SESAR use of the KPAs. NextGen specifies Transformation Objectives in detail (in the IWP and in the domain chapters of the COO) for each area of the ATM system, and describes the fundamental goals of NextGen as the following:

- Meet the diverse operational objectives of all airspace users and accommodate a broader range of aircraft capabilities and performance characteristics;
- Meet the needs of flight operators and other NextGen stakeholders for access, efficiency, and predictability in executing their operations and missions;
- Be fundamentally safe, secure, of sufficient capacity, environmentally acceptable, and affordable for both flight operators and service providers;

NextGen also references the general goals of ATM Transformation from the NGATS Integrated Plan (2004). Six national and international goals and 19 objectives for NextGen are described. These are:

1. Retain U.S. Leadership in Global Aviation

- a) Retain role as world leader in aviation;
- b) Reduce costs of aviation;
- c) Enable services tailored to traveller and shipper needs;
- d) Encourage performance-based, harmonized global standards for US products and services.

2. Ensure Safety

- a) Maintain aviation's record as the safest mode of transportation;
- b) Improve level of safety of U.S. air transportation system;
- c) Increase level of safety of worldwide air transportation system.

3. Ensure our National Defence

- a) Provide for common defence while minimizing civilian constraints;
- b) Coordinate a national response to threats;
- c) Ensure global access to civilian airspace.

4. Expand Capacity

- a) Satisfy future growth in demand and operational diversity;
- b) Reduce transit time and increase predictability;
- c) Minimize impact of weather and other disruptions.

5. Protect the Environment

- a) Reduce noise, emissions, and fuel consumption
- b) Balance aviation's environmental impacts with other societal objectives

6. Secure the Nation

- a) Mitigate new and varied threats;
- b) Ensure security efficiently serves demand;
- c) Tailor strategies to threats, balancing costs and privacy issues;
- d) Ensure traveller and shipper confidence in system security.

In addition to these key performance goals, NextGen sets forth guiding principles for the development and implementation of the enterprise. While not goals, they do establish important achievement markers for industry as the system moves towards the future. The principles are:

- Frequency Bandwidth/Spectrum Capacity Supporting Stakeholder/COI Information Sharing Needs – (i.e. adequate communications capacity and QoS);
- Voice by Exception and Improved Where Necessary;
- Protocol Resolution – Sufficient/Dynamic addressing, secure end-to-end connectivity;
- Data Availability – Push/Pull and Publish/Subscribe capabilities between COIs;
- Content Understanding – metadata tagging and federated search;
- Technology for Timely Decision Making – Data is relevant for action by COIs;
- No Single Point of Failure – an enterprise solution that dynamically allocates resources to continue operations (transport and services);
- Data Interface Oriented – vice a Hardware Interface model, this software and customizable COI interface facilitates ease of improvement and upgrade;
- Information Assurance – Appropriate access to information by authorized COIs
- Cross Domain (i.e. Multi-Level Security or Multiple Levels of Security) Exchange/Gateway Capability;
- A key element of both SESAR and NextGen is System Wide Information Management (SWIM), which is a focus on how the technologies and systems will enable shared awareness for operations;
- The planned technology is very similar – ADS-B, Data Link, Extended Conflict Detection
- Both Systems recognize the primacy of data communications to the cockpit and amongst ground systems (“voice by exception”), while maintaining the requirement for voice for emergency purposes, back up, and for communications with less completely equipped aircraft;
- Both systems embrace a network-centric infrastructure with shared services and distributed data environments interacting semi-autonomously to achieve system-wide efficiencies.

T9.2.3 Differences

SESAR and NextGen differ in their implementation frameworks because they are tied to very different European and US industry structures. NextGen tends to be closely tied to government in a hierarchical framework whereas SESAR appears to be a more collaborative approach, including, but not limited to, ATM ground activities. NextGen, while having a longer timeline to implement, takes a broader approach to transforming the entire air transportation system, including ground activities.

T9.2.4 Flow Management

SESAR

In parallel with all the phases of individual business trajectory planning, a Collaborative Decision Making (CDM) process is in place in which all stakeholders share the necessary information to ensure the long and short-term stability and efficiency of the ATM system and to ensure that the necessary set of ATM services can be delivered on the day of operation.

The key tool used to ensure a common view of the network situation will be the NOP. It is a dynamic rolling plan for continuous operations, rather than a series of discrete daily plans which draw on the latest available information being shared in the system. The NOP works with a set of collaborative applications providing access to traffic demand, airspace and airport capacity and constraints, scenarios to assist in managing diverse events and simulation tools for scenario modelling. The aim of the NOP is to facilitate the processes needed to reach agreements on demand and capacity.

The NOP, in its initial phase, enables collaborative Demand and Capacity Balancing (DCB) through an integrated airspace/airport organization and management in accordance with the nature of the traffic being handled. The NOP supports layered planning on local, sub-Regional and Regional level.

Long-term ATM planning starts with traffic growth forecasts, including user business strategy development, and planned aircraft procurement. The required new assets can be considered as available resources for DCB only when their date of delivery becomes firm. Airspace Users will then declare their intentions through Shared Business Trajectories possibly including the requirement for airspace reservations. Network Management, working collaboratively with all partners will assess the resource situation regarding potential demand. Network Management will facilitate dialogue and negotiation to resolve demand/capacity imbalances in a collaborative manner. Tools will be used to assess network efficiency.

NextGen

The US version places a great deal of emphasis on the collaborative and/or automated decision-making process between the Flight Operations Centres (FOCs)/cockpit and ground Air Traffic Management. The Key Characteristics paragraph of the COO states, "[t]o the maximum extent possible, decisions in NextGen are made at the local level with an awareness

of system-wide implications. This includes, to a greater extent than ever before, an increased level of decision-making by the flight crew and FOCs.”

Traffic information is available via the network to the ground and onboard displays, thus allowing pilots to collaborate with ground control operators on the best strategy for their preferred trajectory. More importantly, NextGen envisions a set of Infrastructure and Information services that, when provided; enable automated collaborative planning systems to achieve efficiencies for individual airlines and the overall system.

T9.2.5 Weather

The primary difference between SESAR and NextGen concerning weather is the way the information is acquired. In NextGen, a centralized government-run weather service is anticipated, and in SESAR the information will be derived from a variety of traditional sources. A more net centric solution would be to allow each carrier to be able to choose whatever information is available from certified sources to provide maximum safety.

SESAR

The information will be derived from a variety of (traditional) sources including an Increased reliance on remote sensing systems, aircraft derived data and satellite-based weather information. With enhanced digital communications services, the provision of Metrology (MET) information will encompass ground-based and potentially airborne automation systems and human users.

NextGen

NextGen foresees weather as moving from a stand-alone display to an integrated decision-making element. A primary objective of NextGen is the establishment of a single authoritative weather service available to all systems communicating within the network. While little is said about how this service will be run, great detail is provided on what type of service will be available. The service will draw data from traditional weather reporting systems, aircraft and other sensors in route including UAVs specifically deployed for weather collection, commercial weather services which will augment the system at the basic provision rate and presumably at premium rates as a choice of individual carriers and aircraft and potentially airborne automation systems and human users as well as from weather national service.

T9.2.6 Infrastructure Service Domains

SESAR

SWIM is supported by a set of architectural elements (so-called SWIM architecture) allowing exchange of data and ATM services across the entire European ATM system. SWIM is based on the interconnection of various automation systems. The SWIM architecture aims at providing specific value-added information management services: the SWIM services. They will:

- Support flexible and modular sharing of information, as opposed to closely coupled interfaces;
- Provide transparent access to ATM services likely to be geographically distributed;
- Assure the overall consistency.

SWIM services will be required to comply with potentially stringent Quality of Service (QoS) parameters, such as integrity, availability, latency, etc. The full impact of those QoS on the proposed architecture will require significant R&D activities. For instance, not all users will have permission to access all data within a domain because of operational, commercial or security reasons.

SWIM integrates Air-Ground and Ground-Ground data and ATM services exchange. The scope extends to all information that is of potential interest to ATM, including trajectories, surveillance data, aeronautical information of all types, meteorological data etc.

NextGen

NextGen establishes the requirement for the provision of a robust infrastructure on which the entire system will rely. The services provided across the enterprise are:

- Information Sharing Services: Enabling operational entities, COIs, services, and applications throughout the NAS to collaborate in a seamless information infrastructure with Air Navigation Service, airport, and flight operations, Shared Situational Awareness, compliance and regulation oversight, and security, safety, environmental, and performance management services.
- Ground Services: Providing surveillance, communications, and flight data management to any service provider regardless of its physical location, thus removing geography as a limiting factor for air assets and ground control.
- Air-Ground Network Services: Frequency-to-airspace sector mapping is abandoned in favour of a dynamic network environment – the “intelligent network.” Data communications are central to Trajectory Based Operations, including the use of 4DTs (pushback and taxi inclusive) for planning and
- execution on the surface, automated trajectory analysis and separation assurance, and aircraft separation assurance... [with] situational awareness of the 4DTs and short-term intent of surrounding aircraft.
- ANSP Infrastructure Services: Summarized with the term “virtual tower.” Such services provide the ability to locate ANSP facilities where optimal, without limitation to airspace proximity
- Aircraft Data Communications Link: Allowing aircraft and ground assets to connect to the data network for collaborative purposes
- Infrastructure Management Services – Insuring QoS
- Mission Support Services - provide information assurance, protocols, and standards applicable for the Net-Centric Infrastructure Services (Access, Connectivity, Processing, Posting, and Pulling).

T9.2.7 Information, Data and Information Services

Information and Data in SESAR and NextGen

A difference between the two documents lies in the treatment of information. While both indicate that data and information are key to integration and net centrality, SESAR, being a more decentralized model, calls for the establishment of a Reference Model for data and for data normalization and standardization. NextGen, envisioning a more centralized government-run approach, goes further, describing not only data but the provision of "information services" in a service-oriented and networked environment. Both concepts call for systems to make use of centralized and decentralized services, delivered in a network enabled, SOA environment, with NextGen suggesting a more centralized approach than SESAR. Collaboration on the development and fielding of these services, and agreement on the standardization of data reference models, could provide great efficiencies to both SESAR and NextGen efforts.

SESAR and NextGen both place a great deal of emphasis on the information enabling the processes, interaction, and automated support of the ATM enterprise. While there are differences in terminology and a core difference in how the information elements are described, the content of the information and that content's purpose are very similar. NextGen describes information elements in the terminology of "services" - using a service-oriented architecture context to describe the automated and ubiquitous nature of the key information elements serving the overall system. SESAR describes the information elements in terms of data models associated with different domains (flight, weather, surveillance, etc) and describes a reference model architecture that, when used, makes the data and information available for use by the system participants.

Key to the continued comparison of the two systems will be an in-depth comparison and integration of the data models and the network-centric services. Each system should be able to use the data and information available within the other to execute the integrated, collaborative, and automated analytical and decision-making functions necessary to execute this transformational ATM.

SESAR

ATM Information Reference Model:

- Within the SWIM, Interoperable ATM information will be precisely defined by a Reference Model;
- Application independent and not constrained by implementation solutions;
- Addresses different domains of information as needed by the Users and expressed in business terms;
- Describes cross-domains data in a consistent way;
- Allows fulfilling the SESAR overall information sharing requirement, across ground and air heterogeneous systems.

The information to be exchanged needs to be modelled explicitly, to allow a precise and concrete definition to be agreed.

Interoperability Models:

SWIM is first introduced for En route/Approach ATC and Network (NIMS) interactions, and later including interactions with Airports, AOC and the Aircraft. Flight information is accessible through SWIM services around 2013. Airspace, Demand & Capacity data are accessible through SWIM services around 2016.

The SWIM services will be organized around 5 data domains:

- Flight Data (including detailed trajectories);
- Aeronautical Data;
- Meteo Data;
- Surveillance Data;
- Capacity & Demand Data (including Air Traffic Flow and Capacity Management Scenario).

NextGen

In addition to the Network Centric Infrastructure, Chapter 5 of NextGen discusses the centralized provision of Information Services across that infrastructure. This is a central component of the NextGen Transformation – that is, the provision of a set of data and information services (a “service-oriented environment”) from which each participant in the ATM system can draw capabilities, whether that is to access data for their own application uses or to actually use another application provided as a service to execute flight operations. The development of these services will be a challenging task, especially given the different data models in use across the industry. Collaboration with SESAR on the reference data models discussed in SESAR may benefit NextGen transformation efforts – just as collaboration on the development of centralized services might benefit SESAR participants.

In addition to the Network Centric Infrastructure, Chapter 5 of NextGen discusses the centralized provision of Information Services across that infrastructure. These are:

- Weather Information Services;
- Robust Precision Navigation Services;
- Surveillance Services (Cooperative and Non-Cooperative);
- Flight Plan Filing and Flight Data Management Services;
- Flow Strategy and Trajectory Impact Analysis Services;
- Aeronautical Information Services (AIS);
- Geographical Information System Services (GIS).

The development of services to support flight operations will be a challenging task, especially given the different data models in use across the industry. Collaboration with SESAR on the reference data models discussed in SESAR may benefit NextGen transformation efforts – just as collaboration on the development of centralized services might benefit SESAR participants.

T9.2.8 Aircraft Participation in SWIM

SESAR

The introduction of an Air to Ground Data Link Ground Management System, which is a SWIM node and offers the aircraft a single point of access on the ground with filtering of the shared information that is needed by the aircraft and the update of onboard databases while the aircraft is still at the gate. Benefits are expected through simplification of connectivity functions and on saving multiple connection infrastructures. Safety requires a high availability of the A/G Data link Ground Management System as failure of a system at sub-regional level would jeopardize the complete communication with the aircraft in that sub-region.

NextGen

SWIM is an integral part of the NextGen concept, with the aircraft serving as a node on the network. SWIM encompasses the ability of aircraft and ground assets to collaboratively participate within an enterprise that is providing automated information cockpit-to-cockpit, cockpit-to-ground, ground-to-cockpit, and ground-to-ground. NextGen envisions a virtual network in which each node represents a part of the system –so all information is “system-wide.” Each node participates in the system all the time – and user access and automated tools and services are used to ensure adequate data provision and QoS.

T9.2.9 CNS Development and Impacts

Much ground-based equipment in Europe will reach end of life by 2018 – this is a major driver. Proposing 4 stages – Stage 1 is ADS-B out – then ATSAW, then self-separation (2020 to 2025) and finally the possible need for another link for advanced applications like ASAS (2025). There will be a focus on R&D for possible future applications that might require a better link than 1090 MHz CASCADE program fits into SESAR process. A Joint Undertaking will take place. NextGen and SESAR are working together on joint R&D and hold regular progress meetings.

SESAR

In its simplest form, the 2030 CNS baseline can be characterised as follows:

Communication:

- Communication technologies that enable improved voice and data exchanges between service actors within the system, such as those necessary to support the SWIM functionality and CDM process, for example:
 - Ground-Ground
 - A IP based ground-ground communications network supporting all the ATM applications and SWIM services, together with VoIP for ground segments, including VoIP for the ground segment of the air-ground voice link.
 - Voice
 - 8.33KHz is the standard for voice communications;
 - SATCOM voice for oceanic and remote areas.

- Air-Ground Data link
 - VDL2/ATN.
- Airport
 - A new Airport data-link to support surface communication, using a derivation of the IEEE 802.16.

Navigation:

- Navigation technologies that enable precision positioning, timing and guidance of the aircraft to support high performance, efficient 4D trajectory operations in all phases of flight, for example:
- Primary aircraft positioning means will be satellite based for all flight phases.
- Positioning is expected to rely on a minimum of two dual frequency satellite constellations (Galileo, GPS L1/L5 and potentially other constellations, assuming interoperability) and augmentation as required:
 - Aircraft based augmentation (ABAS) such as INS and multiple GNSS processing receiver;
 - Satellite based augmentation (SBAS) such as EGNOS and WAAS;
- Terrestrial Navigation infrastructure based on DME/DME is maintained to provide a backup for en route and TMA;
- Enhanced on-board trajectory management systems and ATS Flight processing systems to support the trajectory Concept.

Surveillance:

- Surveillance technologies that enable precision monitoring of all traffic to assure safe and efficient operations, including enhanced Traffic Situational Awareness and ASAS.
- For the airspace, Cooperative surveillance will be the norm, complemented as required by Independent Non-Cooperative surveillance to satisfy safety and security requirements. For the Airport both Cooperative and Independent Non-Cooperative surveillance systems will be necessary.
 - PSR will provide Independent Non-Cooperative surveillance;
 - Since aircraft will have the necessary mode S and ADS-B equipment, the choice of Cooperative surveillance technology (Mode S, ADS-B, MLAT) remains flexible, with the service provider determining the best solution for their particular operating environment, based on cost and performance;
 - SMR will provide the Independent Non-Cooperative airport surveillance
- ADS-B-In/Out is provided by 1090 ES;
- With a mandate of 1090 ES-ADS-B-Out, TIS-B will not be needed in the transition to support ASAS applications;
- Satellite based ADS-C for oceanic and remote areas.

CNS beyond 2030

Communication

- Data link becomes the primary means of communications. Voice remains as a back-up;

- Common inter-networking transport mechanism to support the various data-links, managing an end to end Quality of Service;
- Post 2030 implementation of new communications components, comprising terrestrial (wide or narrowband) and space-based components in complement of VDL2/ATN to support the new most demanding data-link services.

Navigation

The availability of other constellations enables increased accuracy and availability. Multi constellation receivers are able to exploit available constellations/satellites (e.g. China, Russia), if the benefits outweigh the added complexity compared to a basic GPS + Galileo combination. Ground based augmentation (GBAS) for Cat II/III approach and landing with backup provided by ILS/MLS, and specific GBAS features may be necessary to meet high performance guidance requirements for airport surface navigation

Surveillance

- PSR is replaced by cheaper forms of Independent Non-Cooperative surveillance;
- The 1090 ES system supporting ADS-B-In/Out is improved and/or complemented with
- an additional high-performance data link.

SESAR

CNS is formulated for 2030 that builds on 8, 33 kilohertz, VDL2/ATN for communication. Navigation builds on satellites for position determination Surveillance system has four fundamental principles that build on primary radar, SSR model S, Wide area Multilateration, ADS-B (builds on 1090 MHz) and monitoring in the aeroplane.

ADS-B equipment has been extensively and successfully tested in operational environments and is an example of a developed SESAR and NextGen technological component.

NextGen addresses transformation as a function of changes to the operational concepts and capabilities between the current state (2018) and 2035. There are interim transformation steps for various sub-domains, but no timelines are discussed for those interim steps to total transformation.

T9.2.10 Anticipated Risks

SESAR

SWIM (including the A/G Data Link Ground Management System) may not meet the required quality of service (which is still to be defined), e.g. with respect to integrity, consistency.

Stakeholders may fail to achieve the required certification of their systems since they will need to carry out a safety analysis of a system that is connected to other stakeholders' systems via SWIM.

Many problems remain particularly with data quality and interoperability.

A key limitation has been the absence of a globally accepted aeronautical information exchange format, but this is now being addressed by AIXM V5.0

NextGen

Automated tools, communications and enterprise management, and improved information flow will naturally provide for increases in efficiencies and effectiveness regarding the ATM System. The overall concept is not, however, without risks. NextGen COO addresses these risks within the appendixes describing additional policy and research needs. Some of the major ones are listed below:

- NextGen assumes a fully available (very high QoS) and robust enterprise network supporting ground, surface, and air assets through all stages of every flight operation. If this network is not reliable, if communications paths and data integrity are not adequately assured, then the automated decision making will not happen, and the efficiencies will not be achieved.
- Moreover, should the system rely heavily on TBO and Flow Management in dense environments and then suffer an outage or data compromise, serious safety or security implications may arise.
- New capabilities and technologies may over-burden the cockpit operation.
- New policies and standards may be needed to ensure data and information security.
- Transformation to “virtual towers” and satellite-based IAPs may present new difficulties in very low visibility conditions.
- There are changing rules, policies, security protections, responsibilities, and authorities for Safety Assurance and Safety Data Information sharing.
- Stakeholders must ensure data integrity across such a wide range of information services, weather, navigation, route planning, etc.)

Both:

- Need to ensure that architectural differences do not impact, for example, how the aircraft is included in the network.
- The investment side of things is a major challenge; stakeholders will need to be convinced that the benefits outweigh the costs.
- Achieving and providing safety for SESAR/NextGen is an enormously tough challenge.

T9.2.11 Contradictions and Major Concept Differences

- NextGen assumes a fully available (very high QoS) and robust enterprise network supporting ground, surface, and air assets through all stages of every flight operation. If this network is not reliable and if communications paths and data integrity are not adequately assured, then the automated decision-making will not happen, and the efficiencies will not be achieved.
- The SESAR Operational Concept time horizon is 2020+: NextGen time horizon is 2025;
- The SESAR Concept essentially has a strict ATM focus: NextGen also deals with other elements that may impact ATM either directly or indirectly (for example Homeland Security);

- The SESAR Concept adopts a largely Gate-to-Gate view with a window on the turn-round process that provides an Enroute-to-Enroute view through shared situational awareness of the status of the process. NextGen adopts a Curb-to-Curb view that encompasses all aspects of airport terminal and passenger operations.
- The SESAR Concept deals with certain issues, for example Safety and the Environment, through some high-level statements and at the KPA level and the detail is the responsibility of other Work Packages: NextGen deals with these issues in detail within the Concept.
- Europe seems to be ahead of the U.S. in data communication, and the U.S. is ahead in defining ADS-B Out.
- Both systems emphasize the increased use of underutilized airports, however there are minor differences. For example, NextGen includes an Airports Preservation Program to “increase community support and protect against encroachment of incompatible land use”, while SESAR states that capacity goals can be met in airspace but that airports are limiting factor.
- SESAR and NextGen differ in the way that Europe comprises several member states that must agree and US is one nation from the start.
- SESAR and NextGen differ in their implementation frameworks because they are tied to very different European and US industry structures.
- The primary difference between SESAR and NextGen concerning weather is the way to acquire the information. In NextGen it seems to be a centralized government-run weather service and SESAR considers the Weather information provision services as outside its scope of work (even it requires that it can use a variety of sources).

NextGen concepts are developed in anticipation of a widely expanding air traffic environment, but also in anticipation of greater technological capabilities for aircraft, ground control systems, surveillance, networks, and automated decision support systems. The overall vision is widely applicable to all operations related to air travel in the US Airspace - from commercial route and passenger planning through ATM and ground support operations.

T9.2.12 Conclusion

SESAR and the US NextGen both have the same basic aim – more efficient use of airspace and better air safety – the implementation frameworks for each are radically different, with the European approach based on a single, multi-stakeholder consortium, and the US model requiring close internal coordination between various government-led programmes to ensure interoperability of components delivered by a variety of consortia.

SESAR tends to focus primarily in Air Traffic Management but has a nearer term for completion. NCOIC highly recommends that the sharing of approaches and lessons learned from each program be made a priority in the other program in order to improve efficiency and avoid stove piping and potential incompatibilities across the Atlantic.

Both organizations are embracing basic network centric concepts. The way each is choosing to implement these is taking a different form.

The common vision is to integrate and implement new technologies to improve air traffic management (ATM) performance – a ‘new paradigm’. SESAR and NextGen combine increased automation with new procedures to achieve safety, economic, capacity, environmental, and security benefits. The systems do not have to be identical but must have aligned requirements for equipment standards and technical interoperability.

SESAR:

- SWIM is a main feature of the SESAR ConOps.
- Information technologies are already available to support SWIM (Datalink may need further Development).
- Institutional barriers (property of data) will need to be mitigated through regulation (if not good will) before SWIM is possible.
- SWIM SUIT will prove the concept using legacy systems using wrapper techniques;
- By year 2025 new systems will be developed to be directly connectable to the SWIM infrastructure, interoperability will be the result.
- Each aircraft should be equipped so that it can achieve adequate end-to-end QoS by being able to receive the required data.
- Investment is a major challenge; stakeholders will need to be convinced that the benefits outweigh the costs.
- The SESAR Operational Concept time horizon is 2025+: NextGen time horizon is 2030+. As a result, all airlines with European routes will be required to harmonize with Eurocontrol solutions early, as each entity seeks long term interoperability solutions.
- Europe is now leading the world in controller pilot data link communications (CPDLC), with 15 airlines already using the service via the first operational implementation at Maastricht Upper Area Control Centre. But that lead is likely to be short-lived, thanks to the revival of US CPDLC plans through the FAA’s budget allocation for a new Datacom system and the expected issuing of a notice of proposed rulemaking on aircraft equipage in 2022.
- A key element of both SESAR and NextGen is System Wide Information Management (SWIM), which is a focus on how the technologies and systems will enable shared awareness for operations. Some on-going initiatives such as ICOG, D-AIM, and SWIM-SUIT will enable legacy systems to operate in the SWIM environment.
- The planned technology is very similar – ADS-B, Data Link, Extended Conflict Detection. ADS-B equipment has been extensively and successfully tested in operational environments and is an example of a developed SESAR and NextGen technological component. The United States is further along on the surveillance part, known as Automatic Dependent Surveillance - Broadcast (ADS-B) Out, while Europe's SESAR is further advanced on datalink communications. Both Europe and the U.S. clearly are moving toward the same goal, although the pace and emphasis during the transition to next-generation traffic management still must be worked out.
- Both systems embrace a network-centric infrastructure with shared services and distributed data environments interacting semi-autonomously to achieve system-wide efficiencies.
- Critical to consider global interoperability and harmonisation.

9.2 Harmonized Certification

The certification of an airliner is final stage of the development process, and can also be the most complex, time consuming and expensive. The certification of a modern airliner takes about 3 000 flying hours over a period of 3-5 years involving 3 to 6 prototype of pre-production aircraft, and it is difficult to compress without significantly increasing risks that could become delays and further costs. Although there has been much progress in ground testing and simulation, it is flight testing that is the ultimate proof that satisfies certification authorities. The increasing capabilities and complexity of successive generations of airliners means that there is more hardware and software equipment and functions to test, and the progress is absorbed in performing increased testing in a comparable time span.

The enormous progress over the past in flight testing and certification is testified by the fact that most current programs reach production and service without a single fatal accident in the development process. The days when a test pilot entered a prototype aircraft not knowing what to expect are long gone, and replaced by a much more scientific, disciplined, controlled and safer development process: (i) mathematical models are developed for the aircraft performance, stability and flying characteristics as a whole and of its constituent subsystems; (ii) the models are validated by extensive tests in aerodynamic wind tunnels, engine test facilities and ground test rigs covering structures and systems; (iii) the mathematical models are implemented in flight simulators giving test pilots many hours of experience before real flight.

The main benefit of all this modelling, simulation and ground testing is that flight testing and certification are much more efficient, going through a larger number of test points in a shorter time, with almost complete safety, because: (i) the telemetry data from flight testing is compared in real time with simulation models on the ground; (ii) in the case of agreement it is possible to proceed to the next test point without delay as long as flight endurance allows; (iii) in case a discrepancy appears the testing is suspended until the cause is identified and corrected, so that the incident does not become an accident; (iv) this process allows a faster exploration of the full flight envelope and operating conditions, starting from the safer central part and then gradually extending to the boundaries.

The extensive pre-flight testing does not mean that there are no surprises in flight testing: (i) some phenomena like laminar to turbulent flow transition cannot always be predicted accurately in wind tunnel tests; (ii) similarly some engine operating characteristics cannot be fully simulated on the ground; (iii) complex systems can have many combinations of partial failure modes. Even considering only aerodynamics, CFD (computational fluid dynamics), wind tunnels and in-flight measurements can all show different results. The substantial effort in ground testing and simulation serves to reduce the risks of flight testing and allow certification with minimal upsets.

The discovery of major deficiencies in flight testing or certification triggers a long and costly process: (i) identification of the cause(s) of the deficiency; (ii) design of a solution; (iii) testing of the design; (iv) implementation in at least prototype production; (v) incorporation in the existing prototype or additional aircraft; (vi) resumption of the flight testing and certification.

This is an example of the fact that the later a deficiency is found the longer and the more expensive it will be to correct. The whole purpose of the development process is to use earlier and cheaper testing to identify and correct as many issues as possible so that less crop up at the last stage of flight testing and certification when the consequences in delays and cost will be greater.

The preceding account assumes that the certification process concerns only essential issues without duplication or unexpected requirements. That was not always the case in the past. There were instances some decades ago when different national certification required different tests for the same purpose, duplicating the effort and increasing cost with no benefit. The harmonization of certification standards avoids such costly duplications without benefit to safety or efficiency. Since FAA and EASA are the leading certification authorities the continuation of common or compatible certification standards, and the mutual acceptance of certification results, should continue as new technologies emerge and possibly new aircraft configurations as well.

Dissimilar certification rules or non-acceptance of other certification runs the risk of becoming disguised protectionism or lead to a non-level playing field. The acceptance of 'grandfather rights' allowed the second-generation Boeing B737 to keep earlier passenger evacuation rules, thus seating more passenger in a smaller cabin than the new Airbus A320 that had to meet more recent and stringent certification rules; this unfortunate episode had at least the positive consequence of the agreement between the FAA and EASA that 'grandfather rights' could not be invoked in the future. Another episode was the FAA requirement that in the event of an in-flight disintegration of an engine of the Airbus A340 there would be no possibility of severing fuel lines; this required a considerable redesign of the fuel lines in the wing of the aircraft; the EASA also raised some issues on updates to the Boeing B747, and eventually a broader based agreement was reached with FAA on certification rules, to the benefit of the worldwide aviation community.

The FAA and EASA certification rules are the 'de facto' world standard since aircraft that would not meet them could not fly in Europe and the US pre-empting much of the possible airline market. The EASA and FAA are an essential element in keeping aviation as the safest mode of transport, by making sure that all aircraft producers and their products deserve the trust of passengers. An inevitable consequence is that certification can become a hurdle to newcomers to the market that do not have either the technology demonstration or the program discipline capabilities to go through a complete certification process. The introduction of new technologies, and eventually of new aircraft configurations like flying wings or joined wings, will put new challenges on certification that must be addressed by close consultation between industry and the authorities, so that aircraft can be designed to meet all the requirements they will have to satisfy.

The harmonization of certification by EASA in Europe and FAA in the US (Key Topic 9.3) sets the standard for these processes essential for the safety of air transport.

KEY TOPIC T9.3 HARMONIZED CERTIFICATION

T9.3.1 Coordination Between EASA and FAA

The overall framework for harmonized and coordinated certification between EASA and the FAA is currently established by the agreement between the US and the European Union on cooperation in the regulation of Civil Aviation Safety. This agreement entered into force on the 1st of May 2011 and this formalises the mutual trust that was built over the years between the US and EU in the fields of airworthiness approvals of civil aeronautical products; and approval and monitoring of maintenance facilities; environmental testing and approvals of civil aeronautical products; and approval and monitoring of maintenance facilities.⁴⁴

The agreement reflects the structure of a “classical” agreement in the areas of aviation safety, a “BASA” as are called the existing Bilateral Aviation Safety Agreements between the US and some EU Member States (EU MS). As in the cases of the BASAs, the agreement is based on mutual trust of each other’s system and on the comparison of regulatory systems. Moreover, the FAA and EASA at authority level prepared the so-called 3rd level texts (**Technical Implementation Procedures**, TIP for Airworthiness and Environmental Certification and the Maintenance Annex Guidance – MAG for Maintenance) that define

how the Parties will implement and work in order to achieve the objectives set out in the Agreement and its Annexes).

The Agreement also establishes a series of committees/sub-committees ensuring its effective functioning:

- Implementation of the agreement, for handling disputes and the amendment and adoption of new annexes, will be responsibility of the Bilateral Oversight Board (BOB). The Union will be represented in the BOB by the European Commission assisted by EASA and accompanied by the Aviation Authorities as representatives of the EU MS.
- Discussions at technical level (FAA-EASA) and the development, approval and amendments of the TIP and MAG will be assured by the Certification Oversight Board (COB) and the Joint Maintenance Coordination Board (JMCB) respectively, being both boards accountable to the BOB.

The main purposes of the agreement are to automatically accept certain approvals issued within the other certification system and enable the reciprocal acceptance of findings of compliance during validation processes. Furthermore, the agreement supports the continuation of high-level regulatory cooperation and thus promotes a uniform high degree of safety in air transport. This will facilitate trade in goods and services covered by its scope and limit as much as possible, the duplication of assessments, tests and controls to significant regulatory differences.

⁴⁴ Information Note. Agreement between the United States of America and the European Union on cooperation in the regulation of civil Aviation Safety. EASA web page.

Its scope covers the airworthiness approvals and monitoring of civil aeronautical products, the environmental testing and approvals of civil aeronautical products and the approval and monitoring of maintenance facilities.

To complement this agreement, series of guidelines have been commonly developed to establish the process through which the FAA and EASA intend to promote rulemaking co-operation in the early stages of the rulemaking process. The objectives of this rulemaking cooperation arrangement⁴⁵ are to:

- Exchange regulation intentions and priorities of the participants to align as much as possible their respective rulemaking programmes.
- Identify rulemaking initiatives of common interest that through regulatory collaboration would allow the FAA and EASA to: avoid unnecessary divergence and duplication of work, maximize available resources, and further harmonisation.
- Define the corresponding working methods to be followed by the participants when executing tasks which have been considered as of common interest.

The FAA and EASA rulemaking agreement foresee 3 possible working methods, as indicated in the Figure 9.6, by which the participants will execute rulemaking tasks in the areas of common interest.

Figure 9.6 - FAA and EASA rulemaking agreement foresee 3 possible working methods

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“Rulemaking Cooperation Guidelines for the Federal Aviation Administration and the European Aviation Safety Agency”. FAA, EASA, 2013.

Finally, the agreement gives to the parties the possibility to agree on additional areas of cooperation by amendment of the agreement.

T9.3.1.1 Technical Implementation Procedures for Airworthiness and Environmental Certification (TIP)

The last revision of this document was made in September 2017.

The purpose of the TIP is to define the procedures for approving the design of civil aeronautical products and articles eligible for import into the U.S. and the EU, the process for obtaining eligibility for import, and the means for providing continued support of those civil aeronautical products and articles after import.

The TIP is based on continuous communication and mutual confidence in the FAA's and EASA's technical competence and ability to perform regulatory functions within the scope of the TIP.

The FAA and EASA mutually recognize each other's aircraft certification systems, which includes EASA recognition of FAA's designee system and FAA recognition of EASA's design and production organization system.

T9.3.2 Grandfather Rights

According to sources such as Skybrary, grandfather rights are defined as the arrangement under which later derivatives of an initial aircraft type design can be manufactured under variations to the original Type Certificate thereby avoiding the more complex procedures involved in gaining approval under a completely new Type Certificate.

The effect of this is that although the standards applied to enable the issue of as Type Certificate have always progressively increased over time, in the light of experience and general technological progress, these benefits are not reflected in the certification of 'similar' aircraft by means of variations. There is no general time limit to these grandfather rights and they can remain effective over a long period.

Grandfather rights refer to the right of a manufacturer to continue certifying successive derivatives of a mature aircraft type under the certification rules applicable when the original design was cleared, despite subsequent advances in safety regulation.

This following Figure 9.7 shows how to determine certification basis for derivative airlines types. The chosen method is a set of step-by-step guidelines for the certification of derivative types. These aim to enforce compliance with the latest regulations.

Figure 9.7 - Diagram about how to determine certification basis for derivative airliner types
Source: Boeing and the UK Civil Aviation Authority

Besides, grandfather rights are currently used in the European Union to allocate airport slots. Grand-fathered rights have also been established in the Commission Regulation 1702/2003, with the establishment of EASA. This grandfathering allows that now new type certificates for the related products need to be issued for certain type certificates dispensed prior to 28 September 2003 by Member States (JAA) in accordance with Regulation no 1702/2003.

T9.3.2.1 Historical Perspective of Grandfather's Rights

Relevant Boeing and Airbus aircraft families has made extensive use of the grandfather's rights to avoid the burden of complex and expensive certification process according to new safety requirement.

Derivatives have not posed much of a problem to the European Authorities (JAA). Its first certification was awarded to Saab's SF340, in May 1984. That aircraft, and all those which have followed it, including the ATR series, the Airbus fleet from the A320 onwards and British Aerospace's 146/RJ series, have all been original aircraft certificated to standards which have required little amendments to comply with the latest - and proposed - changes to the JARs.

The FAA, on the other hand, has had to deal with the Boeing and McDonnell Douglas (MDC) fleets, the derivatives of which include the world's best-sellers.

Without grandfather rights, the 747-8 would have not been certified as the passengers in the nose section of the main deck only have one way of exiting the plane in an emergency, whereas the new legislation required all planes to have 2 directions for all passengers to go in case of an emergency evacuation, front and backwards. European regulators insisted at that moment on Boeing to be required to undertake a full evacuation demonstration of the new 747 variant - something it avoided doing when the -400 was introduced in 1989. Although under previous 747 stretch development studies, such as the 747X of 2001, Boeing had intended to adopt an all-new certification path, but it finally pursued certification for the 747-81/8F under an amended 747-400 type certificate.

The 747-400 was itself approved as an amendment to the certification of the original 747-100 that was launched in 1966. European Joint Aviation Authorities¹⁾ insisted in the 1980s that the cockpit/upper-deck floor of the Boeing 747-400 be strengthened to contemporary standards, to protect the flight-control runs which pass through it. Although at that moment the FAA disagreed, JAA insistence translated into that European-registered 747-400s having upper-deck floors built to a higher specification than those registered in the USA and elsewhere.

The latest issue concerns the Boeing 737-X series and whether, despite being a re-winged, reengineed, re-instrumented version of the previous series, it will gain any advantage over the A320 by virtue of grandfathering anomalies. The Boeing's 737-X series (the 737-600/700/800) complied with 362 out of 377 of the latest FAR/JARs, and that the ten or so "reversions" (derivative privileges) granted complied with the ICPTF guidelines. By the end of 1995, Boeing had admitted that there were some five items yet to be clarified, but it is reluctant to list them. One of them was the issue of whether the 737-800 shall be permitted, given the limitations imposed by cabin emergency-exit regulations, to carry 179 or 189 passengers. A 737 has never been submitted to the JAA for certification - it was originally certificated by European national aviation authorities. The FAA, on the other hand, being the 737's original certificating authority, says that 189 is permissible under FAR grandfather rules.

On 2000 grandfather rights were finally killed on both sides of the Atlantic. A new US Federal Aviation Administration rule has replaced the regulation which allowed completely new aircraft models in a well-established family, like Boeing's 737 series, for example, to continue to be produced to some of the out-of-date certification standards in force when the first 737 was produced. The JAA upgrade also its previous regulation, that was a compromise solution requiring that new models in an existing family of aircraft do not have to meet the letter of the latest certification laws, provided that the new version could demonstrate "equivalent safety" by some other means. If it could not, the updated model had to satisfy the same certification standards that would apply to a completely new aircraft type.

T9.3.2.2 Future Perspective of Grandfather's Rights

Besides this overall agreement on not application of grandfather rights, there is some challenges that problem might be reactivated in the future, as could have been happened with the upcoming application of new ICAO regulation for emissions.

On 8 February 2016, the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) finalized a proposed performance standard for new aircraft that will mandate improvements in fuel efficiency and reductions in carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions. The standard, the first ever to impose binding energy efficiency and CO₂ reduction targets for the aviation sector, was hammered out at the tenth meeting of ICAO's Committee for Environmental Protection (CAEP). It will apply to all new commercial and business aircraft delivered after 1 January 2028, with a transition period for modified aircraft starting in 2023. The standards will on average require a 4% reduction in the cruise fuel consumption of new aircraft starting in 2028 compared to 2015 deliveries, with the actual reductions ranging from 0 to 11%, depending on the maximum take-off mass (MTOM) of the aircraft.

If this standard would have been deemed to be applied only to new designs certified after the expected application date (instead to all aircraft rolled out of a factory), in-service aircraft, those already flying before the date the standard takes effect, will not be affected by this new regulation. Most of the "future" airplanes that are already announced (B777X, A330neo, etc) will acquire their type certificates well before 2024 and in essence would therefore grandfather in existing production lines and possibly derivative products as well, what could prolong the current period of limited efficiency improvements by delaying the introduction of new aircraft designs by manufacturers wishing to avoid triggering the standard⁴⁶. If the grandfather clause would adopted, then a standard applied in 2020 would cover only 5 percent of the global fleet in 2030.

In the future, it is expected that these grandfather rights may reappear as modifications to the new aircraft models are extended. Therefore, the procedure to be followed will be very similar to the current one since aircraft owners will try to achieve maximum use of their investment.

The conflicting issues which have to be resolved are, on the one hand, the need for safety regulation to be able to advance, taking advantage of experience and technological improvement; and, on the other hand, the need for manufacturers to produce aircraft to approved designs which can remain basically unchanged long enough to be built, tested and put into operation, and then to achieve sufficient sales for a reasonable return on investment.

T9.3.3 Certification Challenges in China with the ARJ21 and C-919

Although China's government has had a great interest in manufacturing commercial aircraft, it has not had much success. Until recently, China's aircraft manufacturing industry's production was limited almost exclusively to serving the Chinese military. Consequently, almost all of China's commercial aircraft have been imported from foreign manufacturers. In

⁴⁶ Efficiency Trends for New Commercial Jet Aircraft, 1960 to 2008. ICCT: International council on Clean Transportation

2008, the Chinese government consolidated its efforts to develop a commercial aircraft manufacturing industry by setting up a new state-owned commercial aircraft manufacturing company, the Commercial Aircraft Company of China (COMAC), to build two domestic aircraft: a regional jet, the ARJ-21, already under development, and a narrow-bodied aircraft, the C919.

In the 1970s, China made the first of several attempts to build a commercial jet. The most successful of these was the Y-10 jet transport, an aircraft broadly similar to the Boeing 707. Although a number of test flights conducted in the early 1980s were apparently successful, the plane cost significantly more than western planes. For this reason, Chinese airlines found that it was more profitable to purchase aircraft from Boeing and Airbus. Only three Y-10 aircraft were built, and the program was discontinued due to design and cost problems.

Following the cancellation of the Y-10 program in 1983, China developed a plan with the objective of proceeding from local production and assembly of foreign designs to local development with foreign assistance. The final step will consist of achieving completely independent local development without foreign assistance by 2010.

Following these objectives, an agreement was reached with McDonnell Douglas to assemble the MD-82 narrow-body airliner in Shanghai. Between 1986 and 1994, a total of 35 MD-82 were assembled. Then, the two partners planned to assemble 40 MD-90s, an upgraded derivative of the MD-80 series, but Boeing stopped producing the aircraft following its merger with McDonnell Douglas, and the program was suspended.

After the termination of the MD-80/90 attempt, in 1997, China persuaded a consortium that includes Airbus and Singapore Technologies to join AVIC in the development of a 100-seat regional jet, the AE-100. This program ended in 1999, when Airbus concluded that the program no longer fit into its strategic plan.

Subsequently, China focused on smaller regional jets and a consortium between several companies was formed in 2000 in order to develop and produce a regional jet, designed for flights of less than three hours and seating 70 to 105 passengers, known as the ARJ21.

In 2002, another Chinese aircraft manufacturer, the Harbin Aircraft Industries Group, formed a joint venture with Brazil's Embraer to assemble Embraer's ERJ-145 family of 30-to 50-seat regional jets in Harbin. However, the facility delivered only 41 ERJ-145 aircraft over seven years before production ended in 2011.

More recently, the Chinese industry appears to have shifted its focus to larger aircraft in the 130-to 170-seat class. In 2008, a joint venture between Airbus and a Chinese consortium to perform final assembly of the Airbus A320.

Finally, China's indigenous commercial jet project known as the C919 was launched in 2008.

In the following image (Figure 9.8), it can be seen a timeline of China attempts to manufacture commercial aircraft:

Figure 9.8 - China attempts to manufacture commercial aircraft

However, the China indigenous aircraft, the ARJ21 and the C919 have experienced delays due to several problems during tests flights. A key problem of the delays has been a lack of systems integration skills. As several parts of the aircraft are produced by different manufacturers, the finished products are having compatibility issues during final assembly. Quality has also been a problem. Certain parts of the aircraft have failed to meet quality requirements.

In addition, one of the main problems in the construction of China indigenous aircraft is that there is not intellectual property protection, which implies that international companies often agree to transfer only dated technology. This issue has been a great problem for the ARJ21 and it may be a problem too for the C919.

T9.3.3.1 ARJ21

The ARJ21 is a twin-engine regional jet, manufactured by the Chinese aerospace company COMAC.

This project started in 2002, and it has experienced significant delays compared to the initial plan. The first commercial flight took place in June 2016, six years later than planned, and only two ARJ21 aircraft had been delivered as of February 2017 (both to Chengdu Airlines, a company owned by COMAC).

Depending on the version, the ARJ21 has a maximum seating capacity of 105 and a maximum range of 3,700 km, which makes it a direct competitor to Embraer E175 and E190, as well as to Bombardier CRJ900 and CRJ1000.

As it was said before, the ARJ21 has had several delays. In 2010, an ARJ21 wing failed to reach the predicted load rating during static testing. This wing's failure led the Civil Aviation Administration of China (CAAC) to limit the aircraft flight envelope during its flight test program. In addition, other problems arose during the flight testing program: two components of the testing program had not been completed, icing tests had been delayed and stall speed tests had not begun yet. These problems lead to delays in obtaining type certification. Wing cracks and avionics were other problems that contributed to the delays.

Obtaining a FAA type certification is a precondition for the ARJ21 to enter the global aviation market. Since 2003, the aviation authorities of China and USA have been negotiating the ARJ21 application for FAA type without success.

However, the ARJ21 achieved the type certification from the Civil Aviation Administration of China (CAAC) in 2014, which allows the aircraft to carry out regional flights. On 29 November 2015, COMAC delivered the first ARJ21 to Chengdu Airlines and the first commercial flight took place in the Chengdu Shuangliu Airport on June 28 2016.

T9.3.3.2 C919

The COMAC C919 is a narrow-body twinjet airliner developed by Chinese aerospace manufacturer COMAC. The programme was launched in 2008 and production and its first flight took place on 5 May 2017. The C919 can carry 156 to 168 passengers with a range of 3000 nautical miles. It is intended to compete primarily with the Boeing 737 and Airbus A320neo and it is planned to enter commercial service in 2021 with China Eastern airlines.

On the 24th November 2011, the preliminary design phase for the C919 ended and the assembly of the first C919 prototype began on December 2011. The flight testbed was expected to complete final assembly in 2014 and perform its first flight in 2015. However, there were several delays due to technical difficulties and supply issues. Finally, the first flight took place in 2017 and the first 150-seat C919 is scheduled to be delivered in 2021.

The C919 has not obtained yet a type certification from CAAC, which will take about three to four years. In April 2017, European Aviation Safety Association (EASA) agreed to help validate Chinese aviation authorities' certifying process of the C919's airworthiness. An EASA endorsement of the C919's airworthiness would increase its export prospects, especially in Asia and the Middle East. After EASA certification, the C919 could hope to win approval from the FAA sometime in 2020.

T9.3.3.3 C929

In 2016, COMAC and United Aircraft Corporation of Russia (UAC) signed an agreement to co-develop a 250-seat, 290-ton, 7,450-mile-range plane tentatively designated the C929. Its first flight is targeted for 2022, and it will potentially enter into service by 2025. The C929's construction will use large percentages of composite and titanium parts in order to reduce its weight, thus boosting payload, range, and fuel efficiency to compete with the Boeing 787 and Airbus A350. Like the C919, the C929 will likely use foreign parts, especially in the engines.

T9.3.4 Certification of Novel Aircraft Configurations

The configuration of civil aircraft has evolved little since the 1920s. Almost without exception, passengers have been transported in a tubular fuselage, with the empennage at the rear and the engines mounted either under the wings, or at the rear. Although major advances in aerodynamics and flight control systems have contributed greatly to improve the performance of the classic configuration, the advent of new design materials and design processes, along with a far better understanding of the aerodynamic and structural interactions that occur in different phases of flight, are driving some radical ideas for the future.

Regarding aircraft configurations, several options are being considered for the future:

- Development of integrated and interdisciplinary functional aircraft design methods, including systems, software and integration aspects considered from the conceptual design phase
- Integrated blended wing body and tail-mounted open rotor concepts
- Aircraft configurations regarding type of energy (e.g. hydrogen, electrical engine...)

The following image (Figure 9.9) shows some different types of possible aircraft configurations based on the level of investment required (low, medium and high), as a function of time (2015, 2025 and 2050):

Figure 9.9 Revolutionary aircraft configurations

Source 16: From Air Transport System 2050 Vision to Planning for Research and Innovation, EREA

Then, they are described some of the revolutionary aircraft configuration that could be expected for the future:

- Blended wing body:** today's classical aircraft configurations features separate structures for providing lift (wings) and carrying the payload (fuselage). This results in a heavier structure, additional wetted surface and associated viscous drag. The flying wing configurations is recognised as the most efficient aerodynamic solution, but presents challenges in many other areas, such as its great structural complexity, that could be mitigated with the development of advanced composite materials and production processes.

- Prandtl joined-wing plane concept:** for a given wing span and lift, the Prandtl-type biplane, with wings connected at the tip, could provide a theoretical induced drag during low-speed phases such as take-off, climb, descend and landing. In addition, this radical change in configuration could provide a potential fuel burn reduction of 10%.

- Tilt-rotor aircraft:** Tilt-rotors combine to some extent the hover advantages of helicopters with the higher-speeds of turboprop aircraft, overcoming the problem of helicopter speed being limited by the loss of main rotor efficiency at higher forward speeds. The next generation of tilt-rotors will feature a partially tilted wing to improve rotor efficiency at hover.

- Personal air transport:** for personal air transport, short-range small aircraft that provide low emissions and easy handling could be used. Such aircraft would be operating along with others at lower altitudes and speeds with features as reduced weight, reduced fuel consumption, simpler maintenance or increased reliability. However, this concept will require the resolution of a number of major technological issues, including environmental control, ice protection systems and engine technology.

Supersonic business transport: using supersonic business transport to link growing business metropolises in North America as well as in Europe and Asia would provide a potential reduction in flight time, being capable of travelling long distances in only a few hours. However, significant technological challenges remain, including:

- Development of high temperature carbon fibre materials;
- Sonic boom overpressure on the ground;
- Airport noise;
- Easy to handle, reliable aircraft;
- Low-emission, high-speed propulsion.

The previous aircraft configurations considered are only a few examples of the radical changes that are currently being studied. However, these revolutionary configurations could present challenges in the certification process as they present a great change compared to current configurations.

Aircraft certification is the process whereby an applicant requests an approval from an aviation regulatory authority, such as the FAA or the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), for manufacturing a new aircraft model or making changes to an existing aircraft. Aircraft certification processes use approved standards, guidance, tests, methods, procedures as well as data submittals and plan documentation to achieve regulatory approval for aircraft type certification.

In order to certify the revolutionary aircraft configurations that are expected in the future, it will be necessary to improve current certification methods or to develop new ones in order to assure that these aircraft are safe and efficient. The certification methods that will be required are based in three pillars:

1. One pillar represents computational capabilities, which consist of high-speed super computers that can model the physics of air flowing over an object, be it a wing, a rudder or a full airplane. Improved computational tools would allow to reduce costs, time, risk and it would provide a great increase in aircraft design efficiency and quality. In addition, unconventional configuration concepts could be explored more easily and with greater confidence during early design stages. Therefore, to certify new aircraft configurations through computational methods, it will be necessary to develop faster and more accuracy algorithms.

One of the main goals, which is expected to be achieved by improving computational tools, will be to certify new technology or vehicle concept with more limited use of ground or flight testing for validation. This will require the ability of the computational tools to predict absolute performance within known uncertainty bounds over the entire operating conditions.

2. A second pillar represents the experimental methods. In this case, scientists usually put a scale model of an object or part of an object (be it a wing, a rudder or an airplane) in

a wind tunnel to take measurements of air flowing over the object. These measurements help improve the computer model, and the computer model helps inform about improvements to the airplane design, which can then be tested again in the wind tunnel. As the computational tools become increasingly reliable in predicting system performance, the role of wind tunnels should evolve towards physics-based testing for increased understanding of various flow phenomena and for developing extremely high-fidelity data for physical model development and code validation.

Therefore, wind tunnels will continue to play a significant role aircraft certification and testing, which will provide a significant reduction in costs and flight testing.

3. Finally, the third pillar is the flight testing of the design developed. The data recorded in the flight test can be used to validate and improve the computational and experimental methods used to develop the design in the first place.

In the future, one of the main objectives will be to reduce the time required in this phase, since flight testing is the most expensive process and detecting errors in this phase could delay the whole certification process.

KEY TOPIC T9.4 CERTIFICATION PROCEDURES

The certification of an airliner is final stage of the development process, and can also be the most complex, time consuming and expensive.

The Type Certification (TC), i.e. the design approval for the model, should be complemented by the approvals by the Authority of the Design Organisation and of the Production Organisation (organisation demonstrates competence and compliance with regulatory requirements). The Authority empowered to approve products and organizations is an agency of an ICAO member state and is supposed to compile the respective requirements in accordance with Annex 8 to the ICAO Convention "Airworthiness of Aircraft" Part II Chapter 1 "Type Certification". However, this is just the minimum requirements, so different countries might choose a range of levels of severity of the conditions.

To be granted the TC, the designer is asked to demonstrate the compliance to the Authority set of requirements, including analyses (aerodynamic, airframe loading, systems safety), structural tests, other ground tests (functional, fatigue, reliability), flight tests (performance, handling, flutter etc.). Applying for a TC is the start of the certification process and the timing is important because this is where the clock starts ticking. Part 23 airplanes generally have three years from the date of application to be certified; Part 25 airplanes have five years. The certification basis is structured in Mandatory Requirements, the applicable certification code in place at time of TC application, e.g. CS-25 at Change 18. When a company applies for a type certificate, the rules that are in force at the time of application are the rules with which the applicant must comply. If, for example, the Authority changed the certification rules after someone applied for certification, requiring that icing tests be done with 100-micron freezing drizzle instead of the current 40-micron droplet size, the applicant would not have to meet that new regulation. This is where a protracted certification program can run into problems, because if there are delays that push the program beyond the three- or five-year limit, then

the applicant has to apply for an extension and might have to comply with rules that took effect after the initial application. This is the case of the Japanese MRJ, still struggling after more than 10 years to complete the certification.

The flight testing for certification of a modern airliner takes about 3 000 flying hours over a period of 3 to 5 years, involving 3 to 6 prototypes. Before the OEM flies a prototype of the design, the Authority will need to issue an experimental type certificate. Authority personnel will conduct a safety review and check that the airplane conforms to its design. A plan for test flying will cover all requirements. And before Authority test pilots fly in the airplane it must have flown through its full flight envelope. Flight testing is a challenging part of the certification program and it is difficult to compress without significantly increasing risks that could become delays and further costs. Although there has been much progress in ground testing and simulation, it is flight testing that is the ultimate proof that satisfies certification authorities. The increasing capabilities and complexity of successive generations of airliners means that there is more hardware and software equipment and functions to test, and the progress is absorbed in performing increased testing in a comparable time span.

Besides the certification programme for the aircraft, separate certification requirements are specified for engines as well as for propellers and for Auxiliary Power Units (APUs). The time for the development and TC of a new engine is now around 5-6 years and about 10-15 test prototypes are employed (and sometimes destroyed) in ground tests (including subassemblies tests), altitude bench tests and flight tests on the airplane equipped.

The preceding account assumes that the certification process concerns only essential issues without duplication or unexpected requirements from different certification responsible agencies. Before the 90s the standard recognized level worldwide was that of FARs, the regulations issued by US' FAA. The harmonization somehow existed, the first European unified JARs (e.g. JAR-25 'Large Airplanes') were nothing else than the declared transcription of the equivalent FARs. There are, however, a number of areas in which variations and additions to FAR Part 25 have been considered necessary in order to reach agreement to a code acceptable to JAA participating countries, and these differences (Complementary Technical Conditions) were indicated in the specifications. After the creation of EASA in 2003, the requirements began to diverge, as can be observed in an ever growing list of Significant Standard Differences (SSD) between U.S. Code of Federal Regulations (CFR), Part 25 and Joint Aviation Regulation (JAR), Part 25, or European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) Certification Specifications (CS) 25 published by FAA (see www.faa.gov/aircraft/air_cert/design_approvals/transport/transport_intl/sd_list/ssd_nonssd_list/).

Similar negative effects would produce a proposal to grandfather in a large number of current aircraft designs in terms of emissions. If such a grandfathering clause is adopted, then any standard applicable beginning in 2020 would cover only 5% of the global fleet in 2030.

The "grandfathering right" is an Anglo-Saxon general legal principle, still controversially applied in aviation, besides in the certification practices, also in allocating airport slots. Another example of "grandfathering", this time perfectly justified, was introduced when EASA

was established through Commission Regulation (EC) No 1702/2003 of 24 September 2003. It contains a grand-fathering mechanism for certain type certificates issued prior to 28 September 2003 by Member States. These type certificates are deemed to have been issued in accordance with Regulation no 1702/2003 and, as a consequence, EASA does not need to issue new type certificates for the related products. However, since 28 September 2003, all changes to these type certificates or associated datasheet must be approved by EASA.

EASA delivers the primary certification for European aircraft models which are also being validated in parallel by foreign authorities for operation in their airspaces, e.g. the FAA for the US or TCCA for Canada. Conversely, EASA will validate the FAA certification of US aircraft models (or TCCA certification of Canadian models) according to applicable Bilateral Aviation Safety Agreements between the EU and USA, respectively Canada. As an example, the existing "Agreement Between the United States Of America And The European Community On Cooperation In The Regulation Of Civil Aviation Safety" (EU_USA_BASA/en 1 - Revision 3_ March 2016) is continuously extended and improved to cover more situations and to provide regulatory cooperation and transparency. The parties established a Bilateral Oversight Board which is responsible for ensuring the effective functioning of the Agreement. Based on this, a more detailed "Technical Implementation Procedures for Airworthiness and Environmental Certification" (known as TIP) was signed between FAA and EASA, currently at Revision 6 from September 22, 2017. As part of the continued maintenance of confidence in each other's system, the FAA and EASA develop procedures to share and exchange information regarding airworthiness and environmental standards, certification systems, etc. The FAA and EASA recognise that certain approvals can benefit from mutual acceptance. There are specific approvals that will be accepted by the Validating Authority without issuance of its own approval, and therefore no application for validation is required. APPENDIX D of TIP lists 15 FAA and EASA mutually recognized airborne systems standards considered to be equivalent for the purpose of issuing approvals under TIP. This is a good start but far too modest. The reverse, the non-accepted differences, lead to extra efforts and spending in the certification process an avoidable waste.

A harmonisation programme, initialised years ago, should be accelerated to completely eliminate the differences, moving things toward the so-called WORLDWIDE harmonization.

A good step was achieved on September 16, 2015, when the leadership of the certification services/departments of the Agência Nacional de Aviação Civil (ANAC) of Brasil, European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), and Transport Canada Civil Aviation (TCCA) signed a charter establishing the CERTIFICATION MANAGEMENT TEAM (CMT). The CMT oversees and manages collaboration efforts to permit the development and implementation of regulatory and policy solutions common to certification issues and support greater harmonization. In May 2016, the CMT signed its Collaboration Strategy (see https://www.faa.gov/about/office_org/headquarters_offices/avs/offices/air/transformation/certification_strategy/media/cmt_strategy.pdf).

Also the existing co-operation structure of 18 national agencies in the general field of safety, the Safety Management International Collaboration Group (SM ICG) might be extended as scope to cover Certification as well. SM ICG was founded by FAA, EASA and TCCA and is a joint cooperation between many regulatory authorities for the purpose of promoting a common

understanding of Safety Management Systems /State Safety Program principles and requirements, facilitating their implementation across the international aviation community. (The current core membership of the SM ICG includes the Aviation Safety and Security Agency (AESA) of Spain, the National Civil Aviation Agency (ANAC) of Brazil, the Civil Aviation Authority of the Netherlands (CAA NL), the Civil Aviation Authority of New Zealand (CAA NZ), the Civil Aviation Authority of Singapore (CAAS), Civil Aviation Department of Hong Kong (CAD HK), the Civil Aviation Safety Authority (CASA) of Australia, the Direction Générale de l'Aviation Civile (DGAC) in France, the Ente Nazionale per l'Aviazione Civile (ENAC) in Italy, the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), the Federal Office of Civil Aviation (FOCA) of Switzerland, the Finnish Transport Safety Agency (Trafi), the Irish Aviation Authority (IAA), Japan Civil Aviation Bureau (JCAB), the United States Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) Aviation Safety Organization, Transport Canada Civil Aviation (TCCA), United Arab Emirates General Civil Aviation Authority (UAE GCAA), and the Civil Aviation Authority of United Kingdom (UK CAA). Additionally, the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) is an observer to this group.

9.3 Aviation Effects on the Environment

The effects of aviation on the environment can be considered at two levels: (i) locally as the emission and noise near airports; (ii) globally as in-flight emissions worldwide. The aims of reduction of environmental impact can be either compatible or contrasting at the (i) local or (ii) global level. For example, the reduction of fuel consumption is beneficial in all cases because it reduces emissions. The design for high efficiency and low fuel consumption is different at low speeds (glider like configuration) and high speeds (swept wings) and thus lowering local emissions is a trade-off with lowering global emissions. Concerning the type of emissions, CO₂, NO_x and particles that all result from the combustion process again compromises may be necessary among the amount of each that is produced.

The noise regulations of ICAO have long been the standard, although local airports can apply stricter standards that aircraft manufacturers cannot afford to ignore; in principle a single noise standard that could be adhered to worldwide would be ideal. Concerning emissions, like other aspects of global warming and climate change, progress requires considerable international negotiation, with the European Union often the most active promoter. The emerging of the ICAO scheme on emissions is even more desirable than on noise because aircraft emissions are a global issue that cannot be solved at local level like noise.

The environmental effects of aviation could be greater in regions of higher traffic density like Europe and the US; rightly so these are the regions of the world that apply stricter environmental standards, applying to new aircraft, and requiring older non-compliant aircraft either to be modified or retired from service. In the case when the modification of older aircraft for compliance with new environmental standards is not economical, many of them are sold to operate in other regions of the world. Thus, some less developed regions, with lower air traffic densities, operated older aircraft with larger environmental impact, that may or may not be felt locally, but certainly contributes to global pollution. These older aircraft can also pose some safety issues.

KEY TOPIC T9.5 AVIATION EFFECTS ON THE ENVIRONMENT

Contaminants

Contaminants from Aircraft Engine Emissions

- Commercial air travel is expected to double in the next 20 years, which will in turn increase the number of contaminants emitted to the atmosphere. The following contaminants are emitted during the different phases of operation:
- NITROGEN OXIDES (NO_x) – which includes nitrogen oxide (NO) and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂);
- CARBON MONOXIDE (CO)
- UNBURNED HYDROCARBONS – which have almost been completely eliminated from the exhaust stream due to newer engine technologies
- SULPHUR OXIDES
- PARTICULATE MATTER (PM) – which leaves the exhaust as carbon black soot
- VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS (VOCS) – such as benzene and acrolein
- OZONE (O₃)– which is formed from the nitrogen oxides and volatile organic compounds emitted
- SEMI-VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS (SVOCS)
- METALS
- NOISE – this contaminant is discussed in the Aircraft Noise section of the ICAO site
- ODOUR

Most of the focus of international efforts have been on the reduction of NO_x so far (ICAO has an engine certification standard for NO_x which is contained in Annex 16 — *Environmental Protection, Volume II — Aircraft Engine Emissions* to the Convention on International Civil Aviation). Further assessment of the impact of some of these contaminants (for example, particulate matter and metals) needs to be conducted in order to assess the risk to human health and to further the goal of reducing emissions.

Besides NO_x, ICAO has established limits for emissions of CO and unburned hydrocarbons in Annex 16, Volume II. This volume also contains provisions regarding smoke and vented fuel.

Auxiliary power units are also sources of contaminants. However, they are not certified for emissions and it is difficult to estimate emissions from these sources as manufacturers consider the emission rate information proprietary.

Aircraft engine emissions and auxiliary power units are the only sources under the remit of ICAO.

Contaminants from Airports and Associated Sources

Airports also release contaminants from activities such as:

- Ground service equipment;
- Motor vehicles (parking, road traffic);
- Construction;

- Boilers;
- Generators;
- Airport fire training facility;
- Food preparation;
- Engine testing;
- Electricity;
- De-icing;
- Fuel storage facilities.

The contaminants listed above can also be found emitting from airport sources. The VOCs emitted may vary for those emitted by aircraft depending on the fuels used in ground service and road traffic vehicles, and fire training exercises.

Health Effects

Exposure to the contaminants listed above can result in serious health effects. The Table 9.1 presented below lists some of these effects. Local and regional air quality officials are responsible for creating standards to protect human health from the adverse effects of these contaminants.

Table 9.1A – Representative health effects of air pollutants

<i>Pollutant</i>	<i>Representative Health Effects</i>
Ozone	Lung function impairment, effects on exercise performance, increased airway responsiveness, increased susceptibility to respiratory infection, increased hospital admissions and emergency room visits, and pulmonary inflammation, lung structure damage.
Carbon Monoxide	Cardiovascular effects, especially in those persons with heart conditions (e.g., decreased time to onset of exercise-induced angina).
Nitrogen Oxides Particulate Matter	Lung irritation and lower resistance to respiratory infections Premature mortality, aggravation of respiratory and cardiovascular disease, changes in lung function and increased respiratory symptoms, changes to lung tissues and structure, and altered respiratory defense mechanisms.
Volatile Organic Compounds	Eye and respiratory tract irritation, headaches, dizziness, visual disorders, and memory impairment.

Table 9.1B – Representative environmental effects of air pollutants

<i>Pollutant</i>	<i>Representative Environmental Effects</i>
Ozone	Crop damage, damage to trees and decreased resistance to disease for both crops and other plants.
Carbon Monoxide Nitrogen Oxides	Similar health effects on animals as on humans. Acid rain, visibility degradation, particle formation, contribution towards ozone formation.
Particulate Matter	Visibility degradation and monument and building soiling, safety effects for aircraft from reduced visibility.
Volatile Organic Compounds	Contribution towards ozone formation, odors and some direct effect on buildings and plants.

Table 9.1 -Representative health effects of air pollutants
Source: Evaluation of Air Pollutant Emissions from Subsonic Commercial Jet Aircraft, EPA

The following diagram (Figure 9.10) illustrates the percentage of deposition of particulate matter of a specified particle diameter that will reach different segments of the respiratory system.

Figure 9.10 – Polluting particles matter

Source: ICAO Information Paper CAEP-SG/ 20082-IP/05

Environmental Effects

Aircraft and airport emissions can also have serious effects on the environment. These contaminants can affect crop productivity and ecosystem response. In particular, NO_x in the troposphere can contribute to ground-level ozone, excess nitrogen loads to sensitive water bodies, and acidification of sensitive ecosystems according to the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency.

Particulate matter contributes to visibility and soiling issues. They play a key role in creating the hazy smog often found surrounding cities on sunny, warm, dry days.

VOCs also contribute to ozone formation and damage plants, crops, buildings and materials when released at high levels.

ICAO Initiatives to Improve Local Air Quality

One of the initiatives that ICAO has undertaken to improve air quality is the creation (and continued updating) of the document Airport Air Quality Guidance Manual. The manual provides guidance to assist with the assessment of airport emission sources, emission inventories and emissions allocation. The first step to addressing local air quality is to obtain an accurate estimate of the types and amounts of contaminants being introduced to the airshed. Then efforts to reduce these emissions can be pursued.

ICAO is also promoting numerous mitigation measures to reduce local air quality emissions. These mitigation measures include: technology and standards; operational measures; market based measures; and alternative fuels.

Aviation Emissions

Aviation emissions in context

In 2012, aviation represented 13% of all EU transport CO₂ emissions, and 3% of the total EU CO₂ emissions. It was also estimated that European aviation represented 22% of global aviation's CO₂ emissions. Similarly, aviation now comprises 14% of all EU transport NO_x emissions, and 7% of the total EU NO_x emissions. In absolute terms, NO_x emissions from aviation have doubled since 1990, and their relative share has quadrupled (Table 9.2), as other economic sectors have achieved significant reductions (Figure 9.11):

	2005	2014 (% change vs. 2005)	Base forecast 2035 Advanced – Low Technology (% change vs. 2005)
Average fuel burn (kg) per passenger kilometre	0.0388	0.0314 (-19%)	0.0209 – 0.0222 (-46%) (-43%)
CO ₂ (Mt)	144	151 (+5%)	207 – 219 (+44%) (+53%)
NO _x (1,000 t)	650	732 (+13%)	920 – 1049 (+42%) (+61%)
NO _x below 3,000 feet (1,000 t)	53.3	58.8 (+10%)	73.3 – 83.1 (+37%) (+56%)
HC (1,000 t)	20.8	17.0 (-18%)	22.9 (+10%)
HC below 3,000 feet (1,000 t)	7.8	6.4 (-18%)	11.0 (+40%)
CO (1,000 t)	143	133 (-7%)	206 (+44%)
CO below 3,000 feet (1,000 t)	52.4	48.2 (-8%)	85.5 (+63%)
volatile PM (1,000 t)	4.18	4.47 (+7%)	6.93 (+66%)
volatile PM below 3,000 feet (1,000 t)	0.27	0.27 (-1%)	0.41 (+50%)
non-volatile PM (1,000 t)	2.67	2.38 (-11%)	3.16 (+18%)
non-volatile PM below 3,000 feet (1,000 t)	0.15	0.13 (-14%)	0.17 (+11%)

Table 9.2 - Summary of emission indicators based on IMPACT data

Figure 9.11 - Emissions by source

Source: ICAO

Emissions are expected to increase further

The main aircraft engine emissions are considered here in terms of either full-flight (gate-to-gate), or a landing-take-off cycle below 3,000 feet for local air quality purposes.

Figure 9.12 - Emissions from a typical two-engine jet aircraft during 1-hour flight with 150 passengers

Source: FOCA

Aircraft CO₂ emissions (Figure 9.12) increased from 88 to 156 million tonnes (+77%) between 1990 and 2005 according to the data reported by EU28 and EFTA Member States to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). According to data from the IMPACT emissions model, CO₂ emissions increased by 5% between 2005 and 2014. The increase in emissions is however less than the increase in passenger kilometres flown over the same period (2005 to 2014). This was due to an improvement in fuel efficiency driven by the introduction of new aircraft, removal of older aircraft, and improvements in operational practice. The average fuel burn per passenger kilometre flown for passenger aircraft, excluding business aviation, went down by 19% over this same period. However, projections indicate that future technology improvements are unlikely to balance the effect of future traffic growth.

Under the base traffic forecast and advanced technology improvement rate, CO₂ emissions increases by 44% from 144 Mt in 2005 to 207 Mt in 2035.

NO_x emissions have also increased significantly: +85% (316 to 585 thousand tonnes) between 1990 and 2005 according to the Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution (CLRTAP) data from the UN Economic Commission for Europe, and +13% between 2005 and 2014 according to IMPACT data. Under the base air traffic forecast and assuming an advanced NO_x technology improvement rate, emissions would reach around 920 thousand tonnes in 2035 (+42% compared to 2005).

Emissions of HC, CO and non-volatile PM have decreased between 2005 and 2014, while full flight emissions of volatile PM have increased by 7%. However, the total emissions of each of these pollutants are forecast to increase over the next twenty years.

Emissions Monitoring Plan

An Emissions Monitoring Plan (Figure 9.13) is a collaborative tool between the State and the aeroplane operator that identifies the most appropriate means and methods for CO₂ emissions monitoring on an operator-specific basis and facilitates the reporting of required information to the State. The State and aeroplane operator should maintain clear and open communication during the development of the plan. Working collaboratively during CORSIA preparation and implementation reduces potential errors and increases effectivity.

Figure 9.13 - Emissions monitoring

Figure 9.14 – Implementation of emissions monitoring

Emissions Monitoring Options

Draft CORSIA SARPs request (Figure 9.14) an aeroplane operator to monitor and record its fuel use from international flights to determine its annual CO₂ emissions, in accordance with an eligible monitoring (Figure 9.15) method approved by the State to which it is attributed.

To simplify the estimation and reporting of CO₂ emissions from international flights for operators with low level of activity in fulfilling their monitoring and reporting requirements, ICAO has developed the CORSIA CO₂ Estimation and Reporting Tool (CERT).

CERT also supports all aeroplane operators in determining if their CO₂ emissions are under the threshold to be exempt from the CORSIA reporting requirements (= 10 000 tonnes of CO₂ annually).

Aeroplane operators who emit = 500 000 tonnes of CO₂ annually in 2019 and 2020 from international flights, are not eligible to use CERT to monitor and report emissions and must choose one of the five eligible methods for Fuel Use Monitoring (the five methods are equivalent and there is no hierarchy for selecting a method).

However, all aeroplane operators are able to use CERT to fill in any CO₂ emissions data gaps, regardless of their emissions levels.

Emissions can be taxed (Table 9.3), depending on airport (Table 9.4) and are generally higher for older aircraft (Figure 9.16).

Figure 9.15 – Emission Monitoring Methods

Emissions Costs

Aircraft Type	Cost per LTO (Euros/LTO)	Aircraft Type	Cost per LTO (Euros/LTO)
B737	296	DH8	225
B757/767	583	ATR72	108
B787	872	ERJ-190	177
A320	254	MD-90	315
A321	375	MD-82/83	311
A330	756	Business jets	167

Table 9.3 Average emission cost for commonly used aircraft types at Taipei Songshan Airport

Metropolitan Area	NO _x %	VOC%	PM _{2.5} %
Washington, DC	1.22	0.57	0.21
Philadelphia	0.64	0.35	0.20
New York	1.40	0.42	0.41
Denver	1.42	0.54	0.31
San Francisco	1.57	0.63	0.29
Dallas	1.76	0.58	0.23
Minneapolis	1.07	0.59	0.39
Chicago	1.27	0.49	0.36

Table 9.4 Aircraft Emissions Contribution to Metropolitan Area Emissions Inventories

Figure 9.16 - Average age of the global operating aircraft fleet from 2018 to 2028, by region or country (in years)

Exhaust Emissions

For almost all types of emissions, narrow body aircraft emit less greenhouse gasses per seat. Variations between single aisle (narrow body) and twin aisle (wide body) aircraft as well as between different airlines can be seen depending on the type of emission. Since the various airlines used many of the same aircraft types, variations within each emissions species are similar. Carbon Dioxide emissions followed the trend of fewer emissions from narrow bodies across all air fleets examined. The highest emitter of CO₂ was American wide bodies, 28.5534 kg of CO₂ per seat. The lowest emitter was US Airways narrow bodies at 18.5989 kg per seat (Figures 9.16 – 9.22)

Figure 9.17 - Average CO2 Emissions per Seat for Narrow and Wide Body Aircraft for Each Airline

Figure 9.18 - Sustainable Aviation Carbon Roadmap (Source: Sustainable Aviation CO2 Roadmap)

Figure 9.19 - Average HC Emissions per Seat for Narrow and Wide Body Aircraft for Each Airline

Figure 9.20 - Average CO Emissions for Narrow and Wide Body Aircraft for Each Airline

Figure 9.21 - Average NOx Emissions per Seat for Narrow and Wide Body Aircraft for Each Airline

Figure 9.22 - Average SO2 Emissions per Seat for Narrow and Wide Body Aircraft for Each Airline

Fuel

The most basic of the results was which type of aircraft burned more fuel in an hour of operation. In overall fuel consumption for each airline, wide body aircraft burned more gallons per hour for all airlines (Figure 9.23).

Figure 9.23 - Gallons of Fuel per Hour for Each Airline Broken Down by Narrow and Wide Body Aircraft

Fuel Efficiency

Fuel efficiency of aviation has developed continually since the 1960s. Studies undertaken by the International Council on Clean Transportation (ICCT)⁶ found that the gains were particularly large in the 60s and 70s, and though efficiency gains have slowed since 1990, they are estimated to be less than 50% of 1960 levels. A further study has been made by the International Coordinating Council of Aerospace Industries Associations (ICCAIA) using a metric of fuel burn per person per 100km. This interpretation suggests that fuel efficiency gains have continued since 2000, perhaps driven by a greater focus on improving load factors, which would not be accounted for in the ICCT model (Figure 9.24 – 9.26).

Figure 9.24 - Fuel Efficiency and Forecast v Today (Source: ICAO and ICCAIA)

Figure 9.25 - UK Fleet, Average Age (Source: EMRC/AEA (for DfT))

Figure 9.26 - Europe to North America Proportion of Flights in 2015 by Technology Age (Source: Capstats.com)

Future Regulations

The FAA is working through ICAO to evaluate policy options to limit or reduce greenhouse gas emissions from international aviation. ICAO has developed a range of standards, policies and guidance material for the application of integrated measures to address aircraft noise and engine emissions. Efforts include progress on new aircraft technology advancement, operational improvements and development and deployment of alternative fuels, as well as a commitment to develop a global market-based measure for international aviation and appropriate airport and land-use planning. Through the ICAO's CAEP, FAA is supporting development of an aircraft CO₂ emission standard. The standard is expected to reduce aircraft CO₂ emissions by integrating fuel-efficient technologies into aircraft design and development. It has been developed such that effective improvements observed through the CO₂ standard will correlate with reductions of CO₂ emissions by aircraft during day-to-day operations. CAEP is developing an aircraft engine PM certification standard as well. In October 2013, the 38th ICAO Assembly adopted a comprehensive climate change resolution that includes a commitment to develop a global market-based measure to address GHG emissions from international aviation. The U.S. is committed to pursuing development of a global market-based measure (MBM) proposal. It has to be considered as gap filler in the basket of measures that includes technology, operations and alternative fuels. These efforts contribute to achieving ICAO's aspirational goal of carbon neutral growth by 2020 using a 2005 baseline. The U.S. is engaged both in supporting policy and technical work contributing to the proposal for a global MBM. Under this multidimensional regulatory and voluntary structure, aviation has made significant environmental progress. Given the complexity of the industry and the need for different strategies and technological approaches for different types of vehicles and equipment, a coordinated effort will continue between the aviation industry and the many regulatory agencies that share environmental responsibilities.

Noise

Noise development to the present day: down by 80%. The most effective way of preventing noise is to invest in new aircraft technologies and to continually modernize existing aircraft. Major advances have been made in this area over the past few decades, with latest-generation aircraft 25 decibels, or around 80 per cent, quieter than 60 years ago (Figures 9.27 – 9.28).

Figure 9.27 - Development of aircraft noise emissions

Figure 9.28 - Tightening of international noise levels

Many aircraft not only meet these limits but fall significantly below them (Figure 9.29). An Airbus A319-100, a Chapter 3 aircraft, is up to 19.4 decibels quieter than the limit for its Chapter. And some aircraft models fall well below the noise levels for Chapter 4. These include the Boeing 747-8, which is 15.6 decibels below the level, and the Airbus A380, which is 16.7 decibels below.

Figure 9.29 - Aircraft fleet of the BDL airlines

Noise Reduction at Source

The most important method of noise reduction is the replacement of old, and therefore loud, aircraft with newer, quieter ones. An additional option is the upgrading of existing aircraft (Figure 9.30).

Figure 9.30 - Boeing 737 series: development of noise emissions
Source: Harris Miller & Hanson Inc.

Continued efforts may stabilize noise exposure by 2035 but it will continue to be a key challenge

Aircraft noise exposure is typically assessed by looking at the area of noise contours around airports, as well as the number of people within these contours. A noise contour represents the area around an airport in which noise levels exceed a given decibel (dB) threshold (Figure 9.31). The noise metrics and thresholds presented in this report are the L_{DEN} 55 dB and L_{night} 50 dB indicators, in line with what Member States are required to report under the EU Environmental Noise Directive (END). Total contour areas and populations were computed for 45 major European airports using the STAPES noise model. These two metrics were complemented by noise energy, which was computed for all airports in the EU28 and EFTA region (about 2100 airports in 2014).

Figure 9.31 - Example of notional airport noise contours

Noise exposure has stabilized over the past ten years. The total population inside the STAPES Lden and Lnight contours decreased by only 2% (Lden) and 1% (Lnight) between 2005 and 2014, to reach 2.52 and 1.18 million people respectively in 2014 (Figure 9.28, Table 9.5). A similar trend is observed for the total noise energy in the EU28 and EFTA region, which decreased by 5% during the same period. This overall noise reduction is due to technological improvements, fleet renewal, increased ATM efficiency and the 2008 economic downturn. Fleet renewal has led to a 12% reduction in the average noise energy per operation between 2005 and 2014.

Under the base (most likely) traffic forecast, continued 0.1 dB reduction per annum for new aircraft deliveries (low technology improvement rate) could halt the growth of the overall noise exposure in the 2035 timeframe, while a 0.3 dB reduction per annum (advanced technology improvement rate) could lead to a net reduction of the exposure compared to 2014 even under the high traffic forecast. However, in the absence of continuing technology improvements for new aircraft, the population inside the increased Lden 55 dB contour areas could reach 2.58, 3.54 and 4.29 million in 2035 under the low, base and high traffic forecasts respectively. The effects of different trends on total noise exposure are shown in the Figure 9.32:

Figure 9.32 - Future technology improvements could stabilize overall aircraft noise exposure in the 2035 timeframe

Aircraft Noise in Context

Under the Environmental Noise Directive, aircraft noise data from 56 out of 91 airports having more than 50,000 movements/year, were reported by EU Member States. These data showed that for these 56 airports 2.4 million people were exposed to noise levels of 55 dB Lden and above in 2012. An analysis was conducted on the remaining 35 European airports having more than 50,000 movements/year and, combined with the reported data, showed that around 5 million people in Europe were exposed to noise above 55 dB Lden that year.

World Health Organization (WHO) Noise Research

The Lden and Nnight indicators represent average noise over a given time period, so they do not capture the specific characteristics of each noise event or differences between sources of noise (e.g. noise from single events are smoothed out).

In order to support Member States, the WHO regional office for Europe is reviewing the latest scientific evidence and is expected to propose revised dose-response functions in 2016 to help better quantify the consequences of noise on health. As part of this work, WHO is also reviewing the harmful effects of aircraft noise at lower dB levels than the Lden 55 dB and Nnight 50 dB indicators used in this report. Past work on noise dose-response curves and health effects shows that aircraft typically generate more annoyance and sleep disturbance than other sources at the same Lden levels.

	2005	2014 (% change vs. 2005)	Base forecast 2035 Advanced – Low Technology (% change vs. 2005)
L_{den} 55 dB area, 45 STAPES airports (km ²)	2,251	2,181 (-3%)	1,983 – 2,587 (-12%) (+15%)
L_{night} 50 dB area, 45 STAPES airports (km ²)	1,268	1,248 (-2%)	1,058 – 1,385 (-17%) (+9%)
L_{den} 55 dB population, 45 STAPES airports (millions)	2.56	2.52 (-2%)	1.97 – 2.86 (-23%) (+12%)
L_{night} 50 dB population, 45 STAPES airports (millions)	1.18	1.18 (-1%)	0.78 – 1.19 (-34%) (+1%)
Noise energy, all EU28-EFTA airports (10 ¹⁵ J)	9.60	9.16 (-5%)	9.37 – 12.9 (-2%) (+34%)
Average noise energy per operation, all EU28-EFTA airports (10 ⁸ J)	7.29	6.41 (-12%)	4.14 – 5.70 (-43%) (-22%)

Table 9.5 - Summary of noise indicators

Quieter Aircraft Design

The historic picture

There is no doubt that over more than fifty years of the jet age, technology has significantly improved aircraft noise performance, to the point that in 2012, the 57 dBA Leq aircraft noise contour area around Heathrow (Figure 9.32) covered just over a tenth of the area it did in 1974. Even considering significant population growth, 2012 saw a near ten-fold reduction in people within the contour compared with 1974. Gatwick has seen similar reductions (Figure 9.33), with the 57 dBA Leq contour area now around 20% of the size it was in 1979 when noise contours were first generated, and the population affected by that level of noise is just over 10% of the number it was in 1979.

Figure 9.33 - Heathrow departure 90 dBA SEL contours on 27L CPT for selected aircraft

Figure 9.34 - Gatwick departure 90 dBA SEL contours on 26 SAM for selected aircraft

Despite the impact of the 2008 financial crisis and subsequent recession on passenger demand (and flight numbers at most airports), noise improvements over the past decade have been slower than in previous years. In part this is because following the retirement of the Concorde by both Air France and British Airways, the number of flights by extremely noisy, older aircraft from the 1960s and 1970s reduced to close to zero at Heathrow and many other UK airports. It may also be in part because the post-9/11 and financial crisis downturns, combined with the cyclical nature of airline fleet renewal and type introduction mean there hasn't been a significant number of new aircraft operating during the period, and in part because there are fewer potential improvements in noise performance through manufacture following the step changes in performance over the previous 40 years. At Heathrow due to tightening capacity constraints, there has also been a steady increase in aircraft size, the proportion of long-haul flights has increased, and many domestic routes have reduced frequency or disappeared; all of which would have seen noise increasing without the accompanying technological and operational developments.

Today's technology

Airbus A380 The Airbus A380 entered service in October 2007 operated by Singapore Airlines, and began flying into Heathrow in March 2008. In a typical configuration, it is capable of carrying around 525 passengers. If operated as a fully economy class service, it would be able to carry over 850 people. The A380 is one of the quietest wide-body jet aircraft currently in operation, with only the newer and significantly smaller Boeing 787 being quieter. Throughout its design, there was a conscious focus on reducing noise, and ensuring that it was able to meet ICAO's Chapter 4 Standard adopted in 2001 and implemented in 2006. The focus on noise performance was in part to ensure that delayed departures could still operate during the night period at Heathrow Airport, where the Quota Count (QC) system imposes much stricter controls for night-time operations than ICAO's Chapter 4 standard, limiting operations for any aircraft with a QC/2 rating or higher from being scheduled between 2300 and 0600.

The A380 is rated (Figure 9.34) as 2 for departure and 0.5 for arrival noise, allowing its use within the total night period. By contrast, the 747-400 is rated as QC 4 for departure and QC

2 for arrival, meaning it is prohibited from being scheduled to depart from Heathrow after 2300 and before 0700, though it may operate as a delayed departure. The newer Boeing 747-8 model falls within the applicable QC limits.

Figure 9.35 - Heathrow arrival 85 and 90 dBA SEL contours for an Airbus A380 landing 27L compared with a Boeing 747-400, the principle aircraft it is replacing

To put the A380's size and noise performance within its historical context, in a typical configuration, the aircraft allows for a seat capacity increase of 90% over 1992's A340-300, for no additional noise. This step change underlines the potential for quota-based incentives to drive airline and manufacturer action to improve noise performance. Upon its introduction at Heathrow in 2008, operated by Singapore Airlines, the airline, airport, and NATS jointly trialled and implemented new departure procedures to reduce fuel burn and CO₂ emissions while remaining within noise limits - highlighting the potential for noise to be managed within strict limits on other environmental impacts.

Boeing 787 Dreamliner although they were developed at a similar time, and introduced to service within five years of one another, the Airbus A380 and Boeing 787 Dreamliner are quite different types of aircraft. While the A380 is capable of carrying over 800 passengers, the 787 has a more traditional maximum passenger configuration of 330 people. The 787 is the world's first composite commercial transport aircraft and was designed to achieve fuel savings of up to 20% over the Boeing 767 which it replaces. Like the A380, the 787 also operates within Heathrow's strict Quota Count operational restrictions for night-time flying and is quieter than the aircraft types it aims to replace. Airbus A350 In 2004 Airbus began a programme of work to create a new wide-body aircraft capable of longer flights and with a similar capacity to the 787. This has grown into the A350 XWB (extra wide body), a twin-engined aircraft carrying between 250 and 350 passengers depending on configuration. It is expected to begin commercial operations during 2014. Like the 787 it features a composite airframe and is designed to be very fuel efficient. As with other new types, noise performance is promised to significantly improve over existing wide-body aircraft, but data is not yet available to quantify

the gains. Improving existing types Introducing new aircraft types is a slow and typically cyclical process that can be fraught with delays and issues, as recent experience with the introduction of both Airbus and Boeing's new models, the A380 and 787, has shown. Even when new aircraft types are available, reflecting is a lengthy and expensive process for airlines, with significant resource impacts. In addition, despite the existing incentives to improve fleet noise performance, even at Heathrow, there has been no evidence that airlines have changed their normal fleet replacement cycles (for instance, in early 2014, British Airways' long-haul fleet consisted of four Airbus A380s, 55 Boeing 747-400s, 21 Boeing 767-300s and 55 Boeing 777s covering an age range of 0 to 25 years).

The introduction of newer models of existing types does offer the potential for improving noise (and other environmental and efficiency) performance, which, while still representing a significant outlay for airlines, reduces some of the costs and risks associated with purchasing brand new aircraft types. To put that in context, the latest version of Boeing's 747, the 747-8 Intercontinental, introduced in 2005, claims a 30% noise performance improvement over that of its predecessor the 747-400, originally introduced in 1989.

The future

Given the significant improvements in performance in the latest types of aircraft, and the general trend of slowing noise contour reduction over the past decade, in future when new types are introduced, the noise improvements may not be as significant as with previous generations of aircraft. In this context, we welcome industry's ambition to drive further improvements, set out for instance in the Flightpath 2050 vision 20. Assuming a standard fleet life of 25 years, in line with usual depreciation assumptions, and take the last generation of aircraft as being purchased up until 2013 (which does not factor in continuing purchases of older aircraft by both legacy and low cost carriers), we can expect to see significant noise improvements arising from normal fleet renewal exercises as airlines switch from older types to the latest aircraft until at least 2038. To provide context, the Figure 9.35 shows the ages of the fleet in operation at Heathrow during 2013 - significant numbers of aircraft predating the latest generation are still in operation, showing the potential for normal fleet renewal to improve noise performance.

Figure 9.36 - LHR Aircraft fleet 2013 - No. aircraft vs. year built (Source: ERCD data)

Figure 9.37 - ICAO noise chapter performance of wide-body aircraft since 1960 (Source: EASA European Aviation Environmental Report)

Figure 9.38 - Sustainable Aviation Noise Roadmap (Source: Sustainable Aviation Noise Roadmap)

The impact of quieter aircraft (Figures 9.36 – 9.37) can be illustrated from the noise maps of Heathrow and Helsinki airports, which are shown in the Figure 9.38. Both charts show the size of the noise envelope over time and suggest that a combination of engine/airframe improvements and changes to navigation patterns can dramatically alter the shape of noise nuisance.

Figure 9.39 - Shrinking Airport Noise Contours: Heathrow, 1974-2012 (left) and Helsinki, 1990-2013 (right) (Source: Heathrow Airport Ltd, Helsinki Airport)

Aircraft Design

The improvement in the efficiency of technology is frequently cited as the main source of improvements in sustainability for the industry.

The improvements in technology can be easily demonstrated by the diagram below (Figure 9.39), produced by the International Energy Agency (IEA). Whilst it is immediately apparent that the greatest increases in efficiency were made in the early years of the jet age, the industry is continuing on a steep path of improvement (Table 9.6).

Figure 9.40 - Aircraft Efficiency Gains since 1955 (Source: IEA)

Decibel Levels by Aircraft Type

<u>Airline</u> Aircraft type	Engine Type	Takeoff EPNdB	Landing EPNdB	Total EPNdB
<u>American</u>				
MD-80	JT8D-217A/C; JT8D-219	91.4333	93.7	185.1333
737-800	CFM56-7B24/3	88.6	96.5	185.1
757-200	RB211-535E4B	85.7	95.2	180.9
767-200/ER/EM	CF6-80A	92.8	101.7	194.5
767-300/300ER	CF6-80C2B6	91.1	98.4	189.5
777- 200/200lr/233lr (ER)	Trent 892	94	99.5	193.5
<u>Continental</u>				
737-300	CFM56-3B1	87.5	100.1	187.6
737-500	CFM56-3B1	87.3	100	187.3
737-700/700LR	CFM56-7B24	88.6	96.1	184.7
737-800	CFM56-7B26	85.6	96.6	182.2
737-900	CFM56-7B26	87.2	96.4	183.6
757-200	RB211-535	88.1	99.6	187.7
757-300	RB211-535E4B	88.4	95.4	183.8
767-200/ER/EM	GECF6- 80C2B4F	88.5	96.5	185
767-400/ER	GECF6- 80C2B8F	91.2	98.7	189.9
777- 200/200lr/233lr (ER)	GE90-90B	91.3	97.8	189.1
<u>Airtran</u>				
717-200	BR700-715C130	82.1	91.6	173.7
737-700/700LR	CFM56-7B22	86.3	95.9	182.2
<u>UPS</u>				
757-200	PW2040; RB211-535E4	88.5	96.65	185.15
767-300/300ER	CF6-80C2B6F	90.9	98.5	189.4
A300B/C/F/-100/- 200	PW4158	93.1	101.9	195
MD-11	CF6-80C2D1F; PW4462; PW4460	94.5333	104.1333	198.6666
747-400F	CF6-80C2B1F	99.7	101.4	201.1

Table 9.6 - Engine Type, Take-off, Landing, and Total Decibel Levels for Each Aircraft Type Within Selected Airlines

Aviation's Contribution to Protecting from Air Pollutants

The aviation industry is working to reduce the level of pollutants emitted through improvements to aircraft and engine design, operational procedures and fuels.

Changes Made by Airlines

Airlines can help to improve air quality by:

- Switching off main engines on arrival and, where possible, limiting the use of aircraft auxiliary power units by using fixed electrical ground power, ground power units and pre-conditioned air.
- Delaying the switching on of main engines until absolutely necessary on departure.
- Whilst parked at aircraft stands, operating aircraft on the lowest possible energy draw (e.g. turning off unnecessary electrical systems such as In-Flight Entertainment).
- Reducing the number of engines used when taxiing.
- Applying reduced-thrust take-off.

Changes Made by Airports

Airports can help to improve air quality by:

- Providing fixed electrical ground power and pre-conditioned air for aircraft.
- Optimizing the most efficient flow of aircraft when moving between runways and stands.
- Investing in lower emission ground vehicles for use at the airport.
- Considering charging higher landing charges for aircraft with higher NO_x emissions.
- Developing surface access strategies that encourage the use of public transport.
- Using electric towing aircraft.

Air Quality Policies

EU Member States have set air quality targets through European legislation. Some of these targets are reflected as UK-wide objectives whilst others are devolved objectives with separate targets for England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland.

Defra is the Government department with responsibility for setting national policy on air quality to meet these targets. At a local level, local authorities are required to assess air quality and Air Quality Management Areas (AQMAs) are declared if national air quality objectives are not being met.

Two of these targets are for average mean levels of 40µgm⁻³ for NO₂ and PM₁₀ in the UK. Data is available below for a number of UK airports in relation to both targets. There are no specific air quality targets for the UK aviation industry. Instead, air quality at airports is measured as part of a local authority's duties around air quality and any issues are dealt with between the airport and local authority.

Different airports have different obligations for monitoring and reporting air quality, with some reporting requirements necessary by law through planning obligations.

Solutions: Use of Next Generation Biofuels

The Table 9.7 shows which of the 15 airlines carrying the most passengers in the UK have a stated policy on the use of biofuels.

Airline	Commitment to biofuel development	Proposed feedstock source	Source
Aer Lingus	None stated		
American Airlines	None stated		
British Airways	Yes	Domestic waste	British Airways Corporate Responsibility Report 2012
EasyJet	None stated		
Emirates	None stated		
Flybe	None stated		
Jet2.com	None stated		
Lufthansa	Yes	A number of trials operated	Lufthansa Sustainability Report 2014
Monarch	None stated		
Ryanair	None stated		
Thomas Cook	None stated		
Thomson	Yes	Used cooking oil	Thomson Airways press release, Oct 2011
United Airlines	None stated		
Virgin Atlantic	Yes	Waste gases	Airline website
Wizz Air	None stated		

Table 9.7 - Publicly stated policies on use of biofuels by airline.

Source: airline websites

9.4 Safety

In principle all airliners should be equally safe because they meet the same applicable EASA/FAA certification standards, Airbus/Boeing/Bombardier/Embraer and other manufacturers have comparable engineering skills and thoroughly develop operating and maintenance procedures. As consequence, aviation remains the safest mode of transport, although with relatively large differences across the globe. Airlines in Europe and the US have managed on more than one occasion to have a completely accident free year despite operating in the densest air traffic regionally as well as having international flights all over the globe in various weather and other conditions.

The reasons for reduced relative safety in other regions of the world can be several: (i) persistence of extreme weather conditions in some regions, like arctic, tropical or deserts; (ii) operation of older aircraft requiring more careful maintenance; (iii) less adherence to maintenance and operating procedures that conditions (i) and (ii) require; (iv) weaker oversight by authorities. It must also be acknowledged that in all regions of the world the safety standards also vary considerably depending on the type of operation: (i) airliners and business jets are much safer than private aircraft; (ii) transport is safer than crop spraying or firefighting that involve low altitude flying near obstacles and obscurants.

Despite all these differences the quest for higher safety across all operations must continue. The aviation authorities in the US first, and next also in Europe, have banned foreign airlines deemed not to meet adequate safety standards. This is necessary to protect the safety of those flying into and out of Europe and the US and also of residents that could become the victims of eventual accidents. The list of banned airlines could be of use to warn passengers that might be attracted to fly with those airlines in other regions of the world. An effort to cooperate with aviation regulatory authorities worldwide, helping them to implement safety standards, would be a preventive measure leaving bans as the necessary last resort in fewer cases.

Safety in aviation (Key Topic T9.6) is enhanced by analysing accident/incident data (Key Topic T9.7).

KEY TOPIC T9.6 SAFETY IN AIR TRANSPORT

T9.6.1 Introduction

Safety is the top priority for all involved in aviation—and aviation is the safest form of long-distance travel. At 2016 there were over 40 million safe flights. It was made, among others, by a framework that incorporates respect for global standards, cooperation and the value of data. Global standards exist, but they are not being applied universally.

T9.6.2 Safety Standards in Different Regions of the World

The air transport industry plays a major role in global economic activity and development. One of the key elements to maintaining the vitality of civil aviation is to ensure safe, secure, efficient and environmentally sustainable operations at the global, regional and national levels.

A specialized agency of the United Nations, the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) was created in 1944 to promote the safe and orderly development of international civil aviation throughout the world. ICAO promulgates Standards and Recommended Practices (SARPs) to facilitate harmonised regulations in aviation safety, security, efficiency and environmental protection on a global basis. ICAO is the primary forum for cooperation in all fields of civil aviation among its 191 Member States.

Improving the safety of the global air transport system is ICAO's guiding and most fundamental strategic objective. The Organization works constantly to address and enhance global aviation safety through coordinated activities and targets outlined in its Global Aviation Safety Plan (GASP). The Global Aviation Safety Plan or "GASP", is the document which supports the prioritization and continuous improvement of aviation safety. The GASP follows an approach and philosophy similar to that of the Global Air Navigation Plan (ICAO, Doc 9750), also referred to as the GANP. Both documents promote coordination and collaboration among international, regional and national initiatives aimed at delivering a harmonized, safe and efficient international civil aviation system. The GASP initiatives are monitored by ICAO's appraisal of global and regional aviation safety metrics on the basis of established risk management principles — a core component of contemporary State Safety Programmes (SSP) and Safety Management Systems (SMS). In all of its coordinated safety activities, ICAO strives to achieve a balance between assessed risk and the requirements of practical, achievable and effective risk mitigation strategies.

Technical assistance is a major component of ICAO's "No Country Left Behind" (NCLB) initiative which focuses on assisting all States on priority basis to provide support for implementation of ICAO SARPs under all ICAO strategic objectives. Building partnerships and pooling resources among States, international organizations, development institutions and industry is essential for collaboration on and contribution to technical assistance for effective implementation of SARPs and policies by States with sustainable results.

As part of this effort ICAO established the Aviation Safety Implementation Assistance Partnership (ASIAP) during the Second High-level Safety Conference in 2015, as the platform for ICAO and its safety partners to coordinate efforts for the provision of assistance to States. Its members include Canada, China, France, Japan, Malaysia, Republic of Korea, Singapore, South Africa, United Kingdom, United States, Airports Council International (ACI), African Civil Aviation Commission (AFCAC), Airbus, Boeing, the Civil Air Navigation Services Organization (CANSO), the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), the International Air Transport Association (IATA), the World Bank and the Arab Civil Aviation Commission (ACAC).

T9.6.2.1 Europe

In the last 25 years, the aviation sector in Europe has undergone a revolution that would have been unthinkable without key measures taken at EU level. Up to the late 1980s, air transport was fully controlled by State governments and overregulated by rather rigid bilateral agreements and obsolete international conventions. Since then, progressively, the European Union became a leading force and a respected policy maker in the field of air transport. Being highly successful in liberalising the aviation sector in Member States, the EU took the opportunity to pursue its action further. Other important aspects – such as competition rules,

traffic management, safety, security, airport capacity, environmental protection, passenger rights and external relations – were given similar attention. The term air safety designates technical aspects of flying, such as rules for construction and use of aircraft. Europe has a long tradition in rulemaking cooperation in aviation safety, with the first common standards developed around 1990 within the framework of the currently no longer existing Joint Aviation Authorities (JAA). At that time, the European aviation safety authorities collaborated in the development of the Joint Aviation Requirements (JAR) and related procedures, initially in the field of aircraft manufacturing and design, and later also in respect of flight operations, maintenance and crew licensing. The current EU aviation safety system – a set of common safety rules – is based on close relations between the European Commission, the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), Eurocontrol, national civil aviation authorities, as well as aircraft manufacturers, airlines and other undertakings participating in the Single Aviation Market.

In 1991, the Council Regulation No 3922 – based on JAR – on the harmonisation of technical requirements and administrative procedures in the field of civil aviation safety – commonly referred to as EU-OPS – focused, in particular, on measures applicable to the operation and maintenance of aircraft and to persons and organisations involved in those tasks. It was updated in 2006 by Regulations No 1899 and 1900 of the European Parliament and of the Council.

In 2002, the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) came into being with the adoption of the Regulation No 1592 of the European Parliament and of the Council on common rules in the field of civil aviation and establishing a European Aviation Safety Agency. EASA was supposed to cover all aspects related to airworthiness and environmental certification of aeronautical products, parts and appliances, building on the experiences and cooperation of the former group of European aviation regulators (JAA).

The Regulation No 1592 has been amended in 2003 by the Regulation No 1643 of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealed in 2008 by the Regulation No 216 of the European Parliament and of the Council that extended the powers of EASA to aircraft operations and crew licensing and training and also set safety rules on design, production, maintenance and operation of aircraft, certification of organisations and personnel in the aircraft sector and harmonisation and recognition of national certificates throughout the EU. The latest Regulation No 1108 of the European Parliament and of the Council, which was negotiated during the 2009 Czech Presidency, amended the Regulation No 216 in the field of aerodromes, Air Traffic Management and air navigation and enlarged further the powers of EASA to cover safety aspects of airport operations and provision of air navigation services and Air Traffic Management.

The extended duties of EASA are to help the European Commission to develop common standards on safety of civil aviation in EU legislation, ensure uniform application of these standards, issue certificates to EU companies in air transport and conduct inspections. These significant powers in the fields of airworthiness, environment, flight crews, aircraft operations, third-country aircraft, airport operations, air navigation services and Air Traffic Management was executed by a progressive adoption by 2013.

In order to improve air safety and prevent future disasters, it is essential to evaluate all aircraft accidents and incidents and come up with relevant conclusions. To this end, the Council Directive No 56 has been adopted in 1994, establishing the fundamental principles governing the investigation of civil aviation accidents and incidents, facilitating investigations and transposing into the EU legislation a number of fundamental international principles. In 2010, the Directive No 56 has been updated by the Regulation No 996 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the investigation and prevention of accidents and incidents in civil aviation. The effectiveness of air accident investigations has been strengthened, cooperation between authorities facilitated and the rights of victims of air accidents and their relatives reinforced.

Due to the fact, that not only EU airlines fly the EU sky, the Regulation No 2111 of the European Parliament and of the Council established in 2005 a Community list of air carriers subject to an operating ban within the Community and imposed the obligation to inform air transport passengers of the identity of the operating air carrier. The so-called European Blacklist of airlines with low safety standards, regularly updated, includes airlines banned from operating in the EU and airlines which are restricted to operating under specific conditions.

Air safety issues are mainly air carriers' concern. On one hand, airlines are in favour of achieving the highest possible safety performance and harmonising the rules across Member States. On the other hand, they complain that the European Commission does not take due account of their professional views.

Europe plays a leading role as regards aviation safety. Despite the excellent safety performance of aviation in Europe, recent events remind the need to always remain vigilant and constantly search for weaknesses in the system before they manifest in an accident.

At the heart of this system is the concept of safety risks management, namely hazards identification, risks assessment and decision-making on the best course of action to mitigate those risks. The European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), Member States (MS) and industry work closely together in this process. At European level, this process is coordinated by the EASA and documented in the European Plan for Aviation Safety (EPAS).

The fifth edition of EPAS covers the five-year period between 2016 and 2020 and is now an integral part of the EASA's programming activities. This means that the safety priorities identified in EPAS are addressed by specific actions in the EASA's rulemaking or safety promotion programmes, specific actions in the State Safety Programmes (SSPs) or through focused oversight activities performed either by the Agency or the MS.

In comparison with previous editions, the current one is more data driven, providing a clear link with the Annual Safety Review (ASR) and with the EASA's Rulemaking Programme. An increased emphasis has been put on using safety promotion and focused oversight activities to mitigate safety risks.

T9.6.2.2 United States of America

US aviation industry leaders, from the beginning, believed the airplane could not reach its full commercial potential without federal action to improve and maintain safety standards. At their

urging, the Air Commerce Act was passed in 1926. This landmark legislation charged the Secretary of Commerce with fostering air commerce, issuing and enforcing air traffic rules, licensing pilots, certifying aircraft, establishing airways, and operating and maintaining aids to air navigation.

To ensure a federal focus on aviation safety, President Franklin Roosevelt signed the Civil Aeronautics Act in 1938. The legislation established the independent Civil Aeronautics Authority (CAA), with a three-member Air Safety Board that would conduct accident investigations and recommend ways of preventing accidents. On May 21, 1958, Senator A. S. Monroney introduced a bill to create an independent Federal Aviation Agency to provide for the safe and efficient use of national airspace. Two months later, on August 23, 1958, the President signed the Federal Aviation Act, which transferred the Civil Aeronautics Authority's functions to a new independent Federal Aviation Agency responsible for civil aviation safety.

The FAA mission is to provide the safest, most efficient aerospace system in the world. In fact, thanks to the work of FAA, it was created the safest, most reliable, most efficient, and most productive air transportation system in the world. To ensure aviation's future viability, FAA is now working with its federal and industry partners to develop a flexible aerospace system that fully responds to the changing needs of businesses and customers in the 21st century. The strength of the NextGen system depends on lower costs, improved service, greater capacity, and smarter security measures. That is why FAA has defined a vision of the future that integrates achievements in safety, security, efficiency, and environmental compatibility.

The Federal Aviation Regulations, or FARs, are rules prescribed by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) governing all aviation activities in the United States. The FARs are part of Title 14 of the Code of Federal Regulations (CFR). A wide variety of activities are regulated, such as aircraft design and maintenance, typical airline flights, pilot training activities, hot-air ballooning, lighter-than-air aircraft, man-made structure heights, obstruction lighting and marking, and even model rocket launches, model aircraft operation, sUAS & Drone operation, and kite flying.

The rules are designed to promote safe aviation, protecting pilots, flight attendants, passengers and the general public from unnecessary risk. Since 1958, these rules have typically been referred to as "FARs", short for Federal Aviation Regulations. However, another set of regulations (Title 48) is titled "Federal Acquisitions Regulations", and this has led to confusion with the use of the acronym "FAR". Therefore, the FAA began to refer to specific regulations by the term "14 CFR part XX".

T9.6.2.3 Bilateral Agreements

As globalisation advances, aviation safety is increasingly a cooperative, global effort. Civil Aviation Authorities from different countries or regions must cooperate in order to harmonize and coordinate joint efforts aimed to aviation safety.

As safety doesn't stop at European borders, EASA works with authorities worldwide to raise global standards. Being an authority itself, it can understand and address the challenges, and bring different stakeholders together.

In 2014, the Certification Management Team: ANAC (Agência Nacional de Aviação Civil), EASA (European Aviation Safety Agency), FAA (Federal Aviation Administration), and TCCA (Transport Canada Civil Aviation), agreed to greater collaboration between authorities „to more efficiently and effectively develop and implement regulatory and policy solutions to common certification issues“. Globalization of aviation business and emerging countries trigger growing resource demands on authorities. Maximum use of the BASA (Bilateral Agreement of Safety in Aviation) and full recognition of certifying authorities 'capabilities are essential to reduce efforts in validation.

The Technical Implementation Procedures (TIP) were authorized by Article 5 and Annex 1 of the Agreement between the Government of the United States of America (U.S.) and the European Union (EU) on Cooperation in the Regulation of Civil Aviation Safety. In accordance with Article 5 of the Agreement, the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) have determined that the aircraft certification systems of each Authority for the design approval, production approval, airworthiness approval, and continuing airworthiness of the civil aeronautical products and articles identified in this document, are sufficiently compatible in structure and performance to support these procedures.

The TIP is based on continuous communication and mutual confidence in the FAA's and EASA's technical competence and ability to perform regulatory functions within the scope of the TIP. The FAA and EASA, when acting as the Authority for the importing State, shall give the same validity to the certification made by the other, as the Authority for the exporting State, as if they were made in accordance with its own applicable laws, regulations, and requirements. When a finding is made by one Authority in accordance with the laws and regulations of the other Authority and the TIP, that finding is given the same validity as if it were made by the other Authority. Therefore, the fundamental principle of the TIP is to maximize the use of the exporting Authority's aircraft certification system to ensure that the airworthiness and environmental requirements of the validating Authority are satisfied.

As required by the Agreement, the FAA Aircraft Certification Service and EASA Certification Directors have established the Certification Oversight Board (COB), consisting of management representatives from each Authority. The COB shall be responsible for the effective functioning, implementation, and continued validity of these procedures, including revisions and amendments thereto. The COB shall establish its own rules of procedure, its membership, and meeting schedules. The frequency of these meetings will be mutually agreed upon by the COB and will depend on the number and significance of the issues to be discussed between the authorities. These meetings will also be used to discuss and harmonize any major differences in standards and their interpretation that are identified during certification projects between the FAA and EASA and, when significant differences are identified, formal proposals will be raised through the applicable rulemaking committee. The COB will invite management from the responsible policy office to participate on all discussions focused on operational issues (e.g. Maintenance Review Board and Operational Suitability Data).

T9.6.3 Safety Standards for Different Services

T9.6.3.1 Business Aviation

Business Aviation has established a record as one of the world's safest forms of transportation. Professionally flown aircraft of all sizes are operated on unscheduled routes to all corners of the globe, yet the safety record continues to be excellent despite the very challenging operating environment. The exemplary safety record of business aviation can be attributed to professionalism and attention to safe operating practices. The business aviation community promotes safety through industry standards and good training, as well as through monitoring and analysing safety information to facilitate continuous improvement.

The global population (2013) of Business Aircraft consist of about 19,000 business jets and 14,500 Turbo Props. Business aircraft in North America represent 61.2% of the global fleet. South and Central America have approximately 11.6% and Europe 13.0% of the world's fleet. Other regions account for the remaining 14% of the fleet.

The 2013 summarized flight hour totals are as follows (2013): Business Jets – 7,700,000 hours and Turbo Props – about 4,000,000 hours. The flying hours in North America represents 63.4% of the total, Europe 13.2%, Central/South America 12.5%, and the rest of the world 11%.

At business aviation safety requirements are based on Regulation (EU) 376/2014 on the Reporting, Analysis and Follow Up of Occurrences in Civil Aviation, which was built on Directive 2003/42 and on reporting and modern SMS requirements under IRs of BR216/2008. The Key Areas of the Regulation:

- Improved reporting and follow up of occurrences from both mandatory and voluntary reporting processes.
- Introduction of occurrence risk classification.
- Rules on confidentiality of information and Just Culture.
- Provision of Guidance Material and other useful supporting information for industry.
- Analysis-a key part Safety Risk Management process to use and share what is learnt.

The following concepts and actions are elements of safety culture that can be found in many organizations:

- Unqualified commitment to safety as a behavioural pattern and pervasive way of life by top management.
- Unambiguous expectations by each level of management as well as each peer group that, for all employees, safe life patterns and work habits are as normal as breathing and must be practiced off the job as well as on the job.
- Availability of quality, standardized equipment with which to accomplish the assigned tasks.
- Clear, easily understood operating procedures, followed without deviation.
- Inclusive system of communications for collecting, analysing, and exchanging incident data related to safety.

- Non-retribution for submission of incident data.
- Retraining without penalty or stigma when safety is involved.
- System for tracking incident and accident data, analysis of trends, and feedback of results.
- Peer acceptance that accidents are preventable, regardless of operations.
- Peer acceptance that safety is a matter of lifestyle - a matter of culture.

T9.6.3.2 Private Aircraft

The sub-sector of General Aviation (GA) covers noncomplex aircraft operations with an emphasis on non-commercial operations. This embraces aeroplanes, helicopters, sailplanes (gliders) and balloons (including airships). Their uses range from purely sport and recreational activities to general private flying, owner-operators own business use through to some commercial activities such as aerial work, all of which are included in the scope of the non-commercial use.

The regulation for GA must be proportionate: specific activities should lead to specific requirements, just fit to mitigate for the risk. Consequently, the group chose to adopt a wide area of applicability, and principles and guidelines of a sufficiently general nature to be used as appropriate in different cases. This does not preclude that, when coming to specific regulation elaboration, it will be necessary to identify very precise boundaries for application.

GA should be treated differently to Commercial Air Transport (CAT), because it is important to recognise the differences between commercial and non-commercial environments from a safety management perspective.

- Control of Risk: end-use stakeholders in non-CAT aviation generally have much more ability to assess and control the risk of the operation. In many cases, except for very limited risk to third parties, the operators are the only stakeholders exposed to risk.
- Level Playing Field: in the competitive CAT market, driven by a profit motive, a level playing field between actors is necessary to ensure that safety does not enter a vicious downward spiral.
- Cost Burden and Economies of Scale: CAT operations are typically much more repetitive than non-commercial operations. CAT aircraft may fly up to 4,000 hours p.a. whereas non-commercial aircraft may typically fly only 50 to 100 hours p.a. This leads to significant economies of scale for CAT in dealing with fixed costs and other resource requirements including those generated by regulatory compliance.
- Flexibility: CAT operations are usually planned in detail in advance with a limited need for short-term flexibility. By contrast, non-CAT operations are often planned at relatively short notice, tend to be dynamic and may even be opportunistic (e.g. highly weather dependent).
- Private flying including sporting and recreational / leisure aviation as well as personal transport. This form of flying has only one thing in common with CAT, the 3-dimensional aspect and only three areas of overlap or adjacent proximity, which are use of airspace, communications frequencies, and some airports.

GA must therefore be treated as a sector in its own right and not as a watered-down “Commercial Air Transport (CAT) by-product”.

As highlighted by ICAO and for the reasons mentioned above, the level of safety expected for GA may not be the same as the one required for CAT. The available data in various European States show that the currently observed level of safety for GA activities – the least complex ones - is currently indeed not as high as CAT’s.

Public perception seems to accept the current levels of safety demonstrated by the GA community. It is however essential not to compromise that level of safety, by the modification of the regulatory approach.

The group considers that the regulatory approach is not the sole method of assuring a minimum acceptable level of safety, but that both education and the development of an improved safety culture across the community are equally valid. A more liberal attitude to product approvals is also expected to promote innovation and to lead to the rapid introduction of more modern and safer equipment.

Applying safety management principles, careful monitoring of the evolution of the GA safety situation will be of high importance, to be able to take appropriate measures (not necessarily new regulations, as mentioned above) to ensure the safety level remains appropriate.

Transparency for the participants to GA activities will have to be increased: they need to be adequately informed that the level of safety they will encounter may not be the same as in a commercial air transport flight, in order for them to understand and accept the level of safety knowingly.

T9.6.3.3 Agricultural Aviation

Most aerial agricultural operations are flown in heavily laden aircraft, at low level in challenging terrain. Specialised equipment and highly skilled people are needed to operate this sector. Apart from the obvious operational concerns, participants are also subject to many other factors affecting safety. These include business performance, local weather conditions, and personal issues. Despite significant effort from the CAA (Civil Aviation Authority) and the aviation industry, the safety performance in this sector remains poor. The CAA and industry have agreed that a new approach to managing risk is needed.

It was seen the development of Safety Management Systems, known as SMS, as a positive approach to safety related risk. When in place, SMS structure ensures a proactive approach to risk identification and risk management. Risks can then be identified and treated before they lead to unsafe or dangerous outcomes. This is not only for safety, but also for business enhancement. SMS is part of a global change to how regulators carry out their obligations – risk based regulatory oversight.

The CAA is committed to the concept of adopting a risk-based approach to regulatory oversight. This is in line with International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO) requirements for regulatory bodies to develop a State Safety Programme (SSP). The development of the SSP

will be in accordance with ICAO Annex 19 Standards and Recommended Practices. This includes the implementation of a formal SMS by aviation organisations.

The aviation industry is dynamic and safety-risk factors also change. Without ongoing effort, there is a potential for risks to increase due to factors such as introducing new technology, and commercial pressures. The regulator and aviation organisations need to employ a risk-based approach to safety management. One of the main objectives of risk-based regulation for the CAA, is to have structured means to effectively use resources. This ensure that the highest risk sectors of industry will be managed first.

This is one of the main reasons why the agricultural aviation sector was selected to undergo a Sector Risk Profile.

Risk can be defined as the chance something could happen, and risk management as the identification of safety risks enabling proactive control of the potential outcome of these risks.

Many risk elements can be identified in the agricultural aviation SRP. Placing them into risk levels ranging from Medium to Very High. These levels are determined by assessing the likelihood of the risk occurring and the possible consequences. Examples of identified risk elements include aircraft performance and maintenance; operator obligations; pilot training; and airstrip conditions.

T9.6.4 Air Carriers Operating Ban

T9.6.4.1 European Union

The list of air carriers banned in the European Union is a list of airlines failing to meet regulatory oversight standards of the EU, and which are banned from entering the airspace of any member state. All Member States and the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) have the obligation to communicate to the Commission all information which may be relevant to updating the list. This may include reports showing serious safety deficiencies of an air carrier (such as reports of Safety Assessment of Foreign Aircraft inspections performed at airports within the European Community), operating bans imposed by third countries, audit reports drawn up by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (ICAO) following safety inspections (in the framework of the Universal Safety Oversight Audit Programme) of the civil aviation authorities of the 189 Contracting parties to the Chicago Convention, as well as accident-related information or other serious incident-related information.

For the purpose of updating the list, the Commission is assisted by the Air Safety Committee composed by technical air safety experts from all the EU Member States (plus Iceland, Norway and Switzerland which, however, have no voting rights) and chaired by the Commission (the Commission does not have any voting rights). Acting on a proposal by the Commission, the Air Safety Committee adopts its opinion by qualified majority, which is then submitted to the European Parliament before final adoption by the Commission and subsequent publication in the Official Journal.

The decision to include or remove a carrier (or a group of carriers certified in the same State) is taken based on the common safety criteria annexed to the "Basic Regulation" (Regulation 2111/2005/EC establishing a Community list of banned carriers). These criteria take into consideration, for instance, the existence of safety deficiencies on the part of an air carrier, or the lack of ability (or willingness) by an air carrier or authorities responsible for its oversight to address safety deficiencies, operating bans imposed by third countries, audit reports drawn up by third countries or international organisations (ICAO) and substantiated accident related information. All criteria are based on international aviation safety standards.

If an airline considers that it should be taken off the list because it complies with the relevant safety standards, it can address a request to the Commission or a Member State, either directly or through its civil aviation authority. Only the Commission or a Member State may ask for the list to be updated. The Air Safety Committee will then assess the evidence presented by the airline and/or its oversight authority to substantiate its request for being withdrawn from the EC "blacklist" and formulate its opinion to the Commission.

The procedure of adding the airline to the list is the same as that for updating the list. If the Commission or a Member State acquires evidence indicating serious safety deficiencies on the part of an airline or its oversight authority anywhere in the world, they ask for the list to be revised immediately. Indeed, in such cases Member States have the obligation to ask for the update of the "blacklist". A decision is then taken in the light of the common safety criteria for banning established by the "Basic Regulation".

Where the Commission is of the opinion that the continuation of operations into the Community of an air carrier is likely to constitute a serious risk to safety and that such risk has not been resolved satisfactorily at national level (by measures taken by the civil aviation authority of a Member State) it can take provisional measures, whereby the carrier is banned from entering the European air space. These measures are then presented to the Air Safety Committee for confirmation or modification.

As long as the air carrier is subject to a total ban, it cannot operate with its aircraft and personnel in the EC. The airline is placed on Annex A to the regulation whereby the "blacklist" is updated. Equally, as long as an air carrier is subject to a partial ban it can operate only with the aircraft stipulated in the Regulation and cannot expand its network. The airline is placed on Annex B to the regulation whereby the "blacklist" is updated.

Nevertheless, banned airlines can still fly their aircraft into the Community for maintenance (notably to resolve safety deficiencies in this area) without carrying any passengers or payload – the so-called "ferry flights". Also, banned airlines can use other airlines (their aircraft and personnel) on the basis of contracts called "wet-lease agreements". In this way, passengers and cargo can still be transported but only by airlines which fully comply with the safety rules. Furthermore, aircraft which are used for government or state purposes (e.g. transport of the heads of state and/or government), escape the requirements of ICAO. Therefore, these aircraft are considered to be operating "state flights" and can therefore fly into the EC even if they are banned from operating commercial flights. Such flights need however a special authorisation

as foreseen by ICAO, from all the Member States that the plane flies over as well as from the state of destination.

Finally, banned airlines cannot enter the airspace of any Member State and fly over their territory while they are banned (totally or partially).

Airlines which have been banned, or which are being investigated in view of a potential ban, have the right to express their points of view, submit any documents which they consider appropriate for their defence, and make oral and written presentations to the Air Safety Committee and the Commission. This means that they can submit comments in writing, add new items to their file, and ask to be heard by the Commission or to attend a hearing before the Aviation Safety Committee, which then formulates its opinion based on these proceedings and the materials submitted prior to or during the hearing. The rules foresee that carriers and authorities are given a deadline within which they have to respond.

T9.6.4.2 United States of America

In the US the equivalent of EASA is FAA (Federal Aviation Agency). FAA is the part of the United States Department of Transportation. It is basically the National Aviation Authority of the US. The FAA has a blacklist of sorts as well, but its list bans certain countries, not specific airlines, from entering U.S. airspace. This ban may be implemented due to a failure to meet international aviation standards for operations and maintenance (so, the criteria is somewhat similar to the EU list).

Under the International Aviation Safety Assessment (IASA) program, the FAA determines whether another country's oversight of its air carriers that operate, or seek to operate, into the U.S., or codeshare with a U.S. air carrier, complies with safety standards established by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO). The IASA program is administered by the FAA Associate Administrator for Aviation Safety (AVS), Flight Standards Service (AFS), International Programs and Policy Division (AFS-50).

The IASA program focuses on a country's ability, not the ability of individual air carriers, to adhere to international aviation safety standards and recommended practices contained in Annex 1 (Personnel Licensing), Annex 6 (Operation of Aircraft), and Annex 8 (Airworthiness of Aircraft) to the International Convention on Civil Aviation "Chicago Convention" (ICAO Document 7300).

IASA assessments determine compliance with these international Standards by focusing on the eight critical elements of an effective aviation safety oversight authority specified in ICAO Document 9734, Safety Oversight Manual. Those eight critical elements include primary aviation legislation; specific operating regulations; State civil aviation system and safety oversight functions; technical personnel qualification and training; technical guidance, tools and the provision of safety critical information; licensing, certification, authorization, and approval obligations; surveillance obligations; and resolution of safety concerns.

T9.6.4.3 Airline SAFETY Rating

If the airline has an International Air Transport Association Operational Safety Audit certification (IOSA), it earns two stars. This certificate is actually difficult to get, so either the airline didn't sign up to be assessed (which is a little suspicious) or they have failed. The International Air Transport Association awards this certificate biannually to the airlines that meet its standards of operational management and control systems. The IOSA certificate is worth two stars—double some of the other criteria—because the IOSA certificate is a pretty good indicator of an airline's safety rating. Airlines with an IOSA certificate had 77 percent less accidents than those without one in 2012.

If the airline is not on the European Union (EU) Blacklist, it receives one star. If the airline hasn't had one fatality in the past ten years, it receives one star. This includes passengers or crew and the fatality must be due to an accident, which does not include any fatalities due to terrorism or fatalities due to something out of their control (an unidentified object obstructing the runway, etc.). If the Federal Aviation Authority (FAA) has endorsed an airline, it receives one star.

If the country of airline origin has met all eight of the International Civil Aviation Organization (IACO) safety parameters, it receives two stars. They can receive partial credit here—if they meet at least five, they get one star. The eight parameters include Airworthiness, Accident Investigation, Air Navigation Service, Aerodromes, Legislation, Operations, Licensing, and Organization.

There are two exceptions that may cause an airline to lose a star, which are:

- If the airline operates only Russian-built aircraft.
- If the country of origin has grounded an airline's fleet due to safety concerns in the last five years.

Out of 449 airlines, 149 scored the highest safety rating (seven out of seven stars). Below are listed the top ten, each with a seven out of seven rating. Qantas got the top spot, and the rest are listed in alphabetical order.

- Qantas;
- Air New Zealand;
- British Airways;
- Cathay Pacific Airways;
- Emirates;
- Etihad Airways;
- EVA Air;
- Finnair;
- Lufthansa;
- Singapore Airlines.

T9.6.5 References

Žabokrtský M., 2011, EU Air Transport Policy: Implications on Airlines and Airports, Současná Evropa 01/2011.

Regulations:

Council Regulation (EEC) No 3922/91 of 16 December 1991 on the harmonisation of technical requirements and administrative procedures in the field of civil aviation.

Regulation (EC) No 1899/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 amending Council Regulation (EEC) No 3922/91 on the harmonisation of technical requirements and administrative procedures in the field of civil aviation; Regulation (EC) No 1900/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 December 2006 amending Council Regulation (EEC) No 3922/91 on the harmonisation of technical requirements and administrative procedures in the field of civil aviation.

Regulation (EC) No 1592/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 July 2002 on common rules in the field of civil aviation and establishing a European Aviation Safety Agency.

Regulation (EC) No 1643/2003 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 July 2003 amending Regulation (EC) No 1592/2002 on common rules in the field of civil aviation and establishing a European Aviation Safety Agency.

Regulation (EC) No 216/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 February 2008 on common rules in the field of civil aviation and establishing a European Aviation Safety Agency, and repealing Council Directive 91/670/EEC, Regulation (EC) No 1592/2002 and Directive 2004/36/EC.

Regulation (EC) No 1108/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 amending Regulation (EC) No 216/2008 in the field of aerodromes, Air Traffic Management and air navigation and repealing Directive 2006/23/EC.

Council Directive 94/56/EC of 21 November 1994 establishing the fundamental principles governing the investigation of civil aviation accidents and incidents.

Regulation (EU) No 996/2010 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 October 2010 on the investigation and prevention of accidents and incidents in civil aviation and repealing Directive 94/56/EC.

Regulation (EC) No 2111/2005 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2005 on the establishment of a Community list of air carriers subject to an operating ban within the Community and on informing air transport passengers of the identity of the operating air carrier, and repealing Article 9 of Directive 2004/36/EC.

Web Pages:

ICAO, International Civil Aviation Organization, www.icao.int, access: March 2018.

EASA, European Aviation Safety Agency, <https://www.easa.europa.eu/>, access: March 2018.

FAA, Federal Aviation Administration, <https://www.faa.gov/>, access: March 2018.

KEY TOPIC T9.7 ANALYSING INCIDENT/ACCIDENT DATA

For preventing risks related on safety, one opportunity is analysing accident/incident data and decide about which actions will be most effective by using new approaches. In fact, in the past many aviation accidents have been attributable to non-sensitive and non-precise tools, malfunction of sensors, aircraft design, engines, detectors and so on. Nowadays, the use of the principle of active system control offers a good opportunity for further improvements in safety levels.

Statistically, the riskiest phases of flight are taking off and landing especially in bad weather conditions. In fact, as shown in the bottom sketch of Figure 9.41, the landing-related phases of flight have the largest percentage of total accidents: landing (27.3%), manoeuvring (14.8%), approach (11%), descent and go-around (57.8%). Among these latter, the manoeuvring phase of flight represent the fatal accident first occurrences (33.4%), probably related, to human factors and weather conditions.

Figure 9.41 - Upper panel: typical phases of flight, and bottom panel: related - phases percentages of total accidents | Source: I. Schagaev, B.R. Kirk, Active System Control, DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-46813-6_1 Springer International Publishing AG 2018

Over the past 50 years, security and flight safety have improved significantly, and their level is expected to grow even in presence of an increasing volume of air traffic foreseen for the future. 2016 and 2017 are the years with lowest number of fatalities in aviation history, thanks to the continued improvements in safety across almost every operational domain. According to a

preliminary EASA safety overview depicted in the Figure 9.42, 2017 shows the lowest number of fatal accidents in modern aviation history for commercial air transport with large airplanes. This preliminary analysis covers both worldwide operations and those involving the 32 EASA Member States. When all the safety data will be available, a more detailed analysis will be provided and published in the 2018 EASA Annual Safety Review.

In Table 9.8 a recent overview of the statistical analysis in security and safety, performed by IATA, is depicted. However, even if we have seen an important advance in safety systems, the fatal accident occurrence demonstrates the importance of joining forces with the goal to improve safety in aviation community.

Figure 9.42 - Number of fatal accidents in aviation history for worldwide commercial air transport with large aeroplanes. Source: 29191-Preliminary_Safety_Overview_2017_-_Publication.pdf

Rendement en matière de sécurité en 2017

	2017	2016	Moyenne sur 5 ans (2012-2016)
Décès à bord ⁱ	19	202	314,6
Nombre total d'accidents	45	67	74,8
Accidents mortels	6	9 ⁱⁱ	10,8
Risque de décès ⁱⁱⁱ	0,09	0,21	0,24
Accidents mortels touchant des vols de passagers	2	3	5,6
Accidents mortels touchant des vols de fret	4	6	4,6
% des accidents causant des décès	13,3	13,4	14,4
Pertes de coque d'avion à réaction	4	13	10
Pertes de coque d'avion causant des décès	1	4	3,4
Pertes de coque de turbopropulseur	9	7	15
Pertes de coque de turbopropulseur causant des décès	5	4	7,2

Table 9.8 - Statistical yield in security and safety in 2017 compared to 2016. Source: IATA document 2018

Safety Standards in Different REGIONS of the world

In USA the major cause of aeronautic accidents is related to human factor (1468 accidents in 2000) and performance. These accidents records include lack of total experience, lack of recent

experience, human performance and inadequate training. However, the USA is deemed to have the best safety management infrastructure developed so far, as illustrated in the Figure 9.43:

Figure 9.43 - Safety management infrastructure in the USA based on figures from Boeing.
Source: I. Schagaev, B.R. Kirk, Active System Control, DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-46813-6_1
Springer International Publishing AG 2018

In US, the National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB) is responsible for investigations when an accident occurs and together with FAA and NASA provide recommendations, propose practical actions to avoid similar accidents in the future.

In 2002, the European Parliament Directive on Occurrence Reporting in Civil Aviation established an aviation safety management regime similar to that in the USA. **Eurocontrol** is the leading organization in air traffic management in Europe, and together with **EASA** and **EUROCAE**, works in synergy to control function related aviation safety.

In contrast to USA, EU initiatives in aviation safety have been focused mainly on human factor, e.g., training and inspections. However, in the past, this strategy has failed as it concerns the increase in safety levels.

The introduction of satellite links has provided an opportunity to store and analyse the flight data, evaluate the safety aspect of the flight in real time, etc. as shown in the Figure 9.44:

Figure 9.44 - Conventional cycle of information processing of flight information.

Source: I. Schagaev, B.R. Kirk, Active System Control, DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-46813-6_1

Springer International Publishing AG 2018

For long-term analysis, this innovation has allowed to find safety trends over several flights and elaborate new management schemes.

In this context, an important point to be addressed is the pilot's and crew's training about the regulation protocols. Another safety issue is the mental health of the pilot related to human factor. In this regard, many areas of medicine have looked to the aviation industry to develop improvements in safety through regulated, standardized practices. In fact, it is reported that the pilot's fatigue plays an important role in safety risks. Different meta-analysis confirmed that, in general, the mental health of pilots is a key element for improve safety in aviation (Fanjoy, R.O., Harriman, S.L., DeMik, R.J. 2010. International Journal of Applied Aviation Studies. Individual and environmental predictors of burnout among regional airline pilots).

According to the EASA Annual Safety Review 2017, it is possible to establish a list of safety issues based on the past performance of the system by counting high-risk occurrences, or the number of fatalities or through the aggregated risk score. This review provides a statistical summary of aviation safety in the EASA Member States (MS) and provide the possibility to understand, which are the most important safety challenge. The major top safety issues are:

Perception and situational awareness:

- Icing in flight;
- Handling of technical failures;
- Turbulence;
- Airborne conflict;
- Flight planning;
- Decision making and planning;
- Experience, training and the competence of individuals;
- Wind-shear;

- Flight- path management;
- Mental health.

The European Plan for Aviation Safety (EPAS) is developed through the European safety risk management (SRM) process, which is articulated in five steps as shown in the Figure 9.45:

Figure 9.45 - The European Safety Risk Management Process.

Source: EASA AST summary 2017

The EPAS is a key component of integrated Safety Management System (SMS), and is constantly being reviewed and improved.

Safety standard in Europe are assured thanks to the efforts of EASA. The main issue is to apply these standards also outside Europe. EASA maintains close working relations with the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) to support States in fulfilling ICAO safety standard. ICAO promulgates **Standards and Recommended Practices (SARPs)** to facilitate harmonised regulations in particular in aviation safety, and security, hence efficiency and environmental protection on a global basis. In 2015, ICAO established the **Aviation Safety Implementation Assistance Partnership (ASIAP)** to coordinate efforts for the provision of assistance to member States (depicted in the Figure 9.46) and participating organizations. (https://www.icao.int/safety/Documents/ICAO_SR_2017_18072017.pdf)

Figure 9.46 - ASIAP State and Organisational Partners. Source: ICAO Safety Report 2017 Edition

Existing on-board checking systems are designed with the goal to improve aviation safety in future flights using as a reference the available and stored data recorded in-flight. With an on-board processing capability, it becomes possible to simultaneously record and analyse data making possible to check the aircraft conditions in real-time. Signals are recorded by the **Digital Flight Data Acquisition Unit (DFDAU)** which can also accept digital inputs from sensors and another avionics equipment. So far, new standards and available technologies enable to store 2h of cockpit voice data and record 256 12-bit data words per second. Further plans for the development of flight recording are underway, *i.e.*, the use of flash memory which improves the reliability of these records.

Today the “black box” is the major tool and way to improve the existing safety system. In 1999, the FAA introduced new aircraft black box rules, and in 2004, the FAA requested recording of controller pilot data link communication messages. In addition to voice and flight data recording, ICAO, EUROCAE and ARINC are considering video recorder. Moreover, by the end of 2006, the NTSB and FAA have requested video recorders and cameras in the cockpit, especially for small turboprops that do not currently have safety recorders.

The Figure 9.47 shows some advanced international black box trends, and highlight that Europe is somewhat behind about the recent research focus on implemented and announced “black box” projects worldwide:

	<p>China ...and a new data recorder—a spacecraft black box—is also being tested. The black box is faster than its Shenzhou 5 counterpart and contains more storage space, but at only half the size, Xinhua reported (Xinhuanet, 05) (Malik, 05)</p>
	<p>USA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time recorded, 25 h continuous • Number of parameters, 18–1000+ • Impact tolerance, 3400Gs/6.5 ms • Fire resistance, 1100°C/30 m • Water pressure resistance submerged, 20,000 ft • Underwater locator beacon, 37.5 KHz • Battery has shelf-life of 6 years or more • Capability upon activation with 30-day operation
	<p>"Izmeritel" (Russia) new flight recorder</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time recorded, 25 h continuous • Number of parameters, 18–1000+ • Impact tolerance, 3500Gs/6.5 ms • Fire resistance, 1100°C/45 m • Water pressure resistance submerged, 20,000 ft • Underwater locator beacon, 37.5 KHz • Battery has shelf-life of 6 years or more • Capability upon activation: 30-day operation <p>http://www.izmeritel.smolensk.ru/spec1.html</p>

Figure 9.47 - Existing and developmental flight safety recorders.

Source: I. Schagaev, B.R. Kirk, Active System Control, DOI 10.1007/978-3-319-46813-6_4 © Springer International Publishing AG 2018

The next generation of black boxes has to be compact, extremely resilient, active, and with enhanced capability to improve recorded time. Moreover, the smaller size and the decreased weight could provide great improvements in such devices. However, these features, i.e., decreased weight and size and, at the same time, increased resilience, durability and ability to be recovered still represent a great challenge.

The Global Aviation Safety Program (GASP) by ICAO provides a continuous improvement strategy for the implementation of effective safety oversight systems, State Safety Programmes (SSPs) and the development of advanced safety oversight systems, including predictive risk management. The GASP also sets out timelines for the global collective achievement of these near-, mid- and long-term objectives. These timelines are aligned with the established update process for the GASP and the Global Air Navigation Plan (GANP), which are revised on a triennial basis. The GASP is a high level, strategic, planning and implementation policy document developed in conjunction with the Global Air Navigation Plan (Doc 9750). Both documents promote coordination of international, regional and national initiatives aimed at delivering a harmonized, safe and efficient international civil aviation system [Global Aviation Safety Plan, Doc 10004, ISBN 978-92-9258-118-3].

ICAO has established five comprehensive strategic objectives, which are revised on a triennial basis. ICAO strategic objective dedicated to enhancing global civil aviation safety is focused primarily on the State's regulatory oversight capabilities in the context of growing passenger and cargo movements, taking into account efficiency and environmental changes.

More information on the Strategic Objectives can be found on the ICAO website at www.icao.int/about-icao/Pages/Strategic-Objectives.aspx.

The GASP objectives require that the States put in place robust and sustainable safety oversight systems leading to a more sophisticated means of managing safety. In order to meet these objectives, regional aviation safety groups (RASGs) and regional safety oversight organizations (RSOOs) should be involved actively in the coordination and harmonization of all activities undertaken to address aviation safety issues at a regional level, including the use of the global aviation safety roadmap by individual States or a group of States.

The Figure 9.48 provides an overview of the GASP objectives and their associated timelines. The States must first establish an effective safety oversight system prior to implementing an SSP. It is expected that all States will continually progress implementation of Standards and Recommended Practices (SARPs) in order to achieve the GASP objectives and priorities set out in the GASP.

Figure 9.48 - GASP objectives and associated timelines.
 Source: ICAO Doc 10004 Global Aviation Safety Plan 2017 – 2019

A target was set for all African States to attain 60 per cent effective implementation (EI) of the critical elements (CEs) of a State safety oversight system by 2017. This target was adopted by the ICAO Council and endorsed by the ICAO General Assembly as a global measure and formed the basis for the near-term objective included in the 2014-2016 edition of the GASP. It corresponds to a minimum level necessary for a State to perform effective safety oversight and move towards SSP implementation.

The near-term objectives, to be achieved by 2017, take into account the current level of safety oversight systems implementation at the regional and national levels.

The near-term objectives are as follows:

- a) States lacking fundamental safety oversight capabilities are to achieve an EI of at least 60 per cent overall of the eight CEs of a State safety oversight system. States should prioritize the resolution of deficiencies or findings which have the highest impact in terms of safety improvements. The universal safety oversight audit programme (USOAP) protocols, used to assess implementation of ICAO provisions, are categorized according to eight CEs (see Figure 9.49).

Figure 9.49 - Per cent effective implementation (EI) of the critical elements (CEs) worldwide
Source: ICAO Doc 10004 Global Aviation Safety Plan 2017 – 2019

Implementation of CE-6, which addresses licensing, certification, authorization and/or approval obligations, is fundamental to the reduction of accident rates. Furthermore, through a root cause analysis, deficiencies in CE-6 can be traced to protocol questions in CE-1 to CE-5, which establish a safety oversight system. Each deficiency in CE-6 should therefore be

associated with a specific action plan for a State's improvement efforts. Effective execution of the action plan provides the basis for prioritized compliance.

- b) States which have an EI of 60 per cent or greater should implement SSP, which will facilitate addressing risks specific to their aviation systems.
- c) All States and stakeholders are encouraged to put in place mechanisms for the sharing of safety information through their RASGs and other regional or sub-regional fora.

An interesting and important ICAO SARP is represented form Document namely "Manual for the Oversight of Fatigue Management Approaches (Doc.9966)" which support the approaches to fatigue management. Annex 6 (Operation of Aircraft) Part I – International Commercial Air Transport – Aeroplanes, which is relate to flight and cabin crew. Annex 6 (Operation of Aircraft) Part II – International General Aviation – Aeroplanes, this section 2 applies to all international GA operation and Section 3 refer to all operator personnel involved in the operation and maintenance of large and turbojet aeroplanes in GA operations. Annex 11 (Air Traffic Services), which pertain to air traffic controllers.

In addition to the Safety Report, ICAO has created lists of State safety performance indicators (SPIs). A sample set of SPIs was presented at the second High-level Safety Conference held in 2015 (HLSC 2015), through an information paper (IP/01) entitled "Safety data, performance metrics and indicators". The HLSC 2015 recommended that ICAO improve and harmonize those SPIs, taking into account others that were currently in use. Metrics are the core of the SPI process. They constitute the basis from which indicators are drawn. Once a list of metrics is available, providing information such as a definition, the data source, update frequency, unit, scope and safety relevance, State or regional specific indicators can be defined which address the uniqueness of each situation but use the same metrics.

The usage of identifiable metrics allows benchmarking between States and regions even though their safety indicators may differ with regard to their scope, coverage or target. The collection of data is crucial to the development of SPIs. Data can be collected through various ways such as auditing, inspections or reporting.

Occurrence data is typically stored in a database such as the European Coordination Centre for Accident and Incident Reporting Systems (ECCAIRS). The collection of accident and incident data is a well-established aviation safety data collection process executed at the State level.

ICAO USOAP programme has evaluated whether States have effectively implemented an accident and incident database (protocol question 6.507). As of August 2014, only 42 per cent of all audited States have effectively implemented such a database. The regional implementation rates range from 64% in the European region to 13% in Africa as can be seen on the map in the Figure 9.50:

Figure 9.50 - Effective implementation of incident and accident databases
 Source: ICAO Secretariat "Safety data, performance metrics and indicators". Presented at 2015 High-level Safety Conference (HLSC 2015)

The list of safety indicators (see the Table 9.9) has been defined which can be used by States for their safety monitoring programme and to establish baselines which can be used ultimately to define targets and acceptable levels of safety.

A- Safety Indicators			
#	Indicators and Metrics	Type	Usage
1	Effective Implementation of State Safety Oversight System Metrics: • USOAP EI Scores overall • USOAP EI Scores by technical area • USOAP EI Scores by critical element	Predictive	Target
2	Progress in SSP Implementation Metrics: • Percentage of completed gap analysis questions • Percentage of implemented gap analysis questions overall • Percentage of implemented gap analysis questions by element	Predictive	Target
3	Progress in SMS Implementation Metrics: • Percentage of completed gap analysis questions by operator • Percentage of implemented gap analysis questions overall by operator • Percentage of implemented gap analysis questions by element and by operator	Predictive	Target
4	Frequency and Severity of Accidents and Incidents Metrics: • Number and distributions of occurrences by severity level (accident, serious incidents, etc.) and ADREP occurrence category • Number and distribution of fatalities by ADREP occurrence category • Occurrence per number of departures (rate) Note: Occurrences should be limited to specific categories of aircraft and operations like "aircraft above 5 700 kg operating scheduled commercial flights"	Reactive / Proactive	Target
5	Certification of Aerodromes Metrics: • Number and percentage of certified international aerodromes overall and by airspace	Predictive	Target
6	Significant Safety Concerns Metrics: • Number and duration of USOAP CMA significant safety concerns by technical area	Predictive	Target
7	Presence of notable hazardous conditions Metrics: • Number, duration and distribution of safety-related NOTAMS by Doc 8400 C-code categories	Predictive	Monitor
8	Fleet Modernization Metrics: • Average age of all registered and operated aircraft and their distribution by operator • Percentage of all registered and operated aircraft above 20 years and their distribution by operator	Predictive	Monitor
9	Effectiveness of Foreign Operator Safety Assessment Programmes Metrics: • Compliance scores by foreign and national operator	Predictive	Monitor
10	Industry Certification Metrics: • Number and percentage of operators holding industry certificates by type (IOSA, ISBAO, ISAGO etc.)	Predictive	Monitor
11	Extend of Environmental Hazards Metrics: • Average terrain elevation around airports • Percentage of METARS indicating low ceiling or visibility by month and location	Predictive	Be aware

Table 9.9 - Safety indicators
 Source: ICAO Secretariat "Safety data, performance metrics and indicators". Presented at 2015 High-level Safety Conference (HLSC 2015)

Safety Standards for Different Services: Airlines, Business Jets, Private Aircraft, Agricultural

Significant improvements in safety have been made since the start of commercial aviation. The aviation industry continues to evolve, but its top priority is the same: getting passengers to their destinations safely.

Airbus is committed to safety standards and supporting the safe operation of all its aircraft and those that fly aboard them. Therefore, Airbus works to ensure safety in different levels from the design, to the materials/manuals supplied to customers to operate and maintain the aircraft; from the worldwide services delivered in support of the aircraft's operation to the training to the flight – cabin and maintenance crews.

Airbus works with its customers to introduce safety management systems (SMS) as part of its commitment to improving global flight safety and decreasing accidents. Moreover, it is in constant contact with other aircraft manufacturers, airlines and air safety organisation around the world. Furthermore, Airbus Helicopters develops Safety Information Notices and other technical publication to provide customers with valuable information relate to the company's products and services and to improve safety control.

Airbus Helicopters customers can consult the entire library of technical publications through the company's Technical Information Publication on Internet (T.I.P.I) according to their subscription. The European Helicopter Safety Team (HEST) regularly releases guidance to improve helicopter safety.

Airbus Helicopter's activities are focused on meeting industry safety standards and supporting the safe operation of its aircraft. In 1960s, this company developed the Fenestron® shrouded tail rotor which introduced a new level of helicopter safety on the ground and in the air. It is important to share the safety information in order to continue enhancing safety and preventing accidents.

Airbus has several safety information – sharing initiative such as Project "**Destination 10X Together**", a platform upon which Airbus and operators can collaborate to propose pragmatic solutions to key identified safety issues; **Safety First** magazine, that shares lessons-learned with operators and the wider aviation community, and highlights new safety enhancements that Airbus or others have made available; "**Statistical Analysis of Commercial Aviation Accidents**". Focusing on all Western-built aircraft since the beginning of the commercial jet age, this statistical analysis of the air transport sector examines the evolution of hull-loss and fatal accident rates during revenue flights from 1958-2016.

(<http://www.airbus.com/company/safety.html#commercialjetlinersafety>).

According to IATA's Six Point Safety Strategy, a comprehensive data-driven approach to identify organizational, operational and emerging safety issues such as reducing operational

risk i.e., Loss of Control In - Flight (LOC-I), Controlled Flight Into Terrain (CFIT), lithium batteries and integrating remotely-piloted aircraft systems (RPAS) into airspace, and Runway Safety.

In addition to other areas of operational risk, IATA support consistent implementation of SMS, Flight Management System, Cabin Safety, Fatigue as well as enhance quality and compliance through their programs such as IATA Training Qualification and Initiative programs (**SAFETY STANDARDS: CHRONIC CHALLENGES AND EMERGING PRINCIPLES Ibrahim Habli**).

International aviation safety standards are the product of U.S. and EU aviation leadership. These standards are reported in ICAO Annexes and Manual, and since 2013, the number of annexes has grown to 19. Indeed, this last annex was created to improve safety systems. However, standards vary dramatically, as safety analysis is an ongoing process. Safety standards are regularly revised and updated, and typically include a mandatory part covering the necessary requirements for compliance. The creation and the process of new SARP is shown in the Figure 9.51. This entire process takes about two years from initial proposal to formal adoption of a SARP within an annex or procedure for air navigation service (PANS) manual. Since the Chicago Convention, ICAO has incorporated over 12,000 SARPs within the 19 annexes and five PANS, along with supplementary and guidance materials.

Figure 9.51 - Standard making process.

Source: Suzanne K. Kearns *Fundamental of International aviation*. Routledge, Taylor and Francis.

In accordance with ICAO Standards and Recommended Practices (SARPs), States must develop their safety oversight capabilities and implement SSPs. The Global Aviation Safety Plan (GASP) provides a strategy to enhance the implementation of the safety initiatives presented in the global aviation safety roadmap, and to assist States to meet their safety responsibilities.

However, States' priorities should be coordinated through the Regional Aviation Safety Group (RASGs) to address specific safety concerns in line with the global safety priorities and standards. In addition, States and regions should prioritize initiatives associated with the safety

performance enablers to first establish effective safety oversight and then address safety risks effectively. Furthermore, States have an obligation under the Chicago Convention to provide timely notification to ICAO when their national regulations or practices differ from those established by SARPs. By this way, States enhance safety by implementing SARPs through the development, publication and implementation of harmonized regulations at the international, regional and national levels. Similarly, the implementation of industry best practices serves to enhance standardization among service providers (ICAO -2017-2019 rod, in ICAO folder document).

RASGs serve as regional cooperative for an integrating global, regional, sub-regional, national and industry efforts in continuing to enhance aviation safety worldwide. RASGs develop and implement work programmes that support a regional performance framework for the management of safety based on the GASP. The Regional Offices of RASGs are the following:

- Bangkok: Asia and Pacific (APAC) Office
- Cairo: Middle East (MID) Office
- Dakar: Western and Central African (WACAF) Office
- Lima: South American (SAM) Office
- Mexico: North American
- Nairobi: Eastern and Southern African (ESAF) Office
- Paris: European and North Atlantic (EUR / NAT) Office

Industry stakeholders- i.e., ICAO, States, international and regional organizations, industry representatives, air navigation service providers, operators, users, aerodromes, manufactures and maintenance organizations- are involved to continually improve safety (Figure 9.51). In fact, they are encouraged to review the roadmap to identify safety initiatives and actions that support national and regional programmes and work collaboratively with the aim of enhancing safety in a coordinated manner.

General-purpose aviation includes various kinds of aircraft application: administrative, business, air-taxi, tourism, medical, life-saving, agricultural, prospecting, sporting, training, and experimental. Users of GA aircraft, in turn, can be private and corporate owners as well as state and local administrative bodies such as police or fire departments.

Safety standards for GA must be elaborated in a different manner respect the CA and military one. This feature need not have smart devices, which are expensive, and no prof. data record for GA respect the other. In any way, to improve safety in aviation safety standard should be elaborate in an international and common way.

Safety Management Failings by Cause	%
Airframe and Power Plants	32.90
Pilot/Owner and operator licensing	12.97
Past overhaul time	3.78
Past or no 100 hour inspection	3.24
Past or no annual inspection	1.62

Figure 9.52 - Percentage of failures in the practice of Safety management.
Source: Aviation: Landscape, Classification, Risk Dataaleas

IEC 61505 is one of the most widely used standard in the safety domain. One of the key objectives of the IEC 61505 standard is to provide a basis for the development of domain – specific standards and covers all safety lifecycle activities. One safety standard evolving from this is IEC 61508, which includes standards in health care, machinery, nuclear, and automotive. A recent similar and derivative of IEC 61508 in the automotive functional safety standard is ISO 26262, which provides a full coverage of the safety lifecycle activities. The ISO 26262 standard focuses on the development activities at the system, hardware, and software levels. It is important to note that safety standards underline the need to demonstrate an integration between the development processes and the safety activities.

The lack of existing and published rationale, results in making safety standards is one of the major causes of companies' mistakes in this field, due to a poor understanding of the directive that the authorities aim to assess and/or due to lack of experience, *i.e.* due to turnover of staff or lack of engagement with the standardization community. Both researchers and practitioners are working to overcome this challenge.

The lifecycles in both IEC 61508 and ISO 26262 start with a definition and an analysis of the system and environment.

Another important safety standard: the Guidelines for Development of Civil Aircraft and Systems, the ARP4754A safety assessment model, emphasizes the bidirectional relationship between the main development activities (function definition, system architecture, and implementation) and the primary safety analyses, namely: functional hazard assessment (FHA), preliminary aircraft safety assessment (PASA), preliminary system safety assessment (PSSA), system safety assessment (SSA), and aircraft safety assessment (ASA). Independence between functions, systems, or items is often used as a key risk reduction strategy.

The relationship between safety at the design stage and safety at the operational stage is illustrated in the Federal Aviation Administration's (FAA) framework for Safety Management Systems (SMS) (AC 120-92A) (FAA, 2010), depicted in the Figure 9.53:

Figure 9.53 - FAA SMS framework – Feedback between SRM and SA.

Source: FAA 2010

The feedback between SRM and SA is used for providing ongoing safety assurance, and as a means for understanding design and operational weaknesses and improving the effectiveness of the safety controls, aiming to help institutionalize a learning and evolving safety culture.

How do the FAA and EASA ban foreign airlines or remove the ban?

The European Commission with the support of the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) chairs the EU Air Safety Committee (ASC). The Commission is constantly looking at ways to improve air safety standards by working with aviation authorities worldwide. According to International Aviation Law Institute, safety standards are clearly not being met globally. As an example, ICAO has identified Latin America, Africa, and Asia as disproportionately responsible for airline accidents. Moreover, other concerns have been raised by the absence of transparency and accountability in the growing Chinese aviation market.

In Europe, the Blacklist program began, in December 2005. EU Member States identify carriers subject to operating bans within their territory. Then, the FAA and EASA, in coordination with the EU Commission evaluates on common criteria the carriers and publishes at least every three months the EU Air Safety List in the Official Journal of the European Union. This includes one list of all airlines banned from operating in Europe and another one includes airlines that are restricted from operating under certain conditions in Europe. The EU Air Safety List helps to maintain high levels of safety in the EU, but it also helps affected airlines and countries to improve their levels of safety, making the EU Air Safety List a major preventive tool. In fact, banned carriers can request a compliance review from the Commission to be removed from the list.

The European Commission in Nov. 2017 updated the list of non-European airlines that do not meet international safety standards and are therefore subject to an operating ban or

operational restrictions within the European Union. Following this last update, a total of 178 airlines are banned from EU skies:

- 172 airlines certified in 16 states, due to a lack of safety oversight by the aviation authorities from these states
- 6 individual airlines, based on safety concerns with regard to these airlines themselves

Moreover, six airlines are subject to operational restrictions and can only fly to the EU with specific aircraft types [http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_IP-17-4971_en.htm].

It is important to note that, the civil aviation authorities of Member States of the European Union are only able to inspect aircraft of airlines that land at each Union airport. Therefore, the fact that an airline is not included in the list does not automatically mean that it is compliant with all safety standards. With this in mind, it is necessary to improve the international safety standard as the assessment is made against them, and notably the standards promulgated by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO). (http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_IP-17-4971_en.htm).

EASA is therefore implementing technical cooperation projects with partner countries and regions. An example is the "Improving air transport in Central Africa" (ATA-AC) project, where EASA works with a number of African states on several aspects of aviation safety.

In light of this, there are several ways to improve safety such as the need of a new approach, better if it will be dynamic rather than static, to safety management and modelling accident analysis/prevention, which takes account of the varying risks during the different phases of flight and dynamically adapts the safety strategy accordingly. The "soft" regulation of aviation and the lack of strict enforcement also constrain improvements in safety management. These existing schemes of safety management in aviation, easily avoidable by GA aircraft owners and users, are mostly focussed on after flight. The "human" factor being the weakest link in the chain hence it should be better investigated.

The US ("country-based" approach) list is distinct from EU ("carrier-based" approach). The US approach to Blacklist, ensure that all foreign air carriers that operate to or from the U.S. are properly licensed and with safety oversight provided by a competent Civil Aviation Authority (CAA) in accordance with ICAO standards. In this regards the FAA look at the foreign CAA's capability for providing safety certification and at the foreign CAA's ability to provide continual oversight of its carriers. A country's failure to meet ICAO standards is published by the FAA. Moreover, in US the Flight Safety Foundation, which is an international non-profit organization, performs research, inspection, advice, and publishing to improve safety since 1947. This organization has helped protect everyone who benefits from air travel, everywhere in the world and works closely with other aviation organizations, including the Airline Pilots Association, Air Transport Association of America, ICAO, IATA, etc. The Foundation is in a unique position to identify global safety issues, set priorities and serve as a catalyst to address these concerns through data collection and information sharing, education, advocacy and communications.

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9.5 Security

Security is a global issue at least as much as safety because passengers can fly to airports worldwide, outside the jurisdiction of the authorities that apply stricter standards like Europe, the US or Japan. Many of these are popular tourist destinations besides important business hubs. The tendency for some airports to attract smuggling facilitates the infiltration of security threats. As for safety the regions with higher safety standards like Europe and the US could support security cooperation with other countries, especially those chosen as business or tourist travel destinations of its citizens.

Besides airport security another aspect is airways security about which each state should provide adequate warning. The shooting down of Malaysian Airways MH370 over the Donbass region of Ukraine is a tragic example of how easy it is to fail in this domain. The Ukrainian rebels were armed with shoulder-fired surface-to-air missiles that had been used to shoot down several Ukrainian military aircraft. The Ukrainian air force had restricted flying to altitudes above 9 km above the reach of such missiles. They did not know that longer range vehicle mounted surface-to-air missiles had been deployed in the region, and considered airline flights safe at typical cruise altitudes of around 10 km.

Ukrainian air force transport aircraft were also flying at those altitudes, and the missile was intended as a surprise shooting down of one of them and was advertised at internet as such. When it was realized that the target had been an airliner the internet announcement was quickly withdrawn, and a long process of denial, obstruction and destruction of evidence was started, including jamming of investigators communications near the crash site and hacking of their office in the Netherlands. Several airlines had simply decided not to overfly Ukraine, which in retrospect was a far better decision. Ensuring the security of air travel may require cooperation with intelligence services that can inform airlines on measures to safeguard their passengers, by evaluating the risks that their nationals could incur in certain regions of the world.

KEY TOPIC T9.8 ASSISTANCE PROGRAMMES TO IMPROVE AIRPORT SECURITY

Integrating security systems and operations into the planning and design of airport construction and refurbishment projects can be a very complex task. The term "security system" covers a broad range of equipment, technologies, procedures, and operational approaches that need clear and concise guidelines. The task is further complicated by an environment of evolving threats, often accompanied by the implementation of new legal or regulatory requirements and operational updates to counter the changing threat conditions. Finally, security systems are inherently difficult to plan, design, and implement when applied to airports, which are designed to facilitate the fast and efficient movement of customers and goods.

Airports tend to be in a constant state of change in terms of their physical layouts, operations, and tenants. Even as the industry has seen significant mergers of domestic and international airlines, new, alternative carriers are entering the market. And while the number of new airports being built is relatively small, many airports and terminals are being remodelled, expanded,

and upgraded. The majority of changing security requirements will be accomplished in existing facilities that are often decades old, designed at a time when the threat profile and the security environment were dramatically less stringent than they are today.

All these points emphasize that there is not a single, one-size-fits-all solution to the unique problems encountered at each airport when designing and integrating security systems, nor is there a single planning and design approach for the physical space and facilities that can be universally applied to all airports.

In response to the September 11, 2001, terrorist attacks in the United States, and with the potential for future attacks, the President signed into law the Aviation and Transportation Security Act (ATSA) on November 19, 2001. The creation of the DHS (Department of Homeland Security) by the Homeland Security Act of 2002 realigned a patchwork of government activities into a single department with the primary mission to protect US homeland, resulting in the most significant transformation of the U.S. government since World War II. There are numerous advantages to incorporating security concerns into the airport planning and design process at the earliest phases of planning and development.

Timely consideration of such needs will result in less obtrusive, less costly, and more effective and efficient security systems. Such systems are less likely to provoke passenger complaints or employee resistance and are more able to fully meet regulatory and operational requirements. Proper planning can also result in reduced manpower requirements and consequential reductions in airport and aircraft operator overhead expenses. Careful review of the prevalent threat environment, and applicable security standards and countermeasures prior to finalization of construction plans, will help determine an airport's most appropriate security posture. Such a review may also help to reduce reliance on labour-intensive procedures and equipment, which is common when an airport is required to quickly retrofit security.

Inclusion of security experts early in the planning process will result in a better coordinated and more cost-effective approach to security.

Planning for security must be an integral part of any design project undertaken at an airport, including physical structures and IT systems, among others. The most efficient and cost-effective method of instituting security measures in any facility or operation is through planning and analysis at the start of the design process, supported by monitoring and amendment of those analyses, if required, throughout the project. Selecting, constructing, or modifying a facility without considering the security implications for the protection of the general public, the facility, passengers, and airport and air carrier personnel can result in increased risk to persons and assets, as well as have a costly impact on facility modifications, or cause project delays.

The airport operator has a responsibility to provide a safe and secure operating environment and infrastructure. The extent of necessary facility protection should be examined by the local Airport Security Committee, based on the results of a comprehensive security assessment of the existing facility. High priority should be placed on protection of the aircraft from the unlawful introduction of weapons, explosives, or dangerous substances.

Perimeter protection (e.g., fences, gates, and patrols) is the first line of defence in providing physical security for personnel and property at a facility. Some more advanced technologies can reach outside the fence to identify approaching threats or may be used in an environment where there is no fence or physical barrier, such as a water boundary or swamp.

The second line of defence, and perhaps the most important, is interior controls (e.g., access control and checkpoints). The monetary value and criticality of the items and areas to be protected, the perceived threat, the vulnerability of the facility, and the cost of the controls necessary to reduce that vulnerability, will determine the extent of interior controls.

The primary objective of facility protection planning is to ensure both the integrity and continuity of operations, and the security of assets. Any area designated as requiring control for security and/or safety purposes must have identifiable boundaries for that area to be recognized and managed. In some cases, boundaries must meet a regulatory requirement to prevent or deter access to an area. In many instances, however, boundaries may not be hard physical barriers, such as fences or walls; they might instead be painted lines, lines marked and monitored by electronic signals, grass or pavement edges, natural boundaries such as water or tree lines, or simply geographic coordinates. The distinctions between these different areas must be understood by the design team, such that they are clear on how the physical design of space and structures relates to the physical and virtual boundaries.

In order to implement security at an airport, it is necessary to understand and quantify the degrees of security into three key issues:

1. What is the threat to the airport?
2. What is an airport's level of vulnerability relative to each element of that threat?
3. To what extent is the threat/vulnerability likely to change, and why?

A vulnerability assessment is an excellent tool and the primary means for determining the extent to which a facility may require security enhancements. It serves to bring security considerations into the mix early in the design process, which reduces the risk of a more expensive retrofit after the design or construction has begun. Many tools and methodologies are available; all are subjective to varying degrees, largely because, in every case, one must first have a thorough understanding of both short- and long-term threats in order to understand and respond to the three key issues noted above. With this in mind, the planning and design team's response to these points will be a recommendation of a combination of security measures, both physical and procedural, to provide enhanced security and ease of movement for both passengers and employees.

The Airport Security Committee may offer recommendations that consider the following:

- Known threat(s) specific to the airport and/or to the airlines serving it;
- History of criminal or disruptive incidents in the area surrounding the facility, but not primarily directed toward airport operations;

- Domestic and international threats and the general integrity of the transportation system;
- Facility location, size, and configuration;
- Extent of exterior lighting;
- Presence of physical barriers;
- Presence of access control and alarm monitoring systems, closed-circuit television systems, and other electronic monitoring systems;
- Presence and capabilities of onsite staff, law enforcement, and/or security patrols;
- Other locally determined pertinent factors, such as general aviation, commercial operations, and intermodal transportation facilities.

Airport and aircraft operators provide protection through a combination of mobile patrols or fixed posts staffed by police, other security officers, or contract uniformed personnel; security systems and devices; lockable building entrances and gates; and cooperation of local law enforcement agencies. The degree of normal and special protection is determined by completion of a vulnerability assessment and a crime prevention assessment.

The local police department may collect and compile information about criminal activity on or against property under the control of the airport, provide crime prevention information programs to the occupant and federal agencies upon request, and conduct crime prevention assessments in cooperation with appropriate law enforcement agencies.

In addition to physical protection, airport operators also need to keep records of incidents, personnel access, or other activities. Some of the records (such as personnel access) may be collected automatically. Recordkeeping needs, including some video applications, may affect IT systems, cable designs, and equipment locations, as well as require secure data storage. These needs should be coordinated early in the design process.

It is important to consider security systems and procedures from the beginning of the design phase through completion, so that space allocation, appropriate cabinetry and furnishings, conduit runs and system wiring, heavy-duty materials, reinforcing devices, seismic requirements, and other necessary construction requirements are provided in the original plans.

The first step toward integrating security into airport planning, design, or major renovation is the analysis and determination of the airport's general security requirements. The range of available options, configurations, and functions is very broad. There is no single solution, and with very little examination, it is apparent that there are a large number of issues that must be addressed before a best approach and optimal solution can be achieved at any given airport.

The place to start is defining operational requirements, and most common views on the development of a Concept of Operations characterize the process in terms of eight basic questions:

- *What does the project involve: an update of existing infrastructure, a move or expansion into new facilities, operational reorganization, new interfaces with airport departments and government agencies, or mutual aid?*

- *Why is this project happening? What is the impetus: system integration, physical expansion, growth forecasts, outdated technology, new regulatory requirements, inadequate or failing infrastructure, or administrative restructuring?*
- *Who are the users and stakeholders, both internal and external to the organization? What are their operational goals, and what information do they require?*
- *What infrastructure exists? What threats and vulnerabilities exist?*
- *Which new technologies will be most appropriate to best serve the different priorities and interactions among user groups?*
- *What human factors need to be accommodated, such as ergonomics, lighting and noise levels, sight lines, design factors for dealing with multiple technologies and/or multiple events, and certain staffing and training criteria?*
- *What is the realistic budget and where it is coming from? What are the additional related costs, such as those for staffing and long-term training, operations, and maintenance?*

Asking the question “what?” seeks to identify the depth and breadth of security functionality to meet appropriate user requirements. What array of services is the facility expected to offer? What information is it expected to provide, to whom, and for what purposes? This can include a range of points, all needing early identification, as they will drive the detailed approaches to planning and design. What systems and services are needed to meet the user requirements? This is limited to a high-level definition of systems in operational terms rather than in technical terms. Unless there is a specific reason for identifying details of a system, this should initially be generalized. The reasons to identify a new or upgraded system or service may include: a legacy system may exist and continue to be used; or the owner of the facility may have other operational, legal, policy, budgetary, physical space or contractual constraints that limit the ability to make changes to or replace a system. Developing a description of the appropriate level of functionality requirements will serve as the foundation for more detailed design of the systems.

Answering “Why?” will lead to identification of the objectives of the security system project. Why is it needed? For airport expansion and growth projections or consolidation of operational and administrative functions? For outdated or failing technologies and infrastructure, or possibly new regulatory requirements that address operational gaps and user needs? Or, perhaps, for all of the above? As a subset to this, the answer should also identify operational and administrative issues, policies, and constraints affecting the facility, which inform the planning process in determining how the project will be executed to achieve its objectives.

This emphasizes the importance of having all stakeholders engaged in development of the Concept of Operations. The comparison and contrast of views between the executive level and the operational level should identify gaps in the objectives; identify conflicts and redundancies to be addressed and resolved; allow for the identification and resolution of differing levels of criticality and priorities; and provide a baseline for establishing near-term and long-term objectives.

“Who?” addresses the identity of stakeholders, e.g., individual or organizational, internal and external to the security system and its operational elements. It should address the user

requirements as classes or descriptions of users who are meaningful to the organization. In addition, it should include the operational requirements necessary for their primary responsibilities. This also begins to identify the support activities of stakeholders that arise beyond the anticipated operational activities—who owns the facility, who maintains it, who manages and pays for it—thus, also identifying persons or offices who, while not primary users, significantly influence how the project is ultimately designed and operated.

It should also provide the initial identification of the types of personnel, and the number and type of functions that will be located in the facility or interact with it in some form; identify the level and priorities of personnel or organizations that will be engaged in the process during design and development; and identify at a high level the roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders with a definition of their operational interactions, both internal and external.

For any security system, a typical stakeholder list might include the following groups:

- Management/executive staff;
- Communications staff/dispatchers;
- Law enforcement, contract security;
- Airside operations;
- Landside operations;
- Curbside and ground transportation;
- Airport facilities and maintenance;
- Airport development/engineering;
- IT;
- Risk Management;
- Air Traffic Control;
- Airlines;
- Military joint use;
- Adjacent commercial/industrial parks;
- Local/state/regional government;
- Surrounding community.

To answer “when?” one should realize that the development of a security system may not be an isolated project. It will frequently be a part of a larger effort such as a new or renovated terminal and have an effect on many other related activities. It is essential to have a clear but flexible schedule to allow for coordination with related programs, conflict avoidance, and incorporation of opportunities for collaboration with other projects or actions. Often, the timing may be driven by a need to meet regulatory, policy, or other procedural requirements, the nuances of which must be thoroughly understood as part of the driving force behind development.

A preliminary project schedule should reflect at least the following five periods:

- Concept development period;
- Pre-design phase;

- Planning and design period;
- Construction or implementation period, including changeover;
- Useful life of the facility past construction or implementation – This element is often overlooked, but it can establish a basis for later planning for anticipated upgrades, replacement, or expansion, all of which must be reflected in long-term planning and budget considerations.

During planning and design phases, this baseline schedule will be refined and enhanced by the design team based on budgets, resource availability, project scale, and other evolving factors.

Addressing where to locate a new facility can become somewhat complex, especially when the facility has special requirements, or future moves, additions, or changes are planned. These can include different requirements for physical separation or proximity to another facility. For example, regulatory or operational limitations on the facility site may reflect requirements for setbacks from another area for reasons of safety or security; limits in the amount or suitability of the space; infrastructure constraints; adequacy of IT capabilities in alternate locations; budget considerations; threats and vulnerabilities relative to its operations; and access requirements.

“How?” addresses how the facility can be successfully developed and implemented, based on the information developed throughout the process. It includes such issues as funding, personnel, integration of existing and planned infrastructure, architectural constraints, coordination of planning and design concerns, and a list of other locally unique activities and assets to be accommodated in order for the project to move forward. The resolution of “how” is a particularly critical element of the Concept of Operations as it establishes each sequential set of activities, to be set in place for the guidance to be fully effective.

This will vary depending on the particulars of each project, but, in general, should include a rough order of magnitude of “soft” costs such as planning, design, and consulting fees required to develop the project; a similar rough order of magnitude of the “hard” costs such as capital expenses for construction of facilities, IT and communications infrastructure expansion, equipment, labour, and related costs; internal and external professional resources necessary to complete and support the project, such as maintenance and training; and a proposed schedule of steps to be undertaken throughout the process, and milestones to be accomplished.

A key element of the Concept of Operations for the development of an airport security system is a Risk Assessment, the principle components of which are a determination of threats and vulnerabilities. The standard risk formula is $\text{risk} = \text{threat} \times \text{vulnerability} \times \text{consequences}$ [$R = T \times V \times C$]. In fact, a risk assessment is necessary in the general development of airports and other mission critical facilities and should be a standard element of the early supporting activities. The risk assessment can establish some starting points: what systems are in place, what changes are planned, what their strengths and vulnerabilities are with respect to a range of likely threats, and how the security planning and design process can address them in an

optimal operational and cost-effective manner. The actions taken in response to the risk assessment will often include measures designed to increase the ability of a facility to respond to an event or multiple simultaneous events, as well as provide increased safety and security measures as the irregular operations evolve. As some of these measures can increase costs for the development of the security system, it is essential that the assessment provide a clear definition of the risks and vulnerabilities to be addressed during planning and design.

The key elements of a threat and vulnerability assessment include the following:

- Develop a clear perspective of the interrelationships among the facility, the organization, and its assets. Assets include property, systems, structures, business, information/data, and people.
- Identify the threats and vulnerabilities and the risks associated with each. An outside party, preferably a party with expertise in the risk assessment process, can do this initially. The approach used by the outside party may vary from the relatively benign to the very aggressive. Regardless of the approach, the external assessment should be combined with information on the range and probability of threats and vulnerabilities known to the facility owner.
- Quantify the probabilities associated with each of the identified risks. To the greatest extent possible, the probabilities should be based on factual data. Probabilities of risk can be gathered from a range of sources, including local, state, and national agencies that have experience with events and incidents.

Once a set of risks has been identified, planners should quantify the value of losses associated with each risk. This includes financial costs, costs due to loss of use of a facility or function, cost to recover, loss of life, loss of earnings or revenue, and loss of good will and trust. The value of a loss resulting in direct relation to the risk needs to be measured against an established system of values.

Threats and vulnerabilities change over time, as does an organization's response to both. A risk assessment should not be a one-time activity, but should be revisited when experiencing major organizational, facility, or operational changes. An airport operator should not go more than five years between thorough threat and vulnerability assessments; more often if changing conditions warrant.

Situational Awareness

Situational awareness is the perception of events and activities in real or near-real time seen by an individual or group, and their understanding of how those events and activities may be related. More simply stated, one should know what is going on from moment to moment so that the Security Operations Centre (SOC) operator can react, if required.

Situational awareness can be developed through a number of different means. It can include:

- Direct observation of an event or situation;

- Observation reported by third parties;
- Observation through CCTV systems;
- Observation through sensing systems (e.g., fire alarms, security alarms);
- Observation related by news and media outlets.

Too much information, particularly if it is irrelevant or distracting from a critical event, can be detrimental to effective decision making by the SOC operator. Excess information can place such a high demand on human operators or responders that they cannot absorb or process it all and may miss or misinterpret critical points.

This is not to suggest that available information should be limited. An SOC should have access to information where it is appropriate and useful to decision making. Several approaches can be taken to avoid overloading the SOC without losing vital information:

- Disperse blocks of information to different people or teams, who filter critical data to a manager or team charged with decision-making.
- Establish levels of criticality for information or alarm conditions, such that more urgent concerns are elevated for attention sooner.
- Provide a smaller number of points to focus on, while allowing different information streams to be viewed. An example of this is a video wall with a limited number of screens but a high number of video feeds, allowing the SOC operator to select and change their primary views as the situation develops.

Key considerations and elements of effective situational awareness include:

- Good quality information delivered in a timely manner;
- Where situational awareness drives organizational response to an event or activity, reliable bi-directional communications are essential;
- Flexibility to allow for changing conditions;
- The level of situational awareness required of the SOC staff drives the information sources that need to be delivered.

9.6 Fair Trade

Trade disputes are not unknown in aviation at the highest level of the World Trade Organization (WTO). After having initially dismissed Airbus as a 'government aircraft', when it realized this was a serious competitor, Boeing tried to prove its claim at the WTO. The United States on behalf of Boeing filled a complaint that Airbus was subsidized by European governments since it received low interest loans for aircraft development, refundable from subsequent sales. The counter argument was that Boeing benefitted from US Air Force and NASA contracts, for example the Boeing 707 was based on the military transport C-135 and KC-135 tanker. The Air Force owns factories that it can lend to industry at nominal or zero cost; the NASA contracts cover 100% of costs whereas in some EU research programs the industry pays 50%. It is unclear whether the protracted litigation was of benefit to anyone, certainly not

to airlines that want competition between Airbus and Boeing, not a monopoly of either of them.

The reverse process occurred with the EU on behalf of Airbus filling a complaint with the WTO about the US export-import bank low rate loans in support of the exports of Boeing aircraft. The case was won by European side that was allowed to apply penalties as a compensation but may have elected not to do so. The response on the US side was to change the export support law, to one protecting employment in the US and discouraging delocalization of industrial activity abroad. The practical effect in terms of 'export subsidies' was the same except that they now covered a range of industrial sectors wider than just aviation. An example that WTO rulings can be sidestepped by new legislation that aggravates rather reduces the trading inequalities. At present the future of the export-import bank in the US is under discussion in spite of the support of Boeing because it gives loans to foreign airlines competing with US airlines. In the meantime, Airbus has plentifully refunded European governments for the former development loans and is healthy enough not to need them anymore.

The Airbus-Boeing duopoly of large airliners is not alone to come to WTO fillings, since the Canadian government on behalf of Bombardier has accused Brazil of subsidizing Embraer. More recently the tables were turned around in the context of the sale of C-Series in the US at low prices after major cash injections of the Quebec government into Bombardier, that are suspect of financing dumping. Bombardier noted among other things that more than 50% by value of a C-series is American, and that percentage will go higher when the production line moves from Canada to the US as part of the deal with Airbus. Even some Airbus aircraft with American engines have more than 50% American content due not only to propulsion but also several other systems.

Boeing maximizes value in final production that takes place at three sites; the third in a southern state whose laws give less bargaining power than the trade unions have in Seattle. Airbus maximizes value at its partners and has the main two production lines in Europe plus final assembly lines in China and the US, the latter increasing local content. There is substantial international content both in the Airbus and Boeing aircraft, often starting with engine options and continuing with a worldwide supply chain. The airlines have no interest in trade disputes and the Boeing-Airbus competition suits well their bargaining power when buying new aircraft as the Bombardier-Embraer competition did. The link Airbus-Bombardier and Boeing-Embraer if they strengthen would mean that: (i) for more than 150 seats there would still be the choice of Airbus or Boeing and likewise for jets of less than 100 seats a choice between Bombardier and Embraer; (ii) in the range 100 to 150 seats the choice might narrow down from 4 to 2, extending the duopoly to almost all the jet airliner market.

KEY TOPIC T9.9 FAIR TRADE

T9.9.1 International Content in Airbus, Boeing, Bombardier and Embraer Airliners

Aircraft manufacturing is arguably the most contested industry in international trade governance.

The two lead actors in this topic are Boeing and Airbus for long-range aircraft, and Bombardier and Embraer and others for regional aircraft. Ever since Airbus emerged some 40 years ago to challenge Boeing's position as the world's dominant aircraft manufacturer, governments have been accusing one another of illegitimately propping up their respective national champions, while simultaneously professing their own innocence in providing support.

The traditional tools of trade governance are particularly ill-suited to aircraft manufacturing. The basic logic behind trade enforcement mechanisms, whether pursued unilaterally or multilaterally through the WTO, is an attempt to "level the playing field," or to correct the market for the distortions of government interventions. The problem is, when it comes to aircraft manufacturing, there has never been anything close to a perfectly competitive, distortion-free market: It is politics and subsidies all the way down. Not only are subsidies on the production side, but governments are also the most important consumers of aircraft, buying both military planes and consumer planes for publicly-owned national airlines.

Thus, the aircraft market consists of governments subsidizing production by their national champions, then lobbying other governments to buy their planes, often linking these procurement decisions to diplomatic relationships. There is not a good methodology to reasonably price this subsidy. Moreover, this points to the larger problem in trying to arrive at a "fair" outcome in the aircraft subsidy complaints: Given how governments are so deeply and fundamentally involved in the industry, asking what a jet would cost in the absence of government distortions to the market is an impossible question.

Furthermore, the aircraft manufacturing industry shows both the strengths and limits of the rules-based, legal approach to global economic governance. The WTO has made a valiant attempt to discipline some of the more direct subsidies governments provide to their aircraft manufacturers. But the legal record shows it has been a long, drawn-out fight, with no signs of easing. And the institution is not cut out to weigh into the informal, indirect subsidies provided by defence contracts, let alone adjudicate how much diplomatic pressure is appropriate in pushing for a jet sale.

Meanwhile, looming on the horizon is a bigger and potentially far messier aircraft subsidy fight. Recently, China's COMAC, a state-owned aircraft manufacturer, completed a successful first flight test of its new jetliner, designed to compete with Boeing and Airbus. For now, neither Boeing nor Airbus wants to take an aggressive stance against COMAC, as the two Western companies don't want to risk losing out on lucrative sales to China's domestic airlines. But ultimately, they, along with their government backers, will need a strategy for dealing with this new challenger. Perhaps this will finally prompt Boeing and Airbus to aim their attacks away from one another and toward a common threat, just as Siemens and Alstom recently joined forces to take on the China Railway Rolling Stock Corporation, China's state-backed train maker that's winning more and more contracts overseas. In the meantime, expect the aircraft subsidy feuds to continue; at the moment Boeing seems to have lost the battle, but the war is far from over.

T9.9.2 Europe/ Airbus versus US/Boeing at the WTO

Before the US took on Canadian subsidies to Bombardier, it had long been decrying the "launch aid" European governments gave Airbus to help it bring new models to market. The Europeans, for their part, complained about the indirect subsidies Boeing received in terms of inflated defence procurement contracts and NASA research expenditures. The two sides reached something of a truce in a 1992 agreement that set limits on subsidies, but that deal broke down about a decade ago, and since then the disputants have been fighting it out in a series of seemingly never-ending World Trade Organization (WTO) disputes.

The following Figure 9.54 shows the data of the last 10 years where the U.S. has pursued a case before the World Trade Organization (WTO) against illegal European subsidies for Airbus.

The US allege that the low interest loans have given Airbus an unfair advantage, enabling it to capture 50% of the global market for large commercial airplanes, at America's expense, when in fact Airbus has repaid all loans with a profit to the European governments that acted as lenders.

The European Union has filed baseless counterclaims against the US based on military and NASA contracts. It is time for both sides to meet their global trade obligations and eliminate the \$22 billion of illegal subsidies the WTO has said must go.

Figure 9.54 - Aerospace Subsidies Dispute Timetable
Source: Boeing

T9.9.3 Canada/Bombardier versus Brazil/Embraer at the WTO

Brazil and Embraer have also brought their complaints against Bombardier, which are very similar to the grievances alleged by Boeing, to the WTO, in a case that is still pending. All in all, aircraft manufacturing is arguably the most contested industry in international trade governance.

The Airbus-Boeing duopoly of large airliners is not alone to come to WTO filings, since the Canadian government on behalf of Bombardier has accused Brazil of subsidizing Embraer.

Therefore, the main problem between Canada / Bombardier and Brazil / Embraer centres on a conflict over the Canadian government's aid to Bombardier. The aim is to prevent the poisoning of bilateral relations, which recently recovered completely from the impact of a similar struggle in the past.

The conflict has reached the point that the Canadian government threatened to use hundreds of millions of dollars in trade sanctions against Brazil for the use of short-term loans for Embraer, a direct competitor of Bombardier in the global aerospace market.

T9.9.4 The Saga of the C-Series Scale to Eastern Airlines

The Bombardier C Series is a family of narrow-body, twin-engine, medium-range jet airliners by Canadian manufacturer Bombardier Aerospace. The C Series models are the CS100 and the CS300, which have been built with leading-edge technology and systems integration, advanced materials and aerodynamics. They have been designed specifically for the 100- to 150-seat single-aisle market. They are very efficient and economic aircraft, thanks to significant reductions in fuel burn and operating costs. The CS100 aircraft carries between 100 and 135 passengers and offers a great flexibility for many airline business models. On the other hand, the CS300 aircraft is a good solution for mid-sized markets with up to 160 passengers per flight. The CS100 and the CS300 have a range of 3100 and 3300 nautical miles respectively.

According to Bombardier market forecast, in the next years China will be a region with one of the largest fleets in the 60-to 150-seat segment. It is expected that the passenger traffic in cities away from the main hubs of Beijing, Shanghai and Guangzhou grows significantly, which is an opportunity for convincing airlines to opt for the 110-150 seat C Series planes.

Nowadays, Bombardier has a strong presence in the Asian-Pacific region, with 40 airlines that operate 330 Bombardier regional and small single-aisle aircraft, which a great success in the 100-70 150-segment. The launch customer for the C Series in Asia was Korean Air, who ordered 10 CS300 with 10 options. Korean Air have taken delivery of two CS300 aircraft to date and had their first revenue flight from Seoul to Ulsan on January 20, 2018. Therefore, one of the objectives of Bombardier will be keep focusing in the China market and obtaining deliveries from Chinese airlines.

In the following Figure 9.55, it can be seen the number of C series orders in recent years:

C series orders

Figure 9.55 - C series orders, cumulative by year

Source: Bombardier web page

As it can be seen from the previous image, the number of orders of the C series has increased in recent years. The first Bombardier C series deliveries were carried out in 2016, five CS100 to Deutsche Lufthansa and two CS300 to airBaltic. In 2017, a total of 24 C series aircraft were delivered, eight CS100 and seven CS300 to Deutsche Lufthansa, seven CS300 to airBaltic and two CS300 to Korean Air.

In 2016, Bombardier and Delta Air Lines announced that they had executed a firm agreement for the sale and purchase of 75 CS100 aircraft, which meant the largest C series order, as it can be seen in the next Figure 9.56:

Figure 9.56 - C series orders and deliveries by customer
 Source: Wikipedia web page

In addition, in 2017 Airbus and Bombardier signed an agreement through which Airbus would manufacture the C series. Being a part of the model manufactured in US soil, Bombardier will avoid the tariffs of 300% recently imposed by the US Government on C series airplanes. In addition, it will share resources, costs and technology with Airbus, which will be a relief for its deteriorating finances.

This agreement will be very beneficial for both sides, since it will allow Airbus to compete against Boeing, which is its biggest rival. The agreement will be continued even though Boeing lost the case.

The orders from the C-Series pale by comparison with the 10,000 deliveries of the B737 and 8,500 of the A320, both much longer in the market.

9.7 Open Markets

Major exceptions to open markets in civil aviation do exist, generally uncontested. Perhaps the most visible and long-standing is that the Japanese airlines tended to buy Boeing aircraft more often than from Airbus, though the difference has reduced over time. The reason is the Japan to the US trade surplus, that the Japanese government tries to reduce through various measures, including airliner purchases. The Japanese airlines are happy and willing to oblige by buying Boeing aircraft, as long as it is in the national interest, but not otherwise. A possibly isolated instance of the latter was the indictment of former Prime Minister Kokuei Tanaka for prompting some Japanese airlines to buy Lockheed Tristars instead of other American widebodies. When this became known through the enquiry of the US congress on the Lockheed bankruptcy, Tanaka was still prime minister and refused to resign; his party, that had majority in parliament, voted him and itself out of power with a non-confidence vote.

Boeing has consolidated its hold in the Japanese market by including Japanese industry in the production of its aircraft; it has gone further with Japan financing part of the development of the B787 together with some American states. The Japanese have limited their indigenous production to regional aircraft or smaller, for example the Nanc YS-11 in the past and the Mitsubishi MRJ-100 and Honda business jet at present. China has apparently tried to use airliner purchases as a political instrument, depending mostly on its relations with the US, buying more Boeing aircraft during the up periods and less in the down periods. The Airbus final assembly line for the A320 in China is a more stable prospect. It is also possible to find the opposite example of Japan, with Italy and other producing assemblies for Boeing and Airbus.

The times when the US market was closed to Airbus are long gone, and most airlines make the most they can of the Airbus-Boeing competition. In the past Boeing could charge high prices for the Boeing 747, when it was the only jumbo available, possibly financing the rest of the range. More recently in the twin-aisle long range market the preference of major airlines for a twin-engine instead of the Airbus A380 may have allowed Boeing to charge high prices for the B777X stretch. In most sectors of the airline market the Boeing-Airbus duopoly is desirable not only to give airlines bargaining power to keep prices in check; it also promotes technological progress and efficient air travel ultimately for the benefit of airline passengers.

The development of a modern long-range airliner costs over 10 B€ over 5 years. An aircraft manufacturer needs big, sustained profits to finance the development and production until break-even is reached. Bank loans at commercial rates of interest are hardly viable when break-even is 10 or more years away.

The Boeing 787 is an example. Optimistic predictions put development at 10 B\$ over 3 years. At the end of an 8 years development program Boeing had accumulated a 30B\$ debt. Despite favourable conditions from the US states where the facilities are located and a sizeable contribution (20-40%) from Japan.

The B787 was the most successful airliner programme ever, with over 1,000 orders before entering service. Boeing is not stating when the 30 B\$ debt will be covered. With unit prices of around 300 M\$ a 10% profit percentage of 30 M\$ a piece would cover the debt with 1,000 sales, less than those already achieved.

The development of the A380 costs over 16 B€. It is not clear if it will ever be recovered or even if its low rate production is self-sustaining. Yet with a backlog of more than 5,000 aircraft costing 100-450 M\$ each, both companies can survive some large holes in their balance sheets.

KEY TOPIC T9.10 OPEN MARKETS

T9.10.1 The Japanese Market Captive of Airbus

For more than half a century, Boeing has been the top provider of commercial jetliners to Japanese airlines and a major supplier of military equipment and aircraft to the Japanese Ministry of Defence (JMoD). Boeing opened its doors in Japan in 1953, just two years after Kawasaki Heavy Industries and Showa Aircraft were contracted by the US government to maintain US military aircraft, a move that restarted Japan's aircraft industry.

The US's relationship with Japanese industry started in 1956, when Mitsubishi Heavy Industries commenced the licensed production of the North American F-86 Sabre Jet fighter. The relationship continued to grow over the coming years in both the defence and commercial areas, and Boeing expanded the number of programs on which it collaborated with Japanese Industry, as well as the number of partners. During those years, Boeing transferred new technology to Japan and, in turn, Japan used that acquired technology in support of Boeing programs.

Today, Boeing retains deep supplier, customer and partner relationships across Japanese government, industry and civil society.

In the following sections, it will be described the relationship between Boeing and Japan in the military and commercial areas in the past years. The following Figure 9.57 summarizes this relationship:

Figure 9.57 - Relationship between US industry, including Boeing and Japan timeline
Source: Boeing

Commercial Airplanes

Japan has long served as one of the largest financial international markets for Boeing Commercial Airplanes. Over the past 50 years, Japanese carriers have ordered more than 970 Boeing jetliners, and Japan is one of Boeing's largest twin-aisle markets.

In the past decade, nearly 80 percent of the commercial aircraft ordered by Japanese customers have been Boeing products. Japan is the single biggest customer for the 787. Japan Airlines (JAL) purchased more 747s than any other airline customer and All Nippon Airways (ANA) is the largest international customer for the 767 family of airplanes. Together, Japan's major carriers make Japan one of the largest international customers for the 777, with more than 100 ordered.

Japan also plays an important role in launching major new programs. Japan's Nippon Cargo Airlines, together with Cargolux, launched the 747-8 Freighter in 2005. In addition, Japan Airlines and All Nippon Airways were among a number of carriers with whom Boeing held intensive discussions to define and develop the 777 configurations. All Nippon Airways was also a 777 launch customer and became the first Asian operator. Moreover, Japan airlines served as launch customers for the 767-300, 767-300 Boeing Converted Freighter and 737-700ER.

In 2004, All Nippon Airways (ANA) launched the 787 Dreamliner with 50 orders, which represented the largest launch order for a Boeing commercial airplane at the time. In addition, Japan Airlines (JAL) selected the 787 Dreamliner as its next-generation mid-sized twin-aisle airplane and joined the 787 launch team with an initial order of 35 airplanes. All Nippon Airways (ANA) and Japan Airlines (JAL) both collaborated with Boeing in the development of the Dreamliner, sharing their expertise in passenger amenities, airplane performance and

aircraft maintenance. All Nippon Airways and Japan airlines became the first customers to fly the 787 Dreamliner in September 2011 and April 2012, respectively. Since then, both airlines have made incremental 787 orders that include all members of the Dreamliner family: 787-8, 787-9 and 787-10. Japan has more than 90 787s flying today, more than any other country.

Military Airplanes

Boeing Defence, Space and Security and Japan's Ministry of Defence (MoD) have a long history of working together to meet Japan's defence needs. This cooperation dates back to 1956 and the licensed production of the F-86 Sabre by Mitsubishi Heavy Industries (MHI). Boeing continued collaboration with the Japanese industry through licensed production of the Vertol 107 helicopter and the F-4 Phantom.

In 1981, the first non-US delivery of 10 F-15 Eagles began under the Peace Eagle program. Four more F-15s were delivered to Japan in 1983, and in total, Mitsubishi Heavy Industries (MHI) built nearly 200 F-15J/DJ Eagles under licensed production. Today, Japan operates the second largest fleet of F-15s in the world. Boeing is currently involved with Mitsubishi Heavy Industries in upgrading the F-15J/DJ aircraft to fulfil Japan's desired mission effectiveness well into the 21st century.

The F-1 and F-2 fighters developed by Japan, involved the American companies and technology transfer to the US.

Defence, Space and Security has provided many other defence solutions to Japan's Self-Defence Forces. In 1978, the Japan Maritime Self-Defence Force first placed orders for Harpoon anti-ship missiles and, currently, it is second only to the US Navy in terms of the number of Harpoon missiles in its inventory.

Boeing began delivering CH-47 Chinook helicopters to the Japan Air and Ground Self-Defence Forces in 1984. Since then, Kawasaki Heavy Industries (KHI), under license by Boeing, has manufactured and delivered 100 CH-47s to Japanese forces, providing Japan with the world's second largest operational Chinook fleet.

Other deliveries provided by Boeing have been 13 AH-64D Apache Longbows, with the first of them delivered in March 2006, through a license agreement with Subaru. Boeing has also delivered four KC-767 tankers and four Airborne Warning and Control System (AWACS) aircraft to JASDF and continues to provide ongoing support and upgrades for these platforms.

Boeing Partners in Japan

Around 150 Japanese companies are suppliers to Boeing across its commercial and defence product lines. Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, Kawasaki Heavy Industries and Subaru produce components for Boeing commercial models and manage licensed production of Boeing defence products (Figure 9.58). These companies designed and developed 35% of the 787 Dreamliner airframe structure, including the main wing box (the first time that the design and build of such a critical part was entrusted outside the company). Together, they also supply 16

percent and 21 percent of the 767 and 777 airframes, respectively, and have contracted with Boeing to provide 21 percent of the 777X.

Figure 9.58 - Japanese Industry Work-Share Growth
Source: Boeing

Other components provided by Japanese firms include tires, gear boxes, trailing-edge flaps, lavatories, flight deck interiors, altimeters, actuators, valves and video entertainment systems. In addition, Toray Industries is providing composite materials for the 787.

Boeing's partnerships in Japan extend well beyond the above examples. In fact, the company has meaningful collaborations in the technology and environmental areas with Japanese universities, research institutions and various government agencies.

In addition, Boeing also maintains close relationships with the Government of Japan's Ministry of Land, Infrastructure Transport and Tourism (MLIT) and the Japan Civil Aviation Bureau (JCAB) to help ensure ever safer air transportation. The Ministry of Economy, Trade and Industry (METI) is another key partner in terms of Boeing's collaboration with Japan's aerospace industry, as the Aeronautics and Space Research Agency (JAXA).

Airbus in Japan

In recent years, Airbus has significantly strengthened its position in the Japanese commercial aircraft market. Japan airlines' major order for the A350 XWB was an important breakthrough and it was soon followed by orders from All Nippon Airways Holdings for the A320 family and, early in 2016, for the A380. The first of All Nippon Airways' three A380s it is expected to be delivered in 2019. In addition, over 20 major Japanese companies work with Airbus on various commercial aircraft programmes. For example, the A380's forward and rear cargo doors come from by Mitsubishi Heavy Industries while the vertical tail plane's (VTP) leading and trailing edge are manufactured by Fuji Heavy Industries.

In relation with defence and space, Airbus is contributing to Japan's successful space sector by supplying state-of-the-art components for Japanese satellites. Moreover, some of Airbus space technologies were developed in Japan.

T9.10.2 The Japanese Market Captive of Airbus

The commercial air transport industry of the last 20 years has been characterized by the duopoly competition between Boeing, the American aircraft manufacturer, and Airbus, the European aircraft manufacturer.

In relation to orders and deliveries, there has been a strong competition between both companies, as it can be seen in the following figures:

Figure 9.59 - Airbus vs. Boeing orders
Source: Wikipedia web page

In terms of orders, during the decade of 1980s and 1990s, it's clear that Boeing deliveries considerably exceeded that of Airbus. By 2000, little difference remained between both companies. However, during the last few years Airbus has received more aircraft orders than Boeing.

In terms of deliveries (Figure 9.60), Boeing has a clear lead against Airbus in the 14 years, from 1989 to 2002. After that, Airbus started to overcome Boeing during the next years.

Figure 9.60 Airbus vs. Boeing deliveries
Source: Wikipedia web page

If it is compared Airbus and Boeing orders between similar aircrafts, the following results are obtained:

A320 family vs. B737 family

The Airbus A320 family consists of short-to medium-range, narrow body, commercial passenger twin-engine jet airliners manufactured by Airbus that was released in the 1980s. The family includes the A318, A319, A320 and A321. The aircraft family can accommodate up to 236 passengers and has a range of 3100 to 12000 km, depending on model. The A320 family competes directly with the Boeing 737 family, a short-to medium-range twinjet narrow-body airliner developed and manufactured by Boeing that was released in the 1960s. The B737 family is composed of several models with capacities from 85 to 215 passengers.

Figure 9.61 - A320 vs. B737 deliveries
Source: Wikipedia web page

In the previous image (Figure 9.61), it is compared the A320 family and the B737 family deliveries of past years. Taking into account orders and deliveries, the 737 series is the best-selling commercial jetliner in history, with a total of 14543 orders and about 9895 deliveries. In comparison, Airbus has delivered 7979 A320 series aircraft and has received 8125 orders. The B737 has been 55 years on the market and the A320 'only' 40 years.

A350 family vs. B787 family

The Airbus A350 is a family of long-range, twin-engine wide-body jet airliners developed by Airbus. The family includes the A350-800, A350-900 and A350-1000. The aircraft variants can accommodate 280 to 366 passengers and has a range of up to 9,700nm. The A350 family competes directly with the Boeing 787 family, which is a long-haul, mid-size widebody, twin-engine jet airliner made by Boeing. The family variants can seat 242 to 335 passengers and their range varies from 7,000nm to 8300nm, depending on the model.

In the following graphics, it can be seen a comparison between A350 and B787 orders (Figure 9.62) and deliveries (Figure 9.63), cumulative by year:

Figure 9.62 - A350 vs. B787 orders, cumulative by year
Source: Wikipedia web page

Figure 9.63 - A350 vs. B787 deliveries, cumulative by year
Source: Wikipedia web page

As it can be seen from the previous images, the B787 has a clear advantage against the A350 with respect to orders and deliveries due to the late response of Airbus to the Boeing challenge. However, it is important to note that there is an important gap in release dates, since the A350 was released in 2015 while the B787 was released in 2007.

A380 vs. B747

The Airbus A380 is a double-deck, wide-body, four-engine jet airliner manufactured by Airbus. It is the world's largest passenger airliner with a capacity to accommodate 525 to 853 passengers and with a range of 8500nm. The A380 compete with the Boeing 747, the next largest airliner. Depending on the model, the B747 can accommodate 416 passengers to 660 passengers and has a range of 7260nm.

In the following graphs, it can be seen a comparison between A380 and B747 orders (Figure 9.64) and deliveries (Figure 9.65), cumulative by year:

Figure 9.64 - A380 and B747 orders, cumulative by year
Source: Wikipedia web page

The previous image shows that in recent years the A380 has led the number of orders against the B747. However, it is important to note that the B747 was released in 1968, many years before the A380, accumulating in total 1568 orders.

Figure 9.65 - A380 and B747 deliveries, cumulative by year
Source: Wikipedia web page

In terms of deliveries, it can be seen from the previous image that Boeing has had a clear lead in number of deliveries in past years, accumulating in total 1543 deliveries. It is reasonable since the release date of the A380 is 2005, many years after the B747. The four-engined airliner may be a dying species: the B747 is surviving on orders from freighters and the A380 on orders from airlines in the Gulf. The long-haul market is being taken over by the B738/B777 and A350.

Chapter 10 – Attracting Young Talent to Aeronautics

The career inclinations of young people can form gradually more consciously from childhood and primary school (section 10.1), through teenage and secondary school (section 10.2) to adulthood and university (section 10.3), with the influence of educators and the natural family. The choice of employment depends on the image and reputation of the employer (section 10.4) and its ability to provide good living and working conditions (section 10.5) and to foster the commitment and fidelity of the workforce (section 10.6) as a second family.

10.1 – Childhood and Primary School

Aerospace can easily enter the imagination of children, as shown by the story of the “Petit Prince” created by the aviator François Saint-Exupéry in the setting of the Moon. The stories about flying creatures and the visible objects in the universe can take an enormous diversity and lead to a variety of tales, including mythological episodes. The latter raise the question of how far to take these stories, for example Icarus. It is imaginative to build wings of wax to fly higher and higher; and tragic if the heat of the sun melts them and causes a fall. On one hand it warns of the risks of flying, on the other hand it is a story with tragic end. Without venturing into controversial realisms there is in phantasy world plenty of room for flying machines and travels to space objects. Also, demonstrations like balloons and origami paper gliders are quite entertaining for children.

A key aspect (Key Topic T10.1) is catching and retaining the attention of children and also specific programme developed for children (Key Topic T10.2).

KEY TOPIC T10.1 – CATCHING AND RETAINING THE ATTENTION OF CHILDREN

Although flying objects and creatures are usually entertaining for both children and adults, the attention paid to an aviation story or tale is deeply affected by different factors, among which age is included.

Focusing on children, attention span depends on age and on other aspects such as the interest shown in the activity. Generally, attention is a process by which people can address their mental resources to some aspects, the most relevant ones, or also to the execution of determined actions that are considered the most adequate within possible ones. In other words, it is a process that allows people to focus on some stimulus and not on others, and to control and guide their activity to a determined goal.

Attention has multiple variations but the most interesting one is the voluntary attention in which people decide to pay attention whilst in the involuntary attention or passive attention the stimulus attracts people.

In this context, children’s attention span evolves and gets improved along growth, thus at the beginning of childhood, child’s attention span is focused on interesting objects nearby that they can manipulate. In this manner, interest is essential in order to make the child pay

attention to a specific object and no to other one, in such a way that if a new more interesting object shows up, children stop focusing on the first object and start to focus on the new one. In other words, children easily move on from one action to another frequently.

As children grow, attention span increases and becomes more stable as well, so they usually can remain longer periods of time doing an activity. Typically, attention span can even triplicate within 2 or 3 years, from 30 minutes when children are 3 or 4 years old to 1 hour and a half when children are 5 or 6 years old.

At this stage of growth, the main change in children's attention span is the capacity to focus in a conscious and voluntary way thus attention can be focused on determined objects and activities. Besides, parents and teachers hold a key role for children development, including their attention span development as they can stimulate kids to focus on the activities that they want to.

Summarizing, children's attention span depends on their growth and on the interest that objects and tasks awaken in them in such a way that it is difficult for kids to focus on a monotonous and less attractive activity.

Fortunately, flying-related stories are usually entertaining for children. In this manner, they usually enjoy doing activities such as playing with kites, listening to tales that take place in space or watching flying-related cartoon as well as make paper gliders.

Regarding aviation-related cartoon, Super Wings (Figure 10.1) is an animated television series in which a group of different planes travel the world delivering packages to children and solving problems thereby they are called the Super Wings. Being broadcasted since 2015, it has become popular in many countries as their stories are fun for kids.

Figure 10.1 – Super Wings Poster

Additionally, to television series, movies in which aircraft are main characters are also usually entertaining for kids. For example, Planes (Figure 10.2) is an animated movie produced by Disney and released in 2013 in which a crop-dusting plane with a fear of heights lives his dream of competing in a famous around-the-world aerial race. This movie was successful as it grossed \$239.3 million worldwide on a \$50 million budget and, due to this, a sequel was also released afterwards.

Figure 10.2 - Planes Poster

These kinds of funny activities related to aviation can act as an incentive to awaken in kids the feel of loving this thrilling sector and, in this way, they could grow up willing to work in a job related to aviation.

KEY TOPIC T10.2 – SPECIFIC PROGRAMMES FOR CHILDREN

Besides children stories including flying and space objects, related illustrations and origami paper gliders there are many other activities to make STEM funny for young children and, specifically, aerospace. The American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics (AIAA) has developed STEM programs which aims to inspire, influence, and mould the next generation of aerospace scientists and engineers by providing a series of resources and programming to teachers, students, parents, and aerospace professionals. These programs focus on STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) subjects, as these will give pupils the

Figure 10.3 - Micro-Lesson example for K-2

tools to advance aerospace. AIAA supplies teachers with all the tools they will need to stir the curiosity of their students, and those tools are fun, engaging, and, mostly, "hands-on," to ensure the students thrive in their learning environment. From classroom grants, to standards based projects, to our signature program "Generation STEM: Discovering Aerospace Through Experience," AIAA is committed to providing students with exceptional learning experiences, and teachers with the tools and resources to create those moments. Also, AIAA has available "Aerospace Micro-Lessons" (Figure 10.3) that are special prepared for K-12 students and focused on aerospace principles. Each lesson is broken down into grade levels and are meant to spark conversation and interest in aerospace. Lessons will range from engineering, to mathematics, to physics, to highlighting aerospace anniversaries -- all of which will be presented in a way that easily relates to your students.

A variety of educational resources is also available in NASA'S website, it includes several entertaining materials such as: explanatory videos with attractive illustrations; interactive online games and "hands-on" experiences and activities that children can explore as they learn about science, technology, engineering, and mathematics. On one hand, when youngsters get the opportunity to actually watch and manipulate science they get inquisitive and involved with it. Some simple experiments that promote this scope are described by Lauren Eirik (2015) from Rasmussen College. On the other hand, engineering skills can be both fun and rewarding, because building can happen with blocks or even household items like straws and

Figure 10.4 - How strong is a piece of paper?

marshmallows. Building can also happen on the computer using games and programs. For instance, one activity is to test the strength of paper (Figure 10.4), folded in differently shaped columns, by piling books on top. This is very similar to how columns are used to support buildings and other structures, being a funny and clear way to enhance kids' interest on STEM fields, more specifically on engineer. Other activity can be a competition that aims to build

the paper airplane that takes the longest time to fall on the floor, which in a funny way leads to a discussion about some fly principles.

Figure 10.5 - Kid's Club Page

As mentioned before, online games can be an effective way to trigger kids' interest, so in NASA'S website children can find a Kid's Club section (Figure 10.5) with games related to the aerospace.

Sports have a major role in most children's life, they play because it's fun and brings enjoyment. As the science of aerodynamics

has also applications in sports, sports can be a pleasant way to learn about the "aviation world". From ball games like baseball, football and tennis to athletics, skiing, swimming and many other sports, the proper application of some basic principles of aerodynamic can make a difference between winners and losers. Throwing a ball along a curved trajectory or reducing the drag for a runner, all can be explained and improved through the science of flight. Teachers and parents may give some brief explanations of these basic aerodynamic principles or even make some funny experiments, so children can experience the "secrets" of the flight in sports and actually get some tips they might use if they practice the sport.

Also, cartoons may be good channels to boost kid's curiosity about aerospace. For instance, "Super Wings" is a TV show with Friendly airplanes that travel the world and teach kids multiculturalism. UP! is a Disney movie in which one of the main characters unveils hundreds of helium balloons to fly his house to Paradise Falls. Also, Leap! is about two kids, Felicie and Victor, who make their escape from the orphanage using a pair of aerodynamic wings that Victor invented.

Contests and events can also be organized. For instance, in the United States there is a Science and Engineering Festival with events that aim to show where "STEM Can Take You" and with a program named "The Nifty Fifty" which is a group of noted science and engineering professionals who fan out across the country to speak about their work and careers at various middle and high schools.⁴⁷ In Switzerland, Fédération Aéronautique Internationale (FAI) sponsors the Young Artists Contest which encourages young people to demonstrate the importance of aviation through their art, and to motivate them to become more familiar with and participate in aeronautics, engineering, and science.⁴⁸ Also, in London, the Royal Aeronautic Society organizes events that "aim to introduce young people to the wonderful world of aerospace and aviation, with a through life approach to the industry which aims to inspire young people about past and future aerospace achievement". For primary education specifically there are 2 programs: Cool Aeronautics (outreach programme) and Amy's Aviation (two children's animated series called 'Amy's Aviation' that charts the adventures of Amy as

⁴⁷ <https://usasciencefestival.org/>

⁴⁸ <https://www.fai.org/fai-young-artists-contest>

she discovers the wonderful world of aerospace and aviation).⁴⁹ In Portugal, the Aeronautical Promotion Centre along with Nortávia organizes visits for the children to have their first contact with the aeronautical environment, in which they are able to have direct contact with the aircraft and their pilots and mechanics in a playful and relaxed way, thus arousing enthusiasm for the aeronautical culture.⁵⁰

Similarly, but in a larger scale, in France, Tarmaq project aims to bring culture and share aeronautical know-how to all: families, children, curious and professionals. In an area of 35,000 m², Tarmaq, "will make it possible to experience the aircraft in all its forms". The theme park will include a leisure area, with airliner simulators, driving leisure drones, arcade games, a mini-airport for 7-17-year-old to discover the trades of a hub.

In sum, the career inclinations of young people can form gradually more consciously from childhood and primary school, it's all about making STEM fields funny and enjoyable for kids.

10.2 – Teenage and Secondary School

The basic teaching of physics, natural science and mathematics, even at secondary school level, can lead to some understanding of flying in the atmosphere and travelling in space. It is possible to explain why balloons fly up in air; to build and throw some paper planes. To explain how the earth moves around the sun and the seasons; the motion of the moon around the earth and the moon cycle; the rotation of the earth and the daily cycle. About the sun, other planets, the comets and stars. About helicopters and drones. The drones are now so common and cheap that they can be readily used to train piloting skills. Some of these activities can occur in leisure times at school or outside school with the families.

The path of students from secondary to higher education can be illustrated considering two universities in distinct European countries (Key Topic T10.3).

KEY TOPIC T10.3 – STUDENT PATH FROM SECONDARY TO HIGHER EDUCATION

Introduction

The fast development of the aeronautical industry over the last few decades has led to the creation of many jobs for both engineering's and technicians. In the last 10 years, the air transportation industry has employed over 350000 people (figure 10.6). On the other hand that from the perspective of future employment, the scenario has an European context. This is due to the fact that the corporations employing these numbers may be the same in different countries, either because they are cross border transnational companies (like EADS and Airbus), or they are joint ventures (like Thales Alenia Space and Alcatel, Agusta and Westland,

⁴⁹ <https://www.aerosociety.com/careers-education/schools-outreach/primary-education/>

⁵⁰ <https://air-chapter.squarespace.com/blog/2018/1/11/visita-escola-de-aviao-nortvia>

KLM and Air France, etc.) or, finally, they are co-operations on specific projects (e.g. Clean-Sky).

Figure 10.6 - Employment in Passenger Air Transport
<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/es/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52015SC0261>

The student finishing secondary school has a wide and sometimes bewildering choice of university degrees to apply for. Even restricting to Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) the options can be numerous and confusing. The aerospace engineering domain can be attractive from different points of view: technical knowledge acquired, and an interesting job in research, manufacturing or exploitation, with a very good retribution. The fascinating promise of aerospace engineering must be delivered in a high-quality university course that gives the necessary knowledge, skills and ability to reason and work in all these disciplines and their combination. Because universities have an admission exam (with a typical procedure), high school graduates need to have a strong motivation, and to know very well mathematics and physics, to pass steps of the admission process.

In the aerospace industry the fluctuations of aerospace engineering employments depend from the strategies of the main players in Europe: EADS, ESA, Alenia, etc. In present (and the trends is maintained) the "big" members of aerospace industry have a certain specialization in manufacturing of parts and components (table 10.1), and graduates of aerospace faculties may choose first to work in aerospace capabilities present in their country, although there is considerable mobility on the aerospace sector.

	France	United Kingdom	Germany	Italy	Spain
Major competences	Cockpit technologies and manufacture, engine manufacturing, broadest range, e.g final assembly of wide-body aircraft, helicopter, aircraft funding	Manufacturing of wings, strong in related composite applications, engine manufacturing, military products, MRO	Avionics, fuselages, complex cabin equipment, high-liftsystems, vertical tails, manufacture of and technologies for engines, final assembly of large civil aircraft, helicopter	Electronics, Military aircraft, helicopter manufacturing, strong integrated in non-EU value chains	Tail, fin and pitch elevator, growing strength in composites, assemblage of military transport aircraft and helicopters

Table 10.1 - Specialization of bigger member states in the aerospace industry in Europe

(Source: Competitiveness of the EU Aerospace Industry with focus on: Aeronautics Industry, 2009.
https://www.albertacanada.com/EU_AerospaceIndustry.pdf)

In the next section we will present the educational offers of 2 european universities in aerospace domain.

Politecnico di Torino (Italy)

The Politecnico di Torino is considered one of the best Italian universities for engineering studies. The admission test to the Polito is limited, because the students who try to enter are many and coming from all over Italy, and from many european countries. The test to be admitted to the Politecnico di Torino at the three-year degree will not be held on a single date, but in different periods. There are many students who sign up for the test. Precisely the dates of the test are March 15, April 20, May 19, April 20-21, August 31, September 1-2 and September 14. The test consists of answering 42 questions in an hour and a half. The questions are divided into 4 sections related to 4 different disciplinary areas: mathematics, comprehensive verbal, logical and physical themes.

The students have the possibility to obtain the Aerospace Engineering, Laurea (1st degree and Bachelor-level of the Bologna process) in the Deptment of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering ("Collegio di Ingegneria Meccanica, Aerospaziale, dell'Autoveicolo e della Produzione, Classe: ingegneria industriale (L-9), Corso: ingegneria aerospaziale (L-9)"). The program has a duration of 3 years and it held in Italian language, but the first year is common to other graduate programs and is also offered in English language.

An average number of 200 students graduates the program; an average number of 150 graduates not works at the time of graduation (2015-2017 period).

The educational programme is divided in the following sections:

- Scientific and methodological foundations: mathematics and basic sciences (physics and chemistry) for engineering. These courses are held in the first three semesters, although the third-year programme also provides optional courses in mathematics and statistics for students wishing to strengthen their background.
- General engineering: timetabled in the second year, this provides the base common to all industrial engineers and it focuses on industrial technical design, materials science and technology, machinery mechanics, electrical engineering, electronics, applied thermodynamics, heat transfer and structural mechanics (the last three subjects are treated with greater attention to the connection with subsequent courses in aeronautic construction and aerodynamics).
- Aerospace engineering: the third-year covers the core of knowledge in aerospace engineering, including flight mechanics, aerospace construction and structures, aerospace equipment and systems, fluid dynamics and aerodynamics, and aerospace propulsion. These form the basis for the main technical competences of graduates, and for the integration in aerospace industry or to continue further studies.
- Aeronautic maintenance: in the third year, students have more practical options, necessary for the forming a professional skill, focused on aircraft maintenance. These training activities are supervised by the Italian Civil Aviation Authority (ENAC), a member of the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), which guarantees full recognition for the purposes of awarding graduates Aircraft Maintenance Licence Class C, in accordance with EASA Part-66 international norms.

The aerospace engineering programme concludes with a final exam based on an assignment carried out independently by the student, who will present his or her dissertation before a reviewing commission. For students who choose the EASA Part66 a part of the dissertation is associated to an internship in an industry or company.

Before graduating students must also attain English language certification at the level of the Cambridge Preliminary English Test, "Pass with Merit".

Employment opportunities for which graduates in Aerospace Engineering are specifically trained lie mainly in the aerospace field:

- Major European aerospace industries;
- Small and medium-size industries which supply the former;
- Agencies and contractors responsible for aircraft maintenance;
- Airline companies;
- Air traffic management authorities;
- The air force and other military aviation sectors;
- Public and private bodies for testing in the aerospace field.

The multidisciplinary knowledge of the aerospace engineer and some of its specific competences (fluid dynamics and aerodynamics, light structures, computer aided design, advanced materials and technologies, integration of various mechanical systems, sensitivity to safety issues) can readily be applied in a range of jobs outside the aerospace sector (e.g. civil construction, automotive domain, etc.). European-level data show that about 50% of aerospace engineers are employed in other industrial sectors, even in regions where aerospace activities are most strongly established and offer the greatest employment opportunities (France, Germany, UK, Italy, Spain).

The qualification for further studies (Higher Education inside MSc programmes, especially in aerospace engineering), the graduates must to have solid theoretical knowledge, oriented to the engineering practice, of mathematics, physics, aerodynamics, mechanics, etc., excellent language skills and ability to formulate problems in mathematical terms, and also a capacity for analysis and synthesis.

TU DELFT (Netherlands)

Due to increasing number of students in the last years, the TU Delft bachelor programme Aerospace Engineering has determined a fixed capacity, a numerus clausus, of 440 new students that can be admitted into the bachelor's degree programme for academic year 2018 - 2019 (the deadline for application is annually before January 15, and the result is published at April 15). The selection procedure aims at a good match between the student and educational programme and focusses on the Motivation and Academic Performance of an applicant. Every applicant will receive a rank number. Higher final selection scores result in better rank numbers that offers possibility to be placed in the top 440 applicants. The Academic Test (available from March 1 to March 25) is used to determine the score on the criterion Academic Performance. The Academic Test has three sections: Mathematics, Physics, and the First Year Material.

The programme structure (36 months) is based on: 28% aerospace design, 28% aerospace engineering sciences and technology, 27% basic engineering sciences, and 17% minor. The average studying week has 42 hours (16 hours -lectures, 8 hours - projects and laboratory courses, and 18 hours self-study/tutorials), being 100% english-language BSc (&MSc) programme.

In the first year, students learn the basic engineering sciences, such as mechanics and calculus, and the main focus is to apply these disciplines in the aerospace design projects. The second year is dedicated designing systems and processing measurement data. With an intensive mathematics courses, the topics briefly discussed in the first year are exploited in depth, providing with a solid theoretical background in aerodynamics and orbital mechanics. The aerodynamic courses are accompanied by practical applications using two aerodynamic tunnels. The first semester of the third year allows extended the student education by means of minor programmes. Students can choice to do this at other Tu Delft faculties, at other universities in the Netherlands or at one of partner universities. The last semester consists of the final BSc courses, and offers a practical flight with a Cessna Citation aircraft to carry out measurements in flight. Everyone finishes the third year with the Design Synthesis Exercise

(working with a team of students on an original and relevant design assignment, in many cases the design project being proposed by aerospace companies or research organization.

The necessary profile of an aerospace engineering student must be included the capacity to acquire new maths and physics skills at a rapid pace, ability to solve multidisciplinary design in a team, and capacity to study in an international-oriented environment.

A study regarding career for graduates (year 2017) concludes that:

- 88% of MSc graduates find a job within 6 months after graduating
- 40% become employed in the Aerospace sector
- 60% find a job within other engineering (wind energy, automotive) sectors, consultancy or management.

MSc programmes have the following directions: Space Flight, Flight Performance & Propulsion, Aerodynamics & Wind Energy, Control & Operations, and Aerospace Structures & Materials.

10.3 – Adulthood and University

The student finishing secondary school has a wide and sometimes bewildering choice of university degrees to apply for. Even restricting to Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) the options can be numerous and confusing. Aeronautics and aerospace should be presented as:

- an advanced technology that takes most benefit of mathematics and physics, and is thus an ideal combination of all three rather than a narrowing down of focus into one of them;
- one of the most interdisciplinary branches of engineering since a flying machine involves most technologies: mechanics of flight, aerodynamics, propulsion, structures, materials, production, control, avionics, computing, telecommunications, man-machine interface;
- an enabler of a variety of vehicles, including airliners, high-performance aircraft, light private aircraft, helicopters, convertibles, drones, space launchers, satellites, space stations and interplanetary explorers;
- the ability to integrate all these technologies in vehicle that is safe, efficient and environmentally friendly while allowing fast travel to a wide range of destinations, some previously inaccessible.

The fascinating promise of aerospace engineering must be delivered in a high-quality university course that gives the necessary knowledge, skills and ability to reason and work in all these disciplines and their combination.

European universities offer a wide choice of high-quality aerospace education, with comprehensive curricula (Key Topic T10.4) and strong collaboration (Key Topic T10.5).

KEY TOPIC T10.4 – ANNALYSIS OF A COMPREHENSIVE AEROSPACE CURRICULUM

The aerospace is one of the main technological sectors of the European Union and a strategic sector to guarantee the future of European integration, its independence, prosperity and its competitiveness in the global economy. In short, it is a catalyst for growth and qualified employment.

The European aerospace industry has evolved over the past 40 years through a general and collective effort of public and private institutions, large companies, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), academia and research, etc., to become an industry leader in the world. Today, aeronautics and air transport are among the main drivers of European cohesion and competitiveness, representing 220 billion euros and providing 4.5 million jobs in Europe, a figure that is expected to double in 2050. These data reveal that aeronautics plays a key role in facilitating European economic growth and social inclusion, providing income to regions that are otherwise isolated and helping people to broaden their horizons.

There are two fundamental aspects that must be taken into account and that affect directly to the implementation of university aerospace studies: the availability of qualified professionals and the breadth of the environment in which the aerospace sector develops and for which professionals must be trained.

Attracting talented younger generations is one of the big challenges that faces the aerospace industry nowadays. In order to maintain European leadership and competitiveness in the aerospace sector, it is essential to attract young talent with high quality university courses that provide the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities that allow them to work in an efficient way within the aerospace field.

In the following sections, it is given an overview of the main courses related to aerospace studies that are available in Europe, with special attention for the Spanish case.

Universities with aerospace engineering studies

Once students finish secondary school, it is possible to choose a great variety of aerospace degrees across Europe (figure 10.7). In Europe, aerospace education is usually structured in a three-year bachelor's degree in aerospace engineering, with exceptions such as the Spanish case, which offers a four-year degree. Once students have finished these studies, they can choose a later specialisation with a two-year Master in various disciplines within the aerospace sector.

In Europe, many universities offer studies in aerospace engineering, with bachelor, masters and doctoral programs. The following image shows some universities that offer Degrees in Aerospace Engineering marked with a black point. As it can be seen, France, United Kingdom, Spain or Germany are the countries with more programs available.

Figure 10.7 - European universities that offer Degrees in Aerospace Engineering

The duration of the degree programs of the universities considered in the previous image, is indicated in the figure 10.8.

Figure 10.8 - Duration of the European Degrees in Aerospace Engineering

The previous graphic shows that most degree programs have a duration of four or three years, however, other countries such as Germany or Greece are the exception, with studies programs with a duration of two or five years, respectively.

Later, these studies can be extended with a two-year master's in aerospace engineering, which is also offered by the universities. Within this master, it is possible to choose several specialisations such as airports, propulsion systems or aerospace structures. In addition, other types of masters offered provide the opportunity of enlarging knowledge in other disciplines related to the aerospace sector such as, for example, space flight or energetics. The trend in recent years is studying a Degree in Aerospace Engineering, in which students acquire knowledge about the basic principles of aerospace technology and engineering sciences and, then, students continue their training with a master, which provides them the opportunity to specialize in a specific area of the aerospace field.

On the other hand, aviation is an extensive sector, and, for that reason, it is difficult to cover all the areas related to the aerospace industry in the study programs offered by the universities. Therefore, depending on the university, the degrees in aerospace engineering cover different disciplines within the aviation sector, such as airports, management or air navigation.

After analysing the degrees offered by the different universities, the areas that have been considered are the following ones:

- Aircraft: this area is related to the basic operation principles of an aircraft
- Airport: this area refers to the airport processes and its operation mode
- Propulsion: it refers to the basic principles of the aircraft engines system

- Science/materials: this area is focused in the mathematics principles of the aircraft performance as well as the study of aerospace structures and materials
- Management: it refers to all the business management within the aviation sector
- Navigation: this area is focused in the air traffic management
- Systems: this area is related to the aircraft systems such as avionics and electronic systems.

The following table 10.2 shows the areas mentioned above, and which of them are covered by the degrees of the different European universities that have been considered for the analysis.

University	Aircraft	Airport	Propulsion	Science/ materials	Management	Navigation	Systems
Polytechnic University of Catalunya	x		x	x			
University of Sevilla	x	x				x	
Polytechnic university of Valencia	x	x	x	x			
University of Leon	x	x		x			
University of Cadiz	x		x	x		x	
Polytechnic University of Madrid	x	x	x	x		x	x
European University of Madrid	x			x			
Carlos III University of Madrid	x		x				
University of Rey Juan Carlos	x	x	x			x	
University of Alfonso X el Sabio	x	x	x			x	
Polytechnic University of Milan	x		x	x	x		x
Polytechnic University of Turin	x		x	x	x		
Sapienza University of Rome	x		x	x			x
University of Luigi Vanvitelli	x		x	x		x	
University of Bologna	x					x	x
University of Padova	x			x	x	x	
University of Pisa	x		x				
Zurich University of Applied Sciences	x	x	x		x		
Delft University of Technology	x		x	x			
Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences	x	x			x		

University	Aircraft	Airport	Propulsion	Science/ materials	Management	Navigation	Systems
Inholland University of Applied Sciences	x			x			
Institute of Technology Carlow	x			x			x
University of Limerick	x			x	x		x
FH JOANNEUM Graz	x		x		x		
University of Patras	x		x	x	x		
Kaunas University of Technology	x			x			x
Vilnius Gediminas Technical University	x		x	x			x
Polytechnic University of Bucharest	x	x	x	x	x		
Transilvania University of Braşov	x			x	x		
Technical University of Košice	x		x		x	x	
BRNO University of Technology	x			x			
Czech Technical University in Prague	x			x		x	
Riga Technical University	x		x	x			
Newport University Centre for Educational Development	x		x	x	x		
University of Belgrade	x	x	x			x	
National Technical University of Ukraine	x			x		x	
Ecole-air de Salon de Provence (military school)	x			x		x	
ENAC Toulouse	x	x				x	x
ENSMA Poitiers	x	x	x	x			
ISAE-SUPAERO Toulouse	x	x		x			
University of Bristol	x			x		x	x
University of Glasgow	x			x		x	x
Politechnika Warszawska	x			x		x	

Table 10.2 - Areas covered by the European degrees within the aerospace sector

In the following points, it is included a brief description of the main universities that offer aerospace engineering studies, with the Spanish case analysed in detail.

10.3.1 France

In France, several institutions offer courses in aerospace engineering:

- In the first place, ISAE-SUPAERO Institut Supérieur de l'Aéronautique et de l'Espace, a world leader in higher education for aerospace engineering, which was officially created in October 2007 from the merging of two institutions: ENSICA and SUPAERO. It is located in Toulouse and it offers a degree program, the ingénieur ISAE-SUPAERO Degree, a program which is based on a multidisciplinary core curriculum comprised of courses in three main areas: science, humanities, engineering and businesses. It also offers a Master of Science in Aerospace Engineering, 15 Advanced Masters and 6 Doctoral programs.
- ENAC Ecole nationale de l'aviation civile, which is also based in Toulouse and belongs to the Ministry in charge of Civil Aviation. It trains pilots, air traffic controllers and engineers for future work in aerospace companies and in the public sector of civil aviation. It offers several degree programs including ENAC engineer, two masters and eight advanced master's courses.
- ENSMA Ecole nationale supérieure de mécanique et d'aérotechnique, which is based in Poitiers. It offers a degree in Aeronautics, Transport, Mechanics and Energy with a possibility of choosing the following specialisations in the third year: aerodynamics, energetics, heat transfer, structures, advanced materials and computer science and avionics. It also offers several masters in turbulence, aeronautical mechanics and energetics, air and ground transportation, etc.

10.3.2 Italy

The main universities that offer aerospace programs are the following ones:

- The Polytechnic of Milano, a scientific-technological university that trains engineers, architects and industrial designers. It offers a three-year bachelor's degree in aerospace engineering, a training program focused on the acquisition of a solid background in methodological aspects and basic subjects, such as the study of flight mechanics, aerospace technologies, aerospace propulsion systems and on-board systems. Graduates in Aerospace Engineering may continue their studies with a Master of Science in Aeronautical or Space Engineering.
- The Polytechnic of Turin, which offers a three-year bachelor's degree in aerospace engineering, within the department of mechanical and aerospace engineering. After the degree, students can continue their studies with a two-year master's in aerospace engineering, with the following specialisations: aerospace structures, propulsion systems, aeromechanics, aero-gas dynamics and space. It also offers a master's in aerospace engineering.
- The University of Rome "La Sapienza". It offers a three-year bachelor's degree in aerospace engineering and two Master of Science Degrees (Aeronautical Engineering and Space and Astronautical Engineering). After the Master of Science Degree, the training in Aerospace can be continued at Sapienza by joining one of three one-year Professional Master Courses

in Civil Aviation, in Satellites and Orbiting Platforms, or in Space Transportation Systems. Finally, the educational offer is completed with a three-year Ph.D. Course in Aeronautical and Space Engineering.

10.3.3 United Kingdom

The universities that offer Degrees in Aerospace Engineering include:

- Cranfield University, which offers the widest range of disciplines and is well equipped with research and simulation resources (>200 graduates per year). This university is highly specialised in one-year masters and does not offer any bachelor's training. It attracts many foreign students (>50%).
- The University of Bristol, offering degree courses and research in aeronautics and space. The aerospace engineering department has close links with major industrial companies, including Leonardo Helicopters, Airbus and Rolls-Royce.
- University of Glasgow, with a wide offer in aerospace training, including several degrees and masters.

10.3.4 Germany

Germany is a hub of state-of-the-art developments in the field of Aerospace and Avionics. That is why they have a large number of universities that offer studies in the sector. Below are the three examples of universities as well as the degrees, master and university degrees they offer:

- Bremen University of Applied Sciences. This is the public university of the applied sciences, which is situated at Bremen in Germany. This institute has various courses with bachelor's degree programs offered, while twenty-six master's degree courses are offered. In the field of aeronautics, it has a first program: Master's degree in Aeronautical Management and a second program: Master's degree in aerospace technologies.
- Technical University of Applied Sciences Wildau. The Technical University of Applied Sciences Wildau has twenty degree programmes in direct study programmes, and 2 in distance learning programmes. Relative to aeronautics, they offer an Aviation Management master's degree and also an Aeronautical Engineering/Aeronautical Logistics master's degree.
- Technical University of Munich. This is a research university with campuses in Arcisstrasse, Garching and Freising-Weihnstephan. It is a member of TU9, and until now, it is the only state university dedicated to technology. They offer a program orientated in Earth Oriented Space Science and Technology and an Aerospace Engineering master's degree.

10.3.5 Netherlands

In Netherlands, the most important university is the TU Delft, which is a reference in aerospace with more than 100 graduates per year. It offers a Degree in Aerospace Engineering and, during the first two years, students can acquire knowledge in aerospace design projects,

aerospace technology and basic engineering sciences. In the third year, students can choose a minor program between the followings:

- Simulation, verification and validation
- Production of aerospace materials
- Systems engineering and aerospace design
- Aerospace flight dynamics

The university also offers a two-year master's in aerospace engineering, with the possibility of choosing between six specialisations:

- Aerodynamics and wind energy
- Aerospace structures and materials
- Rotor design
- Flight performance and propulsion
- Space flight

10.3.6 Switzerland

The ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences is one of the universities of applied sciences in Switzerland, which provides aerospace training. It offers a three-year bachelor's degree in aviation, with the possibility of choosing one specialisation from the fourth semester. The specialisations available are the following ones:

- Technics and Engineering, which is focused in aircraft systems and mechanics, as well as in maintenance and certification
- Operational engineering, which is focused in security management and airports processes
- Finally, the aviation degree program can be combined with obtaining a commercial pilot license, which makes possible to shorten the training period since the academic basis for the licensing theory is already provided in the Aviation degree program.

10.3.7 Spain

The professional environment in which the aerospace sector develops is very broad. Any study on the aerospace sector cannot lose sight of the broad framework in which this sector is framed, which is none other than the vast and complex aerospace system. In this area, aircraft, satellites and missiles move, which demand the performance of a series of essential agents for their development: manufacturers, airlines, airports, ATM's, R & D Centres, etc.

Figure 10.9 -The Aerospace System
(Source "La industria aeroespacial 2003", ETSIA)

The relevant components of the Aerospace education include the airports and Air Traffic Management System or ATM.

In the field of airports, Spain is proud to host the first airport operator in the world and the fourth provider of air navigation services in Europe, Aena. The Aena Group is a group of companies dedicated to airport management and the provision of air navigation services. Through *Aena Aeropuertos S.A.* (of which Aena owns 100% of the capital) manages 47 airports and 2 heliports in Spain and participates directly and indirectly in the management of another 26 airports around the world. It is the first airport operator in the world by number of passengers, with more than 200 million. Through the public body, Aena provides air navigation services. Aena is the fourth provider of air navigation services in Europe and participates prominently and actively in all projects of the European Union related to the implementation of the Single Sky. The professionals who manage this network of airports and air navigation have been formed mostly in the aeronautical schools of the UPM.

The purpose of the bachelor's Degrees is to obtain a general education in one or several disciplines by the student, aimed at preparing for the exercise of professional activities. The overcoming of these teachings gives right to the obtaining of the corresponding title of Graduated.

The official university degree programs are specified in the curricula that are prepared by the universities, subject to the rules and conditions that apply to them in each case. These curricula must be verified by the Council of Universities and their implementation must be authorized by the corresponding Autonomous Community. Additionally, official university degrees are

subject to an evaluation procedure every 6 years, starting from the date of their registration in the RUCT, in order to maintain their accreditation. The *Agencia Nacional de Evaluación de la Calidad y Acreditación* (ANECA) is responsible for establishing the necessary verification and accreditation protocols. After the authorization of the Autonomous Community and the verification of the curriculum, the Ministry of Education and Science will submit to the Government the proposal for the establishment of the official title and its registration in the RUCT, whose approval by agreement of the Council of Ministers will be published in the *Boletín Oficial del Estado* (BOE).

Each study plan of a degree title contains 240 credits, which include all the theoretical and practical training that the student must acquire:

- Basic aspects of the branch of knowledge
- Compulsory or optional subjects
- Seminars
- External practices
- Targeted work
- Final Degree Project
- Other training activities

Each degree concludes with the elaboration and public defence of a Final Degree Project. Each and every one of the degrees is assigned, at the proposal of the University where it is taught, in one of the following branches of knowledge:

- A. Arts and Humanities.
- B. Sciences.
- C. Health Sciences.
- D. Social and Legal Sciences.
- E. Engineering and Architecture.

The curriculum of a degree must contain a minimum of 60 credits of basic training, of which at least 36 must be linked to some of the subjects listed in annex II of Royal Decree 1393/2007 for the branch of corresponding knowledge. These subjects must be specified in subjects with a minimum of six credits each and must be offered in the first half of the study plan.

The remaining credits up to 60, if applicable, must be configured by basic subjects of the same or other branches of knowledge, or by other subjects as long as their basic character is justified for the initial training of the student or its transversal nature. If the degree includes external internships, these must have a maximum length of 60 credits and should preferably be offered in the second half of the study plan. The end of the degree project can have between 6 and 30 credits, be oriented to the evaluation of competences associated with the degree and therefore must be done in the final phase of the study plan.

Additionally, students can obtain academic recognition in credits for participation in cultural, sports, student representation, solidarity and cooperation activities up to a maximum of six credits of the total curriculum studied.

In the case of qualifications that qualify for the exercise of regulated professional activities in Spain, as is the case at hand, the curriculum must guarantee and must be designed in such a way as to obtain the necessary competences to obtain that profession and must if there is an adaptation to European regulations.

Access to official bachelor's degrees requires holding the bachelor's degree or equivalent and passing the exam. The fulfilment of these conditions give access to obtaining a place in the public system of university education. The global calculation of the offer of university places is higher than the demand. However, the greater demand to study in certain universities and especially, to take certain qualifications produces local imbalances between supply and demand. For this reason, and in order to objectify the access mechanisms to the University, the University Council approves annually, at the proposal of the respective Universities, access limits for all or some of the studies that make up its academic offer.

In Spain, several universities offer degree courses in the area of aeronautics, being the Polytechnic University of Madrid the one that provides the greatest number of graduates.

One of the most important characteristics of the UPM University is that the program in aerospace engineering contemplates several disciplines in the student training. That is, as the aerospace industry is a very wide sector, there are many areas that are necessary to take into account. At European level, it only exists a title denominated Aeronautic Engineer, but it does not include all the competences or skills that are required in the aerospace industry. Most European universities offer three-year degrees, which provide general knowledge about the sector, without including important specialisations such as air navigation or airports and focusing most of them in the vehicle.

However, the Aerospace Engineering Degree of the UPM University contemplates almost all the professional areas of the complex and wide aerospace system, including aircrafts, propulsion, air navigation, airports and aerospace technologies.

In addition to the UPM University, there are other national centres that offer studies in aerospace engineering. Nowadays, the Degree in Aerospace Engineering is taught in eleven schools (in brackets, it is indicated the university and the year in which the degree in aerospace became available):

- Superior Technical School of Aeronautical Engineering and Space (UPM / 2010-11)
- Superior School of Engineers of Seville (US / 2010-11).
- E.T.S.I. Industrial and Aeronautics of Terrassa (UPC / 2010-11).
- Superior Technical School of Design Engineering (UPV / 2010-11).
- School of Industrial Engineering and Information Technology of Leon (ULE / 2010-11).
- Superior Polytechnic School of Castelldefels (UPC / 2010-11).
- Superior Polytechnic School (Carlos III University of Madrid / 2010-11).
- Superior Polytechnic School (Alfonso X el Sabio University of Madrid / 2010-11).
- Polytechnic School (European University of Madrid / 2010-11).
- Superior Engineering School (University of Cadiz / 2011-12).
- E.T.S. of Telecommunications Engineers (Rey Juan Carlos University of Madrid/ 2011-12)

The following table 10.3 offers a comparative analysis of the degrees offered by these centres, which includes:

- Denomination of the degree title offered.
- University / centre where it is taught.
- Previous experience of the centre in aeronautical degrees.
- Year in which the Degree in Aerospace Engineering is offered for the first time.
- Language.
- Number of places available and access notes.
- Specialisations.
- Duration.
- Number of credits of the title.

Title	University/ Centre where it is taught	Previous experience of the centre in aeronautical degrees	Year in which the Degree in Aerospace Engineering is offered for the first time	Language	Places available. Access note	Specialisations	Duration	Number of credits
Degree in Aerospace Engineering	Polytechnic University of Madrid Superior Technical School of Aeronautical Engineering and Space	Degrees to be extinguished: Technical Aeronautical Engineer (in Airports, Aircraft, Air Navigation, Aerospace Equipment and Materials, Aeroengines) Aeronautical Engineer	2010/2011	Spanish	630 11,386	Five specialisations: -Aerospace Vehicles, -Aerospace Propulsion -Science and Technologies -Airports and Air Transport -Navigation and Aerospace systems	4 years	Total: 240 ECTS Basic training: 60 Compulsory common credits: 60 Compulsory specialisation credits: 82,5 compulsory UPM-EIAE credits: 13,5 Optional credits and/or internships: 9-12 Final Degree Project: 12
Degree in Aerospace Engineering	University of Seville Superior Technical School of Engineering	Degrees to be extinguished: Aeronautical Engineer	2010-2011	Spanish/ English	125 12.34	Three specialisations: -Aerospace Vehicles. -Air Navigation -Airports and air Transport	4 years	Total: 240 ECTS Basic training: 64.5 Compulsory 76.5 Optional: 87 Optional internships: 9 Final Degree Project: 12
Degree in Aerospace Vehicles Engineering	Polytechnic University of Catalunya Superior Technical School of Industrial and Aeronautical Engineering of Terrassa (ETSEIAT)	Degrees to be extinguished: Aeronautical Engineer	2010/2011	Spanish/Catalan	60 11.590	Aerospace Vehicles	4 years	Total: 240 ECTS Compulsory: 210 Internships: 0 Final Degree Project: 24
Degree in Aerospace Technologies Engineering	Polytechnic University of Catalunya Superior Technical School of Industrial and	Degrees to be extinguished: Aeronautical Engineer	2010/2011	Spanish/Catalan	60 12.286	Aerospace Technologies	4 years	Total: 240 ECTS Compulsory: 210 Optional: 18 Internships: 0

Title	University/ Centre where it is taught	Previous experience of the centre in aeronautical degrees	Year in which the Degree in Aerospace Engineering is offered for the first time	Language	Places available. Access note	Specialisations	Duration	Number of credits
	Aeronautical Engineering of Terrassa (ETSEIAT)							Final Degree Project: 24
Degree in Air Navigation Engineering	Polytechnic University of Catalunya School of Telecommunications and Aerospace Engineering of Castelldefels (EETAC)	Degrees to be extinguished: Aeronautical Technical Engineer in Air Navigation	2010-2011	Spanish: 25% Catalan: 60% English: 15%	80 10.166	Air Navigation	4 years	Total: 240 ECTS Basic: 60 Compulsory: 120 Optional: 36 Final Degree Project:: 24 Optional internships: 12
Degree in Airports Engineering	Polytechnic University of Catalunya School of Telecommunications and Aerospace Engineering of Castelldefels (EETAC)		2010-2011	Spanish/Catalan	40 9.072	Airports		Total: 240 ECTS Compulsory: 216 Final Degree Project:: 24
Degree in Aerospace Engineering	Polytechnic University of Valencia • Superior Technical School of Design Engineering	Degrees to be extinguished: Aeronautical Engineer	2010/2011	Spanish and Valencian	120 12,29	Five specialisations: -Aircrafts -Aeroengines -Airports -Aerospace equipment and materials -Air Navigation	4 years	Total: 240 ECTS Basic training: 60 Compulsory: 88.5 Optional: 79.5 Final Degree Project: 12
Degree in Aerospace Engineering	University of Leon School of Industrial Engineering and Information Technology	Degrees to be extinguished: Aeronautical Technical Engineer in Aero engines	2010/2011	Spanish/English	60 11,478	Aircrafts	4 years	Total: 240 ECTS Basic training: 60 Compulsory: 132 Optional: 36 Final Degree Project:: 12

Title	University/ Centre where it is taught	Previous experience of the centre in aeronautical degrees	Year in which the Degree in Aerospace Engineering is offered for the first time	Language	Places available. Access note	Specialisations	Duration	Number of credits
Degree in Aerospace Engineering	Carlos III University Superior Polytechnic School	NO	2010/2011	English	70 11,269	Two specialisations: -Aerospace Vehicles -Aerospace Propulsion	4 years	Total: 240 ECTS Basic training: 78 Compulsory: 129 Optional: 12 Internships: 12 Final Degree Project: 12
Degree in Aerospace Engineering	Alfonso X el Sabio University Superior Polytechnic School	NO	2010-2011	Spanish	80	Four specialisations: -Aircrafts -Aeroengines -Airports -Air navigation	4 years	Total: 240 ECTS Basic Training: 60 Compulsory: 159 Optional: 9 Internships: 0 Final Degree Project: 12
Degree in Aerospace Engineering in Aircrafts	European University of Madrid Superior Polytechnic School	NO	2010/2011	English	40	Aircrafts	4 years	Total: 240 ECTS Basic training: 60 Compulsory: 138 Optional: 12 Internships: 12 Final Degree Project: 18
Degree in Aerospace Engineering	University of Cadiz Superior Engineering School of Cadiz.	NO	2011/2012	Spanish	70 11,55	Two specialisations: -Aircrafts -Aerospace equipment and materials	4 years	Total: 240 ECTS Basic training: 60 Compulsory: 145.5 Optional: 16.5 Internships: 0 Final Degree Project: 18
Degree in Aerospace Engineering in Air Navigation	Rey Juan Carlos University	NO	2011-2012	Spanish	55 9.416	Air Navigation	4 years	Total: 240 ECTS Basic training: 78 Compulsory: 114

Title	University/ Centre where it is taught	Previous experience of the centre in aeronautical degrees	Year in which the Degree in Aerospace Engineering is offered for the first time	Language	Places available. Access note	Specialisations	Duration	Number of credits
	Superior Technical School of Telecommunication Engineering							Optional: 18 Internships: 18 Final Degree Project: 12

Table 10.3 - Degrees in Aerospace Engineering offered in Spain

In this section, it is analysed in detail the Degree in Aerospace Engineering of the Polytechnic University of Madrid, which is taught by the Superior Technical School of Aeronautical Engineering and Space (ETSIAE).

First, this degree became available in the 2010-2011 academic course, when the Aeronautic Engineer and Aeronautic Technical Engineer Degrees extinguished.

The Degree in Aerospace Engineering of the UPM University is structured in a common basic training and the following specialisations:

- Aerospace Vehicles
- Aerospace Propulsion
- Navigation and aerospace systems
- Airports and air transport
- Science and aerospace technologies

After a common basic training the first two courses, students choose a specialisation for the last two courses, where they acquire the competences and skills of those specialisations.

The study plan complies with the provisions of the Resolution of January 15, 2009 of the Secretary of State for Universities (BOE, January 29, 2009) and by Ministerial Order CIN / 308/2009, of February 9 (BOE, February 18, 2009).

The Degree in Aerospace Engineering of the UPM University is composed of 240 credits. They are distributed as it is indicated in the following table 10.4.

Credits distribution		Number of credits
Basic credits		60 ECTS.
Compulsory common credits		60 ECTS.
Compulsory specialisation credits	Aerospace Vehicles	82,5 ECTS.
	Aerospace Propulsion	82,5 ECTS.
	Science and aerospace Technologies	82,5 ECTS.
	Airports and air Transport	82,5 ECTS.
	Navigation and Aerospace Systems	82,5 ECTS.
Compulsory credits of UPM-ETSIAE		13,5 ECTS
Optional credits and/or internships	Specialisation of Science and Aerospace Technologies	9 ECTS
	Rest of specialisations.	12 ECTS
Credits of Final Degree Project		12 ECTS.

Table 10.4 - Credits distribution of the UPM Degree in Aerospace Engineering

As it can be seen in the previous table, students' study 133,5 common credits for all the specialisations and 82,5 credits of compulsory subjects for the specialisations of Aerospace Vehicles, Aerospace Propulsion, Navigation and Aerospace systems and Airports and Air Transport. In the case of Science and Aerospace Technologies specialisation, they are 85,5 credits.

In addition to the previous credits, there are the optional credits and the credits belonging to the Final Degree Project.

The following table 10.5 shows the list of subjects, which are part of the study plan of the Degree in Aerospace Engineering offered by the UPM.

Subjects	Subjects	ECTS	Specialisations
Mathematics	Mathematics I	9	All
	Mathematics II	9	All
	Mathematical methods	6	All
	Numerical calculation	3	Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Mathematics extension	6	Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Statistics	6	All
Economy and Business Management	Business Economics	6	All
	Business and Project Management	4,5	All
Aerospace production	Aerospace Manufacturing	3	All
	Aerospace Production Systems	3	Aerospace Vehicles, Aerospace Propulsion
physics	Physics I	6	All
	Physics II	6	All
	Meteorology	3	Airports and Air Transport, Navigation and Aerospace systems
Design engineering	Graphic expression	6	All
	Graphic design	3	Aerospace Vehicles, Aerospace Propulsion, Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Mechanical design	4,5	Aerospace Vehicles, Aerospace Propulsion
Science and technology of materials	Chemistry	6	All
	Material science	6	All
	Construction materials	3	Airports and Air Transport
	Structural Materials for Propulsive Systems	3	Aerospace Propulsion
	Composite materials	3	Aerospace Vehicles, Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Aerospace alloys	3	Aerospace Vehicles, Aerospace Propulsion, Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Alloys	3	Science and Aerospace Technologies
Aerospace Technology complements	Specialisation Orientation Conferences	1,5	All
	Aerospace Technology	6	All
	Computing	6	All
	Computational Fluid Dynamics	3	Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Finite element method	3	Science and Aerospace Technologies
	MEF and CFD	4.5	Aerospace Vehicles, Aerospace Propulsion
Electrical and Electronic Engineering	Electronics and Automation	6	All
	Electric engineering	6	All
	Electrical installations	4,5	Airports and Air Transport, Navigation and Aerospace systems
Mechanics and thermofluidic dynamics	Classical Mechanics	6	All
	Thermodynamics	6	All
	Fluid mechanics	6	All
	Analytical Mechanics	3	Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Orbital Mechanics	3	Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Applied thermodynamics	3.75	Aerospace Propulsion
	Heat and Mass Transportation	3.75	Aerospace Propulsion
	Fluid mechanics II	6	Aerospace Vehicles, Aerospace Propulsion, Science and Aerospace Technologies
Aerodynamics, Aeroelasticity and Flight Mechanics	Aerodynamics and Flight Mechanics	6	Airports and Air Transport, Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Aerodynamics	6	Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Aerodynamics, Aeroelasticity and Flight Mechanics	9	Aerospace Propulsion

Subjects	Subjects	ECTS	Specialisations
	Aerodynamics and Aeroelasticity	9	Aerospace Vehicles
	Flight Mechanics	6	Aerospace Vehicles, Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Aeroelasticity	3	Science and Aerospace Technologies
Air Transport Engineering	Air Transport	3	All
	Air Transport Engineering	6	Airports and Air Transport, Navigation and Aerospace systems
Air Traffic Management Engineering	Air Traffic Management	6	Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Air Traffic Control and Management	3	Airports and Air Transport
	Positioning, Guidance and Control	4,5	Navigation and Aerospace systems
Resistance of Materials, Elasticity and Structures	Resistance of materials and Elasticity	7,5	All
	Solid mechanics	3	Aerospace Vehicles, Aerospace Propulsion, Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Structures	6	Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Structures	3	Airports and Air Transport
	Steel structures	4,5	Airports and Air Transport
	Concrete structures	4,5	Airports and Air Transport
	Aeronautical Structures	4,5	Aerospace Vehicles, Aerospace Propulsion
Airport Engineering	Vibrations	3	Aerospace Vehicles, Aerospace Propulsion, Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Aerodromes	6	Airports and Air Transport
	Construction	6	Airports and Air Transport
	Buildings and Facilities, Urbanization and Access	6	Airports and Air Transport
	Geotechnics	3	Airports and Air Transport
	Geodesy and Topography	4,5	Airports and Air Transport
	Airports	6	Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Airports facilities	4,5	Airports and Air Transport
Navigation and Aerospace Systems Engineering	Operation Engineering and Airport Management	3	Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Introduction to Air Navigation	3	Airports and Air Transport, Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Communications and Networks	4,5	Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Geodesy and Cartography	4,5	Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Communications and Surveillance Systems	4,5	Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Automatic Control Systems	3	Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Air Navigation Systems	4,5	Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Radio Frequency Systems	4,5	Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Digital Treatment of Information	4,5	Navigation and Aerospace systems
Aerospace propulsion	Avionics	4,5	Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Aerospace Systems Engineering	3	Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Air reactors	6	Aerospace Propulsion, Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Alternative Aeronautical Engines	4,5	Aerospace Propulsion
	Air reactors	4	Aerospace Vehicles
	Alternative Aeronautical Engines	2	Aerospace Vehicles
	Rocket engines	3	Aerospace Vehicles
	Aircrafts Propulsion	3	Airports and Air Transport, Navigation and Aerospace systems
	Alternative Aeronautical Engines	3	Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Engine Systems	4	Aerospace Propulsion
Fuels and lubricants	2	Aerospace Propulsion	
Aerospace vehicles	Rocket engines	4,5	Aerospace Propulsion, Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Control and Optimization	6	Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Aerospace vehicles	6	Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Space vehicles	3	Aerospace Vehicles
	Fixed Wing Aircrafts	6	Aerospace Vehicles
	Rotary Wing aircrafts	3	Aerospace Vehicles

Subjects	Subjects	ECTS	Specialisations
	Missiles	3	Aerospace Vehicles
Sustainability and Sustainability	Legislation and Management	3	Airports and Air Transport
	Operation and maintenance	6	Airports and Air Transport
	Maintenance and Certification of Engines	7.5	Aerospace Propulsion
	Maintenance and Certification of Aerospace Vehicles	6	Aerospace Vehicles
	Final Degree Project	12	All
	Professional and Academic English	6	All
	Internships or optional	6	Science and Aerospace Technologies
	Internships or optional	12	Aerospace Vehicles, Aerospace Propulsion, Airports and Air Transport, Navigation and Aerospace systems

Table 10.5 - List of subjects of the Degree in Aerospace Engineering study plan by the UPM

KEY TOPIC T10.5 – COLLABORATION AMONG EUROPEAN UNIVERSITIES WITH AEROSPACE ENGINEERING DEGREES

The University of almost all countries offer Programs in Aeronautic/Aerospace Engineering and therefore it would be almost impossible to give a precise idea of the different organization adopted in such diversified academic systems. Moreover, beyond the structure of engineering programmes, the programme contents themselves may vary considerably from one institution to another.

On this topic, as well in many others concerning specific scientific/professional/cultural contexts, different non-profit Associations/Networks/Partnerships have been created by Academic/Governmental Institution to share common backgrounds and visions of the general characteristics required to the University Degree Programs in each specific field.

Therefore, a criterion to select possible examples concerning the organization of typical University Degrees in Aeronautic/Aerospace Engineering could be that of focusing on those ones participating to specific networks existing in this field, such as PEGASUS and EASN.

In particular, the Partnership of a European Group of Aeronautics and Space Universities - PEGASUS represent one of such networks.

PEGASUS (www.pegasus-europe.org) has been formed from an initiative taken by the four main **French Grandes Ecoles** involved in aerospace with the aim of attracting the best students and also to offer highly relevant educational and research programmes.

PEGASUS partners are public and/or non-profit institutions of higher education in aeronautical / aerospace engineering located in the EU.

- 20 Founding Members in 1998;
- Presently 25-member Institutions;
- European countries represented.

Co-ordinated change and innovation are required to achieve objectives to be defined through close links and interaction with our aerospace Industry and relevant Government agencies. PEGASUS is open to all EU institutions providing a sufficiently qualified education in aerospace engineering. These programmes must include:

- Degree-awarding programmes;
- Continuing Education;
- Research;
- Intercontinental Affairs.

The participating Institutions (as of 2014) to the PEGASUS Partnership are depicted in Figure .

Partners of the Pegasus Network are categorised as:

- Full Partners, who fulfil the conditions stipulated by the internal procedural regulations.
- Probationary Partners, who joined the Pegasus Network according to the Internal Procedural Regulations and have not yet been upgraded to the Full Partner status.
- Associate Partners, namely institutions not fulfilling all admission requirements but, nevertheless, in possession of a high reputation.

Country	Institution	Country	Institution
	Politecnico di Milano Politecnico di Torino Università degli Studi di Napoli Università degli Studi di Pisa Università degli Studi di Roma		RWTH Aachen TU Berlin TU Braunschweig Universität Stuttgart TU Dresden
	Ecole-air de Salon de Provence ENAC Toulouse ENSMA Poitiers ISAE Toulouse		Cranfield University University of Bristol University of Glasgow
	TU Delft		KTH Stockholm
	UPM/ETSIA Madrid US/ESI Sevilla UPV/ETSID Valencia		CVUT Prague
	IST Lisboa		Politechnika Warszawska

Figure 10.10 - Academic Institutions (as of 2014) members of the PEGASUS Partnership.
Source: https://www.pegasus-europe.org/userfiles/Pegasus_presentation.pdf

The PEGASUS associated partners are shown in Figure .

PEGASUS Associate Partners			
Country	Institution	Country	Institution
	Kazan State Technical University		Kharkiv Aviation Institute
	Ufa State Aviation Technical University		
	Moscow Aviation Institute		

Figure 10.11 - Associated Partners of the PEGASUS Partnership.
Source: https://www.pegasus-europe.org/userfiles/Pegasus_presentation.pdf

All partners have agreed on a specific curriculum description format, PEGASUS Course Catalogue in 2009 enabling an immediate understanding of the level of education provided by the partners. The PEGASUS members agree that a new European system for QA in Aerospace Engineering Education should be applied for on a voluntary basis and if possible should not duplicate existing accreditation systems. The new system should focus on the qualifications and skills of the graduates right after graduation. PEGASUS, through PEGASUS-Industry Alliance, has established an entity for developing a

quality/excellence label, named PERSEUS which is awarded at Master Level (level 5 of Bologna process) on the basis of peer reviews and site visits.

According to the PEGASUS Course Catalogue (https://www.pegasus-europe.org/userfiles/Pegasus_Brochure_issue3.pdf), the commonalities of the programmes in Aeronautic/Aerospace Engineering have been classified into the following categories:

- **FS: FUNDAMENTAL SCIENCES**

They are the background scientific knowledge required to understand and utilise techniques and methods used in aerospace engineering. FS include courses such as mathematics, physics, chemistry, computer science basics, etc.

- **ES: ENGINEERING SCIENCES**

They are sciences applied to general engineering purposes, such as mechanics, fluid mechanics, gas dynamics, electronics, telecoms, software engineering, simulation tools and techniques, etc.

- **AE: AEROSPACE ENGINEERING SCIENCES**

Among engineering sciences, those having a strong orientation towards aerospace have been identified separately. They include: aerodynamics, propulsion techniques, aeronautical structures & materials, aircraft design, flight dynamics, air traffic control, aircraft operations, aviation safety, avionics, space engineering, among others.

- **GC: GENERAL COURSES**

Today, engineers can no longer limit themselves to purely technological projects, and they are in need of knowledge and skills in various "soft" sciences domains. These general courses include a large variety of topics (often proposed as optional courses) such as economics, finance, management, project management, history of aviation & industry, foreign languages, etc.

- **IT/FYP: INDUSTRIAL TRAINING / FINAL YEAR PROJECT**

Most PEGASUS engineering programmes include also one or several periods of practical training, in laboratories or industrial structures. These may take place during the training program (industrial training/internship) and/or right at the end of it (Final Year Project). In this case, the practical training period is rather long (generally 4 to 6 months) and represents an opportunity to apply to real industrial problems the skills acquired during the period of courses.

In some countries with a strong centralised administration of education (France, Italy) little dispersion in their programmes' profiles can be found. However, their programmes are also quite similarly balanced as those of Spain, Portugal and Sweden. For instance, in all those countries, the proportion of basic science and technology (the sum of the first two categories: FS and ES) is roughly the same, 40% to 50% of the overall curriculum (although the respective weights of FS and ES may vary more importantly according to some national inclinations towards more or less theoretical studies). Conversely, in countries with a long tradition of decentralised education (Germany, UK), the dispersion between categories is greater from one university to another.

Nevertheless, some German universities (Stuttgart, Munich, Dresden and Aachen) show a similar proportion of basic science and technology (50%) as French, Italian, Spanish and Swedish institutions.

A summary of the different percent composition (in terms of ECTS) of the Degree Programs in Aeronautic/Aerospace engineering in the PEGASUS Universities is shown in Figure 10.12.

PEGASUS AEROSPACE ENGINEERING PROGRAMMES (Continental Europe)

Figure 10.12 - Percent composition (in terms of ECTS) of the Degree Programs in Aeronautic/Aerospace Engineering in the PEGASUS Universities.

(Source: https://www.pegasus-europe.org/userfiles/Pegasus_Brochure_issue3.pdf)

PEGASUS member institutions are characterized by diverse aerospace engineering specialities which are reflected through a variety of courses or programmes, some of which are mandatory for all students while others are optional (electives). Some topics are widely taught across the PEGASUS engineering programmes, such as aerodynamics, aeronautical structures & materials, aircraft design, propulsion & combustion. Others are more concentrated in some member institutions, which put on emphasis on certain specialities like aircraft operations, air traffic control, space engineering & technology, etc. However, it is also possible to list “strong” areas for each institution.

FRANCE

ENAC (Toulouse) Aircraft operations, aviation safety, airline/airport operations & management, air traffic management; Aircraft navigation, avionics, communications; Aircraft Design, Subsystems and Integration; Performance, Stability and Control.

ENSICA (Toulouse) Aircraft design, subsystems & integration; Aircraft navigation, avionics, communications; Structures, materials; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Space engineering & technology.

ENSMA (Poitiers) Aerodynamics, gas dynamics, heat transfer; Structures, materials; Propulsion, combustion.

SUPAERO (Toulouse) Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Propulsion, combustion; Aircraft, navigation, avionics, communications; Space engineering & technology; Structures, materials.

GERMANY

RWTH AACHEN Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Structures, materials; Propulsion, combustion; Aircraft design, subsystems & integration; Production and maintenance.

TU BERLIN Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Propulsion, combustion; Aircraft operations, aviation safety, airline/airport operations & management, air traffic management

TU BRAUNSCHWEIG Aircraft operations, aviation safety, airline/airport operations & management, air traffic management; Aircraft navigation, avionics, communications; Structures, materials.

TU MUNICH Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Space engineering & technology; Propulsion, combustion; Structures, materials; Aircraft navigation, avionics, communications.

UNIV. STUTTGART Propulsion, combustion; Aircraft design, subsystems & integration; Structures, materials; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics.

TU DRESDEN Structures, materials; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Propulsion, combustion; Space Engineering & Technology; Aircraft Navigation, avionics & Communications.

ITALY

POLITECNICO DI MILANO Structures, materials; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Propulsion, combustion; Space engineering & technology; Rotary Wing Systems and Non-conventional Aircraft.

UNIV. DI PISA Structures, materials; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Performance, stability & control, flight dynamics; Space engineering & technology;

POLITECNICO DI TORINO Structures, materials; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Propulsion, combustion; Aircraft design, subsystems & integration; Performance, stability & control, flight dynamics; Space engineering & technology.

UNIV. DI NAPOLI Structures, materials; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Aircraft navigation, Avionics, Communications; Performance, Stability and Control; Aircraft design, Subsystems and Integration.

UNIV. DI ROMA Space Engineering & Technology; Structures, materials; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Propulsion, combustion; Performance, Stability and Control, Flight Dynamics.

THE NETHERLANDS

TU DELFT Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Space engineering & technology; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Aircraft design, subsystems & integration.

PORTUGAL

IST LISBOA Aircraft navigation, Avionics, Communications; Performance, Stability and Control, Flight Dynamics; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Propulsion, combustion;

SPAIN

ETSIA MADRID Propulsion, combustion; Aircraft operations, aviation safety, airline/airport operations & management, air traffic management; Aircraft navigation, avionics, communications; Structures, materials; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics.

UT SEVILLA Structures, Materials, Aircraft Operations, Aviation Safety, Airlines / Airports Operations and Management, Air Traffic Management, Production & Maintenance, Aerodynamics, Gas Dynamics, Heat Transfer, Aircraft Navigation, Avionics, Communications

SWEDEN

KTH STOCKHOLM Structures, materials; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Performance, stability and control; Aircraft design, subsystems & integration; Propulsion, combustion.

UNITED KINGDOM

UNIVERSITY OF BRISTOL Structures, materials; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Aircraft design, subsystems & integration; Performance, stability & control.

CRANFIELD UNIVERSITY Aircraft operations, aviation safety, airlines/airports operations & management, air traffic management; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics; Structures, materials; Aircraft design, subsystems & integration.

UNIVERSITY OF GLASGOW Structures, materials; Aircraft design, subsystems & integration; Performance, stability & control; Aircraft operations, aviation safety, airlines/airports operations & management, air traffic management; Aerodynamics, gas dynamics.

CZECH REPUBLIC

CVUT PRAGUE Aircraft Navigation, Avionics, Communications, Aircraft Operations, Aviation Safety, Airlines / Airports Operations and Management, Air Traffic Management, Aerodynamics, Gas Dynamics, Heat Transfer, Aircraft Design, Subsystems and Integration, Performance, Stability and Control, Flight Dynamics.

ITALY

The Italian University System is organized, after the Bologna process on three-degree levels as shown in Figure 10.13.

Figure 10.13 - Organization of the Italian University system.
Source: www.universitaly.it

There are several Italian Universities offering First Cycle (Bachelor), Second Cycle (Master) and Ph.D. Degrees in Aerospace/Aeronautical Engineering. However, since the Bachelor offers limited work opportunities it seems more appropriate to limit the analysis only to Master and Ph. D courses.

In Italy there are 11 National Universities offering a Second Level (master's degree in aerospace/Aeronautical Engineering). Detailed information on the organization and specific contents of each Degree Program can be found, as shown in Figure 10.14, on a site provided by the Italian Ministry for University and Research <https://www.universitaly.it/>.

Università degli Studi di BOLOGNA (University page)		Website
Aerospace Engineering , FORLÌ [scheda completa (SUA-CDS)] [scheda sintetica] [Course website]	LM-20	
Politecnico di MILANO (University page)		Website
Aeronautical Engineering , MILANO [scheda completa (SUA-CDS)] [scheda sintetica] [Course website]	LM-20	
Space Engineering , MILANO [scheda completa (SUA-CDS)] [scheda sintetica] [Course website]	LM-20	
Università degli Studi di NAPOLI "Federico II" (University page)		Website
AEROSPACE ENGINEERING , NAPOLI Interateneo [scheda completa (SUA-CDS)] [scheda sintetica] [Course website]	LM-20	
Università degli Studi della Campania "Luigi Vanvitelli" (University page)		Website
Aerospace Engineering , AVERSA [scheda completa (SUA-CDS)] [scheda sintetica] [Course website]	LM-20	
Università degli Studi di PADOVA (University page)		Website
Aerospace Engineering , PADOVA [scheda completa (SUA-CDS)] [scheda sintetica] [Course website]	LM-20	
Università degli Studi di PALERMO (University page)		Website
Università di PISA (University page)		Website
Aerospace Engineering , PISA [scheda completa (SUA-CDS)] [scheda sintetica] [Course website]	LM-20	
Università degli Studi di ROMA "La Sapienza" (University page)		Website
Aeronautical engineering , ROMA [scheda completa (SUA-CDS)] [scheda sintetica] [Course website]	LM-20	
Space and astronautical engineering , ROMA [scheda completa (SUA-CDS)] [scheda sintetica] [Course website]	LM-20	
Università degli Studi ROMA TRE (University page)		Website
Aeronautical engineering , ROMA [scheda completa (SUA-CDS)] [scheda sintetica] [Course website]	LM-20	
Università del SALENTO (University page)		Website
AEROSPACE ENGINEERING , BRINDISI Interateneo [scheda completa (SUA-CDS)] [scheda sintetica] [Course website]	LM-20	
Politecnico di TORINO (University page)		Website
Aerospace Engineering , TORINO [scheda completa (SUA-CDS)] [scheda sintetica] [Course website]	LM-20	

Figure 10.14 - Italian Universities offering a master’s degree in Aeronautic/Aerospace Engineering.
Source. <https://www.universitaly.it/>

The meaning of the symbols on Figure 10.14 are as follows:

- Accession requirement → undergraduate degree
- Offered by University Institution
- Compulsory admission test
- Admission test not required
- Face to face class lessons
- Duration 2 Years (4 semesters)

Program with international agreements

Courses taught in English

Full information on learning outcomes, study plan, syllabus, professors, opportunities for international mobility of students, placement opportunities, etc. can be obtained by accessing the link “SUA-CDS” or the “Course web site”.

Typical catalogues of some master’s degrees offered by the Italian Universities are shown in 10.15. As indicated previously, in Italy there is a strong centralised administration of education which binds the Institutions to provide a curriculum with little dispersion in their programs.

1st Year										
Code	SSD	Course Title	Num Sec	Language	Course location	Type	Sem	CFU	CFU Group	
081066	ING-IND/06	AERODYNAMICS		IT	BV	M	1	10.0	10.0	
096008	ING-IND/03	FLIGHT DYNAMICS		IT	BV	M	1	10.0	10.0	
083768	ING-IND/04	AEROSPACE STRUCTURES		IT	BV	M	1	10.0	10.0	
099255	ING-IND/04	AEROSPACE STRUCTURES		IT	BV	M	1	10.0		
099245	ING-IND/04	DYNAMICS AND CONTROL OF FLEXIBLE AIRCRAFT		IT	BV	M	2	10.0	10.0	
096024	ING-IND/06	COMPRESSIBLE FLUID DYNAMICS		IT	BV	M	2	10.0	10.0	
096010	MAT/08	NUMERICAL MODELING OF DIFFERENTIAL PROBLEMS		IT	BV	M	2	6.0	6.0	
099268	ING-IND/14	MACHINE DESIGN		IT	BV	M	2	6.0		
099256	ING-INF/04	ADVANCED AEROSPACE CONTROL		IT	BV	M	2	6.0		
083903	ING-IND/10	HEAT TRANSFER AND THERMAL ANALYSIS		IT	BV	M	2	6.0		
084149	ING-IND/15	COMMUNICATIONS SKILLS		IT	BV	M	2	2.0		
099257	ING-IND/03	TECHNICAL COMMUNICATION IN ENGLISH		IT	BV	M	2	2.0	2.0	
2nd Year										
Code	SSD	Course Title	Num Sec	Language	Course location	Type	Sem	CFU	CFU Group	
091224	ING-IND/04	AERO-SERVO-ELASTICITY		IT	BV	M	1	8.0	24.0	
091254	ING-IND/06	INSTABILITY AND TURBULENCE		IT	BV	M	1	8.0		
091253	ING-IND/06	EXPERIMENTAL FLUID DYNAMICS		IT	BV	M	1	8.0		
099244	ING-IND/06	COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS		IT	BV	M	1	8.0		
097502	ING-IND/14	MECHANICAL SYSTEMS RELIABILITY		IT	BV	M	1	6.0	6.0	
091222	ING-IND/35	MANAGEMENT OF AEROSPACE PROJECTS		IT	BV	M	1	6.0		
051177	MAT/09	OPERATION RESEARCH		IT	BV	M	1	6.0		
091335	ING-IND/06	AERODYNAMIC PROJECT		IT	BV	M	2	6.0	12.0	
051173	ING-IND/06	ROTOR AERODYNAMICS		IT	BV	M	2	6.0		
091336	ING-IND/03	DESIGN OF WIND TURBINES		IT	BV	M	2	6.0		
091339	--	GRADUATION THESIS AND FINAL WORK		--	--	V	1	20.0	20.0	
091339	--	GRADUATION THESIS AND FINAL WORK		--	--	V	2	20.0		

Figure 10.15 - General contents of the Aeronautic Engineering master’s degree (taught in English at the Polytechnic of Milan)

Source: www.polimi.it

10.4 – Careers in Aeronautics and Space

The kind of multidisciplinary competence in advanced technologies necessary in the aerospace sector is also sought in other sectors, such as:

- the automobile, railway and other transport and non-transport industries looking for better aerodynamics, lighter strong structures, more efficient engines, advanced control, safe traffic management;
- the consulting companies needing managers of technological projects, that require scientific skills out of reach of economists or legal people and find that the latter aspects can be assimilated to a sufficient extent by engineers.

Although an aerospace engineer would have as a first-choice aeronautics or space, it may happen that some consultant companies are quicker to offer professionally enticing and well-paid job opportunities, often advertising before the university degree is complete. The aeronautical industry can have the lead if it invites promising students to stay during their university course, thereby establishing early links that ensure their choice before other attractions arise.

The unrelenting technological progress changes the shape of the aerospace industries (Key Topic 10.6) and the careers it offers (Key Topic T10.7).

KEY TOPIC T10.6 – EVOLUTION OF THE AEROSPACE INDUSTRY

The aerospace industry is currently experiencing profound changes. With emerging countries such as China, India, Brazil and Russia entering into the market, global competition is steadily on the increase. Whilst long-term growth predictions are generally positive, continued success can only be achieved by those who excel at developing and implementing innovative product and service concepts, particularly with regard to environmental and ecologically sustainable issues. In order to serve the global market and sell technologically highly specialised products, cooperation between companies as well as entire regions is essential. The strategic response to the rapidly changing world has been the bundling of resources and competencies by clustering.

Within this context, EACP (European Aerospace Cluster Partnership) was established (figure 10.16) in 2009. This initiative provides a permanent platform for mutual exchange, policy learning, and cooperation to achieve high-level performance among European aerospace clusters. It focuses on the exchange of experiences concerning both cluster policy and the implementation of effective solutions needed to address various challenges faced by the partners. In order to be admitted to the network, a member must represent all segments of the regional aerospace sector, including industry, R&D and administrative bodies.

Figure 10.16 - Stakeholders represented within EACP (Source: EACP web page)

After 5 years of existence, EACP currently constitutes a network of 42 aerospace clusters (figure 10.17) from 17 European countries, thus largely covering the entire aerospace value chain in Europe.

Figure 10.17 - EACP Cluster map (Source: EACP web page)

Since its inception, EACP has been based on a set of core values (figure 10.18) which shape the culture and define the character of its transnational approach. As the most active aerospace collaboration platform, EACP provides a permanent framework for information exchange and policy study as well as opportunities for mutual transnational cooperation between its members and all market actors. With a focus on European clusters, EACP shapes the future trajectories for international cluster relations, whilst acknowledging the regional needs, challenges and characteristics of the aerospace sector. This relies on the core values of trust, engagement, dependability and joint added value generation, rendering EACP a network based on plurality and mutual commitment. In a global context, EACP strives to position Europe as the leading centre for innovation and competitiveness in the aerospace realm, thus addressing the contemporary challenges of an increasingly globalised world. Taken together, EACP represents a set of cooperative values and close interaction, both of which stand in line with its vision to strengthen the whole through the diversity of the many.

Figure 10.18 - EACP values (Source: EACP web page)

The main objective of the EACP initiative resides in improving the global competitiveness in Europe through intense inter-cluster collaboration. This goal is pursued (figure 10.19) within three major fields of action:

- Knowledge exchange
- Push innovation
- Strengthen EU position

All EACP activities follow these guidelines to improve competitiveness in a European context.

Figure 10.19 - EACP fields of action

- **Knowledge exchange:** to enable inter-cluster knowledge exchange, presentations and discussions on best practice are conducted at regular EACP meetings. Participation in the European Strategic Cluster Partnership (ESCP) allows for the exchange of experience and knowledge regarding economic, political and social developments that affect aerospace and other industry sectors. Thus, the regional clusters are not only prepared for possible future developments, but also work to further cluster excellence.
- **Push innovation:** the second main objective is pursued by developing skills and qualification among the existing and future aerospace workforce. Examples include the establishment of other EU-projects which specifically target technological innovation, such as the CARE and BeAware or CANNAPE. These and other projects are supplemented by EACP match-making events, as part of which EACP unites actors from industry and R&D to develop new ideas needed to improve technology, products and processes.
- **Strengthen EU position:** the third main objective constitutes a number of activities related to the continued internationalisation of the member clusters, their regions and resident companies. A crucial factor in this regard is the development of a competitive aerospace supply chain in the EU. Specific problems faced by suppliers are to be monitored and integrated into the EU technology roadmap. In order to improve the EU's global competitiveness in the aerospace sector, a strategic assessment of future technological fields as well as collaborations with strategic actors are planned. In this manner, EACP also supports the efforts of other institutions such as ASD, ACARE, CleanSky, EASN, Sesare and EEN.

KEY TOPIC T10.7 – CAREES IN THE AEROSPACE SECTOR

T10.7. 1 – About the Sector

The global Aerospace and Defence industry will strengthen in 2018 as revenues are forecasted (figure 10.20) to increase by 4.1 percent, doubling last year's 2.1 percent growth. The recovery of global gross domestic product (GDP), stable commodity prices, and heightened passenger travel demand are likely to ramp up growth in the commercial aircraft sector in 2018.

The sector can be divided into two major areas:

- aeronautics industry and
- air transport.

Figure 10.20 - 2018 Forecast for the Aerospace Industry
Source: Deloitte 2018 Global Aerospace and Defence Industry Outlook

Aeronautics Industry

According to the European Commission, Aeronautics is one of the EU's key high-tech sectors on the global market:

- the EU is **a world leader in the production of civil aircraft**, including helicopters, aircraft engines, parts and components
- the EU has a **trade surplus for aerospace products**, which are exported all over the world.

The European aeronautics industry develops and manufactures **civil and military aircraft, helicopters, drones, aero-engines** and **other systems and equipment**. The industry work involves **designing components and systems and generating CAD models and drawings**; work such as **fluids analysis or thermal analysis**; **manufacturing the technology**; **developing and testing it**; and **supporting the products in service**.

Big manufacturing companies include **Airbus, BE, Leonardo Embraer and Bombardier**, who design, manufacture and build aircraft, and **Rolls-Royce, Safran, General Electric and Pratt and Whitney**, who design, manufacture and build engines. **Liebherr, Cobham and GKN** are other big names. There is a large network of smaller suppliers who support the big companies.

Productivity is considerable and despite high employment costs, the sector is **quite profitable**. A sizeable share of value added is spent on **research and development (R&D)**, which is reflected in an increasing number of patent applications. (European Commission).

Air Transport

According to **Aviation Benefits Beyond Borders**, the **Air transport** (figure 10.21) supports **11.9 million jobs** and **\$860 billion in GDP in Europe**. The air transport industry in Europe directly generated an estimated 2.5 million jobs in 2014.

Figure 10.21 – Air Transport in Europe

The total impact – including those from the operations of the air transport sector itself, the impact of the air transport sector's procurement of inputs of goods and services from its supply chain, and the impact of employees of the air transport sector and its supply chain spending their wages – mean the **air transport sector supported 6.9 million jobs and contributed \$531.9 billion to GDP in Europe**. (Aviation Benefits Beyond Borders, 2014)

Moreover, substantial benefits derive to regional economies via the catalytic impacts of tourist spending, much of which is generated by tourists travelling by air. In 2014, **the spending of tourists arriving at their destination by air is estimated to have added 5 million to employment and \$328.1 billion in GDP**. (Aviation Benefits Beyond Borders, 2014)

At the same time, according to most recent statistics from the latest edition and **Eurostat data**, the EU air transport cluster and airport related activities direct contribute to the **EU's GDP in €110bn** while the **overall total impact, including the indirect effects, is as much as €300bn**.

T10.7.2 – Human Dimension of the sector

Employment in Aerospace and Defence industry has been increasing and, in 2015, reached its maximum by employing 847.700 people (Figure 10.22). Employment in the aerospace sector is **particularly significant in Europe (Figure 10.23), mainly in the United Kingdom, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, Poland and Sweden.**

Figure 10.22 - Aerospace and Defence Industry Employment between 2010-2015
Source: Aerospace and Defence Industries Association of Europe

Figure 10.23 - Aerospace Industry Overview

Aeronautics Industry

According to the Aerospace and Defence Industries Association of Europe (ASD), 65% of employment in the Aerospace and Defence sector accounts to aeronautics related careers (figure 10.24):

Figure 10.24 - Aerospace and Defence 2015 Employment Breakdown
Source: Aerospace and Defence Industries Association of Europe

Air Transport

According to **Aviation Benefits Beyond Borders**, the air transport industry in Europe directly generated (Figure 10.25) an estimated 2.5 million jobs in 2014.

- **533,000** of those people (21% of the total) were in **jobs for airlines or handling agents** (for example, flight crew, check-in staff, maintenance crew, reservations and head office staff).
- **Another 174,000 people (7% of the total) worked airport operators** (for example, in airport management, maintenance, security, and operations).
- **1.4 million jobs (57%) were on-site in airports, at retail outlets, restaurants, hotels, etc.**
- A further **311,000 people (12%)** were employed in the **manufacture of civil aircraft** (including systems, components, airframes, and engines).
- **Air navigation service providers** employed an additional **84,000 people (3%)**.

Figure 10.25 - Total jobs and GDP generated by air transport in Europe, 2014

Figure 10.26 - Map of the Direct Employment at Airports in Europe, 2013
 Source: Economic Impact of European Airports, InterVISTAS

European airports (figure 10.26) are a source of a wide variety of job categories, with different positions spread on-site and off-site across the airports (Figure 10.27).

Figure 10.27 - Direct Job by Employment Type
 Source: Economic Impact of European Airports, InterVISTAS

The direct employment generated by airports is affected by the size of the airport and the mix of traffic handled. Direct employment data was gathered from 125 airports representing 71% of

European passenger traffic. For those airports where no employment information could be obtained an econometric model was developed to infer their direct employment. Analysis was conducted of the airports from which data was collected to analyse the relationship between direct employment and characteristics of the airport. The results are summarised in Figure 10.28:

Airport Size / Traffic Type	Comment
Less than 1 million traffic units	Each increase of 1000 traffic units increases employment by 1.2 Jobs
1 million - 10 million traffic units	Each increase of 1000 traffic units increases employment by 0.95 Jobs
Over 10 million traffic units	Each increase of 1000 traffic units increases employment by 0.85 Jobs
Connecting passengers	Connecting passengers generate 3% less direct jobs than origin/destination passengers
LCC passengers	LCC passengers generate 20% less direct jobs than non-LCC passengers

Figure 10.28 - Factors Determining Airport Direct Employment
(Source: Economic Impact of European Airports, InterVISTAS)

The latest edition of the **Eurostat data** reported that the EU air transport cluster and airport related activities **directly employ around 1.9 million people and directly or indirectly support 4.7 million jobs**. According to the European Commission, since the completion of the aviation internal market, direct employment in aviation has remained stable while the aviation market was booming. While over the period 2000-2013 passenger traffic in the EU has grown at a compound average rate of +3.0% p.a., i.e. totalling +47% over that period, employment in the air transport cluster saw a net reduction of -7.0% over the same 13-year period. These developments took place in a context of rapidly increasing productivity and more widespread recourse to outsourcing.

In the European report (2015) "Study on employment and working conditions in air transport and airports" is indicated a percentage of 60% men and 40% women in air transport.

T10.7.3 Careers in aeronautics and air transport

This sector can be divided into two major areas:

- **Aeronautic Industry** - includes prime contractors and system designers (aircraft manufacturers, missile and satellite manufacturers, designers of on-board electronic systems and others), engine manufacturers (propulsion system designers) and equipment manufacturers (pneumatic, electric, electronic, mechanical). It is based on trades classified into 3 categories:
 1. engineers (system engineer, mechanical design engineer and others),
 2. senior technicians (logistic technician, method preparer and others) and
 3. operators (boilermaker, fitter-fitter and others).

- **Air transport** - includes the transportation of people, goods and mail on regular lines and non-scheduled activities (charter, taxi, plane rental with pilot, flight training and others). It relies on aeronautical maintenance activities and airport assistance activities (rack and field operations, shipboard trades, civil aviation professions).

T10.7.4 Needs and tendencies

Air transport (maintenance technicians, pilots and cabin crew)

The commercial passenger aircraft fleet is growing, and Airbus forecast suggested it will continue to grow in terms of the numbers of aircraft over 100 seats in the coming years. In fact, the GMF suggests the fleet will more than double from today's level of around **19,000 aircraft to 40,000 in 20 years' time** (Figure 10.29). (Airbus Global Market Forecast 2017-2036, 2017).

Figure 10.29 – Passenger fleet in service will more than double over the next 20 years

Based on the expected increase of passenger fleet in service for the next 20 years, the **2017 Airbus Global Market Forecast Report underlines future needs for:**

1. Maintenance, Repair and Overhaul market (**MRO**);
2. New **pilots** and
3. **Technicians**.

Firstly, this fleet growth will also drive the size of the **MRO business**, which Airbus also expects to double, US\$60 billion to more than **US\$120 billion a year by 2036**, or a cumulative US\$1.85 trillion over the same period. Unsurprisingly, as the fleet grows in Asia-Pacific so too will its share of the overall MRO business with 36% of the value or more than US\$660 billion over the next 20 years (Figures 10.30, 10.31 and 10.32). As represented on Figure 6, MRO demand will more than double over the next 20 years.

Figure 10.30 – Evolution of yearly regional share

Figure 10.31 – Yearly market value evolution

Figure 10.32 – MRO total demand for passenger aircraft above 100 seats over the next 20 years

As the world fleet grows so too does the need for more **pilots and technicians** to meet the needs of airlines and passengers. Airbus forecast (figure 10.33) that over the next 20 years more than a million such professionals will be needed to be trained to the highest levels.

Figure 10.33 – Need for technicians and pilots

According to Boeing, the airline industry will require **637,000 new pilots**, **648,000 new mechanics** and **839,000 cabin crew members** during the period. The Boeing forecast shows the most pronounced demand for pilots, technicians and flight attendants in the Asia-Pacific region, which, according to Boeing, stands soon to surpass North America as the world's biggest commercial aviation market. Specifically, Asia-Pacific will need 253,000 new pilots over the forecast period, as well as 256,000 mechanics and 308,000 cabin crew. While North America promises to command the second highest demand for pilots and mechanics, at 117,000 and 118,000, respectively, Europe will need more cabin crew, at 173,000, than will North America (154,000).

However, the Aviation Technician Education Council (ATEC) Pipeline report shows that **new entrants make up 2% of the aviation maintenance technicians' population annually, while 30% of the workforce is at or near retirement age**, which reinforces the **need to attract women and students to the sector**.

Aerospace Engineers

Aerospace engineers will be other promising career (table 10.6), not only because of the estimated global demand for new passenger airplanes, but also because of the rapid advances in aerospace technology. **Research and development projects**, such as those related to improving the safety, efficiency, and environmental soundness of aircraft, will help sustain demand for workers in this occupation. Aerospace engineers in all areas will continue to be needed as design and production focus on aircraft that are less noisy and more fuel efficient. In addition, **as international governments refocus their space exploration efforts, new companies are emerging to provide access to space beyond the access afforded by standard governmental space agencies**. The **growing use of unmanned aerial vehicles** will create more opportunities for aerospace engineers as authorities find domestic uses for them, such as finding missing persons lost in large tracts of forest or measuring snow pack and other water resources. Commercial interests will also find increasing uses for these unmanned vehicles, and workers in this occupation will find employment in designing and perfecting these vehicles for specified uses. **Employment opportunities should be favourable for those trained in software, such as C++, or with education and experience in stress and structural engineering**. Finally, the **aging of workers in this occupation should help to create openings in it over the next decade**. (*Occupational Outlook Handbook*, 2017)

Occupational Title	Employment, 2016	Projected Employment, 2026	Change, 2016-26	
			Percent	Numeric
Aerospace engineers	69,600	73,800	6	4,200

Table 10.6 - Employment projections data for Aerospace Engineers, 2016-26 Source: Bureau of Labour Statistics, U.S. Department of Labour.

In the United Kingdom (Table 10.7) two-thirds of aerospace engineering graduates are in employment six months after graduation. A fifth of those in employment (Table 10.8) are working as mechanical engineers, and a further fifth are working either as design and development engineers or other engineering professionals (Association of Graduate Careers Advisory Services, 2017).

Destination	Percentage
Employed	66.5
Further study	17.2
Working and studying	3.2
Unemployed	8.3
Other	4.7

Table 10.7 - Graduate destinations for aerospace engineering

Type of work	Percentage
Engineering and building	43.2
Technicians and other professionals	11.1
Retail, catering and bar work	8.8
Business, HR and financial	6.8
Other	30.0

Table 10.8 - Types of work entered in the UK

Internships are often the best way to get your foot in the door. Applying for a graduate programme or a direct entry position are other good ways. Most companies offer lots of training and professional development opportunities, including the opportunity to move into different roles.

According to **Carrie Lambert**, back in 2016, when was capability manager in engine noise at Rolls-Royce, the **aerospace industry seeks graduates from the following disciplines:**

aerospace/aeronautical, chemical, control, electrical, electronics, environmental, instruments, manufacturing, materials, mathematics, mechanical, physics, power systems, software. Also, **areas receiving a lot of attention include:** unmanned aerial vehicles, supersonic aircraft, distributed propulsion, electric aircraft, and higher bypass ratio engine products such as geared fans and open rotor technology. However, **along with a solid technical background, good communication skills are absolutely critical.** Engineers in this sector need to think and reason logically and use a **combination of forensic and creative thinking to solve problems.** There's always a lot to do so the **ability to plan, prioritise and judge** the level of detail and time to spend on a task is important.

Other careers

Also, digital transformation is a reality for A&D industry, so, besides a strong vision from the top management, attracting and retaining talent like data scientists and software experts will be key.

10.5 – Motivating and Rewarding the Workforce

The best motivation and reward for the workforce is openness to new ideas and giving opportunity for sensible innovation that benefits also the company's interests. This is more easily achieved in a small spin-off in a more dynamical atmosphere with less constraints. In many cases a spin-off cannot do more than a specific work, or the initial stages of a larger task and the greater resources of a larger organization are needed to progress further. The commitment of larger resources requires a clear assessment of potential benefit. When that benefit materializes it should reach all levels of the workforce that contributed to it. Some companies:

- share a part of the profits with the employees;
- give employees the opportunity to buy a limited number of shares at favourable prices with the condition that they cannot be sold for a number of years.

Measures like these motivates employees to work harder for the aims of the company they share, knowing that the success due in part to their efforts will be recognized. These objectives relate to the principles of Strategic Human Resource Management (Key Topic T10.8) and their application in the Aerospace Sector (Key Topic T10.9).

KEY TOPIC T10.8 – PRINCIPLES OF STRATEGIC HUMAN RESSOURCE MANAGEMENT

According to HIPAIR Erasmus+ project it is very important that high performance working practices (HPWP) are recognized as important elements of business strategy development, in which the human resources play the key role. HPWPs include, for example, recruitment and integration, employee involvement, internal communication, training and reward and commitment. Strategic human resource management theory asserts that these practices increase employees' knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs), empower employees to leverage their KSAs for organizational benefit, and **increase their motivation to do so** (Becker & Huselid, 1998; Delery & Shaw, 2001). The result is **greater job satisfaction, lower employee turnover, higher productivity, and better decision making**, all of which help improve organizational performance (Becker, Huselid, Pickus, & Spratt, 1997). Therefore, this approach helps to accept and involve the HR function as a strategic factor in the formulation and

implementation of the company's strategies, since human resource management capabilities are important not only for attracting and selecting, but also retaining, motivating and developing the workforce in an organization. **Some practices that were identified in HIPAIR Project and may be effective on motivating workforce are:**

1. **REWARD & COMMITMENT** - practices focused on facilitating a greater sense of belonging to the specific organisation. Financial and nonfinancial incentives establish a sense of stake-holding within the company, having long term positive impact on employees.
 - Compensation plans (production, administrative, administrative, etc.)
 - Flexible working conditions
 - Rooms for nursing mothers
 - Retention policy

2. **EMPLOYEES INVOLVEMENT** - practices that are focused on increase of the involvement and commitment of the employees inside the company. They can help in evaluation and improvement of workers performance as well as achievement of excellence in specific areas.
 - Functional flexibility program
 - Suggestions Programs
 - Organisational Climate and Satisfaction Surveys
 - Employee Engagement Survey
 - Individual Development Plans
 - Employee Action Plans
 - Performance appraisal
 - Annual objectives for each employee, individual and/or global
 - KPI for teams
 - Excellence achievement programme.

3. **TRAINING** - Practices aiming at improvement and development of the skills and competences of the company employees, needed for the specific company goals.
 - Mentoring, Coaching, Tutoring
 - Talent identification and development plan
 - Talent development program to women-leadership in aeronautics industry
 - Specific training plans based on competences/skills matrix in order to answer to identified gaps and to support life-long learning processes

Also, because environment conditions play a role on individual's motivation to perform their work task, employers should guarantee work/task enrichment through more autonomy and discretion in one's job, feedback on performance, opportunity to use multiple skills (i.e., skill variety), identification of the contribution of one's job to the overall work context (i.e., task identity), and knowledge of the significant contribution of one's job to others' lives (i.e., task significance). (Ayca, 2004) This reflects Hackman and Oldham process motivation theory.

Besides the above mentioned, some people's motivation is based on fairness with which they are treated and compare this treatment with the one that is received by others whom they consider relevant for this comparison. Consequently, organizational justice is a key element to enhance worker's motivation. (Adams Equity Theory, 1963) There are ways in which to restore equity such as changing inputs (e.g., working less), changing the comparison group, changing the outcomes (e.g., asking for a salary increase), and leaving the organization. Reward allocation based on an equity principle is not endorsed in all cultural contexts.

As reported by Gibson et al. (2000), process motivation theories have important impact on managers who are involved in the motivational process as per their job nature. However, it is crucial to notice that there are individual differences concerning to the importance given to different properties or results, and that these differences are related to other aspects of the organization. The relationship between the individual and the organization is interactive, of mutual influence in the establishment of a psychological contract - individual motivations and organizational conditions interact in complex ways.

KEY TOPIC T10.9 – HUMAN RESSOURCE MANAGEMENT IN THE AEROSPACE SECTOR

Over the years, Human Resources Management (HRM) faced the requirement to adapt to new markets reality, work forms and workers' needs. Nowadays, it is necessary even a faster adaptation due to the constant market's demand change, technological developments, globalisation and strong competition.

Traditional and rigid forms of work organisation have proved that they are not efficient for motivating the workforce, which is a very important resource to achieve more efficiency and benefits, as employees work harder for the aims of the company they share.

Therefore, the new challenge to be achieved will be to improve and adapt new HRM paradigms, by developing new methods to reward employees, in order to increase productivity and competitiveness in global markets.

In relation to aviation sector, HRM becomes a key issue to assure its competitive position, since it is considered as one of the most innovative industries worldwide. Therefore, in order to maintain the favourable position of the European aerospace industry, companies should pay special attention to HRM matters.

According to the HiPAir project, a strategic partnership co-funded by the ERASMUS+ programme of the European Commission, one of the new forms of work organisation, which have been developed, is the concept of High-Performance Work Practices (HPWP). Though many of the practices referred as high performance are commonly used by most organisations to motivate workers, such as financial incentives, flexible job descriptions and continuous skills development programs, the concept of HPWP is fairly unknown. HPWP can be defined as modern management practices design to stimulate the employees and the organisation performance.

According to literature worldwide, there is a relation between the systematic and integrated implementation of HPWP and performance indicators, such as productivity and profitability. This link may exist due to the effect of HPWP in employee attitudinal and behavioural variables such as job satisfaction, organisational commitment, employee empowerment, etc. Therefore, HPWP could

develop better work conditions, affecting employee perceptions towards his employer, increasing satisfaction levels and the will to do more and better in the workplace.

At European level, no company openly uses integrated sets of HPWP, nevertheless it is possible to identify some isolated practices considered High Performance, such as leadership abilities' development program, job rotation, retain talent programs, etc.

The following table 10.9 shows examples of High-Performance practices which are used in companies at European level:

Recruitment and integration	Interviews, theoretical tests Welcome Induction programs Internship programmes Search talented people in collaboration universities and other training institutions Preparation of job descriptions and selection procedures
Employees involvement	Functional flexibility program (mobility inter and intra-department); Suggestions programs; Organisational climate and satisfaction Surveys; Employee engagement survey; Individual development plans; Employee action plans; Performance appraisal; Annual objectives for each employee, individual and/or global; KPI for teams; Continuous improvement system Excellence achievement programme
Internal Communication	Communication packages for employees; Intranet; Webinars; Communication meetings (involving all the workers, who may present their opinions and suggestions to improve company's procedures)
Training (learning and education)	Scholastic program; Post-graduate studies; Language courses; Training technical and non-technical (internal and external courses); Mentoring, coaching, tutoring; Talent identification and development plan Talent development program to women-leadership in aeronautics industry; Specific training plans based on competences/skills matrix in order to answer to identified gaps and to support life-long learning processes.
Reward and commitment	Compensations plans (production, administrative, management, etc.); Flexible working conditions; Rooms for nursing mothers; Retention policy; Standardized job roles; Compensation, bonuses related with objectives achievement; Salary increment related with objective review.

Table 10.9 High Performance practices used in European companies (Source: Hip Air, High performance work practices in the aviation sector report),

In the following sections, it is included, as examples, companies that use High Performance practices.

T10.9.1 FerroNATS

FerroNATS (Table 10.10) provides the aerodrome control service that manages the operations of aircraft and vehicles within its area of responsibility, both on land and in the air.

Size	+ 130
Products	Air Traffic control services
Location	Spain
Established	2011
Ownership	Ferrovial Services and NATS

Table 10.10 FerroNATS characteristics (Source: Hip Air, High performance working practices best cases)

The professional development of the employees in this company have a strategic value, that why this is one of the company's cornerstones. In order to achieve this objective, since its beginnings in 2011, FerroNATS has been putting in place High Performance Practices. These are some examples of human resources programmes aimed at its employees:

- Career path:

The company informs its employees about the opportunities for career progression and growth and encourages its employees to achieve new professional goals.

Through its internal selection policy, FerroNATS encourages its employees to take part in all the company's selection processes, thereby fostering the professional growth of the team.

- Individual Development Programmes:

FerroNATS has been running Individual Development Programs since 2014. These programmes involve the direct participation of the Human Resources Department, the Operations and Training Department, and the Tower Managers of each unit.

- FerroNATS Secondment Programs

2016 saw the start of the FerroNATS Secondment Program whereby control tower and central office staff are seconded for one to six months to the offices of Ferrovial Services or NATS where they join one of the teams there.

The purpose of this programme is to promote the professional development of employees, enabling them to acquire new knowledge and skills, to create a teamwork culture among FerroNATS and its shareholders, to encourage knowledge exchange, to improve professional practices, and to foster networking.

At FerroNATS there is a professional development path (Figure 10.34) which enables its employees to know where they are and to focus their development on an area of interest within the company. This path is defined below:

The benefits of this kind of programs are reciprocal and they have repercussions for both the employee and the company:

- Increase of the employees' motivation
- Increase of the employees' commitment
- Improvements in the working environment among employees
- Decrease of the staff's rotation
- Greater professionalization of the employees in their workstations

Figure 10.34 Areas of interest in FerroNATS

(Source: Hip Air, High performance working practices best cases)

T10.9.2 Fokker Elmo Turkey

The company develops and manufactures high technology products for the aerospace sector and has been operating in Turkey. Fokker Elmo (table 10.11) is accepted as an expert in electrics in planes and plane motors internationally.

Size	302 employees
Products	Electrical Wiring Interconnection Systems
Location	Izmir, Turkey
Established	2007
Ownership	GKN Group

Table 10.11 Fokker Elmo Turkey characteristics

(Source: Hip Air, High performance working practices best cases)

Golden Idea System is one of the initiatives that aim to continuously improve all functions and involve all employees. The purpose of the system is to humanize the workplace, eliminate overly hard work

and teach people how to perform experiments on their work using the scientific method and how to learn to spot and eliminate waste in business processes.

There are some of the benefits of Golden Idea System:

- Less waste: inventory is used more efficiently as are employee skills
- People are more satisfied: they have a direct impact on the way things are done
- Improved commitment: team members have more of a stake in their job and are more inclined to commit to doing a good job
- Improved competitiveness: increases in efficiency tend to contribute to higher quality products
- Improved customer satisfaction: coming from higher quality products with fewer faults
- Improved problem solving: looking at processes from a solutions perspective allows employees to solve problems continuously
- Improved teams: working together to solve problems helps build and strengthen existing teams

T10.9.3 Groundforce

This is (Table 10.12) an aircraft ground service company.

Size	2335 employees
Products	Auxiliary activities to Air Transport (ground handling activities)
Location	Lisbon, also operates in Oporto, Funchal and Porto Santo Airports.
Established	2003
Ownership	Private/Public/mixed owned

Table 10.12 Groundforce characteristics
(Source: Hip Air, High performance working practices best cases)

Given the fact that Groundforce is a labour-intensive aviation company, that works on shifts, responding to the different flows of the operation (by season, by operational peak, by day of the week, per day) and the inevitable irregularities resulting from an operation that is intended to be just in time, employees are mainly hired for operational areas located on passenger, ramp, baggage terminal and cargo areas according to the specific job description with inherent soft skills.

Prior to their admission, there is a training paid package for each job function with eliminatory stages (according to IATA and ANAC procedures) that also includes on job training, with a binding opinion of a tutor (senior employee on airside operation). This training package allows the company to ensure the compliance with industry regulations and carrying out a first screening of operational talent in the organization. Soft skills are provided by external consultants that respond to strategic training aspects (leadership, communication, assertiveness, coaching, mentoring, etc.).

Other general training in Security, Airside Safety, Dangerous Goods Regulation, Human Factors and OSH (occupational safety and health) at work is given by internal trainers with that specified qualification.

Thanks to the training received, employees have a better perception of the company, its directions, workflows, processes, procedures and are more satisfied with working conditions. Safety is the main focus and employees feel it top-down and everybody assesses the other ones in the same way. Employees also feel that technology has come to stay, revolutionizing forms and methods of work, internal communication and the relationship with different stakeholders.

T10.9.4 Global Training & Aviation (GTA)

They are experts in the operation of full flight simulators. GTA (Table 10.13) invest in high quality training equipment and instructors to provide the most reliable and professional training.

Size	+150 employees
Products	Aviation Training Solutions
Location	Spain & Indonesia.
Established	2002

Table 10.13 Global Training & Aviation characteristics
(Source: Hip Air, High performance working practices best cases)

One of the pillars of Global Training Aviation is the communication between its employees. There exists an information network which connects all employees and generates a very effective communication and it also contributes to make the employee feel involved in circumstances which are not necessary of his main accountability. GTA is based (figure 10.35) on the maximum employees' involvement making them, part of the whole company's functions and tasks. This is applied to all company's positions, so we can find that the Executive Director is developing basic and technical tasks of a project.

Global Training Aviation offers a more effective training through reinforcing the emotional and personal element of teaching. At the same time, GTA stands up for technological excellence which is reflected in its business:

- All the instructors are staff in active in airlines and they share and transmit their passion for what they are explaining.
- The company always uses E-learning and CBTs with the support of an instructor. • Custom tracking is performed during the student's evolution in order to detect and anticipate to possible learning issues.
- Along the training process each instructor receives a personal report of the student from the previous instructor. This lets the instructor know which the student's strengths and weakness are.
- The training schedule is adapted to the multi-culturalism of GTA's students, building a "tailor-made" training process.

Figure 10.35 Factors on which GTA is based
(Source: Hip Air, High performance working practices best cases)

T10.9.5 FTB Lisi Aerospace

The company (Table 10.14) presents the following characteristics:

Size	555 employees
Products	Fasteners for airplanes
Location	Izmir, Turkey
Established	Year 2001
Ownership	Lisi- Fastener Technology

Table 10.14 FTB Lisi Aerospace characteristics
(Source: Hip Air, High performance working practices best cases)

FTB is executing “Lisi Excellence Achievement Program (LEAP Project)” since March 2013, which aims to involve employees to every application/ step at all levels in the company.

The five LEAP principles (figure 10.36) are the following ones:

- Eliminating waste, rework and other recurrent situations at all levels by getting to the origin cause
- Having progress-oriented attitudes at work
- Viewing matters under a different light: The 3 reals: observing facts in the floor with the process workers
- Putting in place work standards produced by the process workers, and checking and improving these standards
- As a matter of routine, think: HSE, quality and then production

Figure 10.36 LEAP Project principles
(Source: Hip Air, High performance working practices best cases)

T10.9.6 MTU Aero Engines Polska

The company (Table 10.15) presents the following characteristics:

Size	580 employees
Products	Aviation business
Location	Rzeszow/ Jasionka, Poland
Established	2008
Ownership	MTU Aero Engines

Table 10.15 MTU Aero Engines characteristics
(Source: Hip Air, High performance working practices best cases)

MTU Aero Engines Polska is an active member of Aviation Valley in Podkarpackie region. During the first years, within the company there were different standards of attitude, work and values, since most employees came from other companies. The company noticed that company culture influences everyday business and decided to carry out Company Culture Surveys, which showed them the directions to be followed.

As a result, the company decided to focus on values such as healthy life style and teamwork and proposed several activities to create team spirit and engagement, improve health, practice hobbies and business together. In addition, the company created a virtual special agent named "Health", who promotes healthy activities at work.

T10.9.7 Pratt & Whitney Rzeszów S.A.

The company presents the following characteristics in the table 10.16:

Size	3500 employees
Products	Aircraft engine manufacturers

Location	Rzeszow, Poland
Established	1937
Ownership	United Technologies Company (UTC)

Table 10.16 Pratt and Whitney Rzeszów S.A characteristics
(Source: Hip Air, High performance working practices best cases)

Pratt&Whitney Rzeszów is an important element of the chain of world aerospace component suppliers and aircraft engine manufacturers. One of the initiatives of carried out by the company is Techno Tour, which aims to change the culture of the firm, and stimulate the activity of the employees, strengthening their sense of belonging to the company. The program will acquaint the employees with the key specialties, technology and strategic areas of the organisation.

T10.9.8 The Southwest Airlines

The company presents the following characteristics in the table 10.17:

Size	46000 employees
Products	Airline industry
Location	Dallas, USA
Established	31 years ago
Ownership	Southwest Airlines Company Institutional

Table 10.17 The Southwest Airlines characteristics
(Source: Hip Air, High performance working practices best cases)

Southwest Airlines has focused on relationships to improve the quality and efficiency of its performance. The organisation works hard at enhancing team building skills by giving employees training for relational competence. In terms of hiring, the company prefer new people who are able to integrate smoothly with other members on a team. With this strategy, every employee share company goals regardless of the functional area in which they work. In this way, it allows them to respond in a coordinated way whenever new challenges arise, or new information becomes available. It also provides a context by which decisions can be made and information shared.

10.6 – Retaining the Fidelity of Employees

The traditional model of society of lifetime work in a company still exists in countries like Japan but is presented by some as a 'lack of mobility', so that the US is a good and Europe is a bad example. In fact, the mobility of employment has more to do with cultural traditions than with company efficiency: are Japanese companies with stable employment less efficient than American companies with volatile employment? The trade surplus of Japan versus the United States tends to suggest the reverse. The fact that Japanese run factories in the US are often more efficient than American run companies also suggests that worker-management relations at an informal level are a contributor to productivity. Worker mobility is essential to allow the more capable to find jobs where their skills are put to better use for the benefit of society, but there is nothing wrong with a company gaining the fidelity of its employees by giving them good working conditions, competitive wages, stable job prospects and

also the prospect of eventual retirement without major concerns. Cooperation with worker unions, if possible, is preferable to confrontation.

Retired workers can also continue to be of benefit to their former employers, by their testimonials of job satisfaction that may help recruit others with comparable competence and allegiance. An interesting example is the Museum of Safran at Villaroche that is run by former employees. Besides having a good collection of company products past and present, it also serves as a meeting place just outside restricted premises. As former employees the 'keepers' of the museum have first-hand knowledge about some the exhibits that were part of their work. They edit documentation about the most famous company products and sell some nice models at reasonable prices. Everyone benefits: the company with a well-run museum, the former employers with a part-time work of their choice and the visitors with knowledge and crafts of their hosts.

The satisfaction employees (Key Topic T10.10) is closely related to the stability of the workforce (Key Topic T10.11).

KEY TOPIC T10.10 – SATISFACTION OF EMPLOYEES

In the journey of the consolidation of a company, employees and collaborators have a key role cooperating for the same goal. In a job environment it is usual that some employees are dissatisfied with their work due to the fact that their conditions in the company are not optimal, so they end up leaving the company which causes a constant rotation in the organizations.

Clearly this is a negative point for the company due to it generates distrust and instability besides it increases the costs in the search and recruiting of new personnel. Thus, keeping the employees is an essential requirement in order to make the company successful.

Related to that, sometimes the wages do not match the working hours or the quantity or, even worse, the quality of the job done by the employees. The fact that an employee feels that he is not valued by the company is completely subjective in such a way that many times increasing wages is not the solution to make the employee happy at work but also the company should provide the employee with the right environment in which he feels comfortable. However, it is also important that the company pays fair and competitive wages according to the job itself and according to the rest of the market.

Additionally, in a market where people work about 8 hours a day it is difficult to find the right moment to solve personal issues thereby employees' value positively having flexibility at work. If a company provide the employees with an environment where schedule changes and other facilities are possible, employees will be willing to stay working for the firm as they feel comprehension and empathy from the company.

Another important factor is that employees feel that their bosses appreciate their work in the company. In this manner, the experience and commitment of the employees along the years should be valued by the company thus it strengthens employees' loyalty.

Definitely, some actions that a company can carry out to improve workers experience are develop, foster and reward the training of employees, the public and private recognition, facilitate schedule flexibility, give opportunities for professional improvement, provide laptop and/or mobile phone for work, value the opinions expressed by the employees, create a good work environment for workers,

promote business trips and so on. In conclusion, at present it is not about to reward the employee in an individual way but nowadays teamwork is the most fostered practice and it is a practice increasingly extended by the benefits it produces, both in the organization and in the employees themselves.

KEY TOPIC T10.11 – STABILITY OF THE WORKFORCE

Employee fidelity can be defined as employees who are devoted to the success of their organization and believe that being an employee of this organization is in their best interest. Not only do they plan to remain with the organization, but they do not actively seek for alternative employment opportunities⁵¹

What is identified in US as a “mobility problem” is a combination of the behavioural loyalty (the perception of the shortage in the labour market) and the Peter Principle (promotion of a person until it reaches its level of incompetence)⁵². A favouring factor in this approach in US is the huge size of the workforce in Aerospace: over 700 000 people employed, compared with about 400 000 in Europe and nearly the same figure in China⁵³. The average productivity (sales per employee) in Japan Aerospace industry is higher (12%) than its US counterpart⁵⁴.

Workforce issues in aerospace are near the top of the list of challenges facing the industry. A significant number of workers in aerospace are eligible for retirement or approaching retirement eligibility in the next five years. Unfortunately, the uncertainty of workforce retirement makes it difficult to plan for the future. Regardless of these issues, companies have to ensure they maintain current expertise while forecasting future hiring needs, such as what skill sets will be needed and when to hire for them⁵⁵

In the fight for talent, aerospace companies face industry-specific challenges. To recruit and retain talent, especially people with the STEM (Scientific, Technical, Engineering, Maths) skills that are so highly prized in many different industries (with critical skills for today and emerging skill requirements for the future). It is currently considered of great importance how best to ensure the transfer of talent from older to younger employees, an issue that is becoming more acute as the older employees retire. They have a relatively high proportion of older workers (approximately 60% of aerospace employees are over age 45 vs. 44% in the overall US workforce. Conversely, approximately 42% of aerospace employees is under age 44 vs. 56% in the overall workforce)⁵⁶.

This lopsided demographic mix, coupled with high attrition rates and increased labour mobility, poses serious risks to the industry. Companies can mitigate the risks with employee retention and succession planning. But as retirement rates creep up, it’s increasingly important to approach the issue of succession in a systematic way that includes leaders and management as well as critical technical employees.

The loyalty of the workforce in an aerospace organization is a very important ingredient in the quality of the output. The first determinant is pay. The average hourly wages in aerospace industry, at \$45

⁵¹ Susan DeFranzo: “Tips to Improve Employee Loyalty” in <https://www.snapsurveys.com/blog>

⁵² Nik Penhale Smith: “The employee mobility problem” in <https://www.effactory.com/knowledge/blog>

⁵³ ***Deloitte Touche Tohmatsu Limited, <http://reports.weforum.org/manufacturing-growth/aerospace-industry-infographics/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.wolframalpha.com/>

⁵⁵ Jim Adams: “**Will the A&D workforce be prepared for the future?**” in <http://usblogs.pwc.com/industrialinsights/>

⁵⁶ Ibidem

(compared with \$30 in automotive industry and \$28 in manufacturing overall), is surpassed only by the \$46 in coal and petroleum⁵⁷ However, such a very meagre gain in pay in the extractive industries is not attractive when the working conditions are considered. The working conditions are the second determinant. And an “esprit de corps” (a feeling of pride and mutual loyalty) is probably the third. This happy combination makes employment in aerospace desirable and competitive within the labour market. What would further enhance the fidelity of the employees? Obviously, a perceived high job security (a reduced risk of being made redundant), a good and reliable pension system, an effective health insurance scheme and an optional extension of the retirement age could only increase the attractiveness and the excitement of the employment in aerospace and retain talent, especially people with the STEM skills.

⁵⁷ <http://usblogs.pwc.com/industrialinsights/>

Chapter 11 – Increasing the Participation of Women in Aerospace

The factors that affect the professional career of women may not be too apparent in childhood (section 11.1) but may have effects in secondary school (section 11.2) and university (section 11.3). The employment opportunities for women (section 11.4) should offer the guarantees of equal treatment (section 11.5) and protection of maternity (section 11.6). The recognition of on the job achievements should include reasonable allowance for special circumstances (section 11.7) and acknowledge the benefits of complementary (section 11.8). The increased participation of women in the aerospace sector is not only a numerical enlargement of the workforce, but also a qualitative enhancement by additional and unique talent (section 11.9).

11.1 Family Influences in Childhood

The traditional attitudes of family and friends that ‘girls play with dolls and boys play with cars’ may already be influencing future career choices. Two real life examples illustrate the trend.

The first example concerns a distinguished lady professor at university, who became head of department of electrical engineering and well renowned for her work on speech acoustics. Her father had a larger Mecano collection, built up during his entire life. When he became too old to use it, he offered it to a nephew, rather than to his daughter. It did not occur him otherwise, although he was a good and dedicated father.

Another example concerns a very bright and mature 6-year-old girl. Her father had a collection of model cars which she freely used in her playtime. Her father also had a collection of real cars, where she travelled in a child seat in the rear bench. As soon as the car stopped, and the father left for some activity, she would sit next to her mother on the driver position and try to drive the car. The father offered her a driving simulator, with which she would drive the car from the rear child seat, imitating the use of controls of the real car by her father.

Once the father gave her a bigger car model and the mother objected: “why are you giving our daughter a car? She is a girl: you should give her a doll”. Well the father had already given her many dolls, and this was the first car. If a boy wanted a doll what would be the reaction?

The Pre-Conceptions about the roles of activities of men and women arise at an early stage and should be countered for girls and boys as soon as possible (Key Topic 11.1).

KEY TOPIC T11.1 – COUNTERING PRE-CONCEPTIONS INDUCED BY SOCIETY ON GIRLS AND BOYS

Research on students’ self-efficacy in math and science subjects shows a startling reality: girls and boys begin developing gender stereotypes and self-selecting out of these subjects as early as second grade. By the time girls reach high school, they make up only 25 percent of students pursuing science and engineering pathways. According to the U.S. Department of Education, in 2015 women earned fewer than 19 percent of bachelor’s degrees in engineering.

Microsoft commissioned a research to understand better what causes girls and women to lose interest in STEM subjects and careers, as well as what strategies and interventions have the greatest potential to reverse this trend. Some of the main results are presented (Figures 11.1 – 11.7) as follows:

Figure 11.1 – Do girls lose interest in STEAM as they get older?

(Source: <https://query.prod.cms.rt.microsoft.com/cms/api/am/binary/RE1UMWz>)

Figure 11.2 – How do real world examples change perceptions of STEM?

(Source: <https://query.prod.cms.rt.microsoft.com/cms/api/am/binary/RE1UMWz>)

Figure 11.3 – What is the impact of female role model?

(Source: <https://query.prod.cms.rt.microsoft.com/cms/api/am/binary/RE1UMWz>)

Figure 11.4 – What is the benefit of STEM learning outside of the classroom?

(Source: <https://query.prod.cms.rt.microsoft.com/cms/api/am/binary/RE1UMWz>)

Figure 11.5 – How likely are girls to choose STEM classes in high school?

(Source: <https://query.prod.cms.rt.microsoft.com/cms/api/am/binary/RE1UMWz>)

Figure 11.6 – What difference does encouragement make?
(Source: <https://query.prod.cms.rt.microsoft.com/cms/api/am/binary/RE1UMWz>)

Figure 11.7 – What happens when support is combined?
(Source: <https://query.prod.cms.rt.microsoft.com/cms/api/am/binary/RE1UMWz>)

Attracting girls to STEM in Schools

Across the EU there are a wealth of communication campaigns and initiatives seeking to attract young people and women to take up jobs in different aspects of the transport sector. This corresponds to evidence of skills shortages and needs relating to an ageing workforce and other limitations on transportation jobs. There is also an assumption that some of the barriers to employment relate to a lack of or ineffective promotion of jobs and/or that there is a need to support and reinforce communication activities in this area.

Directorate General for Mobility and Transport (DG MOVE) project identified 10 **specific communication practices and strategies** that can **promote transport jobs effectively to young people and women**. Among them, the most relevant concerning women attraction in primary and secondary are **“Showcasing real people as role models”** and **“Going into schools, colleges and universities”**.

1. **“Showcasing real people as role models”** - Firstly, mirroring is an important aspect of targeting. This is where communications confirm, albeit on a subliminal level, that the communication is relevant because it reflects the targeted individual. This is highlighted by the significant use of women and young people to confirm that people with these profiles work in different transport sectors. In order to really influence young people on the prospects of jobs in transport, it is necessary to provide them with **concrete examples**, which show what it would be like for them. One of the ways to do this is to provide a platform for young people or women **doing the job** to tell others what it is about. For instance, **Women in Logistics (WIL), UK**, is a networking group, which focusses on three key activities: networking, mentoring and showcasing. WIL aims to provide a platform for women to be part of the wider debate about logistics issues. Three examples of showcasing are highlighted below.

- At WIL networking events, women are given **opportunities to be at the front** to talk about their own experiences and to lead the debate on logistics issues.
- WIL identifies other relevant events and debates and where there is an all-male panel speaking then WIL will make contact and offer help to the organisers so that they are able to put forward **a more diverse line up**.
- WIL also runs an annual awards event, which showcases **very successful women**, putting them in a position where they can be role models for other women in the sector, who can see what can be achieved.

‘Women in Motion’, in Italy, was a Ferrovie project where they selected 80 successful women under the age of 45, working in technical jobs to provide positive examples of young women working in the rail sector. These women visited girls in high schools, and told them their **personal story** and experiences, trying to **overcome the stereotype of girls and proposing the rail industry as a valid career option**. During these meetings, girls had the chance to establish a personal contact, to ask questions and to get more insights.

2. **Going into schools, colleges and universities”** - Secondly, as decisions on future career choices are typically made by young people in an education setting, several organisations addressed this issue by generating opportunities for direct face-to-face contact in schools and colleges by:
 - developing a plan of events in many schools – visiting one or two schools is not enough;
 - not relying on careers fairs – where it can be difficult to compete for attention;
 - working with careers advisors;
 - training job coaches on company processes and taking them to schools;
 - bringing apprentices to talk to school children;
 - offering work experience to school children;
 - helping schools to develop employability skills training/curriculum.

Promoting an increase in the number of female recruits only addresses part of the problem, transport organisations need to:

- Support female **career progression**;
- **Recognise the contribution** of female employees; and
- Facilitate more **flexible working** for carers (male or female).

Finally, it is crucial to mention that promotional efforts which engage young people on a face-to-face basis work well, particularly when they:

- Provide **opportunities to explain** what is involved in the range of jobs available;
- Help young people to understand the **fit** between their skills and transport job;
- Give young people opportunities to **meet others** who are employed in these jobs;
- Effective promotion must be **highly tailored** to correspond to what potential recruits' need.

Besides that, many of the individuals interviewed for this DGMove highlighted:

- What they saw as deficiencies in the **quality and availability of information on the transport sector in public life**;
- The **school curriculum does not necessarily equip young people with the skills** that are needed to be attractive and employable to employers, or enough understanding of what is involved in the wide range of roles available.

Teachers can adopt a growth mindset and explicitly teach female students that academic abilities are expandable and improvable to enhance girls' beliefs about their abilities. Middle school math and science teachers should establish a challenging curriculum focused on exploratory learning that engages female students in risk taking and problem solving to build their confidence in math and science. Girls who are more confident in their abilities to engage in math and science curriculum are more likely to pursue challenging courses in math and science in high school. Middle school math and science teachers should also provide female students with specific feedback on ways to improve their performance and nurture their spatial reasoning skills. This can be done by incorporating teaching and learning practices that build on a student's prior knowledge and help the student make connections. Finally, teachers should avoid any negative stereotypes when working with female students in math and science. They can avoid stereotypes by encouraging female students to enter science fairs, join math competitions or robotic teams, and choose activities that spark inquiry learning and interest in math and science. Additionally, teachers can engage female students in STEM experiences that become transformative, such as hands-on science activities, exploratory trips and field experiences, and positive interactions with female role models.

Attracting girls to STEM outside schools

WISE, campaign for gender balance in science, technology and engineering enables and energises people in business, industry and education to increase the participation, contribution and success of women in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM). WISE members inspire girls to choose maths, physics and computing. WISE members attract, retain, develop and progress female talent in their companies. Our mission – gender parity in the UK's scientific, technology and engineering workforce – from classroom to boardroom.

11.2 Primary and Secondary Schools

In the past separate boys and girl schools tended to put greater influence on girls away from science and technology, even if the curricula were the same, because they induced different choices: majority humanities for girls and majority science for boys, with significant minorities otherwise.

The current practice of mixed primary and secondary schools means that there are similar opportunities for both boys and girls, as far as their choices are not too much influenced by educators, relatives and friends and these young people have their own inclinations and are willing to follow them, which may not be entirely straightforward.

One consequence of all this, sometimes imperceptible, conditioning from childhood is that girls who choose science and engineering tend to be more determined, and due to their strong motivation may achieve better results at university on average than boys.

The gender imbalance in general is either reflected in or a consequence of gender imbalance in education, with different choices according to gender (Key Topic T11.2).

KEY TOPIC T11.2 – GENDER IMBALANCE IN SOCIETY AND IN EDUCATION

Gender parity is an essential issue to understand whether and how economies and societies thrive. In addition, it has a great influence on the growth, competitiveness and future-readiness of economies and businesses worldwide.

According to the Global Gender Gap Report, in 2017, the average progress on closing the global gender gap stands at 68%, which means that an average gap of 32% remains to be closed worldwide in order to achieve universal gender parity.

Figure 11.8 shows the average gender gap that remains to be closed in each world region. At a global level, four regions have a remaining gender gap of less than 30%. Western Europe records a remaining gender gap of 25%, placing it ahead of North America, with a gap of 28%, Eastern Europe and Central Asia, with a gap of 29%, and Latin America and the Caribbean, with a gap of 30%. The East Asia and the Pacific region rank ahead of Sub-Saharan Africa, with a remaining gender gap of 31.7% and 32.4%, respectively, and South Asia, with a gap of 34%. Finally, the last position corresponds to the Middle

East and North Africa, with a gender gap of 40%, which means that it is the region with the higher gender gap to be closed.

Figure 11.8 - Distance from gender parity 2017, by region
(Source: The Global Gender Gap Report, 2017)

Figure 11.9 shows the evolution of the global gender gap since 2006 by geographic region, considering that one means gender equality and zero means gender inequality. It highlights the local progress towards gender parity made over the past decade in regions such as Western Europe, South Asia, Sub-Saharan Africa, Latin America and the Caribbean. While all regions have recorded a narrower gender gap that they did 11 years ago, the figure nevertheless also reveals that more efforts will continue to be needed in all world regions to accelerate progress.

Figure 11.9 - Global gender gap index evolution, 2006-2017, by region
(Source: The Global Gender Gap Report, 2017)

According to the Global Gender Gap Report, if all things held equal, with current rates of progress, the overall global gender gap can be closed in 61 years in Western Europe, 62 years in South Asia, 79 years in Latin America and the Caribbean, 102 years in Sub-Saharan Africa, 128 years in Eastern Europe and Central Asia, 157 years in North America, 161 years in East Asia and the Pacific, and 168 years in the Middle East and North Africa.

These forecasts reflect the current state of progress and serve as a call to action to policymakers and other stakeholders to accelerate gender equality.

Once the global gender gap has been analysed, the objective of the following points is analysing this gender gap from the education perspective, both for global and European level.

2. Education

2.1 Global level

The world, taken as a whole, has achieved the target of gender parity at all levels except tertiary education. However, this is not true of all regions, country income groups or individual countries. Only 66% of countries have achieved gender parity in primary education, 45% in lower secondary and 25% in upper secondary. (Global education monitoring report gender review, 2018).

Between 2000 and 2015, the share of countries that achieved gender parity in primary education increased by 8 percentage points and in upper secondary education by 14 percentage points (Figure 11.10).

Figure 11.10 - Percentage of countries by level of gender parity index of gross enrolment ratio, by education level, 2000 and 2015

(Source: Global education monitoring report gender review, 2018)

As it can be seen from the previous figure 11.10, more countries have achieved gender parity, but disparities persist, especially at higher education levels.

On the other hand, the world is still a long way from ensuring that all children, adolescents and youth, of either gender, are enrolled in school. In 2015, there were 264 million primary and secondary age children and youth out of school. This includes some 61 million children of primary school age, 62 million adolescents of lower secondary school age and 141 million youth of upper secondary school. After a decline in the early 2000s, out-of-school rates have stagnated.

Gender disparities in out-of-school rate have narrowed substantially over the last 15 years. Globally, a gap exists only in primary education: 9,7% of primary school-age girls and 8,1% of boys are out of school. In lower and upper secondary education, there is parity overall, but disparities emerge at regional level.

In tertiary education, only 4% of countries have achieved parity, with the gender imbalance increasingly at the expense of males. Overall, there are more females than males in tertiary education in almost all regions. However, in many countries, although women outnumber men as graduates, they lag behind men in completing science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM degrees). That is, women are a majority of university graduates, but a minority of STEM graduates (Figure 11.11):

Figure 11.11 - Percentage of female graduates from science, technology, engineering and mathematics programmes and all tertiary programmes, 2015
(Source: Global education monitoring report gender review, 2018)

2.2 European level

Once it has been analysed the gender gap in education at a global level, in this section it is included several specific examples for the European Union related to gender parity in education.

2.2.1 Primary and secondary education

The number of students found in each of the earliest levels of education varies between the EU Member States. This reflects, to some degree, the demographic structure of each population and also country-specific policies relating to the provision of primary and secondary education.

In the European Union, there were 28, 7 million students in primary education in 2015. The 49% of these students were women and the 51% were men, as is shown in Figure 11.12:

Figure 11.12 - Distribution of students by gender in primary education, 2015
(Source: Eurostat statistics)

Therefore, the gender distribution in primary education was balanced. In secondary education, an analysis of graduates from upper secondary (Figure 11.13) and post-secondary non-tertiary education (Figure 11.14) shows differences between the sexes. Generally, in upper secondary education, the gender distribution was relatively balanced while among post-secondary non-tertiary education graduates there was a fairly clear pattern of more female than male graduates.

Figure 11.13 - Distribution of upper secondary education graduates by sex, 2015
(Source: Eurostat statistics)

Figure 11.14 - Distribution of post-secondary non-tertiary education graduates by sex, 2015
(Source: Eurostat statistics)

2.2.2 Tertiary education

Tertiary education, which is provided by universities and other higher education institutions, is the level of education following secondary schooling. It plays an essential role in society, by fostering innovation, increasing economic development and growth.

In the European Union, there were 19,5 million tertiary education students in 2015, of which 46% were men and the 54% were women (Figure 11.15):

Figure 11.15 - Distribution of tertiary education students by sex, 2015
(Source: Eurostat statistics)

If it is analysed the different levels of the tertiary education, it is obtained that the share of women among tertiary students was slightly higher among those studying for master's degrees (57%), somewhat lower for those studying for Bachelor' degrees (53%) and following short-cycle courses (52%). For doctoral students, however, the majority (52%) of students were men (Figure 11.16):

Figure 11.16 - Distribution of tertiary education students by level and sex, 2015
(Source: Eurostat)

On the other hand, different choices across study fields between women and men is a relevant characteristic of gender differences in education patterns in the European Union.

Across the European Union, almost one third (32%) of all students in tertiary education were studying social sciences, journalism, information, business, administration or law in 2015. There were considerably more females than male students studying social sciences, with women accounting for 57% of all students with this field of education (Figure 11.17). The second most common field of education was engineering, manufacturing and construction-related studies which accounted for 15% of all tertiary education students. In this field, almost three quarters (74%) of all students were male. The third largest field of study was health and welfare, with a 13% share of all tertiary education students. In this field, women accounted for close to three quarters (72%) of the total number of tertiary students. Among the remaining fields of education shown in Figure 11.17, the highest share of female students was recorded for those studying education (where 77% of all students were women), while women accounted for almost two thirds (64%) of all students studying arts and humanities. By contrast, within natural sciences, mathematics, statistics and information and communication technologies the share of men in the total number of tertiary students was 61%.

Figure 11.17 - Distribution of tertiary education students by field and sex, European Union, 2015
(Source: Eurostat)

Therefore, taken as a base the results showed in the figure 11.17, it is concluded that science, technology, engineering and mathematics fields of study are much more prevalent among men, whereas social sciences, health and humanities are much more common among women.

2.2.3 Teaching staff

Analysing the number of teachers (Figure 11.18) in primary and secondary education, there is a clear dominance of female over male teachers. In 2015, 2, 2 million persons worked as primary school teachers in the European Union. Women were predominant, accounting for 85%. In addition, there were an estimated 1.9 million lower secondary teachers in the European Union in 2015 and a slightly lower number (1.6 million) of upper secondary teachers. Within lower secondary education in 2015, men accounted for 32 % of all teachers, while in upper secondary education men accounted for 40 %, 8 percentage points more. In relation to teaching staff in tertiary education, there were 1,4 million people teaching in tertiary education in the European Union in 2015, of which the 58% were men and the 42% were women.

Therefore, in contrast to the teaching staff in primary and secondary education, where women were the majority, in tertiary education the majority of teaching staff were men.

Figure 11.18 - Distribution of teaching staff by gender, 2015
(Source: Eurostat)

11.3 Choice of University Degrees

For a long time, most women who choose engineering at university opted for Chemical Engineering, where in many cases the majority of students were girls; in contrast few girls chose other branches of engineering like civil or mechanical engineering. The anecdotal explanation that chemical engineering is closer to cooking carries no substance and is just one more form of biased judgement.

The real explanation may be that in former times a lady civil engineer might feel uncomfortable among uneducated construction workers, and a lady mechanical engineer might not be at ease in a factory shop full of rough workers, although some could brave the situation successfully. A better prospect for women inclined towards science would be to work in a chemical laboratory or medical profession less distributed by the pre-conceptions and discriminations of society.

The situation has improved significantly in both respects. More branches of engineering put more emphasis on office and laboratory work, like engineering design and informatics. The attitudes of society have improved with regard to gender equality and respectful treatment, though not to the extent of overcoming all barriers.

Nevertheless, the progress is noticeable in some aerospace engineering degrees: from 10% women 30 years ago, to 20% women 15 years ago to 30% women now. It is a slow progress, on the scale of one step by generation; 30% is already a not too small minority showing how much more room for improvement still remains.

Although girls perform as well or better than boys in STEM subjects several external factors influence their choices in other directions (Key Topic T11.3)

KEY TOPIC T11.3 – PERFORMANCE AND CHOICES OF WOMEN CONCERNING STEM

1. Choice of STEM Subjects

The National Centre for Universities and Business offer an excellent infographic poster, (Figure 11.19) Talent2030 Dashboard, which shows progress to their targets for women in engineering. In 2017, one of their targets was met: 50% of Physics GCSE students were girls.

Figure 11.19 - Women in STEM subjects in the UK

In 2016, the proportion of women in full-time engineering faculty posts in Canada was 14.9 percent, a 1.5 percent rise since 2012.

The number of women graduating in a core STEM subject has continued to grow for another year (Figure 11.20). These women are talented individuals qualified to take up the exciting opportunities available in STEM and help address the persistent skills gaps across the UK. However, due to more rapid growth in the number of men graduating in these subject areas the percentage of graduates who are women has dropped from 25% to 24%.

Figure 11.20 - Evolution of women in STEM subjects

Whilst WISE are encouraged by the growth in women pursuing core STEM education at all levels, they are still severely underrepresented in areas such as engineering and computing.

We would encourage universities to engage more women to apply by reviewing their marketing materials, entry requirements and offering taster days to women before they apply – actions which have had a marked impact in the apprenticeship sphere. WISE can support universities to tackle this challenge. Additionally, universities should consider training their outreach officers in People Like Me to help them engage effectively with local schools and prospective students.

Women graduating in core STEM subjects

Encouragingly for the third year in a row, the growth rate in the number of women graduates in physical science (Figure 11.21) has exceeded that of men. Women now represent 41% of graduates in physical sciences, perhaps a sign that concerted efforts to encourage girls to consider studying physics may be starting to reap the rewards.

Figure 11.21 - Women in physical science

In mathematical sciences, the number of women graduates has remained static at 39 % since 2015/16 (Figure 11.22):

Figure 11.22 - Women in mathematical sciences

However, in computer science the growth in the number of female graduates is well behind the growth in the number of male graduates (3.1% vs 9% respectively). This year women represent just 15% of computing graduates, down from 16% last year (Figure 11.23):

Figure 11.23 - Women in computer science

The picture is similarly disappointing in engineering where for the third year in a row, women represent just 14% of graduates (Figure 11.24):

Figure 11.24 - Women in Engineering and Technology

The only core STEM area where the number of women graduates has decreased is Architecture, Building and Planning subjects where the women now represent just 27% of graduates compared to 35% in 2015/16 (Figure 11.25):

Figure 11.25 - Women in architecture, building and planning

Despite the continued growth in most core STEM areas, they still lag behind other STEM degrees on gender balance (Figure 11.26):

Figure 11.26 - Women in STEM areas

2. Why not choose STEM?

A study of 1,327 Swedish secondary school students explored why more boys are attracted to STEM subjects at university and more girls are attracted to subjects in the Heed (health, elementary education and domestic) spheres.

This difference was partially explained by “social belongingness”: teenagers felt they would fit in better in subjects that had more of their own gender. But another important factor was “self-efficacy”: the belief that one can succeed in a domain. We tend to approach domains where we feel we are competent and avoid those in which we do not. Boys and girls both had high self-efficacy in the Heed

subjects, but boys chose not to pursue them. The researchers suggest that this may reflect the low social value and rewards associated with careers in these spheres.

In contrast, girls on average had much lower self-efficacy ratings in Stem, despite outperforming boys across school subjects. Even in one of the most gender-neutral countries in the world and despite the evidence of their own marks, girls still seem to be succumbing to the stereotype that girls aren't as capable in these subjects.

3. University environment influence on women persistence in STEM fields and careers

Women in engineering majors enter college with the same levels of interest and intent to persist in the major as male peers, yet fewer women complete undergraduate degrees in STEM fields and persist into related careers (National Science Board 2016).

Overall, research shows **that women who have positive experiences in STEM majors via supportive faculty members and peers, research experiences, or participation in engineering organizations are more likely to continue taking STEM classes, complete degrees and continue on to post baccalaureate STEM careers** in comparison to those who do not (Beyer 2014; Gayles and Ampaw 2016; Hughes 2010; Kezar and Holcombe 2017; Litzler and Young 2012; Marra et al. 2009; Neumann et al. 2016; Ro 2011).

Many women in science and engineering report experiences with discrimination and bias that make it difficult to persist and succeed in their majors. Women in science and engineering have a long history of feeling **marginalized, isolated, and subject to stereotype** threats within their majors, a feeling that tends to grow over time (Marra et al. 2009; Neumann et al. 2016). **Favouritism and differential treatment** also detract from positive experiences that increase persistence and academic success for women, as male and female **faculty in science and engineering have been found to favour and be more responsive to male students in comparison to females** (Milkman et al. 2015; Moss-Racusin et al. 2012). Further, reports of bias in the form of **sexual harassment from classmates and faculty** are all too common for undergraduate women in science and engineering (Morris and Daniel 2008). **Differential treatment and bias towards women in science and engineering** also have negative underlying consequences for women's perceptions of their own abilities. More recent work suggests that **women underestimate their performance on engineering tasks compared to men** (Woodcock and Bairaktarova 2015).

Additional research has shown that **unwelcoming environments contribute to decreased self-confidence, self-efficacy, the tendency behave in self-limiting ways that negatively impact overall success and persistence for women in science and computing** (Haines et al. 2001; Morris and Daniel 2008), with **gender discrimination related to lower academic performance** (Beyer 2008).

4. How to attract women to choose STEM subjects at university?

To attract more girls to study Stem subjects at university and enter Stem careers, we need to tackle the stereotypes they are exposed to and we need to do this early. One way to encourage girls is to use appropriate role models. As part of a campaign to coincide with International Women's

Day, **Speakezee**, a platform that connects academics with non-academic audiences, is working with the Institute of Physics and the Girls' School Association to send young female graduate Stem students into schools to talk to and inspire young teenage girls to consider pursuing Stem topics at A-level. Professor Brian Cox may be the popular face of physics for mass viewing audiences in the UK, but young girls need individuals they are more likely to relate to if they are to be persuaded not to abandon their Stem potential.

11.4 Employment Opportunities in Academia and Industry

Women tend to perform at least as well or better than men on average in university studies and has a relative percentage more proceed to a research and academic career. The underrepresentation of women in academic positions may be a question of time due to the slow promotion in university positions, or an indication that university after all is not so gender equal, or a combination of both.

Concerning employment in government agencies and services there are areas where women are more numerous, but that is mostly the exception, with a still bigger imbalance in industry, which some corporations try to reduce. To attract women industry and services should offer the same incentives as for men plus the assurances of equal treatment.

It may happen that the advertisement for positions is not even, and implicitly stresses factors that are not gender neutral, even when trying to encourage women to apply. It is not only the selection process that needs to be fair, it is also the mechanisms to access potential candidates and the offers that are made to them appeal equally to both genders.

The aviation sector has both jobs requiring STEM skills as well as not (Key Topic T11.4).

KEY TOPIC T11.4 – JOBS IN THE AVIATION SECTOR

1. Women in STEM and Engineering Jobs

The National Centre for Universities and Business offer an excellent infographic poster, Talent 2030 Dashboard, which shows % of female engineering professionals in the UK (Figure 11.27 and 11.28).

Source: Kelly Services. How to Find (and Keep) STEM Talent, 2012

Figure 11.27 - Graduates in STEM

Figure 11.28 - Women graduate in STEM

2. Recruitment

Among 10 good practices identified by **DG Move 2** of them are useful concerning employment opportunities for women.

1. Working with Men to engage Women

In the face of skills shortages and recruitment gaps many transport companies are having to take a hard look at the profile of their workforce and recognise the low and limited representation of women. This study highlighted how successful recruitment strategies recognise the importance of men in any plan to empower women and increase and improve recruitment. Men are part of the solution. Several organisations identified the importance of working with existing male workers to better understand the focus of recruitment promotion. Men can provide insights into the challenges of the work and how best to overcome them. They can engage and support the planned communication actions. It is important not to alienate existing workers, which could happen if they are not consulted or engaged in efforts to recruit more women. In many cases, there is a basic need to make changes to the culture at work so that it is a place where women want to work. This means that men need to recognise the contribution of women and that going forward the company needs women to remain strong.

2. Providing opportunities to experience the job

It is difficult for young people to understand the diverse range of roles available across different transport sectors. The evidence suggests that it is difficult to change minds and behaviours unless people are given opportunities for some form of direct engagement.

'#Nolimitsforwomen', Lufthansa, Germany

As part of its #Nolimitsforwomen week, Lufthansa provided an opportunity for women to apply for a career day with the company. The winner could choose from a wide range of professions mostly in operative areas that are typically male-dominated. Logistics, aircraft maintenance, or the air-traffic control centre; there are many possibilities. In addition to offering a look behind the scenes, the biggest

German airline will provide travel to Lufthansa headquarters as well as accommodation in Frankfurt for the lucky winner.

Agreed with the summary of Barbara Link, a manager at General Electric, about **effective recruitment approaches**, which centre around six elements:

1. The recruiters are engineers, scientists, and managers of engineers and scientists, not the Human Resources Division representatives.
2. Employees chosen as corporate recruiters are those who exhibit strong interpersonal skills, who "care and go the extra mile."
3. Recruitment occurs at a targeted group of universities.
4. The company maintains a corporate presence on each campus, interacting with faculty, students, and staff.
5. Entry-level recruits rotate through a series of technical and management assignments to learn about program opportunities.
6. Co-op programs enable the company to evaluate potential employees while they pursue projects that support the work of the GE laboratories.

Additional linkages with universities have been developed by many companies to identify prospective employees.

3. Employment opportunities in industry that don't need STEM

When we talk about careers in aerospace most people instantly think of pilots and engineering jobs. However, airlines rely on many individuals to perform their job in order to keep them in business. They include baggage handlers, ticket agents, avionics technicians and others. Women should be also aware of this and work should be done in order to attract them to these jobs too.

In fact, air transport services accounts for a variety of employment types (Figure 11.29):

Figure 11.29 - Direct Job by Employment Type
(Source: Economic Impact of European Airports, InterVISTAS)

For instance, to be a cabin crew member there's no necessity to follow STEM education. Some airlines don't even request for a university course and just ask for high school education, as the case of Qatar Airways presented below (Figure 11.30):

Current Opportunities

QR17579 - Cabin Crew Recruitment Event Kiev | 23rd June 2018 | Qatar Airways | Doha

Organisation:	Qatar Airways	Job Function:	Cabin Crew
Division:	Cabin Services (Division)	Employment Type:	Full Time - Permanent
City:	Middle East Qatar Doha	Last date of application:	23-Jun-2018

About You:

To be part of this winning team, you need to meet the following requirements:

- Minimum age of 21 years
- Minimum arm reach of 212 cms on tip toes
- Minimum high school education with fluency in written and spoken English
- Excellent health and fitness
- Willingness to relocate to Doha, Qatar
- Outgoing personality with good interpersonal skills and the ability to work with a multinational team.

Figure 11.30 – Recruitment file from Qatar Airways

Jobs related to ground handling service do not also require STEM education, some professions are:

- Scale Assistance Traffic Technician;
- Baggage Handling;
- Passenger Handling;
- Aircraft Marshaller;
- Ramp Handling;
- Fuel and oil handling services;
- Airport Security;
- Flight dispatcher.

11.5 On-the-Job Treatment and Preventing Abuse

The professional activities are not immune from the problems that affect society in general and must address them to reduce their effects rather than become an excuse of refuge from inappropriate behaviour.

Companies usually take seriously, up to and including grounds for dismissal, two types of inappropriate action, and they should add a third.

An employed that proves to be professionally incompetent and causes disservice to customers or harms the reputation of the company can be rightly dismissed. Similarly, an employee that misuses company resources or fails to carry out important duties may face consequences. Using the workplace an opportunity for gender abuse, whichever way, should have a similar sanction to incompetence or dishonesty, because all three are improper forms of conduct.

In most institutions, including large ones, individual rights are not equally applied. A successful top executive may have much more reward than all others that contributed to the result; a failed worker may be dismissed whereas a failed top executive may have a generous retirement offer that cannot

be refused. Countering gender abuse may face similar difficulties, especially if the culprit is up and the victim down the hierarchical ladder; this should be countered by putting more responsibility on those who have more power and should be more ethical in its use.

The issues of women on the job treatment need to be considered very seriously in order to have access to this major half of the workforce (Key Topic T11.5).

KEY TOPIC T11.5 – INTEGRATION OF WOMEN IN THE AEROSPACE SECTOR

Concerning on-the-job treatment and preventing abuse, there 3 main factors to take into consideration:

1. Women Mentoring Programs;
2. Women job satisfaction determinants;
3. Women Networking.

1. Mentoring

One way that organisations can improve the recruitment and retention of women in the aviation and aerospace industry is by offering support to their female professionals through **mentoring**. Evidence shows that the assistance of a mentor is important for women at all stages in their careers (Ehrich, 2008; Singh et al., 2002; Vinnicombe and Singh, 2002; 2003), but especially in terms of **career advancement** (Durbin and Tomlinson, 2010; 2014; Lineham and Walsh, 1999; Ragins, 1999). Mentoring also acts as a channel for the **exchange of tacit knowledge and information that is often linked with promotion opportunities** (Durbin, 2010; Swap et al., 2001). Mentoring is of particular significance for women as it may help them to **break through the 'glass ceiling'** (Lineham and Walsh, 1999; Ragins, 1999). Mentoring also **increases women's visibility within organisations** (Hersby et al., 2009) and contributes to **raising aspirations and levels of self-confidence** (Institute of Leadership and Management, 2011). However, mentors are harder to come by for women, especially in male-dominated industries (Durbin, 2010; Durbin and Tomlinson, 2014).

Alta is an Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) co-funded project to design a mentoring scheme for women in the aviation and aerospace industry. The project was based on a knowledge-exchange partnership between the **University of West of England**, the **Royal Aeronautical Society (RaeS)**, the **Royal Air Force (RAF)** and **Airbus**. These partner organisations recognised the critical role that women play in their industry and through a **formal mentoring programme, wanted to support their female professionals and encourage more into leadership roles**. Aligned with the project Alta is a mentoring scheme, providing **one-to-one mentoring from successful women, and a network** that's dedicated to ensuring that talented women reach their full career potential, for the benefit not only of individuals but also our industry as a whole.

Alta positive aspects:

- When we asked women what they were specifically looking for from alta, they told us that they were looking for **advice** on careers and behaviours, **access to female role models**, matching with a mentor who could clearly meet their needs, being able to choose a mentor, **clear structure and guidance** on mentoring, the choice **about how to meet (i.e. face to face or via social media)** and involvement in a **mentoring community and attendance at alta networking events**.

- The '**woman to woman**' aspect of *alta* was appealing to most women as they felt other women could help to show them the way, share common experiences and establish woman to woman trust. They also felt that *alta* could ultimately help more women into managerial and leadership roles.
- The project offered **the potential to build a network** of support for women in aviation and aerospace that will lead to an increase in the numbers of women working (and progressing) within what is a vital business sector within the UK economy as a whole.

2. Attention to women's job satisfaction determinants

On job treatment should consider women's determinants for job satisfaction (Table 11.1) and design their jobs ensuring these factors. For instance, in 2015, independence on work, be part of a larger team, valorisation of work by the supervisor, flex time and job stability were pointed as crucial to women workforce in aviation.

Women
Independence in my work
Part of a larger team; supervisor values my contribution; flex time
Job stability

Source: Aviation Week 2015 Workforce Study

Table 11.1 – Some determinants for job satisfaction of women

3. Networking

Establishing networks of women to share experiences and promote opportunities are perceived to be an important element of improving working conditions (DGMove, 2016)

There are several organizations aiming to help women through networking opportunities:

1. **Women in Aviation International** is a non-profit organization dedicated to the encouragement and advancement of women in all aviation career fields and interests. Women in Aviation International provides: education resources, scholarships, outreach programs, annual Conference and Job Fair, girls In Aviation Day (girls ages 8-17) and girl Scout Aviation Patch.
2. Women in Aerospace (WIA) is dedicated to expanding women's opportunities for leadership and increasing their visibility in the aerospace community. Networking is one of the many significant benefits of joining Women in Aerospace. Comprised of individuals from an array of disciplines and technical experiences, WIA members are given a number of opportunities to meet equally driven colleagues at events held throughout the year. <http://www.womeninaerospace.org/about/mission.html>

3. **Women in Aerospace Europe (WIE)** - *Being a part of our ever-growing network means benefiting from our programmes and special member offers, as well as connecting with like-minded professionals through our local communities.* <http://wia-europe.org/>
4. **The Royal Aeronautical Society's Women in Aviation & Aerospace Committee (WAAC)** *was established in 2009 to encourage more young women to consider aviation and aerospace as a worthwhile and exciting career. It also exists to provide support for women already working in all sectors of aviation and aerospace.*
5. **The International Aviation Women Association (IAWA)** *is an international organization for women who hold positions of impact in the aviation and aerospace industry. Founded in 1988, IAWA brings together women of achievement and promotes their advancement throughout the world. Women are assuming greater and more visible roles within the industry. Through annual global conferences, regional receptions and connects, IAWA provides a forum to share views on matters of importance to the industry, as well as to women in general. Women should have five years' leadership experience in aviation or aerospace to apply for IAWA membership. However, our conference is open to all women in our industry.* <https://iawa.org/>

One best practice identified by DGMove project (2016):

- **SNCF Au féminin (Réseau de Femmes), France** - *The SNCF works with Ambassadors/Role Models through its 'Réseau de Femmes'. Launched on 26 January 2012, the network has been chaired since September 2016 by Francesca Aceto. This network is dedicated to employees who want to strengthen the role of women in the company and enhance their place in society. SNCF Au féminin is both a 'physical' network, with regular meetings in Paris or in regions, to know and conduct collective reflections (Think tank), and a "virtual" network thanks to the extranet site open to women executives of the group. Space of exchange, information and animation, this extranet site is the daily link of SNCF Au féminin throughout the territory. SNCF Au Féminin has a Charter detailing commitment of the company and the network to promote the inclusion of women in transport professions.*

4. In sum

Create a culture that:

- *has zero-tolerance for incivility and undermining;*
- *recognizes employees' contributions and cares about their well-being, and;*
- *respects employees' work-life obligations and responsibilities.*

Create systems and policies that:

- *Invest in skills-based training and overall professional development;*
- *Provide transparent paths with clear, fair criteria for mobility and advancement;*
- *Provide opportunities for formal and informal mentoring;*
- *Provide other networking opportunities, and;*
- *Offer a variety of options to manage multiple life responsibilities, without any career penalties.*

Implement role-level changes:

- *Communicate clear work goals and relevance of tasks to the corporate objectives;*

- Clarify what needs to be done, how, and when it needs to be done;
- Eliminate, when possible, conflicting demands, expectations, and role disruptions, and;
- Infuse new resources or reallocate existing ones to streamline work procedures.

11.6 Protection of the Family, Maternity and Parenthood

The protection of the family and children is a fundamental value of society that the law tries to ensure in all situations including employment. There are still cases of dismissal using collateral arguments that cannot be accepted for their consequences and are equivalent to a disguised violation of the prevailing law.

How the parenthood allowance is shared between the parents is a family matter that should not be interfered with. Special circumstances have also to be allowed for. In some cases, a change of type of work or a different assignment can make more compatible company priorities and family needs, by adjusting schedules or timetables.

Although many in modern times advocate complete mobility, there is nothing wrong with children becoming fond of the employer of their parents, whom they grow to see as a reliable part of their life, perhaps wishing to follow a similar career, continuing their parents work for another generation.

The associations that foster women participation in aviation (Key Topic T11.6) are also a forum for their integration and protection of their rights.

KEY TOPIC T11.6 – THE ASSOCIATIONS THAT FOSTER WOMEN PARTICIPATION IN AVIATION

IAWA (International Aviation Women’s Association) is a non-profit association providing a worldwide network dedicated to promoting the advancement of women in the aviation and aerospace industries at all levels across the globe. IAWA sponsors informative meetings, hosts receptions and connects, publishes newsletters, and keeps its members updated on the latest industry developments.

The president of this association is Alina Nassar, she holds a degree in Law and a Notary Public graduated with Honours from the University of Costa Rica. She is specialist in aeronautical law and she is the first Latin American women to hold the position of President of the International Aviation Women’s Association.

With the objective of enhancing the development of women in aviation, the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) in conjunction with the International Aviation Women’s Association (IAWA), is offering an Aviation Scholarship for a professional woman in this field.

Candidates who are selected for the ICAO-IAWA Aviation Scholarship will be able to augment their professional experience in aviation by working on and contributing to specific aspects of the ICAO work programme at the international level for a period of nine months.

IAWA is supporting ICAO in its efforts to promote the development of women in aviation by providing voluntary contributions and by assisting in identifying those candidates who meet the requirements for the ICAO-IAWA Aviation Scholarship (Table 11.2) and Awards (Table 11.3):

Requirements
An advanced university degree (Masters' level or equivalent), in an aviation-related discipline.
A minimum of two years of experience in supporting technical work of an international aviation or aerospace organization, a civil aviation authority, or similar related organization.
Fluency in English is required. Knowledge of any other of the following ICAO languages is an asset: Arabic, Chinese, French, Russian, Spanish.

Table 11.2 - Requirements for ICAO-IAWA Aviation Scholarship

Selected candidates will work under the guidance of experienced professionals in the Air Navigation Bureau at the ICAO Headquarters in Montreal.

The Air Navigation Bureau (ANB) is responsible for providing technical guidance to the Air Navigation Commission (ANC), the Council and the Assembly. ANB provides technical expertise in aviation-related disciplines to States, industry and all elements of the Organization. The Bureau is also responsible for maintaining and implementing the Global Aviation Safety Plan (GASP) and the Global Air Navigation Plan (GASP), including its aviation system block upgrades as well as producing yearly safety and air navigation status reports. The Bureau develops technical studies and proposals for Standards and Recommended Practices (SARPs), and Procedures for Air Navigation Services (PANS) for further processing by the governing bodies of ICAO. The Bureau also develops related procedures and guidance material. The Bureau also manages the Universal Safety Oversight Audit Programme (USOAP) that monitors all States on a continuous basis.

Awards
Be a demonstrated leader in her field of aviation.
Be supportive of mentoring, educating and advancing women in the aviation profession.
Be a role model for young women and a professionally supportive peer to women in her field or company/firm.
Be a respected team player by both men and women.

Table 11.3 - Criteria for the ICAO-AIWA Aviation Awards

IAWA is currently affiliated with the following organizations: Airports Council International, ALTA, Aviation Week, IATA, ICAO, ISTAT, Royal Aeronautical Society, among other.

11.7 Recognition of Professional Achievements

The recognition of professional achievements must of course be objective and fair, using the same criteria applied in the same way, regardless of gender, age or belief. However, fairness also means equal opportunities, and while applying the same final criteria, all should have the same opportunities to attain those objectives.

The adjustment of working conditions, or schedules or responsibilities to account for special individual circumstances of women or other groups is not a favour, but rather having an even playing field inside the company as the company would like to have in the market versus its competitors, promoting a loyal division of tasks within the organization.

Reverse discrimination may not be the best way to correct gender inequalities nor forced statistical equality: women do not need favours they only need equal opportunities and fair treatment, and this applies not only to gender issues, but also to other potential forms of discrimination that could creep into the workplace.

Women have had remarkable successes in aviation (Key Topic 11.7) in spite of modest recognition, suggesting they could achieve more in more favourable circumstances.

KEY TOPIC 11.7 – ACHIEVEMENTS OF WOMEN IN AVIATION

Women were present in aviation activities since the first flights. However, until the 70s their presence was, with rare exceptions, mainly as passengers on-board of male-piloted vehicles. Prejudices formed in the general social life were exacerbated in aviation. Claude Grahame-White (1879-1959), a British pioneer of flight (he is credited with the first night flight) is quoted saying that “women are not temperamentally suited to fly an aeroplane”.

This biased opinion persisted over decades, determining a large delay in pioneer women penetrating in male-dominated aviation professions. The notable exceptions were the effect of a combination of factors:

- outstanding qualities (Hanna Reich);
- the encouragement of a political system using women images for propaganda objectives (Valentina Teleshkova, the first woman in space, Lydia Litvyak and Yekaterina Budanova – the only women among the combat flying aces in WWII);
- powerful support from families (e.g. Jacqueline Cochran’s husband was one of the richest men on the planet, Jacqueline Auriol was the daughter-in-law of the French president, Amelia Earhart’s exploits were financed by her husband, a press magnate, Marga von Etzdorf who was the first woman to fly for an airline when she began co-piloting for Lufthansa in 1927 was presented her first aircraft by her grandfather for her birthday.);
- luck.

Only in 1929 a Canadian was the first woman to earn a master's degree in aeronautical engineering. In 1930, Ellen Church, a pilot and nurse, who was unable to secure work flying proposed to airline executives that women be allowed to act as hostesses on planes. She was hired on a three-month trial basis by Boeing Air Transport and selected the first seven flight attendants for airlines, requiring them to be under 115 pounds, nurses and unmarried⁵⁸.

Only in 1937 Sabiha Gökçen of Turkey became the first trained woman combat pilot, participating in search operations and bombing flights during the Dersim Rebellion. While Gökçen was not the first to have participated in military operations, she was the first woman to have been trained as a military pilot, graduating from the Aircraft School⁵⁹. While in Soviet Airforce certain women-only units were used in combat during WWII, other military strictly prohibited combat participation of women. Only

⁵⁸ Bednarek, Janet R. Daly; Bednarek, Michael H. (2003). *Dreams of Flight: General Aviation in the United States*. College Station, Texas: [Texas A&M University Press](#).

⁵⁹ Altunay, Ayşe Gül (25 March 2001). *"Dünyanın İlk Kadın Savaş Pilotu: Gökçen"* [World's First Women's War Pilot: Gökçen] (in Turkish). Istanbul, Turkey: [BİA Haber Merkezi](#)

in 1991, the United States Senate lifted the ban on military women flying in combat and in 1993 women were permitted to fly fighter jets. UK had done the same two years earlier.

One of the most dramatic forms of prejudices against women was the refusal by NASA to train any woman-astronaut in the early stages of the space flights in the 60s. US did not send a woman in space until 1983, 20 years after Russia' Valentina Teleshkova orbital flight. And although this first US woman-astronaut, Dr. Sally Ride, was arguably one of the best and the brightest NASA had to offer, she was a Mission Specialist and not a Pilot or Mission Commander. And it was another 12 years (February 3, 1995) until NASA had a female PILOT (Col. Eileen Collins). And then, 4 years after that, Col. Collins became the first Mission Commander⁶⁰.

Back in early 60s, Jacqueline Cochran and another outstanding woman pilot, Jerrie Cobb, (a professional pilot who owned 4 FAI altitude record and was a test pilot for North American Aviation) took the initiative to engage a total of 13 women including Cobb (so called "Mercury 13" by analogy with "Mercury 7", the first group of astronauts recruited by NASA) to participate, at a private clinic, in the very same physical and psychological tests that were used to select the original astronaut applicants. All 13 passed the tests. However, NASA was unimpressed. On 17 and 18 July 1962, Representative Victor Anfuso convened public hearings before a special Subcommittee of the House Committee on Science and Astronautics to determine whether or not the exclusion of women from the astronaut program was discriminatory, during which John Glenn and Scott Carpenter testified against admitting women to the astronaut program. Glenn stated at the hearing "men go off and fight the wars and fly the airplanes," and "the fact that women are not in this field is a fact of our social order"⁶¹. None of the women who had passed the tests were military jet test pilots, nor did they have engineering degrees, which were the two basic experiential qualifications for potential astronauts. Women were not allowed to be military jet test pilots at that time. On average, however, "Mercury 13 girls" had more flight experience than the male astronauts. "NASA required all astronauts to be graduates of military jet test piloting programs and have engineering degrees. In 1962, no women could meet these requirements." This ended the Mercury 13 programme. The American space programme did not open the ranks of its astronaut corps to women until 1978.

The discrimination was not limited to space flight. The airline industry was also a biased field. United States Commerce Department regulations required pilots to have flown a large number of hours before being licensed for commercial airline flight. Only in the military they could acquire sufficient flight hours, and since the U.S. services barred women from flying (before 1970), they were routinely denied work in commercial piloting. Women eventually began to enter U.S. major commercial aviation in the 1970s and 1980s, with 1973 seeing the first female pilot at a major U.S. airline, American Airlines. American also promoted the first female captain of a major U.S. airline in 1986 and the following year had the first all-woman flight crew.

Even today a strong imbalance is still observed both in the pilot professions and in the non-pilot aviators. Data provided by FAA annual statistics⁶² are significant: as of December 31, 2017, women are just over 7% of the total of the certified civilian pilots (both private and commercial) and less than 5% of certified airline pilots. Other positions in aviation show a similar imbalance, e.g. just over 2% of the

⁶⁰ All Hallonquist: <http://www.mercury13.com/>

⁶¹ https://web.archive.org/web/20151211072933/http://nasa.la/static/qualifications_for_astronauts_hearing_1962.pdf

⁶² https://www.faa.gov/data_research/aviation_data_statistics/civil_airmen_statistics

mechanics are females. The only reverse imbalance is for flight attendants, of which only 20% are male. The total non-pilot professions employ women roughly a third of the total, the strong effect of flight attendants mix (see Table 11.4 below):

CATEGORY	TOTAL 2017	OF WHICH WOMEN	% WOMEN
Pilot--Total	609,306	42,694	7.01%
Student	149,121	19,219	12.89%
Recreational (only)	153	14	9.15%
Sport	6,097	229	3.76%
Private	162,455	9,971	6.14%
Commercial	98,161	6,267	6.38%
Airline Transport	159,825	6,994	4.38%
			6.66%
Flight Instructor Certificates	106,692	7,105	
Remote Pilots	69,166	3,462	5.01%
Non-Pilot--Total	671,222	195,993	29.20%
Mechanic	286,268	6,855	2.39%
Repairmen	35,040	1,847	
Parachute Rigger	6,192	597	
Ground Instructor	66,423	4,924	
Dispatcher	20,664	3,867	
Flight Navigator	64	0	
Flight Attendant	222,037	176,471	79.48%
Flight Engineer	34,534	1,432	

Table 11.4 – Gender imbalance in aviation

When processing the data provided by FAA for the last 20 years one can observe that today women's participation in the aviation sector is still low, but the trend is slowly growing (see Figure 11.31 below):

Figure 11.31 – Percentage of women in aircraft jobs

11.8 Reaping the Benefits of Complementarity

Women and men can have different sensibilities, distinct approaches to the same problem and complementary abilities that can be of benefit to the balanced and efficient performance of many tasks. Choosing which skills fit best each task is part of the efficient management of human resources in a company.

Gender based discrimination is not only unfair but also a loss of valuable talent. The combination of different talents in a cooperative and open-minded environment of equality promotes the emergence of new ideas and allows pursuing them to achieve the best results in less time and with reduced effort.

A greater participation of women in aeronautics is not only an enlargement of the workforce in numbers, it is also an enrichment in quality and talent, which are the foundations of inventiveness and competitiveness, on which depend the continuing European leadership in an ever more competitive world with new challengers.

One of the most common preconceptions is that women have a disinclination to science, by her selves or compared with men. In fact, there are countries where the majority of women choose science (Key Topic T11.8) and they are not necessarily the nations rated as most gender equal.

KEY TOPIC 11.8 – WOMEN CHOOSING EDUCATION IN STEM

Portugal leads (Figure 11.32) the list of OCDE countries with the largest number of women attending high education on STEM courses and with career ambitions in these areas.

According to OCDE statistics, 57% of women are already studying these subjects at national universities. The percentage far exceeds the average of 39% among OECD countries. But the analysis of these numbers is far from linear. If there are reasons to celebrate a greater female presence in science, engineering and mathematics courses, in information and communication technologies women are still fewer. Manuel Heitor, the Portuguese Minister of Science, Technology and Higher Education, says that "we have a good job done, but it's not enough. There is still a long way to go in this matter. "

However, there are reasons to celebrate. Not only, Portugal is being able to attract a growing number of women to highly employable courses that were once recognized as "typically male", moving to the much-desired gender parity, as it is at the top of the list, pushing for middle of the table countries like the United States, Germany or France.

According to Minister Manuel Heitor, the OECD conclusions in the study "The Pursuit of Gender Equality", which analyses gender parity in the various countries, "make clear the international recognition that Portugal has today in the areas of science and technology and that is the result of work done over the last 20 years in programs such as *Ciência Viva*."

Despite this, the Executive member recognises that the battle for the increasing qualification of the Portuguese and the capture of a greater number of women for the STEM areas is not yet concluded in its several fronts. "If it is true that in higher education courses Portugal has more women than most countries, and even in engineering there is already a specialty of clear female prevalence, the same

does not happen in information technology where gender inequality is still great" says the minister. Manuel Heitor gives as an example the areas of digital, where women, "still remain underrepresented in universities and companies in Portugal", he says.

A sub-representation that is larger as we go through the top positions. "Companies in Portugal still limit women's access to leadership positions and career development opportunities", he recognises.

Only four in every ten embark in higher education

While acknowledging the importance of continuing the policy of attracting women to these areas and the continued investment in the development of STEM skills, for the potential for employability they demonstrate, Manuel Heitor has no doubt that the national battle is far from being limited to the gender parity in higher education. "The great battle we have to fight is to extend access to higher education to all," he explains, recalling that "only four out of every 10 young people come to universities in Portugal, and increasing this ratio should be the top priority."

Figure 11.32 – Percentage of women studying in STEM areas

Last year, the OECD's "Education at a Glance 2017" report already warned of this problem by noting that 31% of Portuguese adults aged 25 to 30 did not have the 10th grade completed. A percentage that is double the average of the OECD countries. In older generations, between 25 and 64 years, the percentage of those with no secondary education rises to 53%. In 2016 (data considered by the OECD in the report), only 24% of the Portuguese adult population (between 25 and 64 years old) had higher education. The average of OECD countries was 37%. Disaggregating the data, we noticed that only 15% of Portuguese university students attended integrated masters (with a minimum duration of five years).

Last year's "Education at a Glance" was already reporting national progress in the presence of women in STEM courses but noted that in the specific case of information technology inequality was all too

obvious. The study supported the national increase in the number of graduates in the STEM areas with a higher percentage of graduates in Engineering, since Information and Communication Technologies registered in the last year in Portugal one of the lowest rates of graduates among the OECD countries: 1%.

11.9 Enlargement of a Workforce with Broader Talent

The current dominance of the world aerospace market by two continents (Europe and US) is increasingly challenged by other countries, like BRIC (Brazil, Russia, China and India) with large populations and resources. It is claimed that there are 200 000 university students in aeronautics in China alone, showing how much importance the regime attaches to this sector.

Europe cannot match the number of people in some of the countries that are its main customers and can only sustain its position with smaller number of more talented professionals, that continue to lead the way in basic science and its application in engineering and technology to deliver the goods and services that modern society expects.

The challenge of hard science (STEM – Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) means that there are proportionally less candidates than for soft skills and services. This makes the STEM able professionals the key actors of future prosperity of the aerospace sector in Europe, forming a community in which both genders can contribute equally.

The challenges that women have faced in their professional careers are best demonstrated by the real-life stories of those that distinguished themselves by their achievements in several sectors; a pair of examples is given in 4 areas.

11.10 Examples of Outstanding Women

A – HUMANITIES AND SCIENCE:

- Maria Moliner produced the first literally dictionary of the Spanish language at a time when discrimination was far more severe than today;
- Marie Curie was also discriminated, was more fortunate to receive help from her husband and due recognition during her lifetime.

B – DARING AVIATORS:

- Amelia Earhart was the first woman to fly across the Atlantic with a tragic outcome of an attempt to cross the Pacific Ocean;
- Hanna Reich was the only pilot small enough to fit into the V-1 for the first manned flight tests of this first flying bomb, and carried out many other dangerous missions during the WW2.

C – WOMEN TEST PILOTS:

- Jaqueline Cochran held FAI speed records flying the Lockheed F-104 Starfighter;
- Jaqueline Auriol held FAI speed records flying the Dassault Mirage.

D – WOMEN ASTRONAUTS:

- Valentina Tereshkova was the first woman astronaut in Soviet times;

- Dava Newman career spans astronaut, MIT professor and NASA deputy administrator.

The achievements of Maria Moliner (Key Topic T11.9) and the challenges she had to overcome (Key Topic T11.10) show the prejudices against women outside the aviation sector. Amelia Earhart daring flights (Key Topics T11.11) contributed to the visibility of women in aviation, consolidated by women astronauts, such as Valentina Tereshkova (Key Topic T11.12) from the Soviet Union and Dana Newman (Key Topic T11.13) from the United States.

KEY TOPIC 11.9 – THE ACHIEVEMENTS OF MARIA MOLINER

Maria Moliner produced the first literary dictionary of the Spanish language at a time when discrimination was far more severe than today. The novelty and scope of such a huge task provoked both admiration and envy. She followed her great passion for words to compose a “divergent”, revolutionary and innovative dictionary, which was unusual for that time, including among them foreign ones, colloquial usage, slang and acronyms not contemplated in the academic dictionary of the Spanish Royal Academy. The “Diccionario de uso del español” represents her enormous task, but it was not her only one.

Maria Moliner was born in Paniza, Saragossa in 1900 and died in Madrid in 1981. She graduated from the Faculty of Philosophy and Arts, History Section, University of Saragossa in 1921 with a special award. She belonged to the generation of the first women university graduates in Spain who pursued a profession. In fact, in 1922 she passed the state examination to enter the Association of Faculty Archivists, Librarians and Archaeologists. She worked as a public sector employee in this association until 1970.

Maria Moliner is considered as a pioneering figure in librarianship in Spain only when the democracy has been restored in this country. In her early adulthood she dedicated herself mainly to the reorganization of Spain’s system of public libraries and to the boost she gave to such libraries, understood that this was the way to give a brief of hope in a rural Spain that was largely illiterate.

Her works and goals were to disseminate culture and literacy. During the dark period of the Second Republic, followed to the Civil War, the ideals of democracy and equal opportunities were subject to oppression and ostracism.

Maria Moliner dedicated herself to the cause of disseminating culture with her outstanding intuition that this would be the right way to mitigate the injustice, irrationality, and misery of a Spain. Moliner alone undertook the enormous task of editing an extremely important book, the famous dictionary that bears her name. This attitude and efforts came from her fascination, passion and interest in linguistic expression and grammar derived from a Spanish cultural historian, philologist and literary critic, Americo Castro, who challenged some of the prevailing notions of Spanish identity.

KEY TOPIC 11.10 – THE CHALLENGES OF MARIA MOLINER

1. Life

María Moliner was born in Paniza (Zaragoza, Spain) on March 30, 1900 within a family composed by the doctor Enrique Moliner Sanz and Matilde Ruiz. Her parents moved to Almazán (Soria) in 1902 and then almost immediately to Madrid. In the capital city, María Moliner studied at the Free Education Institution. In 1912, her father travels to Argentina as a Navy doctor but never returns, a fact that deeply marked María. The family circumstances forced her to collaborate in family maintenance from very young. She continued her baccalaureate studies at the General and Technical Institute of Zaragoza. After that, she graduated from the faculty of Philosophy and Arts, History section at the University of Zaragoza in 1921 with an outstanding qualification and an extraordinary award. In 1922, she passed the state examination to enter the Association of Faculty Archivists, Librarians and Archaeologists. It was the sixth woman who entered in the Association. In 1923, she obtained her first posting in the Simancas Archive in Valladolid, Spain.

After that, she requests the transfer to the National Historical Archive but she did not achieve it. However, she obtained a post in Murcia, in the Archive of the Treasury Department. In 1925, she married Fernando Ramón y Fernando, a physics professor, with whom she had four children. At the beginning of the 1930s, the family moved to Valencia: Fernando to the Faculty of Sciences and María transferred there by the Treasury Department.

The period in Valencia was a high point in Moliner's life, both personally and professionally. In the professional sphere, she became fully involved in cultural enterprises that reflected the spirit of the Second Republic. Moliner taught grammar and literature at the Cossío School and was a member of the governing board and secretary of the Friends' Association. She was involved in the organization of popular libraries, public libraries today). She also managed the library at the University of Valencia (1936-37), where her husband was a lecturer, as well as the Office for Book Purchases and International Exchanges. She undertook teaching duties at the Free Education Institution, and during the Second Republic, she introduced a ground-breaking system of rural libraries. Once war broke out in 1936, she found ways of sending books to soldiers in the front line. After the war was over, she and her husband both suffered reprisals: she was dropped eighteen places on the promotion scale, and he was suspended from his job without pay for three years (they would both be reinstated years later). In 1946, they moved to Madrid with their four children, and she became head librarian at the capital's Higher Technical School of Industrial Engineers.

Moliner dedicated these years, in which she was not involved in the major decision-making spheres of either politics or culture, to the mammoth task of compiling a dictionary of Spanish usage, which is acknowledge throughout the world as a vital tool for this language. Nevertheless, her candidature to the Spanish Royal academy in 1972 was rejected. If she had been accepted, she would have been the first woman to join the academy.

It was in her early adulthood that she dedicated herself mainly to the reorganization of Spain's system of public libraries and to the boost she gave to such libraries, understood to be centres of literacy and cultural dissemination in a rural Spain that was largely illiterate.

In 1975, she was diagnosed a cerebral arteriosclerosis and she finally died on January 22, 1981.

In the following points, it is included the achievements that she reached throughout her life as well as the challenges that she had to overcome.

2. Challenges

- In 1912, her father travels to Argentina as a Navy doctor but never returns, a fact that deeply marked María;
- From very young, she was forced to collaborate in the family maintenance due to the family circumstances;
- María Moliner was part of a generation of pioneers who accessed the University as a result of the 1910 decree and, for that reason, she had to compete in a world of men;
- After the Civil War was over, she and her husband both suffered reprisals: she was not allowed to hold leadership posts, and he was suspended from his job without pay for three years.
- During the Franco's dictatorship, she was barred from taking part in Spanish politics and cultural policy, losing her professional category. She did not fully recover it until 1965.

3. Achievements

- In 1921, she graduated from the faculty of Philosophy and Arts, History section at the University of Zaragoza with an outstanding qualification and an extraordinary award;
- In 1922, she was the sixth woman who entered in the Association of Faculty Archivists, Librarians and Archaeologists;
- On the one hand, she obtained her first posting in the Simancas Archive in Valladolid in 1923 and, on the other hand, she obtained her second post in the Archive of the Treasury Department in Murcia in 1924;
- In 1931, she ascended to the maximum category of the Faculty Corps and began to manage the Valencia Archive;
- In 1933, she was appointed a member of the Valencian delegation of the education trust, the Patronato de Misiones Pedagógicas. In addition, she was commissioned for the organization of rural libraries;
- In 1935, she participated in the creation and development of the Cossío School and managed the School Library in Valencia;
- In 1936, she was appointed Director of the Valencia University Library and occupied several positions in the Central Board of Archives, Libraries and Art Treasury;
- In 1937, Moliner published the "Instructions for Attending to Small Libraries" and she assumed a new responsibility: the direction of the Office for Book Purchases and International Exchanges;
- In 1946, she moved to Madrid where she incorporated to the Higher Technical School of Industrial Engineers;
- In 1966/67, the first edition of the Dictionary of Spanish usage was published by the Gredos Publishing House in two volumes;

- Numerous libraries in Spain bear María Moliner's name, as does a prestigious award funded by Spain's Ministry of Culture for projects encouraging reading in small local, rural, public libraries.

KEY TOPIC 11.11 – THE DARING FLIGHTS OF AMELIA EARHART

The 20th century marked a positive change for aviation in general and for women in aviation as in another field. In fact, in 1930s, America women power started to be in more demand and the fledging air transportation industry began to see the advantage of women in aviation and as a passenger to keep the aircraft industry running. Furthermore, women were encouraged to educate themselves for engineering. As an examples Boeing Air Transport hired the industry's first stewardesses. It is worth to mention that a major breakthrough for women followed in 1934 when Helen Richey was hired as a pilot for Central Airlines. Unfortunately, her employment lasted only a few months because of pressure from male airline pilots.

Looking deeply in the past, although women have flown since 1908, and give a great contribution in aviation and in women consideration only in 1930, nearly all of them were restricted to general aviation such as private planes or support jobs. Thanks to their efforts, leading women pilots also took part in the development of commercial air travel by writing articles and giving speeches on the safety, convenience, and even luxury of air travel. Among those women, Amelia Earhart is the most-known one, even if she was not the pioneer female pilot (before America had a notable number of other memorable female pilots), which gained international attention. Earhart's fame grown immediately after her first achievement. She was the first woman to cross the Atlantic by air as a passenger.

Furthermore, she defined for the decade what women pilots were trying to prove: ***Flying is safe, and women make good pilots***. The Hollywood film *Amelia*, 2009 has increased her notoriety to the vast public.

Her life was dedicated to improving the women's self-confidence, not only in aviation field. Her outstanding experiences and dissemination brought her global fame and charm, persisting still today as an icon to women. In addition to her flying, Earhart served as president of the NinetyNines, vice president of the National Aeronautic Association, assistant general traffic manager of Transcontinental and Western Air, and a member of the Guggenheim Committee for Aeronautical Education in Primary and Secondary Schools. During her life, she wrote best-selling books and popular columns about her experiences, endorsed commercial products, and lectured in the aviation department at Purdue University in 1935. She performed aviation records at a time when there were hardly any female pilots bring the women freedom and capable to perform the same duty and mission, even better than men.

Amelia Earhart was born on July 24, 1897 in Kansas. She grew up "here and there" spending her youth moving between Kansas, Iowa and Canada - due to the continuous changing's job of her father. She entered in Chicago High School where she graduated in 1915 and entered college in 1916, attending the Ogontz College in Rydal, Pennsylvania. In 1918, Amelia spent the Christmas time, visiting her sister in Toronto and she was very affected by a "tragic" view; the sight of four wounded soldiers walking on crutches together down the street. Amelia decided not to stay and graduate in Ogontz School, but to move to Toronto and join in the war effort. She became a Voluntary Aid Detachment nurse at the Spadina Military Convalescent hospital in Toronto, caring for wounded World War I soldiers. Many of the patients at the hospital where she worked were pilots. In 1918, she attended her first flying exhibition while serving as a Red Cross nurse's aide in Toronto, Canada.

In early 1919, she enrolled at Columbia University in New York entered in the premedical program. Furthermore, she took her first flight in California in December 1920, with veteran flyer Frank Hawks, and declared, "As soon as I left the ground, I knew I myself had to fly." In 1921, Earhart passed her trials for a National Aeronautic Association license and she participated in exhibition flying at the Pacific Cost Ladies Derby at the Sierra Airdrome in Pasadena and she bought her first airplane, a Kinner Airster.

In 1922 she performed her first aviation record, obtained a women's altitude record of 4,267 meters (14,000 feet), at Rogers Field. Amelia was among the first score of women received the FAI certificates. On May 16, 1923 Amelia was issued certificate number 6017 by the FAI becoming the 16th woman to receive an official Fédération Aéronautique Internationale pilot license. By the end of 1923 Amelia had accumulated almost 300 solo flight hours and became the first woman which had ever fly higher before.

In 1928 Amelia received an exciting offer. The Captain Hilton H. Railey, asked her if she would like to be the first woman to fly across the Atlantic. Amelia enthusiastically agreed to this adventure. The Table 11.5 lists some major records set by Amelia Earhart:

Amelia Earhart Record Setter	
1922	— Feminine altitude record of 4,267 meters (14,000 feet).
1928	— First woman to fly across the Atlantic as a passenger in the Fokker F.VII <i>Friendship</i> .
1929	— Feminine speed record
1930	— Feminine speed record
1931	— First woman to fly an autogiro
1931	— Autogiro altitude record of 5,612 meters (18,415 feet).
1932	— First woman (and only the second person) to fly solo and nonstop across the Atlantic. Also first person to cross the Atlantic twice by air
1932	— First woman to fly solo and nonstop across the United States.
1933	— Reset her transcontinental record.
1935	— First person to fly solo from Honolulu, Hawaii, to the U.S. mainland (Oakland, California)
1935	— Speed record between Mexico City and Washington, D.C.
1935	— First person to fly solo from Mexico City to Newark, New Jersey.

Table 11.5 – List of Amelia Earhart Record Setter.

(Source: <https://airandspace.si.edu/explore-and-learn/topics/women-in-aviation/earhart.cfm>)

Amelia did not try to make any money from her flying. She considered it not only a sport, a passion, a dream, but also a way where women can find the freedom which they are seeking. She tried to demonstrate that women could learn to fly as quickly as men, obtaining same results and progresses in all fields. She was truly an inspiration to women, her attitude toward success and failure outlined in the following quote, "Women must try to do things as men have tried. When they fail, their failure must be but a challenge to others." Earhart's goal was proving that flying is safe and that women make good pilots. She was constantly training, learning, writing, and prone to divulgate her experience with a key message for all the women. Thanks to these outstanding features and her perseverance she realized ones of her goals: on 21-22 May 1932, Amelia Earhart pilots this Lockheed Vega 5B (Figure 11.33) in a solo flight across the Atlantic from Newfoundland to Ireland, and nonstop across the United States, both first for a woman. This flight made her the first person to fly across the Atlantic twice.

Because her flight was five years to the day after Lindbergh's and because there was a perceived physical resemblance between them, Amelia's nickname was "Lady Lindy."

Figure 11.33 – Amelia Earhart's Lockheed Vega 5B.

(Source: <https://airandspace.si.edu/collection-objects/lockheed-vega-5b-amelia-earhart>)

During her aviation career, Earhart wrote books and articles endorsing automobiles and other products, driving women to encourage their husbands to fly instead of driving or taking a train on business trips, and suggesting that flying was the best method of travel for a family vacation. By this way she helping airlines promote travel to female passengers and improvement in industry. Furthermore, she is designing women's clothing and luggage, launched a fashion house to manufacture and market clothing designed by her, opening her first shop in New York.

In 1935 Amelia became the first person to fly solo across the Pacific Ocean from Hawaii to California. This was also the first flight in which a civilian aircraft carried a two-way radio. In the same year, she became the first person to fly solo from Los Angeles, to Mexico City. Amelia testified before the U.S Senate regarding plans to place aviation under control of the Interstate Commerce Commission.

During 1936 and 1937, Earhart formed a close alliance with Purdue University and became a visiting professor started as a part-time career consultant in the Counsellor in Careers for Women which represented the culmination of her career, where she could share her philosophies with young women. She continued her job at Purdue, serving as a part-time career counsellor for women and an advisor in aeronautics.

In 1936, Amelia was honoured by women geographers and she illustrated before a Senate sub-committee on air safety. That same year she acquired a Lockheed Electra 10E airplane, financed by Purdue University. With her new airplane, she started planning for a flight around the world at the equator. Earhart used the aircraft, which had a ceiling of 27,500 feet, to test and observe human reaction to flights at high altitudes. In fact, in 1937, Earhart began her round – the – world flight at the equator in Oakland, California and set a new record for fastest east to west (Oakland to Honolulu) travel in 15 hours and 47 minutes in March. A second round-the-world attempt started, departing from Miami, and traveling form west to east. After completing 22,000 miles of the flight, Amelia route to tiny Howland Island, losing radio contact with U.S. Her disappearance on July 2, 1937, while trying to land on tiny Howland Island in the Pacific Ocean, came as she attempted to set a spectacular new record—a circumnavigation flight near the equator. Amelia Earhart was declared legally dead in superior court in Los Angeles, CA on January 1939.

In Figure 11.34 is depicted Earhart in the cockpit of her Electra plane in 1937, not long before her disappearance at the age of 39 on an attempted circumnavigation flight.

Figure 11.34 - Earhart in the cockpit of her Electra plane in 1937.

(Source: Beyond Amelia Earhart: Teaching about the History of Women Aviators. OAH Magazine of History, July 2010 (Courtesy George Palmer Putnam Collection of Amelia Earhart Papers, Purdue University Libraries))

Amelia Earhart succeeded well in her dual goals—the air transportation industry and women pilots.

Nowadays, women have gained full access to military and commercial cockpits, Space Shuttle and aerospace technology as well. The website of the Smithsonian's National Air and Space Museum (http://www.nasm.si.edu/research/aero/women_aviators/womenavsp.htm) is dedicated to review the history of female pilots and highlight the growing contributions of woman in that sector (Figure 11.35):

Figure 11.35 – Women in aviation

KEY TOPIC 11.12 – VALENTINA TERESHKOVA

Figure 11.36 – Valentina Tereshkova as astronaut

Valentina Vladimirovna Tereshkova (Figure 11.36) was the first woman to go into space. She is the only woman in the world who made a space flight alone. In 1963, she spent almost three days in space and orbited Earth 48 times in her space capsule, 'Vostok 6'. That was her only trip into space. Tereshkova later toured the world to promote Soviet science and became involved in Soviet politics. After Yuri Gagarin became the first man in space in 1961, Tereshkova volunteered for the Soviet space

program. Although she did not have any experience as a pilot, she was accepted into the program because of her 126 parachute jumps. At the time, cosmonauts had to parachute from their capsules seconds before they hit the ground on returning to Earth.

[<https://www.space.com/21571-valentina-tereshkova.html>]

In choosing Tereshkova for the role of the first woman-cosmonaut, in addition to the successful completion of training, the ability of the candidate to conduct active social activities was also taken into account, to appear in public on numerous trips around the country and the world.

Valentina Tereshkova easily communicated with journalists and other people, gave laconic and natural answers to questions.

In 1968-1987, Valentina Tereshkova headed the Committee of Soviet Women. In 1969, Vice-President of the International Democratic Women's Federation, a member of the World Peace Council.

In 1987-1992, she was a Chairman of the Presidium of the Union of Soviet Societies of Friendship and Cultural Relations with Foreign Countries. In 1989-1992, she was a People's Deputy of the USSR from the Union of Soviet Societies of Friendship and Cultural Relations with Foreign Countries and the 'Rodina' Society.

In 1992, the Chairman of the Presidium of the Russian Association for International Cooperation. In 1992-1995, First Deputy Chairman of the Russian Agency for International Cooperation and Development. In 1994-2004, the Head of the Russian Centre for International Scientific and Cultural Cooperation.

In 1983, a commemorative coin with the image of Valentina Tereshkova was produced - she became the only Soviet citizen whose portrait was in life placed on Soviet coins.

Tereshkova remains active in the space community, and her legacy is widely celebrated in everything from books to museums to stage productions.

In 2017, London's Science Museum opened a temporary exhibit called "Valentina Tereshkova: First Woman in Space," which celebrated her contributions through artefacts as well as photographs (Figure 11.36 to 11.38).

[<https://www.space.com/21571-valentina-tereshkova.html>]

Figure 11.37 – Valentina Tereshkova with decoration

After her flight, Valentina Tereshkova no longer flew into space. She became an instructor-cosmonaut, worked in the Cosmonaut Training Centre as a senior research fellow, even graduated from the Zhukovsky Air Force Engineering Academy, becoming a candidate of technical sciences, professor and writing over five dozen scientific papers.

Valentina Tereshkova now.

Figure 11.38 – Valentina Tereshkova now

81 year of her life Tereshkova celebrated on March 6, 2018. She is a retired Major General, spends a lot of time with her family, and also continues to pursue a political career. So, in 2016 during the next parliamentary elections Tereshkova was elected a deputy of the State Duma of the Russian Federation. The first woman cosmonaut is very fond of her native region, strives to help Yaroslavl orphanage, native school, to improve the city and help to open new educational, production and infrastructure facilities in it.

KEY TOPIC 11.13 – DANA NEWMAN

She was born in 1964. She is a former Deputy Administrator of NASA. She is also the Apollo Program Professor of Aeronautics and Astronautics and Engineering Systems at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology and a Harvard–MIT Health, Sciences, and Technology faculty member in Cambridge, MA. She is a MacVicar Faculty Fellow (awarded for contributions to undergraduate education), former Director of the Technology and Policy Program at MIT (2003–2015), and former Director of the MIT–Portugal Program (2011–2015).

Figure 11.39 – Dana Newman now

As the Director of MIT's Technology and Policy Program (TPP), she led the Institute's largest multidisciplinary graduate research program. She has been a faculty member in her home department of Aeronautics and Astronautics and MIT's School of Engineering since 1993.

In the following points, it is included the achievements that she reached throughout her life as well as the challenges that she had to overcome.

Achievements

- Investigating human performance in varying gravity environments
- She was the principal investigator on four spaceflight missions
- She was a Co-Investigator on the Mental Workload and Performance Experiment (MWPE) that flew on STS-42 to measure astronaut mental workload and fine motor control in microgravity
- She also developed the MICRO-G space flight experiment to provide a sensor suite and study human adaptation in extreme environments
- She was the MIT Principal Investigator on the Gravity Loading Countermeasure Suit, or Skinsuit, which flew the International Space Station as an ESA technology demonstration from 2015 to 2017
- She is the author of Interactive Aerospace Engineering and Design, an introductory engineering textbook, has published more than 300 papers in journals and refereed conferences, and holds numerous compression technology patents

Challenges

- Promoting the development of space activity suits, namely the BioSuit;
- Sending American astronauts to Mars in the 2030s;
- NASA teams are doing some of the most impressive work anywhere on Earth to support exploration, discovery, and technology off of it;
- Reach for new heights, and work to expand humanity's presence in the solar system while strengthening America's leadership here on Earth;
- On the ground, astronauts will be expected to explore extreme environments like the Olympus Mons, a volcano the size of Arizona that's nearly three times the height of Mount Everest;

They also developed a custom robot that can simulate a full range of human movement and withstand the uncomfortable prodding required to ensure a proper fit.

Figure 11.40 - Female astronaut spacesuit designed by Dava Newman

Suits will need to be easier to don and doff, provide greater freedom of movement, and be comfortable for long haul journeys. Newman's solution is called the BioSuit and looks a bit like a superhero's costume, but it's actually just a form-fitting math problem.

In order to survive in the vacuum of space, human bodies require pressure. EMUs⁶³ solve this problem by creating a pressurized vessel, sort of like a mini airplane cabin. By contrast, the BioSuit employs semi-rigid ribs traced across the body to provide mechanical counter pressure while letting the wearer retain a full range of movement.

Gold fibres are woven through the outfit and paired with biometric sensors to collect data that helps mission control keep tabs on the crew. The snug units protect astronauts, provide greater freedom of movement and more physically taxing experiments.

Beyond its good looks, the BioSuit will also be safer. If a micrometeorite or piece of space junk pierced an EMU, the suit would rapidly depressurize, leaving the astronaut out of luck in outer space, but the BioSuit could be patched with next-gen duct tape.

⁶³ The Extravehicular Mobility Unit (EMU) is an independent anthropomorphic spacesuit that provides environmental protection, mobility, life support, and communications for astronauts performing extra-vehicular activity (EVA) in Earth orbit.

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